

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.3 AWP Y2 including PARC Project Portfolio Version 5

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/institution	Short description of changes
1	27/01/2022	GB and GSB members	
2	21/02/2022	PARC CT and MB members	Second version of the AWPY2 with the budgetary information including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the PMs per partner in the detailed work description of each WP - the table 2.3d Summary effort table - the tale 2.3.e Other major costs items - the table 2.3.f Overview of planned budget per project Update of the Annex Project portfolio

			taking into account HaDEA comments
3	21/03/2023	PARC CT, MB members and task co-leaders	<p>Updated version of the AWPY2 taking into account HaDEA comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The list of partners participating in each project in Y2 has been added and the format has been harmonized between the different WPs - A table summarizing the connexion between deliverables, additional deliverables and projects reports and landmarks has been added in Annex of the AWPY2 after the PARC Project Portfolio - A table summarizing the links between projects and objectives has been added in section 1.2 Expected impacts - Specific comments on the different WPs have been addressed. - The list of participants and PMs for WP5 have been updated. The Table 2.3 Summary of efforts has been updated accordingly
4	17/05/2023	PARC CT, MB members	<p>Updated version of the AWPY2 taking into account HaDEA comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific comments on the different WPs have been addressed. - The contribution of the Irish partners has been added and the WP1 and WP4 budget have been modified to reflect their participation - The numbers of PMs per partner in the detailed work description of each WP have been updated - The tables 2.3.d, 2.3.e, and 2.3.f have been updated - The content of the section 2.2 has been moved in Annex I of the AWPY2. The description of work of the Participant UCPH for Y2 has been updated in section 2.2. - The PARC project portfolio has been changed in Annex II instead of Annex I - Typos have been corrected - The list of additional deliverables has been updated to reflect delays planned from Y1 to Y2 - Specific questions from HaDEA have been answered in a separate document
5	14/06/2023	PARC CT	Corrected tables 2.3.d and 2.3.f included.

Abstract

This Annual Work Plan (AWP) describes the activities to be implemented during the ‘PARC year’, including the updated Project Portfolio with projects that are in the planning/executive phase. The AWP covers the period from May 2023 to April 2024 which are referred to as ‘PARC years’.

Key Words

Work Plan, Project Portfolio Period M13-M24

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List of abbreviations

<p>3R: Reduction, Refinement and Replacement ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion AE: Affiliated Entity AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway API: Application Programming Interfaces ASR/ AWP: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans BPR: Biocides Products CA: Consortium Agreement CEC: Chemicals of Emerging Concern CL/ ML: Chemical Leader/ Methodology Leader CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging CMS: Content Management System COPCSD: Common Open Platform on Chemical Safety Data CPR: Cosmetic Products CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability CT: ANSES PARC Coordination Team DEPB: Data and Ethics Protection Board DMP: Data Management Plan DNT/ANT: Developmental and Acute Neurotoxicity DoA: Description of Action EC: European Commission ECHA: European Chemicals Agency ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disrupters / endocrine disrupting compounds EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis EFSA: European Food Safety Authority ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment EWS: Early Warning System FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles GA: Grant Agreement GB: Governing Board GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices GS: Grant Signatory GSB: Grant Signatory Board HA: Hazard Assessment HBM: Human BioMonitoring HBM GV: Health-based Guidance Values HRMS: High Resolution Mass Spectrometry IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment IB: International Board IPR: Intellectual Property Rights IVIVE: <i>in vitro</i> - <i>in vivo</i> extrapolation JRC: Joint Research Centre KEs: Key Events LCA: Life-cycle assessment MB: Management Board MCRA: Monte Carlo Risk Assessment</p>	<p>MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events MS: Member States NAMs: New Approach Methodologies NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment NGTxC: non-genotoxic carcinogens NHs: National Hubs NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points NTS: Non-Targeted Screening OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OO: Operational Objectives PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic PBPK: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic POD: Point of Departure PPPR: Plant Protection Products, QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control QAWG: Quality Assurance Working Group QIVIVE: Quantitative <i>in vitro</i> / <i>in vivo</i> Extrapolation QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management R&I: Research and Innovation RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals S2PD: Science-to-Policy Dialogue SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management SF: Stakeholder Forum SO: Specific Objectives SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda SS: suspect screening SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design T/TL: Task/Task co-leaders TTC: Toxicological Threshold of Concern THSD: Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors UCWG: Use Case Working Group(s) UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency US-NTP: US National Toxicology Program WHO: World Health Organization WP/ WPL: Work Package / WP co-leaders WWTP: Wastewater treatment plants</p>
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Structure of the Annual Work Programme

1. Coherence with part B of the proposal

1.1 Annual Work Plan (AWP) objectives

In this second year, the Partnership should enable all actors to work together to implement the different activities. After a first year of start-up, 57 projects are underway. Five new projects will start: 4 in the field of monitoring (WP4) and 1 case study related to innovation in risk assessment (included in a Year 1 WP6 project P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU).

The management of PARC will continue to improve its progress and quality monitoring process based on the feedback of the first year through the regular consultation of the different PARC boards and participants.

During this second year, work on the European human biomonitoring (HBM) study in the general population is continuing taking over from the activities carried out in HBM4EU. The occupational studies will be launched as well as the implementation of the pilot study in the environment. New sampling methods for human biomonitoring will be developed and validated. New projects on non-targeted screening / suspect screening in the environment (sentinel organisms) and in food will complement the existing ones. On hazard and risk assessment, PARC will continue to work on closing the identified regulatory data gaps regarding the selected mycotoxins and BPA alternatives/analogues and on the development of innovative methodologies that will directly contribute to chemical hazard identification, risk assessment and regulation. PARC will provide support innovation and transparency in chemical RA through improved exchange and re-use of data between different RA actors and disciplines, and through innovative data analytical approaches. It will also support the development and consolidation of concepts and tools for RA, also considering Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials and their operationalisation.

At the European level, PARC will promote the further development of existing and new infrastructural and human capacities related to laboratory networks including reference laboratories and exposure monitoring networks. At the international level, PARC will increase its visibility as a European hub for the implementation of new approach methodologies, development of Adverse Outcome Pathways and implementation of Integrative Approach for Testing and Assessment. The networking activities, collaborations with international organisations will contribute to this objective. Synergies with ongoing and future research programmes and the implementation of inter-agency will contribute to the development of reliable methods and tools. Based on the generic data management plan and the training of data Champions, Liaisons and FAIR implementation task (FIT) group, the FAIR culture will be developed and tested through case studies.

The specific objectives of this second year are:

- At the PARC management level (WP1)
 - To maintain an effective management and governance framework
 - To prepare the first periodic report due at M18
- A common science policy agenda (WP2)
 - To prepare background documents with chemical leaders on prioritised substances
 - To provide the first version of PARCopedia, the PARC's community platform for knowledge exchange and chemical risk assessment innovation.
 - To produce a draft version of NGRAroute, the proposal for a roadmap towards the regulatory uptake of Next Generation Risk Assessment for discussion with relevant parties in- and outside of PARC.
- Synergies, collaborations and awareness
 - To continue the development of interactions within the Partnership and continue to establish collaborations and synergies at national, European and international level (WP3)

- In terms of scientific activities within the framework of the PARC Project Portfolio

- **Priorisation**
 - To continue to develop the principles of prioritisation of activities, evaluation of the relevance of projects proposed for initiation (WP2)
 - To prepare the third AWP with the MB and GSB following input and guidance on the strategy to be implemented from the Governing Board (GB) (WP1)
 - To implement a prioritisation process to define chemicals/matrices/endpoints for future monitoring studies (WP4)
- **Monitoring of chemicals**
 - To initiate an EU-wide general population HBM survey, occupational surveys in health care sector and waste sector and to develop targeted surveys (WP4)
 - To conduct an environmental monitoring study on per-/polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) (WP4)
 - To develop innovative sampling and analytical methods through projects in the field of human, environmental and food monitoring (WP4)
- **Hazard assessment of chemicals:**
 - To perform studies to close the regulatory data gaps for selected mycotoxins (*Alternaria* toxins and enniatins) and BPA alternatives through *in vitro* testing for several endpoints (endocrine disruption, genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, immunotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity, metabolic fate and bioactivation) (WP5)
 - To continue the development of innovative methods on five different endpoints immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption (WP5)
 - To continue with the development of innovative methodologies that will directly contribute to chemical hazard identification, RA and regulation (WP5)
- **Further development of AOPs, IATAs:**
 - To facilitate different core and extended groups on omics, AOPs, bioinformatics, effect markers, PBK, *in vitro/in vivo* mode of actions, and establish an inventory and map available knowledge (WP5)
 - To initiate studies to characterise co-regulated gene networks for already established AOP to make them quantitative, linking AOP and generate high quality ADME data (WP5)
 - To further develop and refine quantitative networks of AOPs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity, to assess their human relevance and to identify associated NAMs (WP6)
 - To re-design, based on this work, regulatory relevant IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and (re-) evaluate the applicability of developed IATAs by means of dedicated case studies in an iterative way (WP6)
- **Exposure assessment of chemicals**
 - To continue the development of strategies for aggregated exposure via the development of realistic models and the functional design to connect models to assess exposure through different living environment for different source of entry in the general population (lifetime) and in the context of occupational exposure (WP6)
 - To continue the model development on exposure to mixtures observed in real life and the refinement of PBPK models for human risk assessment (WP6)
- **Risk assessment of chemicals**
 - To continue the on-going practice reviews by substances and effect (WP6)
 - To analyse the state of the art in risk assessment (RA) for mixtures, and how to take into account new approaches and methodologies (WP6)
 - To perform case studies to identify regulatory needs in environmental risk assessment and the state of the art in biodiversity impact assessment (WP6)

- To start a case study for further mapping of the needs for the PARC model network (WP8)
- Data management
 - To finalise the PARC data policy, update the data management plan (DMP) with clusters of project-level DMPs and develop a white paper on PARC FAIR ambitions with its roadmap (WP7)
 - To finalise the landscaping of existing databases and data platform and create a proof of concept for the FAIR PARC data hub (WP7)
- Support to the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability
 - To move forwards with the translation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) criteria into a toolbox (WP8)
 - To initiate the development of the PARC Early Warning System (EWS) and the respective computational framework (WP8, WP4)
 - To develop the interface to provide access to computational models (WP8, WP6)
- Network reinforcement and building capacities
 - To finalise the overall architecture and best-fit solution for building the information catalogues (laboratory networks, protocols, QA/QC, ...) (WP9) To identify existing training needs and map identify relevant available training option, define the training and learning resources within the PARC Consortium (WP9)

1.2 Expected impacts

The second AWP will reinforce the cross-disciplinary network between EU and national risk assessors through the collaboration between participants in the different projects and activities implemented in the Project Portfolio.

Through the collaboration with EU Research projects and clusters (EURION, ASPIS, EHEN), with JRC, and international organisations (e.g., OECD), PARC is a hub for the implementation of Human and environmental monitoring, development of NAMs, AOPs, Exposure and PBK Models in line with the Next Generation of Risk Assessment (NGRA). The establishment of a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), knowledge tools and catalogues will contribute to foster the regulatory uptake of PARC Knowledge.

At the scientific level, the PARC Project Portfolio contains 57 projects started the first year with 5 new ones planned in Year 2, including 1 case study related to innovation in RA, which is part of the WP6 project P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU that started Y1.

The work favouring collaborations between different networks of participants working in public health (general population, target populations and workers), environmental protection, monitoring of different sources for different classes of substances and people working in RA, hazard assessment (HA) and exposure quantification. The first projects are geared towards achieving our scientific objectives and in particular the construction of a common approach and the sharing of data through the development and application of PARC's FAIR data policy, knowledge and methods. The AWPY2 will contribute to the achievement OO7, OO8 as well as initiate work aligned with OO10, OO12.

From an economic point of view, the second year will contribute to the development of collaborations with existing networks, seeking complementarity and identifying training and quality assurance needs in order to support the development of innovative approaches and encourage their inclusion in the RA scheme. The aim is to develop a scientific approach to support innovation in chemistry while reducing risks for health and the environment. Achieving these objectives will require long-term work, but the second year will enable the expectations of the various stakeholders to be better characterised, the approaches and tools available to be discussed and the regulatory requirements for concepts such as SSbD and EWS to be better defined, while continuing to develop integrative approaches. The AWPY2 will contribute to the realisation of OO9, OO11 and OO13.

Table 1.2: Links between projects/activities and objectives

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES (SO)	OPERATIONAL OBJECTIVES (OO)	PROJECTS/TRANSVERSAL ACTIVITIES CONTRIBUTING
SO1 - cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA	OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC	WP1 - T1.1; T1.4; WP2 - T2.1; T2.2; WP3 – T3.1; T3.3; WP4 - P4.3.4.a*;
	OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH)	WP2 – T2.3; WP4 - P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.4.a*;
	OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy	WP2 – T2.1; WP4 - P4.2.b*; P4.3.1.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.3.b*; P4.3.4.a*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.4.a; WP7 – T7.1; WP8 – T8.1;
	OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge	WP2 – T2.2; T2.3; WP3 – T3.1; T3.2; T3.3; WP4 - P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.b*; P4.3.4.a*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e; WP7 – T7.2; WP8 – T8.3;

SO2 - carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemical RA	OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives	WP2 – T2.2; WP3 – T3.3; WP4 - P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.b*; P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e; WP8 – T8.1; WP9 – T9.1; T9.4;
	OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA	WP2 – T2.3; WP3 – T3.2; WP4 - P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.3.1.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.4.a*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.3.a; WP7 – T7.1; T7.2;
	OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA	WP1 – T1.1; WP2 – T2.1; WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.3.b*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.c; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.e; WP8 – T8.2;
	OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform	WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.1.5.a;

SO3 - access to R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA	created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes	P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b*; P4.3.4.a*; WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; WP9 – T9.2; T9.3;
	OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA	WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.b*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.4.a*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d; WP7 - P7.2.2.a; P7.2.2.b;
	OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake	WP4 - P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b*; WP5 - P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.3.a; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.2.b*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e; WP8 – T8.1; T8.3;
	OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.	WP4 - P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b*; P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.3.a; WP5 - P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P6.4.2.a; WP6 - P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.2.b*; P6.4.2.c; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;
	OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres	WP4 - P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.4.a*; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP9 – T9.1; T9.2; T9.3;

	OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA	<p>WP4 - P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.b*; P4.3.4.a*;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.2.1.b;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.b*; P6.4.4.d;</p> <p>WP7 - P7.2.2.b;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.4;</p>
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* = Projects starting Y2.

1.3 Correspondence with part B of the proposal

For this second AWP, the actions initiated in the form of projects, case studies and those activities corresponding to recurrent tasks are presented by WP and tasks using the structure described in Part B. AWPY2 has been designed to be intrinsically linked and complementary to the seven-year activity plan (Description of Action or DoA). It will provide the necessary basis on which to continue building the Partnership in the following years. This is true for the specific challenges, the scope of PARC as well as for the activities that will be initiated during the second year of PARC.

1.4 Construction of the PARC Project Portfolio

The PARC Project Portfolio constitutes a rolling overview of the PARC Projects implemented, providing detailed information on timelines, outputs, etc. Transversal activities are detailed in the GA. The PARC Project Portfolio is administered by the Coordinator and updated each year to integrate new Projects and follow those that have been implemented. It serves as a basis for the preparation of the AWP. The Project Portfolio annexed to this 2nd AWP is a compilation of all projects' summaries concerned that are already implemented and those additional ones that have been proposed and reviewed under task 2.1 and validated to start during the 2nd year of PARC. Other projects that were also submitted and that are still under discussion have not been included in this Project Portfolio yet but may be taken up in the next rolling plan.

2. Annual Work Programme Activities

2.1 Annual Work Programme

2.1.1 Structure of the Annual Work Programme

The structure of the Annual Work Programme (AWP) is based on the work packages (WP) description of transversal activities as well as more specific activities that are related to projects. A more detailed descriptions of projects is available in Annex.

2.1.2 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

The second Annual Work Plan will cover a duration of 12 months (1 May 2023 to 30 April 2024). All WPs will be active in Y2.

2.2 Detailed work description

For all the WPs, the full description of work by projects is available in the Project Portfolio in Annex II.

Table 2.3.a: Annual Work Programme Activities for each set of activities

WP N°	WP1	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES
WP title	Coordination and Management		
Partner N°	1	1.13	2
Partner short name	ANSES	EHESP	SpF
PM/partner1	108.8	4.5	8.7
Start	M13		M24
End			

Objectives

The main goal of WP1 is to ensure the coordination, the strategic scientific and administrative management of PARC, including impact evaluation and the ethical issues management, in cooperation with the different governance bodies of the Partnership. The specific objectives of WP1 for year 2 are:

- Task 1.1: Maintain an effective management and governance framework for the PARC consortium in compliance with the legal, ethical, financial and administrative rules and regulations and ensuring the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.2: Manage the tools to ensure the Partnership’s progress and guide the PARC consortium and its activities in maintaining the course set out in the Grant Agreement, to achieve milestones and produce the agreed deliverables, within the defined budget and abiding by the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.3: Maintain and update the monitoring framework for the Partnership;
- Task 1.4: Ensure communication and collaboration between the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB), notably composed of Ethics and Data contacts points from WP4, 5 and 7 and the PARC Consortium, and ensure that the PARC Participants follow the Ethics Charter in order to reduce and/or address ethical issues that may arise during the Partnership implementation.

Description of work

WP1 – Coordination and Management – will closely interact will all Work Packages (WPs) in order to support them in the management and implementation of the work, but also in order to create synergies and to follow-up and monitor the work progress. All tasks of WP1 are closely interlinked and complementary and will involve the following contributors (depending on the task):

- the Grant Signatory Board members (GSB): *EEA (AT), VITO (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), CIPH (HR), MU (CZ), UZIS (CZ), DEPA (DK), HB (EE), EEA (EU), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU), THL (FI), TTL (FI), ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL), NPHC (HU), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UI (IS), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LSMU (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), NIOM (PL), INSA (PT), FMUL (PT), NIJZ (SL), JSI (SI), ISCIII (ES), CSIC (ES), SEPA (SE), FOPH (CH), SZU-SK (SK), UKHSA (UK), EPA (IE)*;
- the WP co-leaders (WPL): *ANSES (FR), EAA (AT), EEA (EU), GCSL (EL), INSA (PT), Spf (FR), UBA (DE), BfR (FR), RIVM (NL), KEMI (SE), VITO (BE), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), UNINA (IT), MU (CZ), ISCIII (ES)*;
- the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs): *EEA (AT), DOMG (BE), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), CIPH (HR),*

¹ PMs have been allocated to the Grant Signatories for the management of their affiliated entities and their role of NHCP. In some cases, the Grant Signatories do not have any PM as they do not manage any AEs and are not NHCP in PARC.

MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), SpF (FR), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), AUTH (EL), NPHC (HU), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UI (IS), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), NIOM (PL), APA (PT), NIJZ (SL), ISCIII (ES), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), SZU-SK (SK), UKHSA (UK), EPA (IE);
- the National Hub Co-Coordinator (NHCs): *UKHSA (UK) and SZU-SK (SK).*

Task 1.1: Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All GSB members and WP co-leaders (as stated above)

The activities of this task will be managed by the PARC CT composed of the PARC Coordinator, the Deputy-Coordinator and the ANSES Project managers. The PARC CT will ensure an efficient management of the PARC activities and associated administrative and budgetary issues.

Management of the consortium and organisation of the Governance Bodies meetings:

- Ensuring the respect and proper implementation of the “Terms of reference and rules of procedure” by the PARC GB and of the Consortium Agreement (CA) by the PARC GSB.
- Setting the dates and organising the Partnership Consortium and Governance Bodies meetings (MB, GB and GSB) to take place during the 2nd year of PARC:

For the GSB:

- A physical meeting of the GSB should be organised in June in order to prepare the AWP of the next year and update the PARC SRIA, and prepare for consultation of the GB early July.
- A virtual meeting of the GSB should be organised in November/early December to discuss progress and approve the AWP for the next year and associated budget and annual summary report of the previous year before submission to HaDEA.
- Additional virtual GSB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised, if needed.

For the GB:

- A virtual meeting of the GB should be organised in June or July to validate the strategy and get inputs from the GB for the preparation of the future AWPs.
- A physical meeting of the GB should be organised in November. The objective will be to provide input and opinions on the PARC progression (AWPs, SRIA) before submission to the HaDEA in December and discuss progress, indicators, sustainability, as well as the strategy for the next AWP that will be worked on by the MB and GSB over the spring/summer.
- Additional virtual GB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised on other specific topics if needed.

For the MB:

- Monthly MB meetings will be organised all along the year, with two physical meetings, probably one meeting in June back-to-back to the GSB meeting and one in November, back-to-back to the GB meetings. The other MB meetings will take place online.

Follow-up of the Partnership’s activities and budget

- Managing the information system (EMDESK) for the monitoring of the budget and organise training sessions to help the financial administrators of the PARC institutions to ensure a proper and efficient use of the system.
- Updating on request the Partnership handbook describing the internal requirements and specifying the common rules to be followed by all PARC Participants.
- Assisting participants on specific administrative and financial issues.

Contractual documents generated by PARC activities

- Pursuing the preparation of contractual documents generated by PARC activities: IPR, Material Transfer Agreement and Data Transfer Agreement; preparing, signing, and managing, when relevant, other PARC related agreements (e.g., confidentiality and collaboration agreements) that will arise during the 2nd year.

Communication:

- Granting access rights to the PARC Consortium SharePoint when requested in order to ensure that all individuals involved in PARC have access to internal working documents and calendar of meetings and actions to be done for the year 2 of PARC.
- Providing rules and repositories to the PARC Participants for external communication
- Addressing any questions related to PARC.

Task 1.2: Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders, NHCPs, NHCs, DOMG (BE), INSA (PT), NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

The activities of this task will be managed by the PARC CT in close collaboration with the MB, GB, GSB, NHCs and the CL/MLs. The MB will specifically play an active role to ensure the efficient setting up of the monitoring of the scientific progress and of the overall strategy of the Partnership, making sure that the PARC activities, resources and AWP are aligned. It will also ensure the relevance of the PARC work plan with regard to external events with WP3 (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives).

Scientific steering and synergies

- Moderating the MB meetings and ensuring the cross-cutting scientific links between WPs
- Assisting the PARC NHCs in coordinating the National Hub (NH) contributions and activities in PARC
- Ensuring the follow-up of opportunities for synergies (with WP3) (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives, National, EU and international initiatives ...)
- Proposing amendments of the GA or solutions / redress actions to resolve any issues, and escalating unresolvable risks or issues to the relevant boards.

Preparation and submission of AWP Y3 with the Project Portfolio in Annex, and periodic report

- Coordinating the preparation, collection and submission to HaDEA of:
 - i) The 3rd AWP and updated PARC Project Portfolio in December 2023. This will be done in close collaboration with the MB members, the Task co-leaders, the PARC Participants, the Task 2.1 partners, and in consultation with the relevant PARC governance bodies (see task 1.1 for the organisation of the Governance Bodies meetings).
 - ii) The first Periodic Technical and Financial Reports in December 2023.

Follow-up of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones

- Monitoring and ensuring close follow-up of the Partnership's implementation of the 2nd AWP, ensuring respect of the different deadlines, and achievement of milestones, deliverables and additional deliverables.

Task 1.3: Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

Co-Leaders: DOMG (BE), INSA (PT)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

The initial monitoring frame and first set of indicators will be further refined to ensure the key useful and impact-generating results and relevant target groups are clearly identified in order to maximise PARC's

impact and exploitation.

Activities to be performed in the 2nd year include to:

- Further develop the set of indicators, originally containing output, outcome and impact (quantitative and qualitative) indicators, in collaboration with the MB, GSB and the GB, NHs and stakeholders, to ensure their relevance for evaluating the progress of the Partnership’s key, useful and impactful results and focus of the relevant target groups to maximise this impact and exploitation. Consult different PARC boards on the first set of indicators
- Finalise the first revised monitoring frame and document on first set of indicators further to the consultations
- Continue the interaction with WP2 – task 2.2 on sustainability – for the development of surveys for sustainability indicators
- In close collaboration with WP3, easily interpretable indicator leaflets will be prepared that form the linkage between the objectives, key results and (expected) impacts of PARC. These indicator leaflets will be important to track the progress of PARC and to feed into the discussions on sustainability (WP2).

Task 1.4: Ethics framework

Co-Leaders: NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

This task aims at maintaining an ethical perspective throughout all the Partnership’s activities and set up collaborative and constructive processes to ensure ethical considerations are properly taken into account.

Activities to be performed in the 2nd year include to:

- Organising consultations and dialogue between the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) that was implemented during the year 1 and the MB through the WPs’ Ethics contacts points who have been nominated in order to develop and facilitate the uptake of proper ethics and data protection processes.
- Ensuring that the PARC Participants are aware of, and acknowledge the Ethics Charter developed by the PARC CT and the Task 1.4 co-leaders in collaboration with the DEPB during year 1, in order to reduce and/or address ethical issues that may arise during the Partnership implementation.
- Organising at least one annual DEPB meetings (likely one physical and one online) with the option to schedule extraordinary online meetings if it proves necessary. DEPB members may also be invited to speak during other Governance Bodies meetings (MB, GSB, GSB) on ethics and/or data relevant topics.

Deliverables:

D1.8 AWP Y3 including the Project Portfolio – Leader: ANSES (M20)

D10.4 OEI - Requirement No. 5 – Leader: ANSES (M20)

Additional Deliverables:

NA

WP N°	WP2	Lead Beneficiary	EAA/EEA
WP title	A common science-policy agenda		

Partner N°	Partner short name	PM/partner	Start	End	M24
1	ANSES	13.2	M13	End	M24
1.1	INSERM	4.5			
2	SpF	1.5			
3	EAA	3.5			
3.6	UG-AT	1			
4.2	DOMG	1			
5.2	EV-ILVO	1			
7	MOH-	0.5			
8	MU	5.9			
10	DEPA	0.5			
11	HB	0.5			
11.1	SOM	1.5			
12	EEA	15			
14	TTL	0.5			
15	UBA	5.6			
16	BfR	18.3			
17	NPHC	5.5			
18	UI	0.5			
20	ISS	2			
21	RSU	0.5			
22	NPHSL	1			
25	RIVM	0.5			
26	NIPH	1			
26.2	STAMI	1			
26.3	NILU	2.5			
27	NIOM	3			
29	INSA	15			
29.2	DGS	1			
29.3	ENSP	5.6			
30	SZU-SK	1			
31	JSI	0.7			
32	NIJZ	2			
34	ISCIII	0.5			
36.2	GCSL	5			
49	EFSA	5			
52	Cefas-Defra	1			
59	UOB	9			

Objectives

The main goal of WP2 is to establish a dialogue and priority-setting process bringing together regulatory entities and Risk Assessment (RA) agencies in Europe (European and national entities and agencies) to develop a strategic R&I agenda for chemicals RA in collaboration with the scientific community and to continue to work on the sustainability of the partnership.

The specific objectives of WP2 for year 2 are:

- Task 2.1:
 - o Following the implementation of the project review process and providing input for the on-going and new projects in terms of chemical RA and regulatory and policy needs.
 - o Preparing the Background documents
 - o Setting a Rapid Response Mechanism
- Task 2.2:
 - o To provide a first live version of PARCopedia, PARC's community platform for knowledge exchange and chemical RA innovation.
 - o To produce a draft version of NGRARoute, the proposal for a roadmap towards the regulatory uptake of Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA), that can be finalised in year 3 by a broad discussion with relevant parties in- and outside of PARC.
- Task 2.3: Maintaining the continuous dialogue with the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) and translating their needs into actions, elaborating sustainable frameworks and further developing and refining the monitoring framework with T1.3.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 2.1: Priority setting

Co-leaders: ANSES (FR), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU)

Key Partners: EAA (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), GCSL (EL), DGS (PT)

Task 2.1 will ensure the link between the high-level priorities and the activities that will be implemented in PARC through projects providing input in terms of RA and regulatory and policy needs. This will be done via the implementation of the project review process and in close collaboration with the PARC Coordination Team (CT), the NHs for their national needs, the MB for the research work and task 2.2 to warrant the adequate identification of regulatory demands under a science to policy dialogue.

Task 2.1 will continue to follow the on-going projects and their outcomes and will apply to new submitted projects the review process. This will ensure that the work currently developed through the projects described in the Project Portfolio will improve the process for the development of future strategies in terms of policy implementation in Risk Management (RM) and governance of chemicals legislation in Europe

and at National level.

Based on substances/groups and methods/innovative tools that have been ranked in the framework of a first round of mapping of needs and prioritisation (D2.1. Prioritisation criteria report), T2.1 will prepare, with the appointed Chemical Leaders (CLs), background documents that will formulate the regulatory problems and introduce how the PARC projects contribute to addressing them (M24). These contributions will then be updated on a yearly basis in the scoping documents (T2.2). For methods/tools, policy and regulatory needs will be documented with the support of Methodological leaders.

Task 2.1 will set up the principles and process for a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), based on HBM4EU's experience (M18). The aim of the mechanism is to allow for National and European policy-makers to submit project requests for specific information to the PARC Consortium thus ensuring that the PARC responds to new and urgent needs for information on chemicals in the EU policy community and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for substance nomination.

One of the aims of PARC is to support policymaking through research, namely the Chemicals' Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) and Zero-Pollution (ZP). EEA and ECHA are coordinating the CSS Framework Indicator work at EU-level, together with the support of other EC DGs and EU agencies. Therefore, EEA, ECHA and the JRC would like to organise a workshop for the PARC consortium on the CSS indicators. During this workshop, the CSS indicators list would be shared, with timelines and data needs. A 2-way discussion with the PARC consortium is foreseen to ensure that PARC projects feed directly into these indicators, and to hear from the partners new potential ideas. The EC will also present the SRIP and its links to the CSS indicators. Preparatory documents will be circulated ahead of time for adequate preparation ahead of the workshop.

Task 2.2: Knowledge Management

Co-leaders: BfR (DE), INSA (PT)

Key Partners: AUTH (EL), UOB (UK), ANSES (FR), CEFAS (UK), DEFRA (UK), EAA (AT), EEA (EU), ENSP (PT), GCSL (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MU (CZ), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), SOM (EE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), UKON (DE)

A2.2.1 PARCopedia

The scoping study for the knowledge management platform PARCopedia drafted in year 1 will be circulated among all PARC partners, and their feedback will be integrated. The pilot version of PARCopedia will be tested among PARC members, and their feedback will be utilised to improve the test version and move to the first final version of the platform.

A2.2.2 PARCroute

The NGRAroute, the proposal for a roadmap towards the regulatory uptake of NGRA, will be further elaborated involving the ad-hoc S2PD network set up for this purpose, with the aim of producing a draft roadmap document at the end of year 2. The work begun in Y1 related to the ad-hoc network will go on. Work on the communication structure will be continued. Major elements of the targeted work plan that has begun in Y1 in collaboration with the related activities in WPs 4-6 will be tackled.

A2.2.3 CLs/MLs

Meetings with the Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs) will be organised in order to keep track of the work being developed by the CLs/MLs. Scoping documents for the chemicals and methodologies will be prepared by the corresponding CLs/MLs and a report on the work done will be prepared at the end of Y2.

Task 2.3: Sustainability

Co-leaders: INSERM (FR), NPHC (HU)

Key partner: DOMG (BE)

A2.3.1 National hubs needs & peer-to-peer learning

The mapping of needs of NHs is a living process. The first PARC NH survey, sent out during the 1st year of PARC will enable the development of a baseline for the PARC NHs, and to gather some preliminary information on the needs and expectations of the NHs themselves. The results of this 1st survey focusing on the mapping of the existing knowledge gaps, requests, suggestions and expertise of the NHs will be transposed into training and capacity building programmes in WP9 ‘Building infrastructural and human capacities’ to contribute and promote the development of the NHs. The results of the survey will also contribute to the identification and proposal of materials to support the work of the NHCPs. The results and actions, elaborated together with WP9, will be described in the first report on the national needs (D2.8). A new survey will be created and launched in the second year of the Partnership to identify the new needs of the NHs based on the inputs of by the NH Contact Points (NHCPs).

The peer-to-peer learning process established in the first year of the Partnership will continue to support the sustainable development of the NHs. The process will be coordinated and the development of the NHs will be monitored by the NH co-Coordinator (NHCs). An annual meeting will be organised to discuss the outcomes of the first survey and to initiate collaborations among the NHs.

A2.3.2 Exit strategy

As a first step, through the analysis of the results of the 1st NH survey (discussed above), task 2.3 will identify those activities that are already “sustainable” in some ways at national levels. The results of the survey carried out during the first year will be analyzed. The launch of a separate survey, focusing on the question of sustainability of PARC activities, at the end of the 1st year of PARC, will initiate the discussions on the sustainability of PARC activities at the European level and the path to achieve this, including the potentially most relevant operational systems for each of the activities. The harmonisation of HBM studies and the long-term infrastructures and needs for sustainability of HBM are already discussed within task 4.1 and will be integrated into the discussions on the PARC exit strategy.

Depending on each activity identified and its level of structuring in Europe, different targeted steps will be identified to analyse the relevant regulatory framework, the relevant (existing or not) networks and requirements needed for the future.

These discussions will also take place in Y2 not only in the different PARC boards, notably the GB whose active involvement will be sought on this subject, but direct contacts with some of the PARC partners and with the coordinator in Y2 will take also place to further define the exit strategy and the different activities that need to be sustained. These discussions will contribute to the identification of additional interactions and outreach actions, which will take place specifically with EU agencies and directions, some national ministries and agencies and major EU infrastructures (e.g., EIRENE) and project clusters (EHEN, EURION, ASPIS, etc.). These interactions will not cover only research options but also policy options and opportunities linked to the implementation of the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability. Open discussions will be encouraged to feed into the sustainability discussions at EU level and contribute to the development of. Different options for frameworks will be developed for long-term sustainability of the activities identified in the first year of the Partnership. This will serve as the basis of the first PARC sustainability report (D2.9).

Deliverables:

D2.4 1st Mapping of Needs report– Leader: ANSES (M18)

D2.5 Rapid Response Report – Leader: ANSES (M18)

D2.6 PARCopedia – Leader: BfR (M18)

D2.7 1st Report on national needs – Leader: NPHC (M18)

D2.8 1st Annual CL/ML reports' coordination and submission – Leader: INSA (M21)

D2.9 1st PARC Exit Strategy Plan and sustainability report – Leader: INSERM (M24)

Additional Deliverables:
 AD2.1 Draft NGRA roadmap document - Leader: BfR (M24)

WP N°	WP3										Lead Beneficiary										INSA/GCSL																								
WP title	Synergies, collaborations and awareness																																												
Partner N°	1	2	3	3.1	3.8	4	4.2	6	7	8	10	12	14	15	16	17	18	20	20.4	21	22	24	25	26	26.2	27	29	29.1	29.5	30	31	31.2	31.2	32	34	35.7	36	36.1	36.3	36.4	36.2	37	38	50	59
Partner short name	ANSES	SpF	EAA	AGES	UMIT	VITO	DOMG	CIPH	MOHCY/SGL	MU	DEPA	BEA	TTL	UBA	BfR	NPHC	UI	ISS	IUSS	RSU	NPHSL	LNS	RIVM	NIPH	STAMI	NIOM	INSA	APA	UAVR	SZU-SK	JSI	NIB	NIC	NIZ	ISCI	KEMI	AUTH	EFET	NKUA	UOC	GCSL	BPI	FOPH	UKHSA	UOB
PM/partner	1	0.5	4.7	2	3	1	2	1	1	2.5	1	13	1	2.8	0.9	14	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	3.3	1.5	35.7	3.5	2.5	1	1.5	7	1.5	5.5	2	1	4.5	5.5	10.2	7.9	19	2.5	1	2	1
Start	M13										End										M24																								

Objectives

The main goal of WP3 is to boost the impact of PARC outcomes through the diffusion of the knowledge produced within the Partnership while fostering synergies and collaborations with other projects/programmes at national, EU and international levels.

The specific objectives of WP3 for year 2 are:

- Task 3.1: Running the International Board (IB) and Stakeholder Forum (SF), and ensure effective interaction with PARC’s projects,
- Task 3.2: Continue the implementation of the communication strategy for PARC and promote its continuous improvement based on specific requirements from WPs,
- Task 3.3: Continue establishing collaborations and synergies with identified relevant scientific/regulatory/policy initiatives at national, EU and international levels.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 3.1: Building effective interactions

Co-Leaders: EAA (AT): Stakeholder Forum, AUTH (EL): International Board, PARC ambassador

Partners: ANSES (FR), , EEA (EU), UBA (DE), IUSS (IT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), NIB (SI), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), GCSL (EL)

Activity 3.1.1. Running of Stakeholder Forum (SF)

In year 2 of PARC, the SF (established in year 1) will be further consolidated. –Together with the SF members, Terms of Reference will be developed on the engagement, objectives and desired outcomes of the PARC SF. In cooperation with WP co-leaders, topics to be presented and discussed in the SF will be identified, as well as which consultations should be conducted. Two meetings will be organised to present the work progress and the main outcomes and to get feedback from SF members (all partners)

Interactions with industry, in particular on the subjects of NAMs and of SSbD, will be promoted in close collaboration with the relevant WPs (AUPh, ANSES).

Activity 3.1.2. Running of the International Board (IB)

Task co-leaders and partners will work in close collaboration to promote the interaction between the IB members and PARC WPs. Two meetings will be organized to present the work progress and the main outcomes and to get feedback from them on the performance of Projects within PARC. Those meetings will also stimulate the interactions between PARC and external bodies (all partners).

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Co-Leaders: EEA (EU), NPHC (HU)

Partners: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), UMIT (AT), VITO (BE), DOMG (BE), CIPH (CR), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), UI (IS), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UNINA (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), SZU (SK), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), ISCIH (ES), KEMI (SE), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), UKHSA (UK), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

A3.2.1 Website and social media channels

The PARC website and the social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook and Instagram accounts) will be maintained and updated continuously by EEA, NPHC, FMUL, INSA, EFET, NKUA, BPI, and GCSL.

A3.2.2 Development and implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy plan

New communication products (e.g., PARC Magazine, microsite for citizens, additional interactive media design and animated communication products) will be developed to increase PARC's visibility, build and grow the PARC brand and engage stakeholders. The PARC Newsletter will be published twice per year. The roadmap for the production of communication materials and tools will be updated. A continuous dialogue will be maintained with the different WP co-leaders/contact points to translate the latest PARC results into communication and dissemination outputs, ensuring a coherent approach. All public project deliverables and the links to all peer-reviewed publications produced under the project will be made available via the PARC website. Webinars, meetings and training activities for transfer of good practices, experience and knowledge will be organised in collaboration with WP9 partners involved in A3.2.2: UMIT, EEA, NPHC, LNS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIJZ, EFET, NKUA, UOC and GCSL.

A3.2.3 Surveys and other tools to assess stakeholders' perception and concerns

Outreach activities will be carried out to raise awareness. The first citizen survey will be organized to

gather new data specifically tailored for project needs and collect more in-depth information about citizens' perceptions and concerns about PARC-related subjects. Furthermore, focus group discussions will be organized. The countries hosting focus group discussions will be selected in an internal call. Communication with the scientific community and with all stakeholders, including the general public, regulators and policy makers will be done through the different communication channels and with the involvement of the NHs. Partners involved in A3.2.3: AGES, EEA, NPHC, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, NIB, UOC and GCSL.

A3.2.4 Risk communication

A survey for mapping the risk perception of the different stakeholders on risk communication will be developed by NIJZ and EFET. The survey will be performed in Greece and Slovenia for validation purposes.

A.3.2.5 Monitoring of indicators

Monitoring of indicators through bibliometric analysis, network analysis and other data and tools will continue to feed into task 1.3 by DOMG, EEA, NPHC, INSA, NIB and GCSL.

Task 3.3: Networking and Synergies

Co-Leaders: INSA (PT), NKUA (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), UBA (DE), FMUL (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), EFET (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

A3.3.1 Inventory of scientific activities relevant to PARC

Update of the established database of partnerships, projects, networks and activities including platforms relevant to PARC within the frame of an efficient and dynamic collaboration strategy (all partners).

A3.3.2 SYNnet and roadmap for promotion of synergies

Continue updating SYNnet and expanding the network to include new partnerships, projects, etc. and respond to PARC demands for synergies.

Creation of a strategy for network analysis based on bibliometric tools in order to respond to key impact indicators (FMUL, NKUA, UOC).

Contribution to the dissemination of training programmes developed within PARC (EFET, NKUA, INSA).

A3.3.3 Development of internal and external interaction strategies

Revise and update of the interaction strategy between SYNnet and WPs in order to identify and address internal needs and gaps (BPI, ENSP, NKUA, GCSL, INSA, UBA).

Coordinate with WP and Project leaders to create adequate incentives for external scientific activities that are relevant to PARC. SYNnet activities will be announced and published at the PARC website increasing the visibility of joint activities and of the external projects themselves. The synergies will be further strengthened through the organisation of networking events, particularly, the first SYNnet Forum, to promote dialogue and knowledge sharing among scientists (ENSP, FMUL, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, NKUA, UAVR, UOC, BPI).

Deliverables:

No deliverable planned for WP3 in Year 2

Additional Deliverables: none

WP N°	WP4	Lead Beneficiary	UBA/SpF	
WP title	Monitoring and exposure			
Partner N°	1			
Partner short name	ANSES			
PM/partner	55.7			
Partner N°	1.1			
Partner short name	INSERM			
PM/partner	16.6			
Partner N°	1.2			
Partner short name	INRAE			
PM/partner	60.3			
Partner N°	1.3			
Partner short name	CEA			
PM/partner	17.2			
Partner N°	1.4			
Partner short name	INERIS			
PM/partner	24.5			
Partner N°	1.5			
Partner short name	CNRS			
PM/partner	6.8			
Partner N°	1.6			
Partner short name	INRS			
PM/partner	9.3			
Partner N°	1.7			
Partner short name	ONIRIS			
PM/partner	13.9			
Partner N°	1.9			
Partner short name	OFB			
PM/partner	2.8			
Partner N°	1.10			
Partner short name	BRGM			
PM/partner	14.6			
Partner N°	1.11			
Partner short name	LNE			
PM/partner	0.5			
Partner N°	1.12			
Partner short name	CSTB			
PM/partner	12			
Partner N°	1.13			
Partner short name	EHESP			
PM/partner	10.6			
Partner N°	2			
Partner short name	SpF			
PM/partner	59.5			
Partner N°	3			
Partner short name	EAA			
PM/partner	2.5			
Partner N°	3.4			
Partner short name	MUI			
PM/partner	15.18			
Partner N°	3.5			
Partner short name	MUW			
PM/partner	1			
Partner N°	3.6			
Partner short name	UG-AT			
PM/partner	4			
Partner N°	3.9			
Partner short name	UNIVE			
PM/partner	10.9			
Partner N°	4			
Partner short name	VITO			
PM/partner	48.6			
Partner N°	4.1			
Partner short name	KU Leuven			
PM/partner	11.9			
Partner N°	4.3			
Partner short name	UH			
PM/partner	1			
Partner N°	4.4			
Partner short name	PIH			
PM/partner	5.5			
Partner N°	4.5			
Partner short name	OVAM			
PM/partner	15			
Partner N°	4.6			
Partner short name	ISSeP			
PM/partner	26.1			
Partner N°	4.7			
Partner short name	UAntwerpen			
PM/partner	19.2			
Partner N°	5			
Partner short name	SCIENSANO			
PM/partner	25			
Partner N°	5.2			
Partner short name	EV-ILVO			
PM/partner	1			
Partner N°	6			
Partner short name	CIPH			
PM/partner	1			
Partner N°	7			
Partner short name	MOH-CY/SGL			
PM/partner	4.7			
Partner N°	8			
Partner short name	MU			
PM/partner	55.3			
Partner N°	8.1			
Partner short name	SZU-CZ			
PM/partner	1.7			
Partner N°	8.2			
Partner short name	VSCHT			
PM/partner	5.6			
Partner N°	8.4			
Partner short name	JU			
PM/partner	1.2			
Partner N°	10.1			
Partner short name	AU			
PM/partner	33.7			
Partner N°	10.3			
Partner short name	REGIONH-RH			
PM/partner	3			
Partner N°	10.4			
Partner short name	UCPH			
PM/partner	15			
Partner N°	13.1			
Partner short name	SYKE			
PM/partner	13			
Partner N°	14			
Partner short name	TTL			
PM/partner	12.7			
Partner N°	14.1			
Partner short name	FFA			
PM/partner	2.2			
Partner N°	14.3			
Partner short name	UOULU			
PM/partner	1.8			
Partner N°	15			
Partner short name	UBA			
PM/partner	74.8			
Partner N°	15.1			
Partner short name	BfG			
PM/partner	14			
Partner N°	15.2			
Partner short name	UFZ			
PM/partner	45.3			
Partner N°	15.6			
Partner short name	KUM			
PM/partner	7.3			
Partner N°	16.1			
Partner short name	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME			
PM/partner	21			
Partner N°	18			
Partner short name	UI			
PM/partner	3.5			
Partner N°	19			
Partner short name	MOH			
PM/partner	1.5			
Partner N°	20			
Partner short name	ISS			
PM/partner	11.9			
Partner N°	20.2			
Partner short name	CNR-JRSA			
PM/partner	14.4			
Partner N°	20.3			
Partner short name	IREM			
PM/partner	6			
Partner N°	20.5			
Partner short name	UMIL			
PM/partner	3			
Partner N°	20.6			
Partner short name	UNINA			
PM/partner	1.6			
Partner N°	20.7			
Partner short name	UNIPD			
PM/partner	1.3			
Partner N°	21			
Partner short name	RSU			
PM/partner	25.9			
Partner N°	21.1			
Partner short name	UL			
PM/partner	3.3			
Partner N°	22			
Partner short name	NHPSL			
PM/partner	0.5			
Partner N°	23			
Partner short name	LSMU			
PM/partner	4.6			
Partner N°	24			
Partner short name	LNS			
PM/partner	40.9			
Partner N°	24.3			
Partner short name	UniLU			
PM/partner	15.9			
Partner N°	25.1			
Partner short name	KWR			
PM/partner	3.1			
Partner N°	25.2			
Partner short name	TNO			
PM/partner	0.5			
Partner N°	25.3			
Partner short name	RUMC			
PM/partner	6			
Partner N°	25.5			
Partner short name	UU-IRAS			
PM/partner	2.9			
Partner N°	25.6			
Partner short name	VUA			
PM/partner	15.8			
Partner N°	25.7			
Partner short name	WR			
PM/partner	13.6			
Partner N°	26			
Partner short name	NIPH			
PM/partner	13			
Partner N°	26.2			
Partner short name	STAMI			
PM/partner	4.9			
Partner N°	26.3			
Partner short name	NILU			
PM/partner	3.3			
Partner N°	26.5			
Partner short name	NMBU			
PM/partner	1.1			
Partner N°	26.7			
Partner short name	UNN			
PM/partner	0.3			
Partner N°	27			
Partner short name	NIOM			
PM/partner	10.7			
Partner N°	27.2			
Partner short name	UG-PL			
PM/partner	6.4			
Partner N°	27.3			
Partner short name	WULS-SGGW			
PM/partner	7.8			
Partner N°	29			
Partner short name	INSA			
PM/partner	9.1			
Partner N°	29.3			
Partner short name	ENSP			
PM/partner	2			
Partner N°	30			
Partner short name	SZU-SK			
PM/partner	4			
Partner N°	31			
Partner short name	JSI			
PM/partner	34.2			
Partner N°	31.4			
Partner short name	ULFFA			
PM/partner	8.8			
Partner N°	32			
Partner short name	NIJZ			
PM/partner	11.7			
Partner N°	32.3			
Partner short name	ARSO			
PM/partner	7			
Partner N°	33			
Partner short name	CSJC			
PM/partner	30.4			
Partner N°	33.4			
Partner short name	ULPGC			
PM/partner	0.4			
Partner N°	33.3			
Partner short name	UGR			
PM/partner	30			
Partner N°	34			
Partner short name	ISCIH			
PM/partner	34.4			
Partner N°	34.1			
Partner short name	EASP			
PM/partner	7.4			
Partner N°	34.2			
Partner short name	FISABIO			
PM/partner	3.8			
Partner N°	34.5			
Partner short name	IISPV			
PM/partner	1			
Partner N°	34.6			
Partner short name	INNST			
PM/partner	4.5			
Partner N°	34.7			
Partner short name	UCLM			
PM/partner	5.5			
Partner N°	34.8			
Partner short name	UPV-EHU			
PM/partner	5			
Partner N°	35.3			
Partner short name	ULUND			
PM/partner	4.3			
Partner N°	35.4			

PM/ partner	12.5	9.2	9	29	6.4	4.1	39.5	7.7	11.9	1	8	6.2	0.2	4.5	9	1.5	4	1.1	0.5	3	3	3.67
Start	M13							End							M24							

Objectives

The main goal of WP4 is to monitor chemicals guided by regulatory and policy challenges both in humans and in the environment, observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways, international activities, and coordinate with the WHO initiative on HBM. The specific objectives of WP4 for year 2 are:

- Task 4.1: Initiation of an EU-wide general population HBM survey, initiation of occupational surveys in health care sector and waste sector, developing targeted surveys (design and supporting materials), preparing implementation of following aspects in above mentioned surveys: effect biomarkers, innovative (sampling) techniques for Human Biomonitoring (HBM), update and integration of QA/QC aspects and analyses plan in the HBM surveys, evaluation of new chemical analysis methods needs.
- Task 4.2: Development of a process to define priority chemicals/matrices/endpoints for environmental monitoring studies. Starting a first monitoring study on per-/polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs).
- Task 4.3: Novel methodologies will be developed for improvement and renewal of current monitoring approaches, with a focus on early life stages and on early warning systems for the timely observation of the occurrence of chemicals of emerging concern in the environment-food-human continuum. The work will be covered in 5 ongoing projects (started in year 1) and 3 projects starting in year 2.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 4.1: Human Biomonitoring

Co-Leaders: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EAA (AT), EHESP (FR), FFA (FI), TTL (FI), FISABIO (ES), FOPH (CH), HSE (UK), KI (SE), IMROH (HR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), INSST (ES), IOM (UK), KUM (DE), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), KU Leuven (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH (IL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), NPHSL (LT), ONIRIS (FR), UKHSA (UK), PIH (BE), REGIONH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), RUMC (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), THL (FI), UA Antwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UGent (BE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), ULFFA (SI), ULPGC (ES), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), UNIVIE (AT), UNN (NO), UOULU (FI), UOC (EL), UPV/EHU (ES), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), CIPH (HR), SHSO (CY), SDU (DK), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), UFZ (DE), NPHC (HU), UI (IS), VSCHT (CZ), EASP (ES), SECO (CH)

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies

The implementation of a general population HBM survey will be prepared and initiated (linked to P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO). Proposals for add-ons to be implemented, as small-scale research components, in the general survey will be finalized. The add-on topics are: i) implementation of effect biomarkers (linked to P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO), ii) identify the contribution of specific environmental compartments, products and food to internal exposure levels (in collaboration with T4.2, and (iii) apply innovative sampling methods (Dried blood spots (DBS), Silicone wrist bands (SWB), Volumetric absorptive micro-sampling (VAMS) and screening methods (Suspect screening (SS), Non targeted screening (NTS) (in collaboration with T4.3).

Project proposals for targeted surveys will be developed and submitted in Y2 to be initiated in Y3 (ISCI, LNS, SpF, UBA, VITO). Preliminary priorities for targeted studies include: dietary exposure to e.g., food related exposures in young children, prenatal and newborn exposure to e.g., endocrine disruptors and POPs, health effects and risk factors related to (accumulated) exposure in the middle-aged population (40-69y) and elderly (70-85y), time trends in repeatedly sampled cohorts/regions and/or biobanked samples, PFAS hotspots. A European hotspot network initiated under HBM4EU will be maintained and expanded through regular network meetings.

During the first year, two occupational surveys focusing on the waste management sector (linked to P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL) (phthalates, metals, flame retardants, bisphenols) and the health care sector (linked to P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_RUMC) (HMPs and disinfectants) (HSE, INRS, INSST, IOM, MU, RSU, RUMC, TTL, UGR) have been designed. Ethical permissions are applied in each participating countries in the end of Y1 and beginning of Y2. Samplings related to these studies will start in Y2 for the waste management sector (AU, INSA, ENSP, ISS, KUL, LNS, MOH-CY/SGL, NIOM, STAMI, UMIL, UNIPD, UNINA, UNISANTE, WULS-SGGW, ULUND, IPA) and the health care sector (HSE, INRS, INSST, IOM, MU, RSU, RUMC, TTL, UGR). Samplings will include also samples collected for effect marker analyses (which have been planned in collaboration with P4.1.3.3a) and applying new innovative methods (T4.3: linked to P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02).

The project P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL will be finalized during Y2 of PARC.

Supporting materials will be developed in relation to the preservation and the storage of the samples that will be collected in the HBM surveys. In close collaboration with EFSA, we will further explore harmonization of questionnaire types (FFQ, FPQ24h, food categories, response options, etc.) and/or application of the Foodex2 system, as well as possibilities for digitalization (eg. apps) for the collection of dietary exposure information. We will also consider the use of materials such as (dynamic) informed consents and materials to support the reporting of personal results to the participants (CIPH, CSIC, EAA, EASP, FOPH, Fraunhofer-IBMT, IMROH, INSA, ISCI, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MOH-IL, MUW, NIJZ, NIOM, PIH, RSU, SpF, STAMI, THL, UBA, UGR, ULUND, UMU, UOULU, UPV).

Details per project

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO: Partners that will contribute to the general survey in children (6-11 years) are UKHSA, RegionH-RH, RSU, University Tartu/Health Board, NIOM, WULS-SGGW, SZU-CZ, NPHC, SZU, ISCI, INSA, AUTH, JSI, MOH-CY/SGL, UBA, SPF, EAA, LNS partners that will contribute in teenagers (12-17 years) are UKHSA, RegionH-RH, NIPH, RSU, NIOM, WULS, JSI, AUTH, INSA, UBA, SPF, VITO/PIH, MOH-IL and partners that will contribute in adults (18-39 years) are UKHSA, LSMU, RSU, University Tartu/Health Board, UI, NIPH, SZU-CZ, EASP, UPV, AUTH, INSA, MOH-CY/SGL, ISS, UBA, SPF, ISSeP, LNS, MOH-IL. RIVM may contribute depending on final decision. Substance groups prioritized for analysis are in children: Phthalates and substitute DINCH, Bisphenols, Pesticides, metals in urine, Mercury (hair), in teenagers: PFAS, Phthalates and substitute DINCH, Bisphenols, arsenic species, pesticides, in adults: PFAS, metals in urine/blood, pesticides, bisphenols. In all age groups cotinine, creatinine and specific gravity will be assessed. First sample collection activities will start as of M13, overall coordination will be taken up by VITO supported by ISCI, UBA, SPF, LNS, INSA, RegionH-RH. A workshop is organized M13 with all study partners in Brussels.

- P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL: During year 1, a mapping study on the implementation of a sentinel surveillance systems as a tool to collect reliable and statistically representative data on environmental and occupational exposure and health on a European level has been performed (linked to

P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven) (AU, INSA, KUL, LNS, MU, NIOM, RSU, RUMC, SpF, UGR, ULUND, UNINA, UNISANTE). Based on this mapping exercise six countries are selected to collect data using the sentinel network. This activity is planned to start during Y2. Data analyses will continue in the beginning of year 2. These are performed by INSA (PT), SpF (FR) and TTL (FI). Based on the results of the statistical data analyses, conclusions and recommendations for general population studies are made, report of the study is written (TTL (FI) SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT). Scientific publication is drafted (TTL (FI) SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT)).

- P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven: This project is currently further in discussion (go/no go landmark). A meeting will be held in May to discuss if this project will be stopped.

- P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_RUMC: In the beginning of year 2, ethical permissions are applied, hospitals and volunteering participants are recruited for the study. The sampling campaign will be launched. The following partners are participating in these activities: TTL (FI), RUMC (NL), MU (CZ), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), ENSP (PT), HSE (UK), IOM (UK), INSST (ES). The identification of the laboratories for exposure and effect marker analyses (as well as wipe and air sample analyses) will be completed during the first half of year 2. This activity is lead by RUMC and TTL and made in collaboration with task 4.1.2. Data management plan is prepared by RUMC and TTL with the support from the other partners (see the list above) and A4.1.4.

- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL : Year 2 will be devoted to the submission of the study protocol to the Ethical Committees Data Management Plan in collaboration with WP7, the online training on the implementation of the study protocols and procedures (collaboration with WP9), the development of the monitoring campaigns (biomonitoring and environmental monitoring). The following partners are participating in these activities: ENSP-UNL/Portugal, AU/Denmark, ISS/ Italy, UNIPD/Italy, UMIL/Italy, UNINA/Italy, WULS/Poland, ULUND/Sweden, STAMI/Norway, AUTH/Greece, INSA/Portugal, TTL/Finland, LNS/Luxembourg, MOH-CY / Cyprus, NIOM/Poland, IOM/UK, HSE/UK and UGranada/Spain.

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No project for this activity.

In terms of laboratory analysis and quality assurance, the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods will be updated and completed as required to cover the needs in the design of the different HBM surveys (AU, AUTH, BPI, CEA, EHESP, FFA, FISABIO, IMROH, INSA, IPA, ISCIII, ISS, JSI, KU Leuven, KUM, LNS, LSMU, NIOM, NIPH, NPHSL, UKHSA, RSU, RUMC, SpF, STAMI, SZU-SK, THL, UAntwerpen, UGR, ULFFA, ULPGC, ULUND, UMIL, UNN, UOC, UOULU, USI, VSCHT).

The Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) (JSI, IPA, ISCIII, UAntwerpen, and WR) and collaborating partners (LNS, MU) will work in close collaboration with T9.1 and T9.3 on the QA/QC aspects and comparability of the HBM data generated under T4.1. In addition, QA/QC aspects related to the innovative sampling techniques will be further elaborated and included in the design of HBM surveys (IPA, ISCIII, LNS, MU, ONIRIS, UAntwerpen, UGR, UNIVIE, and UOC). The working group on reference analytical methods (IPA, ISCIII, ISS, IVL, LNS, MUI, NIPH, SCIENSANO, UAntwerpen, ULUND, UNIVIE, and UOC) will evaluate the needs for development of new analytical methods for

exposure. Work will progress towards the design and future implementation of the chemical analysis action plan for the different HBM surveys (IPA, LNS, MU, NIOM, RSU, RUMC, SCIENSANO, SpF, THL, TTL, UAntwerpen, UBA, UGR, and ULUND).

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information

- P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_Derivation of HBM-GVs_UBA: Year 2: Health-Based Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) will be derived for a second set of prioritised substances (ANSES, NIPH, RUMC, TTL, UBA, Unisante, MOH-IL). HBM-GVs for selected substances or their specific exposure biomarkers will be derived according to the strategy agreed under HBM4EU and described by Apel et al. (2020; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113622>). In principle, all lead experts conduct a literature search on the substance under consideration to determine the current state of toxicological/epidemiological knowledge. Depending on the data basis, the experts decide whether epidemiological data, or else a recognized external toxicity reference value respectively occupational exposure limit, or a point of departure from an experimental study together with toxicokinetic information is used to derive the HBM-GV. Thus, HBM data are only included in the derivation if studies are available that show a relationship between human internal exposure and health effects.

The substance dossiers including the derived values will afterwards be reviewed by experts involved via the national hub.

NIPH and TTL will work on mercury. It is to be examined whether and, if so, which significant published toxicological findings need to be added to the dossier in the HBM4EU Deliverable D5.12. The findings on the toxicology of mercury presented in the HBM4EU Deliverable D13.7 should also be taken into account. Based on this, it should be clarified whether the provisional HBM-GVs for the general population (7 µg Hg/l urine, 3.5 µg Hg/l blood) which were derived within HBM4EU can be adopted. AUTH offered support regarding modelling work.

A task group on chromates has been established by Radboudumc with collaboration of TTL, Unisante, SECO and partly ANSES which will work on Chromium VI. The need is seen to complement the existing HBM4EU dossier and risk-related value on chromium VI with regard to correlations of lower air concentrations and body burden.

A further task group was suggested by MOH-IL and NIPH-FHI with the focus on PFAS, whose work could particularly benefit from being planned for a longer period of time to incorporate results from other work packages. Additionally, partners agreed to check which other international institutions derive similar health-related guidance values as the HBM-GV and to what extent these values can be adopted to avoid duplication of work. If possible, further HBM-GV derivations will be made according to future PARC prioritization. A face-to-face meeting in Berlin is planned for 2023.

- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO: This project will be continued. In Y2, a new approach for linking exposures and health effects will be explored. This approach will consist of a feasibility study that will explore the use of archived (stored in biobanks) samples previously collected in cohorts to quantify past exposures and link them to effect biomarkers and health outcomes (BPI, EEA, EHESP, Fraunhofer-IBMT, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, SpF, TTL, UBA). To perform this feasibility study, we will work on (i) The definition of the study criteria for measurements of exposures and effect biomarkers with the aim to link past exposures to current health effects and (ii) the development of a data analysis approach in collaboration with A4.1.4-Data management and analysis to link past exposures and health outcomes.

Year 2 will be devoted to continuing the integration of standardised health measurements and questionnaires in HBM surveys conducted under PARC:

- Selection of effect biomarkers and related analytical methods, matrices, and health outcomes (VITO (Lead), AU, AUTH, EAA, CSIC, TTL, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, NLZOH, SECO, Sciensano, SpF, UGR, UKHSA, ULPGC, UNINA, UNIPD, USI)

- Development of standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, physical activity, dietary and occupational data to include in PARC HBM general and occupational surveys (SpF (Lead), EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, TTL, UBA). A feasibility study will explore the possibility to assess past exposures to prioritized chemical substances from biobanked samples collected in cohorts in relation to adverse health effects.
- Inventory and identification of ongoing European Health Examination Surveys (HES) and associated biobanks (Preliminary: SpF (Lead), EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer, CSIC, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, TTL, UBA, UPV/EHU; Additional partners may be included based upon their interest in participating in the feasibility study)
- Definition of the study criteria for measurements of exposure and effect biomarkers (Preliminary: SpF (Lead), VITO (Lead), AU, AUTH, CEA, EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer, CSIC, INRS, INSA, INSST, ISCIII, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, MU, NIJZ, NIOM, NLZOH, RUMC, RSU, Sciensano, SECO, STAMI, TTL, UKHSA, UBA, UGR, UNINA, UNIPD, USI UPV/EHU)
- Development of a data analysis approach (SpF (Lead), AU, AUTH, CEA, EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer, CSIC, INRS, INSA, INSST, ISCIII, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, MU, NIJZ, NIOM, NLZOH, RUMC, RSU, Sciensano, SECO, STAMI, TTL, UKHSA, UBA, UGR, UNINA, UNIPD, USI UPV/EHU)

A4.1.4 Data management and analysis

- P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO: Year 2 will be devoted to the identification of partners that will take up the statistical analyses: final selection (Partners involved: AU, AUTH, BPI, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, Sciensano, SPF, SZU-SK, TTL, UBA, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO), the arrange data access (Partners involved: AU, AUTH, EASP, INRAE, JSI, MU, NIPH, SPF, TTL, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO). There will be a focus on the development of a statistical analysis plan (Partners involved: AU, AUTH, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, JSI, LNS, MU, NIPH, SPF, TTL, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO), the Data analysis (Partners involved: AU, AUTH, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, JSI, LNS, MU, NIPH, SPF, TTL, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO), the interpretation of the results and discussion (Partners involved: AU, AUTH, BPI, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, Sciensano, SPF, SZU-SK, TTL, UBA, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO), the initiation of the results reporting phase (Partners involved: AU, AUTH, BPI, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, Sciensano, SPF, SZU-SK, TTL, UBA, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO).

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

- P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO will be continued in Y2. The project's goal is the preparation of a sustainable human biomonitoring and surveillance system for Europe. The questionnaire survey on a vision for a future HBM system for Europe developed in Y1 will be distributed and results processed. Cornerstones of the EU HBM system from the requirements of the PARC partner countries and the criteria and components relevant for comparison with international HBM programmes will be defined (FOPH, INSA, ISCIII, LNS, LSMU, MOH-CY/SGL, NIPH, SpF, SZU-CZ, UBA, VITO). This project will be run in close collaboration with WP2 and the PARC Exit Strategy.

Planned activities for Year 2:

- Distribute the survey on the vision for a future, sustainable HBM system for Europe and process results (VITO, ISCIII, UBA, SpF, FOPH, INSA, LNS, LSMU, NIPH, SZU-CZ, MOH-CY)

- Define the cornerstones of the EU HBM system from the requirements of the PARC partner countries and the criteria and components relevant for comparison with international HBM programmes (VITO, ISCIII, UBA, SpF, FOPH, INSA, LNS, LSMU, NIPH, SZU-CZ, MOH-CY)
- Identify action points for development of each component of the future EU HBM system (EU-wide representativeness, prioritization process, terms for inclusion of studies, infrastructure, governing and coordination structure, sustainability, ..) to be addressed in the coming years (VITO, ISCIII, UBA, SpF, FOPH, INSA, LNS, LSMU, NIPH, SZU-CZ, MOH-CY)

Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

Co-leaders: INERIS (FR), AU (DK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EA (UK), EAWAG (CH), EFET (EL), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), FISABIO (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NKUA (EL), OFB (FR), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SYKE (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCLM (PT), UFZ (DE), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UniLU (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), ISCIII (ES), VUA (NL), NILU (NO), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), NMBU (NO), SpF (FR)

- P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU: this project focuses on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) with the purpose to establish and validate environmental monitoring structures for the long-term work in T4.2. In Year 2, this project will focus on monitoring activities (analysis and QA/QC). A detailed monitoring plan will be developed targeting i) PFAS in the freshwater environment and ii) EDCs in a multicompartment approach. This plan will include the final selection of target compounds, based on the information collected in Year 1, ensuring comprehensive analytical approaches also involving suspect and non-target screening, sum parameters (for PFAS) and effect-based methods (for EDCs), for example in tiered approaches or linked to specific monitoring purposes (e.g., hotspots vs. background monitoring) (P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS). Eventually, this plan will specify the analysis of each sample.

Based on criteria developed in Year 1 laboratories will be appointed for the chemical analyses. Detailed agreements will be made with each of the involved laboratories specifying the chemical analyses (e.g., compounds, methods and performance criteria) as well as time frames. QA/QC aspects will be assessed following consultations with the QA/QC group established under WP9, to ensure inputs as well as harmonization across PARC. Partners involved: SLU; BfG; NKUA; UFZ; MU; SCIENSANO; AU; INERIS (The list of partners involved in this activity is not complete and can evolve based on the assignment of the analytical work which will be decided during the previous phase of “Design of the monitoring campaign”). The data reporting will use formats and procedures developed in Year 1. Concepts for data analysis will be developed, including statistical methods. A Statistical Analysis Group will be set up in collaboration with WP7 and inter-linked with its homologue in T4.1 to ensure harmonised treatment and exploitation of the data. Following initial work in Year 1 on the conceptual approach to a feedback mechanism, this will be refined in collaboration with T2.1 and applied on a test basis to the first year of the pilot project. Partners involved: UFZ; NKUA; SLU; MU; UBA; CSIC; INERIS; AU. The list of partners involved in this activity is not complete and can evolve based on the assignment of the analytical work which will be decided during the previous phase of “Design of the monitoring campaign”.

- P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS: In order to identify and prioritize relevant research questions in the field of environmental and multisource monitoring, this project develops a mechanism to define monitoring studies, i.e. a framework for the automated assessment of large lists of compounds with the purpose of defining priority chemicals/matrices/endpoints for further work. This work was started in Year 1, in collaboration with T2.1 and T8.2, and will be continued in Year 2. This includes the preparation of D4.1 (M20). Further to this, Year 2 will focus on the implementation of this framework, including the set-up of suitable infrastructure, tests of applicability in defined case studies and potential adjustments.

Ultimately, the mechanism will be applied as a basis for the definition of new monitoring studies, responding to regulatory needs as mapped by T2.1. In year 2, the project will focus on the configuration and deployment of an automated on-line tool supporting the prioritisation framework (M16) [NKUA, SLU, INRAE, INERIS, UFZ, BfG, CNR-IRSA, NILU, CSIC, EAWAG] and on the test of the prioritisation framework on small case study(ies) (M26) [AU, INERIS, UBA, NKUA, EAWAG, CSIC, NILU, UFZ, UAntwerpen]

T4.2 will take the lead to establish an Ecotoxicology Working Group across WPs, involving partners in WP5, WP6 and WP9 with interest in effects on ecosystems and related risk assessment. Initial discussions have taken place in Year 1. In addition, T4.2 will work actively on building links to T4.1 and T4.3, facilitated by WP4 co-leaders, for optimized collaboration and long-term integration of human biomonitoring, environmental and multisource monitoring and innovative methods.

Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Co-Leaders: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), , INERIS (FR), INRS (FR), , IRFM (IT), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), ONIRIS (FR), ORU (SE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UBAH (UK), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), VITO (BE), WR (NL), AUTH (EL), BPI (GR), CNR-IRSA (IT), EV-ILVO (NL), FMUL (PT), GCSL (GR), GeoZS (SI), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), ISCI (ES), ISS (IT), IVL (SE), JU (CZ), KUM (DE), LNE (FR), NIB (SI), NIJZ (SI), NILU (NO), NIOM (PL), , OFB (FR), , STAMI (NO), SU (SE), SYKE (FI), THL (FI), TNO (NL), , UG-AT (AT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UNIABDN (UK), VSCHT (CZ), WULS-SGGW (PL)

A4.3.1 Transversal actions

- P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept Paper_MU: The manuscript of the final concept on innovative monitoring methods will be submitted early year 2 and revised according to the reviewer comments. [Lead: MU, Participants: INRAE (FR); VUA (NL); ANSES (FR); BRGM (FR); EAWAG (CH); EHESP (FR); INRS (FR); JSI (SI); LNS (LU); MUI (AT); UAntwerpen (BE); UBA (DE); UFZ (DE); VITO (BE); WR (NL); EV-ILVO (BE); NILU (NO); OFB (FR); UL-FFA (SI); AUTH (EL)].

- P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QA/QC Issues_WR. This project will define minimum quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) requirements to be used specifically for chemical screening methods based on chromatography coupled to High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) and biological effect-directed analysis (EDA) and will be closely linked to the activities in 9.3 (Joint activities – harmonisation, and its project: towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing). In this, existing international standards (e.g. ISO/IEC 17025, OECD GLP) are taken into account and serve as a basis for more detailed and dedicated protocols/procedures (and where appropriate criteria). In year 2 the review of existing QA/QC measurements for all steps from sample preparation, data acquisition, data processing, and result reporting will be finalized and a first draft of a guidance document will be presented, [Partners involved: Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ONIRIS (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (GR), EV-ILVO (BE), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), LNE (FR), WULS (PL)].

- P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03-Early Warning System_SLU. This project will support the development of an early warning system (EWS) in WP 8 by ensuring that data generated by innovative (self) sampling methods in combination with suspect/NTS/EDA approaches can be used to identify and to prioritize hazardous substances. In year 2, a methodology for integration of innovative sampling tools in an early warning

system will be developed and the literature review on the integration of suspect/NTS/EDA approaches in EWS will start. This project will formulate criteria for the categorization of annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format [Lead: SLU (SE), Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (GR), ISS (IT), NILU (NO)].

- P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP. This project consists in developing a comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS/NTS/EDA related data processing. Based on the conceptual work on an open access workflow in year 1 the development of a first operational version will be started in year 2. This includes the coordination and start of the group work (1-5) to build the first prototype version, the identification of large-scale datasets to be used to test the workflow and the identification and application of data processing related QA/QC provisions for large datasets. [Lead: EHESP, Participants: INRAE, MUI, UFZ, ANSES, UniLU, WR, VUA, INRS, ONIRIS, MU, UCPH, JSI, KWR, UBA].

A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts

- P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE. The objective of this project is to develop a proof-of-concept permitting to test and assess the performances of selected innovative sampling (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) and exposure measurement related methods (HRMS based SS/NTS and EDA) in comparison with those of conventional and targeted approaches. The study focus on mother-newborn/child pairs, During Year 2 the sample sourcing and sharing will be finalized. The main activities are connected to the analysis of the samples and include the sample preparation and chemicals analysis by high resolution mass spectrometry and effect-directed analysis for subset of samples The main expected output is to characterize current gap between conventional and innovative approaches, then contribute to scientifically support the prioritisation of some of them for further short to medium term implementation, and document/guide the need for further developments/improvements for others before implementation at larger scale. This will include the consolidation of the respective roles of all partners in the defined workplan, a first round of sample analyses based on individual partner capacities and the elaboration of a methodological harmonization basis from those individual capacities including an interlaboratory assay [Lead: INRAE (FR), Participants: EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (SP), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (SP), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), CSIC (SP), ISCII (SP), ISS (SP), SU (SE), AUTH (GR)].

- P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS. The objective of this new project is to develop a proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based screening methods for exploring occupational exposure in workplaces to chemicals of emerging concern. This project will closely connect to S4.1.1.5 for sample collection originated from occupational surveys dedicated to both healthcare and waste management sectors. One expected output is to assess the performances of selected innovative sampling (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) and exposure measurement (HRMS based SS/NTS) related methods, in comparison with those of conventional and targeted approaches. Another goal is to evidence new exposure markers associated to the considered occupational exposures. The project will start by elaboration of the detailed study design including an overarching global roadmap and the detailed workplan for sample preparation and analysis, QA/QC issues and alignment of identification methods of involved partners. Year 2, several actions will be realised: the consolidation of the refined global roadmap including a detailed workplan for selection of chemicals, sample analysis (from sample preparation to data processing), the inventory of the innovative methods developed by the partners. SOPs from WP4.1 occupational survey projects with the required information for SS/NTS, DBS and SWB sampling will be used and adapted.[Lead: INRS (FR), Key participants: WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (SP), STAMI (NO), LNS (LU), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), WR (NL), AUTH (EL)].

A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts

- P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01_Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH. This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on fingerprinting of wastewater treatment plant influents as a proxy for community wide human exposure assessment and on screening of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) into the water cycle. In year 2, the development of targeted and screening methods including validation for the assessment of human exposure will be continued [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), JU (CZ), UG-PL (PL).] For the environmental exposure assessment, the prioritization of features and patterns from screening data and the method development for new enrichment tools will be finalised [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), VITO (BE), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (LV), UG-PL (PL).]. The Method for high-throughput EDA (Effect-Directed Analysis) [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), KWR (NL), VUA (NL), ISS (IT), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), VITO (BE), UL-FFA (SI), JU (CZ), INRAE (FR), UG-PL (PL)] and the data mining methods and proof of concept on existing datasets [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR)] will be developed. The design of Pan-European Study will be realised and the goals will be planned [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), UG-PL (PL)].

- P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS. This project will elaborate and conduct a proof-of-concept demonstrating the potential use of sentinel animal species for capturing human exposure to emerging chemicals along the food chain. Year 2, a consensual study design will be elaborated among contributing partners (selected animal species, sample sourcing, analytical strategies for sample analyses, partner complementarities). A special caution will be paid also to the link with other existing initiative for mutualisation and optimization of the envisaged workplan (e.g., Life Apex). The actions that will be realised are the consolidation of the refined global roadmap and including a detailed workplan for selection of species, sample analysis, including all steps from sample preparation to data processing. A first set of relevant and accessible archived samples will be identified from the proposals from a consultation. [Lead: ONIRIS (FR), Participants: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfR (DE), Eawag (CH), CSIC (SP), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), JU (CZ), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).]

A4.3.4 Project Food samples based proof-of-concepts

- P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure_ANSES. This project will elaborate and conduct a set of complementary studies to illustrate the facility of innovative screening approaches (SS/NTS/EDA) to investigate real life complex co-exposures and emerging chemicals from food items. In Year 2 the global roadmap will be refined including the selection of food items and major classes of chemicals to focus on, the inventory of SS/NTS/EDA methods among the participants, the elaboration of the detailed workplan for method developments/improvement and sample analysis, from sample preparation to data processing, the consolidation of the respective roles of all partners in the workplan and the definition of minimal common QA/QC requirements to be specifically applied for HRMS/EDA based screening approaches applied to food matrices in link with P4.3.1.b_T02 [Lead: ANSES (FR). Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA

(NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL), EV-ILVO (BEL), GCSL (GR).]

Deliverables:

D4.1 Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals/matrices/endpoints for projects - Leader: INERIS (M20)

Additional Deliverables

AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies – Leader SpF. This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14)

AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances) - Leader: UBA. This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M24)

AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories – Leader INERIS/AU. This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M24).

AD4.5 Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) _ Leader INERIS/AU. This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14).

AD4.6 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTS/EDA approaches – Leader INRAE/VUA. This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14).

AD4.7 Summary of analytical methods applied in the pilot study (PFAS and EDCs), including a list of laboratories - Leader: INERIS/AU (M18)

AD4.8 Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies - Leader: TTL (M18)

WP N°	WP5	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES/BfR
WP title	Hazard Assessment		
Partner N°	1		
Partner short name	ANSES		
PM/partner	82.2		
Partner number	25.7		
	25.8		
	26		
	26.1		
	26.2		
	26.3		
	26.4		
	26.5		
	26.6		
	27.1		
	27.2		
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	33.2		
	33.4		
	34		
	34.5		
	35.2		
	35.6		
	35.10		
	35.12		
	36		
	37		
	41		
	50		
	52		
	54		
	58		
	59		

Partner short name	WR	WU-TOX	NIPH	IMR	STAMI	NILU	NIVA	NMBU	NVI	IEP-NRI	UG-PL	INSA	UAVR	JSI	NIB	NIC	ULFFA	MFUM	UNAV	UPO	ISCI3	IISPV	KI	SU	SLU	UU	AUTH	BPI	EAWAG	UKHSA	Cefas-Defra	EA	UINABDN	UOB
PM/partner	9.6	6.6	46	7.5	20	6	13	4	12	21.4	19.1	34.2	7	7	34	36	12	0.3	32	16	49	53.5	1	7.5	34	31	19.6	44.3	23	3	25.3	0.5	0.3	18
Start	M13										End										M24													

Objectives

The main goal of WP5 is to focus on Hazard Assessment (HA) for human and environmental health on three different directions: fill data gaps, develop and/or improve methodologies for HA to progress towards Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). The specific objectives of WP5 for year 2 are:

- Task 5.1: Continue pursuing the objectives from Year 1: Closing the identified regulatory data gaps regarding the selected mycotoxins (Alternaria toxins and enniatins) and BPA alternatives/analogues through in vitro testing targeting the following endpoints: endocrine disruption, genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, immunotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity, metabolic fate and bioactivation.
- Results will be shared with national and EU agencies involved in this task to ensure timely regulatory uptake of the results.
- Task 5.2: Continue with the development of innovative methodologies that will directly contribute to chemical hazard identification, risk assessment and regulation. WP5 will continue focusing on five different endpoints: immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption.
- Task 5.3: Continue with the objectives from Year 1:
 - Establishing different core or extended groups relevant for the activity of this task: omics, AOPs, bioinformatics, effect markers, PBTK, *in vivo/in vitro* mode of action,
 - Establishing an inventory and mapping available knowledge, reference *in vivo*/human datasets, activities and models in systems biology, PBTK and AOP frameworks and prioritising additional studies and
 - Initiating studies to characterise coregulated gene networks, for already published AOPs (to make them quantitative) and linking chemicals to available AOPs, linking omics data to human physiopathology, generating high quality ADME data and ultimately building new AOPs.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 5.1: Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

Leader: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), Co-leaders 5.1.2: BPI (EL)

Participants:

Activity 5.1.1: ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), IMR (NO), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), ISCI3 (ES), ISS (IT), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), STAMI (NO), TTL (FL), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT), UNAV (ES), UNIVIE (AT), WU-TOX (NL)

Activity 5.1.2: BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), NIB (SI) NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), SU (SE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UU (SE)

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health

- P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE: The Enniatins A, A1, B and B1 have testing priority. Alternariol and Alternaria monomethylether are among the prioritized compounds for the alternaria study program.

Review papers on existing toxicological data on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins have been prepared and will be published during Y2. All project partners are involved in the preparation of these review papers. The start of the studies depends on the availability of test item and resources, the centralization of the substance order/manufacturing has been ongoing in Y1, substances will be synthesized during Year 2. The *in vitro* studies agreed upon on Natural Toxins (enniatis and Alternaria toxins) to close data gaps will include the genotoxic, endocrine disruption, immunotoxic and other potential hazards characterization. Overall, the studies will provide urgently needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatis and Alternaria toxins. Reports will be available by Month 36 (M36). Experimental work will start Y2. We are in contact with the scientific officer from the feed and contaminants unit from EFSA regarding the availability of data on the enniatis and beauvericin program since EFSA is preparing for a possible update of the opinion. The program of studies and timelines for availability of data was shared. We are in contact with the OECD AOP project to exchange information.[Participants: BfR, UNIVIE, NIB, SCIENSANO, INSA, UNAV, ISS, BPI, INRS, NVI, STAMI, NIPH, IMR, ANSES, WU-TOX, Fraunhofer-IBMT, TUB]

- P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR: The agreed set of *in vitro* studies on BPA alternatives/analogues have the aim to close data gaps on non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, endocrine disruption, developmental neurotoxicity, immunotoxicology, and biotransformation (metabolism, bioactivation). Results will be shared with Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modellers in 5.3. Experimental work will start as soon as the test items are available. The studies will provide results for the reports available by Month 36 (M36). We are in contact with both ECHA and RIVM regarding the proposed study program on BPA alternatives in order to avoid duplication of efforts. Contact has been made with the EURION cluster regarding endocrine disruption studies.

Experimental work for each of the five endpoints:

➤ 1. Endocrine Disruption

1.1. *In vitro* Human H295R Steroidogenesis Assay (OECD TG 456) (ISS)

1.2 Effect of BPA and alternatives in thyroid hormone synthesis key events using *in vitro* test (under consideration by EURL ECVAM (ISCI))

1.3 Analysis of the data by assay (I.e. calculation EC50 and BMD values, fold changes) (ISS, INRAE, ISCI)

➤ 2. Developmental Neurotoxicity

2.1 *In vitro* screening of cellular effects of BPA and BPA alternatives (CNRS, INRAE)

2.2 Molecular analyses for the identification of relevant biomarkers (CNRS, INRAE, LIH)

2.3 Epigenetic analyses for the identification of relevant biomarkers (LIH)

2.4 Data Analyses, identification of biomarkers, proposition of new AOPs / implementing existing AOPs (LIH)

➤ 3. Immunotoxicity

3.1 Identification of immune cell targets and effects of bisphenols on immune functions. (UMIL)

3.2 Investigation of the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown and related immunobiochemical pathways. (MUI)

3.3. Investigation of the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the glucocorticoid system. (ULFFA)

3.4 To provide new mechanistic data for AOP development, the effects of BPA analogs on the intracellular calcium homeostasis of both resting and stimulated immune cells will be evaluated. (ISS)

➤ 4. Carcinogenicity

4.1 *In vitro* test as foreseen in the battery of genotoxicity testing as defined by EFSA (INSA, ISS)

4.2 *In vitro* genotoxicity of BPA and BPA alternatives and relevant metabolites will be assessed on hepatic 2D and/or 3D (spheroids) cell models developed from HepG2 using micronucleus, comet and transcriptomic assays (collaboration with T5.2a). (INSA, IBMT, NILU)

4.3 Non-genotoxic carcinogenicity of BPA and BPA alternatives will be assessed. Bhas 42 cell transformation assay (following OECD guidance document) (INRS, INSA, ISCIII, TTL, NILU)

➤ 5. Metabolism bioactivation routes and kinetics

5.1 *In vitro* study of the metabolic fate and bioactivation pathways of key BPA alternatives (BPA, TBBPA & BPS as “gold standards”; halogenated BPA analogues such as TCBPA ; PF201; BPS-MAE & BPS-IP, diglycidyl ethers;... and identification of involved enzymes and enzyme kinetics in differentiated HepaRG cells (HPR). For a selected set of available substances, ³H or ¹⁴C complete mass-balance studies will be performed. (INRAE)

5.2 Absorption studies with intestinal models (when deemed necessary) and isoform-specific biotransformation with quantitative measurement of Km and Vmax as input of PBPK modelling in experimental models other than HepaRG cells to highlight also possible interindividual difference (ISS)

[Participants: ISS, UMIL, INRAE, TTL, UL FFA, MUI, ISCIII, INRS, IBMT, AUTH, CNRS, LIH, SDU, NILU, INSA]

For both projects we are in close contact with partners within PARC, especially 5.2, 5.3 and WP6 in order to exchange data.

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment)

- P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_Ugent: the selection of the compounds to be tested will be finalized and testing with single compounds will start. In parallel, the selection of mixtures to be tested during Y3 will be carried out in Y2 also considering the results of toxicity testing with single compounds. Specifically, the following OECD tests will be carried out with mixtures of natural toxins:

- 1) OECD 243: *Lymnaea stagnalis* Reproduction Test (SLU)
- 2) OECD 211: *Daphnia magna* reproduction test (UGent)
- 3) OECD 201: Freshwater Alga and Cyanobacteria, Growth Inhibition Test (*Chlorella vulgaris*) (UAVR)
- 4) OECD: harpacticoid copepod development and reproduction test with *Nitocra Spinipes* (UGent).

Exposure scenarios for invertebrates will be conducted through dietary exposure of mixture of toxin-producing strains ordered from certified culture collections (e.g., same strains as used for individual testing) [Participants: SLU, UGent, UAVR]

- P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU: the review of the current knowledge on BPA alternatives concerning the regulatory needs will be finalized and published and therefore the bisphenols (single compounds and mixtures) to be tested in Y2 will be decided taking into consideration our AD5.1 BPA Alternative, prioritization workshop. In addition, toxicity testing will start in certain organisms depending on the needs that will be identified in the review paper. A long list of assays can be conducted by the involved partners covering a wide range of organisms (e.g., fish, aquatic invertebrates, alga, marine bacteria, earthworms, soil microorganisms, xenopus, *C. elegans*) and effects (e.g., acute effects, effects on reproduction and on endocrine system). In Y2 and before starting the experiments with real-life mixtures, a series of tests will be conducted mainly with high-throughput screening assays (e.g., Microtox® Acute Toxicity Test) on single compounds and binary or mixture of low complexity to derive some principles of how the BPA analogues behave in mixtures. As regards the effects on endocrine system a

tiered approach in testing will be followed, e.g., firstly, level 3 tests will be carried out and depending on the results level 4 tests maybe be conducted as well. Identification of most suitable candidates for individual NAM will take place Y2. [Participants: BPI, SLU, IISPV, SDU, INERIS, INRAE, NIB, IEP-NRI, UU, UG-PL, UAVR, EAWAG, NIVA, UFZ, SU]

Task 5.2: Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Leader: DTU FOOD (DK), VUB (BE), Co-leaders 5.2.2: MU (CZ)

Participants:

Activity 5.2.1: AIT (AT), ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), Cefas-Defra (UK), DTU (DK), IfaDo (DE), INRAE (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), UU-IRAS (NL), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), IUF (DE), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), NPHC (HU), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), TiHo (DE), UAntwerpen (BE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UIBK (AT), UKHSA (UK), UKL (DE), UKON (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), ULFFA (SI), UNAV (ES), UU (SE), VUA (NL), VUB (BE), WR (NL)

Activity 5.2.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UPO (ES)

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

-P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE: The development of tests that can identify tissue and substance specific effects related to distinct aspects of non-genotoxic carcinogenesis will be continued in Y2. Based on the compiled lists, a selection of model non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTXCs) chemicals will be made to scientifically validate the selected NGTXCs test methods. For accuracy evaluation, a large set of compounds will be selected and tested. The set-up of novel NAMs for identified gaps in the assessment of NGTXC will be initiated [Participants: INRAE, BfR, ANSES, INSERM, NIB, UL-LACDR, UNAV, IRFM, RIVM, UKHSA, UKL, NILU]

- P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE: An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further Mode of Action (MoA) exploration, as well as Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP) and read-across development synergies. Exploration of Nuclear Receptor-driven effects will focus on the characterization of BPA alternatives' interaction with the nuclear receptors PPARg, PXR, CAR, RXRa using stable reporter cell lines and biophysical (crystallization, 3D structure determination) approaches. Synergies between ongoing projects and other subtasks of WP5.2a, 5.1 and 5.3 will be further extended in Y2. Significant developments are also expected on the human mesenchymal stem cells (2D/3D), BPA alternatives effects on adipocyte (human, murine) and zebrafish models. Several articles characterizing the interaction of bisphenols with CAR, and of their halogenated analogues with PXR and PPARg are envisaged. Intra-task collaborations will further be increased so to enhance complementarities and grant the development of NAMs targeting a refined assessment of the effects of Metabolism Disrupting Chemical (MDC). On top effects of selected substances on triglyceride accumulation in liver cells will be analysed. Involvement of mTOR signaling in metabolic disruption will be assessed.

Actions /Experiments:

1. Extended assessment of Nuclear Receptor (NR) activities testing (PPARg, PXR, CAR) using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds (INSERM)

2. *In vitro* assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterization established (BfR, UIBK, UU-IRAS, UFZ, UAntwerpen and UU)

[Participants: INRAE, BfR, INSERM, IfaDo, UU-IRAS, UAntwerpen, UU, UIBK, UFZ]

- P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU: Characterization of the molecular mechanisms that can be exploited for NAM -Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors (THSD)- testing will be continued in Y2. *In vivo* studies are planned to start in 2023 whilst already initiated *in vitro* and *in silico* assay developments

will go on. A rodent multi-organ transcriptomics study as well as a transcriptomics cross-species comparison of *in vivo* rodent liver toxicity with human stem cell-based *in vitro* assays will be performed. The evolutionary conservation of the Thyroid Hormone System (THS) axis will be further characterized to make better use of non-human NAMs to inform on human health risks. The ongoing literature review to extrapolate THSD from fish/amphibians to mammals/humans will be expanded to a bisphenols case study. Publication of the ‘Endocrine Disruptor-Thyro project’ in a Special Topic in Frontiers in Toxicology is envisaged [Participants: DTU, VUB, BfR, SDU, UAntwerpen, VUA, ISCIII, INSERM]

- P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm: in Y2, activities related to the set-up of *in vitro* systems that allow assessing key events in the immune system function or dysfunction will be continued. This includes further exploration of the different *in vitro* systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity and characterization of their usefulness and limitations to come to a testing strategy (MUI, NPHC, RIVM, LIST). To determine common markers of immunosuppression and response to vaccination, studies in human, animal and in different primary cells and cell lines will be further combined to identify the most relevant *in vitro* or *ex vivo* system for human health (INSERM, NIPH, INSA, LIH). Studies on NAMs and assays for immunotoxic events by (mixtures of) model or priority compounds including mycotoxins and bisphenols will be continued to support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs (UL-FFA, UFZ, WR).
[Participants: INSERM, NIPH, MUI, NPHC, RIVM, UU-IRAS, UL-FFA, INSA, UFZ, WR, LIH, LIST]

- P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU : The selection of candidate compounds for assay development will be continued as well as setting up the NAMs for Developmental and Acute Neurotoxicity (DNT and ANT) to fill up the gaps in the current DNT *in vitro* test battery. The established partners’ assay list will be used to design a comparative study on performance, sensitivity, specificity and redundancy. Improved characterization of the models for the presence and function of transporters/receptors is planned. Novel zebrafish models for higher-level Central Nervous System behavioral/cognitive endpoints, including response, anxiety-like behavior, learning and memory effects will be developed, evaluated and used.
[Participants: INSERM, UU, NIPH, IUF, UKON, RIVM, UFZ, ISCIII, TiHo, AIT, NMBU, UG-PL].

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

Based on the review activity done in Y1 (AD5.1) under the project P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU, the activity 5.2.2 will use selected BPA alternatives to develop, optimize and establish new approach methodologies (NAMs), if the BPA alternatives will be found suitable for the specific endpoint as e.g., positive test chemical. In case, that BPA alternatives will not be best candidates for development of a specific method, the alternative chemical will be selected and used for the development and optimization of NAMs. With respect to horizontal priority (priority chemicals), NAMs will be developed in 3 main areas of research:

- i) *in silico* and modelling tools for hazard assessment of chemicals to ultimately support grouping of substances and read across approaches based on NAMs,
- ii) invertebrate's methods (advancing invertebrates models as NAMs for the hazard assessment of chemicals) and
- iii) vertebrate's methods (advancing vertebrate aquatic models (e.g., zebrafish, xenopus embryos) for environmental hazard assessment of chemicals).

Y2 will be fully dedicated for development of NAMs, where first assays are expected to be delivered. The activity A.2.2 in the Y2 will be closely aligned with other PARC tasks, specifically with WP 5.3 (data derived in 5.2.2 will be offered for AOP development / modeling), WP6.1&6.2 (building NAMs confidence for regulatory purposes), WP7 (data management) and WP9 to identify synergies.[Participants: BfG, BPI, EAWAG, IISPV, INERIS, MU, MUI, NIB, NIC, NIVA, SDU, SLU, UAntwerpen, UFZ, UG-PL, UPO]

Task 5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

Leader: UL-LACDR (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), INSERM (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE)

Participants:

Activity 5.3.1 and 5.3.3: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIH (ES), ISS (IT), KIT (DE), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), NPHC (HU), Sciensano (BE), UFZ (DE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIABDN (UK), UOB (UK), WR (NL)

Activity 5.3.2: ACES/SU(SE), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), DTU (DK), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KIT (DE), KU-Leuven (BE), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NPHC (HU), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL)

Activity 5.3.4: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), EA (UK), ETHZ (CH), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIH (ES), ISS (IT), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), UFZ (DE), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation & A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

A5.3.1 and A5.3.3 (Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment) were combined in a single project for coherence purposes.

- P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR: In Y2, partners will further develop the project that has been started in Y1. A workshop will be organized on data requirements for systems toxicology (in collaboration with 5.3.2). Different specialty groups (immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, EDCs, metabolic disruption) will gather relevant mode of action data that will be useful to develop AOPs in 5.3.2. A major objective is to establish novel reference transcriptomics data sets for prioritized NAMs (which will be characterized in task 5.2) using available data and additional omics data derived experimentally. Partners will also continue to develop new bioinformatics tools to facilitate qualitative and quantitative mechanistic interpretation of omics data. Amongst others, this will involve co-regulated gene network analysis in combination with TXG-MAPr tool development and protein-protein association network approach (PPAN). These tools will also support AOP development in 5.3.2. Furthermore, we will fill the human data gaps that are necessary for translation of biological systems toxicology information from human *in vitro* test systems to the human *in vivo* situation. A focus will be on target organs that are relevant for toxicology and for which clinical samples are available. We will start generating additional omics data from available selective biobank human samples. This will ultimately support the human relevance of NAMs studies. At the end of the year, case studies will be identified to evaluate the applicability of the tools developed in this project [Participants: UGent, MUI, ISCIH, INSERM, ISS, UL-LACDR, BPI, KIT, NPHC, WR, Sciensano, NIPH, UNIABDN, UFZ, UG-PL, IRFM, UIBK, UMIL, AUTH, UOB and IISPV].

A5.3.2 AOP development

- P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm: Year 2, the core group of this project (CG) will continue to develop new tools supporting AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathway) development, in particular artificial intelligence (AI) and text mining tools. CG will support the work of the Specialty groups (SGs): SG1 (Immunotoxicity), SG2 (Endocrine and metabolic disruption), SG3 (Neurotoxicity) and the Effect Marker Group (EMG) using these tools. It has to be noted that all CG partners are also involved in the SGs so that their technical support is made easier. CG will organize the workshop initially planned in year 1 and will summarize the conclusions of the AOP workshop in a short report to be largely shared.

[Participants: ACES or SU, AU, AUTH, BfG, BPI, DTU, IISPV, Inserm, IRSN, ISS, KI, KIT, KU-Leuven, LIST, MUI, NILU, NIPH, NPHC, UG-PL, SDU, Sciensano, UAntwerpen, UGent, UKK/UoC, UIBK, UL-LACDR, UMIL, UNIVIE, WR and Cefas-Defra].

A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology

- P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Fraunhofer: A review of the conceptual and knowledge gaps in IVIVE-PBK models to define relevant case studies, case study compounds and relevant case study problem formulations, was started in 2022 and was finalized in month 12 of the project. The second year will focus on case studies, the generation/or identification (of existing) *in vitro* ADME data and their integration into the PBK models. As the modeling will be done in this project, but data will be mainly generated in WP5.1 and 5.2, and analytical approaches might be done in WP4, this project will work highly integrative. Partners from T5.1, 5.2 and WP4 will directly be invited to case studies and potential partners will be identified within a joint workshop in the beginning of year 2. One of a case study will be about a tiered testing strategy, i.e. which cells and which culture conditions are needed to parameterize the PBK model for inhalation exposure with substance-specific ADME data. This is of particular importance taking into account the low throughput and analytical challenges (and thus high costs) attributed to *in vitro* ADME models working with air-lifted (ALI) exposure conditions. By including detailed organ kinetics like blood brain barrier (BBB), it will also improve the predictive quality of PBK or IATA in the integrated risk assessment framework. These models will be of particular interest to the endpoint DNT, which is of high interest in PARC. The PBK model developed within this project will help to address susceptibility differences in the human population. Another case study will address the kinetic relevance of the human microbiome. The main question at this stage is the metabolic competence of the human microbiome compared to e.g., metabolism in the liver and the integration of the observed metabolites into the PBK model. These and other regulatory questions will guide the case study work in this project. Model case study compounds will be used, which do have *in vivo* ADME data. These data will be used for uncertainty analyses.

[Participants: ANSES, ETHZ, IISPV, INERIS, Inserm, ISCIII, ISS, Fraunhofer-ITEM, NVI, UKK/UoC (DE), UIBK, UNIVIE, WR,WU-TOX, EA, AUTH, UFZ, Cefas-Defra and NIPH].

Deliverables:

D5.1 New approach methodologies Report - Leader: BfR (M18)

D5.2 New PBK Models Report - Leader: Fraunhofer-ITEM (M24)

D5.3 New AOPs Report - Leader: INSERM (M24)

Additional Deliverables

AD 5.4 – Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and AD 5.6 – Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritized endpoints. These ADs were initially planned Y1 (M12) but are postponed to Y2 (M14) and they are being merged to only one AD 5.4. Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints. Leader UL-LACDR (M14)

AD 5.7 – Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms – Leader UL-LACDR, SCIENSANO. This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M18)

WP N°	WP6													Lead Beneficiary							RIVM/KEMI															
WP title	Innovation in regulatory risk assessment																																			
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	1.12	1.13	3	3.1	3.4	4	4.5	4.6	4.7	5	5.1	5.3	7	8	10.1	10.2	10.3	10.4	10.5	11.2	13.1	14	14.2	15	15.2	15.4	15.5	

Partner short name	PM/partner	Partner N°	Partner short name	PM/partner	Partner N°	Partner short name	PM/partner	Start
ANSES	71.3	16.1	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME	7.5	32	NIJZ	18	M13
INSERM	15.2	16.4	IfADo	12	32.1	OI	6	
INRAE	6.1	18	UI	2.3	32.2	NLZOH	0.1	
INERIS	23	20	ISS	27	33	CSIC	64	End
INRS	3	20.1	ICPS	7.8	33.3	UGR	8	
ONIRIS	25.5	20.3	IRFM	10.5	34	ISCHII	22	
IRSN	4.5	20.4	IUSS	6.5	34.3	FINBA	9.6	
OFB	8.5	20.7	UNIPD	5	34.5	IISPV	36.5	
GSTB	6.7	21	RSU	3	34.7	UCLM	34.5	
EHESP	0.5	23	LSMU	3.2	35.1	UGOT	25.2	
EAA	3.5	24	LNS	8	35.2	KI	410.5	
AGES	17	24.2	LIST	12	35.3	ULUND	2.5	
MUI	6	25	RIVM	52.8	35.5	RISE	12	
VITO	39.2	25.1	KWR	3.7	35.6	SU	54	
OVAM	1.3	25.2	TNO	8.2	35.7	KEMI	16.6	M24
ISSEP	12	25.3	RUMC	6	35.8	IVL	10.7	
UAntwerpen	25.4	25.4	UL-LACDR	23.3	35.10	SLU	20	
SCIENSANO	75	25.5	UU-IRAS	22.6	36	AUTH	46	
UGent	15	25.6	VUA	0.5	37	BPI	42.5	
VUB	21	25.7	WR	7.9	38	FOPH	1	
MOH-CY/SGL	1	25.8	WU-TOX	24	40	UNISANTE	16	
MU	72.7	26	NIPH	23.2	41	EAWAG	13.3	
AU	20.1	26.2	STAMI	24.4	44	FOEN	5	
DTU FOOD	36.5	26.3	NILU	2.5	45	USI	3	
REGIONH-GE	14	26.4	NIVA	9.4	46	UNIBAS	23	
UCPH	2	27	NIOM	12.5	49	EFSA	4	
SDU	4	27.1	IEP-NRI	19.6	50	UKHSA	3	
UT	18	27.2	UG-PL	15.5	52	Cefas-Defra	17.3	
SYKE	3.5	28	FMUL	5	53	UKCEH	9.7	
TTL	9.3	29	INSA	14.3	54	EA	0.5	
Tukes	2	29.3	ENSP	5.3	59	UOB	13.5	
UBA	33.7	29.4	UC	17.8	60	UCL	3	
UFZ	31.3	29.5	UAVR	14.1				
UKOLD	31	31	JSI	26				
UOS	8.5	31.1	GEoZS	8.2				

Objectives

The main goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) as ultimate goal. The specific objectives of WP6 for year 2 are:

1. Task 6.1: To further develop and refine quantitative networks of AOPs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity, to assess their human relevance and to identify associated NAMs. To re-design, based on this work, regulatory relevant IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and (re-)evaluate the applicability of developed IATAs by means of dedicated case studies in an iterative way.
2. Task 6.2: To further develop and apply innovative methods, tools and concepts and perform

integrative risk and health impact assessments based on internal and external exposure of humans exposed to single chemicals and mixtures from multiple sources and routes for different living environments (including workplace).

3. Task 6.3: To continue implementation and further refinement of case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA
4. Task 6.4: To develop an efficient and protective regulatory workable RA methods through in-depth analysis of collected data for mixtures, articles, NAMs and biodiversity.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 6.1: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

Co-Leaders: SCIENSANO (BE), UL-LACDR (NL)

Partners: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP-UNL (PT), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KWR (NL), LIST (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), STAMI (NO), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UKHSA (UK), UKCEH (UK), VUB (BE), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)

A6.1.1: Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes

In Y2, we will continue the development of IATAs for the 'low-hanging fruit' endpoints, *i.e.* genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with a focus on (1) thyroid hormone system disruption and (2) antiandrogen activity) and liver toxicity (with a focus on fibrosis) for selected regulatory framework(s) and specific population groups. Based on the outcome of the mapping exercise on the availability and maturity (*i.e.* the level of completeness) of existing AOPs and existing NAMs, and the extent to which these NAMs have already been mapped to AOPs for these endpoints, AOP networks (AON) will be designed and/or refined. In case sufficient information is available, AON will be (partially) quantitated. The type of modelling used for quantitation will depend on the AOP. Ideally, dynamic modelling will be performed. However, this type of modelling is very data demanding, which may not always be available, hence, more simple models may need to be used. Gaps in data, being of either qualitative or quantitative nature, identified based on discussions with the relevant partners involved in T6.1 and WP5 will be filled, where needed, by performing additional tests in collaboration with WP5. It should be noted that semi-quantitative or qualitative AON are useful for informing IATA development as well. The IATAs will be based on human relevant AOPs/AONs. Therefore, the AOPs/AONs developed for the three health effects will be subject to human relevance assessment by applying the first version of the modified workflow designed in Y1. The latter is based on the draft workflow for human relevance assessment developed by RIVM. The workflow involves qualitative and quantitative considerations and relies on toxicological, epidemiological and clinical data, and will also undergo different cycles of refinement. Since this activity directly relates to scientific criteria for NAMs (A6.4.2), the progress made and possible issues encountered will continue to be discussed in regular WP6 meetings. In addition to AOPs that have been developed with a primary focus on human adverse effects, AOPs focusing on non-mammalian model species will be used as well to assess the potential for cross-species extrapolation to human health. The overall set of human-relevant AOPs will be connected in a cross-species AON allowing to identify the key events and associated NAMs that will be used to design IATAs for the selected health effects. The human-relevant AONs will be used to (re-)design IATAs for the selected health effects in close collaboration with OECD and according to OECD guidance. IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be an iterative process consisting of various cycles of optimisation, thereby taking into account the feedback from different stakeholders (A6.1.3). The progress made, issues encountered and the draft IATAs will be reported in AD6.9 (UL-LACDR, M24). Additionally, a strategy for achieving IATAs for more complex endpoints (e.g., developmental neuro/immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity) will be further developed. This work was initiated in Y1 (Spring 2023) with a series of dedicated workshops, organized in close collaboration with WP5.3 and related initiatives, such as the OECD Expert Groups for developmental neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, ATHLETE, ONTOX, EU-ToxRisk and

RISK-HUNT3R. The outcomes of the workshops will be used for defining an appropriate strategy, which will be reported in AD6.1 (SCIENSANO, M18).

- P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM: This project is focused on the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathway under study. In year 2, the project will decide on the problem formulation and approach for the development of a workflow for human relevance assessment, will complete the inventory of relevant existing approaches for assessment of human relevance, weight of evidence and uncertainty analysis, will finalize the definition of and carry out the case studies for further improvement of the workflow, will organize face-to-face meeting(s) with the project team and will schedule and prepare for a stakeholder workshop to discuss the first set of case studies [Partners involved: AUTH (EL); RIVM (NL); ENSP (PT); BPI (EL); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); ; IISPV (ES); LIST (LU)]

- P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen: IATA development for endocrine disruption. In year 2, this project will integrate information on readiness of methods from external activities such as OECD TDM EG and perform additional readiness assessments if required. This project will also design and develop IATAs v0.1 for thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) and for (anti-)androgenicity (AA) and will identify critical linkages in the AOP networks / conceptual IATA models for development of quantitative KERs and/or models [Partners involved: UAntwerpen (BE); UKHSA (UK); MU (CZ); AUTH (EL); UGent (BE); INSERM (FR); UL-LACDR (NL); RIVM (NL); ISS (IT); DTU (DK); SDU (DK); LIST (LU); BPI (EL); UG-PL (PL); IISPV (ES); STAMI (NO); KI (SE); IRFM (IT); ENSP-UNL (PT); Sciensano (BE); CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), JRC (EU)].

- P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano: In year 2, this project will finish initial inventory of existing (draft) AOPs and AOP networks relevant for genotoxicity, will design IATA_v1.0 for genotoxicity based on an inventory of NAMs and AOP network. This project will also design and execute initial case study for genotoxicity, including initial data acquisition. This project will realise the initial quantification of AOPs related to genotoxicity based on an initial case study and literature data and will perform a systematic review of the variability of the various genotoxicity methods within and between laboratories (to identify the main drivers of variability) [Partners involved: Sciensano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE), UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (EL), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO), IRFM (IT), NIPH (NO), WR (NL), MUI (AT)].

- P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR: IATA development for liver toxicity. This project was initiated in Y1 (Spring 2023) with a series of dedicated workshops, organized in close collaboration with WP5.3 and related initiatives, such as the OECD Expert Groups for developmental neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, ATHLETE, ONTOX, EU-ToxRisk and RISK-HUNT3R. The outcomes of the workshops will be used for defining an appropriate strategy, which will be reported in AD6.1 (SCIENSANO, M18). In year 2, this project will finish initial inventory of existing (draft) AOPs and AOP networks that are relevant for fibrosis. This project will also broaden AOPs and AOP networks towards other endpoints relevant for the liver. This project will design initial IATA for fibrosis based on inventory of NAMs and will design and execute initial case study for fibrosis, including initial data acquisition. It will finish the development of generic dynamical modeling framework for qAOP development and realize the initial quantification of AOPs related to fibrosis based on initial case study and literature data [Partners involved: UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WR (NL).]

A6.1.2: Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

The draft versions of the IATAs (v0.1) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity as well as the draft workflow (v1.1) for human relevance assessment developed in A6.1.1 will be evaluated through

case studies. Like the development, the evaluation of IATAs will be done in close collaboration with OECD. Under the coordination of the case study leader, case study teams will investigate the case study regulatory hypothesis that was defined in Y1 with the selected relevant case study compounds. The case study teams consist of both *in silico* and *in vitro* NAM experts that represent the critical (pre-)validated NAMs that can be mapped to the AOP/AON. Scientists with expertise on QSAR modelling, PBK modelling, omics analysis, and uncertainty analysis are included in the case study teams as well. For ultimate integration of the data into QIVIVE, we will make a link with the experts and tools established in T5.3. Reports on the case study modeling and experimental activities will be submitted for review via the project management system under T2.1. In the IATA case studies, the lessons learned by different stakeholders from previous case studies mapped in T6.3 will also be implemented as soon as this information becomes available. The design of the case studies and the results obtained will be reported together with the draft IATAs and draft workflow for human relevance assessment (A6.1.1) in AD6.9 (UL-LACDR, M24). [AUTH, BPI, CEFAS, DTU, ENSP, Fraunhofer, IISPV, INRAE, ISS, KI, KWR, MU, MUI, RIVM, SCIENSANO, SDU, UAntwerpen, UG-PL, UKHSA, UL-LACDR, VUB, WR, WU-TOX]

A6.1.3: Stakeholder engagement

For each of the health effects addressed we will continue the interactions with relevant related (research) initiatives, such as EURION, EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX and HESI GTTC, established in Y1. This will be done through dedicated meetings, with the aim to achieve synergies. For a wider stakeholder involvement, the progress made on AOP/AON and IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be discussed with a diverse group of stakeholders in the annual two-day WP6 workshop, with the explicit aim to collect feedback on the work done and input on the next steps. Participants of this meeting will include WP6 partners, relevant WP/task leaders of PARC, representatives of national/European regulatory agencies, OECD, JRC, industrial partners and NGOs. Where needed, additional meetings will be organised between representatives of relevant related research projects/programmes and T6.1.1 partners, with the aim to discuss in detail the AOP/AON and IATA development. [RIVM, SCIENSANO, UL-LACDR, STAMI, ISS, UG-PL, BPI].

Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment

Co-Leaders: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE)

Partners: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CSTB (FR), DTU FOOD (DK), EFSA (IT), EHESP (FR), ENSP (PT), FINBA (ES), TTL (FI), FMUL (PT), FOPH (CH), Fraunhofer (DE), GGeoSZ (SI), ICPS (IT), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), KI (SE), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), IUSS (IT), IVL (SE), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), ONIRIS (FR), RIVM (NL), RUMC (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SECO (CH), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAVR (PT), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)

A6.2.1 Aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers

- P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO: from the inventory of realistic source-to-dose models for the general population, the existing model parameters and the gap analysis (models and data for model parameters), the development of realistic models (for identified gaps) will continue. This involves the translation of the mechanistic understanding of source-to-dose exposure into conceptual models, for two aspects (i) direct exposure to chemicals released from consumer products and materials, and (ii) direct and indirect exposure via release and transfer from the environment. Case studies will be organized around the chemicals (at least metals, PFAS, phthalates, lindane), products, and environmental sources prioritized for the project

and will start during this second year. Case studies include several aspects: set up of scenarios, model parameterization, model runs and interpretations and verification of model outcomes. In year 2, the project will continue the generation of the mechanistic understanding of source-to-dose exposure and will continue on scoping and elaboration of the case studies. The inventory of existing data to parametrise the conceptual will continue, and this work will be focused on needs for selected case studies. [Partners involved: VITO (BE); RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); LNS (LU); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT), UoB (UK), IISPV (ES)].

- P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES: the strategy to assess aggregate exposure through different living environments (occupational, general environment, domestic environment) and different routes of entry (inhalation, dermal, ingestion) will continue to be developed. From the inventory of the associated models and tools and the analysis of their structure, their input and their output, a functional design will be established to connect models. The development of case studies on at least metals, pesticides, PFAS, phtalates will continue with the organization of the data, tools, models and by studying the applicability of the proposed methodological approach to combine heterogeneous datasets. The project will develop innovative approach for aggregate exposure based on current methods and guidance recommendations. [Partners involved: ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), RIVM (NL), VITO (BE), UU (SE), NIOM (PL), INSA (PT), TNO (NL), NIJZ (SI), AU (DK), TTL (FI), RUMC (NL), GeoZS (SI), LNS (LU), ISSeP (BE), CSTB (FR), EFSA (EU), MU (CZ), WR-BIOM (NL), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), NIPH (NO), KWR (NL), IVL (SE), ISCII (ES), FOPH (CH), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), UOB (UK), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL)]

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life

In year 2, the activity 6.2.2 will participate to two projects: the refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment (P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS) and mixtures (in collaboration with activity 6.2.3, P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM).

- P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS: based on the inventory made in year 1, the refinement of existing PBPK models and the development of new ones will be started for metals, pesticides, mycotoxins, bisphenols and PFAS. The objectives will be to be able to deliver PBPK models for compounds for which no models are available yet (e.g., some mycotoxins), for exposure routes that are not implemented yet (e.g., inhalation and dermal contact for PFAS), for sensitive populations (e.g., lead in the developing fetus), and for target organs (e.g., detailed description of the blood-brain barrier for metals and bisphenols). The harmonization of physiology equations and parameters through life will start and QSARs for parameters related to kinetics and partitioning will be developed. Different sources of data will be used for the model parametrization and evaluation: either from literature, or from newly generated data in PARC (e.g., in WP5). Meanwhile, case studies will be set up by defining the regulatory framework and identifying the cohort data to be analyzed. [Partners involved: INERIS (FR), AUTH (EL), IISPV (ES), ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), SLU (SE), NIPH (NO), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL), WR (NL) IRFM (IT), IVL (SE), TNO (NL)]

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment

- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM: in year 2, the working groups on hazard and kinetics will continue to collect, organize and develop information to set toxicological thresholds as well as kinetic models and parameters for the prioritized chemical families and effects (e.g., pesticides and NAM/NAN effects, PFAS and immune effect, metals and kidney effects, metals and DNT effects). The ongoing case studies cover mainly mixtures of substances from the same chemical family (pesticides and NAM/NAN effects, PFAS and immune effect, metals and kidney effects, metals and DNT effects); in the next steps of

the project, we will also cover mixtures of substances from different chemical families (based on co-exposure from HBM data and on common health effects, e.g. developmental effects – covering pesticides and metals)

Mixture kinetic models will be applied when needed to convert external to internal HBM-GV or exposure and vice-versa. From the working group on HBM data, the first set of real-life of mixtures crossing regulatory silos will be produced from combined exposure at European and national levels by applying statistical methods on selected HBM studies. This might trigger the need for additional hazard data or additional chemicals to be grouped in assessment groups. The observations will be discussed with WP5 and might result in the generation of new hazard data. The scientific and innovative output of the three working groups will be combined to start to perform first risk assessment for the prioritized chemical families and effects for general and occupational populations. The three working groups will continue to jointly improve the strategy to perform risk assessment and write a handbook. Case studies will show impact for selected regulatory silos (prioritized chemical families) and examples will be provided of an overarching regulatory silo approach (e.g. real life mixtures from HBM data). Statistical methods to study the link between mixtures biomarkers of exposure and health effects will be compared and applied to cohorts with sufficient information on biomarkers of exposure and biomarkers of effect. Work will be performed in close cooperation with WP7 (linked to the project and via data champions) and WP4 on data generation. Furthermore, statistical models will be incorporated in task 8.3. (model infrastructure). Training will be given to stakeholders and synergy will be discussed with particular EFSA and ECHA. More interaction is foreseen with EFSA panels and relevant working groups. The MCRA Integrated Risk Assessment Dashboard will be extended with occupational data and risk interpretation. PARC will not be mandated to perform real-risk assessment, but PARC will offer tools, concepts and realistic examples/case studies on how the risk assessment can be innovated. In year 2, this will be further discussed with DG SANTE, DG ENVI, DG EMPL, EFSA and ECHA. This will drive the work in year 3.

[Partners involved: ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), UGR (ES), DTU (DK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), IVL (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), RUMC (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), SECO (CH), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGR (ES), UNIPD (IT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), INRAE (FR), KWR (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), UNIVIE (AT), IRFM (IT), IPA (DE), INRAE (FR)].

A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators

- P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO: the project will continue the exploration of possibilities to fill data gaps for data-poor chemicals identified and prioritized in year 1, via in-silico modelling of exposures, derivation of population-specific exposures and spatio-temporal and interindividual variations, and establishment of exposure-effect associations by linking exposure, lifestyle, geographical, SES, and health status data, comparing multiple time frames, regions and populations. A quick scan of newly available health impact assessments and environmental burden of disease calculations, exposure data, and exposure-effect functions will be performed. Additional data gaps to be addressed in the course of PARC will be identified and prioritized. [Partners involved: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), RUMC (NL), Sciensano (BE), STAMI (NO), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE)]

- P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS: the project will continue the activities related to exposure-effect relationships initiated in year 1: inventory of existing exposure-biomarker of effect-health outcome relationships, incorporation of effect biomarker measurements as surrogate markers for toxicity associated with chemical exposure which would allow health impact assessment for (pre)clinical outcomes, development of an integrative approach to take different lines of evidence (in vitro, in vivo, and human data, mode of action, biomarkers of effect) into account to establish human relevant exposure-effect relationships, addressing all associated uncertainties, and development of a Weight-of-evidence (WoE)

approach for selection of exposure-effect functions including information from epidemiological, toxicological and mechanistic studies. In addition, an inventory of and comparison will be made of existing methodologies, indicators and frameworks (WHO, ECHA, etc.) used for cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) related to health impact of chemical exposures. Methodological issues related to cost metrics and opportunities for harmonization of Social Cost Benefit Analyses approach will be identified. Other methodological improvements identified and prioritized in year 1 may be initiated as well, for other issues that will still be identified, feasibility of addressing those during the course of PARC will be assessed and activities will be planned accordingly. [Partners involved: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIPH (NO), OI (SI), RIVM (NL), Sciensano (BE), UBA (DE), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL)].

- P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS: the design of the first case studies to calculate health impact, burden of disease, risk/benefit and/or cost/benefit focusing on chemicals, exposure-(biomarker of) effect relationships, exposure scenarios, and methodological improvements and innovations prioritized in year 1, will be finalized and implementation will be initiated in this project. Additional case studies for PARC year 3 will be prioritized (according to the criteria established in year 1, which will be updated and refined if needed) and prepared. [Partners involved: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), KI (SE), NIPH (NO), OI (SI), RUMC (NL), Sciensano (BE), STAMI (NO), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE)].

- P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO: in year 2, the project will focus on the development of the first indicators (proposed in year 1) to assess the human health risk and/or impact of selected exposure scenarios (including between- and within-person variance estimates and dynamics of population exposure and health risk) to inform policy makers and to contribute to the Partnership monitoring framework will be initiated. [Partners involved: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), OI (SI), Sciensano (BE), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL)].

Task 6.3: Review of risk assessment methodology

Co-Leaders: SU (SE), BPI (EL)

Partners: UCL (UK), INSA (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), INRAE (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), MUI (AT), DTU (DK), REGIONH (DK), UCPH (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE), UNIBAS (CH), KEMI (SE)

The initiated projects will continue during M13-M24, with further refinement of reviews and analysis through case studies as well as further exploration of stakeholder interactions. Case studies will be ongoing for two to five years, with six of the case studies finalized in M24. One additional case study will be initiated M13 and finalised M24.

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews

- P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU; Case studies reviewing substance-specific RA depending on intended use. The reviews of substance-specific assessments depending on intended use will continue through three case studies. The case studies are described below and will evaluate differences and similarities, and subsequent implications, across legislations. [Partners involved: SU (SE), UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)].

- CS12_MethodOSOA_SU: An analysis of risk assessment processes, including significant differences between processes, strengths of the current system(s), and potential gaps, overlaps, or inefficiencies will be initiated. The work during Y2 will focus on what the scope of substances that have been regulated under various EU chemical regulations is, if there are differences in the risk

assessment outcomes, what conclusion can be drawn concerning cumulative exposure and if cumulative exposure can be assessed by current regulatory frameworks. (SU (SE), KI (SE)).

- CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL: During Y2, the impact of similarities and differences in hazard and exposure assessments in terms of derivation of regulatory migration limits or maximum allowed content in products and articles will be assessed based on a list of known uses and corresponding legislation for selected plasticisers compiled by scanning the literature and through the use of the EUCLEF database. Justifications in relation to intended use, risks and benefits, including socio-economic assessments, and availability of alternatives as well as potential and available solutions for harmonization will be reviewed (UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), and IRFM (IT)).
- CS14_BiocidesRA_SU: During Y2, the review of how substances with biocidal properties are regulated and assessed when used in cosmetic products compared to biocidal products, including how scientific data is used, consequences of the potential differences in regulation and risk assessment, and suggestions for harmonization in the regulation of substances with biocidal properties will continue. The regulation of substances with biocidal properties under BPR and CPR will be scrutinized, identifying the most important differences. In addition, 5-10 risk assessments performed under CPR and BPR will be analysed and compared, focusing on the use of scientific data, transparency, and scientific rationale of the evaluation. (SU (SE), KI (SE)).

- P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI; Case studies reviewing effect-specific RA: The reviews of effect-specific assessments will continue through six case studies. The case studies are described below and will include aspects such as sensitization and developmental neurotoxicity as well as use of non-animal methods for identification of endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity. [Partners involved: REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), EAA (AT), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR)].

- CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH: Year 2 will be devoted to mapping the regulatory practices for skin sensitizers across regulatory areas in EU. A systematic review of components in risk assessment methods will be performed, including the IATAs described by OECD (Guideline 497) and QRA2 adopted by SCCS, including gaps of knowledge (REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH)).
- CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB: The critical analysis of the SCCS risk assessments, initiated the first year, will continue using a selection of group B cosmetic substances with potential ED activity with a somewhat lower priority. Cosmetics Europe and SCCS will be included as relevant stakeholders to formulate recommendations and best practices with respect to the inclusion of NAMs and/or new methodology (NGRA) in the human risk assessment process of substances with potential ED activity Year 2 will be devoted to continuing the analysis of RA by SCCS for a selection out of 14 high priority substances (list B) with a somewhat lower priority i.e. substances for which no evaluation had been initiated under REACH or the outcome of the evaluation was an environmental ED concern. A reporting of the safety evaluation *modus operandi* of the selected Group A & B substances performed over the timeframe of 2 years will be done. A final meeting will be organised with the relevant stakeholders to formulate recommendations and best practices with respect to the inclusion of NAMs and new technology to cover the biological complexity and as such enable the prediction of human health effects for substances with potential ED activity (VUB (BE), INRAE (FR)).
- CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS: Continued review of the methodologies and practices employed under different regulatory frameworks related to genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment as well as identification of possible strategies to increase regulatory application and acceptance of QSAR based approaches (including classification purposes). Year 2 will be devoted to continuing discussing all identified gaps and inconsistencies with the most relevant stakeholders (e.g., in ECHA, EFSA, OECD, and other relevant frameworks) to possibly propose improvements to the legislations. Particular attention will be paid to reviewing the current state of the art of the

regulatory use of (Q)SAR approaches, to promote their acceptability by reducing uncertainties and to support the incorporation of the most recent innovations (ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)). In particular: a mapping of existing documentation, regulations and related guidelines, a revision of regulatory practices for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity classification and risk assessment and finally an identification of possible strategies to increase regulatory application and acceptance of QSAR based approaches will be done. In parallel, identification of relevant available NAMs, IATAs and AOPs will be pursued to support incorporation of the most recent innovations.

- CS15_DNT_SU: Year 2 will be devoted to assessing if the conclusions drawn by the test laboratory from observed effects in guideline DNT studies are reliable and balanced, as indicated by a novel typology and if a uniform statistical analysis of behavioural outcome data, developed for high statistical power, can identify previously unreported effects. (SU (SE)).
- CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI: Year 2 will be devoted to the development of reliability and relevance criteria for the evaluation of selected *in vitro* methods based on identified non-validated existing *in vitro* test methods assessing prioritised endpoints relevant for the assessment of EDCs. (BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), UBA (DE)).
- CS18_ED-classes_BPI: Year 2 will be devoted to explore how *in vitro*, *in silico* and read-across approaches identified can be used under PPPR, BPR, REACH and CPR to assess (a) endocrine adversity, (b) endocrine activity and to establish a biological plausible link between the endocrine activity and the adverse effect (c) (BPI (EL), INSERM (FR), EAA (AT), IRFM (IT), VUB (BE), UBA (DE)).

A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods reviews

- P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU; Case studies reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA
The reviews on the use of tools, criteria, and methods in regulatory RA will continue through eight case studies, seven case studies initiated in Y1 (one case study (CS6) initiated in Y1 will not be pursued) and one initiated in Y2. The case studies are described below and include general aspects such as application of risk-based benchmarks, uncertainty analysis, and handling data gaps as well as aspects related to occupational RA and ERA. [Partners involved: SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE), SU (SE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), JSI (SI), UCL (UK), TTL (FI), KI (SE), RSU (LV), INERIS (FR), KEMI (SE), ULUND (SE), BPI (EL), MUI (AT), LSMU (LT), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), DTU (DK), UCPH (DK)].

- CS1_CARB_SYKE: A synthesis report on risk-based decision benchmarks in risk assessment methodologies under different EU regulatory frameworks, including the results from previous actions such as the compilation of relevant data, and definition of the scope and methodology will be drafted. Stakeholder engagement through interviews and workshops will continue. (SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE)).
- CS2_RiskReduction_SU: A literature review on methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk will be performed. Semi-structured interviews with relevant stakeholders on the effectiveness of current risk assessment methodologies in reducing risk will be initiated. Assessment and comparison between methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk will be performed. ((SU (SE), UBA (DE), STAMI (NO), UCL (UK), JSI (SI)).
- CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND: Collection of information on practical challenges through a questionnaire with follow up interviews has been finalised. The interviews and questionnaire will be used as basis to search for and identify examples where uncertainty analysis or uncertainty analysis done with quantitative expressions have been beneficial to an assessment. ((ULUND (SE), KI (SE), BPI (EL), UBA (DE)).
- CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU: This case study starts year 2. An inventory of EU regulations

and policies relevant for chemical data gap filling as well as approaches used will be done. A report will be produced that provides a systematic overview of how chemical data gaps are addressed across EU regulations and policies, including an assessment of similarities, differences, and possibilities for cross-policy harmonization of data gap filling approaches. Potential synergies both within and outside PARC, including PARC T8.1 on SSbD, will be explored during the work planned for Y2. ((DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), KEMI (SE), SU (SE)).

- CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG: Mapping of topics and identification of substances with several different effect values as case studies, identification of similarities and differences, and areas requiring further analysis will continue. A review regarding aquatic and sediment RA will be done. Case study on comparative assessment of pro- and retrospective effect values will be initiated. (EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), UBA (DE)).
- CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS: Substances and scenarios to be used for comparisons will be selected to analyse secondary poisoning assessment across several regulatory frameworks. The results will be assessed against monitoring data. Monitoring data will be obtained from existing national databases (e.g. pharmacovigilance data) and from scientific research papers. As far as possible, nominal conditions will be chosen and misuses and accidental exposures will be avoided. Remaining gaps and uncertainties will be identification and preparation of a stakeholder workshop will be initiated. (INERIS (FR))
- CS8_OccupReproDev_KI: In-depth reviews of the safety margin to reproductive and developmental toxicity for selected substances, including metals and exposures expected in health care, will be initiated. Additional substances will be identified based on the initial overview including toxicity to female and male reproduction, fertility, and development. (KI (SE), TTL (FI), LSMU (LT), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)).
- CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL: A questionnaire study for workplaces and other relevant stakeholders (industrial/employee organisations, authorities), complemented with interviews, will be performed to evaluate how limit values and related information produced under the different regulatory processes are interpreted and used in workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practice. (TTL (FI), KI (SE), JSI (SI), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)).

WP6 annual workshop

A joint WP6 workshop with WP and task leaders, partners, and relevant stakeholders will be organized to discuss activities, focusing on ongoing work and proposals for developments and new case studies to ensure the regulatory relevance. Collaborations with other WPs, in particular WP2 and WP5, will be explored to optimize the output. (KEMI, RIVM, all WP6 partners).

Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Co-leaders: AGES (AT), UNIBAS (CH)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), MU (CZ), AU (DK), REGIONH-GR (DK), UT (EE), EFSA (EU), SYKE (FI), Tukes (FI), UBA (DE), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), USO (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), UI (IS), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LSMU (LT), VUA (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIVA (NO), NIOM (PL), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), ENSP (PT), UC (PT), UAVR (PT), ISCIII (ES), UCLM (SI), UGOT (SE), ULUND (SE), RISE (SE), KEMI (SE), SLU (SE), AGROSCOPE (CH), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), UNIBAS (CH), BUL (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), EA (UK) BPI (EL)

A6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures

- P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot: the results from the survey will be implemented. Based on the outcome and data availability case studies across all regulatory areas will be performed to compare all available mixtures tool with the Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF) approach. The case

studies will be used for generating new information for sizing the MAF but also to identify to what extent the MAF approach is applicable, and if not by how much would the MAF approach provide biased results. The foreseen case studies have their focus on the WFD, food contaminants, food improvement agents and the male reproductive health.

The results of the survey and the case studies will be summarized in the Technical Reports “Evaluation of the stakeholder feedback collected from a survey and expert interviews on the usefulness of current mixture assessment tools” and “Comparative assessment of mixture tools with respect to application domain, feasibility, data demands, protectiveness, reliability, bias.” Both Reports are part of the D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)(Lead partner: UGOT, BUL, Participants: AGES, BPI, EAWAG, UBA, UI, NIVA, ENSP, EA, LSMU, NIOM, UAVR, KEMI, UKCEH, STAMI, NLZOH). Planned year 2 of PARC: Short description of next planned key project action 1: Developing a survey and collecting data including through interviews. Involved Partners: UGOT (SE), BUL (UK), EAWAG (CH), UBA (DE), AGES (AT). Short description of next planned key project action 2: Case Studies. Involved partners all partners.

- P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ: two case studies will be performed, both linking environmental exposure data with effect data and knowledge based on NAMs. Case study 1 aims at the generation of stereotypical reference mixtures based on monitoring data for the development of assessment approaches of the joint risk of compounds that are regulated under different national and European regulations but usually occurring together. Case study 2 will focus on the use on integrated exposure data, effect data, and chemical usage data from monitoring campaigns, NAM measurements and existing databases, to identify the impact of REACH - regulated chemicals within hazardous chemical mixtures consisting of multiple compounds from diverse sources. (Lead partner: UFZ, UBA Participants: AGES, BPI, UI, NIVA, NLZOH, STAMI, EA, UKCEH).

The outcome of the literature review will be summarized in the technical report " Literature review on use of NAM and monitoring data for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation". This technical report is part of the D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81). Planned year 2 of PARC:

Short description of next planned key project action 1: Literature review on use of NAM and monitoring data for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation. Involved partners: UFZ, UBA, UI, ENSP, AGES, tbd

Short description of next planned key project action 2: Case Studies. Involved partners: all partners

A6.4.2. Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods

- P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurvey_UNIBAS. Building on the initial landscaping exercise, structured interviews and online survey with chemical risk assessors, the focus in Y2 will be put on gaps and needs at desk level, in particular on quality/internal validity, relevance, and uncertainty of NAMs, existing barriers (e.g., at technological, organizational, structural, cultural, and individual level), opportunities, and benefits of/from using NAMs at desk level. This will be explored with the help of real-life, context-specific, and scenario-based examples (i.e., vignettes). Based on this, we will combine generic, sector-agnostic as well as sector-specific approaches to understand the commonalities and differences in the current use of NAMs for risk assessment within and across the various chemical sectors, and explore cross-sectorial fertilization of knowledge and practice for the use of NAMs in chemical risk assessment. The knowledge gained from the landscaping exercise and gaps & needs analysis will be summarized in the revised technical report: AD.6.16: “*Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis*”. (Lead partner: UNIBAS, Participants: NIPH; UT; ISS ; UOB; INERIS; UBA; BPI; EAA; UNL; UKCEH; UAVR; NIVA). Planned year 2 of PARC:

Short description of next planned key project action 1: Expand the work done in Y1 to include an environmental focus, with similar aims and objectives. Partners involved: EAA, UAVR, UOB, UBA,

UKCEH, UNIBAS.

Short description of next planned key project action 2: Conduct a more in-depth analysis to identify the key factors and drivers for a successful implementation of NAMs in the regulatory risk assessment practice. Partners involved: BPI, EAA, ENSP, INERIS, ISS, UB, UBA, UKCEH, UNIBAS, UT.

Short description of next planned key project action 3: Identification of real-life, context-specific, and scenario-based examples (i.e., vignettes) to support the development of regulatory relevant case studies. Partners involved: BPI, EAA, ENSP, INERIS, ISS, UAVR, UB, UBA, UKCEH, UNIBAS, UT.

- P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH aims to develop evidence-based tools and guidance for hazard/risk assessment of NAMs, which will be integrated in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework across chemical sectors. Building on key learnings from Y1, in collaboration with an external scientific Advisory Group of leading EU and US experts in the field (13 participants from Karolinska Institutet, ECHA, OECD, I.U.S. EPA, CAAT, Johns Hopkins, EBTC, Radboud University, EFSA, JRC, University of California San Francisco, ONTOX, NIEHS, ONTOX, ASPIS as well as from WP2 (BfR) and WP3 (AUTH) representatives as observers)) (Lead partner: NIPH. Participants: UT, NIVA, UAVR, BPI, ISS, UNIBAS). Year 2, the project will draft protocols for evaluating internal and external validity of in silico studies, as well as start working on reporting standards for different in vitro and in silico NAMs. The project will also conduct preparatory work to identify relevant case studies for testing the draft tools and guidance in Y3 and beyond. (involved partners: NIPH, BPI, ISS, UNIBAS,).

- P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT will build on the outcome of the literature review and of the prioritization process that identified potential regulatory-relevant case studies in Y1. A more in-depth analysis of the existing knowledge of data-driven AI (Artificial Intelligence)/ML (Machine learning) QSARs will be conducted. Activities will include the preliminary description of a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI/ML models for regulatory purposes, and the prioritization of case studies starting in the next step of the project. (Lead partner: UT. Participants: INERIS, IRFM, ISS, NIPH, NIVA, UG-PL, UKCEH, UNIBAS, EA). Planned year 2 of PARC:

Short description of next planned key project action 1: Research priorities and requirements will be finalized: (partners involved: UT, UG-PL, IRFM, UNIBAS, NIPH, ISS, INERIS, UKCEH, NIVA, EA)

Short description of next planned key project action 2: A more in-depth analysis of the existing knowledge of data-driven AI (Artificial Intelligence)/ML (Machine learning) QSARs will be conducted (partners involved: UT, UG-PL, IRFM, ISS, INERIS).

Short description of next planned key project action 3: Preliminary description of a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI/ML models for regulatory purposes (partners involved: UT, UG-PL, IRFM, UNIBAS, NIPH, ISS, INERIS, UKCEH, NIVA, EA)

Short description of next planned key project action 4: Prioritization of case studies starting in the next step of the project (partners involved: UT, INERIS, IRFM, ISS, NIPH (VKM), NIVA, UG-PL, UKCEH, UNIBAS, EA).

A6.4.3. Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy

- P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU will be continued, with the completion of two deliverables outlining the current screening and enforcement structures for chemicals in articles and how chemical hazards are incorporated in LCA (AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures – Leader: TUKES (M24); AD6.15: Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards - Leader: MU (M24). Mapping activities regarding existing data structures relevant to substances in products and materials will conclude, and this will inform a set of case studies used to test the information structures for retrieving information for enforcement and perform an evaluation of different models and the integration of chemical hazards into total LCA. (Lead partner: MU; Participants: KemI, Rise, TUKES, VUA, VITO, TNO).

Planned year 2 of PARC:

Short description of next planned key project action 1: Evaluation of data sources for enforcement, particularly validation of rapid screening methods. Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA.
Short description of next planned key project action 2: Gaps and needs analysis of chemicals enforcement structures and recommendations for optimized structure. Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA.

Short description of next planned key project action 3: Testing the existing information structures by selection of (1) chemical class and (2) product class and tracking how data produced in response to regulatory structures and enforcement is stored in the systems. Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI.

Short description of next planned key project action 4: Case study on incorporation of chemical safety across dominant LCA models, providing comparative evaluation of different models and the integration of chemical hazards into total LCA; Partners involved: MU, KEMI.

A6.4.4. Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity

- P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI Science-policy scoping workshops will continue to clarify regulatory needs and further develop the activity plans and help to prioritise and coordinate research projects. Stakeholder engagement and involvement will be coordinated with WP 2 and WP 3. A report outlining current state of consensus of regulatory needs for ERA development areas will be prepared (AD6.7: Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development area, Leader: KEMI (M24)) (Lead partner: KEMI Participants: UBA, FOEN, EFSA, ANSES, UOS, ULUND, NIVA)

- P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU will continue to collect and curate monitoring data and identify existing PEC models (e.g. PEC CKB, Exposit, Gerda). Collection of monitoring datasets will also be coordinated together with WP 4.2. The outcome from different available and developed PEC models will be compared to a common dataset and to datasets from different member states. (Lead partner: SLU (SE) Participants: UFZ (DE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), UOS (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL), UoB (UK). Regulatory core group: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU).)

- P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ will continue to set up a meta-database with information and data that are species related (e.g. ecological, traits), site related and methods related (e.g. omics data, Pict and Spear concepts) from national and EU-level sources. Network within PARC WPs and externally through partners will be used to identify monitoring and active substance effects data sources. (Lead partner: UFZ Participants: UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE); UKOLD (DE); ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCIII (ES), Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA (EU), ANSES (FR), UKCEH (UK)).

Planned year 2 of PARC:

- Completion of Data collection on monitoring of PPPs and relevant field stressors from different EU countries (project action 1). Partners involved: UFZ, UKOLD, EAWAG, ULUND, ISCIII, UBA, FOEN, ANSES, EFSA, NIVA, UKCEH.
- Compilation and curation of Monitoring data (project action 2): Partners involved: UFZ, UKOLD, EAWAG, ULUND, ISCIII, UBA, FOEN, ANSES, EFSA, NIVA, UKCEH.
- Internal data analysis and discussion with partners (project action 3). Partners involved: UFZ, UKOLD, EAWAG, ULUND, ISCIII, UBA, FOEN, ANSES, EFSA, NIVA, UKCEH

- P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD will continue to build a database for comparative risk quotients. Existing prototype comparative databases will be used as templates for further development. Active substance toxicity and physicochemical data from the current ERA regulatory process will be compiled and use data for exposure calculations will be retrieved from national pesticide registries in different member states. (Lead partner: UKOLD Participants: UFZ, ISCIII, NIVA, EAWAG and ULUND). Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU))

- P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII will continue networking with farmer associations, IPM specialists, voluntary initiatives stakeholders as well as regulatory (PPPR, SUD, CAP) and local and regional public actors in order to address their specific needs in the design of each case study work plan. Case studies are planned for in ES, FR, PL, and NO reflecting different agricultural landscape conditions and climates. In parallel, the generic conceptual model for landscape environmental risk assessment for pesticides and other stressors will be implemented into specific work plans to be tested in the case studies. (Lead partner: ISCIII Participants: UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück UOS (DE), UOB (UK), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), UAVR (PT), SYKE (FI), INERIS (FR), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU))

Deliverables:

No deliverable planned Y2

Additional Deliverables

AD6.1: Strategy document on IATA for more complex endpoints – Leader: Sciensano (M18). This AD was initially planned Y1 (M10) but was postponed to Y2 (M18)

AD6.7: Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas – Leader: KEMI (M24). This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M24)

AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies – Leader: UL-LACDR (M24). This AD replaces the AD6.2 initially planned Y1 and its replacement by milestone MS15 at M12

AD6.10 to AD6.13 are removed from the AWP year 2. They will be replaced by ADs corresponding to the end of the related projects.

AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures – Leader: TUKES (M24)

AD6.15: Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards – Leader: MU (M24)

AD6.16: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis – Leader: UNIBAS (M24).

AD6.8 “Technical report: mapping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks” initially planned Y1 (M12) has been postponed to Y2 and merged with this AD6.16

WP N°	WP7										Lead Beneficiary										VITO/UOB						
WP title	FAIR Data																										
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.6	1.10	4	4.6	5.2	6.1	8	15	15.2	20	24.3	25.2	25.4	25.7	26	26.4	27.2	31	32	34.5	35.2	35.12	36	49	59
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRS	BRGM	VITO	ISSeP	EV-ILVO	IMROH	MU	UBA	UFZ	ISS	UniLU	TNO	UL-LACDR	WR	NIPH	NIVA	UG-PL	JSI	NIZ	IISPV	KI	UU	AUTH	EFSA	UOB

PM/ partner	27.4	3.1	1.5	7.5	5.3	12.5	2	2	7.9	5.5	16	4	7	6	22	1.3	2	5.5	4.1	30	6	30	6	5	7.7	2	15
Start	M13												End						M24								

Objectives

The main goal of WP7 is to support innovation and transparency in chemical Risk Assessment (RA) through improved exchange and re-use of data between different RA actors and disciplines, and through innovative data analytical approaches. The specific objectives of WP7 for year 2 are:

- Task 7.1:
 - o Finalisation of the first version of the PARC Data Policy and deliverable submitted by M18
 - o Updating the DMP with clusters of project-level DMPs
 - o Development of a white paper on PARC FAIR ambitions and implementation roadmap
 - o Continuous training for Data Champions, Liaisons and FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT)
 - o Implementation of use case management workflow
- Task 7.2:
 - o Finalization of landscaping of existing databases and data platforms and making available the analysis of their FAIRness
 - o Creation of proof of concept (PoC) for the FAIR PARC data hub and demonstration of the utility and feasibility of the approach
 - o Implementation of identified use cases and identification of new use cases
 - o Provision of a consolidated set of controlled vocabularies at PARC level, as well as domain-specific standards
- Task 7.3:
 - o Selection and initial implementation of identified use cases and identification of new use cases, if needed.
 - o Development of user guidelines for different statistical analytical (meta-, pooled etc.) techniques and demonstration of the utility and feasibility of different approaches via the selected use cases.
 - o Gap analysis of uncertainty assessment methodologies and demonstration of the process with first domain specific uses cases.
 - o Scoping, gap analysis and initial benchmarking of data / knowledge mining and AI/ML tools.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 7.1: FAIR Data policy and implementation

Co-leaders: TNO (NL), UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL)

Sub-contractors: GFF (BE)

No project submitted for this task

A7.1.1 PARC Data Policy and Data Management Plan

The PARC FAIR data policy will be finalized (M18), including the incorporation of any final suggested topics, gathered via interaction within PARC, on top of topics / sections collected in 2022.

An evaluation of the various online tools for DMPs (DMPonline, DS Wizard, and the OpenAIRE tool ARGOS) will be undertaken as a means to evaluate what is needed to make these FAIR and machine actionable, and to streamline processes for partners as much as possible. The following actions will be undertaken:

1. Establishment of evaluation criteria for the online DMPs (machine actionable, critical mass of use, alignment with stakeholder needs etc.)
2. Survey of PARC projects and PARC partners in terms of their existing use of / familiarity with the different online DMP tools
3. Comparison of the machine actionable nature of existing DMP tools and what additional work would be needed to make the online DMPs machine actionable. If possible, selection of a limited set of DMP tools, to foster clarity of use within PARC, based on projects experience (see below).
4. Report on the comparison and recommendations for PARC projects and overarching PARC DMP and for the tool developers on how to further increase machine actionability and inter-operability of the online DMP Tools.

A PARC WP7 Glossary of key terms will be implemented, as part of the DMP / Data policy to ensure clarity of roles in data management, clarity on meaning of different data management tools and solutions (e.g., data repository versus database versus data lake etc.) and some of the specific FAIR-related terms such as machine-actionable, FAIR-enabling resource etc. These terms will be linked to existing ontology terms where available, or added to the PARC ontology where no existing ontology term exists, and the PARC glossary will be a living document, implemented as part of the PARCopedia and be FAIR itself.

An ongoing activity throughout Y2 will be evaluation and development of the project-level DMPs by the Data Liaisons and Data Champions – the data management sections of the PARC project proposals and implementation plans will be further elaborated, documented via one of the online DMP tools (clusters of projects will be allocated one or other of the tools and asked to reflect on its utility and fitness for purpose using the criteria agreed above), to ensure that there is a clear, and harmonised, plan for the deposition and management of all PARC datasets. Thus, the PARC DMP will be updated based on the clusters of projects and their experiences with the different online DMP tools, and if the different tools are found to serve different purposes effectively more than one may be recommended as part of the overarching PARC DMP.

A7.1.2 Training and organisation

Throughout Y2, the training programme for the Data Champions, Data Liaisons and FAIR implementation Task group will be delivered, leading to sets of facilitators and trainers able to deliver additional training in FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP), and Metadata 4 Machines (M4M). As part of this training, the participants will develop the domain-specific FIPs for PARC, as well as developing tools and solutions to support the implementation of FAIR in PARC.

A white paper on the PARC FAIR ambition will be drafted along with an accompanying PARC FAIR Roadmap. A first presentation on PARC FAIR ambition was presented and discussed at the WP7 meeting in Brno in October 2022, and a landscape mapping and prioritisation exercise implemented to determine where additional use-cases on FAIRification may arise, and what machine-actionable tools and resources are available for different aspects of metadata and data including protocols, raw data, data processing tools and processed data, and summary data, as well as the data mining, uncertainty analysis and integration tools (pooled data, meta-analysis) being developed in Task 7.3, as well as FAIR maturity indicators for databases etc. Based on the mapping and prioritisation exercise, including integrating information from the FIPs, a roadmap for implantation of the PARC FAIR ambitions will be developed and published, which will also feed into the subsequent annual work plans for WP7.

A7.1.3 FAIR Data Use Case Coordination

With the Use Case identification and Use Case Working Group (UCWG) onboarding processes defined in Y1, we can continue in the same vein for the onboarding of Y2 Use Cases that were identified in Y1, and the identification of Use Cases for Y3.

Use Cases that started in Y1 on Human Biomonitoring data and environmental data (embedded in the

projects P7.2.2.a_Y1 and P7.2.2.b_Y1) will be followed up by mapping their roadmaps and stated FAIR data goals onto a common timeline. As part of A7.2.3 the data liaisons will keep this status up to date, so the FAIR overview for all active use cases and projects can be monitored by the FAIR Implementation Task group and help can be offered where needed.

Task 7.2: Data libraries

Co-Leaders: MU (CZ), VITO (BE)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BRGM (FR), EFSA (EU), EV-ILVO (BE), IISPV (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UBA (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UNILU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), KWR (NL)

Sub-contractors: GFF (BE)

Two projects submitted for this task:

- P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO
- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

A7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

The inventory of the major transnational and national databases, repositories, and platforms related to the risk assessment of chemicals will be made available to the PARC project partners, and will be shared openly. In addition, the initial analysis of the FAIRness of the available resources will be provided to partners following application of the ‘as is’ FAIR implementation profile developed in Activity 7.1.2. The landscape will be enriched with newly identified resources resulting from specific use cases, and in consultation with the R&I WPs further steps will be identified to refine the existing or establish new use cases (see A7.1.3) and the actions needed to assure accessibility and re(use) of both regulatory and academic data. These actions will benefit from the established horizontal links between WP7 and WPx (data liaison – data champion structure in projects) and from the increased knowledge and human capacities in FAIR aspects and assessment as a result of the cooperation with and training provided by Go FAIR Foundation (A7.1.2).

In parallel, the activities at the EC level related to the Common Platform for Chemicals Data (CPCD) roadmap, will be consulted as one of the key players and the proposed approaches followed to ensure the coherence of actions in the common European open data space.

A7.2.2 PARC FAIR data hub

A Proof of Concept (PoC) of the data hub will be made available to the PARC project partners and will include functionalities enabling the delivery of the use cases selected in Y1 (P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO; P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO). The data hub will be used for publishing at least one FAIR dataset and enabling at least one end-to-end data flow to demonstrate the feasibility and usability of the concept and the utilities it may offer for closing gaps identified in the various use cases. The PARC FAIR data hub PoC supports/enables the data and/or information exchange with the other WPs (most notably WP2, WP8 and WP9) that were agreed upon in Y1.

Feedback will be collected from the various types of data hub stakeholders to ensure a positive evolution in terms of meeting users' requirements, alignment with the wider landscape and usability.

- P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO: the project is linked to activities planned under 4.2 (multiple exposure monitoring) and specific activities under 6.4 such as the collection of existing exposure monitoring data on pesticides and chemicals in the articles and to some extent with A7.2.1. Within the project, synergies between existing data platforms/networks will be identified, and further actions will be marked to overcome bottlenecks such as incompatible data formats, gaps in standards, missing machine-readable interface, scattered data, interoperability issues, and data reuse obstacles (legal/content). Further

on, broadening the landscaping to other matrices/other priority chemicals will take place once the whole process is completed for the first set of priority substances (PFAS, EDs, pesticides)/matrices (e.g., water) and it will allow the WP7 team to test the approach, further improve the landscaping exercise and assess the expected efforts needed when broadening to other matrices and substances and consequently also improve the design of future use cases. [Participants: MU, VITO, UFZ, BRGM, UNILU, ISSEP, JSI, ANSES, NIVA, UBA, KWR, AUTH, UNIVIE]

- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO: The WP7 HBM data project will build on the Y1 selection of relevant HBM datasets and linked communities, and the roadmap for FAIRification that has been developed. Connections will be created with these systems and databases 1.2 by adopting or creating common interfaces. Projects that will use these datasets include different 4.1.1 activities (HBM survey, monitoring and occupational hazards), Activity 4.1.3 (Guidance Values) and Activity 4.1.4 (HBM Data Analysis) in WP4, several WP6 projects (A6.2.3 -real life mixtures- and A6.4.1 -regulatory risk assessment-) and the T8.2 (Early Warning Systems) and T8.3 (risk modelling network) Tasks in WP8. Starting from the project stakeholders needs, we will design shared data structures and contribute best practices for collaborating on HBM data to PARCopedia. [Participants: VITO, MU, UU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI, WR]

Parts (Schedule)	Actions	Participant Institution(s) (Country)
1. Transfer HBM4EU to PARC (M1 to M36)	Collaboration agreement	VITO
	Data governance system	VITO
	Technical adaptations to platform	VITO
	Operations	VITO
2. Use case management (M1 to M42)	Use case working group	VITO, MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI, WR
	Collaboration/exchange with IPCHEM	VITO
	Collaboration with other related data initiatives	VITO, MU
3. HBM Data Landscape (M7 to M18)	Inventory	MU, VITO, UBA, JSI
	FAIR and sustainability assessment	VITO, MU, ISSEP, JSI
4. Elaboration of solutions for storage, access and reuse (M7 to M24)	Assessment of federated systems for privacy-preserving analysis	VITO, UU, MU
	Architecture for federated platform and services	VITO, MU, UU
	FAIR Implementation Profile and roadmap	VITO, MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI
	Data model, metadata schema and ontology	VITO, MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI, WR
5. Implementation and testing (M18 to M42)		VITO, MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI

A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation

Concrete solutions will further be elaborated and implemented based on specific use cases through the established collaboration between Data Champions, Data Liaisons and the FAIR Implementation Team in UCWGs. Domain-specific use cases will follow the FAIRification methodology (3PFF) provided and finetuned by Go FAIR Foundation in Y1.

For non-WP7 projects, on the one hand, the projects selected in Y1 are supported in implementing their FAIR data use cases and collaboration workflows, i.e.,

- at least one project or use case selected in Y1 that makes available scientific data sources for (re)use in regulatory risk assessment
- at least 2 projects or use cases selected in Y1 that address hazard and toxicological data

- transversal use cases on FAIR elements common to many projects, e.g., use of PIDs, licensing,
- ...
- T8.1 - Safe and Sustainable by Design
- T8.2 - Early Warning Systems
- T8.3 - Integrative Model Network

while on the other hand, domain experts (from R&I WPs) and WP7 data experts will describe additional use cases for the priority data needs of the WPs. Bottlenecks for data reuse and synergies with existing data platforms are identified and use case implementation plans are drafted.

A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation

The combined bottom-up (use cases and projects) and top-down (community standards and shared ontologies) approaches will be used to provide a consolidated set of controlled vocabularies at PARC level as well as domain-specific standards. Deliberation with various data suppliers and data users in accordance with identified use cases and priorities will define choices for technical interfacing with established communities and existing data sources that are deemed relevant by the PARC stakeholders. At the same time, existing validation and harmonization tooling that lowers the barrier in adopting these standards and interfaces will be vetted for recommendation or new tools will be developed.

This topic will also provide important interactions with other WPs, specifically in compiling a durable list of data, metadata and project standards that can be published via PARCopedia (WP2), providing guidance and background info to set up training on these standards (WP9) and supporting projects with strong important collaborative components in adopting a standards-based approach (WP8)

Task 7.3: Innovative analyses

Co-Leaders: IISPV (ES)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), IMROH (CR), INRS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UL-LACDR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), VITO (BE), WR (NL)

A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

(Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, IISPV, KI, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS, UOB, UL-LADCR, UNIVIE, NIVA, MU).

A.7.3.1.a Combined (meta-, Pooled) data analyses

In Y1, a planned scoping review has been started which will continue in the first half of Y2. Based on the inventories of different statistical approaches and computational tools for meta- and pooled analysis (such as Network analysis (Bayesian Network (e.g. combined with expert knowledge), frequentist network and mixed comparison), Bayesian Hierarchical meta-analysis model, and hybrid models like multilevel meta-analysis and Structural Equation modelling), concrete planning and implementation of a first use case will be started, and will lead to a preliminary evaluation of the usefulness of selected approaches and tools. A first set of guidelines /requirements/issues for datasets to be included in meta-analysis will be drafted.

A.7.3.1.b methodologies to combine and integrate hazard and exposure-response information across and within evidence domains.

Also based on the results of the scoping study in Y1, a use case will be started to integrate available exposure studies, human epidemiological studies, biomarker studies, experimental animal studies, and in-vitro studies, e.g., using Bayesian techniques to integrate data for risk assessment. A comparable use case will be set up to integrate heterogeneous data for aggregate exposure assessment.

Potential Use Cases (Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, UL-LADCR, IISPV, KI, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS,

UOB, UNIVIE, NIVA, MU)

Within the framework of WP 7.3.1, we are contacting partners from the different WPs to understand which types of heterogeneous data they have, and which issues they encounter for data integration. We will gather feedback covering the data types, research questions, and data-related and methodological issues, in order to gain a better understanding of what innovative statistical methods are needed for the integration of such data.

Use case 1: A first potential use case will combine data from multiple pregnant women cohorts. Epidemiological data, human biomonitoring data and metabolomics data will be integrated and linked with health outcomes. The plethora of tools mentioned will be integrated into a pipeline that will collect this data and by combining machine learning approaches as well, will derive and conclude to health outcomes.

Use case 2: A second potential use case linked to WP 6.3.2 (Real-life mixtures project) is on multiple-exposure pathway analyses with can integrate multiple mediators and/or multiple outcomes. Current epidemiological analyses on health effects of mixture exposure are mostly limited to single outcome variables, whereas the integration of biomarker information can help to unravel biological mechanisms. Given the pleiotropic nature of e.g. inflammatory and endocrine responses to mixture exposure, and the high correlation between different effect biomarkers, there is a need for methods integrating high-dimensional exposure, biomarker, and health outcome data, enabling the assessment of combined effects and relative importance of the various mixture components and biomarkers in the pathway.

Use case 3: A third potential use case is a study on health impact assessment related to WP 6.2.4, in which data across multiple evidence bases will be combined to estimate the exposure–response curve. Integrating the available epidemiologic, biomarker, and animal data will hopefully result in more precise risk estimates.

Proposed use cases involve the integration of different data sources within or across domains, and thus the variability and uncertainty of heterogeneous data need to be considered, which is consistent with the overall goal of T7.3 and a potential synergy with A7.3.2. We will further evaluate these potential case studies and extend their models to generate a refined approach for integrating incoming extensive, heterogeneous data input.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

Primary activity in Y2 will be implementation of selected use cases. For their implementation and evaluation use cases identified in Y1 for exposure, hazard, risk, health impact assessment, and IATAs in collaboration with WP4, WP5 and WP6, will further be refined and developed. This activity will focus on qualitative and quantitative estimation of uncertainties at the different steps of the domain specific process and methodological approaches used for uncertainty propagation. Domain specific use case groups have been selected and they will be working to define the scope of each use case study. The report will recommend promising methods for further evaluation and refinement if needed.

The scoping study will continue in Y2 and a planned manuscript will be submitted in the first half of Y2.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data

- P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV: A scoping study is already undergoing which will further continue in year 2 with inclusion of an inventory of ontology-based approaches and frameworks for knowledge integration. In year 2, part of methodological development will also start. A detailed plan on use cases, specifically in close relation to the use case on “databases of chemicals in articles with T6.4.3” and AOPs developments in T5.3 will also start in year 2, will be further refined and prioritised to particular endpoints or chemical classes/imported products in collaboration with WP5 and WP6. [Partners involved: IISPV (ES), UoB (UK), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), UL-LACDR (NL), KI (SE), NIVA (NO),

WR (NL)]

Specific actions for year 2 include:

- Development of a classification of the different data / knowledge mining tools in terms of the types of data modalities (structured / unstructured) they work on, as a basis for allocation to specific use-cases. [Participants: IISPV, UoB, KI, NIVA]
- Development of a plan for how to adapt the existing methods to serve the different use-cases – e.g., methodological advances, or adaptation of datasets or data extraction tools etc. [Participants: IISPV, UoB, INSERM, ANSES, NIVA]
- Where gaps emerge that cannot be addressed by existing tools, entirely new solutions may be needed – a roadmap to develop solutions will be developed. [Participants: IISPV, UoB, AUTH, INSERM, NIVA, UL-LACDR]
- Informing development of ontologies – for specific use-cases will start to map terms of existing ontologies and defining missing terms – PARC ontology. Using text mining tools themselves to help develop the ontology and candidate terms and relationships (a hybrid approach including also expert evaluation of suggested terms). [Participants: UoB, IISPV, AUTH, KI, MU, NIVA]

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

The objective of this activity is to identify emerging needs in PARC for innovative analyses on one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. For the current annual plan, we have taken two case studies for the scoping study, which will be further refined and implemented in subsequent years. Most of detail implementation of these two use cases will be done in Y2.

Use case 1 (7.3.4.a): Pharmacophore modelling using machine learning for screening BBB permeation of xenobiotics: This use case aims to investigate the effectiveness of different fingerprints generated based on pharmacophore modeling in deciphering the blood–brain barrier permeation of xenobiotics. With pharmacophore modeling, this study will explore the influence of the P-gp protein in the transportation process. [Partners involved: IISPV, UFZ, JSI]

To achieve this objective, use case will perform following activities:

- The collection of chemical data from reviewed literature sources and databases, followed by a filtering and standardization process to obtain a stabilized 3D structure.
- A scaffold of the collected data will be generated to analyze the distribution of the core structure of the chemical responsible for permeability.
- Stabilization and hydration of the protein retrieved from the protein data bank (PDB) will be undertaken, for docking purposes.
- Different methods will be explored to generate pharmacophore fingerprints including receptor-based and ligand-based methods. The residue-based pharmacophore will be generated by docking the P-gp substrates and extracting the most common residues involved in the interaction. Whereas, the interaction-type pharmacophore will be generated using the docked chemical molecules, which will further be processed with the proLIF library to generate a 9-bit fingerprint and Rdkit.
- The generated fingerprint and classical fingerprint will then be trained on a classical algorithm, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), RF (Random Forest), and naïve Bayes, for comparison. New generation of ML method like graph model will also be implemented for methodological comparison.

This use case has been taken in consultation with WP5 and WP8 and activity will be complemented with Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) experimental data generated in Task 5.3.4a (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer) and the computational tools for the early warning system in Task 8.2.

Use case 2: Scoping study of AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA: Activity 7.3.4 will also collaborate with A6.4.3 with a selected project P3: AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA lead by UT (EE) and work on landscaping and readiness of NAMs based on advanced AI&ML approaches for use in chemical RA. This activity is a collaborative activity between two WPs and WP7.3 will support and provide input to the planned activity of A6.4.3. Here the focus is on the documentation of the data feeding into these models, and of the predictions coming out, and how to ensure transparency of these and their FAIRness. [Partners involved: IISPV, UFZ, JSI]

Deliverables

D7.2: PARC FAIR Data Policy – Leader: TNO (M18)

Additional Deliverables:

None

WP N°	WP8										Lead Beneficiary				AUTH/UNINA									
WP title	Concepts and toolboxes																							
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	3.3	4	4.6	8	10.1	10.2	12	13.1	14	15	20	20.3	20.4	20.6	25	25.4	25.6	25.7		
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	BNN	VITO	ISSEP	MU	AU	DTU FOOD	BEA	SYKE	TTL	UBA	ISS	IRFM	IUSS	UNINA	RIVM	UL-LACDR	VUA	WR		
PM/partner	3.8	11.2	0.5	5.1	2.9	2	2.5	26	2	2.1	3.8	6.8	5.1	9	4	18.8	14.7	2.5	19.1	1.9	1	30.3		
Partner N°	25.8	26.3	26.4	26.5	27.2	28	29.2	31.3	33	34.5	34.6	35.4	35.8	35.10	35.11	35.12	36	36.1	36.2	36.3	36.4	51	52	54
Partner short name	WU-TOX	NILU	NIVA	NMBU	UG-PL	FMUL	DGS	NIC	CSIC	IISPV	INSST	ORU	IVL	SLU	UMU	UU	AUTH	EFET	GCSL	NKUA	UOC	BUL	Cefas-Defra	EA
PM/partner	0.9	5	1	0.3	4	1.7	1	11.7	2	6.2	2	15	8.2	25	17	6	66.5	5	10	12.1	17.5	1.7	0.7	0.8
Start	M13										End													
											M24													

Objectives

The overall goal of WP8 is to support the development and consolidation of concepts and tools for chemical risk assessment, also considering Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials and their operationalisation. The specific objectives of WP8 for year 2 are:

- Task 8.1: Move forward with the translation of the SSbD framework into a toolbox

- Task 8.2: To initiate the development of the PARC EWS and the respective computational framework to support the EWS based on the completion of the identification framework
- Task 8.3: To start implementing case studies for further mapping the needs of the PARC model network, based also on the inventory of models and tools.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 8.1: Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

Co-Leaders: RIVM (NL), EMPA (CH), AUTH (EL)

Partners: INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK)

A8.1.1. Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

In year 2, Activity 8.1.1 comprises two lines of action, the first focusing on timely communication approach for dialogue between PARC 8.1 and the EC (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH), other PARC WPs (AUTH, INERIS, UBA) and outside PARC (RIVM, EMPA, IVL), with the HE WP21-22 and WP23-24 working on SSbD, and the second emphasizing operationalization and non-technical support for the SSbD toolbox. With regard to the communication plan, our primary objective is to raise awareness about the EC SSbD framework and to establish PARC's position within the SSbD landscape (RIVM, UNINA, AUTH). In pursuit of this objective in year 2, we intend to develop both targeted and non-targeted communication materials, including a series of presentations on SSbD operationalization (RIVM, EMPA, UNINA, AUTH), PARC/SSbD flyers/newsletters, webinars, and a contents and roles flowchart (RIVM). Additionally, we aim to create an SSbD webpage on the PARC website where all pertinent information can be housed (AUTH). We are also developing targeted communication materials, including an SSbD toolbox one-pager (RIVM), and plan to issue a call for tools early in Y2 to collect relevant tools for SSbD assessment (EMPA).

In addition to raising awareness, our communication plan also aims to establish stakeholder interaction (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, UBA, ISS, IUSS, UNINA, NILU, NIC, INSST, IVL, Cefas-Defra). This has a dual objective: first, to identify gaps and challenges, incentives and barriers: for this, we will conduct a series of interviews with stakeholders, particularly SMEs (RIVM, IUSS, UNINA). Second, to promote mutual learning and capacity building, we plan to offer training and workshops to industry organizations (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, DTU, IUSS, UNINA, IVL). Designing a toolbox involves several steps, including understanding the user needs, defining the functionality, developing the toolbox including the user interface, and testing the design (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, MU, DTU, TTL, IUSS, UNINA, IVL). As understanding user needs (requirements of industry) is an important aspect for the toolbox to be used, we focus on researching and understanding the needs of target audience. This involves conducting user research, such as interviews, surveys, or focus groups, to gather feedback on what features and tools would be helpful to them.

We are also working on establishing an expert team who will attend the discussions on industry voluntary case studies, for example BASF second test in the coming months (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, IUSS, UNINA, IVL).

Furthermore, we have established a live directory of ongoing SSbD projects outside PARC and are contacting project coordinators to identify synergies and learn from their experiences and best use of resources (RIVM, EMPA, IVL).

The second line of action in activity 8.1.1 is concerned with the operationalization of EC SSbD framework and supporting the toolbox from a non-technical perspective, providing guidance and supporting material (AUTH, SSbD). In Year 2, main focus of the work will be the support of the development of the methodological guidance document that will accompany the initial release of the toolbox (AUTH, RIVM, EMPA, IUSS, UNINA). Moreover, we are currently focusing on identifying a list of lessons learned, as

well as gaps, barriers, and incentives from previous frameworks through a literature review as a follow up of our action in Year 1. We are also thinking of a mechanism to couple the SSbD assessment with the internal innovation process of the company focusing on the needs of SMEs primarily. This is a long-term goal that will benefit from knowledge and information sharing from the industry (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH). Additionally, we have established a team to work closely with our data liaison on various aspects of FAIR data tools and resources, including harmonized terminology (AUTH). We have set specific goals for this effort and have already begun work on a commentary paper to raise awareness of the critical role of FAIR in the operationalization of SSbD. We are collaborating with Work Package 7 to define terminology and other key aspects.

We will maintain close communication with Activity 8.1.2 on the toolbox to identify opportunities for Activity 8.1.1 to provide support (AUTH, RIVM, EMPA). Additional activities in this direction include the identification of gaps and opportunities for the SSbD toolbox development, and more in detail,

- (a) the assessment of information obtained from internal and external expert/stakeholder contact (RIVM, AUTH),
- (b) the identification of user expectations and requirements for the SSbD toolbox (AUTH, EMPA, IUSS),
- (c) the identification of early-stage data and tool requirements for SSbD innovation (AUTH, RIVM, EMPA),
- (d) explicitation of specifics about what is exactly lacking in safety and sustainability assessment data (AUTH, RIVM, EMPA), and
- (e) assessment of the availability of FAIR input data to the tools encompassing the SSbD toolbox (AUTH).

While considering having joint events and workshops with other initiatives such as IRISS, we are planning to hold a series of Webinars (3 webinars) and two workshops in Year 2 (RIVM, EMPA). PARC and specifically Task 8.1 is in close collaboration with IRISS, ensured by regular monthly meetings. The main scope of this collaboration is the alignment and complementarity between the projects, as well as avoid of work duplication, identifying the points where IRISS can support the work being done in PARC.

In addition, by providing standard presentations regarding PARC and SSbD we create an opportunity for all partners RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, UBA, ISS, IUSS, UNINA, NILU, NIC, INSST, IVL, Cefas-Defra) to present our work at different events.

A8.1.2. Toolbox development

The development of the version 0.1 of the toolbox will commence in year 2 (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, UBA, ISS, IRFM, IUSS, UNINA, NILU, NMBU, UG-PL, FMUL, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL, Cefas-Defra) based on the conceptual design in D8.1 and with a view to integrate and involve the SSbD toolbox in PARCopedia (AUTH). Particular attention will also be paid to updating user requirements and functional specifications of the SSbD toolbox to accommodate occupational safety and health aspects (TTL, UNINA). Additional state-of-the-art knowledge on developments and instruments applicable for risk assessment (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, ISS, IRFM, IUSS, UNINA, UG-PL, FMUL, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL, Cefas-Defra) and sustainability assessment (AUTH, INERIS, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, UBA, NILU, NMBU, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL)

will be brought in by the PARC consortium, building from previous experience in other EU projects where toolboxes have been developed (AUTH, IUSS, EMPA, IVL), and experience on nanomaterials (NMs) and chemical mixtures (RIVM) in terms of safe-by-design will be translated to broader applications on chemicals and materials. Additionally, a decision support approach will be developed to enable guided innovation decisions during the various stages in the innovation cycle using multi criteria decision analysis (AUTH, EMPA, SYKE). The development of the toolbox will follow a concurrent engineering, iterative approach (AUTH, IUSS). Within Y2 (October 2023), a demo version 0.1 will be developed (AUTH, IUSS, EMPA, IRFM, DTU, TTL, MU, RIVM), that will suggest a workflow and involvement of tools for early and late innovation stages, with an emphasis to be used by SMEs. The version 0.1 will be available to be presented internally (to EC), and in October, stakeholders including SMEs that we are already in contact

will be invited to use it and provide us feedback. Overall, for the toolbox development an iterative process (concurrent engineering) will be employed (AUTH, IUSS); we will start with simple tools, that will be expanded during the process (AUTH, IUSS, EMPA, IRFM, DTU, TTL, MU, RIVM). This will be in close collaboration with the PARC model network developed in Task 8.3 (AUTH).

More detailed actions regarding the toolbox development, will include the identification and adaptation of existing tools, either within the PARC consortium (MU, AUTH, IRFM, UG, DTU, BUL, IUSS, FMUL, TTL, NILU, ISS, INSST, NMBU, IVL, CEFAS-Defra, RIVM), or outside PARC (EMPA, RIVM, IUSS, UNINA, BNN) to operationalize the EC SSbD framework. This includes tools listed by JRC in the SSbD report to carry out the 5-step assessment, as well as tools (standards, methods, labels, etc.) to evaluate the incorporation of design principles, as developed in a series of EU-projects like NANoREG, NanoReg2, CALIBRATE, GRACIOUS (RIVM, EMPA, IVL), and the presently running collaborating risk governance projects Gov4Nano, NanoRigo, and RISKGON (RIVM), as well as to derive the state of the art in the toolbox development through collaboration with the EU NanoSafetyCluster (RIVM, EMPA, IVL). Also, SSbD toolbox will take stock of the integrated exposure and risk modelling platform INTEGRA and INTEGRA LCA developed in HBM4EU and the Cefic-LRI program (AUTH). Towards the conceptual design of the toolbox, mapping of available tools and tools under development that operationalize SSbD (specific info on relevant TRL and SSbD steps for which these tools may be applied) will be carried out (AUTH, IUSS, EMPA, IRFM, DTU, TTL, MU, RIVM). Equally important is the identification of user requirements for the toolbox, as well as highlighting gaps in available tools and address corresponding opportunities for tool development. These actions will result in the implementation of the compiled tools into the version 0.1 of the toolbox, meaning (a) the physical development of the toolbox based on the conceptual design (AUTH, EMPA, IUSS), (b) the integration of the SSbD toolbox output in PARCopedia (AUTH) and (c) the detailing of specifics about the SSbD toolbox design implementation (AUTH, EMPA, RIVM), together with the mapping of the tools and the instructions to effectively utilize the toolbox, provided in the guidance document that will accompany the v0.1 of the toolbox.

A8.1.3. Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators

The developed toolbox will further be operationalized and applied in use cases, in coordination with task 8.1.3 to operationalize the integration of the toolbox benefitting from the experience gained in selected case studies (IVL, AUTH, IUSS, UBA, FMUL, UNINA, TTL, EEA, KI, BNN, Cefas-Defra, RIVM). A second round of user feedback on the v0.1 of the toolbox will be retrieved on the performance of the toolbox in the respective case studies (IVL, AUTH, IUSS). In order to accelerate both the toolbox development, as well as the methodological contributions from other WPs, SSbD will be part of the cross-WPs bisphenols case study. Additional case studies will be used for the toolbox development in coordination with activity 8.1.3. Work in year 2 will further identify, develop and monitor additional use cases and indicators, supporting the follow-up actions resulting from the conclusions of year 1, taking stock of the input received from various stakeholder interactions e.g with the PARC Stakeholder Forum or formed in WP3 (AUTH, UBA, EEA). This plan will consider the barriers as well as incentives for implementation of different stakeholders that are involved in the use cases (IVL, UBA). Beyond aspects related to chemicals, materials and processes and how these result in safety and sustainability aspects, additional case study definition and execution will be planned, from the viewpoint of occupational safety and health (IVL, UNINA, TTL). The inventory of relevant indicators to follow the progresses of sector applicability of the toolbox will be further evolved, accounting from the various interactions emerging from the Y1 experience within and outside PARC, including the indicator programme foreseen by EEA and in collaboration with Task 3.2.

During Y1 an inventory of candidate case studies is compiled. This is a gross list based on a literature search, a questionnaire to stakeholders in 8.1, reach-out to associated projects, e.g. IRISS and the JRC cases, and also an outreach to other WPs in PARC to identify candidate chemicals.

In Y2, work will start on testing the SSbD toolbox on a selected set of these cases.

Based on the gross list achieved in Y1, we will select cases based on several criteria, in an approach to cover many different aspects and application situations.

We are aiming for 3-5 cases for each of the steps in the SSbD procedure. As it will possibly be difficult to find individual cases that can be tested for all steps, some cases may only be possible for one or the other step.

Specific actions will include:

1. Workshop to discuss and agree on criteria for case studies
2. Assessing the compiled cases in relation to the criteria to shortlist candidates
3. Reach out to shortlisted cases and set up meetings to discuss opportunities for collaboration around the cases. If relevant, define new cases beyond those compiled and try to find collaboration partners
4. Decide on the final selection and establish agreements with the external stakeholders
 - a. Establish working groups/task forces among the 8.1.3. stakeholders, related to each case study
 - b. Each Task force defines a work plan for the work to be carried out, e.g. scope of work, what tools to test from 8.1.2, time plan, resources to be committed
5. Carry out the work including reporting back/exchanging experiences

A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalization

Building on the results of Year 2 presented in the relevant stakeholders will be continued by an analysis of stakeholder needs for education material, training programs and information sharing material (RIVM, BNN, SYKE, TTL, UBA, UNINA, NMBU, FMUL, NIC, INSST, AUTH). This will help to deduce learning goals which in turn will support the selection of appropriate and tailored elements and format of the SSbD knowledge sharing platform based on the collection of existing knowledge sharing platforms and education materials performed in Year 1 of PARC. Based on learning goals identified a decision tree will be developed which will guide the selection of education material, training programs and information sharing material for the knowledge sharing platform (UBA, IUSS, UNINA, AUTH). Criteria will be developed to assess materials with regard to relevance, accuracy, focus and target (RIVM, UBA, UNINA, NMBU, FMUL, AUTH). In addition, based on the findings of the inventories on knowledge sharing platforms and education materials, initial considerations on content-related and structural features of the SSbD knowledge sharing platforms will be made (RIVM, UBA, UNINA, AUTH). These will be used to frame the platform to continue and intensify discussion with PARC partners involved in the technical implementation of the platform (PARCopedia) (AUTH) but also with experts outside of PARC which may support in shaping the platform by contributing to it with their own information/training/education material (RIVM, UBA, UNINA, SYKE). Additionally, in this activity a concrete short-term plan for setting up a 'summer school' on SSbD is included. Finally, JRC, in collaboration with PARC will organize a training autumn school in October on Safe and Sustainable by Design Chemicals and Materials.

The 8.1.1 milestone on the 8.1 communication plan will be published, referring to a generic presentation of 8.1, an informative email/flyer on SSbD framework, a series of presentations of 8.1 goals, and a series of webinars. Additionally, a one-page summary of the work on the SSbD toolbox development will be included in the PARC web page. Part of the 8.1 communication plan is also the launch of the SSbD webpage on the PARC website introducing the SSbD and the activities of Task 8.1.

Task 8.2: Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks

Co-Leaders: SLU (SE), INSERM (FR)

Partners: INRAE (FR), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE), IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), GCSL (EL) NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)

A8.2.1 EW monitoring tools

The development of early warning monitoring tools in humans, environment and products using suspect and non-target screening tools and effect-directed analysis (EDA), in strong collaboration with Task 4.2 and Task 4.3 will continue (SLU, ORU, ISS, VITO). In this sense, the definition of appropriate expectations and outputs from innovative screening methods planned to be developed and applied within Task 4.3 (including Effect Directed Analysis as an early warning tool) (INRAE). Efforts on screening of chemical and environmental legislation for the potential use of early warning monitoring tools will be continued and commenced in a draft informal report (IVL, UBA). Also, the usefulness of the JANUS software (prioritizing the substances, considering the CMR, PBT and ED properties) with the information from WP 4 related to the exposure data will also be explored (IRFM). Suspect lists relevant for this task and published on the NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN-SLE) as they become available will be reviewed, while collaboration with NORMAN will be continued to ensure that the relevant metadata is available in other NORMAN databases (UniLu, NKUA). Text mining tools will also be developed (AUTH) based on the inventory conducted in year 1 which will be able to identify food safety risks, while the literature analysis of existing AI systems in EWS to select the most reliable and useful tools for chemicals prioritization framework will be continued (WR, UG-PL). The PARC EW monitoring tools methodology will benefit from the experiences in the EW monitoring tools from the National scale EWS in England (PEWS) (EA).

A8.2.2: Identification framework

A prioritization framework that will allow us to identify new hazardous substances, their transformation products (TPs) and sources with a special focus on effect-directed analysis (EDA) approaches (linked with activities in Tasks 4.2, 4.3) will be developed (SLU, UG-PL, VITO). The activities will continue with attention to clustering the structural alerts and global molecular features into a hierarchical scheme, to capture the overall chemical properties related to the adverse effects (IRFM, UniLU, NKUA). This information will be used to identify molecular features to be used for screening for potential adverse effects, with the definition of the specific critical effect. Work on the evaluation of existing computational methods and selection of the most promising tools in the context of prioritization framework will be continued (AUTH, NKUA), and if necessary, the knowledge about the disadvantages of existing tools will be used during the development of new tools to meet the identified needs (UniLU, EFET). Research for existing national databases in order to use them in the identification of emerging hazardous substances will also be carried out (AUTH), while samples will be provided from the German environmental specimen bank (UBA) for testing them for long-term target and non-target screening data, together with a curated list of currently marketed substances.

A8.2.3: Applicability and performance testing of EW toolbox

Planning of case studies for humans (→Tasks 4.1 and 4.3), environment (→Task 4.2) and products (→Task 8.1) towards the validation of an early warning system will be carried out (SLU, ORU). A project proposal to make use of long-term non-target screening data from the German riverine environment in EWS will be prepared, as well as planning of case studies for the exposure of prioritized chemical substances (from food or food contact materials) for the validation of an EWS (UBA). Additional planning of cases studies will be based on the multitude of HBM data that will become available, as well as omics data used as early effect markers (SLU, EFET, VITO).

A8.2.4: Computational framework to support the EWS

In Y2, the effort for curation and harmonization, to interconnect the huge amount of data output from the different tasks to develop a proactive EWS will be continued, that will allow the ranking of the potential risks (link with WPs 4, 5, 6) and integrative models (Tasks 6.2 and 8.3), (AUTH) and be made publicly available for dissemination to policy-makers, regulators and other stakeholders (UBA, UniLu, SLU, UMU). EEA will be actively involved in the design of an EWS strategy. Screening of routine chemical management for EWS initiatives will be continued, together with gathering suspect lists relevant for this task (UBA). Collection of in silico tools for chemical and toxicological screening (AUTH) and list of tools useful in the context of risk ranking will continue, together with the identification of possibilities and obstacles in relevant legislation for the implementation of an EWS (UG-PL, UMU). Necessary requirements for the output from an EWS to support prioritization of emerging contaminants in relation to the existing legislation will also be identified (UBA, IVL). Tools to spot critical effects potentially associated to the contaminant will be provided, based on the SMILES as only requested input (UniLu, IRFM). Computational work will include the computational framework for screening possible neurotoxins and working on the BBB permeation prediction model using AI/ML, as well as the adaptation of the INTEGRA platform for early identification of chemical risks (NKUA, UniLU, UMU, IISPV).

Task 8.3 Integrative models

Co-Leaders: WR (NL), AUTH (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

A.8.3.1: Design, implementation and application of the PARC integrative model network

Analysis of 1) user requirements that are expressed by stakeholders in case studies and 2) the model inventory that is being developed, will define the needs for functional links of the various existing or new models and provide advice on the general direction of the model network development (WR-BIOM, AUTH). Input on the needs of the PARC model network will also be provided by collaboration with WP2 (AUTH), where challenges for which the model network could produce innovative results will be identified. Projects carried out across PARC WPs will be used to define model requirements regarding the model network (WR, AUTH) as well as the toolbox web interfaces (WR, AUTH, UU). Additional input on the requirements will follow from case studies (AUTH, WR, ANSES, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIVA, NMBU, NIC, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC).

Task 8.3 in year 2 will focus on further developing PARC infrastructure (based as much as possible on semantic modelling in collaboration with WP7) to support the PARC modeling network, and to establish initial links between the various available models (WR, AUTH). The PARC integrative model network will be developed as a digital ecosystem, linking multiple tools and models. Further development of the PARC modeling network (WR, AUTH) will be facilitated by participation in the cross-WP group on semantic modelling and PARC ontologies (WR, AUTH, IISPV), establishing examples of practically organised data format mappings (link with WP 7). The network will link models for, e.g., aggregate and cumulative exposure assessment, hazard characterisation, risk assessment, uncertainty analysis, HBM analysis and PBK models (AUTH, WR, INERIS, IISPV, IUSS, ANSES, MU), supporting projects of other WPs (link with 6.2.2 and 6.2.3) (WR, ANSES, INERIS, AUTH). A functional design will be developed for aggregate exposure models (link with 6.2.1) (WR, ANSES, AUTH). Also, the inventory of models/tools within the PARC consortium will be completed either by direct participation (ANSES, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIVA, NMBU, NIC, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC) or by links with other PARC projects (WR-BIOM, AUTH). This will set the basis for the identification and modular description of available tools such as INTEGRA (AUTH), MCRA (WR), USEtox (DTU), VEGAHUB (IRFM). The above actions will result in further conceptual model network development. A tool (open-source dynamical system under version control) will be created for

hosting the conceptual design of the PARC integrative model network (AUTH, WR-BIOM). Initial testing of the model network will be carried out during the implementation of case studies.

To better respond to contemporary RA needs and foster the transition towards NGRA, case studies will be implemented in the frame of the relevant project of Task 8.3 and often in collaboration with other projects, that will try to fill the gaps of comprehensive methodological workflows for evaluating multiple lines of evidence. This will pertain to assessment of various domains of exposure to chemicals, such as food consumption and dietary exposure (WR, AUTH), personal activity and environmental exposure (AUTH, WR), HBM data assimilation (AUTH, WR, IISPV), as well as hazard characterisation (WR), including the use of in-silico or in-vitro NAMs (UL-LACDR, UoC, IRFM) and risk assessment (WR, ANSES). The integrative modelling network will include modelling of uncertainties in relation to data and models that are available or will be generated in the field of RA (MU, WR, IISPV). One of the case studies that will be considered is RA of bisphenols (BPA and BPA alternatives). For this group of substances the project needs several types of data, and if these data are not available through the work implemented in other PARC WPs, it will rely on available data from previous EU projects (HBM4EU, HEALS, CROME). The impact of co-exposure to the bisphenols in the biologically effective dose and the way this impacts the QIVIVE extrapolation will also be examined. Aiming at addressing these questions, precise needs for the various models and modules will be mapped and translated to model network needs. More in detail, contribution to external exposure estimates will be delivered by daily intake and exposure estimates will be made for several population groups (WR, AUTH), including the most susceptible ones such as fetus, neonates and children, as well as occupationally exposed and high-end consumer population groups (DTU, SYKE, ANSES). Exposure will be estimated by combining bottom up exposure estimates by aggregating multisource (AUTH), multipathway (DTU, ANSES, NIVA, SYKE, NMBU), multiroute (INERIS, UoC, IUSS) exposure, and top down, by exposure reconstruction of available HBM data (AUTH, INERIS, IUSS, WR). The aim is to identify the needs for aggregate (multi-source, multi-pathway and multi-route exposure) modelling, including multimedia environmental emission and fate modelling, food contact materials migration, as well as percutaneous and inhalation exposure for consumer and occupational settings. Toxicokinetics of bisphenols (AUTH, INERIS, IISPV, IUSS, WR) and especially during the prenatal and perinatal period (AUTH, INERIS) play a particular role. A framework for assimilating HBM data, and translating them into external, intake-level and internal exposure estimates (exposure reconstruction) will be defined (WR, AUTH). Use of quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) will be constructed linked to the model network to describe the toxicodynamics after triggering of MIEs and downstream key events (WR, AUTH, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, IUSS). Dose-response relations, measured for relevant key events will be assessed (WR) combining relevant cell-based system and holistic approaches (UL-LACDR, WU-TOX), including toxicogenomics and co-expression analysis. NAM toxicity assessment metrics and approaches will be used for delivering hazard and risk characterisation estimates. Internal dosimetry models will hold a key role, serving the need for translating external exposure estimates into internal dosimetry metrics, for quantitative in-vitro in-vivo extrapolation (INERIS, IISPV, IUSS, AUTH, WR), while it is also a key component of the models for exposure reconstruction (AUTH, INERIS, IUSS, IISPV, WR-BIOM) starting from HBM data. Moreover, the impact of co-exposure to the three bisphenols in the biologically effective dose and the way this impacts the QIVIVE extrapolation will also be examined (AUTH, INERIS, IUSS).

Deliverables:

D8.1. Report on the conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox – Leader: AUTH. This deliverable was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14).

D8.2 - Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS – Leader: SLU. This deliverable was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14).

D8.4 - 1st Report on the testing and uptake of the SSbD toolbox through use cases – Leader: EMPA (M24)

D8.3. Report on the conceptual design of the integrative tools – Leader: AUTH. This deliverable was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14).

Additional Deliverables:

AD8.3: Conceptualization of a computational system using AI and systems modeling for environmental and human samples and products for the EWS – Leader: AUTH (M18)

AD8.4: Initial results of the application of the integrative model network in use cases – Leader: AUTH (M24)

WP N°	WP9										Lead Beneficiary				ISCIII/MU							
WP title	Building infrastructural and human capacities																					
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.7	1.10	1.11	2	3.8	3.9	4.6	5	6.1	8	8.2	10.1	10.3	15	17	20.3	21	22
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	ONIRIS	BRGM	LNE	SpF	UMIT	UNIVIE	ISSEP	SCIENSANO	IMROH	MU	VSCHT	AU	REGIONH-RH	UBA	NPHC	IRFM	RSU	NPHSL
PM/partner	0.8	3	1.3	2.6	0.8	3.8	3.6	3	2	4.5	3.7	5.1	1	64.6	3.9	5.1	4	2.3	3	1.5	0.4	12.9
Partner N°	24	25.7	26	26.2	26.7	28	29	29.5	30	30.1	31	31.4	32	33	34	34.2	34.4	35.2	36	36.2	37	50
Partner short name	LNS	WR	NIPH	STAMI	UNN	FMUL	INSA	UAVR	SZU-SK	UK	JSI	UL FFA	NIJZ	CSIC	ISCIII	FISABIO	FNS	KI	AUTH	GCSL	BPI	UKHSA
PM/partner	8.3	6	1.9	5	1	4.5	16.5	2.8	3.7	1.2	2.9	1	1.5	12.5	33.7	2	3.8	3.5	3.2	3.1	3.7	1
Start	M13									End					M24							

Objectives

The overall goal of WP9 is to promote the further development of existing and new infrastructural and human capacities related to laboratory networks including reference laboratories and exposure monitoring networks. The specific objectives of WP9 for year 2 are:

- Task 9.1:
 - Finalize the overall architecture and best-fit solution(s) for building the information catalogues on laboratory networks
 - Keep the catalogues created on HBM laboratories and on the fields prioritized in Y1 up to date (air, indoor, articles)
 - Extend the catalogues to include additional laboratory networks (Y2 priority fields: water and sediment)
 - Detect needs for laboratory network promotion or creation
 - Start defining tools to promote and coordinate laboratory networks
 - Develop and implement the concept on the laboratory network dashboard
- Task 9.2:
 - Finalize the overall architecture and best-fit solution(s) for building the information catalogues on environmental monitoring networks

- Further develop the initial version of the catalog on HBM studies, cohorts, projects, networks, and other relevant information
- Further develop the initial versions of the catalogues on projects, networks, and other relevant information in the Y1 priority domains (air, the indoor environment, and articles)
- Initiate the development of catalogues on projects, networks, and other relevant information in the Y2 priority domains (water and sediment)
- Task 9.3:
 - Finalize the inventory of existing definitions, protocols/guidances and QA/QC criteria for the QA/QC topics prioritized in Y1 regarding sampling, chemical laboratory testing, and toxicity testing/kinetic studies
 - Finalize the identification of inconsistencies and gaps in the above, and needs from WP4/WP5
 - Draft generic guidance documents as basic principles for use in WP4 and WP5, for the above topics
- Task 9.4:
 - Identifying existing training needs through interaction with WPs and a survey
 - Map and identify relevant available training options (outside PARC) to meet the training needs identified in Y1
 - Define the training courses and learning resources to be held/developed within the PARC consortium for Y2-Y3
 - Provide support to local training organizers

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 9.1: Laboratory networking

Leader: ISCIII (ES)

A9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of the laboratory networks

(Partners: NPHSL, SZU-SK, ANSES, AU, BPI, BRGM, CSIC, FISABIO, FMUL, INERIS, INSA, ISCIII, LNE, MU, NIPH, SCIENSANO, STAMI, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, RSU, UK, ONIRIS)

The mapping of the existing HBM laboratories and updating of the HBM catalogue will continue in Y2. The same will be done for laboratories and networks on air, indoor and articles (work on those has started in Y1).

In addition, we will start working on the prioritized environmental fields of water and sediment, where the first catalogues will be available by M24.

All the information collected from the different laboratory networks will be included in a dashboard, making accessible the capacities of the laboratory networks in an interactive way. (Partners: ISCIII, GCSL, LNS, NMBU, FMUL). Once the concept of the dashboard is defined in collaboration with WP3 by M12, the activities on its development and implementation will start in Y2.

A9.1.2 Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation

(Partners: FISABIO, INERIS, AU, BRGM, FMUL, INSA, ISCIII, MU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, SCIENSANO, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU)

Based on the first inventories of laboratories, the less developed networks will be identified by M24 and a list of networks that will need promotion or support will be prepared. The list will serve as a living document and will be updated alongside the gradual creation of the catalogues.

A9.1.3 Facilitate the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks

(Partners: CSIC, IPA, INERIS, BRGM, FMUL, INSA, LNE, MU, LNS, STAMI, ISCIII, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU)

In light of the need for better coordination and promotion of selected laboratory networks, initial strategies and tools to achieve a desirable level of coordination and linkage will be defined in Y2.

Task 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities

Leader: MU (CZ)

A9.2.1 Mapping of exposure monitoring capacities

(Partners: ANSES, Inserm, Oniris, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, MU, VSCHT, AU, NPHC, NPHSL, LNS, UU-IRAS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, SZU-SK, CSIC, ISCIII, AUTH, BPI, GCSL)

Mapping of the existing air, indoor, and article exposure monitoring networks as started in the first year will continue in Y2 and will include the development of semi-final catalogues. In addition, the Y2 priority networks (water, sediment) will be mapped with the aim of developing their initial catalogues by M24. Further work will be devoted to the periodical updating of the existing catalogues to assure that by the end of the PARC project the most up-to-date information is reported.

A9.2.2 Strengthening of exposure monitoring capacities

(Partners: ANSES, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, MU, VSCHT, AU, LNS, UU-IRAS, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, GCSL)

The most developed catalogues (HBM, air) will be analyzed to reveal existing gaps. This will be a joint effort including also the assessment of gaps in the existing laboratory networks compiled into catalogues by Task 9.1. Depending on the type of gaps, further consultations will be initiated with the R&I work packages and/or WP 2, 3, 7, and 9 (task 9.4) in order to suggest activities and future actions toward closing the gaps (particularly in the priority fields of PARC).

Task 9.3: Joint activities – harmonisation

Leader: WR (NL)

Partners: UNIVIE (AT), SCIENSANO (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), UBA (DE), RegionH (DK), AU (DK), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FNS (ES), INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), INERIS (FR), LNE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), LNS (LU), , NIPH (NO), UNN (NO), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), NLZOH (SI)

Transversal activity: Towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing

Based on the inventories on QA/QC regarding sampling, chemical analysis, and toxicity testing/toxicokinetics studies, the 5 working groups established in Y1 (see below) will draft a glossary on terminology and guidance documents on various QA/QC parameters with focus on sample types and substances/techniques foreseen to be prioritised/used in Y2-Y3 of WP4 and WP5.

WG-1: Overarching QA/QC working group on sampling. Includes: fit-for-purpose sampling, passive sampling, pretreatment, storage/stability, artifacts, uncertainty. Lead: AU, LNE. Partners: ANSES-LSAI PCPPA, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, Sciensano, MU, AU, LNS, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, FNS, BPI.

WG-2: Overarching QA/QC working group on Performance criteria chemical analysis. Includes: LOD/LOQ, identification, trueness/precision criteria, calibration, validation, batch control, measurement uncertainty. Lead: MU. Partners: ANSES, INRAE, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, RegionH, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, BPI, GCSL.

WG-3: Overarching QA/QC working group on Assessment of interlab comparability chemical analysis.

Includes: (evaluation of) protocols for proficiency testing (PT/ICI/EQUAS), small-scale interlab comparisons, catalogue for PT providers, catalogue (C)RMs. Lead: ANSES, LNE. Partners: ANSES, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, INSA, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, BPI, GCSL.

WG-4: Overarching QA/QC working group on Reporting and acceptability of results from chemical analysis. Includes: reporting requirements, normalisation of results, acceptability of lab data, criteria for qualification of labs. Lead: ONIRIS, LNS. Partners: ANSES, INRAE, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, NMBU, INSA, JSI, CSIC, BPI, GCSL.

WG6: Overarching QA/QC working group on Toxicity testing & kinetic studies. Includes: in vivo and in vitro test systems (novel approach methods, NAMs), reporting. Lead: NIPH, STAMI. Partners: ANSES, INERIS, Sciensano, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, INSA, FNS.

Task 9.4: Training

Leader: INSA (PT)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BRGM (FR), LNE (FR), UMIT (AT), Sciensano (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), IPA (DE), IRFM (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), ULFFA (SI), NIJZ (SI), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FNS (ES), IMM-KI (SE), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR)

Building on data obtained in the training needs assessment surveys (Y1), partners will map available training on the topics identified (43 have been identified in the first survey, being (1) Risk assessment – fundamentals and approaches; (2) Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data; (3) Databases; (4) New approach methodologies (NAMs); (5) Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs); and (6) Statistical analysis, the most frequently indicated topics), and define the new training courses and learning resources to be held/developed within the PARC consortium for Y2-3 of PARC.

The suitability of the identified training (objectives and contents) and adequacy and relevance of learning resources contents will be discussed with experts from other WPs and if suitable, will be disseminated (by M17) through the project website (training courses) or made available on the web-based portal (to be launched by M24).

In what concerns new training courses, project leaders will work with WP contact points on topic prioritization to create a flexible PARC training plan revised/updated every 2 years to adjust to project progress and findings.

Local organizers of training events to be carried out under PARC will receive the support of project leaders and members, namely in what concerns event dissemination, registration support, preparation and distribution of certificates, preparation and distribution of training evaluation surveys, and training evaluation assessment. At least 2 (maximum 3) -person trainings are expected in Y2.

Deliverables:

D9.2 Catalogues on environmental and biomonitoring networks Y1 _ Leader MU. This deliverable was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14)
D9.4: 1st Generic guidance documents for QA/QC on sampling; chemical analysis; toxicity, & toxicokinetics studies – Leader: WR (M24)
D9.5: Report on Training events Y2 – Leader: INSA (M24)

Additional Deliverables:

AD9.1 - Training Plan, version 1- Leader: INSA (M18)

Table 2.3.b: AWP Set of Activities

Activity No	Activity Title	Lead Participant No	Short name of lead participant	Person-Months	Start Month	End month
1	Coordination and management	1	ANSES	214.12	13	24
2	A common science-policy agenda	3/12	EAA/EEA	137.63	13	24
3	Synergies, collaborations and awareness	29/36.2	INSA/GCSL	195.74	13	24
4	Monitoring and exposure	15/2	UBA/SpF	1 431.63	13	24
5	Hazard Assessment	16/1	BfR/ANSES	1 947.05	13	24
6	Innovation in regulatory risk assessment	25/35.7	RIVM/KEMI	1 669.95	13	24
7	FAIR Data	4/59	VITO/UOB	358.02	13	24
8	Concepts and toolboxes	36/20.6	AUTH/UNIN A	406.96	13	24
9	Building infrastructural and human capacities	34/8	ISCIH/MU	260.68	13	24
			TOTAL	6 621.78		

Table 2.3.c: Additional Deliverables List

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	Activity N°	Lead participant Short name	Type ²	Dissemination level ³	Delivery date	Description
AD2.1	Draft NGRA roadmap document	WP2	BfR	R	PU	M24	This draft document will provide a first draft roadmap for NGRA uptake into policy, which it will be further discussed and finalised with the consortium in year 3.
AD4.1	Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies	WP4	SpF	R	PU	M14	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14)
AD4.3	AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances) - Leader: UBA.	WP4	UBA	R	PU	M24	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M24)
AD4.4	Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories	WP4	INERIS/AU	R	PU	M24	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M24)
AD4.5	Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows)	WP4	INERIS/AU	R	PU	M14	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M14)
AD4.6	Concept paper regarding common definitions and short	WP4	INERIS/AU	R	PU	M14	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2

² Indicate the type of each Deliverable using one of the following codes: R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

³ Indicate the dissemination level of each Deliverable using one of the following codes: PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web; CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement (Consortium only); CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

	to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTS/EDA approaches						(M14)
AD4.7	Summary of analytical methods applied in the pilot study (PFAS and EDCs), including a list of laboratories.	WP4	INERIS/AU	R	PU	M18	This summary will describe the different analytical methods applied in the pilot study for monitoring PFAS and EDCs in environmental samples as well as provide a list of the laboratories running the analyses and their credentials.
AD4.8	Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies	WP4	TTL	R	PU	M18	This document will describe the results of the feasibility study and inform if general population surveys can give some indication on occupational exposure to specific chemicals and provide recommendations for future aligned studies how to improve the gathering and analysis of occupational data.
AD5.4	AD 5.4 - Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on	WP5	UL-LACDR	R	PU	M14	The ADs AD 5.4 - Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and AD 5.6 – Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritized endpoints were initially planned Y1

	the prioritised endpoints.						(M12) but are postponed to Y2 (M14) and they are being merged to only one AD 5.4. Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints.
AD 5.7	Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanism	WP5	UL-LACDR, SCIENSANO	R	PU	M18	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M18)
AD6.1	Strategy document on IATA for more complex endpoints	WP6 (T6.1)	SCIENSANO	R	PU	M18	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M10) but was postponed to Y2 (M18).
AD6.7	Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas.	WP 6 (T6.4)	UBA, KemI, FOEN	R	PU	M24	This AD was initially planned Y1 (M10) but was postponed to Y2 (M24).
AD6.9	Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies	WP6 (T6.1)	UL-LACDR	R	PU	M24	Report describing the draft IATA for genotoxicity, endocrine toxicity and liver toxicity, plus the objectives and design of case studies aimed at the interim evaluation of these draft IATAs. This AD replaces the AD6.2. Report

							on the objectives and design of three case studies starting in year 1 for interim evaluation of IATAs initially planned Y1 and which was replaced by <u>the</u> milestone <u>MS15</u> at M12
AD6.14	Report on current screening and enforcement structures	WP6 (T6.4)	TUKES	R	PU	M24	This report will describe the outcomes of surveys and mapping exercise to evaluate methodology and data structures used in enforcement of chemical regulations with respect to substances in products and materials across the European region, and highlight gaps in the current enforcement structures.
AD6.15	Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards	WP6 (T6.4)	MU	R	PU	M24	This report will describe the structures used to incorporate chemical hazards into LCA indicators, and use case study examples to compare across different LCA methods and types of hazard scores.
AD6.16	Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis	WP6 (T6.4)	UNIBAS	R	PU	M24	AD6.8 “Technical report: mapping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks” initially planned Y1 (M12) has been postponed to Y2 and merged with this AD
AD8.3	Conceptualization of a computational system using	WP8 (T8.2)	AUTH	R	PU	M18	The deliverable will describe the conceptual model for the EWS

	AI and systems modeling for environmental and human samples and products for the EWS						computational system geared to address chemicals of emerging concern in environmental and human samples and in consumer products
AD8.4	Initial results of the application of the integrative model network in use cases	WP8 (T8.3)	AUTH	R	PU	M24	This deliverable will report on the first results of the application of the PARC model network for chemical risk assessment as these will pertain to the first round of use cases. Based on these results the beta version of the integrative risk model network of PARC will be developed.
AD9.1	Training plan, version 1	WP9 (T9.4)	INSA	R	PU	M18	Plan detailing type (in-person courses vs. online resources), topics, target audience and timelines of trainings to be carried out/developed in Y2 and Y3 of PARC

2.2. Participation in Annual Work Programme activities

The description of the consortium's participation is to be found in Annex I of the AWPY2.

2.3 Resources to be committed

Table 2.3.d: Summary effort table

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per participant
1-ANSES	108,75	13,20	1,00	55,65	82,15	71,25	27,37	3,82	0,83	364,02
1.1-INSERM	-	4,50	-	16,55	209,90	15,20	3,10	11,20	3,00	263,45
1.2-INRAE	-	-	-	60,25	60,50	6,10	-	0,50	1,33	128,68
1.3-CEA	-	-	-	17,20	-	-	-	-	-	17,20
1.4-INSERM	-	-	-	24,53	16,39	23,00	-	1,50	2,60	68,02
1.5-CNRS	-	-	-	6,75	23,00	-	-	-	-	29,75
1.6-INRS	-	-	-	9,30	11,70	3,00	1,50	-	-	25,50
1.7-ONIRIS	-	-	-	13,85	-	25,50	-	-	0,83	40,18
1.8-IRSN	-	-	-	-	2,00	4,50	-	-	-	6,50
1.9-OFB	-	-	-	2,80	-	8,50	-	-	-	11,30
1.10-BRGM	-	-	-	14,60	-	-	7,50	-	3,80	25,90
1.11-LNE	-	-	-	0,45	-	-	-	-	3,55	4,00
1.12-CSTB	-	-	-	12,00	-	6,70	-	-	-	18,70
1.13-EHESP	4,50	-	-	10,55	-	0,50	-	-	-	15,55
2-SpF	8,73	1,50	0,50	59,45	-	-	-	-	3,00	73,18
3-EAA	4,90	3,50	4,70	2,50	-	3,50	-	-	-	19,10
3.1-AGES	-	-	2,00	-	-	17,00	-	-	-	19,00
3.2-AIT	-	-	-	-	12,00	-	-	-	-	12,00
3.3-BNN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,93	-	2,93
3.4-MUI	-	-	-	15,80	37,70	6,00	-	-	-	59,50
3.5-	-	-	-	1,00	-	-	-	-	-	1,00

MUW										
3.6-UG-AT	-	1,00	-	4,00	-	-	-	-	-	5,00
3.7-UIBK	-	-	-	-	21,20	-	-	-	-	21,20
3.8-UMIT	-	-	2,00	-	-	-	-	-	2,00	4,00
3.9-UNIVIE	-	-	-	4,40	40,00	-	-	-	4,50	48,90
4-VITO	5,20	-	1,00	48,60	-	39,20	53,00	2,00	-	149,00
4.1-KU Leuven	-	-	-	11,90	10,00	-	-	-	-	21,90
4.2-DOMG	3,30	1,04	2,00	-	-	-	-	-	-	6,34
4.3-UH	-	-	-	1,00	-	-	-	-	-	1,00
4.4-PIH	-	-	-	5,50	-	-	-	-	-	5,50
4.5-OVAM	-	0,25	-	15,00	-	1,25	-	-	-	16,50
4.6-ISSeP	-	-	-	26,10	-	12,00	12,50	2,50	3,65	56,75
4.7-UAntwerpen	-	-	-	19,20	44,10	25,40	-	-	-	88,70
5-SCIENSANO	0,30	-	-	25,00	42,40	75,03	-	-	5,08	147,81
5.1-UGent	-	-	-	-	16,70	15,00	-	-	-	31,70
5.2-EV-ILVO	-	1,00	-	1,00	-	-	2,00	-	-	4,00
5.3-VUB	-	-	-	-	22,00	21,00	-	-	-	43,00
6-CIPH	1,10	-	1,00	1,00	-	-	-	-	-	3,10
6.1-IMROH	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,00	-	1,00	3,00
7-MOH-CY/SGL	1,10	0,50	1,00	4,70	-	1,00	-	-	-	8,30
7.1-SHSO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
8-MU	4,40	5,90	2,50	55,34	12,50	72,70	79,00	26,00	64,60	322,94
8.1-SZU-CZ	-	-	-	1,70	-	-	-	-	-	1,70

8.2-VSCHT	-	-	-	5,60	-	-	-	-	3,90	9,50
8.3-OU	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
8.4-JU	-	-	-	1,20	-	-	-	-	-	1,20
9-UZIS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
10-DEPA	1,50	0,50	1,00	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,00
10.1-AU	-	-	-	33,65	15,00	20,10	-	2,00	5,06	75,81
10.2-DTU	-	-	-	-	44,50	36,50	-	2,10	-	83,10
10.3-REGIO NH	-	-	-	3,00	-	14,00	-	-	4,00	21,00
10.4-UCPH	-	-	-	14,95	-	2,00	-	-	-	16,95
10.5-SDU	-	-	-	-	34,00	4,00	-	-	-	38,00
11-HB	1,20	0,50	0,98	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,68
11.1-SOM	-	1,50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,50
11.2-UT	-	-	-	-	-	18,00	-	-	-	18,00
12-EEA	3,00	15,00	13,00	-	-	-	-	3,79	-	34,79
13-THL	0,10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,10
13.1-SYKES	-	-	-	13,00	-	3,50	-	6,82	-	23,32
14-TTL	1,20	0,50	1,00	12,70	2,10	9,25	-	5,05	-	31,80
14.1-FFA	-	-	-	2,20	-	-	-	-	-	2,20
14.2-Tukes	-	-	-	-	-	2,00	-	-	-	2,00
14.3-UOULU	-	-	-	1,80	-	-	-	-	-	1,80
15-UBA	2,99	5,63	2,81	74,75	-	33,65	5,50	9,00	2,30	136,63
15.1-BfG	-	-	-	14,00	10,00	-	-	-	-	24,00
15.2-UFZ	-	-	-	45,30	62,50	31,30	16,00	-	-	155,10
15.3-IPA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
15.4-UKOLD	-	-	-	-	-	31,00	-	-	-	31,00
15.5-UOS	-	-	-	-	-	8,54	-	-	-	8,54

15.6-KUM	-	-	-	7,32	-	-	-	-	-	7,32
16-BfR	4,50	18,29	0,90	-	114,25	-	-	-	-	137,94
16.1-Fraunhofer	-	-	-	21,00	15,20	7,50	-	-	-	43,70
16.2-KIT	-	-	-	-	11,60	-	-	-	-	11,60
16.3-IUF	-	-	-	-	48,00	-	-	-	-	48,00
16.4-IfADo	-	-	-	-	12,00	12,00	-	-	-	24,00
16.5-MLU	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
16.6-UKL	-	-	-	-	12,00	-	-	-	-	12,00
16.7-TUB	-	-	-	-	14,27	-	-	-	-	14,27
16.8-UKON	-	-	-	-	7,50	-	-	-	-	7,50
16.9-TiHo	-	-	-	-	6,00	-	-	-	-	6,00
16.10-UHC	-	-	-	-	1,95	-	-	-	-	1,95
17-NPHC	1,00	5,50	14,00	-	32,20	-	-	-	3,00	55,70
18-UI	1,00	0,50	1,00	3,50	8,00	2,25	-	-	-	16,25
19-MOH	-	-	1,00	1,50	-	-	-	-	-	2,50
20-ISS	1,70	2,00	1,00	11,90	30,00	27,00	4,00	4,00	-	81,60
20.1-ICPS	-	-	-	-	-	7,84	-	-	-	7,84
20.2-CNR-IRSA	-	-	-	14,40	-	-	-	-	-	14,40
20.3-IRFM	-	-	-	6,00	18,75	10,50	-	18,75	1,50	55,50
20.4-IUSS	0,30	-	2,00	-	-	6,50	-	14,70	-	23,50
20.5-UMIL	-	-	-	3,00	9,76	-	-	-	-	12,76
20.6-UNINA	-	-	0,13	1,55	-	-	-	2,50	-	4,18
20.7-UNIPD	-	-	-	1,25	-	5,00	-	-	-	6,25

21-RSU	1,20	0,50	1,00	25,90	-	3,00	-	-	0,38	31,98
21.1-UL	-	-	-	3,30	-	-	-	-	-	3,30
22-NPHSL	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,50	-	-	-	-	12,94	16,44
23-LSMU	-	-	-	4,60	-	3,24	-	-	-	7,84
24-LNS	2,50	-	2,00	40,85	-	8,00	-	-	8,30	61,65
24.1-LIH	-	-	-	-	22,97	-	-	-	-	22,97
24.2-LIST	-	-	-	-	4,50	12,00	-	-	-	16,50
24.3-UniLU	-	-	-	15,90	-	-	2,00	2,00	-	19,90
25-RIVM	4,80	0,50	2,00	-	13,40	52,75	-	19,13	-	92,58
25.1-KWR	-	-	-	3,05	-	3,72	-	-	-	6,77
25.2-TNO	-	-	-	0,50	-	8,18	6,00	-	-	14,68
25.3-RUMC	-	-	-	5,98	-	6,00	-	-	-	11,98
25.4-UL-LACDR	-	-	-	-	46,70	23,30	22,00	1,90	-	93,90
25.5-UU-IRAS	-	-	-	2,92	25,00	22,57	-	-	-	50,49
25.6-VUA	-	-	-	15,75	7,00	0,50	-	1,00	-	24,25
25.7-WR	-	-	-	13,58	9,60	7,85	1,30	30,26	6,00	68,59
25.8-WU-TOX	-	-	-	-	6,60	24,00	-	0,90	-	31,50
26-NIPH	1,20	1,00	1,00	12,95	46,00	23,20	2,00	-	1,90	89,25
26.1-IMR	-	-	-	-	7,50	-	-	-	-	7,50
26.2-STAMI	-	1,00	3,30	4,85	20,00	24,40	-	-	5,00	58,55
26.3-NILU	-	2,50	-	3,30	6,00	2,50	-	5,00	-	19,30
26.4-NIVA	0,60	-	-	-	13,00	9,35	5,50	1,00	-	29,45
26.5-NMBU	-	-	-	1,06	4,00	-	-	0,30	-	5,36

26.6-NVI	-	-	-	-	12,00	-	-	-	-	12,00
26.7-UNN	-	-	-	0,25	-	-	-	-	1,00	1,25
27-NIOM	2,60	3,00	1,50	10,63	-	12,49	-	-	-	30,22
27.1-IEP-NRI	-	-	-	-	21,40	19,60	-	-	-	41,00
27.2-UG-PL	-	-	-	6,40	19,10	15,47	4,10	4,00	-	49,07
27.3-WULS-SGGW	-	-	-	7,75	-	-	-	-	-	7,75
28-FMUL	-	-	4,62	-	-	5,00	-	1,70	4,50	15,82
28.1-PL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
28.2-UM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
29-INSA	6,00	15,00	35,70	9,05	34,20	14,25	-	-	16,52	130,72
29.1-APA	1,00	-	3,50	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,50
29.2-DGS	-	1,00	-	-	-	-	-	1,00	-	2,00
29.3-ENSP	-	5,60	3,00	2,00	-	5,32	-	-	5,00	20,92
29.4-UC	-	-	-	-	-	17,80	-	-	-	17,80
29.5-UAVR	-	-	2,50	-	7,00	14,10	-	-	2,80	26,40
30-SZU-SK	3,10	1,00	1,00	4,00	-	-	-	-	3,70	12,80
30.1-UK	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,20	1,20
31-JSI	0,50	0,72	1,50	34,20	7,00	26,00	29,95	-	2,94	102,81
31.1-GeoZS	-	-	-	-	-	8,20	-	-	-	8,20
31.2-NIB	-	-	7,00	-	34,00	-	-	-	-	41,00
31.3-NIC	-	-	1,50	-	36,00	-	-	11,73	-	49,23
31.4-ULFFA	-	-	-	8,75	12,00	-	-	-	1,00	21,75
31.5-MFUM	-	-	-	-	0,28	-	-	-	-	0,28
32-NIJZ	4,50	2,00	5,50	11,70	-	18,00	6,00	-	1,50	49,20

32.1-OI	-	-	-	-	-	6,00	-	-	-	6,00
32.2-NLZOH	-	-	-	-	-	0,10	-	-	-	0,10
32.3-ARSO	-	-	-	7,00	-	-	-	-	-	7,00
32.4-UKCMB	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
33-CSIC	-	-	-	30,35	-	64,00	-	2,00	12,50	108,85
33.1-ULPGC	-	-	-	0,39	-	-	-	-	-	0,39
33.2-UNAV	-	-	-	-	32,00	-	-	-	-	32,00
33.3-UGR	-	-	-	30,00	-	8,00	-	-	-	38,00
33.4-UPO	-	-	-	-	16,00	-	-	-	-	16,00
34-ISCIII	4,80	0,50	2,00	34,40	49,00	22,00	-	-	33,72	146,42
34.1-EASP	-	-	-	7,35	-	0,50	-	-	-	7,85
34.2-FISABIO	-	-	-	3,75	-	-	-	-	2,00	5,75
34.3-FINBA	-	-	-	-	-	9,60	-	-	-	9,60
34.4-FNS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,80	3,80
34.5-IISPV	-	-	-	1,00	53,50	36,50	30,00	6,20	-	127,20
34.6-INSST	-	-	-	4,50	-	-	-	2,00	-	6,50
34.7-UCLM	-	-	-	5,50	-	34,50	-	-	-	40,00
34.8-UPV/EHU	-	-	-	5,00	-	-	-	-	-	5,00
35-SEPA	1,20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,20
35.1-UGOT	-	-	-	-	-	25,20	-	-	-	25,20
35.2-KI	-	-	-	-	1,00	10,50	6,00	-	3,50	21,00

35.3- ULUND	-	-	-	4,25	-	2,48	-	-	-	6,73
35.4- ORU	-	-	-	12,50	-	-	-	15,00	-	27,50
35.5- RISE	-	-	-	-	-	12,00	-	-	-	12,00
35.6-SU	-	-	-	9,20	7,50	54,00	-	-	-	70,70
35.7- KEMI	3,00	-	1,00	-	-	16,60	-	-	-	20,60
35.8- IVL	0,20	-	-	9,00	-	10,70	-	8,20	-	28,10
35.9- SLV	1,00	-	1,00	-	-	-	-	-	-	2,00
35.10- SLU	-	-	-	29,00	34,00	20,00	-	25,00	-	108,00
35.11- UMU	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16,95	-	16,95
35.12- UU	-	-	-	-	31,00	-	5,00	6,00	-	42,00
36- AUTH	6,05	-	4,50	6,37	19,60	46,00	7,70	66,50	3,20	159,92
36.1- EFET	-	-	5,50	4,10	-	-	-	5,00	-	14,60
36.2- GCSL	3,00	5,00	19,00	1,00	-	-	-	10,00	3,05	41,05
36.3- NKUA	-	-	10,20	39,49	-	-	-	12,10	-	61,79
36.4- UOC	-	-	7,90	7,70	-	-	-	17,50	-	33,10
37-BPI	-	-	6,50	11,85	44,30	42,50	-	-	3,70	108,85
38- FOPH	-	-	1,00	1,00	-	1,00	-	-	-	3,00
39- AGROS COPE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
40- UNISA NTE	-	-	-	8,00	-	16,00	-	-	-	24,00
41- EAWA G	-	-	-	29,30	23,00	13,25	-	-	-	65,55
42- ETHZ	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
43- EMPA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12,50	-	12,50

44-FOEN	-	-	-	-	-	5,00	-	-	-	5,00
45-USI	-	-	-	6,20	-	3,00	-	-	-	9,20
46-UNIBAS	-	-	-	-	-	23,00	-	-	-	23,00
47-SECO	-	-	-	0,20	-	-	-	-	-	0,20
48-ECHA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,00
49-EFSA	-	5,00	-	-	-	4,00	2,00	-	-	11,00
50-UKHSA	2,00	-	2,00	4,50	3,00	3,00	-	-	1,00	15,50
51-BUL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,73	-	1,73
52-Cefas-Defra	-	1,00	-	-	25,28	17,27	-	0,71	-	44,26
53-UKCEH	-	-	-	9,00	-	9,70	-	-	-	18,70
54-EA	-	-	-	1,50	0,50	0,50	-	0,79	-	3,29
55-HSE	-	-	-	4,00	-	-	-	-	-	4,00
56-IOM	-	-	-	1,14	-	-	-	-	-	1,14
57-UBAH	-	-	-	3,00	-	-	-	-	-	3,00
58-UNIABDN	-	-	-	0,46	0,30	-	-	-	-	0,76
59-UOB	3,00	9,00	1,00	-	18,00	13,50	15,00	-	-	59,50
60-UCL	-	-	-	-	-	3,00	-	-	-	3,00
61-EPA	1,20	-	-	3,00	-	-	-	-	-	4,20
61.1-DCU	-	-	-	3,00	-	-	-	-	-	3,00
61.2-UCD	-	-	-	3,67	-	-	-	-	-	3,67
Total PMs	215,02	137,63	195,74	1432,63	1947,05	1669,95	358,02	407,26	260,68	6623,98

Table 2.3.e: Other major cost items (travel, equipment, infrastructure, goods and services)

1 - ANSES	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	32 000	Equipment costs for an incubator CO2 as part of project P5.1.1.a_Y1

Other Goods, Works & Services	32 000	Web tools for on-line conferences/meetings, project management tools, tools for internal communication (documents share, storage etc.)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	306 158	
Total	370 158	
1.2 - INRAE	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	50 000	Consumables and labelled molecules as part of project P5.1.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	104 800	
Total	154 800	
1.3 - CEA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	16 800	Consumables as part of project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 620	
Total	27 420	
1.4 - INERIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	35 319	Cellular models, test items, cell culture consumables (medium, flasks) as part of project P5.3.4.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	89 905	
Total	119 224	
1.5 - CNRS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 000	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 6 meetings as part of project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	6 000	Consumables as part of project P4.2.1.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	29 570	
Total	41 570	
1.6 - INRS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	24 500	Laboratory consumables including for HMRS analysis and other goods as part of projects P4.1.1.4.c_Y1, P4.3.1.b_Y1, P4.3.1.d_Y1, P4.3.2.b_Y2, P5.1.1.a_Y1, P5.1.1.b_Y1, and P6.2.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	25 750	
Total	50 250	
3 - EAA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 940	Consumables as part of project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (HBM survey)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	19 540	
Total	28 480	
3.2 - AIT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	15 000	As part of project P5.2.1.e_Y1 : Consumables for stem cell media, growth factors, coating reagents, HPLC analysis, antibodies, qPCR, high-throughput qPCR chips, Western blot reagents, DNA-methylation EPIC arrays, cell culture plastics, spheroid chips
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 590	
Total	16 590	
3.4 - MUI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	50 335	Consumables as part experiments in project P5.2.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	47 820	
Total	98 155	
3.6 – UG-AT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	4 600	Chemical consumables for analysis as part of project P4.3.3.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 500	
Total	6 100	
3.9- UNIVIE	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	14 000	Consumables for project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	49 770	
Total	63 770	
4 - VITO	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	150 000	Storage, CPU/GPU-computing infrastructure as part of task 7.2 focusing on FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	241 235	
Total	391 235	
4.4 - PIH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence as part of project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 600	

Total	6 660	
4.7 - UAntwerpen	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	11 137	Chemicals, purchase and maintenance of zebrafish transgenic lines, plastic consumables for zebrafish embryo exposures, kits and products for molecular and biochemical analyses, consumables for zebrafish housing, maintenance of zebrafish housing as part of project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	89 024	
Total	100 161	
5.3 - VUB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 400	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 2 meetings as part of project P6.1.1.c_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 000	Running costs and consumables related to experiments in project P6.1.1.c_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	42 350	
Total	74 750	
6 - CIPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend GSB and NHCP meetings
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	1 660	
6.1 - IMROH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 950	Travel and subsistence for: - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (1 660€) - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting in WP7 (2 400€) - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP9 (1 890€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	6 780	
7 – MOH-CY / SGL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 550	Travel and subsistence to attend consortium meetings: - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP1 (2 490€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (1 060€)
Equipment	2 000	Equipment for occupational study as part of project P4.1.1.4.d_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	31 940	Consumables and communication materials for occupational study as part of project P4.1.1.4.d_Y1 (3 000€) and consumables as part of project P6.2.3.a_Y1 (5 500€) Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM surveys as part of task 4.1 (23 440€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 270	

Costs)		
Total	43 760	
7.1 - SHSO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 560	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend one meeting in WP4 (1 060€) and travel related to surveys as part of task 4.1 (500€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 000	HBM surveys under task 4.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	4 560	
8.1 – SZU-CZ	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for: 6. 1 person to attend 1 consortium meeting in WP1 (830€) 7. 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	18 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	230	
Total	20 830	
8.2 - VSCHT	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 000	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 6 meetings as part of project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 820	
Total	11 820	
8.3 - OU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend WP4 annual meeting
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	830	
8.4 - JU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 490	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings as part of project P4.3.3.a_Y1 (1 660€) and for 1 person to attend 1 meeting for task 4.1 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 500	Consumables for analysis as part of project P4.3.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	500	
Total	5 490	
9 - UZIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 622	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 consortium meetings in WP7 (1 422€) and for 1 person to attend 2 National

		Hub Contact Points meetings in WP1 (1 200€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 622	
10 - DEPA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 490	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 490	
10.2 - DTU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	160 000	Costs related to experimentation as part of project P5.2.1.c_Y1 focusing on endocrine disruptors and thyroid hormone disruption
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 824	
Total	172 824	
10.3 - REGIONH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	18 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 840	
Total	28 780	
10.4 - UCPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	22 500	SFC-MS analyses (10 000€) and GCxGC-MS analyses (12 500€) as part of project P4.3.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	14 990	
Total	37 490	
11 - HB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 780	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend to meetings in WP1 (1 660€) and 1 person to attend 2 consortium meetings in WP2 (2 120€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	3 780	
11.1 - SOM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meetings in WP1 (830€) and 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 950	
11.2 - UT	Cost (€)	Justification

Other Goods, Works & Services	18 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 560	
Total	25 500	
13 - THL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	1 060	
13.1 - SYKE	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	29 000	Costs for analyses as part of project P4.2.1.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 900	
Total	47 900	
14.1 - FFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 000	Publications costs related to task 4.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 060	
Total	10 060	
14.2 - Tukes	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 200	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting as part of project P6.4.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 200	
Total	2 400	
14.3 - UOULU	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	2 500	Equipment cost for sampling for activities in task 4.3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 300	
Total	4 800	
15.6 - KUM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	15 000	Lab chemicals, tips, tubes, microsampling devices (VAMS, DBS), Instrument consumables (argon, sample cups), etc. related to project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 320	
Total	19 320	
16 - BfR	Cost (€)	Justification

Other Goods, Works & Services	20 250	Consumables for analyses as part of projects P5.1.1.a_Y1 (12 250€) and P5.2.1.c_Y1 (8 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	148 487	
Total	168 737	
16.1 - Fraunhofer	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	21 500	Consumables for analyses as part of projects P4.2.1.b_Y2 (15 000€) and P5.1.1.a_Y1 (6 500€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	41 055	
Total	62 555	
16.2 - KIT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 500	Consumables for project P5.3.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	8 500	
Total	16 000	
16.3 - IUF	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	40 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	42 120	
Total	82 120	
16.4 - IfADO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	12 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 000	
Total	24 000	
16.6 - UKL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	13 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	810	
Total	13 810	
16.7 - TUB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	27 294	Consumables costs in task 5.1: Reagents, chemicals, HPLC columns, solvents for chromatography, columns for combiflash, glass material, plastic material
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	27 294	

16.8 - UKON	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 700	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1: reagents for toxicological test and reagents for cell culture (hPSC)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 060	
Total	26 760	
16.9 - TiHo	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1: Cell culture medium for stem cell culture, Cell culture plastic ware, cell culture medium additives, antibodies, chemicals
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 720	
Total	22 720	
17 - NPHC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	76 264	Reagents, consumables, kits, cell culture as part of project P5.2.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	24 080	
Total	100 344	
18 - UI	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend a 2 days meetings as part of project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	16 101	
Total	17 161	
19 - MOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 120	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend WP4 annual meeting and for 1 person to attend a 2 days meeting as part of project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	18 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 245	
Total	22 305	
20 - ISS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	45 000	Consumables related to project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	70 780	
Total	115 780	
20.5 - UMIL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	40 000	Consumables for project P5.1.1.b_Y1: Chemicals, antibodies, ELISA kits, cell culture medium and supplements, buffy coats,

		etc
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 613	
Total	41 613	
20.6 – DPH-UNINA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP1
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 357	Publications costs as WP8 co-leader
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	3 320	
Total	11 627	
21 - RSU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	37 440	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (28 940€) Consumables for sample collection and storage of biological and industrial hygiene samples as part of project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1 (5 500€) Publications fees as part of project P6.3.2.a_Y1 (3 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 166	
Total	57 606	
21.1 - UL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	695	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to 1 meeting for project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	700	Consumables (reagents, tubes, micropipette tips, microfilters) as part of project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 220	
Total	2 615	
22 - NPHSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 670	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 6 meetings in WP9 (5 670€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 720	
Total	8 390	
23 - LSMU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence for: - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (1 890€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 400	

Costs)		
Total	17 290	
24.1 - LIH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	32 937	Consumables related to project P5.2.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	32 937	
25 - RIVM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	50 000	Costs for the organisation of workshops (15 000€) and publication fees (5 000€) as part of project P6.1.1.a_Y1 Consumables for project P6.1.1.b_Y1 (30 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	109 320	
Total	159 320	
25.3 - RUMC	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	4 500	Costs for 3x Handheld breath testers of 1500 EURO for exhaled air analysis of ethanol as part of project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 580	
Total	23 080	
25.4 – UL-LACDR	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	100 000	Costs for microscopy, culture facility, flow cytometry, sequencing for projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 (37 500€), P5.3.1.a_Y1 (15 000€), P6.1.1.c_Y1 (23 750€) and P6.1.1.d_Y1 (23 750€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	47 000	Costs for Cell culture, molecular biology, microscopy, transcriptomics, chemicals, disposables, plastics for projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 (47 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	91 810	
Total	238 810	
25.7 - WR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 190	Consumables for project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	80 019	
Total	105 209	
26 - NIPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	63 940	Costs for natural toxins and kits for project P5.1.1.a_Y1 (20 000€) and consumables and analyses for project P5.2.1.d_Y1 (25 000€), and consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (18 940€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	110 191	

Costs)		
Total	174 131	
26.2 - STAMI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	12 000	Lab consumables as part of project P6.1.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	72 030	
Total	84 030	
26.3 - NILU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 000	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings as part of project P5.2.1.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 000	Consumables as part of project P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	27 900	
Total	37 900	
26.5 - NMBU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 830	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP5 (3 000€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP8 (2 000€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Costs for analyses as part of project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 500	
Total	21 330	
26.6 - NVI	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting as part of project P5.1.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	15 000	
Total	16 060	
27 - NIOM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 940	Consumables for projects P4.1.1.4.d_Y1 (2 000€), consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (8 940€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 560	
Total	31 500	
27.1 – IEP-NRI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	32 000	Costs for laboratory materials, reagents and services as part of WP5 including project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	19 304	

Costs)		
Total	51 304	
27.2 – UG-PL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP7.
Other Goods, Works & Services	27 400	Purchase of reagents, organisms for biotests, analytical standards of investigated chemicals, laboratory accessories such as e. g. pipette tips, well plates and microplates for (eco)toxicological tests or other usable laboratory accessories for projects P4.3.3.a_Y1 and P5.1.2.b_Y1 (16 400€) Purchase of reagents, analytical standards of investigated chemicals, solvents for extraction and final analysis using LC-MS/MS or LC-HR-MS technique, laboratory accessories, passive samplers or other sorbents for analyte extraction, purification and concentration such as i.e. SPE columns, LC chromatographic columns, other usable spare part for project P4.2.1.e_Y1 (11 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	19 370	
Total	48 430	
27.3 – WULS-SGGW	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	7 000	Computer for data processing as part of project P4.3.3.a_Y1 (2 000€) and SPE extraction system as part of P4.3.1.b_Y1 (5 000€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	34 190	Consumables and standards, solvents, reagents, services for projects P4.1.1.a.d_Y2, P4.3.1.b_Y1, P4.3.2.b_Y2, P4.3.3.a_Y1, and P4.3.4.a_Y2 Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (8 940€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	7 510	
Total	48 700	
28 - FMUL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 070	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 720	
Total	7 790	
29 - INSA	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	25 000	Laboratory equipment for implementation of project P5.1.1.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	106 490	Purchase of consumables, laboratory materials, reagents, kits, and toxins as part of projects P4.1.1.4.d_Y1, P5.1.1.a_Y1, P5.1.1.b_Y1, P5.2.1.d_Y1 (34 550€)

		Costs for the organisation of SYNnet forum meeting, WP3 annual meeting, International board meeting including teleconference costs (30 000€) Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (28 940€) Organisation of training sessions as part of task 9.4 (13 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	96 915	
Total	228 405	
29.2 - DGS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 920	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (900€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP8 (1 900€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 000	Consumables for WP8
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	9920	
29.3 - ENSP	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 600	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP6
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 530	
Total	16 130	
29.4 - UC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	7 000	Travel and subsistence for fieldwork as part of projects P6.4.4.c_Y1 and P6.4.4.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 960	
Total	16 960	
30 – SZU-SK	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 390	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP4 (3 780€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP9 (3 550€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 150	
Total	21 480	
30.1 - UK	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 890	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9 (1 890€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	1 890	
31 - JSI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	79 790	
Total	88 730	
31.1 - GeoZS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 000	Costs for lab analysis and sample shipment as part of project P6.2.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 120	
Total	7 120	
31.2 - NIB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	52 150	Consumables such as plastic ware, chemicals, media for growth of bacteria and cell cultures, maintenance of fish, food for fish, S9 mix, specific antibodies, preamplification kits, assays for qPCR, etc. as part of projects P5.1.1.a_Y1, P5.1.2.b_Y1, and P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	14 840	
Total	66 990	
31.3 - NIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 700	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP1 (1 700€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP3 (2 000€)
Equipment	2 600	Equipment costs for projects P5.1.2.b_Y1, P8.1.2.a_Y1 and P8.3.2.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 783	Consumables for project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	23 451	
Total	37 534	
31.4 – UL FFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	35 500	Consumables for projects P4.2.1.a_Y1, P4.2.1.b_Y1, P5.1.1b_Y1, and P5.2.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 160	
Total	45 660	
32.2 - NLZOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and	2 400	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP6

subsistence		
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 400	
32.3 - ARSO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 500	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 500	
Total	3 000	
33 – CSIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	72 000	Costs for consumables as part of projects P4.2.1.b_Y2, P6.2.1_b_Y1, 6.2.2.a_Y1, and P6.2.3.a_Y1: solvents, reagents, standards, glassware and supplies of mass spectrometry and chromatography
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	71 371	
Total	143 371	
33.1 - ULP GC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	830	
33.2 - UNAV	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	54 000	Consumables and natural toxins for assays as part of projects P5.1.1.a_Y1 and P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 830	
Total	56 830	
33.3 - UGR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Consumables as part of project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	29 900	
Total	39 900	
33.4 - UPO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	55 090	Consumables (Reagents, plasticware, etc) for project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 660	
Total	56 750	

34 - ISCIH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 880	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 5 meetings as part of WP1
Other Goods, Works & Services	46 940	Reagents and consumables related to projects P4.3.2.a_Y1, P5.1.1.b_Y1, P5.2.1.c_Y1 (38 000€) Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (8 940€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	92 150	
Total	143 970	
34.2 - FISABIO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 000	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 3 meetings in WP6
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 790	
Total	8 790	
34.3 – FINBA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings for project P6.2.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 830	
Total	7 490	
34.5 - IISPV	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	9 000	Consumables as part of project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	109 290	
Total	118 290	
34.6 - INSST	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 360	Travel and subsistence for: - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting for project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP8 (4 240€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Consumables (vials for urine collection, solvents for analysis by Gas-Chromatography, cooler box to keep samples, shipping costs of posting samples) and use of equipment (HS-GC-FID, TD-GC-FID) for project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	3 020	
Total	19 380	
34.8 – UPV/EHU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase	2 720	

costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	6 660	
35.3 - ULUND	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 400	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 510	
Total	7 910	
35.7- KEMI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 000	Costs for the organisation of meetings related to task 6.3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	25 091	
Total	30 091	
35.10 - SLU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	65 220	Consumables for analysis and sampling as part of projects P4.3.3.a Y1 (42 500€), and P5.1.2.b Y1 (22 720€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	95 335	
Total	160 555	
35.12 - UU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	63 000	Consumables including cell painting for project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	41 048	
Total	104 048	
36.1 - EFET	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 000	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 3 meetings in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 830	
Total	12 830	
36.2 - GCSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	31 270	<p>Travel and subsistence for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP1 (2 600€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 5 meetings in WP3 (4 110€) <p>Costs for travel and subsistence for participants to attend Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings, and SYNNet Forum meetings (22 440€)</p>
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 650	Costs for the organisation of Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings and of SYNnet Forum meetings in

		WP3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	24 480	
Total	76 400	
36.3 - NKUA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	64 000	Consumables related to project P4.2.1.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	15 320	
Total	79 320	
37 - BPI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	114 600	Consumables including for in vitro testing, molecular biology, lab materials, chemicals etc. for projects P5.1.1.a_Y1 (41 400€), P5.1.2.b_Y1 (63 200€), and P6.1.1.b_Y1 (10 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	50 720	
Total	165 320	
61.1 - DCU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 000	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 1 meeting for P4.2.1.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 400	LC-MS consumables for project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 000	
Total	7 400	

Table 2.3.f: Overview of planned budget per project and per Work Package

Please note that the Total Y2 budget for a Work Package is based on the provisional budget submitted by each partner for their planned involvement in projects and transversal activities in Year 2.

Work Package 4

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y2	% Budget allocated for Y2 / total WP budget allocated for Y2	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	11 722 774.80	83.17%	36 815 910.98		31.17%
P4.1.1.2.a_Y1	985 918.19	6.99%	5 486 899.73		4.65%
P4.1.1.4.a_Y1	24 964.64	0.18%	81 238.12		0.07%
P4.1.1.4.b_Y1	61 233.75	0.43%	251 504.88		0.21%
P4.1.1.4.c_Y1	242 500.49	1.72%	662 326.26		0.56%
P4.1.1.4.d_Y1	339 859.64	2.41%	994 294.66		0.84%
P4.1.3.1.a_Y1	309 195.00	2.19%	1 718 427.94		1.45%
P4.1.3.3.a_Y1	674 399.97	4.78%	2 556 044.89		2.16%
P4.1.4.2.a_Y1	541 529.99	3.84%	1 502 796.27		1.27%
P4.1.5.a_Y1	127 735.06	0.91%	650 512.44		0.55%
P4.2.1.a_Y1	3 420 298.19	24.27%	7 829 699.86		6.63%
P4.2.1.b_Y2	1 310 357.22	9.30%	2 337 985.49		1.98%
P4.3.1.a_Y1	-	-	265 302.63		0.22%
P4.3.1.b_Y1	295 052.80	2.09%	718 334.93		0.61%
P4.3.1.c_Y1	94 343.23	0.67%	428 558.11		0.36%
P4.3.1.d_Y1	323 900.76	2.30%	1 386 822.18		1.17%
P4.3.2.a_Y1	967 258.51	6.86%	3 341 686.47		2.83%
P4.3.2.b_Y2	245 709.95	1.74%	1 061 158.46		0.90%
P4.3.3.a_Y1	994 396.99	7.05%	2 858 788.63		2.42%
P4.3.3.b_Y2	320 731.43	2.28%	1 262 748.10		1.07%
P4.3.4.a_Y2	443 388.98	3.15%	1 420 780.94		1.20%
Transversal activities	2 372 417.78	16.83%	13 191 035.40		11.17%
Task 4.1	2 023 344.60	14.35%	10 775 148.41		9.12%
Task 4.2	273 952.30	1.94%	2 003 757.83		1.70%
Task 4.3	75 120.88	0.53%	412 129.16		0.35%
TOTAL WP4	14 095 192.59	100.00%	50 006 946.38	118 124 452.00	42.33%

Work Package 5

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y2	% Budget allocated for Y2 / total WP budget allocated for Y2	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total WP Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
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Projects	15 638 894.68	90.97%	50 471 575.69	52.25%	
P5.1.1.a_Y1	1 878 003.23	10.92%	5 073 419.64	5.25%	
P5.1.1.b_Y1	1 104 568.13	6.43%	2 848 689.18	2.95%	
P5.1.2.a_Y1	173 104.38	1.01%	501 413.84	0.52%	
P5.1.2.b_Y1	2 317 332.12	13.48%	8 763 093.91	9.07%	
P5.2.1.a_Y1	1 512 484.50	8.80%	6 526 763.69	6.76%	
P5.2.1.b_Y1	1 182 004.66	6.88%	3 461 276.36	3.58%	
P5.2.1.c_Y1	1 169 975.63	6.81%	3 544 752.38	3.67%	
P5.2.1.d_Y1	1 516 111.34	8.82%	3 884 608.04	4.02%	
P5.2.1.e_Y1	1 564 430.18	9.10%	5 630 487.99	5.83%	
P5.3.1.a_Y1	991 357.80	5.77%	3 586 760.89	3.71%	
P5.3.2.a_Y1	1 100 518.87	6.40%	3 412 358.37	3.53%	
P5.3.4.a_Y1	1 129 003.86	6.57%	3 237 951.41	3.35%	
Transversal activities	1 552 610.16	9.03%	10 267 424.11	10.63%	
Task 5.1	720 301.37	4.19%	4 317 615.98	4.47%	
Task 5.2	543 301.84	3.16%	3 789 645.37	3.92%	
Task 5.3	289 006.94	1.68%	2 160 162.76	2.24%	
TOTAL WP5	17 191 504.84	100.00%	60 738 999.80	96 602 616.00	62.88%

Work Package 6

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y2	% Budget allocated for Y2 / total WP budget allocated for Y2	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total WP allocated Budget / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	12 844 211.70	94.16%	46 976 538.78		64.02%
P6.1.1.a_Y1	424 313.19	3.11%	1 239 617.16		1.69%
P6.1.1.b_Y1	913 750.06	6.70%	2 353 130.88		3.21%
P6.1.1.c_Y1	1 051 171.14	7.71%	2 803 642.52		3.82%
P6.1.1.d_Y1	476 837.40	3.50%	1 485 878.05		2.02%
P6.2.1.a_Y1	363 787.70	2.67%	1 055 911.99		1.44%
P6.2.1.b_Y1	1 085 834.34	7.96%	3 697 979.52		5.04%
P6.2.2.a_Y1	1 004 681.20	7.37%	2 920 162.47		3.98%
P6.2.3.a_Y1	1 982 202.00	14.53%	7 953 531.03		10.84%
P6.2.4.a_Y1	345 505.42	2.53%	2 378 959.32		3.24%
P6.2.4.b_Y1	462 711.90	3.39%	3 337 102.15		4.55%
P6.2.4.c_Y1	234 202.61	1.72%	1 508 242.00		2.06%
P6.2.4.d_Y1	165 939.97	1.22%	1 044 324.19		1.42%
P6.3.1.a_Y1	236 865.00	1.74%	1 485 405.00		2.02%
P6.3.1.b_Y1	584 875.62	4.29%	1 960 703.10		2.67%
P6.3.2.a_Y1	794 164.64	5.82%	1 782 280.16		2.43%
P6.4.1.a_Y1	491 476.11	3.60%	1 218 214.36		1.66%
P6.4.1.b_Y1	233 427.88	1.71%	651 191.00		0.89%

P6.4.2.a_Y1	88 637.56	0.65%	225 291.58		0.31%
P6.4.2.b_Y1	162 225.19	1.19%	445 885.56		0.61%
P6.4.2.c_Y1	135 767.63	1.00%	385 203.69		0.52%
P6.4.3.a_Y1	285 729.38	2.09%	803 677.50		1.10%
P6.4.4.a_Y1	233 395.11	1.71%	1 241 485.27		1.69%
P6.4.4.b_Y1	231 468.86	1.70%	1 389 390.84		1.89%
P6.4.4.c_Y1	231 562.45	1.70%	1 074 869.32		1.46%
P6.4.4.d_Y1	217 442.20	1.59%	930 853.21		1.27%
P6.4.4.e_Y1	406 237.15	2.98%	1 603 606.92		2.19%
Transversal activities	795 976.32	5.84%	7 650 115.06		10.43%
Task 6.1	214 732.50	1.57%	1 869 156.69		2.55%
Task 6.2	69 458.28	0.51%	1 597 601.47		2.18%
Task 6.3	105 656.94	0.77%	774 617.55		1.06%
Task 6.4	406 128.60	2.98%	3 408 739.35		4.65%
TOTAL WP6	13 640 188.02	100.00%	54 626 653.84	73 379 540.00	74.44%

Work Package 7

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y2	% Budget allocated for Y2 / total WP budget allocated for Y2	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total WP allocated Budget / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	1 553 890.78	43.51%	4 833 954.09		22.08%
P7.2.2.a_Y1	751 940.80	21.06%	2 089 805.05		9.55%
P7.2.2.b_Y1	561 153.04	15.71%	1 814 565.88		8.29%
P7.3.3.a_Y1	240 796.94	6.74%	929 583.16		4.25%
Transversal activities	2 017 363.22	56.49%	7 286 033.49		33.28%
Task 7.1	311 848.87	8.73%	1 275 818.67		5.83%
Task 7.2	929 989.67	26.04%	2 997 166.62		13.69%
Task 7.3	775 524.68	21.72%	3 013 048.19		13.76%
TOTAL WP7	3 571 254.00	100.00%	12 119 987.58	21 889 938.00	55.37%

Annex I AWP Y2

1- AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA SECURITE SANITAIRE DE L'ALIMENTATION DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET DU TRAVAIL, FRANCE (ANSES) – PIC : 983552356

During the second year, ANSES will be involved in WP1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9.

WP4

In Task 4.2, ANSES (LHN) could be involved in analytical measurements for the PFAS project, depending on environmental compartments collected and compounds requested.

In Task 4.3, ANSES will lead the project P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02-Other complementary studies_ANSES dedicated to complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples. Anses will also contribute to task 4.3 regarding food packaging. Through the P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02, Anses will participate in the project on sentinel animal species. ANSES will also strongly participate to Data Processing Workflow (task 4.3.1).

WP5

In Task 5.1 ANSES will contribute to fill in the data gaps on mycotoxins. Experiments on absorption and metabolism using in vitro assays are planned. A review on the data available for the kinetic endpoints for enniatins and Alternaria toxins will be delivered.

In Task 5.2 ANSES will be involved in the activities on non-genotoxic carcinogens and the development of NAMs for their detection. In vitro experiments on liver HepaRG cells to investigate various toxicological endpoints (viability, proliferation, apoptosis, oxidative stress, inflammation) after acute and repeated exposure for some selected compounds will be performed. Both High Content Analysis and qPCR will be used.

In Task 5.3 ANSES will begin some work on IVIVE for enniatins.

WP6

ANSES will lead the Task 6.2 and the two projects P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES and P6.2.3_Y1_RealLifeMixtures dedicated to develop methods, tools, case studies and organize data around exposures to multiple sources, routes and chemical mixtures. Anses will be involved into the 6 others projects of this Task in proposing developments and concrete case studies for source-to-dose, PBPK models, and health impact assessment.

In WP7 and WP9, ANSES will participate to the meetings and to collaborative outcomes, including for WP9: Laboratory networking (9.1.), Building exposure monitoring capacities (9.2), QA/QC activities for chemical methods in harmonization purpose (9.3.2), Joint activities - Harmonisation (9.3.) and training (9.4).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
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1. ANSES: ANSES will subcontract RNA sequencing as part of project P5.2.1.a_Y1 focusing on non-genotoxic carcinogens, and binding and partitioning operations as part of project P5.1.1.a_Y1 studying exposure to natural toxins.

1.1 INSERM: INSERM will subcontract electric field pulse motor response tests within the implementation of project P5.2.1.e_Y1 for neurotoxicity.

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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1.1 INSERM – PIC 999997833

During the second year, INSERM will be involved in WP 2.3, 4.1.3, 4.2.4, 5.2a, 5.3.1, 5.3.2, 5.3.3, 5.3.4, 6.1.1, 6.1.2, 6.3, 7.3.3, 8.2.1, 8.2.2, 8.2.3, 9.2.1. Four different labs are involved, JRU 1211, U1194, UMR-S 1124, UMR1085

UMR-S 1124

In WP2, Inserm U1124 teams will be involved in Task 2.3 on sustainability in coordination with WP9 Activity 9.2.1. The goal is to analyze the survey carried out in Y1 and identify the main fields to be sustained.

In WP5, Inserm U1124 teams will be involved in Activity 5.2.1 in the activities concerning the NAM development in “immunotoxicity” and in “Non GenoToXic Carcinogen”. INSERM is Leader of the “immunotoxicity” activity. For NGTXC activity, the work will be made in close collaboration with UMR1085. It will analyse the modifications of cell properties leading to migration or invasion processes by real-time analyses using lab set-up. It aims at identify and characterise biomarkers likely linked with genomic or epigenetic disruption after exposure. For immunotoxicity, UMRS-1124 will participate in the subproject 2: immunosuppression and response to vaccination after PFAS exposure by using several in vitro and in vivo model (influenza response modification, cytokine response...). Part of this activity will also be made by UMR 996 taking advantage of its expertise in skin sensitivity for immunotoxic response. The aim is to ultimately develop NAMs reflecting the response to vaccination which is critical for the regulatory framework (eg PFAS)

In WP5, Inserm is a co-leader of task 5.3. The Inserm teams will be also involved in Activities 5.3.1 & 5.3.3 regarding the systems toxicology project, and in Activity 5.3.2 for the AOP project (in collaboration with UMR 1085 and U1133), where Inserm is co-leading the CG (Core group), and is involved in the Speciality Group SG1 (Immunotox subgroup / leading NGTXC sub-group), SG2 (endocrine and metabolic disruption) and SG3 (neurodevelopmental toxicity). In A5.3.2, during year 2, we will continue to develop AOP-helpFinder that allows to automatically explore the literature, and help to construct and complete AOPs in SGs.

In WP6, the teams will be involved in Activities 6.1.1 for IATA, 6.1.2 for uncertainty analysis, as well as 6.3 where we will perform text mining for case studies 17 & 18. In WP7, the teams will be involved in Activity 7.3.3 for case studies and tools development. In WP8, the teams will be involved in Activities 8.2.1, 8.2.2 and 8.2.3 for development of models and tools based on artificial intelligence that will support early warnings based on the literature. We co-lead the Activity 8.2.3.

U1211

In WP5, Inserm U1211 is inserted into the collaborative effort within Task 5.2.a. which consists in developing an in vitro battery by the combined use of cell cultures, organoids and zebrafish embryos. JRU 1211 contributes to the development and assembly of functional/behavioral (developmental) neurotoxicity tests using zebrafish early development stages. During the second year, JRU 1211 will continue to optimize the EFP MRT method. In addition, it will screen the molecules selected by the consortium. These molecules concern positive and negative controls and molecules of interest for neurotoxicity, in particular of environmental origin.

U1194

IN WP5, U1194 will contribute to T5.2a to characterise by biochemical, cellular and in silico methods the interactions between bisphenols and their analogues with the nuclear receptors using well-characterised and recognised homemade in vitro tests. Also, in WP4, the team will be involved in Activity 4.2.4 by performing measurement of nuclear receptor activities of environmental samples.

UMR1085

In WP2.3 and WP9, UMR1085 will contribute to sustainability activities and as contact.

In WP5, the team will be involved in Tasks 5.2 related to new innovative methodologies in the assessment of epigenicity, transgenerational effects, and immunotoxicity in collaboration with U1124 team. The second year will also be dedicated to the BRB-seq experiments in collaboration with DTU (DK). Then, it will contribute to quantitative system toxicology in the development of AOP based on

system biology in collaboration with U1124 (A.5.3.2.), and in the characterisation of the impact and predictivity of in vitro ADME parameters for PBPK modeling by studying pollutants effects towards activities of main regulatory transporters for PBPK modeling (A5.3.4). Finally, UMR1085 will continue the integration of multi-omics datasets by implementing bio-informatics tools (A.5.3.3).

1.2 INRAE – PIC 999993274

During the second year, INRAE will contribute to WP4 (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3), WP5 (T5.1, T5.2), WP6 (T6.1, T6.2, T6.4), WP8 (T8.2) and WP9 (T9.3, T9.4).

In T4.1, INRAE will contribute to the design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies in particular with regard to the conditions of implementation of innovative sampling methods, and to the data analysis in particular through advanced statistical models for relying exposure and health.

In T4.2, INRAE will contribute to the next steps of the review of existing knowledge on EDCs and PFAs as core team member, to the initial thoughts on the design of the monitoring campaign and to work on the prioritisation framework.

In T4.3, INRAE will contribute through the co-lead of this task, and through a practical implication in all projects developed under this task that rely to the development and application of innovative methodological approaches including high resolution mass spectrometry based suspect and non-targeted screening.

In T5.1, INRAE will contribute to address gaps of knowledge related to bisphenols, with a major emphasis on metabolism (bioactivation), endocrine disruption and DNT (T5.1a).

In T5.2, INRAE will contribute to the development of NAMs on Non-Genotoxic Carcinogenicity and co-leads Project Tasks on NGC and Metabolic Disruption.

In T6.1, INRAE will contribute to the development of a IATA for genotoxicity and will co-lead the related project.

In T6.2, INRAE will contribute to PBPK modelling activities aiming to provide full life exposure estimates and trajectories from external and internal exposure data.

In T6.4 INRAE will contribute to the risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity, especially through a collaborative project with OFB on modelling pesticides impacts at the landscape scale.

In T8.2, INRAE will contribute to the usefulness of the generated data for early warning system.

In T9.3, INRAE will contribute to the definition of appropriate QA/QC criteria and provisions for data generated from innovative methods.

In T9.4, INRAE will contribute to the identification and realisation of selected training activities.

1.3 CEA – PIC 999993274

During the second year, CEA will be involved in WP4 (Task 4.1 & 4.3)

In Task 4.1, CEA-JOLIOT will have a modest contribution to A4.1.2 dealing with laboratory analysis and QA/QC.

In Task 4.3, CEA-JOLIOT will take part to the project 4.3_H01. The team will contribute to the development of innovative sampling methods and LC-HRMS based approaches for the non-targeted screening (NTS) of samples within the perinatal exposure study (H01). It will actively participate to the sample analysis process including sample extraction, sample global profiling (NTS) using LC-HRMS, targeted complementary analysis and data processing of the collected analytical data.

Still in Task 4.3, CEA-SyMMES will be involved in the following task in P4.3.4.b_Y2_F02 Other complementary studies_ANSES. CEA-SYMMES will develop new monitoring methods and tools based on electronic nose technology for multiple exposures (environmental, food, and others) and for emerging chemicals: e.g., non-targeted/suspect screening approaches and effect-based monitoring. In particular, CEA-SyMMES will design novel specific peptides as ligands (via phage display, virtual screening, etc.) for such applications and evaluate the performance in order to obtain significant improvement in sensitivity and selectivity.

1.4 INERIS – PIC 999958063

During the second year, INERIS will be involved in WP 4.2, 4.3, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 6.4, 8.1, 8.3, 9.1 and 9.3.

In WP4, Ineris is co-leading Task 4.2 and in charge with AU of the 2 projects of the activity 4.2.1: the establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors and Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring. Ineris will focus on the design of the pilot study on EDC and the EDA strategy. Ineris will also contribute to a project on task 4.3, activity 4.3.3 which aims at mining information on contaminants of emerging concern in urban waste water and how suspect or non-target screening (SS/NTS) and effect directed analysis (EDA) approaches can be useful (P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH).

Ineris will be involved in WP5, activity 5.1.2b on the development of NAMs (in silico and modelling tools) for hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and mixtures.

In WP6, Ineris will participate to two projects of Task 6.2, in the activity 6.2.2: the refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment (P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS_AUTH) and mixtures (in collaboration with activity 6.2.3, P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM). In the first project, based on the inventory made in year 1, the refinement of existing PBPK models and the development of new ones will be started. The objectives will be to be able to deliver PBPK models for compounds for which no models are available yet (e.g., some mycotoxins), for exposure routes that are not implemented yet (e.g., inhalation and dermal contact for PFAS), for sensitive populations (e.g., lead in the developing fetus), and for target organs (e.g., detailed description of the blood-brain barrier for metals and bisphenols). Different sources of data will be used for the model parametrization and evaluation: either from literature, or from newly generated data in PARC (e.g., in WP5). Meanwhile, case studies will be set up by defining the regulatory framework and identifying the cohort data to be analyzed. The progress of the models' development and the description of the case studies will be reported in a deliverable (first set of PBPK models for lifetime exposures and description of the case studies). In the mixtures project, the parametrization of the models for the mixtures of interest will be pursued. The first applications of PBPK models to perform forward and reverse dosimetry will be performed for the prioritized mixtures using data provided by the WG1 of the mixtures project.

The project P6.3.2.d_Y1_CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS on secondary poisoning of activity 6.3.2d will continue. In task 6.4, Ineris has proposed a new project in the activity 6.4.4 on biodiversity on a Risk Indicator For Chemicals In Terrestrial Ecosystems.

In WP8, Ineris will contribute in the implementation of PBPK models in the modelling platforms (T8.3) and on the (8.1).

In WP9, Ineris will contribute as a member of the French Reference Laboratory in support of aquatic environment monitoring. It will be involved in the development of catalogue of laboratory networks in environmental monitoring (T9.1) and in the inventory of existing methods and guidance on sampling (notably for water) and QA/QC criteria for chemical methods and bioassays in environmental monitoring (T9.3).

1.5 CNRS – PIC 999997930

During the second year, CNRS-SyMMES will be involved in the following task in P4.3.4.b_Y2_F02 Other complementary studies_ANSES.

CNRS-SYMMES will develop new monitoring methods and tools based on electronic nose technology for multiple exposures (environmental, food, and others) and for emerging chemicals: e.g., non-targeted/suspect screening approaches and effect-based monitoring. In particular, CNRS-SyMMES will design novel specific peptides as ligands (via phage display, virtual screening, etc.) for such applications and evaluate the performance in order to obtain significant improvement in sensitivity and selectivity.

1.6 INRS – PIC 998626835

During the second year, INRS will be involved in WP 4.1, 4.3, 5.1, 6.2 and 7.3.

In Task 4.1, INRS teams will contribute in the occupational study in health care sector, by the development of the design (study plan, SOPs, questionnaire, ethics aspect, data analysis,), the application of ethical authorization, the recruitment of companies and workers and the sample collection. We will also continue the work on the feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general survey. INRS will be involved in the planning of the statistical analysis for data that will be generated within occupational studies in Task 4.1.

In Task 4.3, INRS will lead the project dedicated to innovative method in occupational studies P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS, in establishing a common strategic workplan linked to occupational studies performed under WP 4.1. Innovative sampling methods as DBS, VAMS, wristbands and dust will be studied in this project. In parallel, different working groups will be created to exchange, harmonize and elaborate a common SOPs for 1) innovative sampling, 2) analysis of innovative samples with conventional methods, and 3) innovative HRMS based / EDA screening methods using SS/NTS/EDA approaches. INRS will also participate to the projects on QA/QC criteria and data processing workflow.

In Task 5.1, INRS will perform transactivation in vitro assays to detect estrogen receptor agonistic or antagonistic effect of selected members of alternaria and enniatin mycotoxin families following OECD test guideline TG 455 using the stably transfected hER α -HeLa-9903 cell line. INRS will also contribute to review papers on the toxicity of these mycotoxin families. If the proposal is accepted, INRS will contribute to the assessment of the toxicity of bisphenol family members and perform in vitro cell transformation assays on selected chemicals.

In Task 6.2, INRS will contribute to the inventories of exposure models and data. INRS will be involved in activities planned on case studies with a focus on bisphenols by applying approaches to account for multiple sources and routes of exposure in workers.

INRS will work in Task 7.3 on implementing innovative approaches for the analysis of heterogeneous data.

1.7 ONIRIS – PIC 986014022

During Y2, ONIRIS will contribute to WP4 (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3), WP6 (T6.2) and WP9 (T9.1, T9.2, T9.3 and T9.4).

In T4.1, ONIRIS will lead the QA/QC working group in relation with targeted analysis for human biomonitoring. In T4.2, ONIRIS will be involved in both projects related to endocrine disruptors and PFAS, including contributing to the respective inventories, writing a review article on PFAS methods and preparing further monitoring campaigns. In T4.3, ONIRIS will launch and coordinate one of the projects (E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS) and be partner of others (T03, F01 and F02). In T6.2 ONIRIS will continue contributing to pharmacokinetic modelling.

In T9.1 and T9.2, ONIRIS will contribute to the mapping of labs and proposals for future structuring. In T9.3, ONIRIS will co-lead a working group dedicated to reporting/data acceptance for standardisation purposes. In T9.4, ONIRIS will contribute to identifying needs and formulating training proposals.

1.8 IRSN – PIC: 999480726

During Y2, IRSN will contribute to WP6 (T6.1) and WP5 (T5.2).

In T6.1, IRSN will contribute to the mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs, selection of regulatory frameworks and population groups, development of AOP networks for genotoxicity and will participate to the project “Human Relevance”.

In T5.2, IRSN will contribute to the mapping of existing knowledge for the development of AOP on neurotoxicity.

1.9 OFB – PIC 894000307

During Year 2, OFB will maintain its implication in WP 4.2, 4.3 and 6.4.4.

With regard to WP4.2, OFB intends to be involved in the organisation and implementation of the monitoring campaign scheduled in the framework of the endocrine disruptors (EDC) case study, focusing notably on surface waters, in line with the ongoing French national strategy on EDCs. OFB would focus on pesticides that act as endocrine disruptors, in view of their further consideration within the biodiversity protection oriented WP6.4.4 projects.

Regarding WP 4.3, OFB intends to be involved in the selection of sentinel species through the project P4.3.3.b_E02, promoting the use of innovative monitoring techniques for the assessment and early warning on chemicals' impacts affecting biodiversity.

In the framework of WP 6.4.4, OFB aims at supporting the Landscape environmental risk assessment developments of agricultural pesticides, contributing to the assessment of the feasibility of coupling pesticide exposure models with chemical monitoring in sentinel species.

1.10 BRGM – PIC 999993662

During the second year, BRGM will be involved in WP 4.2, 4.3, 7.1, 7.2, 9.1, 9.3, 9.4.

In WP4, BRGM teams will continue its activities in Task 4.2 to support the preparation of the monitoring campaigns for the two selected case studies i.e., projects PFAS and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds. The team will bring its analytical expertise on water matrix and more particularly on groundwater but also on monitoring and knowledge of substances properties. In Task 4.3, BRGM will contribute to suspect and non-targeted screening approaches consideration (activities 4.3.3 and 4.3.4) for environmental monitoring (projects 4.3.3.a and 4.3.1.c) and will contribute in the elaboration of a consensual inventory of method performance and QA/QC criteria for HRMS (activity 4.3.5).

In WP7, BRGM team involved in task 7.1 will contribute to the FAIR data policy for PARC and participate to the identification of cases. BRGM will work on PARC FAIR data platform, harmonization and standards and on targeted solutions for FAIR data (T7.2. activities 7.2.2, 7.2.3 and 7.2.4).

In WP9, BRGM will contribute in the development of catalogue of laboratory networks in environmental monitoring (T9.1), in the inventory of existing methods and guidance on sampling (notably for water) and QA/QC criteria for chemical methods in environmental monitoring (T9.3) and the identification of needs for training (T9.4)

1.11 LNE – PIC 998801144

LNE will be involved in WP4 and WP9.

In WP4, LNE will contribute to WP4.3 and more specifically to the project P4.3.1_T02 on QA/QC issues for non-target screening, suspect screening and EDA, in relation with WP9.3. LNE will also contribute to WP4.1 activities dealing with quality and comparability of the analytical HBM data as well as new QA/QC approaches to support the use of innovative techniques in HBM surveys in PARC.

In WP9, LNE will contribute to

- WP9.1 and more particularly to the activity 9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of laboratory networks.
- WP9.2 for mapping of exposure monitoring capacities
- WP9.3 on QA/QC issues. LNE will co-lead two activities: 9.3.1 on sampling, with a particular focus on uncertainty arising from sampling, and 9.3.3 on PT and CRMs.
- WP9.4 on identification of training needs as well as the inventory of existing training courses and programmes

LNE will act as contact person for Euramet and EMN (European Metrology Network) dedicated to environmental pollution (POLMO) as inputs for WP9 activities.

1.12 CSTB – PIC 999580151

During the second year, CSTB will be involved in WP4 and WP6.

Within Task 4.2, CSTB will contribute to the development of the prioritisation scheme (P4.2.1_2). The possibility to use the data and available samples from the IAQ Observatory will be shared with the partners (P4.2.a). CSTB will contribute to the design of the case-study for sampling and analysis QA/QC

(Activity 4.2.3).

In WP6, CSTB will contribute to activity 6.2.1, which includes two projects: the source-to-dose modelling project and the aggregate exposure project. CSTB will mainly participate in (1) developing inventories of source-to-dose models and data, (2) identifying the gaps for further model developments under the framework of PARC, and (3) case studies of the models.

1.13 EHESP – PIC 998161429

During the second year, EHESP will be involved in T1.4, 4.1, 4.3 and 6.2.

In WP1, EHESP will pursue the co-leading of the task related to ethics frameworks (T.1.4.) and will contribute to the construction and the organisation of the process that will ensure the monitoring of the PARC actions with regard to ethical considerations.

In T4.1, EHESP will work on improving and harmonizing conventional analytical methods used in biomonitoring (e.g., definition of the best suited exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC, implementation of QA-QC activities). In T4.3, EHESP will continue to be involved as a project leader to develop a data processing workflow (T04) to help implement innovative suspect screening and non-targeted methods for human, environmental and food monitoring. In T4.3, EHESP will also be contributing to harmonize (T01) and develop QA/QC for these innovative methods (T02), as well as contribute to the perinatal exposure study (H01).

Finally, EHESP will contribute to the Mixture project in A6.2.3. by participating in WG2 (hazard characterization). Briefly EHESP will contribute to the development of an approach to use health-based guidance values in the mixture risk assessment procedure based on case-studies about prioritised compounds (i.e. pesticides, PFAS).

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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2- AGENCE NATIONALE DE SANTE PUBLIQUE, FRANCE (SpF) – PIC 917843489

During the second year, SpF will be involved in WP 1, 2, 3, 4, and 9 with a major contribution in the WP4 - Monitoring and Exposure activities as a coleader.

In WP1, SpF is involved in Task 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4. SpF will be participating in the overall scientific steering including all activities involving the National Hubs (T1.2) and support the development of the PARC monitoring framework and impact indicators in T1.3. SpF will act as representative of WP4 for the Data and Ethics Protection Board and participate in the discussions related to the Ethics framework (T 1.4).

In WP2, SpF will continue to play its role as French national hub contact point and participate in the sustainability activities, both in the mapping of the needs of the National Hubs as well as in PARC’s exit strategy (T2.3).

In WP3, SpF is involved as a WP4 co-leader in Task 3.2 activities related to communication, dissemination and synergies.

In WP4, SpF organizes and coordinates WP4 co-leaders meeting and task force meetings for general management and steering of the different tasks (T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3).

Within 4.1, SpF will continue to be involved in the design and implementation of the general population survey and will start with the preparatory work for the PARC aligned studies, planning its participation through the new French nutrition and biomonitoring survey. SpF will continue to provide support to the T4.1 leaders in the coordination of the sub-activity 4.1.1.1- Development of supporting materials for the HBM surveys.

SpF will also participate in the development of the targeted surveys and will have a relative contribution in Occupational surveys and in 4.1.4 - Data management and analysis (including activities further exploring the HBM4EU data and their statistical analysis) and 4.1.5 (Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe).

SpF is a project leader of an ongoing project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO

in which a new approach will be explored in the second year. This approach will consist of a feasibility study that will explore the use of archived (stored in biobanks) samples previously collected in cohorts to quantify past exposures and link them to effect biomarkers and health outcomes.

In WP9, SpF will have a small role in T9.2 (Building exposure monitoring capacities). As a WP4 contact point, SpF will facilitate a two-way communication between WP4 and WP9 safeguarding the connection of activities related to the catalogue of human biomonitoring (HBM) and population cohort studies and WP4 particularly T4.1 Human Biomonitoring).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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3- UMWELTBUNDESAMT GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG, AUSTRIA: Environment Agency Austria: (EAA) – PIC 999452014

During the second year, EAA will be involved in WP1, 2, 3, 4 and 6.

In WP1 EAA will be involved as Work package Co leader of WP2, as Grant Signatory and National Hub Contact Point.

In WP2 EAA will be, besides co-leading the WP, involved as a partner in all 3 tasks: T2.1, T2.2 and T2.3. This includes being project contact point and performing project reviews in T2.1. and co-development of PARC/NGRAroute with specific focus on the environmental part in T2.2 and contribute to the sustainability/exit strategy in T2.3.

In WP3, A3.1.1, EAA is responsible for the establishment and organization of the Stakeholder Forum, including the organisation of annual meetings and consultations, partner meetings and the organisation of the work. EAA will also contribute to 3.2 and 3.3.

In Task T4.1. EAA will continue to contribute to preparatory work for the surveys (A4.1.1a.) and effect biomarkers, specifically for PFAS (A4.1.3.3). Within WP4 EAA will also start with the preparatory work for the PARC aligned studies, planned is to participate with a children cohort. EAA could also contribute to method development and harmonisation specifically for PFAS analyses, as EAA has profound knowledge as Chemical group lead in HBM4EU and chemical analyses in various human and environmental matrices including analyses of sum parameters (Total Oxidisable Precursor (TOP), Absorbable Organic Fluorine (AOF), Extractable Organic Fluorine (EOF) besides target analyses.

EAA will further contribute with its knowledge in regulatory risk assessment to WP6: The EAA will participate in case study 18 (T6.3.6) and will provide information on NAMs already applied in the field of REACH and the Biocide Assessment. The main focus will be on read-across examples and will cover human health and environment. Further EAA will contribute within A6.4.2 to project 1: Facilitate the regulatory acceptance & use of NAMs, phase two: Gaps & needs analysis and action plan.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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3.1 AGES – PIC 998254743

During the second year, AGES will be involved in WP 6 (T6.4) and WP 3 (T3.1a and T3.2)

In WP 6, AGES is co-task lead in 6.4 and is involved in coordinating the task 6.4 "Transposing results to risk assessment methodologies", in particular the activity "6.4.1 – Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessments and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures". In 6.4.1, AGES will be involved in two Projects (P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_UGot and P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ), where we will be involved in creating and evaluating a questionnaire and a literature review about NAMS and mixtures but also in case studies to compare the available mixture tools with the MAF.

In WP3, AGES will be involved in task 3.1.a and 3.2. AGES main responsibility is to support the work in task "Establishment and running of Stakeholder Forum (SF)" and "Communication, dissemination and awareness" by creating and evaluating questionnaires.

3.2 AIT - PIC 999584128

During the second year, AIT will be involved in WP5 in A5.2.1, in which AIT will develop and evaluate blood-brain barrier assays for their application in developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) as well as acute neurotoxicity (ANT). Permeability data of selected compounds are also planned to be provided for WP5 Task 5.3. to support the development of kinetic models.

3.3 BNN – PIC 966278305

During the second year, BNN will be involved in WP8 in Task 8.1 on "Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design" and related activities, namely in Activity 8.1.1 "Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalization". Therefore, BNN will contribute to conduct selected expert interviews and support to create specific surveys, ensuring a strong link to the IRISS project activities.

3.4 MUI – PIC 999855437

During the second year, MUI will be involved in WP4 (T4.1 and T4.3), WP5 (T5.1, 5.2, 5.3), and WP6 (A6.1.1, A6.3.2).

In Task 4.1, MUI will be involved in the working group on reference analytical methods.

In Task 4.3, MUI will be involved in the projects E01, H01, H02, T02, T03, and T04.

In E01, MUI will contribute to the creation and validation of a toolbox with innovative methods and tools for monitoring wastewater influent and effluent samples. The toolbox will be used to characterize the community wide exposure to chemicals of concern as well as to assess the release of chemicals of concern to the water cycle.

In H01 and H02, MUI will be involved in the elaboration, validation, and application of workflows for the analysis of samples collected with low-invasive methods (i.e., dried blood samples).

In T02, MUI will provide input for the harmonisation of quality control and quality assurance requirements in non-target analysis.

In T03, MUI will contribute to the development of a conceptual framework for sampling and suspect/non-target analysis tools supporting early warning systems.

In T04, MUI will contribute to the establishment of advanced data processing tools with a special emphasis on the development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library through the collaborative generation of MS/MS reference spectra.

In A5.1.1, MUI will contribute to the investigations of the immune response modulation by target BPA alternatives focusing on key immunobiochemical pathway activities in peripheral blood mononuclear cell (PBMC).

In A5.2.1 (NAMs Human Health), 5.3.1 (Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard) and 5.3.2 (AOP development), MUI will contribute with a NAM for respiratory sensitization in 5.2.1 based on human cell line-derived epithelial immune cocultures and an in house developed exposure platform for gaseous

exposure and applying transcriptomics as well as focused metabolite/protein-based readouts. Experiments will be performed in close collaboration with RIVM, NPHC and LIST and toluene diisocyanate (TDI) will be the preferred compound for model validation.

In project P5.1.2b BPA alternatives_BPI_MU, MUI will contribute to the improvement of the acute aquatic neuro-toxicity assessment procedure based on existing interspecies variability data.

MUI will be co-lead of in the Specialty Group for immunotoxicology (SG1) being responsible for the respiratory toxicology part in 5.3.2 working the use of NAMs for AOP development and contributes in the effect marker group. MUI will have a minor (crosslinking) activity in 5.3.1.

In project P6.1.1.c IATA_Gentox: MUI will be contributing to the uncertainty assessment of NAM based IATAs for genotoxicity, which will be developed within this work package.

In project P6.3.2e SusChemControl, MUI will summarize possible approaches for improving the sustainability of current regulatory procedures of chemical biocides and pesticides, by a parallel assessment of non-chemical alternatives i.e., bioprotectants and IPM.

3.5 MUW – PIC 999989976

MUW will be involved in WP4 (Task 4.1: Human Biomonitoring). In A4.1.1.1. additional supporting materials are to be developed in relation to the preservation and storage of samples collected in the HBM surveys. These include harmonization of questionnaire types and/or use of the Foodex2 system, opportunities for digitization to collect dietary exposure information, use of materials such as (dynamic) informed consent forms, and materials to support reporting of personal results to participants.

3.6 UG-AT – PIC 999873188

During the second year, UG-AT will be involved in A4.3.3.b Tissues from sentinel animals (stranded pilot whales in the North Sea) will be collected and analysed for their EOF and targeted PFAS.

3.7 UIBK – PIC 999869114

During the second year, UIBK will be involved in WP5.2 and WP5.3. In WP5.2 (T5.2a), UIBK will be involved in the development of in vitro assays capable of detecting compounds that are involved in disruption of non-hepatic metabolic signaling. Herein, signaling pathways and molecules under investigation will be insulin signaling, MTOR signaling, and PPAR γ signaling (selection). In WP5.3, UIBK will participate in the systems toxicology project (A5.3.1), the establishment of new AOPs and the expansion of existing AOPs (A5.3.2) and the development of PBK models and the combination with AOPs (A5.3.4).

3.8 UMIT – PIC 999898408

UMIT will be involved in WP3, Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness; and UMIT will be involved in WP9, Task 9.4: Training.

3.9 UNIVIE – PIC 999866883

During the second year, UNIVIE will be involved in WP4 (T4.1, T4.3), WP5 (T5.1, T5.3), and WP9 (T9.3).

In T4.1, UNIVIE will participate in the team that will work on defining QA/QC criteria and general guidelines that will enable the harmonization of the innovative methods that will be developed during the PARC project. Within the same working group, UNIVIE will further contribute to the identification and potential set up of reference analytical methods.

In T4.3, high resolution mass spectrometry will be applied to human matrices (blood, urine, milk) for suspect screening and non-targeted screening, with a special focus on perinatal exposure.

In T5.1, UNIVIE and BfR are task leaders for the activity to close data gaps for natural toxins. Within this activity UNIVIE will investigate *in vitro* the immunotoxic effects of natural toxins (*Alternaria* mycotoxins and enniatins), in order to close existing knowledge gaps.

In T5.3, UNIVIE will participate in the development of AOPs (immunosuppression, endocrine

disruptive activity) that will be based on the integration of *in vivo*, *in vitro* and *in silico* data. Additionally, UNIVIE will perform *in vitro* toxicokinetic studies on *Alternaria* toxins and contribute to the construction of PBK models that will help to identify points of departure. In T9.3, UNIVIE plans to be involved in the activities for data harmonization, focusing on LOD/LOQ criteria and performance parameters, i.e., calibration and matrix effects, as well as recovery and precision. In addition, reporting requirements, specifically normalization criteria in blood and urine, will be addressed.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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4- VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V., BELGIUM (VITO) – PIC: 999645238

During the second year, VITO will be involved in WP 1, 3, 4, 6, 7 and 8.

In WP1, VITO is involved in Task 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4. VITO is GS and manages seven AEs. VITO is WP7 co-leader and MB member and participates in monthly MB meetings. In T1.3, VITO supports the development of the PARC monitoring framework and related output, outcome and impact indicators.

In WP3, VITO is involved as a WP7 co-leader in Task 3.2 activities related to communication, dissemination and synergies.

In WP4, VITO is involved in Task 4.1, Task 4.2 and Task 4.3 and will also safeguard the connections between these three tasks.

VITO is T4.1 *Human biomonitoring* co-leader and attends regular WP4 task force meetings, organizes T4.1 co-leader meetings for general management and steering of the task, and T4.1 project leader meetings.

VITO is also leading several sub-activities in T4.1 i.e., 4.1.1 (Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies, including the design of targeted HBM studies to be initiated from PARC year 3 onwards), 4.1.3.2 (Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes), 4.1.4 (Data management and analysis, including management of the data management helpdesk and statistical working group), 4.1.5 (Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe).

VITO is project leader of three ongoing projects under T4.1:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO (in which VITO coordinates the design, planning, and implementation of the PARC Aligned Studies, including add ons related to evaluation of exposure sources and routes, implementation of innovative sampling and analytical methods, and measurement of effect biomarkers);
- P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO;
- P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO;

and deputy project leader of P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO.

In T4.2, VITO will continue its contribution to P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU with respect to design of the PFAS and EDC monitoring campaigns, participation in the statistical working group and project reporting, and sharing relevant expertise and data with the project partners.

In P4.2.1_2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS, VITO will participate in workshops and in development of the prioritisation framework.

In T4.3, VITO will continue its modest participation in P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE and will contribute to the preparations for P4.3.2.c_H03 Complementary developments to establish links and information exchange with T4.1. In P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH, VITO is a core group member for method development and proof of concept for high-throughput EDA.

In WP6, VITO is involved in Task 6.2.

VITO is T6.2 *Integrative exposure and risk assessment* co-leader and attends regular WP6 task force meetings and organizes T6.2 co-leader meetings for general management and steering of the task, and T6.2 project leader meetings.

VITO is project leader of P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO, in which we will further develop conceptual source-to-dose models and apply these in case studies. VITO is also a partner in the closely related P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES project; here we will participate in case studies specific for the general population and for which performing aggregate exposure is relevant.

In P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS_AUTH, VITO contributes to application of (adapted) PBK models for assessment of multi-route exposure.

In P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM, VITO participates in WG1 to identify risk drivers in real life mixtures based on analysis of human biomonitoring data, in WG2 for mixture risk assessment based on health-based thresholds for internal exposure to groups of chemicals using hazard data, and in WG3 for risk assessment for external exposure using kinetic modeling.

VITO is also co-leader of activity 6.2.4 on health impact assessment, project leader of P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO and P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO, and deputy project leader of P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS and P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS. In these projects, VITO will contribute to derivation of population specific exposure levels and exposure-effect associations for PARC priority chemicals, reduction of uncertainty on exposure-effect relations by development of a Weight of Evidence approach for selection of exposure-effect functions and by incorporation of effect biomarker data, performance of case studies, and development of risk and health impact indicators.

VITO is WP7 co-leader and T7.2 (Data libraries) co-leader and participates in T7.1 (FAIR Data policy and implementation) and T7.3 (Innovation for data analysis and uncertainty). VITO organizes regular WP, Task and project leader meetings.

In T7.1 VITO will contribute to elaboration of the Data Policy (7.1.1) and will lead the management of the use case selection and implementation process (7.1.3). In T7.2 VITO will transversally contribute to all 4 activities: further elaboration of the PARC data landscape, related to the use cases, identified in year 1, in which VITO will be involved; practical elaboration and implementation of the PARC FAIR data hub; developing FIPs and roadmaps for concrete use cases identified in year 1 or in the course of year 2, and practical implementation of the roadmaps; development of (meta)data schemas, vocabularies and ontologies. VITO is project leader for P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO, and deputy project leader for P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO. In this project VITO will technically improve and operate the HBM data sharing platform, and contribute to elaboration of solutions for FAIR and sustainable storage, access and reuse of HBM datasets. In T7.3 VITO will co-lead activity 7.3.1 and work on the 7.3.1 case studies that are defined in the course of year 1.

In WP8, VITO will have a small role in T8.2 (Early Warning Systems) to apply of Effect Direct Analysis as an early warning tool, also connecting this to related activities in T4.3, and to plan case studies in relation to Tasks 4.1. In T8.3 (Integrative models) VITO will contribute to the linkage of HBM data collections to modelling platforms, ontology-based model harmonization, and focus group meetings on integrated modelling platforms and cross cutting issues, thereby safeguarding the connection of these activities to T6.2 and WP7.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
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As foreseen in the GA, an expert in setting up data FAIRification processes, i.e., Go FAIR Foundation, has been subcontracted starting from M5 for a period of 24 months.

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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4.1 KU Leuven – PIC 999991334

During the second year, the unit Epigenetic Epidemiology at KU Leuven will be involved in T5.3. This team will take a co-Coordinator role in A5.3.2 Effect Markers. Next to a literature search it is the objective to integrate knowledge on epigenetic toxicity into the AOP framework of the PARC project. This team has proven expertise in human studies related to epigenetic effects. A key output includes identification of a (new) set of epigenetic biomarkers in the male germ line, that are associated with exposures to environmental chemicals. To reach this goal, year 2 will be used to resume current knowledge regarding effects from environmental pollutants on the epigenome, affecting human health. We will explore the literature and identify data sets present within PARC. This participation will benefit other partners -of WP4, WP5 and WP6- as well, and contribute to the investigation of potential novel biomarkers of biological response in human, which will follow in the next years.

4.2 DOMG – PIC 999575107

During the second year, dOMG will be coordinate task 1.3 where the initial monitoring frame and first set of indicators will be further refined to ensure the key useful and impact-generating results and relevant target groups are clearly identified in order to maximise PARC’s impact and exploitation. In WP2, dOMG will be involved in Task 2.3 on sustainability in coordination with WP9 Task 9.2.1 and task 3.2 on communication to integrate it with task 1.3
DOMG is the national hub contact point for Belgium

4.3 UH – PIC 999874934

During the second year, the Data Science Institute of Hasselt University (UH) will be involved in WP 4, Task 4.1. UH will be involved in the statistical working group (sub-activity 4.1.4) and as such contribute to 4.1.1 (Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct, general population HBM survey, Targeted HBM surveys) and 4.1.4 (Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU, Analysis of the data generated within PARC)

4.4 PIH – PIC 920268780

During the second year, PIH will be involved in WP4 (T4.1).
In A4.1.1, PIH will be involved in the design of the general survey and the preparation of the supporting materials such as informed consent forms; questionnaires; innovative materials and tools.
In A4.1.4, PIH will be involved in the data management and analysis, more specifically in the design of the codebooks, hence making the link to T 4.1.1 (questionnaires) and the data management helpdesk.

4.5 OVAM – PIC 954439649

During the second year, OVAM will be involved in WP4 (T4.1 and T4.2).
In T4.2, OVAM will contribute to P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU with respect to design of the PFAS and EDC monitoring campaigns, project reporting, and sharing relevant expertise and data with the project partners, including characterization (target analyses & non target analyses (LC&GC)) of PFAS in soil & groundwater of risk locations and in non-suspect areas (background). In P4.2.1_2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS, OVAM will contribute to the inventory of regulatory needs, participate in workshops and in development of the prioritisation framework.

4.6 ISSeP – PIC 914156228

During the second year, ISSeP will be involved in WP4 (T4.1 and T4.2), WP6 (T6.2 and T6.3), WP7 (T7.2 and T7.3), WP8 (T8.3) and WP9.
In Task 4.1, ISSeP will be involved through the activities related to the initiation of the general surveys and in the HBM4EU follow-up activities in regard to the supporting materials and the exploration of

the HBM data, their statistical analysis, and exposure-effect associations.

In T4.2, ISSeP will support the work in the two case studies, i.e., PFAS and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds, selected for the P4.2.a_Y1_ “ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey”. In the P4.2.1_2_ “Monitoringframe” project, ISSeP will participate in workshops and the development of the prioritisation framework.

In T6.2, ISSeP will be involved in P6.2.1.b “Aggregate exposure” for developing case studies and providing data. Here ISSeP will participate in case studies specific for the general population and for which performing aggregate exposure is relevant. ISSeP will also contribute to the P6.2.4.a “HIA - Data Availability”. In this project, ISSeP will contribute to the exposure data and health data inventories, as well as to the evaluation of possibilities for in-silico modelling of exposures, and to the derivation of population specific exposure levels and exposure-effect associations for PARC priority chemicals.

In T6.3, collaborating with SYKE, a report on the “comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks in risk assessment methodologies under different EU regulatory frameworks” will be drafted.

In WP7, ISSeP will be involved in T7.2 as Data Liaison for the implementation of FAIR data solutions and use cases. Training on FAIR principles will also be received. ISSeP will also contribute to the projects P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO and P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO.

In T8.3, ISSeP will contribute to establish an overarching conceptual model (Activity 8.3.2) in order to implement the models developed under WPs 4, 5, 6 and 8 and data of WP7 in a functional open PARC tools network infrastructure. ISSeP will participate in the creation of accessible web mapping interfaces (accounting for the user requirements derived in Activity 8.3.1).

In WP9, ISSeP will promote the consolidation of laboratory networks and facilitate the coordination and linkage with other present actors (T9.1). ISSeP will also contribute to the inventory of existing methods and guidance on sampling and QA/QC criteria for chemical methods in environmental monitoring (T9.2), notably for water, air and soil.

4.7 UAntwerpen PIC 999902870

During the second year (Y2), UAntwerpen will be involved in WP 4 (T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3), WP 5 (T5.2 and T5.3) and WP 6 (T6.1).

In Task 4.1, the Toxicological Centre of the University of Antwerp (UAntwerpen) will contribute to the definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods. In Task 4.2, the research group ECOSPHERE together with the Toxicological Centre will contribute to support the survey to identify relevant studies on PFAS present in the environment and in biota, selecting and prioritizing relevant PFAS and EDCs, and to design and operate monitoring campaigns for PFAS and EDCs in both the aquatic and the terrestrial environment and generate data to respond to specific regulatory needs. In Task 4.3, the Toxicological Centre will contribute to reviewing and mapping of approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods and tools for monitoring, QA/QC criteria for suspect and non-target screening, and workplans to apply these methodologies to the use of personal samplers and to wastewater-based epidemiology. In particular, most efforts will be related to the involvement in tasks T4.3_E01 (co-lead of activities related to the milestone on development of suspect and non-target screening approaches for wastewater) and T4.3_H01, while limited participation is expected in 2-3 other tasks.

In Task 5.2, Zebrafishlab will continue to participate on the development of non-mammalian innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling in the areas of metabolic disruption (P5.2.1.b), thyroid hormone system disruption (P5.2.1.c) and developmental neurotoxicity (A5.2.2) by investigating zebrafish (embryos) as models. In A5.3.2, Zebrafishlab will continue to contribute to the development of new AOPs and the expansion of existing AOPs. Zebrafishlab will participate in the core group, will co-lead the speciality group 2, focusing on AOP development for THSD, and will contribute to the speciality group 3, focusing on AOP development for neurotoxicity.

In Task 6.1, Zebrafishlab will continue its contribution to the development of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals (IATAs, A6.1.1), and associated case studies (A6.1.2). Zebrafishlab is co-lead of P6.1.1.b, focusing on the development of IATAs for endocrine disruption, specifically THSD and anti-androgenic adverse effects.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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5- SCIENSANO, BELGIUM – PIC 906160809

During the second year, Sciensano will be involved in WP 1, 4, 5, 6 and 9.

In WP1, Sciensano is involved in Task 1.1 as Sciensano is GS and manages three AEs.

In WP4, Sciensano is involved in Task 4.1 and Task 4.2. In Task 4.1, Sciensano leads Activity 4.1.2.5 *Analyse the exposure biomarkers in the samples emerging from human biomonitoring task*. Partner meetings will be organized for steering this task. Additionally, meetings of other activities from 4.1 will be attended. However, the projects related to 4.1.2 and 4.1.3 still need to be defined. Hence, the exact Sciensano's contribution needs to be determined. Part will be related to the inclusion of epigenetic and genetic biomarkers in the survey (eg susceptibility markers, health effect biomarkers). In addition, Sciensano will contribute to the data analysis in Task 4.1.4 (P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO).

Regarding T4.2, Sciensano will continue to participate in the pilot project on PFAS and EDCs (P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU).

In WP5, Sciensano will contribute to Task 5.1 and Task 5.3.

In T5.1, Sciensano will perform *in vitro* genotoxicity tests (e.g., *in vitro* micronucleus test and GENOMARK) with enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins within the context of P5.1.1.a_Y1-Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE.

Sciensano co-leads T5.3 *Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs* and attends regular WP5 task force meetings and T5.3 co-leader meetings for general management and steering of the task.

In addition, Sciensano participates in project meetings of P5.1.1.a_Y1-Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE, P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR, P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm and P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer.

In T5.3, Sciensano will contribute to P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR, more specifically, to the systematic identification and integration of MOA information covering a diversity of MIEs, KEs, biochemical and omics data, using various data sources and to the establishment of novel reference high throughput transcriptomics datasets. In addition, Sciensano will contribute to the activities of the Core Group to harmonize the AOP development process within P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm.

Sciensano will also ensure the link between T5.3 and T6.1 in order to streamline activities and to avoid overlap.

In WP6, Sciensano is involved in Task 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3.

Sciensano co-leads T6.1 *Integrated approaches to testing and assessment* and attends regular WP6 task force meetings, T6.1 co-leader meetings for general management and steering of the task, and organizes project meetings for P6.1.1.a_Y1_IATA_Gentox_Sciensano.

Sciensano is project leader of P6.1.1.a_Y1_IATA_Gentox_Sciensano, in which an IATA for genotoxicity will be developed based on the AOP framework, followed by the evaluation of its applicability through case studies. Sciensano is also a partner in the closely related P6.1.1.a_Y1_IATA_ED_Uantwerpen project; here we will participate in the design of the IATA for thyroid hormone system disruption and/or anti-androgenic activities. Moreover, Sciensano will contribute to the harmonization of the IATA development and the design of the case studies in the

different IATA-related projects.

Sciensano is also involved in Task 6.2, more specifically in activity 6.2.4 on health impact assessment. In T6.2.4, Sciensano contributes to four projects: P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO, P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS, P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS, P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO. In particular, Sciensano will work on health impact assessment, exposure-effect relationships and health data inventories, the development of case studies as well as the improvement of health impact assessment methodologies and indicators, e.g., taking into account socio-economic status.

Within Task 6.3, Sciensano will contribute to P6.3.1.g_Y1_CS13_Plasticizers_UCL by identifying differences and loopholes in the regulation of plastic additives.

In WP9, Sciensano is involved in Task 9.1, 9.2, 9.3 and 9.4.

In T9.1, Sciensano will contribute to P9.1.1.a_Y1_HBM CATALOGUES_ISCIII_MU (9.1.1) and to the project of T9.1.2 (which is not yet defined), by offering expertise in the use of non-invasive samples (urine, saliva) to measure biomarkers (protein biomarkers, genetic biomarkers, epigenetic (miRNA, methylation), microbiome biomarkers), which can be included in the catalogue within the PARC context.

In T9.2, Sciensano will contribute to P9.2.1.a_Y1_ENV CATALOGUES_MU_ISCIII and to the project(s) of T9.2.2 (not yet defined), by investigating/identifying the gap related to epigenetic/genetic markers for exposure assessment, and exploring whether for instance NGS technologies could be used to measure them.

In T9.3, Sciensano will contribute to P9.3.1.a_Y1QAQC_WR regarding generic QA/QC in toxicity studies, bioassays/effect-directed assays (EDA), and toxicokinetic studies.

In T9.4, Sciensano will contribute to T9.4.1, for which no project was defined yet, by identifying the needs to train other scientists in methods for the measurement of epigenetic/genetic biomarkers.

For all these tasks, the partner meetings will be attended.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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5.1 UGENT – PIC 999986096

During the 2nd year, UGent will be involved in WP5 (Task 5.1b, Task 5.3) and in WP6 (Task 6.1).

In Task 5.1b, UGent is leading the P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent and will focus on environmental toxicity testing of natural toxins in year 2 together with UAVR and SLU. This includes toxicity testing with aquatic invertebrates and aquatic natural toxins (primarily algal toxins) to fill current data gaps. Within Task 5.3 UGent is involved in Project 1 on Systems Toxicology and Project 2 on AOPs. Ugent is focussed on environmental risk assessment and bridging gaps between environmental and human risk assessment through systems toxicology and AOP approaches. In year 2, UGent will contribute to the further development of these approaches in the two projects. This includes application of systems toxicology tools such as Weighted Correlation Network Analysis (WGCNA) and other bioinformatic data mining approaches on available high throughput data sets.

Within task 6.1, UGent is involved in IATA's on STOT and ED and specifically will support the design of IATA's and development of AOP networks. Both tasks 5.3 and 6.1 have clear links where 6.1 builds further on knowledge and tools developed in 5.3. In year 2, UGent's contributions of 5.3 in year 1 can be further integrated in 6.1.

5.2 EV-ILVO PIC 998175591

During the second year, EV-ILVO will be involved in WP 2, 4, and 7.

In WP2, EV-ILVO will be involved in Task 2.2, more specifically within PARCopedia.

In WP4, EV-ILVO will be involved in Task 4.2 and Task 4.3. In Task 4.2 involvement is foreseen for A4.2.2, the inventory of existing projects/monitoring studies as well as A4.2.3 preparing the monitoring campaign. In Task 4.3 involvement is foreseen for P4.3.1.a_T01 (Global collective definition and prioritisation of main concepts, approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods undertaken in task 4.3 (inventories, selection/prioritisation, shared knowledge and visions among environmental-food-HBM communities), P4.3.1.b_T02 (Define minimal common QA/QC requirements to be specifically applied for HRMS/EDA based screening approaches applied to environmental/food/human matrices, and to elaborate corresponding technical guidelines) and P4.3.4.b_F02 (Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based / EDA screening methods on food samples (e.g. aquatic species / fish, drinking water, childhood food...)).

In WP7, EV-ILVO will be involved in Task 7.2 and 7.3.

5.3 VUB – PIC 999902094

During the second year, VUB will be involved in WP5 on *Hazard assessment for human and environmental health* and WP6 on *Innovation in regulatory risk assessment*.

In WP5, VUB is co-lead of Task 5.2 concerning *Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling*. VUB is also co-lead of the ongoing project P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU in which it will continue to develop a human stem cell-based *in vitro* model to better understand the mechanisms of action of thyroid hormone disruptors on the developing liver and compare their responses to rodent *in vivo* studies in order to gain improved knowledge on species differences in chemical-induced thyroid hormone disruption.

In WP6, VUB is involved in Task 6.1 on *Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals* and Task 6.3 on *Review of risk assessment methodology*.

In Task 6.1, VUB will continue to participate in the P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX project with the development of AOP networks, design of IATAs based on the AOP networks and NAMs, and the design and execution of case studies.

In Task 6.3, VUB leads the P6.3.1.d_Y1_CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB activity and will continue with the critical analysis of a selection of SCCS risk assessments, and initiate meetings with relevant stakeholders in order to come to recommendations and best practices with respect to the inclusion of NAMs and/or new methodology in the human risk assessment process of substances with potential endocrine disrupting activity. VUB will also contribute to the P6.3.2.h_Y1_CS18_ED-classes_BPI activity concerning the compilation of a database on existing *in vitro* assays, *in silico* tools and read-across approaches for the assessment of endocrine disrupting chemicals with regard to androgen, estrogen, steroidogenesis and thyroid modalities.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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6- HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO, CROATIA (CIPH) – PIC 998128255

During the second year, CIPH will participate, under the coordination of the relevant task leaders, in WP2, WP3, and WP4:

WP3, Task 3.2. CIPH will contribute through cooperation with other partners in development of communication materials, for example newsletter. Relevant communication and dissemination documents will be translated into Croatian language.

CIPH will participate and contribute in development of an open access and publication strategy, activities for awareness raising and a citizens' survey.

WP4, Tasks 4.1. According to previous participation in HBM4EU project and acquired experience, CIPH will contribute in updating and development of supporting materials for general and occupational HBM surveys, review and update of materials developed under HBM4EU, explore and propose solutions for inclusion of novel aspects in HBM studies implementation and identify and address areas of needs/improvements in PARC.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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6.1 IMROH – PIC 998300333

During the second year, IMROH will participate, under the coordination of the relevant task leaders, in WP4, WP6, WP7 and WP9:

WP4: Task 4.1 Human Biomonitoring (4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies; 4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance; 4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information); Task 4.2 Environmental and multisource monitoring (4.2.1 Mechanism for defining targeted environmental and multisource monitoring studies; 4.2.2 Review of existing knowledge and infrastructure; 4.2.3 Design of targeted monitoring activities; 4.2.4 Monitoring activities, including laboratory analysis and QA/QC; 4.2.5 Data analysis and transfer; 4.2.6 Feedback mechanisms); Task 4.3 Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys (4.3.1 Innovative sampling methods / approaches for individual to community exposure assessment; 4.3.2 In vitro / in vivo bioassays for effect-based monitoring and effect-directed analysis (EDA); 4.3.3 Suspect screening approaches; 4.3.4 Non-targeted screening approaches; 4.3.5 QA/QC and innovative screening methods' performances assessment), particularly in QA/QC for metals and PCBs in human biological samples, and, in coordination with CIPH, preliminary HBM targeted study focused on metals and PAHs (depending on funding);

WP6: Task 6.3 Review of risk assessment methodology;

WP7: Task 7.3 Innovative analyses (7.3.1 Integration and analysis of (heterogeneous) FAIR data); more specifically, IMROH will contribute to the scoping review of methods for pooling heterogeneous data for risk assessment;

WP9: Task 9.2 Building exposure monitoring capacities (9.2.1 Mapping of exposure monitoring capacities; 9.2.2 Strengthening of exposure monitoring capacities).

Participation in these tasks includes IMROH's active participation in WP meetings.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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7- Ministry of Health of the Republic of Cyprus, CYPRUS (MOH-CY/SGL) – PIC 994267946

During the second year, MOH-CY/SGL will participate in:

WP1: All activities involving the National Hub (Task 1.2) and the Grand Signatory (Task 1.1)

WP2: Task 2.3 with input to the efforts towards sustainability

WP3: Task 3.1 primarily as NHCP for input towards the development of effective interactions and in Task 3.2 with feedback to the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy plan and assessment of stakeholder's perceptions and concerns.

WP4: A4.1.1 (Design, Alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies: Planning and implementation of the

waste management occupational survey and the general population HBM survey study (on children / adults and possibly also teenagers). Contributions to the planning and implementation of targeted surveys (e.g. on dietary exposures and / or targeting prenatal exposures). Where feasible, HBM surveys will be coupled to health examination for assessment of relationships between exposures /effects on health and to monitoring of sources for identification of contributions of specific environmental compartments to internal exposure levels. For adult participants, we will explore the feasibility of using personal samplers (e.g. silicon wristbands) for optimized characterization of exposures in association with task 4.3.

MOH-CY/SGL will also contribute towards new analyses of HBM4EU data and biobanked samples (e.g. from the HBM4EU-MOM study).

MOH-CY/SGL will also engage in Task 4.1.5 (HBM sustainability)

WP6: A6.2.3 (mixture exposure and risk assessment) under the coordination of the relevant task leaders. Real-life co-exposure observations of mixtures from HBM data across Europe using MCRA. Prioritization of mixtures from co-exposure using HBM data (Pesticides, PFAS, Heavy metals, Mycotoxins).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

7.1 SHSO – PIC 891074787.

In Year 2, the State Health Services Organization (SHSO) will participate in A4.1.1 for the implementation of the general HBM survey. As the largest healthcare provider in Cyprus, with hospitals and health centres in all cities and districts, SHSO intends to engage in activities linked to participants (e.g. preparatory phase, recruitment and sampling, communication of results and possible couplings with health examinations).

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?

Y

In Year 2, the Department of Labour Inspection (DLI) of the Ministry of Labour, Welfare and Social Insurance will engage in the implementation in Cyprus of the occupational survey on waste management under A4.1.1. In the frame of its role as National Authority for Labor Inspection, the DLI will provide assistance regarding the recruitment of waste management companies and their workers, the dissemination and uptake of results into policy.

8- Masarykova univerzita, CZECH REPUBLIC (MU) – PIC 999880657

During the second year, MU will be involved in WPs 2-9. The major contribution will be, in consistence with the first year, to WP7 and WP9, where MU acts as 7.2 co-leader and WP9 co-leader.

In WP2, MU will collaborate on the development of PARCopedia and NGRAroute. MU will also continue to serve as a national hub contact point, coordinating PARC-related activities at the national level. In addition, MU, from the position of WP9 leader, will actively collaborate and communicate with task 2.3 to establish and maintain proper linkages between WP9 outputs (laboratory catalogues, exposure monitoring catalogues, catalogues on training programs, etc.) and PARCopedia, as well as will support interactions between PARC and EIRENE, which MU coordinates.

In WP3, MU will contribute to the development and maintenance of synergies between the various initiatives, including the EIRENE infrastructure.

In WP4, the MU team will be involved in Task 4.1 and will support the activities related to the initiation of the general and occupational surveys (in the healthcare sector) and in the HBM4EU follow-up activities in regard to the further exploration of the existing HBM data, their statistical analysis, and

exposure-effect associations. In Task 4.2, MU will support the further development and implementation of the two selected case studies, i.e., PFAS and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds (EDCs), and will coordinate WP9 actions to allow for effective cross-WP collaboration and harmonization of efforts. In Task 4.3, the MU experts will, following the definition of the conceptual framework for target analysis, non-target analysis, and suspect screening, contribute to the development of proof-of-concept in HBM and environmental monitoring to characterize and narrow gaps between the conventional and innovative approaches.

In WP5, MU will continue leading and implementing the transversal activity on bisphenol alternatives for which data gaps on adverse effects of individual compounds and of mixtures need to be filled.

In WP6, MU will contribute to activities planned under 6.1, 6.2, and 6.4. In 6.1, MU will contribute to the development and refinement of quantitative networks of AOPs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and liver toxicity and to the (re-)designing of regulatory-relevant IATAs for these endpoints.

In 6.2, MU will participate in activities related to aggregated exposure and real-life mixture assessment (in particular 6.2.3), where the expertise of MU experts in various statistical methods and modeling tools will be utilized. In 6.4, MU will continue co-leading the project (6.4.3) on chemicals in articles and focus on completing project deliverables outlining the current screening and enforcement structures for chemicals in articles and how chemical hazards are incorporated in the life-cycle analysis (LCA).

In WP7, MU will continue co-leading task 7.2, and will further elaborate on the use case related to environmental data and data sources in collaboration with task 4.2. MU will focus on developing the FAIR data hub and the proof of concept of the data hub and on making its key activities complementary with other European initiatives (Common Platform for Chemicals - CPCD, European Open Science Cloud - EOSC) ongoing in parallel. MU also will participate in training in FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP) and Metadata 4 Machines, which will result in the development of domain-specific FIPs as well as other tools enabling the implementation of FAIR principles in PARC.

In WP8, MU will support the development and consolidation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design concept, criteria, and available tools and their operationalization (task 8.1) and will contribute to the development and implementation of the conceptual model supporting integrative modeling approaches, including a case study (8.3).

In WP9, MU will continue co-leading WP9 and task 9.2, and will organize and contribute to the enrichment of the pilot catalogues developed in Y1 in collaboration with 9.1 towards including additional domains, such as sediment and water. To do so, MU will co-organize the preparation of surveys and cooperate with WP2 and 3 on their distribution and collection, analyze the collected information, and transport it into the platform allowing for the development of the respective catalogues.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

8.1 SZU-CZ PIC 999478689

In the second project year, the SZU-CZ team will be involved in the WP4, Task 4.1 Human Biomonitoring, contributing to preparatory activities for HBM general population studies, and will continue to work on the development and finishing of harmonized materials. Due to the experience with long-term regular national human biomonitoring of non-professionally exposed population, SZU-CZ will be involved in the activity 4.1.5, contributing to developing and introduction of sustainable HBM monitoring.

8.2 VSCHT – PIC 999867853

During the second year, VSCHT will be involved in WP4 (tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3) and WP9 (tasks 9.1,

9.2, 9.3. and 9.4).

In task 4.1, VSCHT team will support the activities related to laboratory analysis and quality assurance. VSCHT will participate in the group responsible of the definition of the Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) program at EU level to guarantee the quality, accuracy and comparability of the analytical results in this task.

In task 4.2, VSCHT will participate in the activities related to environmental and multisource monitoring addressing PFAS and endocrine disrupting chemicals, i.e., reviewing the existing knowledge and infrastructure and designing monitoring studies and monitoring activities including laboratory analysis and QA/QC.

In task 4.3, which focuses on the development of innovative methods and tools for monitoring and survey, VSCHT will support the activities related to projects proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based/EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal (P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01) and occupational exposure (4.3.2.b_Y2_H02) to chemicals of emerging concern.

In WP9, the VSCHT team will support activities regarding laboratory networking, building exposure and monitoring capacities, harmonization of chemical analysis, and the training part.

8.3 OU – PIC 998738870

During the second year, OU will be involved in WP4, task 4.1: preparing implementation of aspects: effect biomarkers, innovative (sampling) techniques for Human Biomonitoring (HBM), health effects and risk factors related to (accumulated) exposure in the middle-aged population (40-69y), time trends in repeatedly sampled cohorts/regions and/or biobanked samples.

8.4 JU – PIC 999876292

During the second year, JU team will be involved in WP4 (Task 4.3). JU will contribute to 1) target selection and targeted method development and screening method development and validation in human community exposure assessment; 2) NTS for prioritization of features and pattern analysis to unravel sources in environmental assessment; 3) innovative sampling and analytical methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel animal species (mainly fish).

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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9- USTAV ZDRAVOTNICKYCH INFORMACI A STATISTIKY CESKE REPUBLIKY, CZECH REPUBLIC (UZIS) – PIC: 920415929

UZIS will contribute to the WP7 – FAIR Data through comments and providing national liaison regarding national health datasets. Main tasks during Year 2 will be commenting on the proposal of the template for the data management plan (Activity 7.1.1), contributing to mapping the FAIR data landscape, design of data hub and solutions for fair data (Activity 7.2.1-3), and contributing to the uncertainties scoping study and use cases of uncertainty analysis, namely from the public health data viewpoint (Activity 7.3.2).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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<p>10- The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, DENMARK (DEPA) – PIC: 938989101 During the second year, DEPA will be involved in WP1, 2 and 3; In WP1 as member of the Grant Signatory Board (T1.1.) and National Hub Contact Point (T1.2.) In WP3 as National Hub Contact Point (T3.2.)</p>	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>10.1 AU – PIC 999997736 Two departments from Aarhus University (AU), Denmark are participating in PARC: Department of Public Health (AU-PH) and Department of Environmental Science (AU-ENVS).</p> <p>During the second year (year 2), AU will participate in WP4, WP5, WP6, WP8 and WP9. Specifically, the AU-PH team will be involved in activities of WP4, WP5, and WP6. AU-ENVS will be involved in WP4, WP6, WP8 and WP9.</p> <p>WP4: In year 2, the AU-PH team will be involved in several activities of Task 4.1. In 4.1.1, the AU-PH will contribute to the general survey among young adults with protocol development In 4.1.1.4, the AU-PH will contribute to the waste survey where we will contribute with protocol development In 4.1.2.1, the AU-PH will be involved in defining the best exposure biomarker for the PARC human biomonitoring studies based on the work done and lessons learnt in HBM4EU. In 4.1.3.2, the AU-PH will be a part of the effect biomarker groups and contribute with 1) “<i>liaise with PARC T5.3 and T6.2 to align activities</i>”, 2) “<i>compare substance groups for which effect biomarkers were identified in HBM4EU WP13/14 to T4.1 PARC substance groups</i>”; and 3) “<i>explore whether new/innovative biomarkers should be added to those identified under HBM4EU</i>”. In 4.1.4.2, the AU-PH will be a part of the statistical working group and conducting analyses of the exposure-effect associations & associated pathways.</p> <p>AU (AU-ENVS) will continue co-leading T4.2 and work in the ongoing projects defined by T4.2 (P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU and P4.2.1_2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS).</p> <p>In addition, AU (AU-ENVS) will also be involved in the following projects in T4.3: P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01_Perinatal exposure_INRAE Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern; P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QA/QC_WRQA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA-based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices.</p> <p>WP5: In year 2, the AU-PH team will be involved in Task 5.3. We will be involved as participants in the T5.3.2 specialty group on AOP development on endocrine and metabolic disruption (SG2) and as co-coordinators of the effect marker group (EMG).</p> <p>WP6: In year 2, AU will be involved in Task 6.2 with both groups (AU-PH and AU-ENVS). In 6.2.1, The AU-PH will contribute to the development of an Inventory of existing data sources and gap analysis on occupational exposure In 6.2.3, the AU-PH will be part of the working group 1 and identify real-life chemical mixtures in own human biomonitoring study data.</p> <p>WP8: AU (AU-ENVS) will contribute to T8.2, amongst other activities to the development of concepts</p>	

and plans for effect-based monitoring and effect directed analysis (EDA) of chemicals towards an Early Warning-System.

WP9: AU (AU-ENVS) will continue contributing to T9.1, T9.2 and T9.3, to the PARC QA/QC Core Group and to ensuring WP4-WP9 connections (“WP4 contact point”).

10.2 DTU – PIC 999990655

During the second year of PARC, DTU will contribute to:

- WP5, Task 5.2 by developing QSAR models for several thyroid hormone-related endpoints, as well as conducting a rat *in vivo* study in order to characterize mechanisms of action for TH disruption to inform on NAMs development. This will include multi-organ transcriptomics.
- WP6, Task 6.1 by contributing to development of a IATA for antiandrogenic effects
- WP6, Task 6.2 by supporting the efforts to develop an integrative approach to take different lines of evidence (*in vitro*, *in vivo*, and human data, mode of action, biomarkers of effect) into account to establish human-relevant exposure-effect relationships addressing all uncertainties. Furthermore, as part of Task 6.2, DTU will contribute to the development of a Weight-of-evidence (WoE) approach for selection of exposure-effect functions including information from epidemiological, toxicological, and mechanistic studies. Furthermore, DTU will contribute to the inventory and comparison of existing methodologies, indicators, and frameworks used for cost-analysis related to health impact of chemical exposures.
- WP6, A6.2.3 by leading a case study on mixture risk assessment of PFAS in relation to immune toxicity
- WP6, Task 6.3 by supporting an effort to identify relevant data gap filling methods, their differences in underlying approaches across European legislations, and potentials for harmonization and simplification.
- WP8, Task 8.1 by relating and potentially aligning safe and sustainable-by-design (SSbD) boundary conditions to conditions for quantitative environmental sustainability assessments, such as life cycle impact assessment.
- WP8, Task 8.3, by screening the assumptions and interfaces of the UNEP/SETAC global scientific consensus model USEtox to the requirements to be considered in the PARC toolbox of models and data relevant for regulatory risk assessment in Europe.

10.3 REGIONH – PIC 999654744

During the second year RegionH will be involved in WP 4, WP6 and WP9.

- WP4, Task 4.1.1 in which RegionH-RH is part of the core team preparing the design and requirements for General surveys in preparation for initiation of General HBM surveys under PARC in 2023. In addition, RegionH is involved in the work related to laboratory analysis and quality assurance, with focus on the definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods.
- WP6, Task 6.3 in which RegionH-GE will be involved in task 6.3.1 concerning skin sensitization. The following tasks will be undertaken: mapping of practices by questionnaire and draft of publication, PhD application to UCPH.
- WP6, A6.4.1 in which RegionH-GE is responsible, the following tasks are planned: mapping of current practices, planning and performing first experiments. The initiation of this study is currently being discussed.
- WP9, A9.3.2 in which RegionH-RH will take part in a working group on establishing principles for harmonized determination of LoDs and LoQs for analytical methods.

10.4 UCPH – PIC 999991043

During the second year (year 2), the UCPH team will be involved in activities of WP4 and WP6.

UCPH will contribute to:

WP4:

- The ‘*Subproject 2: Screening of WWTP effluents (and source-related samples) to assess the release of CECs into the water cycle*’ through the activities in Task 4.3, P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH:
 - o MII: Environmental Exposure Assessment, tasks : 1) Method development and proof of concept and 2) Pan-European study
 - o MIII: Data Mining of Existing Data, task: Development of methods and proof of concept on existing datasets
- P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QAQC_WR: We will participate in 2. Inventory and review of existing QA/QC, and 3. Guidance on best practises in non-target measurements.
- P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU: Our main contribution will be to 1. Conceptual framework for sampling tools towards EWS and 2. Conceptual framework for suspect/NTS/EDA tools towards EWS.
- P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data processing workflow_EHESP: Our contribution will be to 3. Development of the First operational version of the workflow in Galaxy.

WP6:

- Task 6.3 by supporting P6.3.2.a_Y2_CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU: *An effort to identify relevant data gap filling methods, their differences in underlying approaches across European legislations, and potentials for harmonization and simplification.* We will contribute to 1. Policy and gap filling inventory and 3. Analysis and recommendations.

10.5 SDU – PIC 999904616

During the second year SDU will be involved in the following tasks in WP5 and WP6:

A5.1.1: SDU will bridge the environmental experimental work performed in WP5.1.2 with the human health related experimental work in WP5.1.1 to support better read across between HH and Env.

A5.1.2: SDU will continue working in activity i, ii, iv and v with focus on closing data gaps for BPA alternatives. SDU uses two animal taxa (vertebrate zebrafish and invertebrate aquatic snail *Lymnaea stagnalis*) for this work.

A5.2.1: SDU will continue to investigate the use of non-mammalian NAMs for extrapolation to human health for THSD: zebrafish embryo assays will be used in a case study for cross-species extrapolation.

A5.2.2: SDU contributes to development of new and innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and the advancement of the use of these models as alternatives to vertebrate testing by investigating *L. stagnalis* and zebrafish embryos as models.

A5.3.2: SDU is co-leading the speciality group 2 focusing on THSD AOPn development by identification of data/knowledge gaps (e.g. KEs, KERs) and further develop relevant AOPs, KEs and KERs).

A6.1.1: SDU will mainly be involved in the development of an IATA for THSD where a large number of AOPs already exists and development of relevant in vitro and in vivo methods is ongoing.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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11- TERVISEAMET, ESTONIA (HB) – PIC 933659727

In year two Health Board continues its tasks as management entity. Supporting our partners with executive assignments and providing project management support in T1.1 and T1.2 of WP1.

Health Board is also active in WP2 steering the National Hub, providing legal and structural support. Together with SoM organizing National Hub meetings and consultations, maintaining relationships

with Hub partners and supporting consultation and information sharing functions.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>11.1 SOM – PIC 998429731 During the second year SoM will continue its work in WP2 T2.2 „Knowledge management and uptake into policy,, In this workpackage next year's activities are not fully in place yet so it is hard to specify exact activities but PARCopedia and PARCroute are one of the biggest project points at this time. Work regards to National Hub meetings and consultations will continue, maintaining relationships with Hub partners and acting as a consultation and information sharing entity. Also, SoM has an interest in WP4 T4.2.</p> <p>11.2 UT – PIC 999895013 During the Y2 UT will continue involvement in WP6, Task 6.4, Activity 6.4.2 on facilitating the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods. UT is involved in three projects: P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurvey_UNIBAS, P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRA_applied in practice_NIPH_VKM, P6.4.2.c_Y1_ML-AI-QSAR_UT (new name P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT). UT leads project P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT and provides expertise also in two other named projects. In Y2 UT will continue with the analysis of the artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) QSAR models, identifying the best practices and further actions to ensure a transparent regulatory use, uncertainty estimation and its communication towards end-users, independent verification and understanding of the outcome of such models, development of reporting standards and decision-making criteria for ML and AI predictive models in the context of NAMs and NGRA. The best examples will be identified and made available as FAIR models/data. UT through collaborator activities above mentioned projects also will be involved FAIR data activities (T7.1) and in the integration computational NAMs (T8.3), evaluation of computational NAMs for the EWS (WP8.2).</p>	
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

<p>12- EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, EU (EEA) – PIC 997912624 WP2: EEA is the WP coleader together with the EAA (Austrian Environment Agency) where the overall management and coordination of the AWP will be done. EEA is also a partner in task 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3. We will work on the review of projects in task 2.1, as well as being contact points, and support the prioritisation work in PARC. In task 2.2. we are supporting PARCroute and the links to policy, and science to policy network. In task 2.3, we will be engaging in work on the sustainability and exit strategy for PARC at EU and national level. WP3: Website development, formatting and layout of communication products. WP8: EEA is a partner in task 8.1 where we will be developing work on SSbD.</p>	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
EEA will subcontract part of the implementation of task 3.2 related to communication tools such as the development of the PARC website, visual and graphic identity, and various communication products (factsheets, briefs, newsletter, videos...).	

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

13- TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS, FINLAND (THL) – PIC 996697893	
In WP4, THL will during year 2 be planning a targeted study under “multitrack” model to quantify dioxins with hierarchical Bayes model using PCB-levels from small serum volume as target dataset. In addition, possible participation to QC/QA schemes for targeted analysis within T4.1.3.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its workU is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>13.1 SYKE – PIC 999478010</p> <p>During the Y2 SYKE will continue participating in WP4, WP6 and WP8.</p> <p>In A4.2.1. SYKE will participate in the development of the prioritization framework.</p> <p>In A4.2.2. SYKE will participate in conducting the inventory of existing monitoring studies/projects concerning PFASs.</p> <p>In A4.2.3. SYKE will participate in preparing the monitoring campaign for EDSs and PFASs.</p> <p>In T6.3 SYKE will continue working with the CS1 Review of risk-based benchmarks (P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS1_CARB_SYKE), which SYKE is leading. The study will be broadened to additional substances (in addition to the substance studied during Y1), which have been identified based on specific selection criteria. The study will aim at evaluating the deficiencies, inconsistencies and gaps in the selected, relevant regulations with a focus on decision benchmarks.</p> <p>In A6.4.4 SYKE will contribute to P6.4.4.b_Y1 by compiling and providing data on the field studies on pollinators on arable land in Finland.</p> <p>In T8.1 SYKE will contribute by involving national stakeholders in the SSbD framework, indicator and toolbox development and by participating in the selection of case studies.</p>	
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

14- TYOTERVEYSLAITOS, FINLAND (TTL) – PIC 999880948	
During the second year TTL is participating WP1, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, and WP8.	
WP1: TTL is NHCP in Finland.	
T3.2: TTL is contributing to communication, dissemination, and awareness.	
A4.1.1: TTL is leading occupational surveys related to waste management and health care sectors. In year two we will start samplings related to these studies.	
A4.1.3: We will prepare human biomonitoring guidance value (HBM-GV) for nickel and select and other substance for HBM-GV setting. Participation in Feasibility study: Explore the possibility to assess past exposures to prioritized chemical substances from biobanked samples collected in cohorts in relation to adverse health effects.	
A4.1.4: We will contribute in further statistical analyses of HBM4EU occupational data.	
T4.3: We are involved in Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening	

methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
 A5.1.1: We will participate exploring the carcinogenic potential of selected BPA alternatives (and/or their metabolites) by testing their genotoxic activity and their epigenetic and cell transformation effects.
 A6.2.1: We are involved in structural analysis and development of a functional design for model connection, and in the occupational case studies.
 A6.2.3: We are involved in the use of HBM data in the risk assessment of real-life mixtures focusing in occupational mixtures.
 T6.3: We are leading project related the use of regulatory information in workplace chemical risk assessment. We are involved in project related to review of guidance values targeting occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants
 T8.1/8.3: We are involved in design of SSbD toolbox and defining case studies for testing of toolbox.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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14.1 FFA – PIC 902952534

WP 4.1 During year 2 Finnish Food Authority (FFA) will continue planning targeted group analyses for small childrens samples (1-6y) (with food use information) from samples available from University of Helsinki nutrition group. Also, samples from parents are available. Possible participation of food related QC/QA targeted analyses.

14.2 TUKES – PIC 972221301

During the second year, TUKES will contribute to activities under WP6, Task 6.4. In 6.4, TUKES will continue its participation to the activity 6.4.3 (Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in chemical products, materials and articles to support the transition to a circular economy).

14.3 UOULU – PIC 999844670

During the second year, UOULU will contribute under WP4 activities, in planning of the targeted studies and giving comments on HBM-GV studies. Activities under WP6 are under development, e.g., biomarkers of exposure.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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15- UMWELTBUNDESAMT, GERMANY (UBA) – PIC 998575910

During the second year, UBA will be involved in all Work Packages. The major contribution will be in WP4 - Monitoring and Exposure, which UBA co-leads.

In WP1, UBA will be involved in the overall executive management and support of the Partnership (T1.1), the scientific steering including all activities involving the National Hubs (T1.2), the impact evaluation and monitoring of performance indicators (T1.3) and in the activities related to the Ethics framework (T 1.4).

In WP2, UBA will be involved in the priority setting and the internal review process of projects (T2.1). UBA will continue to collaborate in the development of PARCopedia and PARCroute (T2.2). In addition, UBA will participate in sustainability activities, particularly PARC’s exit strategy (T2.3).

In WP3, UBA will be involved in activities related to the development of the Stakeholder Forum and the International Board (T3.1), and in activities related to communication and dissemination of results such as the development of the website and the communication strategy (T3.2). In addition, UBA will contribute to the development and maintenance of synergies between PARC and international initiatives, including the EIRENE infrastructure (T3.3).

In WP4, UBA will be involved in diverse Human Biomonitoring activities in T4.1 such as the initiation of an EU-wide general population survey and the development of targeted surveys (including design and supporting materials). In year 2, UBA will collaborate in preparing the implementation of the following aspects in the above-mentioned surveys: exposure biomarkers, effect biomarkers, innovative (sampling) and screening techniques for Human Biomonitoring and analyses plan in the HBM surveys, as well as the evaluation of new chemical analysis methods needs. In addition, UBA will explore approaches for linking exposures and health effects and collaborate on deriving Health-Based Guidance values for a first set of prioritized substances. In year 2, UBA will continue to work jointly on the preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe. In T4.1 (4.1.1 and 4.1.2), parts of the HBM survey(s) (preparations, fieldwork, analysis etc.), depending on the samples and substances to be analysed, will need external support. In 4.1.3, parts of the health-based guidance values literature research and its derivation will be subcontracted.

In T4.2, UBA will continue working on a scheme to define research priorities in the field of environmental and multisource monitoring. In year 2, UBA will collaborate on the development and implementation of a framework for automated assessment of large lists of compounds, including applicability tests in defined case studies (PFAS and ED compounds). In this task, UBA will continue to be involved in designing the monitoring program and planning the chemical and statistical analysis. In year 2, UBA will also start to contribute with analytical measurements for the PFAS project. In addition, UBA will collaborate to a) establish an Ecotoxicology Working Group across WPs and b) build links to T4.1 and T4.3 for optimized collaboration and long-term integration of human biomonitoring, environmental and multisource monitoring and innovative methods.

In T4.3, UBA will contribute to the development of innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys by working on QA/QC requirements for this screening methods and on the usage of such data in an early warning system.

In WP6, UBA will continue to work on mixture exposure and will be involved in human health impact assessment and the development of risk indicators (T6.2). In T6.3 UBA, continues to work on case studies reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in prospective and retrospective risk assessment, on ED assessments as well as uncertainty analysis. In T6.4, UBA will contribute to regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures (e.g., derivation of a MAF) and their regulatory acceptance. UBA will be also co-lead activities on the risk assessment of pesticides to promote the efficient overall protection of biodiversity.

In WP7, UBA will be involved in T7.1 and 7.2. In T7.1, UBA will contribute to the FAIR data policy for PARC and the Data Management Plan. In T7.2, UBA will work on the PARC FAIR data platform and contribute to the development of FAIR data solutions. Within WP7, under the umbrella of the Environmental Data project, UBA will contribute to the identification of synergies with T4.2 (multiple exposure monitoring) and the NORMAN Database System (NDS).

In WP8, UBA will collaborate on the development of the safe and sustainable by design concept and its operationalisation (T8.1). UBA contributes to the analysis of state-of-the-art and lessons learned (including gaps and opportunities) from/of existing work and literature related to the SSbD toolbox. UBA (co-) leads the activities for the development of a knowledge sharing platform and education materials on SSbD. In T8.2, UBA will be involved developing the scientific and technical basis for an

early warning system on chemical risks.	
In WP 9 UBA is contributing to 9.3 and will work on questions of the quality assurance of chemical analysis and data evaluation.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
15.1 BfG – PIC 996893445	
In the second year of PARC (Y2), the BfG will be involved in the WP 4.2, 4.3, 5.2 and 5.3.	
Within A4.2.3, the BfG supports the preparation of the monitoring campaigns for the selected case studies on PFAS and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds (EDCS).	
BfG will also be involved in Task 4.3_ project E01: “Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) for (I) human community and (II) environmental exposure assessment” (P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH). Under theme (II) “Environmental Exposure Assessment”, the BfG will be contributing to the activities towards the development of a high-throughput EDA as well as a NTS approach for the prioritisation of features and pattern analysis to unravel sources. Additionally, the BfG engages in the theme (III) “Data Mining of Existing Data” by co-leading activities on the development of methods and a proof of concept on existing datasets.	
Within task 5.2.b “Innovative methods and tools for environmental toxicity (ecotoxicology) testing and modelling”, the BfG will contribute to the Activity 5.2.2 and the advancement of NAMs for the hazard assessment of invertebrates by developing suitable assays based on the model species <i>C. elegans</i> which can be applied in the context of the project and cross-cutting activities on BPA alternatives.	
Within activity 5.3.2 “AOP development based on integration of in vivo and in vitro datasets” the BfG engages in the activities of the specialty group 2 (SG2) on endocrine and metabolic disruption by contributing to the activities concerning the development of and the identification of data gaps in existing AOPs and the mapping of existing NAMs for anti-androgenic and (anti-)estrogenic disruption.	
15.2 UFZ – PIC 999994632	
In Year 2, UFZ will be involved in WPs 4.2, 4.3, 5.2, 5.3, 6.4, 7.2, 7.3:	
In WP4, UFZ will contribute to Task 4.2 to the design of the monitoring campaign for PFAS and EDCs, to running the sampling campaign and analysing a subset of samples for EDCs (TA4.2.3, A4.2.4 as well as data analysis and management (T4.2.5). Also, UFZ will play a major role in developing mechanisms for prioritisation and the development of project proposal for additional compound classes (A4.2.1). In Task 4.3, UFZ will contribute to the transversal projects on defining minimal common QA/QC requirements (P4.3.1.b_T02), provide expertise in supporting the development of an early warning system (P4.3.1.d_T03) and contribute to the development of data processing workflows within P4.3.1.d_T04 “Advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS”. With respect to human exposure, UFZ will develop and apply HRMS based and EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure, with a focus and sample analysis, advanced data processing and compound identification (P4.3.2.a_H01). UFZ co-leads the project P4.3.3.a_E01 (Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants), where its focus includes screening method development for wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE), the prioritisation of source-related features and patterns,	

the development of high-throughput EDA methods and setting up a pan-European sampling campaign for WBE and environmental exposure to treated and untreated wastewater. In project P4.3.3.b_E02 “HRMS based / EDA screening methods for sentinel animal species” UFZ will contribute in developing a conceptual approach to the use of sentinel species for screening-based environmental monitoring, based on its expertise in aquatic organism monitoring.

In WP5, UFZ will contribute to activities 5.2.1, 5.2.2 and 5.3. In A5.2.1 the impact of chemicals on metabolic disruption will be studied. For the establishment of NAMs to detect immunotoxicity a 24-parameter cytometry-based cellular assay is developed with potential application on BPA alternatives and associated mixtures. The UFZ co-leads PARC research regarding the development of novel DNT assays, and contributes research for the development of a novel zebrafish embryo assay to detect compounds that could interfere with learning and memory. In A5.2.2. UFZ will contribute by establishing an approach to estimate cumulative and persistence toxicity equivalents using NAMs (e.g., for cytotoxicity and neurotoxicity). Furthermore, the UFZ contributes with an automated morphology analysis of the zebrafish embryo, providing essential data for grouping of chemicals (such as BPA alternatives) as well as data needed for the assessment of the specificity of zebrafish assay responses. A multi-omics framework is developed for improving the detection of toxicity pathways by using information from transcriptome, proteome and metabolome with focus on the zebrafish model. In A5.3.1 the UFZ is involved in NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation and its translation to human pathophysiology, and in A5.3.4 in PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology.

In WP6, UFZ will contribute strategies for environmental mixtures to Activity 6.4.1 Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures. Besides, under activity 6.4.4, Exposure (P6.4.4.a), UFZ will work on the predictive capacity of models with respect to environmental concentrations of plant protection products (PPPs) in surface water; in Task 6.4.4.2 Effects (P6.4.4.b), UFZ will contribute predictor identification for environmental risk assessment (ERA); in Task 6.4.4.3 Benchmarking (P6.4.4.c) UFZ will work on ERA benchmarking, and in Task 6.4.4.4 PPP & other stressors (P6.4.4.d), UFZ will work on the reduction of 6.4.4.6 mitigating effects (P6.4.4.e), UFZ will work on effect quantification of PPPs.

In WP7, UFZ will contribute to Activities 7.2.1, 7.2.2, 7.3.1 and 7.3.4. In 7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape, UFZ will work in database and repository identification and integration; in 7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape, UFZ will contribute respective requirement identification; in 7.3.1 Combining heterogeneous data, UFZ will compile an inventory of innovative analysis methods, and in 7.3.4 UFZ will contribute machine learning approaches to be applied in next generation risk assessment.

15.3 IPA – PIC 998343692

IPA has withdrawn its participation to PARC and will no longer contribute to Y2 activities.

15.4 UKOLD – PIC 999856407

During the second year, UKOLD will be involved in WP 6.4, in A6.4.4. In more detail, UKOLD will be involved in the alignment of ERA development goals with research questions and ensure the harmonization of projects in the WP (P6.4.4.a), in the identification and comparison of different data sets that can be used to test PEC models and characterize exposure (P6.4.4.b) and in discussions about the validation and suitability of models for predictions of environmental effects of pesticides (P6.4.4.c) and landscape characteristics that are important to be considered in case studies. Most importantly, UKOLD will lead the benchmarking exercise (P6.4.4.d) that aims to derive methods that allow to benchmark the ecological risk of pesticides against each other.

15.5 UOS – PIC 999855049

During the second year, UOS will be involved in WP 6.4, in A6.4.4. In more detail, UOS will be

involved in the alignment of ERA development goals with research questions (P6.4.4.a), in the identification and comparison of different PEC models and writing the technical report (P6.4.4.b), in discussions about reducing complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products (P6.4.4.c), and in the conceptualization of landscape characteristics, in developing conceptual models for selected case studies, in the integration of (preliminary) outcomes from other 6.4.4 projects (P6.4.4.a-c) and the execution of the first set of case studies (P6.4.4.e).

15.6 KUM – PIC 995625946

KUM will be involved in WP4.

We will contribute to A4.1.2.1: Selection of selection of Exposure biomarkers and analytical methods and to A4.1.2.5: Analysis of exposure biomarkers in the samples emerging from human biomonitoring tasks.

We will contribute to A4.3.2.a: Innovative methods and tools for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals by the development of microsampling methods for trace metal analysis.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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16- BUNDESINSTITUT FUER RISIKOBEWERTUNG, GERMANY (BfR) – PIC: 998771171

During Year 2, BfR will continue its involvement in the following Work Packages (WP):

WP1 Management of AEs, NHCP, Grant signatory.

WP2 Task 2.1 BfR will be involved in the process of priority setting and the review process of new research activities and ensure that they target the regulatory challenges. **Task 2.2 co-leading** together with INSA. This includes coordination of, as well as significant contributions to, the activities PARCroute (development of the NGRARoute roadmap) and PARCopedia (rollout of the first version planned for M18). **Task 2.3** BfR will contribute to the development of the exit strategy for PARC.

WP3, Task 3.2 BfR will contribute to the website and the communication strategy.

WP5 BfR will continue **co-leading** with ANSES the Hazard Assessment for human and environmental health on three main tasks:

Task 5.1 filling data gaps on hazards identified by key stakeholders, starting with natural toxins (Alternaria toxins, enniatine) and BPA alternatives;

Tasks 5.2 developing methodologies that will directly aid chemical hazard identification (with the following endpoints: immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, developmental neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and metabolic disruption);

Task 5.3 progressing towards Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) by establishing different core groups (AOPs, PBTK, in vivo/in vitro mode of action).

BfR will use its expertise in the following WP5 tasks:

Task 5.1 assessing the genotoxic potential and therefore possible carcinogenic effects of Alternaria toxins (e.g. alternariol, alternariol monomethyl ether, teanuazonic acid, altenuen). Also, performing genotoxicity testing on enniatine A, A1, B, and B1 in vitro, applying the following test battery:

Bacterial Reverse Mutation Test (according to OECD guideline 471),

In Vitro Mammalian Chromosomal Aberration Test (according to OECD guideline 473),

In Vitro Mammalian Cell Micronucleus Test (according to OECD guideline 487).

As some substances are mutagenic in vivo but not in vitro, also in vivo tests should be included, e.g. the Mammalian Erythrocyte Micronucleus Test (according to OECD guideline 474) and/or the

Mammalian Bone Marrow Chromosome Aberration Test (according to OECD guideline 475).

Task 5.2 analysing real-life chemical mixtures by NAM, including in vitro kinetic, in vitro dynamic, and in vivo 90-day feeding studies based on OECD TG408. Further develop methods, applying high-throughput compatible phenotypic screening methods (including cell painting) as well as transcriptomic approaches that will be combined with other models and methods from the consortium partners to allow the establishment of an integrated testing and assessment strategy for the identification and differentiation of genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogens.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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16.1 Fraunhofer – PIC 999984059

Fraunhofer IME is involved in WP4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) and WP 6.4 (Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies).

In the field of environmental monitoring, Fraunhofer IME has significant experience in prioritization processes as well as in designing and conducting monitoring studies. In Year 2, Fraunhofer IME will be working in A4.2.1 and A4.2.2 to support the prioritization of chemicals and the planning of sample exchange as well as the review of existing knowledge, namely in the field of PFAS. As soon as samples are available, Fraunhofer IME will additionally work on the chemical analysis of PFAS in environmental samples in the frame of A4.2.4 to yield a first picture of the PFAS burden in the European environment.

Fraunhofer IME is also involved in activity 6.4.4 (Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity). In the field of environmental exposure modelling, Fraunhofer IME has contributed in the development of exposure models over the past years (e.g., GERDA Steps, Steps 1&2, FOCUS SWASH). The aim is it to reduce the complexity of currently used models/methodologies without compromising the level of protection required. In a first step a list of the complex exposure models predicting PPP concentrations in surface will be composed. After that the processes that are included are described and processes which can be simplified will be identified.

Fraunhofer IBMT is involved in WP4 (Human Biomonitoring). In this regard, IBMT has an extended expertise in planning and conducting epidemiological surveys including the preparation of legal & ethical documents, questionnaire development, sampling, sample preparation, sample characterization and clinical-chemical analysis, biobanking and sample logistics. In WP4, Fraunhofer IBMT will support diverse Human Biomonitoring activities. In A4.1.1 IBMT will support PARC partners in the implementation (e.g., preparations, fieldwork, biobanking) of an EU-wide general population survey on the national level (Germany) and the development of targeted surveys (including study design and supporting materials). In addition, IBMT will support exploring approaches for linking exposures and health effects and the preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe. In A4.1.3 IBMT will continue to identify effect biomarkers for the prioritized substances and support related literature research.

Fraunhofer IBMT is also involved in WP5.1.1 (Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern) and WP5.2 (Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling). With its high expertise in in vitro screening and human hazard assessment, Fraunhofer IBMT will contribute in year 2 with standard

OECD TG based screening (In Vitro Mammalian Cell Gene Mutation Tests and Micronucleus Tests) in 5.1.1 and with the development of an advanced 3D in vitro liver model for data generation also as link to WP6. Fraunhofer IBMT is involved in 6.1.1c (IATA Genotoxicity) with activities in the design and execution of case studies.

16.2 KIT – PIC 990797674

During the second year, KIT will be involved in A5.3.1 and 5.3.2.

In A5.3.1 addressing systems toxicology and in A5.3.2 developing new AOPs, KIT participates in the projects and meetings P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR and P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm, respectively. KIT is also involved in the Speciality Group SG1 (Immunotox subgroup / NGTXC sub-group). Specifically, in A5.3.1, during year 2, we will generate transcriptomics data in lung and/or breast cancer cells to support on the one hand the systems toxicology approach with the aim to identify MIE and KE relevant for the action of NGTXC. On the other hand, these data will also be used to support the development of AOPs starting with breast cancer and NGTXC. In this context, KIT also explores the literature and the AOP WIKI database to construct and complete AOPs in SG1.

Furthermore, KIT is involved in the EU project Precision Toxicology (coordinated by the University of Birmingham which is also a partner in PARC) in which human HepG2 cells are exposed to 250 different chemicals and RNAseq data are obtained. Together with Sciensano it is intended to use the GENOMARK biomarker gene set developed in HepaRG cells as a predictor for genotoxicity of chemicals also in HepG2 cells based on transcriptomics. The impact of cell type, exposure time and mode of action of selected chemicals will be studied to further improve the predictivity of transcriptome-based classification of genotoxins.

16.3 IUF – PIC 998707054

The IUF will be involved in Task 5.1 (toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern), focusing on developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), as the team holds great expertise and a broad portfolio of already established and ready-to-use in vitro alternative methods to address multiple key neurodevelopmental processes as part of an international DNT in vitro battery. We will first focus on the testing of different PFAS and their mixtures, a proof-of-concept mycotoxin as well as BPA analogues. Furthermore, the IUF participates in A5.2.1, by developing human-based in vitro methods for DNT and acute neurotoxicity (ANT) testing, with focus on neural network formation and function during the first 1-2 years. In Task 5.3 the IUF participates in AOP generation for DNT and ANT.

16.4 IfADo – PIC 998770686

In the second year, functional assays will be established to analyze (1) lipid accumulation in hepatocytes; (2) the export of bile acids from hepatocytes. At least 15 hepatotoxic and non-hepatotoxic substances will be tested. The results will be interpreted in relation to the genome-wide RNA expression data from year 1 to analyze, which parameters or parameter-combinations allow the best differentiation between hepatotoxic and non-hepatotoxic compounds.

Tasks: 5.1; 6.1

16.5 MLU- PIC 999871539

In the second year the MLU will not be involved in a work package of PARC. We will prepare for a participation in year three.

16.6 UKL – PIC 999885895

During the second year of PARC, UKL will contribute mainly to A5.2.1.a Non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTXCs). Here, we will use primary-like human colonic epithelial cells (HCEC) and colorectal cancer (CRC) cells to assess multiple endpoints related to carcinogenesis, such as oxidative stress, proliferation and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). Several compounds serving as positive and negative

controls will be tested during the 1st and 2nd year to validate the used models and NAMs. In the future, PARC specific chemicals such as mycotoxins and BPA alternatives will be subject to testing.

16.7 TUB – PIC 999986678

During the second year TUB will synthesise the toxins enniatin and alternariol/alternariol methylether by chemical synthesis and/or fermentation combined with downstream processing. The synthetic derivatives will be synthesized in gram-amounts and characterized by state-of-the-art analytics, e.g., HPLC-ESI-MS and NMR spectroscopy for compound identity and purity. The compounds will be handed over to the collaboration partners BfR and UNIVIE (Task 5.1).

16.8 UKON – PIC 999866204

During the second year, UKON will be involved in WP 2.2 and 5.2.

In WP2, UKON teams will be involved in Task 2.2 to support the development of the PARCopedia, PARC's community platform for knowledge exchange and chemical risk assessment innovation and to provide inputs on the NGRAroute, the roadmap for regulatory implementation of Next Generation Risk Assessment.

In WP5, UKON team involved in task 5.2 will contribute to the development of NAMs relevant for detection of acute and developmental neurotoxicity that will be used in case studies on pathway-specific model compounds. UKON team's systems will be implemented for data gap filling of the existing DNT in vitro battery (IVB), in particular for neuronal network formation, neuron-specific signaling, and glial endpoints.

Test methods for acute neurotoxicity will be refined to include mechanistic information, omics data and acute signaling. Case studies on defined compounds will be published.

16.9 TiHo – PIC 999464430

Starting in year 2 TiHo will contribute to the development of new human stem cell-based New Approach Methodologies in the field of Developmental and Adult Neurotoxicology (DNT/ANT) in WP 5.2.a (now 5.2.1e) with special focus on peripheral myelination/demyelination in sensory and motor neurons to contribute an assay to be included in an ANT AOP network (exchange with 5.3).

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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17- NEMZETI NEPEGESZSEGUGYI KOZPONT, HUNGARY (NPHC) – PIC: 998706957

In WP2, NPHC is one of the co-leaders of Task 2.3. Withing this task, NPHC will contribute to the evaluation of the survey focusing on the mapping of the existing knowledge gaps, requests, suggestions and expertise of the National Hubs which will be described in the first report on the national needs (D2.8). NPHC contribute to the new survey. NPHC contributes to formulating the exit strategy (e.g., different options for future frameworks).

In WP3, NPHC is one of the co-leaders of Task 3.2 and contribute to the following activities: updating and elaborating the PARC communication and dissemination strategy, updating the website and social media channels, preparation of communication materials, elaboration of method for the focus group, coordination of the citizen survey.

In WP4, NPHC will design the national HBM survey targeting children in Task 4.1. It will include the submission of the ethical approval and preparation for the fieldwork.

In WP5, NPHC participates in Tasks 5.2 and 5.3. Within Task 5.2 NPHC in collaboration with MUI and RIVM investigates the development of NAMs for predicting chemical compounds involved in respiratory sensitization. NPHC, using in vitro and in vivo approaches will focus on dendritic cell-based NAMs as well as explore the potential development of NAMs based on extracellular vesicles secretion in respiratory sensitization using TDI as a model respiratory sensitizer. The role of NPHC in A5.3.2 is

to contribute to the construction of an AOP for respiratory sensitization and make an inventory of available NAMs (in the frame of the so-called “specialty group1 focusing on immunotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis specialty group 1), as well as to identify effect markers relevant for respiratory sensitization (in the frame of the “Effect marker group or “specialty group4” specialty group 4). The role of NPHC in A5.3.1 is still under planning.
In WP9, NPHC will serve as a WP2 contact point and support the work of WP9 (e.g., translating the needs of the NHs to training program, mapping of the existing exposure monitoring networks). Furthermore, NPHC will participate in the NHCP activities in the different WPs.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
17. NPHC: The representative citizen survey and the preparation of communication products will be subcontracted in T3.2.	
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

18- HASKOLI ISLANDS, ICELAND (UI) – PIC 999884246	
During the second year of PARC, UI will be involved in WP 4, 6 and 9. In WP4, UI is involved in Task 4.1 where we will continue the monitoring campaign for a case study of how a vegan diet may affect the levels of contaminants in blood and urine found in the average population during HBM4EU. Emphasis will be on PFAS, pesticides, acrylamide and metals. The team will also start preparations for the participation in the aligned studies of PARC with repeated sampling of adults in relation to a dietary survey planned for 2024. In WP6, the UI team is involved in task 6.4.1 In WP9 our laboratory will participate in the QA/QC proficiency tests for PFAS.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

19- MINISTRY OF HEALTH, ISRAEL (MOH) – PIC 999596156	
During the second year of PARC MOH will contribute to tasks related to role as grant signatory and National Hub (including meetings and consultations). MOH will continue work on derivation of a health-based guidance value for PFAS as part of activity 4.1.3.1.a. In addition, we will participate in task 4.1.1.1 working group 3 which deals with solutions for inclusion of novel aspects in HBM studies implementation Finally, as part of task 4.1.1 MOH will begin work towards participation in aligned HBM study (<i>pending final decision by VITO on included studies</i>), this will include obtaining ethical approval for the study,	

translating harmonized materials including consent form and questionnaires, and planning the implementation phase of the study.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N

20- ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA, ITALY (ISS) – PIC 999978821

During the second year, ISS will be involved in WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8.

WP5

In P5.1.1a and P5.1.1b ISS will perform the OECD TG 456 to assess adverse effects on steroidogenesis following exposure to natural toxins (5.1.1a) and BPA alternatives (5.1.1b) relevant for human health. In A5.3.2 ISS will participate in speciality group 1, in the AOP working group for NGTxC, and in the speciality group 2, in the development of AOPs for Thyroid Hormone System Disruption (THSD).

WP6

In Task 6.1 ISS will contribute to the projects: “IATA for genotoxicity” (P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX) and IATA for Thyroid Hormone System Disruption.

In Task 6.3 ISS is involved in the project “Review of effect-specific risk assessment” (P.6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI), leading the case study on the “Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches.” (P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS).

In Task 6.4

WP7

ISS will contribute to activities of WP7, in particular tasks 7.1 and 7.2 and 7.3

WP8

Within WP8, ISS will contribute to Task 8.1, in particular concerning activities in Tasks 8.1.1, 8.1.2 and 8.1.3 (i.e., SSbD criteria & methodology, Toolbox Development and operationalization).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

20.1 ICPS – PIC 922722395

ICPS is involved in WP 6.2 (Integrative exposure and risk assessment)

In particular, ICPS will be mainly involved in A6.2.3 where it will participate in the development of case studies of mixture risk assessment of specific Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs). Particular efforts will be put on CAGs related to the nervous system where a tiered approach will be used (first

including prioritised pesticides, then chemicals spotted in the relevant scientific literature and finally chemicals identified in HBM studies). A top-down approach will be used for identification of the indicators for the common effect and the potential mechanistic information, i.e., common AOPs, KE etc. in the AOP-wiki and from in vitro-testing battery using the methodology implemented by EFSA, that could make the grouping more refined in the prioritized mixtures

ICPS will also contribute in the project P6.2.3 Real Life Mixtures with the identification and characterization of real-life mixtures exposure in farmers with available data from Italian farmers application regional/national database.

20.2 CNR-IRSA – PIC 999979500

In the second year all the activities of CNR-IRSA will be carried out in the framework of T4.2. In particular, CNR-IRSA will cooperate in the mapping of existing prioritisation schemes and then in the first phase of the configuration of an automated on-line tool. CNR-IRSA will make available their own experience in the prioritisation of specific classes of compounds, such as PFAS and pharmaceuticals to validate this tool. CNR-IRSA will contribute in the assessment of the effectiveness of the different prioritisation scheme. The rest of the CNR-IRSA's activities will be devoted to the designing (4.2.3) and carrying out (4.2.4) of the pilot study on PFAS, of which the Institute will act as key contributor for PFAS. In particular CNR-IRSA will coordinate the choice of the substances to be analysed, the list of sites in function of the different impacts and sources and the harmonisation of the sampling and laboratory activities. It will also contribute to sample collection and analysis in Italian hot spots and urban areas.

20.3 – IRFM – PIC 999661146

In year 2 will participate to WP 4, 5, 6, 8 and 9.

The goal of Project E01 (P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH) in the Task 4.3 is to mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) for (I) human community and (II) environmental exposure assessment. For WP4 IRFM will participate in activity (I) and during the second year will collect information on Wastewater- Based Epidemiology (WBE) methods available in the network in order to select target biomarkers to be investigated in wastewater and develop and validate targeted analytical methods.

Within WP5, IRFM will be active in 5.2.a, using in silico models for non-genotox carcinogenicity. In particular, we will predict all the selected substances using the models in VEGAHUB. Within 5.3.1, the attention will be related to the use of in silico VEGA models (including read-across) for AOP, to predict the MIE and KE of the selected substances.

In T6.1 the contribution of IRFM will be for the listing and evaluation of existing in silico models in VEGAHUB for the assays included in the IATA (e.g., fibrosis, thyroid, and genotox). In 6.2.2, QSAR will be used in support to the toxicokinetic modelling. Regarding 6.2.3, in silico models will be applied to cluster substances with similar mode of action. IRFM will participate to four case studies within T6.3: for endocrine disruptors, in silico models for genotox and carcinogenicity, plastics and skin sensitization. Within A6.4.2 IRFM will contribute to the project on methods with AI and machine learning for risk assessment, reviewing the available tools and methods published in the literature.

Within A8.1.3 IRFM will contribute to the software system for safe and sustainable by design. Within T8.2 IRFM will contribute to the identification of the criteria, strategy and tools (mainly computational approaches) for early warning systems, in relation to 8.2.2 and 8.2.3. IRFM will be active within 8.3 (8.3.2, 8.3.3 and 8.3.5) for the general network of computer systems in support to risk assessment. The contribution will be mainly related to models for hazard (both for the human and ecotoxicological endpoints), but also tools for environmental properties and physico-chemical characteristics will be addressed, as implemented within VEGAHUB, for predictive models, read-across and prioritization.

Within A9.4.3 IRFM will contribute to training activities for in the use of in silico models.

20.4 IUSS – PIC 997963355

In year 2 IUSS will work primarily on WP8 activities, both in task 8.1 (SSbD toolbox development) and in task 8.3 (contribution to the conceptual design of the PARC model network). In addition, IUSS is involved heavily in WP6 (task 6.2, activity 6.2.2 on PBK model development) and in WP3 (task 3.1, activity 3.1.b) regarding the setting up and running the PARC International Board.

In WP3 (activity 3.1.b), IUSS will support the running of the PARC International Board by keeping a regular contact with the IB members assigned to it and ensuring that the communication between PARC and these IB members is up to date and efficient. IUSS will also support as scientific secretariat the operation of the IB and the respective virtual and physical meetings.

In activity 6.2.2, IUSS will contribute to the further development of the models for As and Hg, and more specifically to the incorporation and validation of multiple routes of exposure (including inhalation and dermal exposure) for all species of mercury (methylmercury, inorganic mercury, and elemental mercury) and arsenic. IUSS will also contribute to the development of the detailed blood-brain barrier model of these compounds, to be able to provide refined internal exposure estimates in the brain during the early developmental stages (including in-utero exposure). The work carried out by IUSS will be included in project P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPB_INERIS_AUTH - Refinement and development of PBPB models for human risk assessment.

In Task 8.1 IUSS will co-lead the activity 8.1.2 on the development of the SSbD toolbox. Technically, IUSS will contribute to the physical implementation of the toolbox based on the conceptual design from D8.1 and will contribute to the integration of the results in PARCopedia. These activities fall within the remit of project P8.1.2.a_Y1_SSbD_toolbox_AUTH.

In Task 8.3 IUSS will support the development of the alpha version of the PARC model network platform and its application in selected use cases. The main use case in which IUSS will participate is the modeling of risk of bisphenols using existing data and models, as well as new datasets and modeling tools developed in the frame of PARC. In particular, IUSS will develop a computational tool based on systems biology and systems toxicology considerations and integrate HBM data and AOP-supporting data coming from omics results. These activities fall within the remit of project P8.3.2.a_Y1_DIMN_AUTH.

20.5 UMIL – PIC 999995796

During the second year, UMIL will be involved in T6.3 Review of risk assessment methodologies, evaluating the potential use of NAMs and any other available relevant information in the hazard and risk assessment of pesticides (in the remit of EFSA). Results can be compared to the ones of a similar case studies carried out in 6.3, in relation to chemical risk assessment in the ECHA, in order to improve the harmonization among different legislations whenever possible. The details are not yet available since the finalization of the project will be in May 2023.

Concerning A5.1.1 BPA Immunotoxicity activities will continue as agreed with the assessment of the effects of the selected BPA analogues on Th cells differentiation (e.g., Th1, Th2, Th17, Treg) and cytokine production, and the coordination of WP 5.1.1 together with ISS.

In A5.3.2, 5.3.3 UMIL will contribute to the activity of the Core group, Immunotoxicology and Neurotoxicology specialty groups settled after the first-year. In particular, UMIL will participate to set the framework for new AOP development or completion in the field of immunotoxicity (focus on respiratory sensitization) and neurotoxicity (focus on adult neurotoxicity) providing feedback on data gaps and suggesting relevant regulatory endpoints in the field of immune- and adult neurotoxicity.

Moreover, UMIL will be involved in WP 4.1, specifically in the activity 4.1.1.4 for the biological monitoring surveys in the Waste management and in the Health care sectors. The identification of biological indicators and the contact with the companies where the surveys will take place will be performed. Additionally, UMIL will support A4.1.2 the definition of the best suited exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies.

20.6 UNINA – PIC 999976590

During the second year, UNINA will be involved in WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP8. The major contribution will be in WP8 (Concepts and toolboxes), which UNINA co-leads. As WP8 co-leader is MB member, it participates in monthly MB meetings and is involved in WP1 and WP3. Regarding scientific activities, in WP8, UNINA will continue to be involved in the development and consolidation of new concepts and approaches (Task 8.1, Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)), whereas in WP4 it will be involved in Task 4.1 (Human Biomonitoring) aimed at consolidating, maintaining and further developing the human biomonitoring platform created in HBM4EU.

In WP1, UNINA will contribute to the scientific and administrative coordination and management activities, participating in Tasks 1.1 (Overall executive management and support of the Partnership), 1.2 (Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans), 1.3 (Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership) and 1.4 (Ethics framework) as a MB member.

In WP3, UNINA will contribute to the Task 3.2 (Communication, dissemination, and awareness) activities related to communication, dissemination and awareness with the scientific community and with all stakeholders that will be done through the different communication channels.

In WP4, UNINA will be involved in Task 4.1 (Human biomonitoring) and specifically in the fieldwork of the occupational studies on the healthcare sector and on the waste management sector. The design, planning, and implementation of the studies will be prepared, building further on experiences from HBM4EU. Furthermore, UNINA will continue the activity for the implementation of sentinel surveillance system as a tool to collect reliable and statistically representative data on environmental and occupational exposure and health on a European level.

In WP8, for Task 8.1, UNINA is co-leading the 8.1.3 activity regarding SSbD use cases. The work will focus on establishing and operating a first iteration of tests of various tools for SSbD in collaboration with industrial partners.

Specifically, in the activity 8.1.1 (Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation). UNINA will proceed in defining how to translate the EC SSbD criteria towards operationalisation, providing its experience in occupational health and taking into account ideas and needs of potential users that may provide guidance to the operationalization of the above-mentioned criteria. UNINA will contribute to the 8.1.2 activity (Toolbox development) addressing aspects relevant to inform toolbox development and its operationalization into use cases. UNINA will provide its strong experience in occupational risk assessment and sustainability that may be useful to provide contribution to the toolbox development, particularly as concerns safety and health of the workforce and the general population. As co-lead of the 8.1.3 Activity (Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators), UNINA will continue to provide efforts to organize the work for this activity. This will include to establish criteria for case studies and to identify suitable ones. An inventory of use cases already going on or being planned elsewhere (to avoid double work and facilitate maximum synergies) will be performed in order to organize possible case studies to test the toolbox applicability. This will be useful to support the operationalisation of the EC framework for SSbD criteria and methodology and to understand possible gaps, incentives and barriers for practical application according to an iterative, learning by doing approach. According to the conclusions derived from the Y1 work, UNINA will continue to work on activity 8.1.4 (Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalisation) sharing information derived from the toolbox application in use cases. The UNINA experience in occupational risk assessment and risk communication will contribute to this aim.

20.7 UNIPD – PIC 999995602

UNIPD is involved in T4.1 (Human biomonitoring) and T6.2 (Integrative exposure and risk assessment) and 6.4 (Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodology).

In particular, in the field of Human biomonitoring, UNIPD is involved in the fieldwork of HBM studies in the general population survey (adults) and occupational surveys (waste and health care workers) (4.1.1 General population survey, Targeted surveys, and Occupational surveys) and in (4.1.2) to define

the best-suited exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC, analyse the exposure biomarkers in the samples emerging from human biomonitoring task, analyse effect biomarkers in samples emerging from the human biomonitoring task). In particular in health care work, we will be involved in the monitoring of anesthetic gases. Regarding T6.2 UNIPD will be mainly involved in A6.2.3 where it will participate in the development of case studies of mixture risk assessment of specific CAGs. Particular efforts will be put on CAGs related to the nervous system.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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21- Riga Stradins University, LATVIA (RSU) PIC 999843118

During the second year, RSU will be involved in WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6 and WP9. The major contribution will be in WP4 and WP6.

In the WP1 RSU is represent as the Grant Signatory Board member and the National Hub Contact Point. In the WP 2 in Task 2.3 RSU as the National Hub Contact Point will participate in the discussions regarding on needs and a concept for a capacity building, developing an exit strategy and further developing and refining the monitoring framework with T1.3. In the WP 3 in Task 3.2 RSU as a National Hub Contact Point will participate in developing and implementing the communication strategy for PARC.

WP4, Task 4.1. (Human biomonitoring): RSU plan to continue contribute in preparation of supporting materials for aligned studies (task WP 4.1.1.1 Supporting materials). RSU is going to participate in the fieldwork in the general population survey (children and adults) (task WP 4.1.1.2 Aligned HBM studies in general population).

RSU is going to participate in the occupational survey focusing on the health care sector (P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_RUMC), and plan to start fieldwork of study, sampling in the work environment and samples collection for effect marker analyses.

Other activity within task is study on the implementation of a sentinel surveillance systems as a tool to collect reliable and statistically representative data on environmental and occupational exposure and health on a European level (P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven).

RSU in the task WP 4.1.2. “Laboratory analysis and quality assurance” - together with the partners are going to work on selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods, in terms of laboratory analysis and quality assurance and work on progress towards the design and future implementation of the chemical analysis action plan for the different HBM surveys.

The project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO will be continued.

WP6, Task 6.3. Work will be continued in the projects:

- P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS8_OccupReproDev_KI: In-depth reviews of the safety margin to reproductive and developmental toxicity for selected substances, including metals and exposures expected in health care
- and in the P6.3.2.c_Y1_CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL: Questionnaire study for workplaces and other relevant stakeholders (industrial/employee organizations, authorities), complemented with interviews, to evaluate how limit values and related information produced under the different regulatory processes are interpreted and used in workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practice.

WP9, Task 9.1 The mapping of the existing HBM laboratories and updating of the HBM catalogue will continue in Y2. The same will be done for laboratories and networks on air, indoor and articles (work on those has started in Y1).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>21.1 UL- PIC 999871830</p> <p>During the second year, UL will be involved in WP1 and WP4 activities.</p> <p>WP1: UL is involved as affiliated entity.</p> <p>WP4: Within the WP4, UL is planning to contribute to the Tasks 4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) and 4.3 (Innovative methods for monitoring). In Task 4.2, UL will continue to participate in the pilot project P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU, and involvement is planned for operating and implementing the environmental monitoring campaign for the selected case studies on PFAS and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds (EDCS). Under the Task 4.3, UL team will participate in the project P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH, continuing to support and contribute with our input in actions A2.0: Collection of information on methods available in the network (support for the review and evaluation of available methods) and A2.2: Method development for new sampling and enrichment tools (contribution to the new sampling tools).</p>	
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

<p>22- NACIONALINE VISUOMENES SVEIKATOS PRIEZIUROS LABORATORIJA, LITHUANIA (NPHSL) – PIC 933651094</p> <p>In the second year of PARC NPHSL will participate in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> WP 1 as the National Hub Contact Point and Grant Signatory Board member. WP 2 in Task 2.3 as the National Hub Contact Point regarding discussions on needs and a concept for a capacity building, developing an exit strategy and further developing and refining the monitoring framework with T1.3. WP 3 in Task 3.2 as a National Hub Contact Point will participate in developing and implementing the communication strategy for PARC. WP 4. Due to the fact that NPHSL is an LST EN ISO/IEC 17025 accredited laboratory, it will be concentrated around laboratory analysis and quality assurance. Therefore, under Task 4.1 NPHSL will participate on the definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods. WP 9 in tasks 9.1, 9.2 and 9.4. Under Task 9.1 NPHSL will focus on identification of existing infrastructures, available knowledge, and various resources. Also, will participate in creating a database of laboratory networks. Under Task 9.2. NPHSL will participate in further developing the pilot monitoring catalogues on Y1 (and Y2)-priority networks, in particular the air monitoring network, as well as will collaborate on the development of Y2-priority catalogues encompassing the aquatic environment. Under Task 9.4 NPHSL will focus on the preparation of materials that will support to training local organizers, and assist in training evaluation assessment. 	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

23- LIETUVOS SVEIKATOS MOKSLU UNIVERSITETAS, LITHUANIA (LSMU) – PIC 972782446

During the 2nd year LSMU will be involved in WP1, WP 4 and WP 6:

WP 1: LSMU is involved as a Grant Signatory Board member.

T4.1 (Human biomonitoring): LSMU will contribute to prepare supporting materials for aligned studies (4.1.1.1 Supporting materials) and to assess relationship between information on occupation and HBM data from general population survey (4.1.1.4 Occupational feasibility study). LSMU is going to participate in the fieldwork in the general population survey (adults) (4.1.1.2 Aligned HBM studies in general population (adults)). In 4.1.2.1 LSMU will contribute to define the best suited exposure biomarkers and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies in PARC. LSMU will contribute analyzing exposure effects in A4.1.4 (Data management and analysis) and preparing a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system in Europe in A4.1.5.

WP6: LSMU will work in a project related to a review of guidance values targeting occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants (A6.3.1 Review of risk assessment methodology (effect specific reviews on risk assessment)) and in OPREMIX project on Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (6.4.1.1 Develop regulatory approaches and methods for chemical mixtures).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

24- LABORATOIRE NATIONAL DE SANTE, LUXEMBOURG (LNS) – PIC 911247586

During the 2nd year LNS will be involved in WP1, WP3, WP 4, WP 6 and WP9 as follows:

WP1 - Partnership Management and Coordination

T1.1- Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

LNS is Grant Signatory and National Hub for Luxembourg, and coordinates the contracts and links with the affiliated entities.

WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness

T3.1 - Task 3.1. Building effective interactions

LNS is part of the international board and have submitted applications for stakeholder forum on behalf of the International Society of Exposure Science (ISES) – European Chapter.

T3.2 - Communication, dissemination, and awareness

LNS will continue the alignment between PARC and the ongoing exposome studies in Europe (EXIMIOUS, EPHOR), as well as with the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN).

WP4 – Monitoring and exposure

T4.1 - Human Biomonitoring

A4.1.1 - Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies

- Transversal activities: LNS is actively involved in the WG's of the S4.1.1 (Development of

supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct) and is co-leading the WG1 concerning the review and update of materials developed under HBM4EU.

- PARC_P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO: LNS will set-up the general population survey in children and adults
- PARC_P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven: LNS participate in the setting-up of sentinel system in Luxembourg together with the 2 major occupational health services.
- PARC_P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_RUMC (own budget) LNS participate in the healthcare survey on behalf of Luxembourg together with the different stakeholders in the country.
- PARC_P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL LNS participate in the healthcare survey on behalf of Luxembourg together with the different stakeholders in the country.

A4.1.2 - Supporting activities progress: Laboratory analysis and quality assurance.

- Within this transversal activity, LNS is leading the S4.1.2.1 Exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods, to ensure prioritisation of compounds to be studied under the general survey and occupational studies.

A4.1.3 - Link exposure and health related information

- PARC_P4.1.3.3a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO: LNS participates in the identification of health outcomes in relation to exposure and is part of the core team for the effect biomarkers.

A4.1.4 - Data management and analysis

- PARC_P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO: LNS works on the further valorization of the data collected in the HBM4EU.

A4.1.5 - Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

- PARC_P4.1.5a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO: LNS works together with VITO towards the set-up of a stable framework beyond the financing only via specific projects

T4.2 - Environmental and multisource monitoring

1. P4.2.1_2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS: LNS participate in the applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring.
2. P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU: LNS participate in the establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring via a pilot addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors. LNS will use its expertise in indoor dust as promising matrix for indoor exposome evaluation.

T4.3 - Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

- PARC_P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR: LNS participates with its analytical chemistry expertise to the definition of QA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA-based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices
- PARC_P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Luxembourg is setting-up a mother – infant cohort and plans to contribute with samples and innovative sampling methods including DBS and wristbands
- PARC_P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS: LNS is co-leading this project with INRS.

WP 6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

T6.2 - Integrative exposure and risk assessment

- PARC_P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO: LNS is leading the WG on Consumers products exposure, in the context of indoor environment exposure modeling and sources identification.
- PARC_P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES: LNS is actively involved in the inventory of existing models and tools for occupational exposure as well as the data inventory and gaps analysis with special focus on the occupational studies developed under HBM4EU.
- PARC_P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM: LNS is participating in the WG1 on HBM data and risk assessment with special focus on the occupational studies developed under HBM4EU

WP9 - Building infrastructural and human capacities

T9.1 - Laboratory networking

- PARC_P9.1.1.a_Y1_HBM CATALOGUES_ISCIII_MU: LNS participates in the further definition of capacities (laboratory networks and information catalogues) for human biomonitoring and population cohorts.

T9.2 - Building exposure monitoring capacities

- PARC_P9.2.1.a_Y1_ENV CATALOGUES_MU_ISCIII: LNS participates in the further definition of capacities (laboratory networks and information catalogues) for environmental monitoring.

T9.3 - Joint activities –harmonization

- PARC_P9.3.1.a_Y1_QAQC_WR2: LNS will work towards the harmonized of QA/QC in laboratory testing for environmental and human biomonitoring. LNS is co-leading the WG on the reporting / data acceptance, with LABERCA.

T9.4 - Training:

- LNS is participating in several aspects of this transversal activity.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

24.1 LIH – PIC 998331858

During the 2nd year LIH will be involved in WP5:

Belongs to WP5/Task5.1a/BPA For BPA and BPA analogs showing a neurodevelopmental toxicity, It is proposed to include epigenetic investigations, as secondary endpoints, particularly DNA methylation. We will look at methylation on both the selected target genes and the whole epigenome after exposure of inducible Pluripotent Stem Cells (iPSCs) pre- and post- differentiation into neurons to BPA and BPA alternatives.

Belongs to WP5/Task5.2a1/immunotox - LIH will address whether human NK cell phenotype and functions are durably altered in adulthood in individuals having been exposed early in life to bisphenol analogs compared with respective-free control subjects. *In vitro*, we will used NK cells derived from Human CD34+ Hematopoietic Stem Cells to investigate how bisphenol analogs alone or in mixture trigger immunosuppression/induce immunotoxicity.

24.2 LIST – PIC 934320200

P_5.2.1_NAMs_Y1_SubProject_RespSens

LIST has already participated in the regular meetings within this activity to work on the AOP for respiratory sensitization and the involved immune cells.

P_5.3.2_NAMs_Y1_SubGroup_RespSens

LIST is participating in the regular meetings currently ongoing in defining the practical work to be performed within year 2. It is foreseen that the members of this activity test chemicals carefully selected for their potential for respiratory sensitization in their respective in vitro model. LIST has established a 3D in vitro model cultured at the air liquid interphase which is able to differentiate respiratory sensitizers (patented and published) and has a senior role in this activity.

P_6.1.1.a_Y1_IATA_Human_Relevance

LIST is participating in the regular meetings currently ongoing.

P_6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED

LIST is participating in the regular meetings currently ongoing and will take a senior role when it comes to thyroid hormone as LIST is test developer for 2 out of 18 assays for thyroid hormone disruption currently under evaluation by EURL ECVAM and NETVAL.

PARC_6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX

LIST is participating in the regular meetings currently ongoing and will contribute with its experience in genotoxicity assays performed *in vitro* in a cell culture model for the alveolar region for which a first publication has already been submitted.

24.3 UniLU – PIC 999878620

During the second year, UniLU will be involved in WP4, WP7 and WP8. More specifically:

A4.2.5: Endocrine disruptors and PFAS project (EDC_PFAS) to improve the identification and exchange of information on endocrine disruptors (EDC) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), including the addition of PARC lists to the NORMAN Suspect List Exchange.

T4.3: Involvement in T4.3_T03 to support the development of the Early Warning System in WP8, as well as T4.3_T04 to establish the necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS. UniLU is also in T4.3_H01/Project 4.3_01 to develop HRMS methods for human perinatal exposure to chemicals of concern, plus T4.3_E01/Project 4.3_02 on mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants.

In WP7 UniLU will be mostly involved in T7.2 and will contribute a member to the FAIR Implementation Team to support the integration of FAIR data within PARC, along with the development and maintenance of FAIR resources to support PARC, such as MassBank and NORMAN-SLE.

In WP8, UniLU is involved in T8.2, specifically Activity 8.2.1 (Concept and validation of suspect and nontarget screening monitoring tools), Activity 8.2.2 (development and evaluation of the computational method) and Activity 8.2.4 (computational framework to support the Early Warning System, specifically with the risk ranking of NERCs)

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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25- RIJKSINSTITUUT VOOR VOLKSGEZONDHEID EN MILIEU, NETHERLANDS (RIVM) – PIC 999991431

During Year 2, RIVM will continue its involvement in the following Work Packages (WP):

WP1 Management of AEs, NHCP, Grant signatory.

WP2 Task 2.1 RIVM will be involved in the process of priority setting and the review process of new research activities and ensure that they target the regulatory challenges.

WP3, RIVM will contribute to the website and the communication strategy and to improve stakeholder involvement.

WP5 Tasks 5.2 RIVM will be involved in developing methodologies that will directly aid chemical hazard identification. More specifically, RIVM will continue its participation in the projects on non-genotoxic carcinogens (P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE), immunotoxicity (P5.2.1_Y1_immunotoxicity_INSERTM), and developmental neurotoxicity (P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_UU).

WP6 RIVM will, together with KEMI, continue to **coordinate** WP6. Regular meetings between WP6 leads, as well as with WP6 task leads will be organised, to discuss management and content. The WP6 leads will also set up and/or participate in meetings with the leaders from other WPs, in particular WPs 4, 5 and 8. Furthermore, WP6 leads will organize meetings to discuss the regulatory implementations of the various projects.

Task 6.1 RIVM will continue to coordinate task 6.1, jointly with the task leaders SCIENSANO and UL-LACDR. RIVM will contribute to the projects on IATA for endocrine disruption (P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen), and IATA for genotoxicity (P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano). RIVM will continue to coordinate the project on human relevance (P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM).

Task 6.2 RIVM will contribute to P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO and In P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES, the strategy to assess aggregate exposure through different living environments (occupational, general environment, domestic environment) and different routes of entry (inhalation, dermal, ingestion) will continue to be developed. RIVM will contribute P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS) and mixtures (in collaboration with activity 6.2.3, P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM). The focus will be on PB-PK models addressing the kinetics of pesticides.

RIVM will coordinate the P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM, the working groups on hazard and kinetics will continue to collect, organize and develop information to set toxicological thresholds as well as kinetic models and parameters for the prioritized chemical families and effects (i.e. pesticides and NAM/NAN effects, PFAS and immune effect, metals and kidney effects mycotoxins and immune and haematological effects). RIVM will contribute to the projects on in 6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators.

WP8 task 8.1

Contribution of RIVM to task 8.1

RIVM is (co)lead of task 8.1 and will (co-)coordinate the activities in 8.1, including organizing regular meeting with partners. During the second year of PARC, contributions of RIVM will consist of

- RIVM will (co)coordinate drafting of the communication plan and making infrastructure blueprint operational aiming at an efficient and timely communication approach for dialogue between PARC 8.1 and the EC, other PARC work packages and outside PARC (activity 8.1.1).
- Also RIVM will (co) coordinate the element ‘Keeping pace with state of the art and lessons learned’ through the systematic identification of gaps, barriers and incentives to gain insight in the completeness, feasibility and applicability of the EC JRC SSbD framework taking into account additional developments. These developments might include aspects such as ongoing work in translating the EC JRC framework to a flexible, tiered, stepwise, stage-gate approach. In co-creation with all relevant stakeholders, these aspects need to be further developed from the conceptual stage to the operational stage (activity 8.1.1).
- RIVM will support the further development of the toolbox and its content providing state-of-

<p>the-art knowledge on developments and instruments applicable for risk assessment and sustainability assessment. Where appropriate RIVM will contribute to the development of tools, and provide input on specific aspects of the design of the toolbox (activity 8.1.2).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RIVM will contribute to further identify, develop and monitor the use cases and indicators. RIVM will support the follow-up actions resulting from the conclusions of year 1 (activity 8.1.3). <p>RIVM will together with UBA co-lead the activity on development of knowledge sharing platform and educational material. Focus of year 1 was the development of the inception plan. In year 2 the activities will build on the inventories and overviews and subsequent assessment made in year 1, now focusing on building on the developing PARC infrastructure to enable knowledge sharing and education (activity 8.1.4).</p>	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>25.1 KWR – PIC 998279769</p> <p>During the second year of PARC, KWR Water Research Institute (KWR) will contribute to WP4, WP6, and WP7.</p> <p>In task 4.3 KWR will contribute to the development of wastewater-based epidemiology for monitoring human exposure to environmental pollutants. This includes the development of analysis methods to detect and measure exposure biomarkers in wastewater and link them to population studies and, ultimately, health endpoints. KWR is going to work with other partners in project E_01 of Task 4.3 on the selection of relevant biomarkers to monitor in wastewater samples. Work will focus on collecting information on available methods as well as establishing suspect lists of exposure biomarkers which have potential to be measured in wastewater and which can be used to derive community-wide exposure data.</p> <p>In activity 6.1.1. KWR will contribute to the development of an integrated approach for testing and assessments (IATA) of potentially adverse effects of substances with the focus on DNA damage (genotoxicity). Mapping and evaluating the advance outcome pathways (AOP) and associated new approach methods (NAM) to design an IATA is planned. The key contribution of KWR is sharing the experience with various in vitro genotoxicity bioassays, as well as our experience with derivation and the use of trigger values for quantitative evaluation of the bioassay results, in the context of water quality assessment.</p> <p>Regarding the aggregation of different exposure sources and pathways (activity 6.2.1), KWR will contribute to the development of a model to evaluate exposure to lead, which also allows us to determine exposure to other substances in drinking water, including those that may emerge or disappear in the water distribution system. In task 6.2.2 KWR will contribute on the availability of models/tools for the risk assessment of PFAS and the required input (monitoring data).</p> <p>In activities 7.1.1 and 7.1.3, KWR will contribute to the efforts needed to safeguard good data quality and availability, and in 7.3.2 to the knowledge relating to the statistical methods including uncertainty that may be applied.</p> <p>25.2 TNO – PIC 999988909</p> <p>During the second year of PARC TNO will contribute to the innovative sampling methods for occupational exposure in P4.3.2b_H02 by developing and testing the CID sensor for crystalline silica in the building & construction sector. In WP6 TNO will actively engage in developing the strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures in activity 6.2.1 by providing input for the inventory of exposure assessment models for multiple sources and routes for general population</p>	

and workers and looking into the interoperability of models for aggregate exposures. Furthermore, TNO facilitates the sharing of information and knowledge on aggregate exposure from the H2020 RISKHUNT3R project. In activity 6.2.2 TNO will contribute to the lifetime PBPK model for PFAS (PFOA, PFOS) by simulating aggregate exposure of workers to PFAS. Furthermore, TNO will work on the generic PBPK model for pesticides, using physicochemical properties of chemicals such as chlorpyrifos, to predict the kinetics of the chemical after oral, dermal or inhalation exposure by simulating kinetics of chemicals with limited to no data. In WP7, TNO is leading task 7.1. As to the task 7.1. TNO will be responsible towards updating the DMP, via interaction with task 7.2, in particular data liaisons/data stewards within the FAIR Implementation Team. Further, TNO is responsible for the PARC FAIR Data Policy (M18, D7.2) (including publication). In addition, TNO will be involved in all other activities of Task 7.1 (7.1.1., 7.1.2, 7.1.3).

25.3 RUMC – PIC 892057785:

In WP4, T4.1 RUMC will co-lead the healthcare survey (P4.1.1.4c_Y2_Occuphealthcare_TTL_RUMC). RUMC will prepare a generic study protocol to support the application for ethics approval in each of the participating country. The involvement of hospitals and, subsequently, the recruitment of healthcare workers will be coordinated to reach the target numbers of participants for each of the priority substance groups of hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anesthetics, and disinfection and cleaning products. RUMC will sign up to analysis of biomonitoring samples in response to a call prepared by A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance; RUMC will contribute to P4.1.1.4.b_Y2_SentinelSystem_KULeuven project by collection of questionnaire data. In A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information RUMC will contribute to P4.1.3.1a_Y2_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA by preparing a first draft substance dossier and guidance value proposal for hexavalent chromium.

RUMC will be involved to P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO regarding the justification of effect biomarkers specifically for the priority substances for occupational studies.

In WP6, T6.2 RUMC will be involved in P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES RUMC and contribute to the analysis of aggregate exposures with a focus on pesticide and biocide applications. The focus will be on the different sources and routes of exposures in biological and conventional farmers, residents close to these farms and consumers in an urban setting. In P6.2.2.a PBPK modelling RUMC will contribute to PBPK modelling of selected pesticides by use of data from on-going human volunteer studies. In P6.2.3.a RealLifemixtures RUMC will contribute to innovative approaches to study mixtures in risk assessment with a focus on pesticides exposures in farmers, residents who live close to farmland and consumers, based on the early results of the SPRINT study. RUMC will contribute to P6.2.4.a HIADDataAvailability from on-going population-based studies related to neurotoxic substances such as organophosphorus flame retardants (OPFR) and pesticides and explore opportunities for the use of the outcomes of these studies. P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO by providing access to data from an on-going studies in occupational and residential settings. In P6.2.4.c HIACaseStudies RUMC will develop a proposal for a study in the Healthy Brain Cohort in 30-39 year old adults to study how exposure to neurotoxic substances (OPFR and pesticides) explains selected cognitive performance evaluated in an experimental setting.

24.4 UL-LACDR – PIC 999974553

During the second year of PARC UL-LACDR will be involved in WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8.

In WP5 UL-LACDR participates in Task 5.2 in the non-genotoxic carcinogenesis project and will uncover the applicability of high throughput microscopy in combination with cell line fluorescent reporters as well as induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (iPSC)-based reporters for determining relevant key event activation. The latter will be established in hepatocyte like cells and mammary gland epithelial like cells. In addition, high throughput transcriptomics will be applied. UL-LACDR is Task leader for

Task 5.3 with a particular focus on activities 5.3.1 and 5.3.3. UL-LACDR also the project leader of the "Systems toxicology" project in T5.3 (P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR). The activities in this project will involve transcriptomics data generation and analysis of human biopsy samples from diseased liver and kidney. Moreover, we participate in the AOP development project 5.3.2.a with contributing to development of AOPs for non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and immunotoxicity (P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm).

UL-LACDR co-leads task 6.1, and leads the STOT project (P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR) within this task. Within task 6.1, in year 2 UL-LACDR will finalize the generic dynamical modeling framework that is currently being developed and which can be used for qAOP development when sufficient dynamic data are available. UL-LACDR is involved in qAOP development for the IATAs on STOT, ED and GENTOX, and will start with creating quantitative descriptions of KERs with data becoming available in year 2, either based on the dynamic modeling framework, or through a response-response modeling approach. Within the STOT and GENTOX (P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano) projects UL-LACDR will also contribute to IATA design and case studies, by generating data with selected NAMs, in collaboration with task 5.3.

In WP7 UL-LACDR will contribute to task 7.1 on data management planning, with a focus on imaging and transcriptomics data. In task 7.2 we will contribute to suitability of existing databases/repositories, and suitability of onsite solutions. In task 7.3 we will actively contribute to the fair implementation taskgroup (FIT) as well as integration of omics data.

In WP8 we will participate to computational toolbox implementation, with a focus on platforms for toxicogenomics data interpretation.

25.5 UU-IRAS – PIC 999985805

During the second year of PARC UU-IRAS will contribute to WP4, WP5, and WP6.

In activity 4.1.1 UU-IRAS will contribute by providing access to readily collected samples in the Specimen-NL study and contributing to discussions on suggested analyses that can be conducted in those samples.

In activity 4.1.4 UU-IRAS will contribute to the project “further analysis of data generated in HBM4EU” (P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO). In this project we are responsible for mixtures analyses and will suggest and lead analyses for mixtures analyses in the HBM4EU Specimen study that were not yet addressed in HBM4EU and in the aligned studies, where possible. There is a strong link with activity 6.2.3 on mixture exposure and risk assessment.

In WP5, UU-IRAS is involved in task 5.1a and 5.2a. In 5.1a new NAMs and assays for immunotoxic events will be developed, with innate immune responses as key events, intestinal epithelial-leukocyte interaction using the toxins: BPA analogs and natural toxins. In 5.2a, a human mesenchymal stem cell model to measure adipocyte differentiation and function of metabolism disrupting chemicals will be further developed. Serum free approaches including transcriptomics, 3D spheroid analyses. Finally, we will investigate the influence chemicals on both models using co cultures.

In activity 6.1.2 IRAS-UU will contribute to an IATA case study on EDCs. In activity 6.2.3 UU-IRAS will contribute to the project on “Real Life Mixtures” by contributing data from the Specimen study, linked to activity 4.1.4, and contributing to methodological developments for the description and interpretation of real-life mixture data and their use in risk assessment (through network analyses).

UU-IRAS is co-lead of activity 6.2.4 on Human health impact assessment and risk indicators. Our research focus in that task is on methodological development of methods for health impact assessment for chemicals (P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS). In year two we will build on the inventorization of methods that was conducted in year 1 and select, in discussion with the group and our co-leads, one

or more specific methodological challenges to work on.

25.6 VUA – PIC 954530344

VUA is co-task leader of task 4.3. Within this task, VUA will contribute with effect-directed analysis and suspect/non-target screening. VUA will also contribute to Task 5.2a with the development of thyroid hormone transport assays and screening of selected chemicals, to be established within the task. The transporters will specifically be aimed to capture effects on the blood-cerebral fluid barrier in the developing child. Other involvements of VUA include product screening for chemical leachates (activity 6.4.3), and scientific and technical tool development for early warning on chemical risks (Task 8.2 and 8.3).

25.7 WR – PIC 999547365

Two different groups from WR are involved, WR-WFSR and WR-BIOM. During the second year, WR will contribute to WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, and WP9.

In WP4, WR-WFSR is involved in Task 4.3 on the development of innovative methods for monitoring and surveys, particularly suspect and non-target screening methods. WR-WFSR is (co)lead of project P4.3.1.b_T02, and will contribute to projects P4.3.1a_T01/1d_T04, P4.3.2a_H01/2b_H02/2c_H03, P4.3.4a_F02.

In WP5, WR-WFSR will contribute to Task 5.2 and Task 5.3. In Task 5.2 the emphasis is on the development and improvement of NAMs for determining the toxic effects of chemicals on the immune system (5.2.1). The focus of WR-WFSR in Task 5.3 is on toxicokinetic experiments, the development of PBK models and the combination of these computer models with mechanistic toxicological information (5.3.4). WFSR also contributes (to a lesser extent) to the activities related to systems toxicology (5.3.1) and AOP development (5.3.2).

In WP6, WR-WFSR will mainly contribute to Task 6.2 with the emphasis on refining PBK models to address specific aspects of human risk assessment (6.2.2) and on the application of PBK models in the risk assessment of chemical mixtures (6.2.3). To a limited extent, work is also being done on the development of IATAs (6.1.1). WR-BIOM will participate in activities 6.2.1 (functional design for aggregate exposure models), 6.2.2 (link of PBK models to model network), 6.2.3 (use of HBM data and statistical models for real-life mixtures), 6.2.4 (link of health impact assessment to model network), with the main objective of aligning the models used or developed in these activities with the model platform being developed in WP8.

In WP7, WR-BIOM will be involved in activities that aim to achieve good alignment of data infrastructures and model platforms, by participating in activities 7.2.2 (linking FAIR data to model network), 7.2.3 (standards and harmonisation), 7.3.2 (uncertainty analysis) and 7.3.3 (linking non-structured data), with the main objective of aligning the models and data used or developed in these activities with the model platform being developed in WP8.

In WP8, WR-WFSR will contribute to Task 8.2 and focuses on the use of AI as a tool for emerging risk identification and early warning monitoring (8.2.1). WR-BIOM is task leader of Task 8.3 (integrative models) which aims to create an integrative network of models for exposure, hazard and risk assessment considering food and other sources.

In WP9, WR-WFSR is task leader of Task 9.3. The activities aim to harmonize as much as possible the diversity of QA/QC procedures and guidelines in the field of laboratory analysis (both chemical analysis, bioassays, as well as toxicity tests and toxicokinetics), and will maintain close connections

with the QA/QC related tasks and activities in WP4.1/2/3, WP5 and WP8.2.

25.8 WU-TOX – PIC 999981634

During the second year of PARC WU-TOX will contribute to WP5, WP6 and WP8.

In WP5, WU-TOX contribute to the following two tasks:

In activity 5.1.1.a Toxins (P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE), WU-TOX will contribute by focussing on extrahepatic metabolism of Enniatins, for instance (anaerobic) intestinal microbial, intestinal epithelial metabolism and potentially placenta in consultation with the other partners in the toxins project in task 5.1.

In activity 5.3.4.a PBK kinetics (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer) WU-TOX will use input from the other tasks and data from the literature to develop a life-stage PBK model for pregnancy and foetal development. In this task we will focus on the toxicokinetic identification of key stages of foetal vulnerability to toxins.

In WP6 WU-TOX is involved in Task 6.1, in projects P61.1.a, P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM), P6.1.1.c, (P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano) P6.1.1.d. (P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR). Here WU-TOX applies the toxicokinetic PBK modelling into quantitative in vitro to in vivo extrapolations. For the toxicodynamics WU-TOX focuses on specific maternal and foetal liver toxicity of the chemicals studied in WP5.

Lastly, WU-TOX will follow the discussion in WP8.3 on integrative models, to explore potential integration of PBK and QIVIVE approaches into hazard and risk assessment of chemicals.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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26- FOLKEHELSEINSTITUTTET, NORWAY (NIPH) – PIC 999478883

During the second year of PARC, NIPH will contribute to:

NIPH will contribute to activities in all sub-tasks in 4.1. We foresee preparatory work to involve our Norwegian Environmental Biobank (NEB) in the general population survey, and contribution to activities related to Laboratory analysis and quality assurance. NIPH will lead sub activity 4.1.2.4 (Harmonise and improve analytical methods across laboratories and define reference analytical methods when possible). NIPH will participate in revision of HBM-guidance values for mercury and PFASs in P4.1.3.1a. NIPH will be involved in all aspects of P4.1.4.2.a (Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU) and will lead the work on exposure-effect associations.

NIPH co-leads activity 5.1.1 with a focus on closing data gaps on hazards for human health. Managing the activities, close contact with the project leaders, interactions with agencies and reporting to the WP leaders/MB is included in the task leader role. Initially, two mycotoxins and several BPA analogues/alternatives will be studied in 5.1.1 and endpoints as genotoxicity, endocrine disruption, immunotoxicology and metabolism and kinetics are in scope. Within activity 5.1.1, NIPH will contribute with experimental work on immunosuppression of the mycotoxins Enniatins and Alternaria species. Further discussions around the Corona vaccination study will be initiated with interesting parties with the goal to submit a project proposal in the area of immunosuppression.

NIPH will contribute to task 5.2 with experimental and theoretical work for further development of NAMs in the areas of immunosuppression and developmental neurotoxicology. In Task 5.2.1e DNT,

we will first focus on the testing of different PFAS and their mixture, and by developing human-based *in vitro* methods for DNT testing with focus on synaptogenesis the first 1-2 years. The data obtained from 5.2 in addition with supplementary literature data will be used in task 5.3 to further develop AOPs for neurotoxicity and immunotoxicity. Scientists from NIPH are coordinating the taskforce (subgroup SG1 and SG3) on immunotoxicology and neurodevelopment in activity 5.3.2. NIPH will contribute to the effect marker study for immunotoxicity in activity 5.3.4.

NIPH will also contribute to several activities under 6.1, 6.2, 9.1 and 9.3 with e.g. further refinement of the plans, contribution of data and integration of data. NIPH will contribute with a case study on aggregated exposure of PFAS's in the EuroMix biomonitoring study in 6.2.1. NIPH will participate in analysis of mixtures/real-life co-exposure observations in 6.2.3. NIPH will contribute to the deliverable "D 9.1 Initial laboratory catalogue and design of the network platform (dashboard) Y1" planned under Task 9.1. NIPH will also be a part of Task 9.3 core group with interest in *in vitro/in silico* work.

Under activity 6.2.4 NIPH participates in two projects on improvement of Health Impact Assessment (HIA) methodologies and inventory of HIA data for PARC priority chemicals.

Activity 6.4.2 – NIPH, represented by VKM, will lead the project "Next generation risk assessment applied in practice", developing validity tools for *in vitro* (year one and two) and *in silico* models/methods (year two).

The experimental infrastructure at NIPH (including VKM) as described in the partner description (human biomonitoring laboratory, bioanalytical labs, *in vitro* labs, molecular biology labs, cell biology labs), register- and biobank studies (MoBa, NEB, HUMIS, EuroMix) and experience with systematic literature reviews and risk assessment will be used in the planned work.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

26.1 IMR – PIC 999548432

During the second year of PARC, IMR will contribute to activities in 5.1.1. To close data gaps on human exposure to Enniatins (and their metabolites) through the consumption of farmed fish, the experimental and computational infrastructure of the IMR will be used as described in the partner description. In short, we will apply previously developed *in silico* analyses pipelines to computationally predict enniatin metabolites and perform (Q)SAR-based toxicity predictions. A multi-criteria decision-making based ranking of mycotoxin metabolites of most concern for human safety will be performed in relation to both their predicted toxicity endpoints and occurrence data obtained from mycotoxin exposure experiments in farmed fish.

26.2 STAMI – PIC 953521738

During the second year of PARC, STAMI will contribute to WPs 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 4.1, 4.3, 5.1.1, 6.1-6.4, and 9.1-9.4.

In task 2.2, STAMI will continue the work with preparing the PARCrouté document for implementation of NGRA, focusing on occupational regulatory toxicology.

In task 3.1, STAMI will establish Stakeholder Forum and International Boards, and in 3.2 STAMI will contribute to occupational safety and health (OSH) related communication, dissemination and

awareness towards relevant European stakeholders.

In WP4, STAMI will continue planning for and will carry out an occupational HBM survey in the waste management sector, including study design and supporting materials (4.1.1), laboratory analysis (4.1.2), linking exposure and health data (4.1.3), and data management and analysis (4.1.4). In 4.3.2, we will continue our work on using wristband sampling for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern. During Y2, STAMI will recruit a PARC funded post doc. for the work in WP4.

In WP5, to close data gaps on human health hazards (5.1.1), STAMI will carry out an immunotoxicity study with *Alternaria* toxins, including reporter assays and omics analysis. STAMI will recruit a PARC funded post doc. for the work in activity 5.1.1.

STAMI is engaged in several tasks in WP6. In task 6.1, STAMI will participate on the planning and executing of four IATA case studies: Human Relevance Assessment (P6.1.1.a), Endocrine Disruption (P6.1.1.b), Genotoxicity (P6.1.1.c), and Specific Target Organ Toxicity (P6.1.1.d). The institute's engagement in these projects will include experimental work. In WP6.2, STAMI will participate in the projects on aggregate exposures (P6.2.1.b), real-life mixtures (P6.2.3.a), and health impact assessment (P6.2.4.c and P6.2.4.d). The institute will continue working on the WP6.3 case studies: Methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment in reducing risk (CS2), Workplace risk assessment methodologies (CS3), Occupational exposure to reproductive and developmental toxicants (CS8), and Skin sensitization and risk assessment methodologies (CS9). In the latter case study, a STAMI researcher will act as co-supervisor of a PhD-student. In P6.4.1, STAMI will continue the work on two case studies to Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures. STAMI will recruit a PARC funded post doc. to support the work in the different projects in WP6.

STAMI will participate on all WP9 tasks (9.1-9.4) and the institute has a co-leader function on a working group in 9.3: Framework for QA/QC of chemical analyses and for biological effect markers.

26.3 NILU – PIC 999654162

During the second year of PARC, NILU will contribute to several activities in tasks 2.2, 2.3, 4.2, 4.3, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 6.1, 6.3, 8.1, 8.2 and 8.3.

In task 2.2 NILU will support the creation of the NGRA roadmap, from the determination of the vision and scope, to the framework development and implementation. NILU will also contribute to the network organization within and outside this task (external projects and stakeholders).

In task 2.3 NILU contribute to the activities towards the exit strategy.

In task 4.2 NILU will contribute with expert knowledge about PFAS and EDCs and with analytical capacity.

In 5.1.1.b Bisphenol-A (BPA), NILU will support the process of data gap filling review in the hazard assessment of bisphenol-A alternatives to improve their risk assessment.

In 5.2.1.a Non-genotoxic carcinogens NILU will apply a 3D breast cancer model and apply innovative NAMs addressing relevant mechanisms for carcinogenesis to identify NGTxCs. Several chemical controls (positive and negatives) will be tested during 1st and 2nd year before moving to the PARC chemicals. In addition, NILU will provide data from the Cell Transformation Assay, an important NAM for the development of an IATA for NGTxCs.

In 5.3.2 NILU will contribute to the development of AOPs

In P6.1.1.c_IATA_GENTOX, NILU will contribute to the design of IATAs based on AOP networks and NAMs

In 6.3 CS11_Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, NILU will contribute to establish interactions within and outside PARC and reviewing the

methodologies employed under different regulatory frameworks.

In task 8.1 NILU will continue to contribute to the co-creation process on operationalisation by furthering activities from year 1. We will translate our experience from SSbD on nanomaterials (NMs) to broader applications on chemicals and materials (8.1.1).

NILU will also support development of the toolbox, where possible by making own tools available. We will translate our experience from SSbD on nanomaterials (NMs) to broader applications on chemicals and materials (8.1.2). Finally we will contribute to the development and testing of use cases decided upon by the T8.1 team (8.1.3).

In task 8.2 NILU will contribute to development of prioritisation mechanism and overall, to EWS (based on the outcomes of activities in T4.2).

26.4 NIVA – PIC 997826585

During the second year of PARC, NIVA will contribute to WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8 in the following manner.

Activities 5.1.2, 5.2.2 and 5.3.2: support the review and assessment of NAMs for ED effects, perform *in silico* (hazard characterisation) and experimental studies (aquatic invertebrate(s)).

A6.4.1: Contribute to review, assessment and guidelines for mixture assessment tools using environmental case studies.

A6.4.2: Support work to assess, demonstrate and develop guidelines for NAMs and NGRA in practice using environmental case-studies

A6.4.4: Support prospective and retrospective risk assessment of plant production products and link predictions to biodiversity and ecological traits metrics.

Activities 7.1.1, 7.1.2, 7.2.1, 7.2.2 and 7.2.3: Contribute to DMP development, FAIR data implementation, develop data libraries and targeted solutions using the Source To Outcome Predictor (STOP) toolbox.

Activities 7.3.1, 7.3.2 and 7.3.3: Develop innovative analysis using the Source To Outcome Predictor (STOP) toolbox on selected environmental case studies.

Activity 8.3.2: Contribute to the PARC model network with the Source To Outcome Predictor (STOP) toolbox using selected environmental case studies.

26.5 NMBU – PIC 999902967

During the second year of PARC, NMBU will contribute to Work Packages (WP) , 3, 4, 5, 6, & 8.

In WP 3, our focus will be on task 3.1a by supporting actively the interactions with relevant stakeholders and the PARC stakeholder forum. NMBU will provide information on National stakeholders in Norway.

A focus area of the second year will be the Task 4.1. by actively contributing to the new PARC biomonitoring platform and to task 4.2. on source elucidation and exposure assessment of humans and ecosystems (One Health). Already ongoing projects will be harmonised with PARC activities. NMBU will contribute to the extension of the PARC biomonitoring network into the Norwegian Arctic.

During the second year, NMBU will contribute to tasks activities 5.1.2, 5.2.2 and 5.3.2 by supporting the assessment of NAM development and contributing to experimental studies. Our main focus will be to establish an *in vitro* neuroendocrine system for neurotoxicity testing. The Zebrafish model will be applied for testing neurotoxicity and specifically the neuro-endocrine system regulating reproduction. NMBU together with NIPH will organise an EDC working group which will meet once per month until the group has identified its contribution.

In WP6, the 2. Year's focus will be on task 6.1. by contributing to the development of new sustainable testing strategies for the risk assessment of chemicals. Especially the coordination of trace analytical methods with toxicological test systems will be further explored and harmonized.

In WP8 our contribution to the integrated tools for risk assessment (activity 8.1.2) as well as evaluating chemicals of emerging concern for exposure risk assessment will be a major NMBU focus. Already available methods and strategies will be further refined and discussed with the WP8 partners.

26.6 NVI – PIC 999511378

During the second year of PARC, NVI will contribute to Work Package (WP) 5. In activity 5.1. 1, to close data gaps on human exposure NVI will perform immunotoxicity studies of Alternaria toxins and enniatins in a model focusing on inflammatory responses in the gut. The model also allows ADME studies and we will provide data input to 5.3 PBPK modelling by providing *in vitro* ADME data as well as toxicological effects on the GI function. The work also contributes to NAM development.

26.7 UNN – PIC 991888051

During the second year of PARC, UNN will contribute to approaches within sample preparation and analysis for biological monitoring in 4.1. In 9.3 UNN will contribute with expertise on harmonisation and developing of criteria for QA/QC.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?

N

27- INSTYTUT MEDYCYNY PRACY IMIENIA PROF. DRA MED. JERZEGO NOFERA W LODZI, POLAND (NIOM) – PIC 999835940

During the second year, Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine (NIOM) will be involved in WP1 Task 1.1, 1.2; WP2 Task 2.1, 2.3; WP3 Task 3.2, WP 4 Task 4.1, 4.3 and WP 6 Task 6.2 and 6.4.

In WP 1 NIOM will be involved especially in Task 1.1, 1.2 coordination, ongoing technical and financial management of NIOM and its Affiliated Partners involved in PARC and administrative management.

In WP2 NIOM will be involved in Task 2.1 and contribute to review of new research activities, supporting the development of integrated EU-wide regulatory process and implementation of priority strategy. In Task 2.3 NIOM will contribute to activities towards the exit strategy and development of monitoring framework.

In WP3 NIOM will be involved in Task 3.2 activities related to communication, cooperation with other partners, awareness with the scientific community and stakeholders through different communication channels, dissemination strategy plan.

In WP4 NIOM will be involved in Task 4.1: Human biomonitoring, especially in design survey in the waste management (4.1.1), best exposure biomarkers definition (4.1.2), roadmap linking exposure to health outcomes (4.1.3) and Task 4.3 NIOM will contribute to development of innovative methods for monitoring and survey (4.3.1).

In WP6 NIOM will be involved in Task 6.2 dealing with aggregate exposure. The exposure model inventory will be investigated to identify the more relevant models in occupational and populational exposures. Additionally NIOM will be involved in case study specific to general life exposure for pyrethroids, parabens and PFAS exposure and case study combining general life and occupational exposure for bisphenols and road traffic. In Task 6.4: Developing and fostering the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory approaches and methodologies, including for groups of chemicals and chemical mixtures and developing a framework to address risks from chemicals in articles and materials on the EU-market in the second year NIOM will be involved in project dealing with optimization of regulatory risk assessment and management of chemicals mixtures in Europe (OPREMIX).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

Y

27.1 IEP-NRI: IEP-NRI will subcontract laboratory calibration and expertise from an ecotoxicologist as part of P5.1.2.b_Y1 focusing on BPA alternatives and associated mixtures ; and expertise from an ecotoxicologist as part of P6.4.4.b_Y1 focusing on reducing the complexity of models for predicted

environmental concentrations of plant protection products and P6.4.4.e_Y1 focusing on quantifying effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts.

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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27.1 IEP-NRI – PIC 998750316

During the second year of PARC IEP-NRI will be involved in the following tasks in WP5 and WP6:

WP 5.1: IEP-NRI will contribute to activity 5.1.2b, where the potential adverse effects of BPA and BPA alternatives will be investigated on following organisms: *Daphnia magna* (acute and chronic toxicity), *Raphidocelis subcapitata*, *Lemna minor*, *Aliivibrio fischeri* (Microtox).

WP 6.4: in activity 6.4.4. Within the project P6.4.4.b_Y1_CS2_SLU, during the second year, other available models for calculating PEC (other than the obligatory ones used in the PPP evaluation) will be identified and their operating characteristics will be recognized. The analysis of existing models will be followed by a comparison and analysis of their underlying assumptions and operating principles. In the following years of the project, the results of the model calculations will be verified with the actual concentrations found in the environment (MEC - Measured Environmental Concentration).

WP 6.4: in activity 6.4.4. Within the project P6.4.4.e_Y1_CS5_ISCIII on Landscape ERA, during the second year IEP-NRI will focus on development the case study reflecting different agricultural landscape conditions on aquatic biota using monitoring data from bot, WFD- compliant monitoring and Natura2000 network supplemented with the literature and research data.

Also, the state of the art of identifying PPP bioindicators on non-target soil organisms will be prepared, with special focus on Poland.

27.2 UG-PL – PIC 999876001

During the second year UG-PL will be involved in the following tasks in WP4, 5, 6, 7, and 8:

Task 4.2: UG-PL will take a part in the realization of activity 4.2.3 and activity 4.2.4 focused on the design on monitoring campaign and on monitoring studies of priority pollutants (selected endocrine compounds).

Task 4.3: UG-PL will contribute to the project P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH: Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I) human community (*wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment*) and II) environmental exposure assessment (*screening of wastewater treatment plant effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle*).

Task 5.1: UG-PL will contribute to the Project “*BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)*” (Activity i) that includes the investigation of the potential adverse effects of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on *Daphnia magna* according to the standardized procedures: *Daphnia sp. Acute Immobilisation Test* (OECD TG 202) and *Daphnia magna* Reproduction Test (OECD 211) as well as on duckweed *Lemna minor* according to the standardized procedure: *Lemna sp. Growth Inhibition Test* (OECD 211).

Task 5.2a: UG-PL will take part in the assessing the suitability of computational methods for the determination of developmental neurotoxicity using AOP framework.

Activity 5.2.2: UG-PL will contribute to the Project “*BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)*” to the Activity iv – that includes the development of new methods/approaches with selected invertebrates (*D. magna* and *A. salina*) as model organisms to assess

environmental hazards of model compounds such as endocrine disruptive BPA alternatives, as well as to assessment available or/and development new QSAR-like models/read across approaches for various type of AOP-anchored endpoints (related mainly to neurotoxicity and endocrine disruption) (Activity iii).

Task 5.3, Activity 5.3.1: UG-PL will develop QSAR models to predict the events recognized as crucial for inducing the considered adverse outcome (including transcriptomic responses leading to KE that triggers AO).

Activity 5.3.2: UG-PL will continue the work within the CG, SG2, SG3, EMG working group. The work will mainly focus on preparing the AOP-anchored database of neurotoxic effects and thyroid hormone system disruption caused by chemicals as a first step in the development of *in silico*-based neurotoxicity/endocrine disruption testing strategy for regulatory purpose.

Task 6.1: UG-PL will contribute to the work on development of IATAs based on AOPs networks for genotoxicity and endocrine disruption, as well as their evaluation through case studies - P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED and P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX projects

Task 6.2, activity 6.2.3: UG-PL will participate in the development of a methodology for testing chemical risk posed by mixtures of compounds using computational methods.

Activity 6.4.2: UG-PL will participate in activities related to defining the framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI/ML models for regulatory purposes. The outcome of this activity will be report including the final decisions on case studies to perform in the next step of the project.

Task 7.1: UG-PL will contribute to work on the implementation of FAIR Data Policy and Data Management Plan in topics related to data platforms and data quality.

Task 7.2 Involvement in the FAIR Implementation Task Force (FIT) as well as carrying out responsibilities and activities of Data Liaison within selected projects.

Task 8.1: UG-PL will contribute to the further work with operationalization of the SSbD criteria and methodology developed by the EC.

Task 8.2: UG-PL will contribute to the work on bioinformatic tools for identification of signals of potentially hazardous chemicals and their scoring.

27.3 WULS-SGGW – PIC 999865137

Task 4.1 WULS-SGGW will contribute to:

- the targeted studies: a. Hotspot HBM - connected with ambient monitoring (water, soil, air,..) children/adults As hotspot Study on adults (40-69y), b. environmental exposures and risk factors for common diseases in the adult population >39y, randomly selected populations
- the general population survey: teenagers, new national HBM campaign
- the general population survey: children, new national HBM campaign
- occupational surveys - occupational survey in the waste management sector and healthcare survey sector

Task 4.3 WULS-SGGW will participate in activities related to:

- Human. Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern
- Human. Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based / EDA screening methods on human samples.
- Environment. Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I) human community and II) environmental exposure assessment.
- Food. Proof-of-concept of HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring food contact material related exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
- Food. Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based / EDA screening

methods on food samples (e.g. aquatic species / fish, drinking water, childhood food...)	
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

28- FACULDADE DE MEDICINA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA, PORTUGAL (FMUL) – PIC 999888320

In year 2, FMUL will continue the activities initiated in year 1, namely in the following work packages (WP): **WP1 | Task 1.1** – ongoing technical and financial management of FMUL and its Affiliated Entities involvement in PARC; **WP2 | Task 2.3** – collaboration in the development of a survey for mapping the needs of the national hubs; also FMUL will continue to participate in the preparation of the ‘exit strategy’, namely collaborating in the identification of activities that need to be sustained and how to pursue it; **WP3 | Task 3.1a** – collaboration in running of the Stakeholder Forum (SF), including the organization of regular meetings and consultations of the SF members, namely through the building up of survey to gather SF's opinion on priorities in terms of research, dissemination and policy; **Task 3.1b** – participation in running of the International Board (IB), including the organization of regular meetings; **Task 3.2** – collaboration in PARC’s regular communication and dissemination activities and development of specific materials; **Task 3.3** – collaboration in the survey for the identification of external activities/projects for the establishment of synergies under PARC and in the survey targeting citizens to understand opinions and concerns about PARC-related subjects, as well as in the SYNnet; **WP6 | Activity 6.2.1** – literature review in scientific and grey literature of existing models and tools for general population to contribute to the inventory to be elaborated under the project ‘strategy aggregated exposure’ and collaboration in the structural analysis and development of a functional design for model connection; **Activity 6.2.4** – review of the literature for scientific evidence and documents in grey literature regarding endocrine disruptors for which health impact assessment (HIA) has been performed and used assessment methods, and of the map of European and national health data registries, including the assessment its feasibility for derivations; **WP8 | Activity 8.1.3** – contribution to the definition of indicators to measure progress on sector applicability of the SSbD toolbox; **Task 8.1.4** – contribution to the development of the knowledge and information platform under the operationalization of the SSbD toolbox and of educational materials; **WP9 | Tasks 9.1 and 9.2** – contribution to the elaboration of catalogues on laboratory networks and HBM studies and networks, including the definition of the parameters to be collected for the purpose of building catalogues on air, indoor/articles, water.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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FMUL has two affiliated entities participating in PARC, with the following activities for year 2:

28.1 PL – PIC 996273421

The involvement of PL in **WP3 and WP4** is being discussed for year 2. PL will contribute with field work to study risk/benefit assessment associated with seaweeds consumption in the portuguese population within WP4 and development of specific dissemination materials within WP3 – **Task 3.2** PL will also contribute with surveys to citizens to collect information about their health risk perception of seafood and seaweeds consumption.

28.2 UM – PIC 999995505

UM will contribute to the literature reviews within WP4, namely with a literature review on the

exposure of children to tobacco smoke. In second year we do fieldwork to study children's exposure to smoking behavior in open spaces such as school entrances and playgrounds. Observational studies will be carried out using an observation grid. After collecting the data, it will be processed to get an idea of the problem of children's exposure to the smoking behavior of adults.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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29- INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE SAUDE DR. RICARDO JORGE, PORTUGAL (INSA) – PIC 998308190

During the second year, INSA will be involved in WP 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 9. INSA will proceed with the tasks and activities initiated in the first year, namely:

In **WP1**, tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.4, INSA, as member of the Management Board (MB), will continue collaborating with the Coordination Team in the management of the PARC activities, the Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans contributing to the relevance of the PARC work plan with regard to external events (as WP3 co-leader) and to the ethics framework. Also, as GS INSA will continue managing five AEs. INSA co-leads Task 1.3, and will be involved in the refinement of the first set of indicators, consultation of PARC internal Boards, and interactions with WP2 (on sustainability) and WP3 (development of leaflets) in order to ensure the adequacy and relevance of the indicator's framework for PARC performance and impact evaluation.

In **WP2**, INSA co-leads Task 2.2 on the knowledge management and the work to be developed will be focused on the management of transversal groups, i.e., Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs), besides being involved in the development of *PARCopedia* and *PARCroute*. INSA will also contribute to Task 2.3, contributing to the interaction with the National hubs.

INSA co-leads **WP3** on synergies, collaboration and awareness and Task 3.3 on networking and synergies. Besides managing WP3 activities in close collaboration with task co-leaders and partners and promoting interactions with the other WPs and the Coordination Team, INSA will also contribute to the activities developed under Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3. In Task 3.1 INSA will contribute to the organization of the Stakeholders Forum (SF) and International Board (IB) meetings and to the consultations to stakeholders and experts within those Boards. In Task 3.2 INSA will participate in the development of communication and dissemination materials, contribute to gather data to feed into impact indicators and promote the internal dialogue and interactions with different end-users; INSA will also be responsible for the coordination of the first survey to citizens to collect information about their perceptions and concerns about PARC-related subjects. Under Task 3.3 INSA will be involved in the update, expansion and management of the SYNnet and the roadmap for its development. In addition, INSA will co-coordinate the organisation of the first SYNnet Forum, to promote dialogue and knowledge sharing among scientists.

In **WP4**, INSA will contribute to Projects and activities within Task 4.1 related to general population and occupational biomonitoring studies.

Under 4.1.1.1 INSA will continue to collaborate in the development of new supporting materials for harmonized development of HBM surveys at European level. Concerning 4.1.1.2 INSA will prepare the fieldwork of the Aligned Studies for children, adolescents and adults and start the implementation of the studies. Concerning 4.1.1.4 INSA will be involved in projects P4.1.1.4.a, P4.1.1.4.b and P4.1.1.d. In project P4.1.1.4.a (feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys) INSA will collaborate in the preparation of the final report and in the dissemination of results (scientific publication

and communications in scientific meetings). In project P4.1.1.4.b (Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system) INSA will participate in the proof-of-concept of the sentinel system. Concerning occupational studies, INSA will participate mainly in the waste management survey (P.4.1.1.d), collaborating in the study planning, participants' recruitment, air and human samples collection, transfer and analysis, particularly of effects biomarkers, as planned for year 2; participation in the study on the health care sector (P4.1.1.c) will be also considered. Under Activity 4.1.2 INSA will collaborate in the definition of the best suited exposure biomarkers and analytical methods and in the identification of laboratories to perform the analysis of effect biomarkers analysis in the samples from the HBM studies.

Under Activity 4.1.3 INSA will participate in the feasibility study to explore the possibility to assess past exposures to the chemicals of interest and link them to effect biomarkers and health outcomes. INSA will continue to collaborate in Task 4.1.4, namely by being involved in the statistical working group and collaborating in the development of statistical analysis plans and in the analysis of data from HBM4EU.

Under Activity 4.1.5 INSA will help in the distribution of the survey on the vision for a future and sustainable HBM system and in the analysis and interpretation of the survey results. INSA will also collaborate in the definition of the requirements from partner countries and components relevant for comparison with international HBM programs and in the identification of action points for the development of the future system.

In **WP5**, INSA, will continue co-leading the management and scientific steering of activity 5.1.1, which is focused on closing the regulatory data gaps of concern for human health, regarding mycotoxins (*Alternaria* toxins and enniatins) and BPA alternatives/analogues. In addition, INSA will participate in the Projects under development (on natural toxins and BPA alternatives/analogues), collaborating in the genotoxicity and carcinogenesis assessment and in the elaboration of related articles. Additionally, INSA will collaborate in task 5.2.1 in activities focused on developing innovative methods and tools for immunotoxicity testing.

In **WP6**, INSA will participate in tasks 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4.

Under Activity 6.2.1 INSA will be involved in project P6.2.1.b (Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures), collaborating in the development of the case studies for aggregate exposure.

Under Activity 6.2.4 INSA will participate in the four interrelated projects on health impact assessment, contributing to the inventory on data availability, to the derivation of population exposure levels and exposure-effect associations for PARC priority chemicals, to the overview of current methodologies, indicators and frameworks used for cost analysis related to health impact of chemical exposures, participate in the case studies on health impact assessment and contribute to the development of risk and health impact indicators.

Under task 6.3 INSA will continue working in a case study on the analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches led by ISS.

Under Activity 6.4.2 INSA will contribute to facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods and will collaborate in the development of an evidence-based framework to ensure objectivity, transparency and reproducibility in the application of NAMs in RA useful across regulations (including e.g., scientific criteria).

Under **WP9**, INSA will lead the mapping of available training, and the elaboration of PARC training plan (with the definition of training courses and learning resources to be held/developed within the PARC consortium for Y2-Y3). In addition, INSA will also contribute to the elaboration of catalogues

on laboratory networks (Task 9.1) and HBM studies (Task 9.2), as well as to the QA/QC activities planned under Task 9.3.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

29.1 APA – PIC 917950286

During the second year APA will be involved in WP2 and WP 3 namely tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3.

In WP2 APA will participate in the NHCP network because it is the principal NHCP representative for PT and will contribute to the dissemination of PARC activities and achievements nationally.

In the task 3.1 it will be involved in the organization and run of Stakeholders Forum

In task 3.2 continue to contribute to the contents and implementation of the draft PARC communication and dissemination strategy.

In task 3.3 APA will participate in collecting information about external activities/projects and setting of possible synergies.

29.2 DGS – PIC 986364095

DGS will be involved in tasks 2.1 and 8.2. Under task 2.1, DGS will continue its collaboration in the Projects' review process to ensure that the work proposed will contribute to improve regulation and chemicals policy in Europe. Under task 8.2., for AWPY2, DGS will contribute to the development of the EWS toolbox, with the identification of the critical indicators supporting policy advice towards a better public health protection.

29.3 ENSP – PIC 960782479

ENSP is involved in WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6 and WP9. In the scope of these WPs, ENSP is enrolled in several projects to be continued in the following years, namely:

In WP2, ENSP is involved in the projects PARCroute and PARCopedia. In PARCroute ENSP will be involved in two main tasks: Task 2 that implies collaborating in the definition of the vision and scope and create a unified NGRA framework and, in Task 3, ENSP will collaborate in defining NGRA topology and mapping the legislation. In PARCopedia, ENSP will be involved in only one main task, namely defining the vision and scope and project management.

In WP3, ENSP is directly involved in Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness and Task 3.3: Networking and Synergies. In the first task, ENSP will collaborate in the development and implementation of a communication and dissemination strategy, including development of communication materials (flyers, newsletters, videos, factsheets, infographics etc), press releases, contact with press, citizens surveys and focus groups. In Task 3.3 ENSP will be involved in the identification and inventory of international initiatives relevant to PARC and in the organization of SYNnet Forum.

In WP4, ENSP is mainly involved in the occupational studies (Task 4.1) and is coordinating the survey on the waste management setting. In addition, several synergies are being developed with other tasks such as Task 4.3: innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys.

In WP6, ENSP is engaged in the several tasks developed in the scope of Task 6.1: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals (Project 1 - IATA for endocrine disruption, and Project 4 - Human Relevance of AOP); Task 6.2: Integrative risk assessment activities, where ENSP will be dedicated to three group of substances namely metals, mycotoxins and PFAS [activities to be

developed in aggregate exposure (6.2.1.) and health impact assessment (6.2.4) - collaboration in the four projects defined for data availability, indicators, methodologies and case studies]; Task 6.4: 6.4.1. - operationalizing the MAF for supporting its implementation under REACH and optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (projects 1 and 2), and 6.4.2 - status of integration and use of new approach methods in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape – project 1).

In WP9, ENSP involvement is mainly in 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities (inventory of existing monitoring and biomonitoring networks, environmental specimen banks, capacities and other resources and identification of existing gaps and obstacles in better use of existing capacities) and 9.4 training activities [identification of training needs (activity 9.4.1), identification of useful learning resources for the web-based portal (activity 9.4.2) and establishment of an internal training plan and external training plan (training courses) (activity 9.4.3)].

29.4 UC – PIC 997826391

During the second year UC will be involved in WP 6.4., particularly in Task 6.4.4. UC will co-leading Project 2 on “Reducing complexity and identifying the most relevant predictors for effects in ERA of PPPs” (sub-task 6.4.4.2 Perform studies to compare different risk assessment methodologies and environmental monitoring) by analysing existing data on soil organism testing obtained with different PPPs and in different soils to better predict toxicity and reduce uncertainty when extrapolating data obtained on artificial soil to different natural soils. UC will also be involved in Project 4 on “Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts” (sub-task 6.4.4.3 Develop holistic and more realistic risk assessment frameworks) by developing monitoring effects on non-target arthropod communities in a landscape case study in vineyards in Portugal (in collaboration with UVAR), relating PPP use patterns at landscape scale, crop management and landscape structure with the status of those organisms communities. This will contribute with monitoring data to better understand how this type of information can be used in an systems-based approach for ERA, including retro feeding the current ERA schemes for NTAs. In this respect we will focus on functional diversity of NTA groups and on the most vulnerable species, linking this PARC activity with the ongoing EFSA funded project AENEAS.

29.5 UAVR – PIC 999865331

UAVR is involved in WP3, WP5, WP6 and WP9.

Regarding WP5, we are involved in several projects within the environmental part: in Task 5.1.b, the toxicity of natural toxins and their mixtures and combination with other co-occurring substances to micro algae, and the effects BPA alternatives and associated mixtures to several aquatic species (in vivo and in vitro). Regarding Human and Health, we are participating in T5.1a, within the molecular alteration underlying bisphenol-associated male infertility and within T5.2a, the development of NAMs based on semen biomonitoring.

Project: 6.4.1.a. Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe. Project OPREMIX looks at current practices and the implementation of chemical mixture assessment approaches (classic approaches, modern and MAF) and related with regulation like REACH, CLP.

Project 6.4.2.a Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape. UAVR is part of the team devoted to develop an environmental focus within the project, regarding the reduction in animals use for testing as human risk assessment, along with the challenge to scale and scope, the use of NAMs is also a focus in the environmental risk assessment.

Project 6.4.4 Landscape and Plant Protection Products- project devoted on both aquatic and terrestrial compartments, linked by the anthropogenic pressures from agricultural practices and the application of plant protection products. Models and tools for Landscape ERA, linking EFSA activities related to

Landscape ERA. Tools and approaches for landscape ERA.

In WP9, our involvement will be mostly on the training activities (T9.4), and we also contributed with information for T9.1 on the Laboratory networking.

Regarding WP3, our activities have not been very active but we are starting looking at synergies with other projects and stakeholders at national level (e.g. ETERNAL project starting date september 2022, <https://www.eternalproject.eu/>) within T3.3. In addition and regarding T3.2 we are considering the potentials for communication, dissemination, and awareness at the national level.

WP4 is under conversation as we started late talking with the WP/project leaders. We have already suggested to add monitoring data available. The ECOMARE CRAM is a infrastructure of UAVR which has as main mission the recovery of marine animals and return them safely to the sea. Within their activity they have access to several marine vertebrates (dead and alive) which enable them to have huge database. Among this, they also have a tissue bank. Although in the beginning they were not part of our team, we can easily bring them in (Hg analysis of several organisms: bivalves, fish, etc from the Atlantic coast and coastal estuarine areas; Hg analysis in seagulls and other marine birds (several matrices); Hg analysis in several matrices of wader species). Besides data, we have also capability of doing and develop biomonitoring in situ, using monitoring adapted ecotoxicological assays. We have also insect data (WFD, EPT and other Portuguese indexes) for river monitoring.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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30- SLOVENSKA ZDRAVOTNICKA UNIVERZITA V BRATISLAVE, SLOVAKIA (SZU-SK) – PIC 999859802

During the second year, SZU is involved in the work packages WP4 and WP9.

In WP4, SZU team will be involved in the task 4.1 Human Biomonitoring, specifically in the activities focused on and supporting general surveys and preparatory work related to targeted studies. Furthermore, SZU will continue in the activities resulting from HBM44EU, incl. exploring and analysing HBM data. SZU will support activities focused on laboratory analysis and quality assurance and will contribute to defining QA/QC criteria and exposure data comparability.

In WP9, within Task 9.1, SZU will contribute to the laboratory networking and building up a database of the laboratory networks. In Task 9.2, SZU will contribute to the mapping of exposure monitoring capacities and development of initial catalogues and their updates.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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30.1 UK – PIC 999841566

UK will be active in laboratory networking in WP9, task 9.1 Building the HBM laboratory network catalogue, involved in mapping of existing laboratory networks and their capacities. According to its expertise, UK will also join the activities in task 4.1 (activity 4.1.1 and 4.1.2) focused on issues concerning human biomonitoring and laboratory analyses.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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31- INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN, SLOVENIA (JSI-SI) – PIC: 999971837

During the second year, JSI will be involved in the WPs 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 9, with the highest extent in WPs 4, 6 and 7.

Within the WP2, JSI will collaborate in the task 2.2 in the development of PARCopedia and PARCroute and will also be active in the task 2.3, contributing to the interaction with the National hubs.

Within the WP3, JSI will participate under the task 3.2 in the development of communication and dissemination materials, contribute to gather data to feed into impact indicators. Under the task 3.3 JSI will collaborate in the update, expansion and management of the SYNnet and the roadmap for its development. Specifically, JSI will take care of synergies with the European research infrastructures and partnership program under the auspices of the EURAMET.

Within the WP4 JSI will continue to contribute to the development of supporting materials, namely SOPs for sampling, sample handling and storage and questionnaires, and digitalization of data acquisition/reporting, particularly for General Survey studies (project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1) (4.1.1.); to the QA/QC activities for the laboratory analysis (4.1.2.); take active role in assessment of the link between exposure and health for As, Hg and Cd (P4.1.3.3.a_Y1) (4.1.3); and will be intensively involved in preparation of data management and analysis plans for further analysis of HBM data already generated (project P4.1.4.2.a_Y1) (4.1.4). In the latter, JSI will lead 4.1.4.2. activity (iv): Exposure sources, routes, and determinants of exposure. With a link to 6.2.3., JSI is contributing also to risk assessment of mixtures, participating in the WG1 (HBM).

In Task 4.2, JSI contribute to the prioritisation strategy (4.2.1) and review of existing knowledge and infrastructure to support the activities on the EDC group of compounds as well as PFAS (activity 4.2.2). JSI will be involved in the design of targeted monitoring activities (activity 4.2.3), and will contribute to monitoring activities, including laboratory analysis and QA/QC (activity 4.2.4).

In Task 4.3, JSI will contribute to the transversal projects on concept paper (P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01), define minimal common QA/QC requirements (P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02), provide expertise in supporting the development of an early warning systems (P4.3.1.d_Y1_T03) and contribute to the development of data processing workflows within P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04 “Advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS”. With respect to human exposure, JSI will share samples and will develop and apply HRMS based screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure, with a focus on sample analysis, advanced data processing and compound identification (P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01). JSI will also take part in the project on occupational exposure (P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02) and will perform the preparation activities for the project P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03- Complementary developments, where JSI is a project leader. JSI will continue with active participation within the project P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01: Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants”, where its focus will include screening methods development for wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE), the prioritisation of source-related features and patterns and analytical method inventory. In project P4.3.3.b_E02 “HRMS based / EDA screening methods for sentinel animal species” JSI will contribute by sample preparation and analysis and will also provide the expertise within the project P4.3.3.b_Y2_F02: Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples.

In WP5, it is foreseen for JSI to contribute to Task 5.2, in particular to learning QSAR models using cutting edge machine learning methods, such as deep learning methods for learning representations of molecules, and tree-ensemble methods for multi-target regression for building predictive models. It is also planned that JSI will be involved in Task 5.3. on systems toxicology, more specifically 5.3.4., where we will apply machine learning methods for automated modelling of dynamical systems to learn PBK models in quantitative systems toxicology.

Within the WP 6, JSI will be involved in Task 6.3_case study 2 and Task 6.3_case study 3. The Task 6.3-CS2: Identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk is focused on understanding the efficiency of different risk management and risk

mitigation measure in terms of how effective they have been at reducing sales/production volumes, and/or concentrations in biomonitoring studies. In Task 6.3_CS3: Evaluation of the efficiency of EU OSH legislation and REACH authorisation/restriction processes to control occupational chemical exposure, JSI will participate as evaluators of the effects associated with selected substances.

In WP7, JSI is actively involved in all three tasks – 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3. In 7.1, JSI will take active role in the implementation of FAIR principles and FAIR training, will contribute to the data policy and data management planning, which will go hand in hand with 7.2 task, where a practical demonstration will be performed on a local level, using existing national HBM datasets and geospatially resolved data. In addition, JSI will act as a data liaison for project P4.1.4.2.a_Y1. In 7.3 JSI will apply methods for data and text mining in the context integrative systems toxicology, participating in knowledge extraction, analysis and integration activities (7.3.3).

In WP9, JSI will collaborate in tasks 9.1-9.4. In the tasks 9.1 and 9.2 JSI will be involved in preparation of HBM and environmental data catalogues (P9.1.1.a, P9.2.1), in the task 9.3 JSI will contribute actively to the activities regarding QA/QC (as part of the QA/QC core group), and in the task 9.4 on identification of training needs as well as the inventory of existing training courses and programmes.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

31.1 GEOZS – PIC 999466370

During the second year, GEOZS will be involved in WP6, activity 6.2.1. GEOZS team will participate in a case study on general life aggregate exposure to metals. Data on environmental metal concentrations from different sources will be prepared for calculations using the selected aggregate exposure model. Activities related to the development of a national inventory of existing environmental data sources, gaps and exposure models will be continued.

31.2 NIB – PIC 999650476

During the second year, NIB will be involved in WP3 and WP5.

NIB team will continue its participation in WP3 (Task3.1, 3.2 and 3.3) and WP5 (Task5.1a, 5.1b, 5.2a and 5.2b).

Within Task3.1 NIB will participate in the activities related to the Stakeholder Forum, within Task3.2 it will be involved in the Communication plan and the activities related to the Citizens surveys, while in Task3.3 it will participate in the activities related to the Research for R&I and possible collaborations, contacts and setting up of database that will be prepared within WP3.

Within the Task 5.1a NIB will be involved in the research on mutagenicity of Alternaria toxins using standardised methodology – Ames assay according to the OECD 471. Further, in Task5.1b NIB will participate in the studies of the adverse effects of BPA alternatives and mixtures of bisphenols in Danio rerio (zebrafish) embryos by performing Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity Test (OECD TG 236). With its specific expertise in advanced in vitro 3D cell models NIB will perform studies related to determination to NAMs for non-genotoxic carcinogens within Task 5.2a and Task 5.2b using human and zebrafish 3D cell models, respectively. NIB will also participate in preparation of the review papers.

31.3 NIC – PIC 998756718

During the first year NIC has been involved mostly in WP 5.2b. Within consortium we set up the data set of BPA alternatives (app. 100 compounds). We determinate their molecular structures and started to predict the toxic properties using different QSAR and read across models available over internet (VEGA HUB models, EPA models, etc.) We will proceed with analysis of the data. For the analysis we will also use diverse chemometrical methods (artificial neural networks, etc.)

31.4 ULFFA – PIC 999923240

For the task 4.2.1 UL FFA will revise the endocrine disruptor prioritization list to be specifically adapted to the locally encountered EDCs with 18 compounds found in our preliminary sampling campaign.

The QA/QC criteria and procedures (activity 4.2.3) will be incorporated in the method for monitoring of 25 endocrine disruptors from classes of natural as well as synthetic steroids and bisphenols, applied to Slovenia’s surface, ground and wastewaters.

The multisource sampling campaign (activity 4.2.4) will be expanded from the Sava river to other geographical regions of Slovenia and their surface waters (Drava, Soča, Pivka and Savinja). The data will be assessed by the EU WfD EQS criteria (activity 4.2.5).

UL FFA has also been involved in WP 5.1 (task 5.1.a) and in WP 5.2 (task 5.2.a). For the task 5.1.a during the second year, UL FFA will investigate the reactivity of newly emerging BPA analogues and alternatives with immune cell lines and evaluate their potency for the activation/inhibition of immune system related glucocorticoid receptor. UL FFA will also contribute to the joint review paper of WP5.1a group.

Regarding task 5.2.a, UL FFA will develop new test for the identification of immunosuppressive drugs, thus trying to establish a NAM for the replacement of a whole-blood assay for immunosuppression. Cell lines, their co-cultures and primary cells will be used and a panel of secreting cytokines upon exposure to known immunosuppressants will be assayed with the aim of establishment of reliable immunosuppressive marker in *in vitro* assays.

Under Task 9.4 UL FFA will focus on the preparation of materials that will support to training local organizers, and assist in training evaluation assessment.

31.5 – MFUM – PIC 999903646

Within WP 5.1 we plan to include 30 breast cancer patients and 30 endometrial cancer patients within year 2. Through *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies toxicity will be tested in translational models. MF UM has performed analyses for the *in vivo* samples and has correlated them with expression of more aggressive cancer features. Within year 2, we will use the gained knowledge for analysis in different endometrial cancer cell line subtypes and analyse their correlation with *in vivo* data when looking at exposure of endocrine disruptors and cancer cell line behaviour.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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32- NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE, SLOVENIA (NIJZ) – PIC : 948891346

In year two NIJZ will participate in WP 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7 and 9. Besides co-ordination of the PARC National Hub, NIJZ will continue to co-lead Task 1.4. Within the latter, the Data and Ethics Protection Board established in year one, will further develop the ethics, the data protection and the intellectual property rights frameworks and endeavor for their implementation in collaboration with other WPs. In WP 2 NIJZ will remain active in T2.3. Within WP3 NIJZ will continue to play a core role in T3.2 and 3.3, and will participate in the outlined strategy for communication, dissemination, awareness, synergies and networking by appropriately targeting various stakeholder groups. The development of the risk communication tools as a discipline per se will continue in order to maximize the results of communication activities. In WP4 NIJZ will participate in HBM general population survey by contributing to harmonization of questionnaires, their validation and digitalization, by supplying the existent and new HBM data, and by reviewing and commenting on the derivation of HBM-GV values, and in assessing of links between exposure and health as well as advancing the use of the already existent national HBM data. NIJZ is a core team member in activity 6.2.1 Aggregate exposure from

different sources and routes for general population. NIJZ plans to participate in exposure models and data inventories, strategy for aggregate exposure in general population such as bibliographic review of methodological approaches to aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes including agency guidance, participation in preparing glossary documents and work in the proposed case studies in activity 6.2.3. Namely, NIJZ will be involved in assessment of mixtures based on HBM data, specifically related to the exposure to metals, the haematological effects of mycotoxins and DNT effects of mixtures. In activity 6.2.4 NIJZ plans to work on the HBM data concerning lead exposure in children and the effect of risk reduction measures. NIJZ also proposes to include RA and HIA concerning the persistent organic pollutants. Although POPs have not been selected as priority chemicals as a group, exposure to POPs is relevant in view of their undoubtful endocrine disrupting properties. EDs. are among the priority chemicals in PARC. The exposure of infants via maternal milk significantly exceeds the current biomonitoring equivalents for the selected POPs, thus indicating a risk to health (see Ahačič et al. 2022. Development of an environmental indicator for tetrachlorodibenzodioxins, tetrachlorodibenzofurans and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls in human milk. Toxicol Lett, 368 S1: S137).

WP7 (T7.2 and 7.3): In intertwining with the activities in task 4.1 and task 6.2 NIJZ will participate in HBM data validation and harmonization, developing linkage of health data with the HBM and environmental monitoring data, and building up an inventory of methods for privacy-preserving analysis of personal, sensitive data.

WP 9: Continuation of capacity building activities in 9.4 based on the results of survey carried out in year1.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

Yes

An expert experienced in using deciduous teeth as a biomarker of exposure (T4.3), and an expert in linking HBM data with the effect data concerning female reproductive health (T4.1).

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Yes

32.1 OI – PIC 986222475

Also during the second year OI will be involved in activity 6.2.4. We plan to spend altogether 6pm work on the projects running within that task. We will take part in all four projects on health impact assessment, contributing to the inventory on data availability and to the development of risk and health impact indicators. In all the projects involved our focus will be on cancer related analyses. We plan also to participate in the case studies on health impact assessment – we have suggested to include a case of incineration and co-incineration products (mainly heavy metals and PAHs) of cement industry in relationship to cancer.

32.2 NLZOH – PIC 949131227

During the second year, NLZOH will participate in the task 6.4.1 NLZOH will perform a study on the polluted site in SE of Slovenia and contribute the knowledge on the fate and behavior of PCB mixtures in water, sediment and biota during the period of 40 years. NLZOH will participate in activities of the task 6.4.1.

32.3 ARSO – PIC 920448812

During the second year, ARSO will participate in task 4.2. ARSO will be involved in activities 4.2.1, 4.2.2, 4.2.3. and will contribute its expertise and knowledge for the two selected case studies i.e. PFAS

and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds in waters. ARSO will also bring its expertise on soil matrix, and monitoring procedures. ARSO will participate at monitoring activities, data analysis and data management and lessons learnt.

32.4 UKCMB – PIC 999582188

During the second year, UMC Maribor will perform sampling for endocrine disruptors in endometrial cancer as has previously been performed in year 1. Additionally, sampling will be initiated for endocrine disruptors in breast cancer. The samples are the processed with mass spectrometry and further analysed by the partner MF UM.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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33- AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (CSIC), SPAIN – PIC 999991722

WP4: Activity 4.1.1, Activity 4.1.3, Activity 4.2.1, Activity 4.2.2, Activity 4.2.3, Activity 4.2.4, Activity 4.2.5, Activity 4.2.6, Activity 4.3.1, Activity 4.3.2, Activity 4.3.3, Activity 4.3.4

WP5: Activity 5.3.4

WP6: Activity 6.2.2, Activity 6.2.3

CSIC will participate in WP4 to generate a database of priority pollutants for study, namely those generating endocrine effects, PFAS/PFOAS, pesticides, metals and chemicals of emerging concern. It will contribute to the elaboration of reports/papers describing the best analytical methods for biomonitoring, environmental and food analysis of the compounds selected for study. It will pay specific attention to high resolution mass spectrometry methods for identification of suspected compounds and non-target analysis. In addition, CSIC will study what is the role of wild fish in the intake of mercury and other metals in general population. CSIC will support RSU in gathering the information on mercury and identifying the main environmental health research issues.

More specifically, this group will contribute to the identification of the additional needed materials after the development of the HBMEU project, specifically the prioritization of compounds of study (A4.1.1). The group has strong expertise in studies of associations between exposures to chemicals and health effects. Specifically, the group will contribute to provide information on PFAS, pesticides, metals (including Cd), bisphenols, mercury (methylmercury), organophosphate flame retardants and phthalates in children, teenagers and adults (A4.1.3).

This group will also contribute to the review of analytical methods for chemical compounds in human samples, particularly those of endocrine disruption activity and PFAS (T4.2).

It will also contribute to the generation of a concept paper synthesizing the state of the art of study of chemical exposures involving inventories, selection and prioritization of the main strategies for environmental exposure, food ingestion and human biomonitoring (P4.3.1.a). It will participate in the determination of the QA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA based screening for the analysis of pollutants in environmental, food and human matrices (P4.3.1.b). It will participate in HRMS based/EDA screening methods for study of perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern in cord blood, meconium and placenta (P4.3.2.a). This partner has also consolidated expertise in the analysis of organic pollutants in waste water and will contribute to the task of using these waters as source of information for assessment of human exposure and identification of risk drivers (P4.3.3.a). The strong expertise of this partner in the use of animals as sentinel organisms for screening exposure to pollutants will be used to contribute to the study of chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel species with HRMS based/EDA methods (P4.3.3.b). In addition, this group will contribute to complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on environmental samples (P4.3.3.c). Potential exposures to chemicals because of food consumption are commonly studied by this

partner and it will also contribute to the implementation of HRMS based/EDA screening methods for the analysis of food samples (A4.3.4.b).

Concerning WP5, the group will participate in the correlation of in vivo, in vitro, toxicokinetic and toxicodynamics with human health effects by analysis of pesticides and PFAS/PFOS (A5.3.4).

CSIC, together with FINBA will participate in WP6 from both source identification of environmental pollutants and biomarkers of exposure. Data on children exposure at different chemicals (e.g. endocrine disruptors, metals, PFAS/PFOS, pesticides) from the Asturias cohort at different ages (birth, 4 years, 8 years) and development and health effects, e.g. ano-genital distance, will be measured and evaluated for associations during growth. Furthermore, CSIC will investigate the distribution of metals and organophosphate and pyrethroid pesticides in general and rural populations, including children and adults. This work will involve the assessment of the main input sources of these pesticides as consequence of diet and lifestyle and, in the rural populations, working activities.

More specifically, the group will participate in the aggregate exposure project, namely on general population case studies (A6.2.1). The group will also provide data for studies on life-cycle PBPK models on pyrethroids, volatile organic compounds, PFOS and chlorpyrifos (A6.2.2). In addition, the group will participate in the real mixture project (A6.2.3) by contribution to the HBM exposure and risk assessment project (WG1), and hazard characterization (WG2), namely on pesticides, heavy metals, PFAS and mycotoxins. The group will also contribute to the MCRA database.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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33.1 ULPGC – PIC 999929739

During the first year ULPGC has been involved in WP 4.1 (activity 4.1.2) related with laboratory analysis and quality assurance, included definition of the best suited exposure biomarkers and analytical methods. During the second year ULPGC will be involved in WP 4.1 (activity 4.1.2 and 4.1.3), related to define the best suited exposure biomarkers and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies in PARC.

33.2 UNAV – PIC 999641746

During the second year, UNAV will be involved in Task 5.2 (activity 5.2.a). However, if some delays occur during the work process of task 5.1.a, due to mycotoxin availability, UNAV will continue to be involved also in this task.

Regarding task 5.2.a, UNAV will continue testing selected compounds with the modified comet assay in 2D and 3D Hepg2 cells using a medium-throughput version of the assay. In addition, the UNAV team will set up the comet assay for global methylation and try to include it in a high-throughput version. Regarding Task 5.1.a, in case of a time-frame of the schedule, UNAV will carry out the proposed genotoxicity tests for mycotoxins (SOS/umu test or mini-Ames).

33.3 UGR – PIC 999882015

During the second year, the UGR will participate in WP4 and WP6. The UGR will focus on continuing the activities initiated during the first months, focusing its work on the following items:

In **WP4** (Task 4.1): UGR will continue to support activities related to general and occupational surveys (mainly in the health sector, but also in the waste sector), leading and collaborating in the writing of specific articles linking exposure and health related information, and the identification of biomarkers

of effect for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes). Specifically:

- In Activity 4.1.1: UGR will continue to contribute to the design, alignment and fieldwork of the HBM studies starting in 2023.
- In Activity 4.1.2, UGR will contribute to activities related to laboratory analysis and quality assurance, leading sub-activity 4.1.2.6 (Selection, assessment and valuation of effect biomarkers in emerging samples from the human biomonitoring task).
- Implementation of adverse health effects assessment in biomonitoring, through measurement of biomarkers of effect and standardized assessment of health outcomes (Project 4.1.3.3a): Selection and application of (molecular) biomarkers of (early) effects in ongoing studies (sentinel and occupational). Obtaining informed consent and ethics committee approval, and initiating recruitment, questionnaires and biological sample collection (sentinel, occupational studies, both in the health and waste sectors).
- UGR will lead the development of activity 4.1.4 (data management and quality assurance): further exploitation of the data generated in the framework of HBM4EU: statistical analysis and writing of articles under specific hypotheses (for this objective two UGR postdocs will work full time under the supervision of VITO (Project 4.1.4.2a).

In Task 4.3, UGR will continue in defining the conceptual framework for target analysis, non-target analysis and suspect screening to characterize and narrow the differences between conventional and innovative exposure approaches. We will start with the recruitment of human samples collected from mother-child pairs. In addition, UGR will contribute to suspect and non-target screening approaches on collected samples.

In **WP6** (Activity 6.2.3: Chemical mixtures): Under WG2 (hazard characterisation), UGR will coordinate a case study on developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) using a tiered approach (first including prioritised pesticides, then chemicals spotted in the relevant scientific literature and finally chemicals identified in HBM studies). A top-down approach will be used for identifying common adverse neurodevelopmental effects and, where available, mechanistic information from AOPs included in the AOP-wiki and from in vitro-testing battery using the methodology implemented by EFSA. UGR will also continue participating in the WG1 on human biomonitoring data analysis and exposure focusing on prioritisation of real-life exposure to chemical mixtures from HBM data and linking such exposures to health effects. Moreover, UGR will contribute to the development and refinement of quantitative networks of AOPs for selected endpoints/AOs (activity 6.2.2.).

33.4 UPO – PIC 999846513

In the second year of PARC (Y2), UPO will be involved in the WP 5.2.

Within task 5.2.b “Innovative methods and tools for environmental toxicity (ecotoxicology) testing and modelling”, UPO will contribute to the Activity 5.2.2 and the advancement of NAMs for the hazard assessment of invertebrates by developing suitable assays. UPO will contribute to the Project “BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)” to the Activity iv, Advancing invertebrates models as NAMs for the hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals. *Caenorhabditis elegans* will be used as organism model to investigate relevant endpoints, e.g. for neurotoxicity or metabolic disruption.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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34- INSTITUTO DE SALUD CARLOS III, SPAIN (ISCIII) – PIC 999507886

ISCIII is WP9 co-leader, T4.1 co-leader, Grant Signatory (GS) and National Hub Contact Point (NHCP).

During the second year, ISCIII will be involved in WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 9.

In **WP1**, ISCIII will contribute to the scientific and administrative coordination and management activities, participating in T1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 as Management Board member and NHCP. In addition, ISCIII will carry out the activities as GS Board member, coordinating eight Spanish affiliated entities.

In **WP2**, ISCIII as NHCP, will be involved in the activities of T2.3 (Sustainability), coordinating PARC activities at the national level.

As **WP9** co-leader, ISCIII will participate on the definition of sustainable frameworks and on the establishment of linkages between WP9 outputs (laboratory networks, exposure monitoring catalogues, catalogues on training programs, etc.) and PARCopedia. In addition, ISCIII will collaborate with T2.3 on the surveys diffusion through the National Hubs, launched by WP9 to collect existing information on laboratory and other networks and to detect knowledge gaps and needs.

In WP3, ISCIII will contribute to the activities related to communication, dissemination and awareness in Task 3.2.

In **WP4**, ISCIII will contribute to activities in Task 4.1, Task 4.2 and Task 4.3. ISCIII is co-leader of T4.1 (Human biomonitoring) coordinating the overall activities. In addition, ISCIII will continue leading the activities related to the HBM QA/QC and laboratory analysis (A4.1.2) and participating in activities related to the preparation of supporting materials for HBM studies, the design and implementation of the PARC aligned studies and targeted studies and the evaluation of the use of innovative methods in HBM studies (A4.1.1), the identification of effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes (A4.1.3), data analysis for existing data sets (mercury in HBM4EU-mom) and preparation of statistical analysis plans for new data (A4.1.4), and the preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe (A4.1.5).

ISCIII is deputy project leader of P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO and participates in P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO and P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSsystem_VITO.

In T4.2, ISCIII will continue its contribution to the project P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU on the establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring by means of two selected case studies, i.e., PFAS and endocrine disruptors.

In T4.3, ISCIII will continue its participation in P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE and will contribute to the preparations for P4.3.2.c_H03 Complementary developments to establish links with the activities on innovative methodologies carried out in T4.1.

In WP5, ISCIII will participate in activities planned under T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3. In T5.1 ISCIII will contribute to fill data gaps on adverse effects of bisphenol individual compounds and mixtures for the endpoints endocrine disruption and carcinogenesis (project P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU).

In T5.2 ISCIII will develop new in vitro and in vivo methodologies, including omics, to assess toxicity in endocrine system (project P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU) and neurodevelopment (project P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_UU). In T5.3, ISCIII will contribute to the definition of Systems Toxicology and its use in human and environmental risk assessment with a focus on regulatory evaluations (project P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR).

In WP6, T6.2, ISCIII is co-leading a project on aggregated exposure (project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse) and has presented a proposal for a case study to compare current pesticide exposure models and scenarios used in EU regulatory assessments with actual monitored levels in humans and food. The initial proposal is for pyrethroids and if accepted may be extended in future years to other pesticides. In addition, ISCIII participates in P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM, contributing with HBM data and performing risk assessment to chemical mixtures.

In activity 6.4.4. ISCIII is leading project P6.4.4.e_Y1_CS5_ISCIII on Landscape ERA, and during the second year, the networking will continue with farmer associations, IPM specialists, voluntary initiatives stakeholders as well as regulatory, and local and regional public actors in order to address

their specific needs in the design of each case stud work plan. Case studies are planned for in ES, FR, PL, and NO reflecting different agricultural landscape conditions and climates.

In WP9, ISCIII will continue co-leading WP9, coordinating WP9 actions to allow for effective cross-WP collaboration and harmonization of efforts. ISCIII, as T9.1 leader, will organize and update the HBM laboratory network and other laboratory networks catalogues developed in Y1 (mainly air, indoor and articles) In addition, ISCIII will create new laboratory catalogues in environmental domains, such as sediment and water. In collaboration with T9.2 will work on the monitoring exposure catalogues (both HMB and environmental). In addition, ISCIII will coordinate the preparation of surveys to collect information to be included in the laboratory catalogues, and cooperate with WP2 and WP3 on their distribution. On the other hand, in the frame of T9.1, first needs for networks development will be identified, and tools for coordination of the laboratory networks will be defined. ISCIII will collaborate with WP3 in the creation of the laboratory network dashboard, to be included in the PARC website. On the other hand, ISCIII will contribute actively to the T9.3 activities regarding QA/QC in the field of HBM, being part of the QA/QC core group, and securing the link between activity 4.1.2 and T9.3.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
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34.3 FINBA: FINBA will subcontract chemical analysis as part of project P6.2.3.a_Y1 focusing on new risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures.

34.5 IISPV: IISPV will subcontract analysis including OMICS as part of project P5.1.1.b_Y1 focusing on hazard assessment of bisphenol A alternatives.

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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34.1 EASP – PIC 999859996:

During year 2 EASP team will contribute to WP4 (T4.1. “General Survey”, A4.1.1.1 “Supporting materials” and A4.1.4 “Data management and Analysis”).

In T4.1, EASP team will carry out the Spanish General Survey in adults in collaboration with UPV/EHU. As it was shown in EASP expression of interest, we plan to conduct the human biomonitoring project in adults (18-39 y) from Andalusia in the frame of the Andalusian Health Survey. During Y2, we will work in the development of the strategy of this project, including fieldwork planification and participant selection. We plan to start the collection of biological samples and the administration of questionnaires by last trimester of 2023. This activity is pending of approval and will be further discussed with VITO team in a specific meeting (18th November 2022).

In A4.1.1.1, EASP team will contribute to the update of supporting materials, specifically questionnaires for general and occupational surveys, according to the priority substances set by PARC. These activities include: update of questionnaire layout, harmonization of information on exposure determinant, identification of exposure to factors related to behaviours, adaptation and update of non-responder questionnaire, satisfaction questionnaire, matrix-specific questionnaires and interviewer manuals (working groups 1 and 2). Likewise, we will contribute to explore and propose solutions for inclusion of novel aspects in HBM studies implementation (working group 3).

In relation to A4.1.4 “Data management and Analysis”, EASP team will contribute to data analysis aimed at identifying sources and routes of exposure (A4.1.4.2), as well as exposure effects (A4.1.4.2) related to the priority substances set by PARC. During Y2 EASP team will also support data analysis focused on the study of exposure to mixtures (A4.1.4.2).

34.2 FISABIO –PIC 951714046

During the second year, FISABIO will be involved in WP 4 (T4.1 and T4.2) and WP 9 (T9.1).

In Task 4.1, FISABIO will contribute to T4.1.2 (laboratory analysis and quality assurance in human biomonitoring) by updating the information on the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods to cover the needs identified in the design of the different HBM surveys (sub-activity 4.1.2.1).

In Task 4.2, FISABIO will be involved in the review of existing knowledge and infrastructure to support the activities regarding the PFAS study in environmental monitoring (activity 4.2.2), the design of targeted monitoring activities (activity 4.2.3), and contributing to monitoring activities, including laboratory analysis and QA/QC (activity 4.2.4).

In Task 9.1, FISABIO will be involved in the identification of existing laboratory networks and drawing up a database of laboratory networks (activity 9.1.1), and leading activity 9.1.2 to promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation.

34.3 FINBA – PIC 909900838

During the second year, FINBA will be involved in WP6.

FINBA will participate in WP6 from both source identifications of environmental pollutants and biomarkers of exposure.

Will be involved in WP6 collecting data on children exposure at different chemicals (e.g. endocrine disruptors, metals, PFAS/PFOS, pesticides) from the Asturias cohort at different ages 18 months, 4, 8 and 11 years and development and health effects:

1. Ano-genital distance, will be measured and evaluated for associations during growth.
2. Proatherogenic Lipid Profile in Early Childhood
3. Weight Status and Obesity

34.4 FNS – PIC 986357790

During the second year, FNS will be involved in WP 9, tasks 9.1, 9.3, and 9.4.

In task 9.1, FNS will contribute to the development of catalogue of laboratory networks. In task 9.3.3, FNS will participate in making available generic QA/QC in toxicity studies, bioassays/effect-directed assays (EDA), and toxicokinetic studies. And in task 9.4 FNS will be involved in identifying existing training courses and materials (activity 9.4.2.) and in preparing a training plan including learning resources (web-based portal), and training events (interdisciplinary and specific to meet WP implementation needs) (activity 9.4.3).

34.5 IISPV – PIC 985772104:

During the second year, IISPV will be involved in WP4 (A4.3.2), WP5 (T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3), WP6 (T6.1 and T6.2), WP7 (T7.2 and T7.3) and WP8 (T8.2 and T8.3).

In WP4, IISPV is involved in project “P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE” linked to Task 4.3 Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys.

In WP5, IISPV is involved in all major tasks with participation in four planned projects of WP5. In particular, IISPV will continue leading and implementing the planned activities of T5.1 and T5.2 on bisphenol alternatives for which data gaps on adverse effects of individual compounds and of mixtures need to be filled. In Task 5.1, IISPV will be leading Bood-Brain-Barrier (BBB) in vitro activity and will be generating permeability data, which will be further used for BBB-PBPK models in A5.3.4. In P5.1.2.b, IISPV will be investigation of the potential adverse effects (e.g. apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action or MIE, effects on reproduction) of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on organisms belonging to different taxa (*activities i. & ii*) and development of ***In silico* and modelling tools (activity iii)**. In Task5.3, IISPV will

be contributing to different planned projects for quantitative systems toxicology and the development of new AOPs, helping with application of text-mining tools (in collaboration with A7.3.3). IISPV will also be contributing to the development of PBPK models and leading planned sub-activities of BBB kinetic modelling in A5.3.4.

IISPV has following involvement in planned projects of WP5:

P5.1.1.b HumTox /P5.1.1.b.s2_Y1_BPA_HumTox_INRAE
P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU
P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR
P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm
P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer

In WP6, IISPV is involved in T6.1 and T6.2 with major participation in four planned projects. IISPV will contribute to the development and refinement of quantitative networks of AOPs for selected endpoints/AOs and to the (re-)designing of regulatory-relevant IATAs for these endpoints. In 6.2, IISPV will participate in activities related to A6.2.2 modelling exposure through life (lead for chemical group PFAS and contributing to development of PBPK models for other chemicals) and T6.2.3 real-life mixture assessment, where the expertise of IISPV experts in various statistical methods and modeling tools will be utilized. IISPV involvement in planned projects of WP6:

P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR
P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS_AUTH
P6.2.3_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM
P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO
P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS
P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS

In WP7, IISPV is involved in T7.2 and T7.3 with major participation in planned transversal activities and projects. In T7.2, IISPV will be participating in landscape and FAIRness assessment of major databases, repositories, platforms relevant for PARC, and starting the development of solutions in selected use cases. IISPV is leading Task 7.3 Innovative Analysis and co-lead of A7.3.2 (uncertainty analysis), A7.3.3 (text mining) and A7.3.4 (other emerging methods) and responsible for task-level planning, coordination, meeting management and reporting.

IISPV is leading the planned project "P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV".

In WP8, IISPV is involved in Task 8.2 and Task 8.3 with active participation in transversal activities and planned projects. In particular, IISPV will be contributing to computational method development for the Early warning systems (EWS) on chemical risks (T8.2) and the development of an overarching integrative model network that encompasses all modelling tools developed and used in the partnership in a harmonised approach (T8.3). Involvement in planned projects:

P8.2.1.a_Y1_EWS_SLU
P8.3.2.a_Y1_DIMN_AUTH

34.6 INSST – PIC 890173948

In the second year the INSST will be involved in WP4 (activity 4.1.1 and 4.1.3) and WP8 (Tasks 8.1, 8.2 and 8.3).

In activity 4.1.1 (Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies), the INSST participates in the occupational survey. The INSST will contribute to the development of the SOPs for the sampling strategy and chemical analysis of the prioritized substances (cytostatic drugs, anaesthetics gases,

disinfectants as well as the questionnaires for the exposure survey. We will recruit around 150 workers from hospitals in Bizkaia (a northern region of Spain) for the exposure assessment (the UG will recruit workers from the south to have a representative sample size for Spain).

In activity 4.1.3 (Link Exposure and health related information) we will contribute to the linking of exposure in occupational settings with health effects, especially providing information on the exposure biomarkers used for the prioritized substances.

In Task 8.1 (Safety and Sustainable by Design) the INSST will contribute to translate the knowledge on SSbD developed in the field of nanomaterials to the general chemical substances. Specifically, on the analysis of the applicability of SSbD tools for nanomaterials to general chemicals (activity 8.1.2).

In Task 8.2 (Scientific and technical basis for an Early Warning System) we will contribute to the validation of monitoring tools to capture exposures.

In Task 8.3 (Integrative models) we will contribute to the inventory of models, specifically with models for exposure and risk assessment of occupational exposures.

34.7 UCLM – PIC 999840208

In WP4, UCLM is involved in task 4.2 on the monitoring of chemicals in the environment and humans considering multiples sources. In particular, UCLM collaborates in the project focused on endocrine disrupting chemicals with the review of existing knowledge and infrastructure, design of monitoring studies, and data analysis and transfer.

In WP6, UCLM will participate in activity 6.4.4 about risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity, namely in two of the projects of that task. Project 2 of Taks 6.4.4 pursues the reduction of complexity of environmental risk assessment of plant protection products through the identification of the most relevant predictors of risk among biodiversity. Our role will consist of providing support to the possible assessment of vertebrate species within the pool of potential predictors. P6.4.4.d_Y1 of activity 6.4.4. is focused on the quantification of the impact of plant protection products relative to other stressors through landscape risk assessment. In this context, we have designed a case study to be developed in farmland areas of central Spain where we will be monitoring biodiversity groups (invertebrates, reptiles and birds) and potentially linking their ecological status to the different environmental stressors, including pesticides. During year 2 of PARC, we will launch the case study implementation.

34.8 UPV/EHU – PIC 999865234

During the second year, UPV/EHU will be involved in WP4 (A4.1.1, A4.1.2)
P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

Sub-activity 4.1.1.1: UPV/EHU is leader of the task regarding the update and conversion of informed consent and information materials for participants of the aligned studies. These activities include coordination with EU legal team to ensure compliance, contacting survey owners regarding their needs to ensure implementation, creation of information leaflets documents for participants, positive and negative response forms. UPV/EHU will also participate in the team that will work on developing and adapting SOPs for biological samples collection, and other supporting materials to the PARC Aligned Studies, that will enable harmonization of the information gathered from participants to the different HBM campaigns undertaken during the PARC project.

Sub-activity 4.1.1.2.: During year 2 UPV/EHU, together with EASP, will participate in the Aligned Studies for the adult population as part of (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO). As shown in

UPV/EHU expression of interest, we will conduct this study in participants from ages 19-39, in the framework of the Health Survey of the Basque Country. During Y2 we will work on the development and logistics of the project, including fieldwork and participant selection. We plan to start the collection of biological samples and administering the questionnaires by mid-end of 2023. (This activity is pending of approval by WP4 leaders, and will be discussed with VITO on the 18th November 2022).

Sub-activity 4.1.1.4. UPV/EHU has also expressed interest in the occupational survey for healthcare workers, and is currently discussing collaboration within this PARC project. UPV/EHU will work together with UGR and INSST, who have already started contacting professionals and developing the survey strategy in a hospital in the Basque Country (P4.1.1.4.ac_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_RUMC).

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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35- NATURVARDsverket, SWEDEN (SEPA) – PIC 998884079

SEPA's main activities under 2023-2024 are linked to the Grant Signatory role. SEPA is responsible for the national environmental monitoring programme in Sweden. Screening of emerging pollutants and health-related human biomonitoring are parts of this programme. Therefore, SEPA's expertise and interests are mainly connected to monitoring and exposure (WP4) and Early Warning System (WP8.2).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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35.1 UGOT – PIC 999981925

During the second year UGOT will be involved in WP 6.4, especially in sub-activity 6.4.1.1. "OPREMIX". (Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe). Main collaborators will be BRUNEL, AGES, UBA and the Ecotoxcentre. Main activities will be to disseminate and evaluate the questionnaire on current practice and the implementation of a range of case studies in which different mixture assessment approaches (classic approaches, modern and demanding in-depth mixture evaluation approaches as well as the MAF) will be comparatively assessed and their performance evaluated in the context of major EU regulations, such as the pesticide Regulation, REACH or the biocide Regulation. It is also planned to establish an in-depth collaboration with UFZ on the role of NAMS for mixture assessment.

35.2 KI – PIC 999978530

During Year 2 KI will be active in Tasks 5.3, 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3 and 9.4.

In WP5, KI will be active in activity 5.3.2 on the development of AOPs for endocrine-mediated pathways. KI will contribute expertise in toxicology, testing and assessment of endocrine disruptors (ED), as well as with expertise in AOP-development, including systematic review methodology and weight of evidence assessment.

In WP6, KI will contribute to activity 6.1.1 on the development of Integrated Approaches to testing and Assessment (IATA) and Defined Approaches (DA), as well as 6.1.2 on the Evaluation of IATAs/DAs through case studies" in activities related to ED. For these tasks, KI will specifically bring expertise on regulatory processes, requirements and needs for the identification and assessment of EDs, development and application of AOP-networks, and weight-of evidence assessment methodology. KI will also

contribute with expertise in epidemiology and human biomonitoring to activity 6.2.4 on the collection and generation of data for health impact assessment (HIA) of PARC priority chemicals’, ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. Finally, KI will be involved in four case studies (CS) in Task 6.3: KI will lead CS8 to review workplace guidance values for reproductive and developmental toxicants and be involved in CS3 on investigating how regulatory information is used in workplace chemical risk assessment. In CS3 and CS8, KI will contribute to study design and data collection through expertise in occupational health and safety regulations, risk assessment occupational toxicology. KI will participate in CS16 on identifying practical challenges for quantitative expressions of uncertainty, contributing with expertise in risk assessment and questionnaire design. Furthermore, KI will be involved in CS17 on developing approaches for evaluating quality of data from *in vitro* studies of ED, where KI will provide expertise on evidence appraisal methodology and regulatory processes and requirements.

In WP7, KI will contribute to iterative refinement of the PARC DMP, training and development of FAIR Implementation Profiles and roadmaps (T7.1), continuous development of the PARC data landscape and implementation of FAIR principles and solutions (T7.2) and contribute to the development of innovative data integration approaches (relating to AOP-related use cases) as well as the cross-WP ontology working group (T7.3). The work entails continuous development and communication/feedback from diverse activities regarding FAIR nanosafety data, including input from KIs involvement in the GO FAIR Implementation Network, the AdvancedNanoIN.

In WP9, KI will contribute to activity 9.4.2 “Existing training courses and materials”. KI together with the other partners will search for existing training courses and programs, and identify existing learning resources responding to the previously identified training needs. The suitability of the identified training (objectives and contents) and adequacy and relevance of learning resources contents will be discussed with experts from other WPs and decided which to be made available. KI will also be active in activity 9.4.3 “Training plan”. In this task the topics identified in the training needs assessment (activity 9.4.1) and information collated in activity 9.4.2, KI will with the other partners create a PARC training plan with training provided by PARC in the next years. In activity 9.4.4 “Support to local organizers” KI will provide support to organizers of training events in PARC for example related to preparation of materials for event dissemination, registration support, preparation and distribution of certificates, preparation and distribution of training evaluation surveys, and training evaluation assessment.

35.3 ULUND – PIC 999901318

During Year 2 ULUND will be active in WP4 and WP6.

In WP4 (Task 4.1), ULUND will participate in the occupational study on waste management (4.1.1.4) by design and preparation including the necessary documents and SOPs, recruit workers and controls and perform sampling and chemical analyses. ULUND will also participate in the general survey for children and adolescents and will during year 2 write amendments to the ethical committees to align with PARC study protocols, recruit and sample the study groups and perform chemical analyses. Also, ULUND will aid in 4.1.2 for laboratory analyses and quality assurance for further development of a sustainable HBM system.

In WP6 (Task 6.3 and 6.4.4), ULUND will participate in further development of innovation in regulatory risk assessment.

35.4 ORU – PIC 999650088

In WP4, task 4.3_T02, ORU will participate in an inventory of existing QA/QC procedures and guidances in SS/NTS (HRMS, EDA) with the goal to develop QA/QC criteria for HRMS and high-

throughput EDA. In P4.3_E01- Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants, ORU will participate in method development and development of a proof of concept for high-throughput EDA. ORU will participate in study design and a toolbox of innovative methods for screening of WWTP effluents and in implementation of the methods for assessing release of chemicals of emerging concern into the water cycle. ORU will be in the core group of M1.3: high throughput EDA for environmental exposure assessment. In 4.3_E02 Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based/EDA screening methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel animal species ORU will be involved in the core group for selection of sentinel species.

In WP8, ORU will be involved in Task 8.2 and contribute to the conceptualization of an early warning system, using monitoring tools for samples from humans, environment, food, and products using effect-based methods, suspect and non-target screening tools and EDA.

35.5 RISE – PIC 999613422

During the first and second year RISE will be involved in WP6

In WP6, RISE will be involved in Task 6.4, project 6.4.3.a, A6.4.3. “Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy”. P 6.4.3.a will be continued year 2, with the completion of two reports (AD 6.4.3.1b: Report on current screening and enforcement structures, AD 6.4.3.1c: Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards, both in M24). Mapping activities regarding existing data structures relevant to substances in products and materials will conclude, and this will inform a set of case studies covering the final aspect of P6.4.3.a. Under A6.4.3, two additional projects will be developed based on the outcomes of AD 6.4.3.1b and AD 6.4.3.1c, to follow in Y3.

RISE is also inventorying of existing databases in conjunction with basic information regarding scope, access, and methods. This includes: 1) Map existing landscaping activities, reports and publications of online chemical databases and chemicals in articles. 2) Summarize a master list of existing chemical databases in previous landscaping activities. The master list will be complemented by results from the survey to member states and potential new findings. 3) Investigate previously used methods to assess chemical databases for parameters like transparency, region, source type, preparation, extractability, legal status, confidence, reliability etc. 4) Suggest initial parameters and criteria to evaluate all identified databases. End of year 1 and beginning of Year 2 this work will be complemented according to further needs in discussion with WP7 and other stakeholders, such as criteria for FAIR-data, data structures etc.

35.6 SU – PIC 999885022

Stockholm University will be involved in WP6.3 Review of risk assessment methodology. Stockholm University will be leading four case studies: Identification of loopholes for substances with biocidal properties; Methods to identify coordination needs towards a ‘one substance one assessment’ approach; Evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies; Identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk. In addition, Marlene Ågerstrand is the co-task leader of 6.3.

35.7 KEMI – PIC 937974093

During the second year KEMI will mainly be involved in WP6.

KEMI is a supervisory authority under the Swedish Government and work to ensure sound management of chemicals, reducing the risk of humans and the environment getting harmed by chemicals. KEMI has three departments, Development of Legislation and Other Instruments, involved in EU work, substance assessments, proposals for regulatory measures and development of rules at EU and

international level; Authorisation and Guidance, evaluating applications for pesticides and providing information and training on rules applying to chemicals; Enforcement and Registries, carrying out inspections and market surveillance, providing national guidance on enforcement, and keeping Products and Pesticides Registers. Given this expertise, KEMI is co-leading WP6 on innovation in regulatory risk assessment. Based on the specific experience in the area of enforcement as well as evaluation of plant protection products, KEMI will be a key contributor in developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles (activity 6.4.3) and establishing holistic risk assessment approaches to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity (activity 6.4.4).

35.8 IVL – PIC 999476361

In WP4 IVL will be active in activity 4.2.1 to ensure that the future monitoring programs are in line with the prioritization activities. In activity 4.2.2 IVL will contribute in the inventory of environmental monitoring programmes and specimen/sample banks as well as analytical methods or chemical compound groups. In activity 4.2.3 IVL will be co-leading the activity for setting up the monitoring programmes for EDCs and partaking in the monitoring programme for PFAS.

In WP6 the IVL team will be active in activity 6.2.1 with specific scientific knowledge in method development and occupational exposures with emphasis on metals. Furthermore IVL contributes in the working groups of consumer exposures and exposure via the environment by identifying data-sets that can be used by PARC. In activity 6.2.2. IVL participates with scientific expertise in occupational exposures, all exposure routes, and also dermal exposure and its contribution to internal dose as input for modelling parameters. In activity 6.2.3 IVL contributes with datasets for the HBM working group. IVL is also active within activity 6.2.4 in relation to exposure data inventories and scientific expertise in the area of derived exposure and effect associations.

In WP8, for task 8.1 IVL is co-leading the activity 8.1.3 about SSbD case studies. The work will focus on establishing and operating a first iteration of tests of various tolls for SSbD in collaboration with industrial partners. In particular, collaboration with case studies already ongoing in Mistra SafeChem will be explored. For Task 8.2 IVL will work with obstacles in current regulation for the implementation of an early warning system.

IVL does not envision the use of subcontractors during the period, and does not envision the use of in-kind contribution from third parties.

35.9 SLV – PIC 997318402

In WP1, SLV contributes by taking on the role as National Hub Contact Point, NHCP as well as coordinating the Swedish National Hub.

In WP8, SLV has no planned activities for 2023.

35.10 SLU – PIC 999887350

In the second year, SLU will be involved in WP 4.2, 4.3, 5.1, 5.2, 6.2, 6.4, 8.2

In WP4, SLU will be involved in Task 4.2 to support the preparation of harmonized protocols for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) monitoring and analysis and preparation of the monitoring campaigns for PFAS. The team will bring its analytical expertise on environmental matrices and more particularly on water matrices, but also their knowledge on monitoring sites and sampling tools. SLU will contribute to effect-directed analysis (EDA) and suspect and non-target screening approaches for environmental multisource monitoring. Monitoring data will be used for prioritization of chemicals in Task 4.2. In Task 4.3, SLU will contribute to target, suspect and non-target screening approaches as well as effect-based monitoring that will be beneficial to early warning systems and will contribute to the elaboration of a consensual inventory of method performance and QA/QC criteria for HRMS and high-throughput EDA. SLU will also contribute to mining chemical information from wastewater

treatment plants for human community and environmental exposure assessments.

In WP5, SLU will be involved in filling data gaps on reproductive toxicity potency of chemicals and relevant mixtures of chemicals in invertebrate water snails (*Lymnaea stagnalis*). Naturally produced algae toxins will be studied in WP5.1a and BPA-alternatives will be studied in WP5.1b. Furthermore, SLU will contribute in development of new advanced methods (NAMs) for the use in toxicity testing on *Lymnaea stagnalis*. This work in WP5.2 will provide tools for a better understanding of the toxic potency with the use of reproductive, developmental, behavioral and genetic endpoints.

In WP6, SLU will be involved in Task 6.2 and contribute to the development of physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models for mixture exposures to PFAS. In addition, SLU will be involved in PBPK model developments for other prioritized substances. SLU will be involved also in activity 6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity to improve the Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA) for plant protection products. Whereas we will be part of two subprojects, project 1 Reduce complexity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity and project 2 Reduce complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity. We will provide and use our monitoring data, expertise in modelling to simplify and improve predictive power of ERA as well as testing and evaluation of potential ecological indexes to contribute to a system-based ERA.

In WP8, SLU will be involved in Task 8.2 and contribute to the development of early warning monitoring tools for samples from humans, environment, food, and products using suspect and non-target screening tools and their coupling to EDA. Risk ranking of contaminants of emerging concern. There will be a strong link to Task 4.2 and Task 4.3 through the development of monitoring and analytical tools relevant for early warning systems.

35.11 UMU – PIC 999881821

During the second year, UMU will be involved in WP 4.1 and WP 8.2.

In WP4, UMU (Maria Wennberg) will be involved in activity 4.1.1a Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct, in WG2 and WG3. MW will bring expertise on questionnaires for HBM and health studies used in Sweden to the group (1 PM for year 2).

In WP8, UMU (Patrik Andersson) will be involved in Task 8.2 on development of an early warning system (EWS). We are leading a workgroup on computational methodologies for early warning. Year 2 will be focused on building the EWS framework and developing text mining tools as a first step of the computational EWS. The initial framework will be described in two deliverables during year 2. (13 PM for year 2).

35.12 UU – PIC 999985029

In WP5, UU will contribute to NAM development by analyzing human neurospheres with Cell Painting and by a novel phenotoxicity score, as well as by establishing epigenomic markers for developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) and endpoints for endocrine disruption-induced DNT (Task 5.2.1). Furthermore, UU will contribute to development of a NAM for the assessment of chemical hazards to marine prokaryotes by integrating high-throughput microscopy and the detection of single-cell phenotypes (activity 5.2.2).

In WP7, UU will scope methods for federated or privacy-preserving data analysis and contribute to methods for uncertainty in hazard evaluation and P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO.

In WP8, UU will scope and evaluate STACKn for integrating models as a front-end access platform for

PARC network.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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36- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, GREECE (AUTH) – PIC 999895692
AUTH is WP8 co-leader, T8.1 and Task 8.3 co-leader, Grant Signatory (GS) and National Hub Contact Point (NHCP).

During the second year, AUTH will be involved in WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9.

In WP1, AUTH will contribute to the scientific and administrative coordination and management activities, participating in T1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 as Management Board member and NHCP. In addition, AUTH will carry out the activities as GS Board member, coordinating 4 Greek affiliated entities.

In WP2, AUTH will contribute on the development of PARCopedia and is responsible for the computational implementation layer of knowledge in the form of a Content Management System (CMS) to connect the data landscape created by the data-generating WPs 4-6 and 8-9 (overseen by WP7) with one or more portals, embedded in the PARC website.

In WP3, AUTH has the responsibility of Activity T3.1.b, related to the establishment and running of the International Board (IB), where in Y2, the relevant IB meeting has to be organised and to take place, where AUTH will also have the responsibility of preparing the respective minutes and translating the meeting outcomes into input on knowledge on the state of the art in chemical risk assessment, of relevant key initiatives in RA globally. In addition, AUTH will contribute to the communication, dissemination, and awareness activities, as well as in networking and synergies, with particular emphasis to activities related to the SSbD concept and implementation.

In WP4, AUTH will be involved in Task 4.1, and more specifically in P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL - Occupational survey in the waste management sector, where samples from occupants in the electronic waste sector will be collected and analysed for heavy metals and toxic organic compounds. In Task 4.3, AUTH will be involved in 8 of the 12 projects, related to innovative methods, QA/QC requirements to be specifically applied for HRMS/EDA based screening approaches, generation of data to support EWS, and advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS.

In WP5, AUTH will be involved in Task 5.3, and more specifically in the use of omics data, system biology models, towards the development of AOPs and in kinetic models to support human pathology, thus involved in the following projects: P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR - Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment; P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm - AOP Development; P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer - PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology. AUTH has a significant experience in bioinformatics and systems biology models and is co-leading the WG on computational approaches towards the development of AOPs.

In WP6, AUTH is involved in the Task 6.1, in the development of IATAs, contributing with omics data from human cohorts, in vitro and in vivo models, as well as bioinformatics analysis to the following projects: P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM - Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies; P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen - Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption; P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR - Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA)

for Systemic Target Organ Toxicity. AUTH is also co-leading activity 6.2.2 on modelling exposure through life, and is involved in the project P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH Refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment, where has the responsibility for coordinating the work towards the development of generic PBPK models development. AUTH will also contribute in the project P6.2.3_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM – RealLifeMixtures, both with the selection of real life mixtures with available data from cohorts, as well as in the kinetics analysis of mixtures.

In WP7, AUTH is involved in Task 7.1, in the processes of FAIR data policy and implementation by providing input on the FAIR requirements on exposure, hazard and risk data modelling. In Task 7.2 AUTH will contribute on identification of the requirements for a PARC FAIR data hub, and in the translation of the draft architecture that will be cross-checked with WP2 and WP8 for integration with PARCopedia and with modelling toolboxes, where AUTH has the responsibility of development. In Task 7.3, AUTH will contribute with computational methods to maximise the reliability and usefulness of meta- and pooled analysis of heterogeneous exposure and omics data, with uncertainty analysis tools and the development of AI and text mining algorithms in the project P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV - Alternative Predictive Testing Strategy for the Safety of Chemicals based on Integrative Systems Toxicology.

AUTH is co-leading WP8, as well as T8.1 and Task 8.3. In Task 8.1, AUTH work will focus on the translation of the EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation and the communication of Task 8.1 with stakeholders outside PARC, as well as in the computational implementation of the toolbox to be development. The work in Task 8.1 will be included in the project P8.1.2.a_Y1_SSbD_toolbox_AUTH - Development of a toolbox for supporting SSbD (under AUTH responsibility). In Task 8.2, AUTH will be responsible for the further evolution of the EWS concept, as well as the development of the respective computational toolbox that has to be developed to support the PARC EWS, contributing to the project P8.2.1.a_Y1_EWS_SLU - Conceptualization of early warning monitoring tools. In Task 8.3, AUTH has the responsibility of the development of the model network, while, as developers of INTEGRA, are collaborating closely with colleagues from PARC to link internal dose estimates of parent compounds and metabolites with system biology models, towards systems biology based AOPs, while ensuring interoperability with the data available and the respective uncertainty analysis requirements defined in WP7. In order to render INTEGRA interoperable with the rest of the model network, modifications will be done in the direction of following the common input-outputs formats (entry points) that will be commonly decided in T8.3 for the PARC model network, including necessary modules for adapting to the required spatial and temporal scale(s). In this sense, INTEGRA will be able to provide modelling services to the various parts of the source to effect continuum based on user needs, among other developed available modules in PARC network. AUTH is also responsible for the respective project P8.3.2.a_Y1_DIMN_AUTH - Preparing design and implementation of the PARC model network with a conceptual model based on existing and new collaborations.

With regard to WP9, AUTH will contribute to the further development on building exposure monitoring capacities, mainly as liaison of WP8.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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36.1 EFET – PIC 959188478
During the second year Y2, EFET will be involved in WP3 (Synergies, collaborations and awareness), WP4 (Monitoring and exposure) and WP8 (Concepts and toolboxes).

In WP3, EFET is involved in Task 3.2 on Communication, dissemination, and awareness and Task 3.3 on Networking and Synergies.

In task 3.2 EFET will be involved in activity ‘Development and implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy plan’ and will contribute to the development of communication materials and their translation in Greek. EFET will actively repost announcements of PARC in its website and social media, in order to raise awareness to the citizens and other national stakeholders. Also, EFET in collaboration with NIJZ is responsible for the activities on Risk Communication, and the development of a Risk Perception questionnaire towards stakeholder representatives who act as risk communicators in PARC and start the questionnaire validation.

In task 3.3, will contribute to the database of partnership (SYNnet) by providing data on national research projects (e.g. with EFSA’s projects).

In WP4 (Monitoring and exposure), EFET is involved in task 4.2 and will collaborate with NKUA in the EDCs monitoring campaign.

In WP8 (Concepts and toolboxes), EFET is involved in Task 8.2 ‘Early warning system (EWS) ‘and will contribute to the development of EWS and the creation of a prioritization framework for chemical substances. EFET in collaboration with AUTH and NKUA will contribute in validation of the EWS.

36.2 GCSL – PIC 912807637

During the second year, GCSL will be involved in WP1 (Coordination and management), WP2 (A common science-policy agenda), WP3 (Synergies, collaborations and awareness), WP8 (Concepts and toolboxes), WP9 (Building infrastructural and human capacities) and probably in WP4 (Monitoring and exposure).

GCSL is WP3 co-leader and member of the MB of PARC and participates to the MB meetings.

In WP1, GCSL is involved as partner in all tasks (T 1.1 on Overall executive management and support of the Partnership, T1.2 on Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans, T1.3 on Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership and T1.4 on Ethics framework).

In WP2, GCSL is involved as partner in Task 2.1 on Priority setting and Task 2.2 on Knowledge management and uptake into policy. More particular, under Task 2.1, GCSL will participate in the following activities: a) Implementation of the priority strategy, b) Peer-review of the projects and c) Development and implementation of a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM). Under Task 2.2, GCSL will participate in the activities concerning PARCopedia and PARCroute and more specifically in the conceptual development and content generation/ roadmap development thereof.

In WP3, GCSL is involved in Task 3.1 on Building effective interactions, Task 3.2 on Communication, dissemination, and awareness and Task 3.3 on Networking and Synergies.

GCSL is WP3 co-leader and together with INSA (WP3 co-leader) organizes regular WP and task co-leaders meetings.

GCSL will work as partner in both activities of Task 3.1 concerning the Running of Stakeholders Forum and International Board. In task 3.2 GCSL will be involved in activity A3.2.2 Development and implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy plan and will contribute to the development of communication materials.

In Task 3.3 GCSL will contribute to the update of the established database of partnerships, projects, networks and activities (Activity A3.3.1 Inventory of scientific activities relevant to PARC) and to the revision and update of the interaction strategy between SYNnet and WPs (Activity A3.3.3 Development of internal and external interaction strategies).

In WP8, GCSL will participate in Task 8.2: Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system

(EWS) on chemical risks and more specifically in the project P8.2.1.a of Task 8.2 entitled “conceptualization of early warning monitoring tools”.

In WP9, GCSL will be involved in Task 9.1: Laboratory networking, Task 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities, Task 9.3: Joint activities – harmonization and Task 9.4: Training and will contribute to the mapping of the existing HBM laboratories and to the updating of the HBM catalogue (Activity A9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of the laboratory networks) to the list of networks in need for promotion or support (Activity A9.1.2 Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation) to the development of strategy and tools for a desirable level of coordination and linkage (Activity A9.1.3 Facilitate the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks) to the development and implementation of the dashboard (Activity A9.1.4 Develop an interactive tool (dashboard) to show the capacities of the laboratory networks) to the mapping of the existing air, indoor, and article exposure monitoring networks (Activity A9.2.1 Mapping of exposure monitoring capacities) to the determination of existing gaps in the catalogues (HBM, air) (Activity A9.2.2 Strengthening of exposure monitoring capacities) to the identification of training opportunities (Activity A9.4.2 Identification of existing training courses, programs and opportunities (outside PARC) on topics identified) to the creation of a PARC training plan (Activity A9.4.3 Training plan) and to supporting local organizers of training events organized under PARC (Activity A9.4.4 Support to local organizers)

GCSL has also expressed interest in participating in certain projects of WP4.

36.3 NKUA – PIC 999643007

During the second year, NKUA will be involved in WP3 (Synergies, collaborations and awareness), WP4 (Monitoring and exposure) and WP8 (Concepts and toolboxes).

In WP3, NKUA is involved in Task 3.1 on Building effective interactions, Task 3.2 on Communication, dissemination, and awareness and Task 3.3 on Networking and Synergies. In Task 3.1., NKUA will contribute to the selection criteria and recruitment of the PARC stakeholder forum and international board. Moreover, NKUA will be responsible for guiding a member of the international board and a member of the stakeholder forum. NKUA will assure that these PARC bodies operate as expected. In task 3.2, NKUA will contribute to the creation of communication materials and their translation in Greek, will actively repost announcements of PARC in the social media, and will try to raise awareness to the citizens by performing dissemination activities. In Task 3.3, NKUA will lead the establishment of SYNnet, which is the database of partnerships, projects, networks and activities. Moreover, NKUA will assure its population with the synergies and will contribute to the update of the internal and external interaction rules.

In WP4, NKUA is involved in Task 4.2. NKUA will contribute to the application of wide-scope retrospective suspect screening of EDCs and PFAS in digitally archived high-resolution mass spectrometry data. Therefore, NKUA will provide exposure data which will be fed to the prioritization scheme of T4.2. Moreover, NKUA will contribute to the selection of samples for the monitoring campaign that is envisioned within T4.2. NKUA will support the organization of the workshop that will assist the sample collection and its distribution to analytical laboratories. NKUA will provide knowhow and lessons learnt based on its participation in the LIFE APEX project.

In WP8, NKUA is involved in Task 8.2. NKUA is activity co-leader together with UMU and AUTH. NKUA will contribute to the conceptualization of the early-warning system. Moreover, NKUA will review the computational tools required to support the EWS. NKUA will contribute with additional computational tools and more specifically in the early detection of signals in the scientific literature and in the grey literature using text mining approaches. NKUA is a member of the NORMAN Association and is a major contributor in the NORMAN Database System. Therefore, NKUA will bring in additional

lines of evidence that can be used in the establishment of the EWS. Finally, NKUA will draft the deliverable “Conceptualization of a computational system using AI and systems modeling for environmental and human samples and products for the EWS”.

36.4 UOC - PIC 999588978.

During the second year of PARC project the UOC will participate in WP3 Tasks: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, WP4, Task:4.1, WP5 Task:5.1, WP8, Tasks 8.2, 8.3

Task 3.1

Our institution will continue its contribution under this task in projects such as: a) Dissemination to local/regional authorities in the EU via targeted written reports and articles in specialised press, newsletters etc. b) Dissemination to research community and experts from diverse fields through scientific publications in international peer-reviewed journals with high impact factor and participation in international conferences. c) Dissemination to entrepreneurs and industry through articles on business magazines, participation in industry conferences/events, as well as social media. d) Dissemination to the general population and other stakeholders the projects website, targeted video, TV and radio as well as articles in specialised press, newsletters, press releases, leaflets, and brochures.

Task 3.2

The UOC will continue the contribution to the preparation and publication of different leaflets and brochures describing chemical hazards, specially designed printed material which will target different population groups. We will also contribute to the design of the Web site with all relevant and latest information for chemical hazards and risk assessment methodologies.

Task 4.1

The Laboratory of Toxicology will participate in all procedures needed for the sampling, sample preparation, analysis and interpretation of the results regarding the chemicals of interest. We will use micronuclei frequency, hair analysis and telomeres’ length as real life exposure biomarkers for close and effective biomonitoring implemented in general population and special/high risk/vulnerable groups. Studies in occupationally exposed population to different pollutants will also be conducted. Furthermore, statistic combination of biomonitoring data of various origin will be used to obtain valuable, unique results and trends.

Task 5.1

Primary Human Nucleus Pulposus Cells (hNPC) proliferation assay, Primary hNPC migration assay, Primary hNPC neuronal differentiation assay, Neuronal morphology, immunotoxicity studies as well as traditional sub-chronic and chronic rodent toxicity studies will be performed by the UOC for the evaluation of the chemicals tested in this task.

Task 8.1

Liquid chromatography - mass spectrometry (LC-MS), Gas chromatography - mass spectrometry (GC-MS) High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) ELISA spectrophotometers will be used for the experimental analysis of certain compounds in different matrices This will contribute to the evaluation and the improvement of the models under development in this task.

Task 8.2

Under this task the UOC will design, evaluate and implement the “Real-Life Risk Simulation” model (RLRS). This model evaluates low-dose long- term exposures and could also enhance more than one chemical and multiple routes of exposure. The outcome of the model will give results of Exposure estimates for multiple chemicals, Risk characterization based on aggregated/cumulative exposure, Exposure assessment for different population groups over a long period of time.

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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37- BENAKI PHYTOPATHOLOGICAL INSTITUTE, GREECE (BPI) – PIC 998193633

During the second year, BPI will be involved in WPs 3, 4, 5, 6, and 9. More specifically:

T3.2: BPI is contributing to the Development of a graphical identity for PARC as well as in all actions related to communication through the website or social media.

T3.3: BPI is contributing to various activities that aim to facilitate Networking and Synergies inside and outside PARC.

A4.1.2: Laboratory analysis and quality assurance. BPI will be involved in the respective transversal activities.

A4.1.4: BPI will contribute to P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU project in “Sources and routes” as well as “Exposure- effect” activities to link HBM4EU data with exposure sources and effects respectively.

T4.2: BPI will contribute in the establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors as well as in the establishment of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring.

T4.3: BPI staff will be involved in Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern, as well as occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.

A5.1.1: BPI will participate by exploring the AR transactivation potential of selected Enniatins and Alternaria natural toxins as well as the estrogenic potential of Alternaria Toxins.

A5.1.2: BPI is co-leading the project of BPA alternatives and associated mixtures- identification of data gaps and NAM development.

A5.3.1: BPI will be involved in the “Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment” project.

A5.3.2: BPI will be contributing in the AOP development project in the areas of immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption and in the group of Effect markers.

T6.1: BPI will be involved in the development of IATAs in the areas of genotoxicity and endocrine disruption as well as in assessing the Human relevance of IATAs.

A6.2.1: BPI will be involved in the Aggregate exposure project.

A6.2.3: BPI is leading the Hazard group inside the Real-Life mixtures project, where several Case studies are going to be implemented in order to add compounds in groups based on their toxicological properties (common effects).

A6.2.4: BPI will be involved in the health impact assessment Case Studies to commence on Year 2.

T6.3: BPI is 6.3 co-leader. BPI also leads the project “Review of effect-specific risk assessment” and leaders of the Case studies 17 and 18 on Endocrine disruptors inside this project. In addition, BPI participates in the project “Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in risk assessment” in Case study CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND.

A6.4.1: BPI is involved in 2 projects inside 6.4.1 (Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe and Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessments through the use of monitoring data and NAMs).

A6.4.2: BPI is participating in 2 projects (Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape and Next generation risk assessment applied in practice).

WP9: BPI is involved in 3 projects inside WP9 (Building capacities in human and environmental biomonitoring, harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing) as well as in transversal activities for training.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties	N

(articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	

38- Département Fédéral de l'Intérieur, SWITZERLAND (FOPH) – PIC 957586329	
During the second year, FOPH will be involved in A4.1.1 and T6.2. In activity 4.1.1, we are contributing to the development of questionnaires for the harmonized studies, by reviewing the questionnaires regarding relevance for priority substances and harmonization for different age groups. In activity 6.2.1. We are contributing to the projects “aggregate exposure” and “source-to-dose modelling”. In the project “aggregate exposure” together with other partners we will conduct two case studies on priority substances: one on metals and one on PFAS. Also, we contribute to model selection for both projects.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

39- AGROSCOPE, SWITZERLAND - PIC 998365711	
Agroscope is involved in WP6 (A6.4.4) aiming to support policy-making and the regulatory processes by developing regulatory feasible approaches for reducing risks to humans and the environment. Focus will be on the mitigation of pesticide impacts on biodiversity on a landscape scale through agri-environmental interventions (incl. flower strips, hedges).	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
No subcontracting of tasks is envisaged.	
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
No, we do not envision use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties.	

40- Policlinique Médicale Universitaire de Lausanne, SWITZERLAND (UNISANTE) – PIC 903030134	
During the second year, Unisanté will be involved in T4.1 and T6.2. In T4.1, we will prepare the further analyses and extension of the SKIPOGH cohort. This phase will include the submission of amendments to the ethical committee, the random selection of existing participants for further analyses (Phtalates and Calux analysis) as well as the recruitment of new volunteers. In activity 6.2.1. The exposure model inventory will be investigated to identify the more relevant models in occupational and populational exposures. A structural and functional analysis of the selected models will be conducted in order to identify similarities and potential connections points. The structural analysis will support the development of an aggregated strategy.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement	N

(MGA))?	
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

41- EIDGENOESSISCHE ANSTALT FUER WASSERVERSORGUNG ABWASSERREINIGUNG UND GEWAESSERSCHUTZ, SWITZERLAND (EAWAG) – PIC 998124569

In the second year, Eawag will continue to be active in work packages 4, 5 and 6.

WP4 (Uchem, Ecotox Center): Using our experience from recent national and international monitoring studies targeting EDCs, we will contribute to activity 4.2.2 and 4.2.3: review of existing knowledge and infrastructure and monitoring project design. Also in T4.2, we will contribute to the pilot project on establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of pilot studies addressing PFAS and EDCs. In T4.3, we will mainly contribute to the projects on wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment and screening of WWTP effluents and source-related samples to assess the release of CECs into the water cycle using emerging methods such as suspect/nontarget screening and bioassay-directed analysis. Further, we will contribute our experiences in suspect and non-target screening to transversal topics.

WP5 (Utox): In activity 5.2.1., we particularly contribute to the analysis of acute fish toxicity predictions using the RTgill-W1 cell line assay (according to OECD TG 249). In activity 5.2.2., we will continue to develop NAMs for neurotoxicity using the zebrafish model with a specific focus on identifying molecular markers for transient and persistent neurotoxic effects. We will moreover continue our work on machine learning models (*in silico* tools) for toxicity predictions for aquatic organisms with a specific focus on neurotoxicity in fish. Establishment of a synthetic biofilm community with a flow-through option for toxicity assessment will be initiated.

WP6 (Ecotox Center): We will continue to work on our case study 7 (Regprep) “Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Differences and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides» under T6.3 as planned. We will be involved in activity 6.4.1 on “Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe » as well as in sub-activity 6.4.4.2 “Comparative studies between different risk assessment methods and environmental monitoring” and sub-activity 6.4.4.3 development of holistic and more realistic risk assessment frameworks”.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
The Utox group intends to subcontract OECD TG249 analysis of BPA alternatives.	
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
No, we do not envision use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties.	

42- EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH, SWITZERLAND (ETHZ) – PIC 999979015

ETHZ is involved in WP5, specifically in task 3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology, which we co-lead with ITEM. Our goal is to create microbiome-integrated PBTK models that account for gut microbial metabolism as a key biotransformation process impacting human responses to chemicals, and use them to derive human exposure equivalents needed to apply new approach methods in toxicological testing. We will optimize an in vitro test method to assess metabolic parameters for chemical transformation by complex human gut microbial mixtures. This method will be applied to determine quantitative parameters needed for microbiome-integrated PBTK models. We will then integrate these parameters into in silico PBTK models and step-wise assess the relevance of microbial metabolism for toxicokinetics of priority parc chemicals. Additionally, we will evaluate zebrafish as a model test method for characterizing the impact of microbial metabolism on biologically relevant concentrations. Finally, we will contribute to establishing a complete PBTK model for natural toxins (Alternaria toxins).

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
We intend to subcontract 16S-rRNA-sequencing of microbial samples to yet undefined companies from the private sector.	
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

43- EIDGENOSSISCHE MATERIALPRUFUNGS- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT, SWITZERLAND (EMPA) – PIC 999907138

In the second year, Empa will continue to be active in work package 8. Empa is co-leading Task 8.1 on “safe and sustainable by design” and is co-leading activity 8.1.2. on “Toolbox development”. In this function, Empa is involved in all planning activities of Task 8.1. Empa will in particular contribute to the conceptual design of the toolbox for SSbD and evaluate tools to be added. In addition, Empa will start the development of missing tools in the SSbD process and embed these tools in the toolbox.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

44- FEDERAL DEPARTMENT FOR ENVIRONMENT, TRANSPORT, ENERGY AND COMMUNICATIONS, SWITZERLAND (FOEN) – PIC 999439210

FOEN is co-leading case study 7 in task 6.3, which was recently merged with other case studies to 6.3.2.a. In this function FOEN is involved in planning activities, conceptual developments as well as

data analysis. Furthermore, FOEN is part of the regulatory core group in activity 6.4.4. In this function FOEN is involved in activities establishing holistic risk assessment approaches to support and promote an efficient overall protection of biodiversity.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

45- UNIVERSITA DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA, SWITZERLAND (USI) – PIC 999585874

In year 2, USI will continue to be actively involved in both WP4 and WP6, specifically it will be involved in the following tasks and activities. A4.1.2: Laboratory analysis and quality assurance: Define the best suited exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC. Sub-activity 4.1.3.3: Roadmap to explore the links between exposures to prioritized chemical substances and health concerns in the occupational setting. In WP6, the focus will be on P6.2.4.a – Support data availability for health impact assessment (HIA): A concise inventory will be made of chemicals for which HIA has been performed in international scientific and grey literature, including the specific context (including occupational settings) and methodology. USI proposes to look at populations exposed to aromatic amines (compounds that were part of HBM4EU). Comparison of the observed health effects with the predicted effects using in vitro to in vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) methods.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

46- UNIVERSITAT BASEL, SWITZERLAND (UNIBAS) – PIC 999907914

During the second year UNIBAS will be involved primarily in WP6 with a specific focus on task 6.4. UNIBAS is co-leading – together with AGES – task 6.4 “Transposing results to risk assessment methodologies”. Within this task, UNIBAS is leading activity 6.4.2 “Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods”. In Year 2, we will concentrate on the continuation of three projects: “Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape” led by UNIBAS, “Next generation risk assessment applied in practice” led by NIPH (represented by VKM) and “Landscape and readiness of computational new approach methods based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals’ next generation risk assessment” led by UT.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement	N
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(MGA))?	
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

47- State Secretariat for Economic Affairs, SWITZERLAND (SECO) – PIC 889610475

Contribution in A6.2.3 (mixtures) WG 2 (hazard): Reporting line and knowledge exchange of used terminologies from OECD effect-biomonitoring AOP activity.

Contribution in A4.1.3 (effect–biomarkers): Adding characterised HBM effect-biomarker data from OECD effect-biomonitoring AOP activity. Adding suggested effect-biomarker mixture threshold terminologies and preliminary assessment values & guiding principles to derive them.

Contribution in A4.1.3.1 (HBM GV): Adding suggested effect-biomarker mixture threshold terminologies and preliminary assessment values & guiding principles to derive them. Using a confidence assessment scheme for assessing key studies in HBM GV derivation. In principle we aim to provide harmonisation between OECD and PARC activities related to biomonitoring.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

48- EUROPEAN CHEMICALS AGENCY, EU (ECHA) – PIC 894182376

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) is task co-leader of Task 2.1, coordinating the prioritisation process. During the second year ECHA will help to develop and define a proposal for an overall PARC Prioritisation process and prioritisation criteria. The criteria are intended to assess the policy/regulatory relevance of project proposals so the knowledge generated within PARC can contribute to EU regulatory science and policymaking. ECHA will contribute to the pool of internal reviewers created for the project review process and will act as a reviewer of several PARC projects. ECHA’s knowledge on regulatory science will also serve to guide PARC projects towards regulatory uptake through continuous interaction with different working packages and projects leaders and its participation in workshops and bilateral discussions when required. ECHA can also support the selection of case studies for further data generation (e.g. on substances of concern) and the development and validation of methods. As part of this activities ECHA will organise, together with EEA, EFSA and the JRC a workshop for the PARC consortium on the CSS indicators. During this workshop, the CSS indicators list would be shared, with timelines and data needs. The objective is to ensure that PARC projects feed directly into the CSS indicators, and to collect from partners new potential ideas. In this Workshop the EC will also present the SRIP and its links to the CSS indicators.

To allow for National and European policy-makers to submit requests for specific information to the

PARC Consortium thus ensuring PARC responds to new and urgent needs for information in the EU policy context and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for substance nomination, ECHA will also help to set up the principles and process for a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), building on the HBM4EU’s experience.”	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

49- EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY, EU (EFSA) – PIC 893964320

WP 2. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) is task co-leader of Task 2.1, and together with ECHA and ANSES, is coordinating the prioritisation process. During the second year EFSA will support and contribute to the overall PARC Prioritisation process and prioritisation criteria for regulatory relevance of the projects submitted under the AWP. EFSA will contribute to the pool of project contact points and project reviewers. EFSA will also contribute to the following up of individual projects and direct interaction with the TL and project leaders thereby supporting the regulatory impact of the proposed work. EFSA can also support the selection of case studies for further data generation (e.g. on substances of concern) and the development and validation of methods.

WP 6. EFSA is contributing to T6.2 and T6.4 projects advising and supporting the regulatory impact of the proposed work. In particular, projects on aggregated exposure, mixtures, source to dose and the protection of biodiversity. EFSA is also a member of the Scientific Advisory Group for the T6.4 project PARC_VKM project: “Next generation risk assessment – in practice”

WP7. EFSA will continue advising and supporting T7 projects in the areas of data formats and databases to ensure EU-wide harmonization of standards.

Ad hoc support and discussions with TL from WP5 and T6.1.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

50- Department of Health, UK (UKHSA) – PIC 986454887

In year2, UKHSA will take part in WP2, 4, 5, 6 and 9.

WP2- T2.3 Sustainability and exit strategy for PARC. Here UKHSA as a NHCC will continue to contribute to annual surveys, evaluation of the responses from the NHCP, liaise with WPCoL to ensure the needs of the WPs as well as the NH is recorded and acted upon. Run NH meetings virtually and face to face. Write reports and report back to MB as necessary.

UKHSA – as a NHCC will work with WP2 to develop performance criteria for the NHs, produce indicative data and report these to the WPCoL and MB.

WP4- activity 4.1.1- planning UK input to the general HBM survey. In relation to this will contribute to A4.1.2, Laboratory analysis, and quality assurance, the selection of biomarkers and study design. Will contribute to the development of novel matrices – non-invasive matrices and minimally invasive such as blood spots.

Project 4.1.3.b/c - roadmap linking exposure to health outcomes. Here UKHSA are leading the input to PFAS - and will describe the biomarkers of effect which can be assessed in the general survey. Will contribute to the discussions, meeting and related activities in this task wider than PFAS.

WP5 – project 5.3.1a - hazard assessment method development – the details are yet to be agreed.

WP6 – task 6.1 Co-lead for the IATA on thyroid function and anti-androgen activity. Bringing in expertise from the OECD Non-genotoxic Carcinogens IATA. Develop a strategy for validation of NAMs.

WP9 task 9.3 - contribute to the development of a survey to gather training needs, from WPCoL and NHCP and will use this information to support NH training programmes.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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51- BRUNEL UNIVERSITY LONDON, UK (BUL) – PIC 999749610

In year 2, BUL will contribute to WP 6, sub-activity 6.4.1.1, by designing a questionnaire for practitioners in regulatory agencies in Europe to establish regulatory approaches and practices regarding mixture risk assessment. This will contribute to the building of a consistent overarching scientific framework that can be adapted to the different protection goals (public health, occupation health, environmental protection), different chemicals (biocides, pesticides, industrial chemicals, food contact materials, etc.), data situations (data-rich versus data-poor chemicals) and regulatory contexts (prospective versus retrospective assessments, large-scale versus scenario specific approaches). Brunel will also contribute to the analysis of the data gathered. We anticipate the task to be completed by the end of 2023. As and when work on WP6 evolves, BUL team may contribute also to other activities. The plans have been agreed upon in close cooperation with ECHA.

BUL also contributes to T8.1 by working closely with Defra in Year 2 to choose and involve national stakeholders in the SSbD framework, feed that into the task lead, and support the design and operationalization criteria for the SSbD toolbox development. BUL will also help with metrics (indicators) development and selection.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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52- THE SECRETARY OF STATE FOR ENVIRONMENT, FOOD AND RURAL AFFAIRS, UK (Cefas-Defra) – PIC 999904713

During the second year, Cefas will be involved in WP5 on *Hazard assessment for human and environmental health* and WP6 on *Innovation in regulatory risk assessment*.

In WP5, Cefas will contribute to task 5.1 (toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern) and will focus on the environment, evaluating different alternative models (wild type fish embryos and marine invertebrates) to characterize the hazard from several PFAS and their mixtures, including developmental and neurotoxicity as well as endocrine, neuroendocrine, and metabolic disruption. Cefas will also contribute to task 5.2 (innovative methods and tools for environmental toxicity testing) by advancing and validating NAMs for hazard assessment. Cefas will focus on invertebrate models, especially marine, as they are key ecologically but have no current representation in regulatory testing. Cefas has a strong interest in characterizing receptors, focusing on the ligand binding domain to allow cross species extrapolations. Cefas can also contribute to task 5.3 (AOPs and PBTK models) as we employ both omics technologies and apical endpoints to characterize the hazard. Our plan is to use the blue mussel, a bivalve mollusk, filter feeder and important seafood source to characterize the toxicokinetic profile of SSRIs, a group of highly lipophilic human pharmaceuticals of increasing use. In general, Cefas is an advocate of One Health and will work towards integration of human and environmental health. The role of Cefas in WP5 is still under planning.

In WP6, Cefas will contribute to task 6.1 (IATAs on thyroid disruptors and anti-androgens). We will support the design of these IATAs and the development of AOP networks by using comparative approaches involving both zebrafish and stickleback models to increase confidence. Cefas has a strong history in test methods for androgens and anti-androgens as we developed spiggin, the glue protein in the male three-spined stickleback, as a robust biomarker of exposure. The spiggin gene has been used in generating a transgenic fish model (RADAR assay and now OECD TG251).

Both tasks 5.(1, 2, 3) and task 6.1 have clear links where task 6.1 builds further on knowledge and tools developed in WP5.

During the second year Defra will be involved in WP2 and WP8. In WP2, we have prioritised involvement in PARCroute, and will contribute to review of task 5 “table of contents” - covering the main body of the roadmap. For WP8, Defra will contribute to activity 8.1.2 on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbd), to choose and involve national stakeholders in the SSbD framework, feed that into the task lead, and support the design and operationalization criteria for the SSbD toolbox development

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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53- UK CENTRE FOR ECOLOGY & HYDROLOGY, UK (UKCEH) – PIC 897953251

In Y2, UKCEH will contribute to discussion and workshops building towards projects for submission in September 2023 and subsequent years, with main practical work commencing 2024. We are currently involved in the following work packages and tasks.

In WP4, T4.2, specifically projects relating to (i) Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors, and (ii) Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring. In T4.3 we will aim to be involved in developing innovative tools for monitoring specifically non-target screening and emerging chemicals identification.

In WP5 UKCEH will be specifically involving ourselves in tasks 5.1b and 5.2a and 5.2b and all tasks in 5.3; but we are still looking to engage with task leads for these activities.

In WP6 UKCEH will be involved in tasks including specifically T6.3 and T6.4; and tasks relating to aggregate exposure, exposure through life and concurrent mixtures in task 6.2.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?

N

54- ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, UK (EA) – PIC 998712001

In Year 2, EA will build on previous meeting input in the tasks which they are part of. We are currently involved in the following work packages and tasks;

In WP4, task 4.2, we will continue our involvement specifically in projects relating to (i) Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors, both of which are of specific interest to our organisation. In task 4.3 we will begin to be involved in taking the insights from all of this work package into early warning systems from year 2 onwards. We have a specific interest in the development of innovative tools for monitoring specifically non-target screening and emerging chemicals identification.

In WP5 from year 2 onwards members of our Chemicals Assessment Unit at the EA will be specifically involving ourselves in Activity 5.3.4., where we gain the skills and expertise required to adapt and apply PBT models in regulatory risk assessment.

In WP6 from year 2 onwards members of our Chemicals Assessment Unit at the EA will be involved in tasks including specifically 6.3, review of existing risk assessment methodology, and various sub activities in 6.4, transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies. We will strive to ensure that environmentally relevant methodologies are promoted and input on regulatory applicability of methods;

In WP8, task 8.2 we will continue to input to the work on early warning systems, having input our own National perspective of our work on early warning systems in the first year, we will collaborate on next steps.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

55- HEALTH AND SAFETY EXECUTIVE, UK (HSE) – PIC 999461811

In Y2, HSE will contribute to WP4.1, specifically to the occupational surveys (A4.1.1.4). The e-waste participation is at the institute's own cost, the healthcare participation is through PMs. We will contribute to drafting of SOPs, seek ethical approval for UK participation and recruit and undertake field work sampling. We will also contribute to discussions in T4.3 on innovative sampling such as dried blood spots and will look to participate in discussions around laboratory analysis/approval. Any additional involvement in other WPs will be at the institute's own cost.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

56- INSTITUTE OF OCCUPATIONAL MEDICINE, UK (IOM) – PIC 999464818

In Y2, IOM will contribute to T4.1, specifically to the occupational surveys (A4.1.1.4), these being the waste and health care studies. We will contribute to drafting of SOPs and contribute to the ethics submission, field work recruitment and sampling (resources dependent on available PM). Any additional involvement in other WPs will be at the institute's own cost.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

57- UNIVERSITY OF BATH, UK (UBAH) – PIC 999842924

UBAH will contribute to coordination of project E01 in WP4, task 4.3: - Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) for (I) human community and (II) environmental exposure assessment. UBAH is a co-leader of E01.

UBAH will develop methods for WBE biomarker analysis, develop WBE approaches for community-wide exposure to chemicals and contribute to a pan-European study planned in 2024 in EO1.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

58- UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN, UK (UNIABDN) – PIC 999929448

UNIABDN will contribute to WP4 and WP5.

WP4 – Project 4.3.2a H01 (Perinatal): UNIABDN will contribute by continuing to collect human fetuses and conducting chemical analyses based largely on other funding. This data will be published and shared collaboratively as required. Further human fetal samples will be available for collaborative analysis by partners in this sub-WP project as required. The aim is to enable the data from targeted and untargeted screening and novel analyses of the other study cohorts in 4.3.h01 to have a reference point against what is actually in the human fetuses rather than in the mother. The objective is to provide validation in translating novel matrices and methods in maternal and neonatal/post-natal life to direct risk levels to the human fetus.

WP5 - T5.3 A5.3.3 (Translation to Human Pathophysiology (integrated into A5.3.1): UNIABDN will contribute collaborative access to various human fetal data sets (as part of SAFeR and the previous human fetal collection, FeGo), including ‘omics (RNAseq, proteomics, metabolomics) and chemical analyses, largely funded by other studies. UNIABDN will also contribute expertise in understanding human fetal development, physiology and effects of environmental and lifestyle factors, including chemical exposures.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

59- THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM, UK (UOB) – PIC 999907526

UOB is WP7 co-leader. During the second year UOB will be involved in six Work Packages (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6 and WP7).

In **WP1**, UOB will contribute to the coordination of scientific and administrative management of activities in task 1.1 (executive management), task 1.2 (scientific coordination), task 1.3 (progress monitoring) and task 1.4 (Ethics management) and as a Management Board member. In addition, UOB

is the coordinator of H2020 project PrecisionTox, which currently holds the presidency of ASPIS. In this capacity, UOB will be synergising activities between ASPIS and PARC.

In **WP2**, UOB will contribute to the development of PARCopedia and is responsible for its regulatory utility by integration with contributions made by UOB and other partners to PARCroute (task 2.2) and work being conducted at establishing Open Source, controlled vocabularies, and ontologies in WP7. In 2.2, UOB leads Regulatory landscape mapping.

In **WP3**, UOB will contribute to the communication and dissemination activities of PARC (task 3.2) including via organisation of training and capacity building activities.

In **WP5**, UOB will contribute to task 5.1 (toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern) for both human health (A5.1.1) and the environment (A5.1.2) by the inclusion of the concept of Phylotoxicology and omics data regarding the modes of action and potential adverse effects of endocrine disrupting substances. Contributions will also be made by the development of alternative *in vivo* non-sentient models for testing systemic toxicity and omics approaches useful in human toxicology as well as ecotoxicology (task 5.2), hence assessing systems toxicology that can be applied to both areas of hazard assessment and chemicals regulation. UOB will be working up new project in WP5 for additional contributions starting in the third year.

In **WP6**, UOB will contribute to (i) task 6.2 (integrative exposure and risk assessment), specifically to modelling aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes and sources (A6.2.1 Children exposome to metals, PFAS, (S)VOCs, emerging chemicals, flame retardants, PAHs); (ii) task 6.4 (Facilitating the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods), specifically to the landscaping survey (A6.4.2) for both human health and the environment plus contributions to the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning for integrating an environmental focus, and to risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity (A6.4.4).

In **WP7**, in addition to overall co-leading the WP, UOB is co-leader of task 7.1 on data policy and data management plan and are now also co-leader of T7.3 overall and activity 7.3.3 as sub-task co-lead. UOB is developing the data policy sections related to ethics of animal and human samples, as well as to the sections on FAIR data and PARC’s ambition and FAIR roadmap (task 7.1). UOB is co-leading the training programme for Data Champions and Data Liaisons to support implementation of PARC’s data management policy (task 7.2), as well as being the WP7 representative for the PARC Ethics and Data Management Board, and the link to **WP9** activities on “Building infrastructural and human capacities”. UOB will contribute to ontology development as part of activity 7.3.2 during the second year, as well as to a scoping study, analysis of existing text mining methods, and commencement of development of new ontology-based text mining methods in ecotoxicology for activity 7.3.3. In task 7.2 UOB will contribute to the definition and development of FAIR data storage, access, and dissemination systems, and will be involved in the cross-WPs ontology workgroup thus contributing to the relevant tasks while planning to be heavily involved in the ontology development process. UOB is also contributing to sub-tasks on heterogeneous data analysis and uncertainty analysis.

Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties	N

(articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	

60- UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON, UK (UCL) – PIC 999975620	
In WP6 , UCL is involved in task 6.3. UCL will act as deputy lead for Project P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU. In addition, UCL will continue leading the case study on plastic additives (6.3.1.a_Y1_CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL) and contribute to a case study on identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk (P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS2_RiskReduction_SU) part of project P6.3.2.a_Y1_GenToolsRA_SU.	
Does the Beneficiary plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the Beneficiary envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

Annex II AWP Y2

PARC PROJECT PORTFOLIO

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Executive Summary of PARC activities in Y1 and 2

After the Partnership kick-off meeting in Paris in May 2022, the work packages have started their tasks organised as transversal activities or as projects. The first months of PARC saw intense activities to develop internal procedures, establish communication within PARC and develop the networking within and between work packages. Nomination of the members for the international board, Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB), Stakeholder Forum (SF), are on-going. Meetings with the Governing Board (GB) and the Grant Signatory Board (GSB) have allowed the review of PARC progress and discussions on future orientations. A collaboration agreement with JRC, exchanges with the OECD and WHO are being implemented. All of these activities contribute to the implementation of a strong network as identified in PARC's first operational objective (OO1). An extranet open to all the consortium and specific work areas for each board have been set-up (PARC SharePoint). A first version of the PARC website has been launched and the graphical identity of PARC designed. In most of the participating countries, national hubs have been established to exchange and feed expertise, knowledge and needs (OO2). Based on the previous prioritisation exercise performed in HBM4EU and during the initiation phase of the partnership, projects have started during the first year and a project review process and criteria is defined (OO3).

Human health:

Biomonitoring

The design and implementation of biomonitoring activities in the general population and targeted populations are ongoing. A working group on Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) for human biomonitoring studies was set-up to prepare the analytical phase. As add-on studies will be performed using innovative methods, a cluster of projects was established to share the experience in different domains about the use of suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect direct analysis methodologies and innovative sampling. In close collaboration with specialists of exposure in different domains, questionnaires and tools are under development for further use. The design of targeted add-on studies is also in preparation. All of these activities are aligned with PARC's operational objective 8ⁱ. During year 2, the sampling will start for the general population. Two planned occupational studies 1) Waste sector, 2) Health care sector, will also be implemented during year 2.

The derivation of Human based guidance values in relation with health are ongoing and follow-up on work previously performed in HBM4EU. A working group for statistical analysis has been established and will continue its activities to define methodological guidelines. A roadmap to link exposure to chemicals of concern with health concerns is under development.

Hazard Assessment

The strategy for hazard identification and characterisation of **mycotoxins** (Alternaria toxins, Enniatins toxins) have been discussed to fill in the established data gaps. Similarly, a project concerning Bisphenol A (**BPA**) **analogues and alternatives** has been planned.

Under WP5 Task 5.3, the development of **PBK and quantitative systems toxicology** will work on different questions with the generation or identification (of existing) in vitro kinetics data and their integration into the PBK models. The case studies will focus on absorption (inhalation, oral), distribution (human blood brain barriers), on metabolism (isoform specificity, gut microbial metabolism) in relation with hazard characterisation studies for mycotoxins, PFAS and pesticides. The work performed will be related to

ongoing projects in relation with the projects on going in WP6.2. Several prioritised chemical families are studied: PFAS, pesticides, metals, bisphenols and mycotoxins. Inventory of models with their characteristics were gathered in a database and described using a common roadmap. A working group on the parametrisation of the physiology and anatomy and their dynamic evolution through life was established.

Development of new methods and tools for Risk Assessment:

The close collaboration with on-going clusters of research projects such as ASPIS¹⁰ and EURION¹¹ allows PARC to initiate some projects that will move forward the development of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) and integrated approach for testing and assessment (IATA) for five endpoints: **Neurodevelopment, Endocrine disruption** (EURION), **carcinogenicity** (ASPIS), **organ toxicities** (ASPIS), **metabolic disruptors** (EURION), and **immunotoxicity**. The main pathways of these adverse effects are addressed jointly by projects in WP5 tasks 5.2. Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling and 5.3. Quantitative Systems Toxicology and development of new AOPs and Physiologically based toxicokinetics models (PBPK), and IATA case studies in WP6 task 6.1.

During Y2, the work will continue on the development of IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption focused on thyroid hormone system disruption and antiandrogen activity and liver toxicity with a focus on fibrosis. The work consists in the design and refinement of AOP networks (AON) with the objectives of modelling. Gaps in data, identified by partners will be filled in when needed with additional tests in collaboration with WP5.3. The IATAs will be subject to human relevance assessment by applying the workflow designed in Y1 involving qualitative and quantitative considerations and relying on toxicological epidemiological and clinical data. In addition to AOPs developed on human adverse effects, AOPs focusing on non-mammalian species will be used to assess the potential for cross-species extrapolation to human health. The progress made, issues encountered and the draft IATAs will be reported and discussed during dedicated workshops. The draft versions of IATAs will be evaluated through case studies based on modelling and experimental studies and reported. Along the year, interactions with related research initiatives will be organised to engage stakeholders (national/European regulatory agencies, OECD, JRC, industrial partners and NGOs). A strategy for achieving IATAs form more complex endpoints (developmental neuro/immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity) will be developed through workshops in close collaboration with WP5 Task 5.3 and related initiatives (ATHLETE, ONTOX, RISK-HUNT3R) and reported (AD6.A) end of Y1. All of these activities will contribute to enrich the datasets for the development of AOPs and AONs, the design of IATAs and their assessment to move towards the next generation of hazard assessment with a close collaboration at international level in line with our operational objectives OO5ⁱⁱ and OO12ⁱⁱⁱ.

Work under WP 6 Task 6.4 will promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for use in chemical risk assessment for human health. Interviews and online survey with chemical risk assessors will be undertaken and used to conduct an in-depth analysis to identify the key factors and drivers for a successful implementation of NAMs in regulatory risk assessment practice. This will be used for the development and application of criteria for risk assessment methodologies using NAM approaches. The work to develop evidence-based tools and guidance for hazard/risk assessment of NAMs will be integrated in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework across chemical sectors.

Mixtures

In the projects on Real life mixtures, a model inventory for mixtures was performed in complement of the one done on single substance. A strategy to perform risk assessment of mixtures was implemented and applied on the mixtures of interest: pesticides, PFAS and immune effects, metals and kidney effects, mycotoxins and immune and haematological effects. HBM data for more than 50 studies including HBM4EU studies were organized and summarised. WP6 Task 6.2 will also develop an inventory of realistic **source to dose** models for the general population, identifying data and model gaps. It will translate mechanistic understanding for two aspects: direct exposure to chemicals from consumer products and materials and direct and indirect exposure via release and transfer from environment (Source to Dose). The strategy to assess **aggregate exposure** through different living environment by different routes (inhalation, dermal, ingestion) will continue to be developed and different sources have been identified to feed the exposure models (occupational and general life). The working group on hazard and kinetics will continue to collect, organize and develop information.

The projects on the Development of regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures have complemented the recent literature reviews on the current approaches related to mixtures with information on the current regulatory practices in order to identify the main gaps and needs and possible ways forwards across regulations. In Y2 a survey for collecting data through interviews on current assessment practices and data availabilities will be finalised. The mixture tools will be compared regarding their practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands.

Risk Assessment in a regulatory context

Several reviews of risk assessment methodologies have been started under Task 6.3 to evaluate the state of the art of different regulations, and understand differences and similarities. They are based on the substances' intended use across legislations, the effect specific risk assessment (endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, developmental neurotoxicity, and skin sensitisation), and the tools, criteria and methods used, also including risk assessment for the occupational setting.

Impact Assessment

To develop human health impact assessment, under task 6.2.4, a concise inventory was made for chemicals and mixtures prioritised for PARC. An inventory of methodologies and frameworks for health impact assessment and environmental burden of disease calculations and associated uncertainties was performed as a basis for further methodological improvement. A set of criteria for prioritisation of case studies was established, followed by a proof of concept and a list of case studies was proposed. An inventory of existing types of risk and health impact indicators based on partners' expertise and stakeholder input was established for further development.

Environment:

Monitoring

A general framework for the implementation of a new European monitoring programme is under development. Pilot studies have been started for the monitoring of PFAS in freshwater and endocrine disruptors in different environmental compartments. At the boundaries between human health and environment, a project was launched under task 4.3 to monitor chemicals of concern in wastewater with

the development of innovative methods based on suspect screening, non--targeted screening and effect direct analysis.

An inventory of existing prioritisation schemes is under preparation in T4.2. Environmental and Multisource Monitoring. This is a first step towards the development of a framework for automated assessment and prioritisation of chemicals/matrices/endpoints deserving attention for future monitoring projects. A pilot project on the monitoring of per-/polyfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) has started with the goal of establishing the complex task of environmental monitoring.

Environmental Hazard Assessment

Under Task 5.2, two projects on natural toxins and BPA alternatives have started and will fill in data gaps on substance and mixtures toxicity applying a battery of OECD tests *in vitro* and *in vivo* to different organisms. For the “BPA alternatives” project, the OECD tests will be associated with the development of new approach methodologies based on *in silico* modelling, use of invertebrates’ methods and advancing vertebrates aquatic organisms.

Environmental Risk Assessment

To develop environmental risk assessment methods that support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity several projects and scoping activities have been launched. The projects aim at better assessing effects on overall biodiversity and the possibility to simplify (i.e. less resource demanding) the methods used for the environmental risk assessment (ERA). The projects are:

1. exploring the ways to simplify (Predicted Environmental Concentration) PEC calculations within the environmental risk assessment frameworks.
2. developing a protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources including only the information and processes proved to be relevant by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling.
3. ensuring that results of any independently performed ERA for a plant protection product can be used as a benchmark for other (PhytoPharmaceutical Products(PPPs)).
4. developing and exploring how landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures can be used to improve the current risk assessment methods
5. aiming to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for use in chemical risk assessment for the environment are ongoing.
6. advance the regulatory assessment of unintentional mixtures in the environment.

Cross-cutting activities:

Innovative Methods

PARC will also provide innovative methods and capacities to monitor chemicals in appropriate human and environmental matrices. Analytical developments will also be performed to identify **non-targeted (NTS) and suspect screening (SS)** methods to detect **emerging contaminants** and support the monitoring of real-world **mixtures**. PARC will take advantage of new tools and technologies to increase the efficiency of toxicity testing such **high throughput *in vitro* test systems, ‘omics¹², high content analysis** and methods

in computational toxicology. PARC will contribute to the development of multi-step approaches using initial predictions of toxicological potential based on *in silico* tools, including **Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR)** directed **read across** models, **molecular docking** and **Thresholds of Toxicological Concern (TTC)** based on Cramer classification.

By developing **modelling approaches** able to combine multiple sources and scenarios of exposure through different routes (oral, dermal, inhalation), PARC will contribute to the “**one substance, one assessment**” approach. To ensure the establishment of next generation of risk assessment (**NGRA**) based on the use of new approach and methodologies, demonstration of their reliabilities and relevance will be supported through case studies within the partnership in close collaboration with international bodies (OECD).

Safe chemical products, materials and articles

Activity 6.4.3 are developing approaches for how the currently available information on substances in products and materials can be integrated in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments. It has started with a comprehensive review of chemical databases and gap and needs analysis of analytical testing methodologies. This activity will enable a systematic risk-based identification of priority substances, articles, and materials and will support enforcement and substitution of chemicals in articles and inform how sustainability assessments of articles can be achieved with respect to chemicals. Moreover, it will evaluate the requirements for inventory data and applicability of Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) methodology (including European Union Environmental Footprint (EU-EF) to assess toxicity impact.

In relation with the implementation of the CSS, PARC will develop the use of **integrative exposure modelling**, which also will facilitate the implementation of the concept of “**Safe and Sustainable by Design**” (SSbD) chemicals and materials. The improved information transfer structures for chemical products and articles will also allow the identification of priority substances from regulatory databases which will contribute to establish the “**early warning systems**” (EWS).

FAIR data and models, toolboxes

Although access to information on chemicals and their toxicological properties has improved considerably, e.g. through REACH or EFSA’s new open access platform¹³, RA agencies and regulatory bodies, at the EU and Member state (MS) level, find themselves confronted with gaps in knowledge or seemingly conflicting results^{14,15,16}. The aim of the Partnership is to enable all the scientific communities involved in chemical RA, as well as risk managers and stakeholders, to have **access to high-quality data by facilitating their accessibility, interoperability and usefulness** for research. In the context of **Open Science**, PARC will **promote harmonisation of data and exchange** between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology...) to promote transparency, support RA, and allow for reuse. It will ensure data and associated information is **FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and addresses the General Data Protection Regulation (**GDPR**) related challenges for data exchange. A dedicated, federated data hub, hosting core functionalities and tools complementary to existing platforms (including new FAIR data repositories), will be set up for cases where existing solutions do not satisfy the needs of the PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP). This hub will be kept as light as possible, and its sustainability will be addressed starting from its set-up. The Partnership will strive to support the implementation of an **EU-level common data portal** and to ensure the toolboxes developed in the Partnership are sustainable.

To implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment (OO10), a contract was established with the go FAIR foundation to train scientists in different domains

related to FAIR Data and case studies started in WP7. Data management has been set up and data champions and stewards have been nominated. Catalogues of capacities and training are under development within WP9 to consolidate existing and develop new analytical, toxicological and fit-for-purpose networks of laboratories and research centres (OO11) and to build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical risk assessment (OO13).

Capacities

The partnership will support the development of **capacities and networking and will develop training programmes to enhance the skills of scientists risk assessors** and managers to deal with new tools and understand scientific risk assessment methods. It will promote the further development of existing and new infrastructural and human capacities related to laboratory networks including reference laboratories and exposure monitoring networks.

Knowledge management

Knowledge management (PARCopedia) and uptake into policy (PARCroute) will be implemented to facilitate the (co-)creation, organisation, contextualisation, and sharing/dissemination of the knowledge acquired by the Partnership. PARCopedia will also integrate this knowledge with that from other projects or platforms worldwide, in particular from other Horizon 2020/HE projects.

PARC research and innovations activities are described by projects under the concerned WPs. In the following sections, the WPs' main activities and related projects are summarised. More detailed information for each project is available in the full project description forms. These forms could be made available upon request to the CT.

WP4 Monitoring and exposure – 20 PROJECTS

Guided by regulatory needs, WP4 aims to develop and improve the chemical monitoring and exposure assessment capacities in Europe as depicted in figure 1. The overall goal is a better understanding of the environmental and human exposure to chemicals from multiple sources including pathways of exposure between the environment and humans. In support of a “one substance, one assessment approach” new monitoring approaches will be applied to complement existing monitoring schemes. Robust, reliable and fit-for-purpose innovative tools and methods will be developed, primarily to support and facilitate exposure assessment for vulnerable sub-populations and the early warning detection of chemicals of emerging concern. The work under WP4 is divided into three tasks that address the objectives of developing a) the human biomonitoring platform initiated in HBM4EU, b) environmental and multisource monitoring, and c) innovative methods and tools for monitoring.

Chemical monitoring guided by regulatory challenges

Fig 1: WP4 General approach and vision

T4.1 Human Biomonitoring – 9 PROJECTS

A HBM survey targeting the general population will constitute the basis of a well aligned human biomonitoring (HBM) surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate internal exposure data (see Fig.1). Statistically derived internal exposure reference values will allow for the evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. In addition, targeted HBM surveys will address specific research and policy questions related to vulnerable groups (young children, pregnant women), highly exposed groups (workers, hotspot residents) or time trends. Priorities will be identified in cooperation with WP2 (‘A common science-policy agenda’). Further to the work achieved in HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu>) and in coordination with WP9 (‘Building infrastructural and human capacities’), activities are being designed and implemented to ensure the quality and comparability of the HBM results. Harmonisation and improvement of analytical methods across laboratories will be implemented, defining reference analytical methods when possible. Special efforts will also be devoted into developing useful tools for the improvement of the HBM laboratory network. Task 4.1 will further develop the HBM4EU strategy to derive Health-Based Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general and/or the occupational population. Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse health effects. Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (‘FAIR Data’). In collaboration with WP2 co-leaders and partners, the ultimate goal of this task is to prepare a long-term sustainable HBM and surveillance system for exposure to chemicals in Europe.

PARC Aligned Studies

Fig 2: PARC Aligned Studies

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies – 5 PROJECTS

S4.1.1.1 Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.2 General population survey – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

Project Title	General population human biomonitoring survey		
Project	GenHBMSurvey		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Liese Gilles	VITO	Belgium
	liese.gilles@vito.be		
Deputy Project manager	Susana Pedraza Diaz	ISCIH	Spain
	ISCIH PARC		
	<PARC@iscii.es>		
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	81
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.2
Project Id	P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project This project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental and human health protection. Demonstrating the effectiveness of existing policies is essential for maintaining public trust and securing the ongoing collaboration of industry and stakeholders. Human biomonitoring conducted through

harmonised approaches and quality assured analytical methods at European scale generates coherent data on the internal exposure of the European population to priority substances in different European regions. Human biomonitoring results from HBM4EU and PARC provide a baseline and time trends against which to track the efficacy of the European Green Deal's Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (PARC HBM data will for instance feed into CSS indicators).

Comparing human biomonitoring data from across Europe can highlight regional differences linked to variations in environmental quality, climate, diet, consumer behaviour and lifestyle (see expected outputs). This project will also identify exposure to chemicals of emerging concern, including substitutes for banned substances, in the population can serve as a warning of undetected risk. Measuring effect biomarkers and studying associations with health outcome data will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Data gaps filled by this project are expected to include:

- New internal aggregate and mixture exposure data and reference values for prioritized chemicals for all four geographical regions of Europe.
- Spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure.
- Increased understanding of the sources and pathways of human exposure.
- Associations of exposures with (early) adverse effects and health impact.
- Identification of emerging chemicals of concern.
- An understanding of population exposure and the exposure of vulnerable groups against health-based human biomonitoring guidance values
- Advance methodologies for assessing health effects due to exposure to chemical mixtures through real-life co-exposure assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will support the discoverability, accessibility and availability of high quality, reliable and coherent datasets on human exposure to chemicals at European level, supporting the sharing and reusing of human biomonitoring data across legislative silos. The HBM data can support time trend development and evaluation of policy efficacy (e.g., effect of REACH restrictions on exposure levels). Baseline human exposure data also allow comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC. In addition, data on internal exposure generated by human biomonitoring provide a complete picture of human exposure and can be used to enhance chemical risk assessment by providing information on actual human exposure via multiple exposure pathways likely to be regulated under separate policy silos. An understanding of the contribution that different exposure routes make to the overall exposure (taking into account differences in exposure modifiers, such as age and gender, as well as profession) provides the starting point for deciding on risk management measures under legislative silos. As such, this project contributes to the 'one substance, one assessment' approach included in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. In addition, identifying upstream exposure routes in various material flows - including in consumer products, via diet and in the occupational setting - can inform targeted efforts to minimize exposure by eliminating chemicals from material flows. Over the long term, the availability of information on exposure to chemicals in specific material flows, including products, will stimulate the production of safer chemicals, products and materials.

The results of the general population survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- ✓ PARC project partners, Governing Board members (responsible for RA at EU/national/regional level), EU agencies, and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; monitor the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability

- ✓ Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN: deriving policy recommendations for reduction of exposure, use of articles, chemicals production and release; evaluating the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- ✓ Citizens: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.
- ✓ Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions: release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.

Key words: Human biomonitoring (HBM), internal exposure levels, determinants of exposure, exposure-effect associations

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project contributes to the aim of T4.1 to perform an HBM survey targeting the general population which will form the basis of a well aligned HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate baseline internal exposure data. This project will deliver the statistically derived internal exposure reference values that will allow for evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability.

By collecting and generating HBM data for PARC priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe, the project will contribute to SO2 "European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I program to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment". The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

This project will deliver new HBM data with EU wide coverage for period 2023-2026, building on existing capacity. The partners responsible for HBM conduct in their country/region are supported by this project and HBM practices are harmonize.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- ✓ Other T4.1 projects:
 - P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO
 - P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA
 - P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO
 - Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys
 - P4.1.1.4b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven
 - Targeted surveys
 - P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_RUMC
 - P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL
 - P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
 - P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO
- T4.2: analyse associations between sources, external exposure data and internal exposure
- T4.3: development and proof of concept of innovative tools and methods
- WP1: indicators to monitor progress and impact
- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP5: identification of effect biomarkers relevant for specific chemicals, age groups and health outcomes
- T6.2 projects: internal exposure data can be used to feed into aggregate and internal-external exposure modelling, mixture risk assessment, and health impact assessment/burden of disease

- Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures
- Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies
- Refinement and development of PBPK models for risk assessment
- Real-life mixtures assessment
- Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
- Inventory of HIA data for PARC priority chemicals
- Case studies on health impact assessment
- Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
 - ✓ WP7: FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data; innovative data analysis
 - ✓ WP8: Early Warning System
 - ✓ WP9:
 - ✓ inventory of HBM/HES studies (T9.2) that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey
 - ✓ laboratory networks (T9.1) as an essential key in the QA/QC programme organization (T9.3) and implementation as well as in the analysis of the samples
 - ✓ training activities (T9.4) that can cover issues related to all the study phases (sampling, chemical analysis, statistical analysis, etc.)

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- **D4.3; D4.8; D4.12:** Progress report on the general survey (M36; 48; 60)
- **D4.13:** Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach (M81)

Project Reports:

This project will deliver a statistical analysis plan (M48) and the results of the data analyses with interpretation and discussion will be summarized in a progress report and published in scientific peer-reviewed publications by different responsible partners (M70-M74).

Projects Landmarks:

- Final selection of countries/studies included in the general survey + implementation plan (M8)
- List of mature innovative methods to implement in selection of HBM surveys (M10)
- Finalization of study design for the HBM surveys (M12)
- Finalization of sample collection for general survey (M48)
- Finalization of analysis of exposure biomarkers in the general survey (M53)
- Database general survey complete (M56)

Partners List:

Core partners: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), SPF (FR), UBA (DE), LNS (LU), RegionH (DK), INSA (PT).
 Partners involved in statistical analysis of the data: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), EASP (ES), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), IPA (DE), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU, MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), PIH (BE), Sciensano (BE), SLU, SPF (FR), SZU-SK (SK), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 20 PM

Expected ODC (Other direct costs: travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables) for the second year of the project: 10 765 €

S4.1.1.3 Targeted surveys

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.4 Occupational surveys – 4 PROJECTS

P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL

Project Title	Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys		
Project	OccupFeasability		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	18M
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The main idea of this project is to develop an approach to investigate if it is possible to analyse the data from HBM4EU general population studies to identify occupationally exposed groups, and to evaluate how general (adult) population studies can identify possible higher exposure of occupationally exposed groups. This will be done for selected HBM4EU priority chemicals, which are cadmium, PAHs and bisphenols that has been measured in HBM4EU aligned studies in adult population.

Thus, **the main scope of the project** is to analyse the existing (HBM4EU) biomonitoring data for its further use in the identification of occupational exposures.

The project is designed as a feasibility study with limited duration and resources.

The project aims to improve the use of HBM data to explore predictor variables that impact the exposure levels measured and thus contribute also to some of the variability observed. The results of the feasibility project can be used in general population HBM studies planned to be performed under WP4. Thus, one of the main user groups of the project results will be researchers performing general population HBM studies.

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and OSH processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of exposure. When performing general population risk assessment, potential confounding effect of occupational exposure needs to be identified and eliminated, if present. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes. When setting reference values (or BGVs under ECHA OEL process) to distinguish occupational exposure from background (environmental, consumer) exposure, it is important to ensure that the background levels are not confounded with occupational exposure. As this is designed as a feasibility study to proof the concept there is currently no need for alignment the timeline with policy's agenda.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output will be recommendations on the use of occupation-related information from general

population studies:

- Is it possible to identify some occupational groups and their exposure from the general population data? How much occupational exposure may contribute to explain the highest percentiles of exposure values in general population surveys?
- How should information on occupations be analysed in general population studies?
- Can analysis of population surveys be used to screen possible less well-known occupational exposures?

In addition, the project will provide recommendations for future general population studies for the collection of data relevant for the identification of occupational exposure from general population data.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

If successful, the information generated in this project may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes. It is also expected to contribute to the design and analysis of future general population HBM studies.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, general population, aligned studies, Cd, BPA, PAH

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

P4.1.1.4.a addresses especially operational objectives OO7 and OO10. In this project, existing human biomonitoring data on priority compounds is used to identify the possible occupational origin of the chemical exposures trying to understand how much occupational exposure contributes to general, adult population total exposure to different compounds and whether it is possible to identify possibly new occupational exposure sources from general population survey datasets. Thus, it responds to the need to better understand exposure sources in order to refine risk assessment. In the project, new advanced data analyses are performed for the identification of occupational exposure. The results can be used in the RA of the chemicals.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is highly linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked include:

- Project: General population HBM survey
- Project: Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
- Project: Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

It also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregated exposure assessment from different sources (task 6.2.1), WP7 on FAIR data and can also possibly feed in to WP8 toolboxes.

Links outside PARC

Outside PARC it is closely related to HBM4EU, since it will analyse the data collected/generated within HBM4EU.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.8. Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies (M18). This deliverable describes the availability of occupational information in the existing general population datasets and gives an overview on the usefulness of this data in the identification of potential occupational exposed groups and final recommendations for the future studies.

Project Reports:

None identified at present. Project results will be reported in AD4.8

Projects Landmarks:

Since this is planned to be only a short feasibility study, there are no official landmarks planned.

Partners List:

TTL (FI), SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2023 (M18)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 3 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 2 500 €

P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven

Project Title	Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Sentinel System		
Project Manager	Lode Godderis Lode.godderis@kuleuven.be	KULeuven	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.4
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven		

* The project has been broken down at M48 to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M48-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The aim of this project is to evaluate whether a sentinel system can be used in an occupational setting to assess environmental exposure, next to occupational exposure. It aims to explore, design, and implement a European sentinel surveillance system to support human biomonitoring (HBM) surveys in the general adult population via occupational physicians/nurses. In that manner, it aims to assess the total exposure (environmental and occupational) of a representative sample of European working adults to a selection of chemicals (see PARC General population survey, substances put forward in adults: PFAS, pesticides, bisphenols, metals, mercury).

By facilitating the recruitment of adult participants for the PARC General population HBM survey and the collection of data and samples, this project will contribute to all objectives and regulatory frameworks that are of relevance for the General population HBM survey. This project will additionally support the Health & Safety at Work – EU Strategic Framework (2021-2027), which aims to maintain and improve the high health & safety standards for EU workers and will help to prepare for new crises and threats. By creating data on aggregated exposure from multiple sources the project supports EU zero pollution agenda, EU one-

substance-one evaluation goals and exposome network/projects.

Main expected outputs of the project

By facilitating the recruitment of adult participants for the PARC General population HBM survey under PARC and the collection of data and samples, this project will contribute to all objectives and regulatory frameworks that are of relevance for the General population HBM survey. This project will additionally support the Health & Safety at Work – EU Strategic Framework (2021-2027), which aims to maintain and improve the high health & safety standards for EU workers and will help to prepare for new crises and threats. By creating data on aggregated exposure from multiple sources the project supports EU zero pollution agenda, EU one-substance-one evaluation goals and exposome network/projects.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

By facilitating the recruitment of adult participants for the PARC General population HBM survey under PARC and the collection of data and samples, the expected outcomes and impacts are similar to those of the General population HBM survey.

Key words: Human biomonitoring (HBM), occupational exposure, environmental exposure

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project contributes to the design of a sustainable EU-wide HBM surveillance system. By collecting and generating HBM data for PARC priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe, the project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I program to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Other T4.1 projects
- General population HBM survey
- Occupational HBM surveys
- Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys
- Development of supporting materials for the HBM surveys (SPOs, health related measurement, questionnaires)
- Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposures and health concerns (questionnaire and protocol for health measurements/sample collection)
- Design of a sustainable EU-wide HBM surveillance system
- WP 3.2 Communication, dissemination and synergies: Awareness raising campaigns will be carried out by using targeted communication materials on the impact of environmental and occupational exposures on human health.
- WP7: FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data; innovative data analysis
- WP8: Early Warning System

WP 9.4 Training: An online training module is needed for the recruited occupational physicians/nurses. This online training module will contain information about the sentinel system, recruitment of workers, sample collection, questionnaires, chemicals, etc.

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects, e.g. the Exposome Project for Health and

Occupational Research (EPHOR)

- Several participating countries have already used the sentinel system in an occupational setting. In Belgium, the PROBE (Hazardous chemical Products Register for Occupational use in Belgium) was set up to assess the occupational exposure of workers to a selection of hazardous chemicals. In the “Peilstation Intensief Melden” (PIM) study (The Netherlands), a group of motivated and trained occupational physicians (OPs) reported occupational diseases by using a sentinel surveillance system. The French Surveillance Medicale des Risques (SUMER) study, a national cross-sectional survey of occupational risks, collected good-quality exposure data through the sentinel system.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach (M81)

Project Reports:

None identified at present

Projects Landmarks:

Mapping exercise: inventory of opportunities and barriers in each country: M1 –M6

Go / NoGo per country

- Setting up the sentinel system in a selection of countries on national levels, network building: M7-M12
- Implement proof-of-concept of the sentinel system for recruitment and sample collection for the general population survey in adults in the selected countries: M13 – M42
- Evaluate the successfulness: M43 – M48

Partners List:

KU Leuven (Belgium), INSA (Portugal), ENSP-UNL (Portugal), UNINA (Italy), MU (Czech Republic), RSU (Latvia), SpF (France), UGR (Spain), NIOM (Poland), RUMC (The Netherlands), AU (Denmark), LNS (Luxembourg), STM (Luxembourg), STI (Luxembourg), UNISANTE (Switzerland), ULUND (Sweden), BPI (Greece).

Schedule for the first period of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 1 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 2 350 €

P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_RUMC

Project Title	Occupational survey in the healthcare sector		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HealthcareSurvey		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Paul Scheepers paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl	Radboud University Medical Centre (RUMC)	Netherlands
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48M
PARC Workpackage	4	PARC	4.1.1

number

Task/Activity/Sub-activity:

Project Id

P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_RUMC

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

In this project we will study how working in the healthcare sector may contribute to the uptake of chemicals. Biomarkers of exposure and effect will be used to study work practices in three areas in hospital settings: hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics and disinfection and cleaning products (biocides). The main scope of the project is to perform a cross sectional study in the hospital-based healthcare to study priority chemicals of concern by use of exposure and effect biomonitoring and contribute to further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions. The project will target the following chemicals:

- Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs)
- Inhalation anaesthetics
- Disinfectant and cleaning products (including biocides)

The project is designed as a cross-sectional observational study. We aim for 20-24 hospitals in 10-12 EU member states. The main output will be an assessment of exposure to prioritized chemicals based on the use of biomonitoring and supported by occupational hygiene measurements and other contextual data. In addition, the project will provide recommendations for improved work practices to secure healthy and safe working conditions.

Overall, the project aims are to introduce human biomonitoring as an approach to study both exposure and effects related to the use of chemicals in hospital-based healthcare. This will lead to more awareness and better understanding of how work practices contribute to internal exposure to chemicals and how these practices can be further improved to reduce uptake of these chemicals.

More specifically the project aims to:

- Identify chemical exposures of concern and relevant exposure scenarios in the hospital-based healthcare;
- Study how human biological monitoring (HBM) can inform chemical risk assessment of hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection products and cleaning products (biocides);
- Contribute to the further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions
- Study contributions from different sources of exposure, also outside work, in assessment of aggregated exposure;
- Develop HBM-based approaches for the assessment and management of chemical exposures in hospital-based healthcare.

The regulatory processes

In 2019 it was agreed that hazardous drugs, including cytotoxic drugs, should adhere to minimum requirements for the protection of health and safety of workers, in particular those provided for in the Council Directive 98/24/EC and in the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive 2004/37/EC (CMD). Development of a new guidance to support the implementation of safe use of hazardous medicinal products at work is currently ongoing based on a previous evaluation (European Commission, 2021). In December 2021, the European Parliament proposed to bring reprotoxic chemicals under the remit of the CMD. This will require further development of protocols for measurement of chemical exposures on the workplace, especially for periods of higher susceptibility such as during pregnancy.

Main expected outputs of the project

- A dataset describing the current exposure to selected chemicals in approximately 20-24 hospitals in approximately 10-12 EU Member States
- An improved understanding of how current work practices in the hospital-based healthcare translate to internal exposure to selected chemicals

- Recommendations for policy changes in line with current and new health and safety procedures and sustainability programmes on national and EU level

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of chemical exposures;
- Recommendations for risk management leading to improved work practices
- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM approach as input for risk assessment and health impact assessment
- For policymakers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): evaluating the efficiency of current regulations and further development of these existing regulations and implementation of the new harmonised guidance on safe use of HMPs including cytotoxic drugs.

Key words: occupational exposure, hospital, risk management measures, hazardous medicinal products, cytotoxic drugs, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection, cleaning, biocides

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The healthcare survey is an occupational study that contributes to increased understanding/ awareness of the chemicals used in the hospital-based healthcare setting (OO6). It has been designed to support the recent policy actions under EU CMRD (carcinogens, mutagens and reproductive toxic substances directive), with the recent inclusion of hazardous medicinal products. Based on the prior experience on occupational studies performed in HBM4EU we will introduce established and innovative biomarkers of exposure and effect related to selected priority chemicals (hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics and disinfection/cleaning products). For this we will develop a network of laboratories and research centers in 10 countries (OO11). We expect that our results will support health and safety policy, including the development of biological guidance values (OO8).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked include:

- Project: P4.1.1.2.a General population HBM survey
- Project: P4.1.1.4.b Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
- Project: P4.1.1.4.d Occupational survey in waste management
- Project: P4.3.2.b Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
- Project: P4.1.3.3.a Roadmap from exposure to health

In addition, close collaboration is made with following activities/projects within T4.1:

- T4.1.1.1 activity related to development of supporting materials for fieldwork
- T4.1.2 on QA and analytics related to selection of laboratories
- T4.1.4 related to statistical data analyses

This also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes of exposure for the general population and workers (task 6.2.1) and mixture risk assessment (task 6.2.3). Since the exposure of health care personnel typically consists of mixed exposure to several

compounds, the data collected can be used as a case study in 6.2.3.

Links outside PARC

There are links the following projects outside PARC:

1. Previous HBM4EU occupational studies on chromates, e-waste and diisocyanates
- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs
- Inhalation anaesthetics study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2491)
- Ethanol exposure assessment study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2492)
- Masarykova Univerzita (MU). National network of monitoring of drugs in the hospitals and pharmacies in Czech Republic and Slovakia (see: <https://www.cytostatika.cz/>)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7 Progress report on occupational surveys (to be submitted by TTL in M48).

Project Reports:

None identified at present

Project Landmarks:

- Identification of study populations in different countries (M4)
- List of selected chemicals and corresponding exposure biomarkers (M8)
- List of exposure and effect biomarkers in collaboration with 4.1.3b (M8)
- Questionnaires, SOPs and information materials (prepared in collaboration with 4.1.1.1 (M10)
- Study protocol and application for ethics approval (M12)
- Online training on the implementation of the study protocols and SOPs (M14)
- Submission of the study protocol and participant documents for ethics approval (M14)
- Data Management Plan in collaboration with WP7 (M16)
- Field work with (bio)monitoring and contextual data collection completed (M32)
- Analysis of the samples completed (performed under 4.2) (M36)
- Data analysis (performed by 4.1.4) completed (M42)
- Final results and recommendations (M48)
- Information materials for workers and other stakeholders (M48)

Partners List:

TTL (FI), RUMC (NL), MU (CZ), AU (DK), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), SGGW (PL), ENSP (PT), HSE (UK), IOM (UK), UGR (ES), INSST (ES)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 21 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 49 915 €

P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL

Project Title	Occupational survey in the waste management sector
Project	Occup_Waste
Acronym (15 letters max)	

Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Susana Viegas Susana.viegas@ensp.unl.pt	ENSP-UNL NOVA National School of Public Health	Portugal
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The European Commission adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan - one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. With measures along the entire life cycle of products, the new Action Plan aims to make EU economy fit for a green future, strengthen competitiveness while protecting the environment and provide new rights to consumers (EC, 2020). As Europe moves towards a more circular economy, the product of today will become the raw material of tomorrow. The waste management sector is expected to play a pivotal role in this development.

Based on this, an increase is expected of the number of workers involved in processes and tasks related with waste streams where the potential for circularity is high. Some of these waste streams are for instance electronics, batteries and vehicles, plastics, textiles, general household, and construction and buildings materials. The reuse and recycling of these materials could result in an increase of exposure (e.g., metals, flame retardants, phthalates) of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain such as collection, sorting, dismantling, shredding and further pre-processing and purification of waste components to allow their use as raw materials in different processes and industries (e.g., textile, plastics - and also PVC, furniture, construction). Additionally, the increase in waste volumes and complexity may reduce the capability of the sector to process waste safely.

In the scope of HBM4EU project an exploratory study in occupational exposures in electrical and electronic waste (E-waste) processing was developed and a study protocol using a cross sectional survey design to study worker's exposures and compare these to the exposure of non-exposed individuals preferably was implemented (Scheepers et al., 2021). This study protocol can be adapted to future European-wide occupational studies developed in the scope of PARC such as the one described here.

Overall, **the project aims** to understand waste management workers exposure to chemicals since new materials in the waste stream may pose additional risks to waste sector workers. The waste streams that will be the focus of this study are the e-waste and plastics (household and industry).

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and OSH processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of exposure. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs and impacts expected from the project are:

- Provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely: companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed.
- Evaluate the usefulness of BM as a tool to assess complex exposures such as the ones that can happen in these occupational settings.

- Identify the project outputs value as a contribution for identifying exposure scenarios at the general population level.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- PARC project partners and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU OSH directives
- Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.
- Workers and trade unions, industrial hygienists, occupational physicians: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for risk management.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, waste management, circular economy

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge since it will provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures and risk assessment in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely : companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed in different regulatory frameworks (e.g. OSHA, Environment, REACH). The project will also boost the existing networks of laboratories and research centres and develop new ones and it will contribute to build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Considering the data that will be produced by the project it can be linked to **WP2** (Knowledge management and uptake into policy) and with **WP3** (Synergies and collaborations). Also, **WP5** (Hazard Assessment), particularly with the tasks developed in the scope of characterizing AOPs and relevant effect biomarkers since the project will also integrate the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOPs) approach to allow a better understanding of the mechanism of action of the chemicals and mixtures and to select the most suitable biomarkers of effect to be used. Within **WP4**, the project is linked to all other WP4.1 activities and projects, especially to Occupational survey on health care workers (sharing e.g. some standard operating procedures (SOPs)), on the development of survey materials (4.1.1.1), project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO on roadmap from exposure to health (4.1.3.3), QA and analytical activities (4.1.2), statistical data analysis activities (4.1.4). In addition, the project is linked to task WP4.3: Innovative sampling methods and metabolomic studies since these new methods are planned to be tested within the project.

Additionally, this project will have several linkages with WP6 (innovation in regulatory risk assessment) where the exposure to several substances will trigger multiple collaborations such as development and use of integrative models to determine and quantify the internal exposure to chemicals from different routes and sources of exposure and to combine several routes and sources of exposure and/or exposures obtained from different methodologies. The data generated within this project can be used for the assessment of risks of mixed exposure to multiple hazardous substances within waste management sector. Along the same lines, links with WP9 (capacities) will probably emerge when planning the study and also in a later stage, when the data will start to become available and used for training and capacity building purposes.

Links outside PARC

The EU-OSHA's is developing a third foresight cycle that looks at changes in work that may result from the EU's transition to a circular economy (CE) and the potential impact on occupational safety and health (OSH) (<https://osha.europa.eu/en/emerging-risks/circular-economy>). Our project, developed in the scope

of PARC, will provide useful information to streamline this objective. Additionally, our project will continue the work developed in the scope of HBM4EU Project, particularly in what concerns to the E-Waste study since it intends to use the samples (biomonitoring and industrial hygiene samples) already collected and look for other substances that were not targeted in the E-Waste study (Scheepers et al., 2021). These are for instance cobalt and antimony due to their possible presence in this type of waste and the need of exposure data already recognize in the IARC evaluation developed recently (Karagas et al., 2022). Additionally, for those results of E-waste study that were not possible to be analysed in detail during HBM4EU, an extensive statistical analysis will be performed for the further refinement of waste management study design to be developed in PARC.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7: First Progress report on occupational surveys (M48).

Project Reports:

The project results are proposed to be reported in the form of D4.7 due to M48

Projects Landmarks:

- 1: Field work collection completed (by M27)
- 2: Analyses of the samples collected (HBM4EU and more recent sampling campaigns) completed (by M32) with (bio)monitoring, environmental monitoring (industrial hygiene samples) and contextual data
- 3: Data analysis completed (by M36)
- 4: Final results and recommendations for future studies (M48)

In addition, following landmarks are planned, namely:

- List of selected chemicals for each waste stream and corresponding exposure biomarkers, list of effect biomarkers relevant for selected chemicals
- Study protocol including standard operating procedures
- Data Management Plan in collaboration with WP7
- Online training on the implementation of the study protocols and procedures (collaboration with WP9)
- First manuscript with the main messages
- Policy brief and guidance for companies on the management of risks present at waste management
- Additional scientific publications on specialist topics

Partners List:

ENSP (Portugal); AU(Denmark); ISS (Italy); UNIPD (Italy); UMIL (Italy); UNINA (Italy); WULS (Poland); ULUND (Sweden); STAMI (Norway); AUTH (Greece); INSA (Portugal); TTL (Finland); LNS (Luxembourg); MOH-CY (Cyprus); NIOM (Poland)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/09/2025 (M42)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 32 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 49 577 €

S4.1.1.5 Implementation of innovative methods

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information – 2 PROJECTS

S4.1.3.1 Propose health-based HBM guidance values – 1 Project

P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA

Project Title	Propose health-based HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		
Project Manager	Petra Apel Petra.apel@uba.de	UBA	Germany
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.3.1
Project Id	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		

*The project has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved. If the review is positive, there will be two project phases M1-M36 and M37-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Task 4.1 includes human biomonitoring (HBM) to support EU chemicals policy. As a prerequisite for a health-related interpretation of HBM results, guideline values are needed that have been derived epidemiologically or toxicologically and relate directly to measured human exposure. The purpose of the present project is therefore to derive and agree on further such values for priority substances identified within PARC for which specific exposure biomarkers are defined in sub-task 4.1.2. Consensus on these values should be reached within the PARC project to achieve broad scientific acceptance for these values and to ensure a harmonized assessment of HBM results. It is envisaged that the values will be agreed in stages, first at the 4.1.3.1.a project level and then via NHC and NHCPs within a wider circle of experts involved in PARC. HBM-GVs for the general population and/or workers are generally intended to be derived according to the agreed strategy for deriving HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020)¹, but continuous development of the strategy is planned and will be taken into account when deriving the values.

In individual cases, PBPK/TK modelling may be necessary and corresponding results would then have to be made available within PARC. Cooperation with sub-task 5.3.4 should be sought in this regard. A level of confidence should be attributed to the derived HBM-GVs.

Main expected outputs of the project

Over the course of the seven-year PARC project, a set of HBM-GVs will be successively established. These assessment tools can then be used for health-related risk assessment of survey results in the general population and in the workplace. After 36 months at the earliest, it may be helpful to review within PARC whether approaches to prioritization, value derivation, and consultation need adjustment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Comparison of PARC HBM data with HBM-GVs allow statements on whether citizens or subpopulations in European regions are at risk of health effects and whether measures for risk mitigation have to be recommended or adapted. With the help of further information e.g. on marketing and findings from HBM accompanying questionnaires on individual product use, the use of HBM-GVs as an assessment tool can have an improving effect on regulations for food, cosmetics, etc. HBM-GVs can also be used to assess local

event-related HBM investigations.

Furthermore, HBM-GVs can also be used to develop impact indicators that illustrate physical exposure and possible health risks in a simple and easily accessible way, helping to inform a wider audience (e.g. citizens). HBM-GVs can also be used as a basis for risk assessment of mixtures, e.g. by applying the hazard index approach or mixture assessment/ allocation factors.

Key words: health-based human biomonitoring guidance values, human biomonitoring guidance values, HBM-GVs, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Based on survey data, HBM-GVs make it possible to check whether the risk assessments and risk reduction measures carried out in the context of substance and product regulation or in the workplace are appropriate or need to be corrected (operational objective OO4, OO8, OO9, OO10, OO12). In line with the description of action (DoA), the HBM-GVs as project results could also contribute to potential PARC responses to new and urgent needs for information at EU and national level (operational objective OO6). Cooperation with other international R&I initiatives in the field of biomonitoring and chemical risk assessment will also be promoted (operational objective OO5)

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- 4.1.4 data management and analysis
 - 5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health
 - 5.3.2 AOP development based on integration
 - 5.3.4 PBTk models and quantitative systems toxicology
 - 6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment
 - 6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators
 - 6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews
- WP7: Fair data

Links outside PARC

- *National activities on guidance values*
- *EFSA/ECHA activities*
- *OECD activities on guidance values*
- *i-HBM activities on guidance values*

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances) (M24)

Project Reports:

1. Substance dossier on Cyhalothrin (pyrethroid) and proposal of HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level (M12, UBA)
2. Substance dossier on UV filter Uvinul A plus and HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level (M12, UBA)
3. Substance dossier on aluminium and compounds and HBM-GVs for the general population and workers, coordinated at project level (M12, ANSES)

Projects Landmarks:

Draft substance dossier on nickel (TTL)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), AUTH (GR), MOH-IL (IL), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), TTL (FI), RUMC (NL), UBA (DE), Unisante (CH), Uni Oulo (FI)

Schedule for the first period of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/ 2025 (M36)

Costs (M1 – M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 32 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 14 485 €

S4.1.3.2 Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.3.3 Link HBM studies to health examination and dietary studies – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO

Project Title	Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth		
Project Manager	Hardiesse Bessonneau Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr Sylvie Remy Sylvie.remy@vito.be	SpF VITO	France Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-kirsten.baken@vito.be For effect biomarkers : Andrea Rodríguez Carrillo (andrea.rodriguezcarillo@vito.be)	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	52
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/ Sub-activity:	4.1.3.2 and 4.1.3.3
Project Id	P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

- Building on HBM4EU recommendations for further implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers in HBM studies and the linkage of HBM and health examination surveys (HES), this project aims to develop a roadmap that identifies concrete actions to undertake to foster investigations on the link between chemical exposures and health outcomes through biomarkers of effect. The project will be conducted in a two-step approach; I. first, the integration of standardized effect biomarker and health measurements and questionnaires in HBM surveys conducted under T4.1.1 – HBM surveys design; II. Second, a feasibility study to explore the possibility to assess past exposures to prioritized chemicals and determine effect biomarkers levels from biobanked samples collected earlier in cohorts and evaluate the prospective associations with health outcomes that will be collected under PARC. A case study will be applied to a specific PARC priority substance through retrospective analysis. This project will establish a core strategy for linking past exposures to current health effects, and create a baseline assessment that will guide future surveys combining biomonitoring and health examinations. In that capacity, the project will deliver tools and information for measuring exposure and health-effect

biomarkers that could be used alongside the classical toxicological, regulatory framework-driven risk assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome
- Supporting materials for PARC surveys:
 - Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data
 - Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC surveys
 - Investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results and data of this project are of interest to:

- PARC project partners
- Governing Board members
- EU commission and agencies
- EU national bodies
- Broader scientific community
- Policy makers and regulators

The generated information materials will provide tools for a more comprehensive and integrative biomonitoring of chemical exposure in Europe and ascertain to study relationships among risk factors, health promotion and protection behaviors, and health status.

Key words: Human biomonitoring, biomarkers of effect, health outcome assessment, Molecular epidemiology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T4.1: Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers, if input to regulatory needs can be derived, to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse effects (LNS, SpF, UGR, VITO). Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (RSU, SpF).

Through the activities on exposure monitoring and toxicology, the Partnership will foster a better understanding the health impacts of exposures and, thereby, indirectly contribute with evidence for health cost estimations.

This project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is mainly linked to T4.1 activities:

- General Survey
- Targeted surveys
- Occupational surveys
- Definition of standardised materials (questionnaires, protocols, etc.)
- Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

- Data management and analysis

WP2: Prioritization of substances and uptake into policy

WP7: FAIR data management and technical issues related to the linkage of HBM and HES

WP9: Inventory of HBM/HES studies that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results and materials developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN)
- OECD interdisciplinary activity 'Addressing combined exposures and effects by using Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) knowledge in combination with relevant effect-biomarkers'
- OECD expert group related to Working Parties on Hazard and Exposure Assessments (WPHA/WPEA)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

There is no specific PARC deliverable for this project. The results will feed into T4.1 deliverables

- MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys (M12)
- AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (M12)
- AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (M12)
- D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey (M36)
- D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey (M48)
- D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey (M60)
- D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81) contribution with the final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM programme for Europe

Project Reports:

R 1: Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including

Standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data (SpF, M14)

R 2: Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC general and occupational surveys (VITO, M12)

R 3: Progress report on investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts (SpF, M22)

R 4: Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome (SpF-VITO, M52)

Projects Landmarks:

L 1: Identification of effect biomarkers associated with exposure to the chemicals and age groups studied in (add ons of) the general HBM survey and first occupational surveys + implementation plan (M12)

L 2: Data management plan on implementation in the HBM4EU surveys (M12)

L 3: Finalization of the case study, data analysis and data transfer (M40)

Partners List:

SpF (France), VITO (Belgium), AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), CEA (France), CSIC (Spain), EAA (Austria), EHESP (France), Fraunhofer (Germany), KI/IMM KI (Sweden), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), INSST (Spain), ISCIII (Spain), ISS (Italy), JSI (Slovenia), KULeuven (Belgium), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIOM (Poland), NLZOH (Slovenia), UKHSA (England), RUMC (Netherlands), RSU (Latvia), Sciensano (Belgium), SECO (Switzerland), STAMI (Norway), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), Ugent (Belgium), UGR (Spain), ULPGC (Spain), UNINA (Italy), UNIPD (Italy), UOC (Greece), UOULU (Finland) , USI

(Switzerland), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), WULS-SGGW (Poland)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/08/2026 (M52)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 75 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 19 015 €

A4.1.4 Data Management and analysis – 1 PROJECT

S4.1.4.1 Data management

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.4.2 Data analysis – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

Project Title	Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU		
Project	DataAnalysisHBM4EU		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Eva Govarts	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Eva.govarts@vito.be		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.4.2
Project Id	P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Within the context of the HBM4EU project, a large range of human biomonitoring data has been generated via the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults, teenagers and children, occupational studies (chromium VI, diisocyanates and e-waste), the MOM-study (mercury exposure during pregnancy) and the SPECIMEN study (pesticide hotspots). Much useful information has already been obtained during HBM4EU and more publications are expected to be out soon. It is nevertheless foreseen that research questions will remain or will emerge from the data analysis, and not all the generated data are analysed. In order to make optimal use of the available HBM4EU data and use the results to feed into the design of HBM studies planned under PARC, further statistical analyses will be performed on HBM4EU data. More information can be generated on exposure sources and routes, exposure-effect and pathway analyses.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental, human and worker health protection. Europe’s zero-pollution agenda should depart from an understanding of how the bodies of European citizens are polluted with synthetic chemicals, and make reducing the chemical body burden and associated health impacts a key priority. Measuring exposure and effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health, and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Output will be generated with regard to exposure sources and routes and exposure-effect and pathway analyses. More information will be obtained on exposure sources and routes by linking HBM data with external exposure (e.g., products/articles, environmental monitoring, lifestyle, food consumption patterns) data (measured, estimated or modelled), both on individual level (as gathered by the HBM studies) as well as obtained on an aggregated level within the time frame of the HBM sampling. Results on exposure-effect associations and exposure-effect pathways will be obtained from the further analyses of data generated within the HBM4EU Aligned Studies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the data analyses planned in this project can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
 Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support risk assessment and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
 Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability and zero pollution action plan.
- Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions
 Release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.
- Citizens
 Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Key words: Human Biomonitoring, HBM4EU, exposure routes, exposure-effect analyses, health effects, effect biomarkers, pathways.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The results of the project will feed into the design of HBM studies planned under PARC. This is part of the objective of Task 4.1 on further developing the HBM platform, generating new HBM data. And to the overall goal of WP4 in observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways.

For the analyses of exposure sources and routes, geospatial information should be derived based on the geolocation of the participants or an aggregated level as NUTS. For this, the project will get support from partners involved in the R&I funded European Human Exposome Network (EHEN). Training will be organised for the study data owners to derive these geospatial variables for their participants. The data for this project will be shared via the PEH Data Platform initiated within HBM4EU. The newly generated data (geospatial information as environmental data) will be added to this PEH Data Platform as well. A network of research centres will be built to explore the exposure sources/routes and exposure-effect analyses. The results coming out of this project will be communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication on results data analyses with regard to specific research questions
- T4.1: design of general, targeted and occupational HBM surveys
- T4.2: external exposure data

- T6.2: exposure routes (modelling) and exposure-effect associations (risk and health impact assessment)
- WP7: linking of data sources and routes, data management plan, case study HBM data, innovative data analysis
- WP9: maybe training is needed on data analysis

Links to other projects:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO
- P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
- P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_RUMC
- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL
- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO
- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM
- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will perform further analyses on data generated and collected within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project will contribute to:

- Deliverable D7.1 Data management plan (M6)
 - Milestone MS7 Establishment of working groups (M12) by establishing a statistical working group with experts on HBM data analysis.

Project Reports:

R1: Statistical analysis plan (M18 – VITO)

R2: Progress report statistical analyses (M36 – VITO).

Projects Landmarks:

L1: Access to the HBM4EU data is granted (M14 – VITO).

Partners List:

Project manager: VITO (Belgium)

Project team: AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), EASP (Spain), INRAE (France), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), ISCIII (Spain), ISSeP (Belgium), JSI (Slovenia), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), SPF (France), SZU-SK (Slovakia), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), UGR (Spain), UNIVIE (Austria), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), VITO (Belgium)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05:2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 53 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 28 561 €

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO

Project Title	Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.1.5.1_a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO		
Project Manager	Liese Gilles liese.gilles@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.5
Project Id	P4.1.5.1.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO		

* The project has been broken down at M66 (that corresponds to the Final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM program for Europe report). As the implementation of the EU HBM survey will not depend on PARC but on decision taken at that time about the follow up of PARC. A new project could follow for the period M67-M81 after having reviewed what has been achieved and if the evaluation is positive.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The general population human biomonitoring (HBM) survey under T4.1 (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO), running from 2022-2028, will form the basis for chemical exposure assessment of European citizens within PARC. While the aim is to advance the concept of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in the PARC general population survey, further steps towards implementation of a long-term sustainable HBM framework for exposure to chemicals within Europe will in parallel be taken in this project.

A long-term sustainable and inclusive HBM surveillance system for exposure to chemicals within Europe to succeed the PARC general population survey will be prepared. This system will build further on scenarios explored and recommendations developed under HBM4EU and take lessons learned from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and PARC general survey and innovative approaches developed under various PARC Tasks into account. In addition, experts in charge of HBM surveys conducted in Europe, the USA, Canada, Japan, South Korea and Australia will be consulted. By 2028, a final concept should be ready for implementation to guide and support the HBM survey that succeeds the general survey under PARC.

The sustainable HBM system should allow to obtain truly representative and maximally harmonized exposure data for Europe to provide useful results for policy makers and to answer the information needs of citizens. The relevance of HBM results will be increased by optimisation of the number of countries and subjects to be included and samples to be collected and analysed, for instance via reduction of costs and increased efficiency of fieldwork. Harmonization will be maximized via upfront alignment of studies and application of guidelines/protocols/SOPs/supporting materials.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental and human health protection. The exact regulatory processes and frameworks for which future EU wide HBM campaigns will provide input will depend on the regulatory strategies and questions that are most prominent at that specific point of time.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will deliver a blueprint for a sustainable long-term Human biomonitoring program in Europe for implementation after PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of a European HBM surveillance system with regular frequency can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
 Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support risk assessment and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
 Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability.
- Citizens
 Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Baseline human exposure data will be suited for comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC.

Key words: sustainable HBM programme, Europe, Harmonized, chemical RA toolbox.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will prepare the development of a sustainable HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

WP4:

T4.1: general population HBM survey

T4.2 & T6.2: associations between sources, external exposure to (mixtures of) chemicals and internal exposure

T4.3: development and proof of concept of innovative tools and methods

WP2: prioritization, sustainability and exit strategy

WP3: synergies

WP5: effect biomarkers

WP7: FAIR data

WP8: early warning system

WP9: capacities and infrastructure

National Hubs: implementation of the framework

Links to other projects:

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey
- International key players in HBM research such as CDC (NHANES), Health Canada (CHMS), Japan, South Korea, Australia

- ISES HBM working groups

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D2.22: 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81).

Project Reports:

R1: 1st interim progress report (M24 – VITO)

R2: 2nd interim progress report (M48 – VITO)

R3: Final report (M66 – VITO)

Projects Landmarks:

None identified at present

Partners List: UBA (Germany), LNS (Luxembourg), ISCIII (Spain), VITO (Belgium), SPF (France), INSA (Portugal), LSMU (Latvia), FOPH (Switzerland), NIPH (Norway), SZU-CZ (Czech Republic), MOH-CY (Cyprus)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 11 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 4 240 €

T4.2 Environmental and Multisource Monitoring – 2 PROJECTS

Monitoring studies will be performed to fill in the gaps in exposure data for an integrated assessment of pollution affecting environmental and human health. Based on a review of existing knowledge, activities and infrastructure of chemical analysis in the environment, Task 4.2 will design and conduct monitoring activities with the aim to track the source and route of chemical exposure, supporting the development of an early warning system in WP8 ('Concepts and Toolboxes'). This includes defining a sampling strategy, using existing samples and sampling programmes, and selecting analytes and methods (see Fig 2).

Fig 3: PARC environmental monitoring strategy

Particular attention will be paid to a QA/QC concept (in collaboration with the PARC QA/QC Group established in WP9). Data analysis will develop and apply new digitalisation and machine learning-based methods. The exploitation of the data could include spatial analysis of exposure levels, input data for exposure factors, evaluation of time trends, and comparison with benchmark values for environmental and human health protection, mixture toxicity assessment, and integration of chemical data and bioanalytical responses. In collaboration with Task 2.1, a feedback mechanism will be established to analyse whether or not the regulatory needs were met and whether new issues of scientific and/or regulatory significance

emerge which should feed into new monitoring activities. Task 4.2 will implement a prioritisation process to define chemicals/matrices/endpoints for future monitoring studies and will conduct a monitoring study on PFAS and EDCs (see Fig 3).

Fig 4: Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring

P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU

Project Title	Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EDC and PFAS pilot		
Project Manager	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk	Aarhus University	Denmark
	Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)		PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.2.1
PARC Workpackage number	4		
Project Id	P4.2.1.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Establishing a process for environmental and multisource monitoring is a key component in PARC. It has the purpose of supporting the EU chemical risk assessment in relation to policy needs identified in the field of i) environmental ecosystems and ii) human exposure, with a strong link to human biomonitoring. Together with the prerequisite of building on existing structures and knowledge, these objectives make environmental and multisource monitoring a complex task in PARC, which needs highly optimized processes to be fully beneficial.

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are two compound groups of regulatory interest, due to concerns about persistence, mobility and toxicity (PFAS) and toxicity (EDCs), potentially in combination with other undesired properties and effects. There is a need for long-term monitoring of these compounds in different matrices, to characterise their sources and evaluate the effect of risk-reducing measures in support of the EU's Zero Pollution ambition. A pilot project focussing on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) was started in Year 1, with the purpose to establish and validate environmental monitoring structures, including a review of state-of-the-art methods as well as design of monitoring study for the long-term work in T4.2. This project will continue in Year 2, with a focus on the actual monitoring study to be performed, and also proceed into Year 3.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs of the project will include:

- Review of existing knowledge for the list of candidate EDCs and PFAS (Y1):
- Characterisation of compound classes, exploration of possibilities of grouping
- Review of analytical methods
- Survey for inventory of available data and on-going monitoring studies
- A study design (Y1 and Y2), followed by a more detailed monitoring plan targeting i) PFAS in the freshwater environment and ii) EDCs in a multicompartment approach, including:
 - target compounds
 - analytical approaches also involving suspect and non-target screening, sum parameters (for PFAS) and effect-based methods (for EDCs)
 - the QA/QC concept
 - criteria for selection of laboratories with documented expertise in the field of the project
- Monitoring data in Y2
- Establishment of a feedback mechanism in Y3 that also addresses lessons learnt, with a view to adjustments in the task structure and workflows for future monitoring projects in PARC (Y3).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

End-users: DG ENV, national environment agencies, ECHA.

Expected impact:

- Combination of existing and new monitoring data for the establishment of a baseline for two prioritised compound groups (PFAS and EDCs) that pose a risk to European environmental ecosystems in support of:
 - EU water legislation, in particular for improvement of lists of priority pollutants, e.g. List of Priority Substances under the Water Framework Directive (WFD), Groundwater Directive (GWD), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), etc.)
 - EU Soil Strategy
 - assessment of the effectiveness chemical management measures (e.g. ECHA PFAS restriction proposal).
- comprehensive assessment of environmental contamination by EDCs in terms of effect-based assessment for a broad spectrum of species-specific endocrine activities, representative of different modes of action, thereby identifying the links between observed ED activities and sources of emission of biologically active EDCs (REACH, CLP).

Key words: Pilot study, EDCs, PFAS, environmental monitoring, knowledge gaps, freshwater, multicompartment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project is tightly intertwined with the PARC overall aim to strengthen the EU's capacity for chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment, as well as closely linked to projects developing innovative models and concepts for chemical risk assessments. The project will develop, test and validate a workflow for the design and operation of further monitoring campaigns in PARC, thereby ensuring that the future environmental and multisource monitoring will be designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the identified regulatory needs.

The project will promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives by applying innovative methods. The analytical monitoring work will contribute to consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories

and research centres. The project will also include a feedback mechanism, with a review function for prioritisation, which will foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. The above-mentioned steps will be tested on the two case studies (PFAS and EDCs) of this pilot project, thereby supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes already identified under HBM4EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Collaboration with T2.3, T4.1, T4.3, WP7 and T9.2 in the review of existing knowledge and infrastructure, which has the purpose to avoid duplication by re-using existing data, samples and other experiences.
- Collaboration with T4.1, T4.3 and WP9 to support the definition of the QA/QC concept, application of innovative methods, criteria for selection of laboratories.
- Contacts to T4.1, T6.2 and WP7 regarding data analysis and data management and transfer.

Links outside PARC

PFAS have been amongst the prioritized substances in HBM4EU and were addressed as a priority group of chemicals under the recent Horizon 2020 European Green Deal Call (January 2021). Three research projects have been funded under this call.

The same considerations apply to EDCs, which are an obvious example of mixture exposure, as addressed under Area 8.2: “Fostering regulatory science to address combined exposures to industrial chemicals and pharmaceuticals: from science to evidence-based policies”. Three research projects have been approved for funding under this call: ALTERNATIVE, LIFESAVER and PANORAMIX, which can provide relevant inputs to this PARC pilot project.

Relevant collaboration opportunities are also identified with the LIFE APEX project, in particular as regards the procedures for sample exchange, protocols for sample preparation and storage, etc.

The NORMAN network will be invited to contribute, whenever relevant, in the activities of the PARC project. Links will also be established to national/regional monitoring activities, according to the prerequisite of building on existing knowledge and infrastructure, e.g. reusing samples or linking activities to existing sample stations.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories (M12)

AD4.5. Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) M12

Project Reports:

Final report on on-going projects (M36, INERIS/AU)

Projects Landmarks:

Draft technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (M12, INERIS/AU)

Partners List:

INERIS (FR), AU (DK), INRAE (FR), MU (CZ), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), CNR-IRSA (IT), IVL (SE), NKUA (GR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), CSTB (FR), SpF (FR), OVAM (BE), ISSeP (BE), Uantwerpen

(BE), LNS (LU), VUA (NE), NILU (NO), JSI (SL), UL FFA (SL), ARSO (SL), ISCIII (ES), FISABIO (ES), UCLM (ES), EA (UK), UKCEH (UK), EFET (GR), BPI (GR), Sciensano (BE), BfG (DE), UFZ (DE), SLU (SE), Eawag (CH), CEH (UK), CNRS (FR), CSTB (FR), EV-ILVO (BE), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), ISS (IT), INSERM (FR), NIJZ (SI), NMBU (NO), ONIRIS (FR), OFB (FR), UniLu (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 380 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 346 629 €

P4.2.b_Y2_ENVMonitoringframe_AU_INERIS

Project Title	Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Monitoringframe		
Project Managers	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk	Aarhus University	Denmark
	Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Expected starting date	13	Expected duration	18
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.2.1
Project Id	P4.2.1.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS		

Status: Initiation/Planning

Summary of the project

Monitoring environmental pollutants is crucial, for example to characterise their sources, to assess human and ecosystems exposure, and to identify compounds that need more stringent post-authorisation regulation or a full ban. Monitoring data are also instrumental to evaluate the effect of risk-reducing measures in support of the EU's Zero Pollution ambition. However, monitoring studies and/or control campaigns are costly and time-consuming ventures, and there is a need to optimise these efforts and focus them on the most relevant groups of compounds/matrices/endpoints. Prioritization steps should also ensure that no important chemicals are overlooked in a monitoring plan. This project will particularly focus on poorly- and/or non-adequately monitored (groups of) chemicals and unintentional mixtures of emerging concern. The aim is to develop an impartial, transparent, and reproducible framework to dynamically prioritize chemicals or groups of chemicals, matrices and endpoints for which focused monitoring projects need to be developed. The dynamic framework enables its application to be adapted to regulatory needs and questions, with the ability to respond to new and emerging risks.

The full project comprises of six tasks (a) to f), see below). It has to be noted that tasks a) to c), which relate to the development of the framework, are already part of the AWP for Year 1, while tasks d) to f), which relate to the testing and implementation of the system, will start in Year 2 and are the main focus of this project proposal.

- **Compilation of regulatory needs for monitoring**
 - (in collaboration with T2.1, T6.3 and National Hub Co-coordinators)
- **Mapping of existing prioritisation schemes and scoring systems**

- (in collaboration with T6.4 and T8.2)
- **Development of a prioritisation framework for T4.2**
- co-creation process through a series of sequential workshops (three workshops planned) with PARC partners and stakeholders, using the Delphi method
- **Configuration and deployment of an automated on-line tool supporting the prioritisation framework**
- for exploitation of large lists of substances and datasets from different sources (cf. as available in the NORMAN Database System, WISE at EEA or IPCHEM at JRC). The results of the prioritization tool developed in T4.2 will be made available on the PARC website. The existing prioritisation tool of the NORMAN Network might be a relevant starting point
- **Test of the prioritisation framework on small case study(ies)**
- iterative improvements and fine tuning will be carried out based on provided feedback. Case studies could include wastewater samples, for further discussion and decision at the planned workshop.
- **Application of the prioritisation framework to address regulatory needs**
- as defined in the first phase of the project, potentially updated after consultation with the competent authorities, with the purpose of describing the target of new monitoring studies for further work in PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project:

Altogether, including the preparatory phase (see AWP Year 1, T4.2.1 M1-M12), the project will deliver:

1. An inventory of existing prioritisation schemes and regulatory contexts they could be used for.
2. A qualitative Prioritisation Framework that allows the classification of environmental contaminants into action categories (depending on regulatory actions needed and identified areas of concern)
3. Lists of priority (groups of) substances based on identified areas of concern (e.g. hazards, potential risks, ubiquity etc.), using a quantitative scoring system for ranking
4. Lists of specific monitoring actions/campaigns in response to existing regulatory needs (e.g. source identification, compliance checking of emission limits, effectiveness evaluations of specific regulations including substitution measures, occurrence in specific compartments or matrices), also addressing knowledge gaps (e.g. new matrices to be monitored or assessed)

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Impact expected to support current regulation and/or applied risk assessment (RA) will include among others:

- Categorisation and prioritisation of compounds that pose a risk to European freshwater systems (i.e. List of Priority Substances under the Water Framework Directive (WFD)), and marine environment (Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD))
- Categorisation and prioritisation of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) under REACH, for which further regulatory actions are needed (e.g. compounds that have hazardous properties, such as PBT, ED, CMR and that are found in the environment).

The framework will be based on and consider scientifically established prioritisation schemes, both international (e.g. OECD U.S. EPA) and European approaches (e.g. STE methodology (Spatial, Temporal and Extent factors of PNEC exceedances) from JRC in the context of the WFD, the prioritisation approaches from NORMAN or the Nordic Council of Ministers), thereby ensuring an efficient and relevant prioritisation approach, applicable for future monitoring projects on different geographical scales. The initial inventory will also include results of other projects, e.g. SOLUTIONS and GlobAQUA. However, these projects were developed as conceptual approaches rather than operational tools with a focus on the water phase. The approach proposed in this project aims to go beyond this scope as it is going to cover multiple and endpoints relevant for both human and environmental health.

Overall, the ambition is to define a cross-regulation and cross-compartment prioritization mechanism where the selection of chemicals/matrices/endpoints (effects) would be based on multiple lines of evidence. The

prioritization mechanism should also serve the function of Early Warning System (developed in synergy with PARC T8.2). In this context in particular, it will be relevant to also consider time trends, i.e. whether about the environmental concentration or the use of a chemical is increasing over time. Moreover, the framework should consider both the hazard and risk of chemicals. The prioritisation of many individual chemicals might also be used for grouping approaches with a view to joint regulations. Finally, effect-based methods could be applied to address unknown compounds or additive effects that might be overlooked when considering individual chemicals only.

Key words: Prioritisation, risks, hazards, monitoring, matrix, endpoints, groups of compounds, emerging contaminants, regulatory needs, knowledge gaps, environmental compartments

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The proposed project is tightly intertwined with the PARC overall aim to strengthen the EU's capacity for sound chemical risk assessment, by generating lists of (groups of) substances for specific actions in response to identified knowledge gaps/regulatory needs to protect human health and the environment. Moreover, the project is also closely linked to developing innovative models and concepts fit for future chemical risk assessments by producing an impartial, transparent approach for planning proposals for monitoring studies in PARC and beyond.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

5. **WP-2.1.** Develop & implement prioritisation strategy
6. **WP4.1** Human exposure via the environment
7. **WP6.2** Integrative exposure & risk assessment
8. **WP6.3** Regulatory needs
9. **WP7.2** Data libraries
10. **WP8.2** Early Warning System

Links outside PARC:

A wide range of initiatives involved in the prioritization of chemicals for monitoring purposes will be addressed in this project. These will be systematized in the inventory as a first activity prior to development of the actual prioritization framework. NORMAN will be a relevant source of information, including the action categories approach and the SUSDAT list of the NORMAN Database System. Links to prioritization activities by other groups and organizations (e.g. JRC, Nordic Council of Ministers, USEPA) will be explored as part of the inventory, as outlined above. The NORMAN methodology will be a starting point for the further development of a new prioritisation scheme in PARC, including elements and approaches from other available sources as decided by the project group. Interested stakeholders, e.g. CHEMSEC or PARC Activities (e.g. 8.2.2: Prioritization framework) and their approaches will be included as considered useful in the project.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.1. Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals / matrices / endpoints for projects (M20)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Final project report (M30)

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Workshop 3 to reach consensus for technical specifications/ features for the prioritisation methodology and the on-line tool (M18)

Landmark 2: Launch of the online operational tool for prioritization of environmental multi-source monitoring (Landmark: M24)

Landmark 3: Results of Case studies (M28)

Landmark 4: Results of first implementation of the online tool (M28)

The outcomes of workshop 3 in M18 and the results from the case study(ies) in M28 are critical landmarks for the achievement of the proposed framework.

Partners List:

UBA (DE), INERIS (FR), AU (DK), SLU (SE), ANSES (FR), ARSO (SL), BPI (EL), CEH (UK), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (FR), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EAWAG (CH), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), INRAE (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NILU (NO), NKUA (EL), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), Sciensano (BE), SpF (FR), SYKE, UAntwerpen, UFZ (DE), ULFFA (SL), VUA (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2024 (M30)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project (second year of PARC): 31 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project (second year of PARC): 136 700 €

T4.3 Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys – 9 PROJECTS

Innovative (self-)sampling approaches will be evaluated for applicability in large scale monitoring programmes and specific surveys addressing population groups such as the occupational population. Innovative high-throughput *in vitro* and/or *in vivo* bioassays for effect-based environmental and human exposure monitoring will be improved. Suspect Screening approaches will be harmonised across the environment-food-HBM communities in terms of definitions, objectives supporting policy context, and technical implementation. Non-Targeted Screening approaches will be promoted and harmonised to complement multiple exposure assessment across the environmental, food safety and HBM fields and to comply with regulatory needs. These innovative approaches will be evaluated through complementary proof-of-concepts each dealing with a given particular new sampling and measurement approach applied to a given exposure/sample type and sub-population.

Fig 5: Projects structuration under Task 4.3

Fig 6: T4.3 Projects timeline

A4.3.1 Transversal actions – 4 PROJECTS

P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept Paper_MU

Project Title	Global collective definition and prioritisation of main concepts, approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods undertaken in task 4.3 (inventories, selection/prioritisation, shared knowledge and visions among environmental-food-HBM communities)		
Project Acronym	Concept paper		
Project Manager	Elliott James Price	MU	CZ
Deputy Project manager	elliott.price@recetox.muni.cz	-	-
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	12*
PARC (Month number)	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept paper_MU		

* This project will be closed M12, the final concept paper manuscript will be submitted early year 2.

Status: Closed

Summary of the project

Task 4.3 focuses upon assessing the potential of innovative methodological approaches to enhance characterization of chemical exposures. As a prerequisite, an alignment of main definitions and shared understanding of the objectives and strategical vision associated to those emerging approaches in the specific context of supporting policy for RA/RM is necessary. The purpose of the present project is then to stimulate this crossed discussion among representative of the environment, food safety and HBM communities, to finally elaborate a concept paper describing this conceptual and strategical positioning and projection. In particular, the landscape of innovative (self-)sampling methods will be surveyed with regards to implementation for chemical hazard /exposure risk identification, in link with 4.1.1 and 4.3.2 related

activities. The concepts of non-target analysis (NTA) and suspect screening (SS) will be clarified and the current capabilities of NTA/SS and effect-directed analysis (EDA) data to support chemical agent prioritisation and early warning will be described. For instance, the distinction/overlap between NTA and SS with respect to whether division is limited to divergent data processing procedures or extends to differing analytical data acquisition is unclear, and the representativeness of measures from fractionated samples for composite toxicity profiles is a pressing question for EDA. Focus will be afforded to identifying areas of shared interest across the environment-food-HBM domains and knowledge exchange to generate a common vision on capabilities and capacity of the approaches within and across different communities. Currently, there is no guidance for the incorporation or use of these innovative methods to support policy and alignment of concepts across domains represents the first steps of filling the knowledge gap for policy needs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Alignment of understanding and expectations from the environment-food safety-HBM communities with regard to innovative methodological approaches
- Enhancement of the availability and usefulness of new empirical evidence used for chemical hazard and exposure risk characterization through this conceptual alignment

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders:

Current landscape is that these innovative approaches and their potential application towards regulatory purposes are not well understood. As such, consolidation of a shared vision will enable improved communication and facilitate better understanding, which should enable expansion of a more diverse base of stakeholders and end-users with vested interests in the trajectory of development for these emerging methodologies, adding value.

End-users would be those within the domain of applying innovative methods and the harmonisation further cross domain communication and cooperation. Direct impact upon applied RI, regulatory support or legislation is minimal, the development is a concept of how to progress the scientific field to in future provide a tangible contribution.

Key words: innovative methods, critical review, dry blood spots, silicone wristbands, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, bioactivity assays, chemical mixtures, exposure profiling

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The task directly contributes to facilitating the transition to next generation evidence-based risk assessment through the development of conceptual frameworks and strategies within the arena of innovative technologies (sampling, NTA/SS, EDA) to advance the identification and prioritisation of novel and emerging contaminants of concern with perceived, potential of real risk. The task will outline common R&I strategies that should be taken on the basis of the consensus viewpoint of experts in the field. This viewpoint will then be communicated, raising awareness about future development strategy for incorporation of novel approaches in chemical RA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4/A4.1.1 & A4.3.2: The task will contribute to the planned pro/con expert review and analysis, QAQC consolidation and implementation of DBS/SWB.

WP3: The task will attempt to clarify the discourse of innovative technologies, since currently available information is often unclear for stakeholders leading to misunderstanding. Communication of intended remit, pros and cons of the emerging strategies to broad range of stakeholders should be supported.

WP7: The task will advocate a need for open science policy and push FAIR principles as a primary need to advance the uptake of innovative technologies. The implementation strategy should be supported from WP7.

WP9: The task will outline and justify the development strategy for the field and thus will identify areas of

need for capacity building and training that can then be mobilised via WP9.

WP2: The task includes development of concepts of how to progress innovative sampling, NTA/SS & EDA within a reporting for policy context; linking highly focussed needs to the broader agenda of Science-policy uptake and priority setting of WP2.

WPs 5,6,8: The task includes the conceptual development of frameworks related to chemical annotation that incorporate e.g., exposure, risk and hazard indices and uncertainty, with implications for early warning.

Links outside PARC:

1. HBM4EU – extension of many activities developed in WP15 (mixtures incl. prioritization e.g., CECscreen) WP16 (emerging chemicals incl. NTA/SS/EDA approaches),
2. H2020 European Human Exposome Network – includes generation of empirical data via novel technologies
3. ESFRI European Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure – provision of service and consolidation of conceptual ambiguities within exposome research
4. H2020 European Cluster to Improve Identification of Endocrine Disruptors – includes generation of empirical data via novel technologies
5. The Periodic Table of Foods Initiative – food composition, use and health
6. BP4NTA – US-based working group focusing on NTA concepts and reporting, including for regulatory purposes (mostly via involvement of US EPA).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD.4.6 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTA/EDA approaches - M12.

Project Reports:

- R1. Common definitions for NTA/EDA approaches (M12, MU)

Projects Landmarks:

1. Draft concept paper (M9, MU)
2. Submitted concept paper (early year 2, MU)

Partners List: MU (CZ); Participants: INRAE (FR); VUA (NL); ANSES (FR); BRGM (FR); EAWAG (CH); EHESP (FR); INRS (FR); JSI (SI); LNS (LU); MUI (AT); UAntwerpen (BE); UBA (DE); UFZ (DE); VITO (BE); WR (NL); EV-ILVO (BE); NILU (NO); OFB (FR); UL-FFA (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2023 (M12)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: Not applicable, the project is expected to end on M12

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: Not applicable, the project is expected to end on M12

P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR

Project Title	QA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA-based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	QA/QC for HRMS and EDA		
Project Manager	Hans Mol	WR (WFSR)	NL
Deputy Project manager	Jochem Louisse	-	-
	jochem.louisse@wur.nl		

Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QAQC_WR		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Suspect and non-target screening (SS/NTS) is a key component in PARC to find chemicals beyond the currently known and prioritised ones. The chemical and biological effect-based approaches for SS/NTS are relatively new and quality assurance and quality control is not yet well established and harmonised. This project will consist to develop a transversal action aiming at defining minimal common quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) requirements to be used specifically for chemical suspect and non-targeted screening methods (SS/NTS) based on chromatography coupled to resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and biological effect-directed assays (EDA). This project will inventory the existing QA/QC procedures, guidelines, proposals (and interpretations thereof) in the food, environmental and human biomonitoring (HBM) domains, identify inconsistencies and gaps, and aims to align and establish procedures and criteria across the application domains.

Main expected outputs of the project

- 1) More consistent and comparable data from suspect- and non-target screening methods generated by multiple laboratories (within application domains)
- 2) Implementation of harmonised approaches across application domains (environment, HBM, food)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a necessary follow-up of the work achieved under HBM4EU, where a number of QA/QC provisions, guidance SOP, and supporting template for QA/QC data analysis were produced in the particular context of the Specimen Study (pesticide screening in 2000 human urine samples from 5 countries by 5 different laboratories). From that basis, the goal of the present project is to deliver to end-users interested to implement those innovative screening approaches an extended and consolidated QA/QC framework to be applied more globally for a wide range of different applications within the environmental-food-HBM communities. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users and stakeholders through improvement of data quality / comparability.

Key words:

Quality Control, Quality Assurance, suspect screening, non-target screening, identification, effect-directed assays

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

This project will deal with necessary QA/QC provisions specifically dedicated to the innovative approaches developed under task 4.3. Indeed, the analytical chemistry community has developed for many years appropriate QA/QC provisions for assessing the performance of conventional targeted methods applied to environmental, food or human matrices. The situation is less mature for emerging and innovative approaches where the objectives differ from the previous ones. A main need for qualitative (or semi-quantitative) suspect and non-targeted approaches relies on the precise and transparent documentation of the method application range, i.e., the contour of the accessible markers of exposure, in order to possibly compare and well interpret the results obtained by different methods. This workline was explicitly included in the task 4.3 DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is very closely linked to WP9/task 9.3, and WP4, specifically to the QA/QC activities therein (T4.1.2, T4.2.4). Several experts/key contributors from these tasks are also involved in the present project 4.3_T02 that will permit to establish this necessary articulation. While in T9.3 overarching frameworks are

set, this activity focusses specifically on HRMS and EDA based screening methods, and for that the generation of experimental- and experience-based QA/QC criteria and requirements, and establishing QA/QC programs of SS/NTS and EDA. Prioritised substance groups in activities in T4.1 and T4.2 are taken into account with respect to type of chemicals addressed (e.g., PFAS and endocrine disruptors, EDCs), and possible integration of QA/QC programs (e.g. proficiency testing using the same control materials in both target and screening methods).

Links outside PARC (between 2-8 lines):

Within the below mentioned projects and already existing regulations/guidance documents, QA/QC for screening methods has been (partially) addressed to various levels of detail. This project will link with and build forth on these projects:

HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>)

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>)

MetroFood (<https://www.metrofood.eu/>)

JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

EU-TOXRISK/RISKHUNT3R (<https://www.eu-toxrisk.eu/>)

Food screening regulations, e.g., dioxins Calux Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644;...

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.5: Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (M12)

MS7: Establishment of working groups (M12)

Project Reports:

Protocol/guidances for QA/QC in suspect and non-target screening methods (M36).

Guidance on identification (levels) of substances found by SS/NTS (M36).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Completion of review of existing QA/QC procedures in HRMS-based SS/NTS
- Completion of review of existing QA/QC procedures in EDA
- First draft guidance on best practices in non-target measurements
- Verification of practical feasibility of procedures and criteria from draft guidance
- Fit-for-purpose guidance document on non-target measurements

Partners List:

Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (GR), EV-ILVO (BE), CSIC (ES), LNE (FR) NILU (NO), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 24 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 42 655 €

P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU

Project Title	Illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human
Project Acronym (15)	Early Warning System Tools

letters max)			
Project Manager	Lutz Ahrens Lutz.ahrens@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Georgios Niarchos georgios.niarchos@slu.se	-	-
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	60
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1.c
Project Id	P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Establishment of an early warning system (EWS) for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances is a key component in PARC and current EU regulatory actions. For prioritization of new chemicals, several tools have been developed that can be used in combination or independently, among which suspect and non-targeted screening coupled to effect directed analyses approaches. This project will support the development of EWS under WP8 (task 8.2) by ensuring that data generated through those innovative methods can be used to identify and prioritize hazardous substances in human, food and environmental matrices that may be associated with a potential risk. The project will illustrate the usefulness of early warning monitoring tools both for environmental samples (e.g. soil, sediment, sludge, dust), human samples (e.g. blood), food (incl. drinking water) and products (incl. waste streams, recycled products). The project will identify in particular chemical properties, toxicological endpoints and HRMS features relevant for the EWS, initially with the purpose to gather all necessary ones, and then identify criteria to assign relative weights to each parameter and endpoint.

Main expected outputs of the project

Review already existing information related to innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as early warning monitoring tools

Contribute/formulate criteria for categorizing annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format.

Elaborate a proof-of-concept illustrating (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to EWS.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate proofs-of-concepts and tools of relevance to risk assessors and policy makers at national and EU level. Innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches are of utmost importance for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances at an early stage. Cutting edge tools will be conceptualized and illustrated for establishment of an EWS. End-users include ECHA, EFSA, EEA, national environmental and chemical agencies, national food safety authorities, NORMAN, researchers, industry, NGOs, national consumer protection organizations and the general public.

Key words:

Early warning system (EWS); early warning monitoring tools; Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA); suspect and non-targeted screening (NTS); high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS); innovative sampling

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project will establish a proof-of-concept illustration of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning systems and harmonized framework from environment-food-human. This will ensure that the generated data can be used to support the development of early warning systems under WP8 to communicate risks, facilitate awareness of risks

and disseminate warnings to inform risk assessors and risk managers at an early stage of future challenges or emerging risks, linked to other activities and future projects in PARC.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.c_Y3_E03-Other compl. studies_ORU-MTM: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.4/P4.3.4.b_Y3_F02_Other compl. studies_ANSES: Ensure useful output for EWS

WP5: Effect-directed tools based on bioassays using new approach methodologies (NAMs).

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...). FAIR Data libraries.

WP8: Conceptualization of an Early Warning System (EWS) from sampling/NTS/EDA methods in humans, environment, food and products combining exposure and hazard data. Computational methods for text mining, data curation and hazard scoring.

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches.

Links outside PARC:

- HBM4EU (data, models)
- HEALS, CROME-Life
- UBA NTS Portal with BfG (Water, suspended matter)
- NORMAN Network activities
- DG ENV Early Warning System project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Project Reports:

Scientific developments and results will be part of the deliverable D4.10

Projects Landmarks:

-Conceptual framework for innovative (self-) sampling for early warning monitoring tools has been established (M40)

-Conceptual framework for integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning systems has been established (M50)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (GR), ISS (IT), NILU (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 10 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 3 750 €

P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP

Project Title	Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS. Identify gaps / necessary methodological improvements for retrospective use of NTS HRMS data (digital sample freezing platform) and EU capacity in terms of centralized data repository		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Data processing workflow		
Project Manager	Arthur David	EHESP	FR
Deputy Project manager	Arthur.david@ehesp.fr		
Project manager	Jade Chaker	-	-
Project manager	jade.chaker@ehesp.fr		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data processing workflow_EHESP		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Considering the vast amount of chemicals present on the market, there is currently a substantial lack of data on human and environmental exposure to these chemicals, preventing the implementation of efficient regulatory approaches by policy makers with regard to the risk assessment of such complex real-life mixtures. Hence, suspect screening and non-targeted analyses based on high-resolution offer great promises to identify emerging and chemical mixtures without a priori. The lack of comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for suspect (SS) and non-targeted screening (NTS) data processing however appears as a crucial issue and current major bottleneck for efficient implementation of these approaches. Indeed, a wide range of software tools are today available to perform one or several components of such data processing and extraction of the useful information from the raw data, including peak picking, peak alignment, and annotation. But still no consensual guidelines were proposed regarding both a preferable selection from this panel of existing tool or their fine appropriate parameterization in the context of NTS. Overall, an integrated, sustainable, and open access solution permitting to perform all these necessary steps with sufficient QA/QC consolidation for support to policy application and sufficient high throughput capacity for application to large scale cohorts, is still lacking and is urgently needed.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Built strong and dynamic consortium within the environment-food safety-HBM scientific communities to harmonize and mutualize the current and future resources
 - Updated CECScreen database with the aim to improve the annotation quality
 - Pursued development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library through the collaborative generation of MS and MS/MS reference spectra
 - Developed comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS
 - Defined appropriate quality strategies to ensure retrospective analyses/early warning system
 - Developed / improved appropriate data processing workflow dedicated to bioassay data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project appears as a pre-requisite methodological development related activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) new consolidated ground to implement SS/NTS approaches at larger scale and provide new data on human and environmental exposure for policy makers. This medium-term perspective

should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building within the EU), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input, including sanitary agencies, risk assessors, and public health authorities..

Key words:

Suspect screening; non-targeted screening; data processing, annotation, user-friendly workflow; CECScreen database; reference library; marker identification; automation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The development of this comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS is a necessary step for all the projects that will use these strategies in WP4 and other related WPs. Following the work done in HBM4EU, the development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library as a key stone of the annotation workflow underlying to these HRMS-based suspect screening approaches applied across the environment-food-human continuum is clearly part of the defined DoA for task 4.3, as well as the establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for better efficiency and deployment of NTS (e.g. inspired from the Workflow for Metabolomics W4M/Galaxy user friendly environment).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.c_Y3_E03-Other compl. studies_ORU-MTM: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.4/P4.3.4.b_Y3_F02-Other compl. studies_ANSES: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed bases of harmonisation and development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>), JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

France-Exposome, Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB, ELIXIR-FR, <https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/elixir-fr/>), ELIXIR and EIRENE infrastructures

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from suspect/NTS approaches (e.g., inspired from W4M/Galaxy) - M54.

Project Reports:

Report on the Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS – EHESP, M60.

Projects Landmarks:

- Conduct a strategical review of already existing initiatives and tools worldwide with all involved partners to select the best options for the envisaged workflow – M9, EHESP
- Assignment of most of the tasks and development to all partners completed – M12, EHESP
- Release of an operational prototype version of the user-friendly workflow – M42, EHESP

□ All planned outputs on track – M60, EHESP

Partners List:

EHESP (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (DE), MU (CE), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 37 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 47 800 €

A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts – 2 PROJECTS

P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Perinatal exposure		
Project Manager	Jean-Philippe Antignac jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr	INRAE	FR
Deputy Project manager	Tarek Moufawad Tarek.moufawad@oniris-nantes.fr	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Capturing the complex real human chemical exposure requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches. These ones, from sampling to exposure data generation and analysis, are however requiring a better consolidated development and a better documented performance assessment before large scale implementation in human cohorts. As formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA), early stage human exposure appears in particular as a high concern not yet well addressed, both in terms of risk assessment and link to health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). New sampling methods (e.g., silicone wristbands and/or dried blood spots (DBS)), compatible with the non-invasiveness and restricted sample requirements typically expected for those sub-populations represent potentially relevant options to be considered in that context. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) coupled to effect directed analysis (EDA) are another new trend in analytical laboratories with high potential. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches, with a focus on human samples collected from

mother-newborn/child individuals. By definition screening approaches should permit to capture simultaneously various substances from different classes, relying on the global prioritization strategy from WP2, including both non persistent and persistent organic chemicals of emerging concern.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for perinatal exposure assessment
- Documenting real life mixtures associated to perinatal chemical exposure
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure measurement approaches for HBM. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input.

Key words:

Biomonitoring, perinatal exposure, innovative methods, dry blood spots, silicone wristbands, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, risk assessment, and risk management decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations, face some limitations for large scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of a priori known and selected markers of exposure. From this global picture, a specific concern formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA) is related to a need for a better characterization of exposure for particularly vulnerable sub-populations, notably new-borns and young children. Human foetal exposure also appears as a not yet well addressed high concern in the context of linking this early exposure to human health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). This project is aiming to contribute addressing those issues related to the PARC objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.1/4.1.1: Pro/con expert review and analysis, QAQC consolidation and implementation of DBS/SWB

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed bases of harmonisation and

development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.5: 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring - M48.

Project Reports:

Scientific developments and results will be part of the deliverable D4.5

Projects Landmarks:

- Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners – M6
- Sample sourcing and sharing completed – M12
- At least 50% of planned analyses completed – M24
- All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track – M36

Partners List:

INRAE (FR), EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (SP), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (SP), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), CSIC (SP), ISCII (SP), ISS (SP), SU (SE), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 84 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 187 785 €

P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Occupational exposure		
Project Manager	Sophie Ndaw, Baninia Habchi, Ogier Hanser Radu Duca sophie.ndaw@inrs.fr; baninia.habchi@inrs.fr ogier.hanser@inrs.fr; Radu.duca@lns.etat.lu	INRS LNS	FR Lux
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	P4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS		

Status: Initiation/Planning

Summary of the project:

In the workplace, most workers are co-exposed to various chemicals at the same time and same place. More, the European Commission adopted a **new Circular Economy Action Plan** where Europe moves towards a more circular economy. The reuse and recycling of materials could result in an increase of exposure of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain. Innovative approaches are needed for better characterizing the nature and effects of those multiple exposure on workers' health since the conventional targeted analysis are limited to *a priori* known biomarkers. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) enabling the detection of biomarkers of exposures and effects and coupled to new sampling methods such as dried blood spots (DBS) and silicone wristbands (SWB) represent promising new options and solutions in this context. However, these approaches are not yet widely applied in the field of human exposure assessment and biomonitoring. Both improvement and harmonization are needed before implementing these novel approaches in EU to support policy and prevention actors. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches (see Annex 1 and occupational survey projects WP4.1), for particular assessment of occupational exposure.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Validation of innovative approaches by using selected case studies
- Scientifically and regulatory supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Roadmap for further developments/improvements needed for long-term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for occupational exposure assessment
- Contributing to document real life mixtures associated to occupational chemical exposure, for waste management and health care sectors
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed the developed early warning systems through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The results of the survey should benefit to different stakeholders:

- consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure measurement approaches, which will benefit to a number of end-users including laboratories (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input;
- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of emerging chemicals exposures, further recommendations for risk management.
- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM approach as input for further risk assessment and health impact assessment related mainly to emerging chemicals of concerned or unknown potential process related occurring chemicals.
- On a longer term, policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.

Key words: Biomonitoring, occupational exposure, innovative methods, dried blood spots (DBS), silicone wristbands (SWB), suspect screening, non-targeted screening, exposures and effect biomarkers, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The main objectives of this project consist of developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the suitability of innovative methodological approaches such as SS/NTS and innovative sampling methods for

occupational exposure assessment in Europe. Furthermore, this project contributes and improves the chemical risk assessment by studying the samples collected under Occupational survey projects (T4.1.1.4): **P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL** and **P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_RUMC** including regulated compounds, banned compounds and new/emerging compounds, potentially formed along the production process. In addition, a new network of laboratories and research centers will be developed and coordinated by the 15 European institutions participating in this project and each partner will be involved in the respective National Hubs (NH).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4: 4.1.1/T4.1.1.5 occupational surveys:

- Identification of the partners involved in the sample collection
- Identification of suitable case studies to test and validate the innovative sampling methods from T4.3_H02
- Identification of cohorts required for the proposed project (type, volume, number, collection method, etc.)
- Organisation and management of the sampling collection in collaboration with task 4.3.
- QA/QC consolidation between tasks 4.3 and 4.1 through the establishment of a specific working group in charge of evaluating advantages / limitations, necessary caution before use and implementation etc...
- Preliminary test / possible improvement before applying to real samples.
- Contribution to the evaluation of innovative sampling methods and suspect / non-targeted screening approaches based on the comparison with exposure markers obtained with conventional targeted methods

4.3.1. Transversal:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of innovative sampling approaches
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data
- 4.3.2. Human based proof-of-concept
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01_Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6: Potential use of the generated new exposure data from innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS for exposure assessment in regulatory risk assessment

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of the generated new exposure data from innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS for early warning systems

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS approaches

Links outside PARC:

- HBM4EU legacy: WP8 of the HBM4EU project conducted studies on occupational exposure among chromate workers, e-waste workers and diisocyanate-involved workers. In those studies, multiple occupational exposures have been shown, which highlighted the need of novel methods to access poly-exposures. The present project is aiming to capitalize on those HBM4EU results to expand its scope. Various exposome research projects (amongst which EPHOR) develop innovative sampling approaches for occupational exposure assessment that are very relevant for this task.

- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Expected Project Reports:

Scientific developments and results will be part of the deliverable D4.10.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Refined study design of case studies co-built and completed with all involved partners (M24)

Landmark 2: Sample sourcing and sharing completed (M30)

Landmark 3: At least 50% of planned analyses completed (M48)

Landmark 4: All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track (M60)

Landmark 5: Identification of emerging chemicals and contribution to the prioritisation process of chemicals of interest (M60)

Partners list: INRS (FR), LNS (LU), WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (SP), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), , UAntwerpen (BE), TTL (FI), MU (CZ), JSI (SI), WR (NL), BPI (GR), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 8 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 13 830 €

A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts – 2 PROJECTS

P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH

Project Title	Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community (<i>wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment</i>) and II. environmental exposure assessment (<i>screening of wastewater treatment plant effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle</i>).		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Wastewater based epidemiology		
Project Manager	Werner Brack werner.brack@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Barbara Kasprzyk-Hordern bkh20@bath.ac.uk	UBATH	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.3
Project Id	P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Wastewater can serve as a source of information with respect to human exposure, by measuring specific human metabolites in raw sewage (wastewater-based epidemiology – WBE). WWTPs are a main source for complex mixtures of chemicals in surface water, impacting the environment and human health (e.g., via drinking water). This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on (i) wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment and (ii) on screening of WWTP effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) into the water cycle. The development of wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) as well as the screening of effluents using suspect and nontarget screening (SS/NTS) approaches and effect-directed analysis (EDA) will deliver innovative methods for community wide human exposure assessment, environmental exposure assessment and the identification of CECs of (eco-)toxicological concern. The European-scale monitoring data generated by these methods as well as a re-evaluation of existing data will greatly improve our knowledge on CECs in wastewater and their primary sources as a basis for the revision of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive with regard to reducing CEC emissions, providing candidate compounds and information on their sources for priority/river-basin-specific chemicals in the context of the Water Framework Directive, and providing information on chemical mixtures for the revision of REACH with regard to environmental mixture concerns.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Innovative screening / targeted methods for community-wide chemical exposure assessment by WBE
- Innovative screening methods and workflows for environmental exposure assessment of wastewater
- Europe-wide human community exposure patterns via targeted and non-targeted WBE
- Wastewater and source patterns representing typical emission scenarios in Europe
- Prioritisation of compounds of concern emitted with wastewater for further assessment

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We will develop innovative analytical approaches that will define future approaches to exposure studies, both in the context of environmental and public health. This project is potentially transformative for several stakeholder groups including, regulatory sectors (e.g. water quality/control authorities) and public health agencies.

Key words

wastewater, wastewater-based epidemiology, suspect and nontarget screening, compound prioritization, community exposure assessment, mixture risk drivers, effect-directed analysis

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project provides human exposure (via WBE), environmental and multisource monitoring data for regulatory purposes from the mining of existing HRMS-based datasets and Pan-European monitoring studies (OO8, OO10). The project enhances the collaboration between the partners conducting WBE and wastewater monitoring through consolidated and harmonised analytical and data processing workflows (OO11). Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of environmental monitoring as an innovative approach feeding into regulatory risk assessment (OO12, OO9).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The proposed project will be closely linked to Tasks 4.1 (Human exposure assessment) and 4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) providing innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys supporting these tasks. This project will inform on toxicity data gaps of concern based on realistic human and environmental exposure (Task 5.1) and will closely collaborate with Task 5.2 on innovative tools for toxicity testing, filtering Task 5.2 tools for methods useful for effect-directed analysis. The project will provide valuable measured human and environmental exposure information as input to Task 6.2. The project will also feed in directly into Task 8.2 aiming at the establishment of an early warning system.

Links outside PARC

Within the EU Horizon 2020 COST action SCORE (www.score-cost.eu), activities in the field of WBE are initiated and coordinated. While the main focus was on illicit drugs, the focus is shifting towards current, in-use compounds to investigate patterns of factors related to lifestyle, disease and environment. Hydra-EWS: Marie Curie initiative led by University of Bath (UBAH), in which connection with task 4.3 is already made, possibly providing synergy. E-PRTR programme (<https://industry.eea.europa.eu/#/home>) VANDALF: National Danish project aiming to develop and implement a risk assessment platform based on NTS and effect-based methods to identify CECs in wastewater, will be closely linked through the involvement of the coordinator UPCH. NORMAN network: Strong collaboration and exchange, use of and exchange with NORMAN database system.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.2 Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M35)

Project Reports:

Final report (M36)

Projects Landmarks:

- Targeted WBE methods developed and harmonised (M22)
- WBE Suspect- and Nontarget screening methods developed and harmonised(M22)
- New sampling and enrichment tools developed and tested (M22)
- Prioritisation of source-related features and patterns conducted (M22)
- Methods for retrospective mining of heterogeneous datasets (M24)
- Methods for high-throughput EDA developed (M30)
- Pan-European study for WBE and environmental exposure by wastewater conducted (M30)
- Datasets from Pan-European Study evaluated (M36)

Partners List: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), ISS (SP), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), UL-FFA (SI), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (PL), VITO (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 94 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 167 285 €

P4.3.3.b_Y2_EO2-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel animal species		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Sentinel animals		
Project Manager	Ronan CARIOU ronan.cariou@oniris-nantes.fr	ONIRIS	FR
Deputy Project manager	Gaud DERVILLY gaud.dervilly@oniris-nantes.fr	ONIRIS	FR

Expected starting date	13	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	P4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.3
Project Id	P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS		

Status: Initiation/Planning

Summary of the project:

Capturing the complex real chemical exposure of human and/or in the environment requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) coupled to effect directed analysis (EDA) are a promising trend developed within PARC T4.3 in that purpose. Within the One Health concept, animal sentinel species can serve as a source of useful information with respect to both human exposure to chemical hazards through the food chain and ecotoxicological considerations related to the environment. Species with bioaccumulation capacities especially appears of interest for SS/NTS screening of chemicals based on higher concentration levels than those observed in human biological matrices. Selected species will cover marine and terrestrial environments. Candidate species are marine mammals, molluscs, gulls, pigeons, raptors and bees. The sample sourcing of such sentinel species also stands as less laborious compared to human matrices, especially if already available in a specimen bank. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess then relevance of animal sentinel species upon applying those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches. It will feed the early warning system on chemicals of emerging concern, the end-users being the food and environment policy makers.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Documented advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some animal species for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Documentation of real-life mixtures associated to environmental health and human food chain
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2
- General food law and environment policy makers aware of the main findings

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide eventually a list of exposure markers pinpointing potential chemicals of emerging concern. This perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input.

Policies related to the human food chain are a first target. It includes the general food law (Reg 178/2002), as well as the recently revised official control regulation (Reg 2017/625) and other regulations for business operators (Reg183/2005 Reg 852/2004, Reg 853/2004). For example, EFSA recently noted in its opinion on PFASs (doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223) that a representative set of occurrence data are still lacking for many foods and, therefore, recommended to gather such data for a wide range PFASs in a broad range of widely consumed foods. Consequently, it is advised in the Commission Recommendation 2022/1431 that Member States should also consider testing for the presence in food of emerging PFASs, in addition to the 4+18 cited.

Policies related to the environmental aspects are another target. It includes the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Dir 2008/56/EC) in which Qualitative descriptors for determining good environmental status n°8 and n°9 deal with contaminants giving rise to pollution or concern for human consumption. Such approach is also about to be extended to terrestrial environments according to a current proposal for a Nature Restoration Law.

Key words:

Sentinel species, human food chain, environmental health, innovative methods, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, risk assessment, and risk management decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations, face some limitations for large-scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of *a priori* known and selected markers of exposure. Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of sentinel animal species is directly connected to task 4.3 DoA, in particular with regard to fostering collaboration of environmental, food safety and HBM communities.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects) (between 2-8 lines):

WP4:

4.1: Check Human internal exposure to highlighted exposure markers

4.2/4.2.2/P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU: Mutualized resources

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.4.b_Y3_F02_Other compl. studies_ANSES: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

Links outside PARC:

Tight connexions with the Norman network and Life Apex consortium for taking advantage of existing tools developed for monitoring the environment and top food chain biota, respectively. It includes sample handling, QA/QC procedures and highly visible data repositories.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.14. Final report on the application of new exposure assessment approaches (*i.e.* from sampling to data interpretation) to support regulatory needs (*i.e.* lessons learnt and conclusions/perspective for sustainable follow-up) (M81).

Expected Project Reports:

Report 1: Report on the application of innovative methods combined with suspect/NTS/EDA approaches for animal sentinel species – ONIRIS (M60).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners (M24)

Landmark 2: Sample sourcing and sharing completed (M30)

Landmark 3: At least 50% of planned analyses completed (M48)

Landmark 4: All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track (M60)

Landmark 5: Relevant actors approached for promoting the dissemination of the findings at regulatory level within the CSS framework via interaction with ECHA and EEA and other national agencies (M48-M60).

Partners list: ONIRIS (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfR (DE), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), JU (CZ), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 36 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 55 160 €

A4.3.4 Food samples based proof-of-concepts – 1 PROJECT

P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure _ANSES

Project Title	Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	F02-Food items exposure		
Project Manager	Sophie Mompelat sophie.mompelat@anses.fr Julien Parinet julien.parinet@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.4
Project Id	P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure _ANSES		

Status: Initiation/Planning

Summary of the project:

Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), and Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) combined with HRMS, represent a revolution in the field of monitoring chemicals present or potentially present in food, allowing to cover a much larger chemical range than the approaches used until now (low resolution) in the regulatory field. However, the application of these innovative approaches in food is still limited. In addition, the performances of SS/NTS/EDA approaches need to be better assessed in order to be adapted to a regulatory context and harmonisation. This project aims to develop and to qualitatively and quantitatively compare various analytical strategies and

workflows (from food sample preparation to data acquisition and data processing) in order to identify their complementarities or overlap in terms of captured exposure markers (known, emerging and unknown chemicals) in food. A preliminary step will consist in the selection of specific food items related to particular risk situations for both general and particularly vulnerable populations (*e.g.* infant food), as highlighted by EFSA as a major issue for risk assessment. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the relevance of the implementation of such developed screening methods as part of the monitoring and control plans. This would allow to identify original contaminant mixtures from field data. The longitudinal follow-up of the data generated by these means would also allow highlighting both emergences (unregulated substances) and misuses (regulated substances). It will feed and help to structure the early warning system on chemicals of emerging concern, the end-users being the food policy makers.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones through the evaluation of the chemical coverage potential of different SS/NTS/EDA methods
- Qualitative and quantitative assessment of the performances of the developed SS/NTS/EDA methods in order to implement one or more methods that will cover the largest possible chemical range and thus limit the failure to detect hazardous substances potentially present in a sample
- Definition of the needs for further developments/improvements for long-term implementation
- Generation of FAIR data to support the monitoring of real-life mixtures, and especially to support the exposure assessment of vulnerable population groups (*e.g.* children)
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2
- Awareness of general food law policy makers regarding key findings of the project and the data generated

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

By providing a clearer picture of the complementarity and performances of the methods compared in this project, the project should open the door to the integration of new innovative methods and tools needed for a more exhaustive monitoring for end-users, including the laboratories in charge of implementing control methods. Actors from the early warning systems will also benefit from the innovative methods capabilities to generate external exposure data. The production of field data through the application of these new tools will allow risk assessors and risk managers to have a broader view of the real-life chemical mixtures to which consumers are exposed. This will provide scientific data for guiding further toxicological studies and hence support the paradigm shift in risk assessment of these chemical mixtures.

Policies related to the human food chain are a first target. It includes the general food law (Reg 178/2002), and official control regulation (Reg 2017/625) as well as specific food laws such as Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006, Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004.

Key words:

Monitoring, food, innovative methods, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

Food monitoring is supported by the use of targeted analytical methods focusing on a selection of a relatively limited number of chemicals, compared to the number and diversity of chemicals constantly appearing on the market. The development of new and innovative analytical approaches is needed to support and renew the monitoring of the actual complex chemical mixtures in food to which consumers are exposed. The improvement and provision of new methods and tools is therefore a prerequisite to meet the need, formulated by European agencies (including EFSA) and in the EC Roadmap for the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, for a paradigm shift in exposure/risk assessment and the establishment of an early warning system. This project aims to contribute to the fulfilment of these needs as expressed in the

PARC's objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.2.b_Y2_E02_Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.4/P4.3.4.c_Y3_F01_Food contact material_tbd: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6:

Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7:

Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8:

Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

WP9:

Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC:

In order to carry out the project, it would be preferable to capitalize on the projects already initiated by the partners in the margin of PARC. As such, there will be links between this task and French TDS3, ANR AlimOmic, PhD Emergexpo, PhDs and other projects conducted by the contributing partners.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Expected Project Reports:

R1: Final Report on the application of the developed suspect screening/NTS/EDA approaches to real samples originated from environmental/food/HBM surveys designed by other PARC components (e.g.4.1, 4.2) - M48, ANSES.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

L1: Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners (M18)

L 2: Sample sourcing and sharing completed (M24)

L 3: Methods development/improvement completed (M24)

L 4: At least 50% of planned analyses completed (M30)

L 5: All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track (M42)

L 6: Relevant actors approached for promoting the dissemination of the findings at regulatory level within the CSS framework via interaction with ECHA and EEA and other national agencies (M36-M48).

Partners list: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 40 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 164 150 €

WP5 Hazard Assessment - 12 PROJECTS

The overall goal of WP5 is to overcome the major challenges in hazard assessment for human and environmental health. The specific objectives are:

- a) to close data gaps identified by key stakeholders;
- b) to improve the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies, thereby promoting the availability and applicability of new approach methodologies (NAMs) in risk assessment;
- c) to contribute to the improvement of mechanistic understanding of toxicity by analysing all available data and applying systems toxicology approaches and taking into account AOPs and to improve modelling approaches such as PBPK modelling. The work envisaged is divided into three tasks: T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3

T5.1 Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern 4 PROJECTS

This task aims to investigate and close existing data gaps through toxicity testing. The following groups of substances have been selected for the first round of testing: natural toxins, in particular the mycotoxins enniatins and those derived from *Alternaria* -their presence in food products is of concern-, as well as alternatives to BPA. Activities on toxins will address existing data gaps left open by regulatory data requirements, such as toxicokinetics data or comprehensive studies like the Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity study (OECD 2018a). The latter study is also envisaged for other groups of substances of concern, which may include synthetic contaminants such as BPA alternatives/analogues not assessed by industry for authorisation or PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances).

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health – 2 PROJECTS

P5.1.1.a Y1 Toxins BfR UNIVIE

Project Title	Hazard identification and hazard characterisation of the mycotoxins enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins in order to close data gaps and improve risk assessment for human health		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Toxins		
Project Manager	Doris Marko doris.marko@univie.ac.at	UNIVIE	Austria
Project manager	Jessica Dietrich jessica.dietrich@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Natural toxins have no manufacturer or supplier that is responsible for providing hazard data. Due to climate changes, the human exposure to natural toxins will likely increase and regulatory agencies have asked for more hazard data to improve the risk assessment. This will ultimately result in recommendations on which natural toxins should be closely monitored in food feed and food products (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) in order to prevent adverse human health effects and setting maximum levels in food and feed based on knowledge. This proposal will initially focus on two classes of emerging mycotoxins, i.e., enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins where there is a pressing regulatory need for more specific hazard data. Preferably, the studies will be performed according to OECD test guidelines, but in some cases no guidelines are available to address the specific endpoints and NAMs will be employed.

EFSA's CONTAM Panel stated in a scientific opinion on the risks to human and animal health related to the presence of beauvericin and enniatins in food and feed that there might be a health concern regarding chronic exposure to enniatins however there is insufficient data to assess the risk on chronic exposure. Also, in the case of *Alternaria* toxins, the scientific Panel was not able to conduct a systematic risk assessment due to the lack of data. This underlines that further research, in terms of hazard identification and characterization, is required for both toxins.

Additionally, for both Enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins major data gaps were identified in toxicity data in a recent report from the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and the Environment (VKM et al., 2019).

Main expected outputs of the project

The study will provide urgently needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. The data is necessary for subsequent *in vivo* studies which are required to establish health-based guidance values and to perform an appropriate risk assessment and provide an efficient consumer protection.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate toxicological data (mainly focusing on hazard identification and characterization), aiming at incorporating it in risk assessment performed in EU Agencies to set health-based guidance values that could therefore trigger the establishment of maximal levels in food in the context of Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006.

Key words: Natural toxins, *Alternaria* toxins, enniatins, mycotoxins, genotoxicity, endocrine effects, immunotoxicology, *in vitro*, *in silico*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project was designed in order to fill data gaps regarding the main representatives of emerging mycotoxins groups of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins as defined by EFSA. The results are needed to identify critical toxicological effects for subsequent *in vivo* studies which are needed to establish health-based guidance values and to perform an appropriate risk assessment and provide an efficient consumer protection. A working group was formed in which specialists on *Alternaria* and enniatins were combined with specialists in genotoxic, endocrine effects and immunotoxicological endpoints in order to design and deliver a program of studies. Review papers are in progress to summarise the existing data. Frequent meetings were held in order to share as much relevant information as possible. The long-term objective is to establish a European network of scientists interested and having experience in studying natural toxins.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Human exposure to the mycotoxins will be monitored in WP4. Analytical support in measuring the test items in test media is needed in order to support PBPK and IVIVE modelling.

- **WP5.2 and WP5.3:** The test items will also be studied in selected NAMs in WP 5.2 (Cf. project on immunotoxicology). Data that will be generated on kinetics and toxicity will be used in task 5.3 in order to improve and expand existing models (AOP and PBK).
- **WP6:** Hazard data generated will be used in WP6 to build IATAs. Since most mycotoxins will be present in food and feed as mixtures, selected mixtures will also be tested. Relative Potency Factors could therefore be derived where possible and will provide important support for the assessments of risks of mixtures.

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- EFSA- link to the Scientific Committee and Emerging Risks Unit European Food Safety Authority, Parma, Italy, through prof. George Kass. Also, Hans Steinkeller from feed and contaminants unit was interested in especially the results from the enniatins toxicology program.

OECD project Using Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP) to address combined exposures to chemicals with relevant effect-biomarkers. 2022-2025

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

Project reports

R1: Submission of two review papers on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins addressing the relevant endpoints of the project (M11, Alternaria; M13, enniatins) – BfR, UNIVIE

R2: Reports available with data generated – M36 (April 2025) – BfR, UNIVIE

Projects Landmarks:

- First test items available to start experimental studies (M13, BfR)

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), UNIVIE (Austria), BPI (Greece), IBMT (Germany), IMR (Norway), INRS (France), ANSES (France), INSA (Portugal), NIB (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), STAMI (Norway), UNAV (Spain), NVI (Norway), WU-TOX (Netherlands), ISS (Italy), NVI (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 182 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 332 307 €

P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR

Project Title	Hazard assessment of bisphenol A alternatives to close data gaps of concern for human health and improve their risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	BPA_HumTox		
Project Manager	Kiara Aiello	BfR	Germany
	Kiara.Aiello-Holden@BfR.Bund.de		

Deputy Project manager	1. Endocrine Disruptors: Catherine Viguié (INRAE) and Sabrina Tait (ISS) 2. Developmental Neurotoxicity: Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja (CNRS) 3. Immunotoxicity: Emanuela Corsini (UMIL) 4. Carcinogenicity: Maria Silva (INSA) 5. Metabolism: Daniel Zalko (INRAE) & Emanuela Testai (ISS)		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration PARC	36
PARC Workpackage number	5	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.b_Y1_HumanTox_ISS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Due to the restrictions on the use of bisphenol A (BPA) in consumer products, which is the most widely used and studied bisphenol, a number of BPA substitutes have emerged. For most BPA alternatives, information on potential effects on relevant endpoints for human health is either missing or too limited for a sound hazard assessment/characterization. BPA alternatives are already being found in humans and the environment and have raised concerns in a regulatory context. With the upcoming restrictions on BPA, BPA’s alternatives’ tonnages and frequencies of use are expected to severely increase in the coming years.

Therefore, this project aims to fill the identified data gaps, and providing a complete data set for at least four relevant BPA alternatives. The selected alternatives were identified in an ad hoc Workshop together with ECHA and EFSA, following a tiered approach (Details on the prioritization basis can be found at the workshop Report AD5.1). We will fill the knowledge gaps on human health on the following five toxicological endpoints:

1. Endocrine Disruptors;
2. Developmental Neurotoxicity;
3. Immunotoxicity;
4. Non-genotoxic Carcinogenicity;
5. Metabolism (biotransformation, potential bioactivation pathways, toxicokinetics).

This project will also contribute to the identification of molecular biomarkers to develop a method to rapidly predict the possible effects of BPA alternatives. The identification of molecular biomarkers enables the determination of the mechanism(s) through which BPA alternatives act; identifying the key steps of their modes of action will be a key driver in the synergy between Work Package 5 and 6 regarding the improvement/production of Adverse Outcome Pathways.

Main expected outputs of the project

The data obtained will feed mainly into the hazard assessment component of risk assessment and will provide modellers with input for PBPK and QIVIVE models contributing to definition of experimental strategies in an animal-free environment.

Such data will also provide risk assessors with the information needed to conduct a reliable risk assessment essential to the identification of the adequate risk management procedures to implement in order to protect the health of exposed populations through the preparations and implementation of guidelines and directives at national, European and international levels. This will contribute significantly to the enhanced protection of public health and requirements for safe food, consumer products and adequate drinking water.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The Project will provide *in vitro* data on a set of toxicological endpoints for BPA alternatives that have not been assessed by the industry, to support assessors in conducting an adequate risk assessment and implementing suitable regulations.

With this project we will address the concern of the general population regarding this kind of substances, contributing to the production of safe products, such as plastic bottles, food cans and cash receipts, therefore minimizing the risk of adverse effects for end users.

Key words:

BPA analogues, risk assessment, endocrine disruptors, developmental neurotoxicity, immunotoxicity, metabolism, kinetics, *in vitro* methods, cognitive impairment, carcinogenicity

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

A significant contribution to the PARC project will be made, providing useful data regarding BPA alternatives for both general awareness as well as for the needs of regulatory bodies. The data will provide also input for modellers working in PARC to build an experimental strategy relying only on NAMs. A working group was formed in which specialists on BPA alternatives were combined with specialists in genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, developmental neurotoxicology, and immunotoxicological endpoints in order to deliver a program of studies. Frequent meetings were held in order to share as much relevant information as possible. A Workshop between WP/T leaders, project partners, EFSA and ECHA was organized to build a list of priority BPA alternatives for study (AD5.1), considering the regulatory gaps and needs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP4:** elucidation of the structure of yet unknown metabolites of BPA alternatives that may be used as potential biomarkers of exposure and related effect biomarkers.
- **WP5: Tasks 5.1.2.b, 5.2.1 and 5.3** production of major BPA alternatives metabolites for toxicological screening, notably as regards their potential to activate Nuclear Receptors; Characterization of bioactivation pathways mechanistically involved in the onset of endpoints such as immune-toxicity and genotoxicity and T5.3: Production of data (Km, Vmax, hepatic clearance) and direct interaction with PBPK modelers working in T5.3.
- **WP5.3.2:** mechanistic data generated will be used in the development of AOPs (e.g. DNT endpoint)
- **WP6:** Data generated will be used in the hazard and risk assessment. Potency factors will be derived for the assessment of mixture effects. Task 6.1
- **WP7:** Task 7.3: data and text mining - data provision

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- EURION as regards the endpoint 5. Metabolism, on the metabolic fate of BPA analogues, the proposed project relies on the use of the human HepaRG cell line, a relevant human hepatic model displaying a broad panel of XMEs, also currently used in H2020 EURION by INRAE in the context of the GOLIATH project (Augmentation of the applicability domain of the CYP induction test method: OECD draft TG, TM2009-14, for EDCs/MDCs). Such studies will enhance the possibility to interpret results obtained in PARC in the most accurate manner, while no overlap in activities is foreseen.

- National Italian project: PRIN2017 ‘Endocrine disruptors: investigation of the effects on the immune and nervous systems (EDoNIS)’ Ref N. 2017MLC3NF
- Interaction and use of data in the forthcoming “Cluster 1 – Health “ Topics WP 2023-2024 (2. Developmental neurotoxicity and 2.03 on Endocrine Disruptors)

Activities are coordinated with a BPA alternatives project initiated at RIVM.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project outputs will feed mainly into D5.4 - Report on closing data gaps due in M36. In addition, some results generated may also contribute to D5.3 - 1st new AOPs report (M24).

AD5.1: M9 (January 2023) - Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives. Associated Task: 5.1. Leader of the deliverable: Many Partners ANSES/BfR, BPI, MU. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of a strategy to fill data gaps when in vivo study is needed. Associated Task: 5.1. Leader of the deliverable: ANSES/BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/NSA

Project Reports

Closing data gaps report: M36 - Gathering the data obtained within this project with the contribution from each one of the five mentioned endpoints. The deputy project managers will be in charge of their endpoint:

1. Endocrine Disruptors: Catherine Viguié (INRAE) and Sabrina Tait (ISS)
2. Developmental Neurotoxicity Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja (CNRS)
3. Immuno: Emanuela Corsini (UMIL)
4. Carcinogenicity: Maria Silva (INSA)
5. Metabolism: Daniel Zalko (INRAE) & Emanuela Testai (ISS)

Projects Landmarks

Re view BPA alternatives addressing the five endpoints of the project. This will result in a Paper (M14).

Months 1-18: Acquisition or synthesis/purification of labeled compounds; R-HPLC methods developed for the profiling, optimized separation and quantification of selected BPA alternatives and their metabolites (labeled molecules); for Metabolism endpoint: HPLC methods developed to monitor the metabolization of BPA alternatives not available as radio-labeled compounds

Metabolism, Bioactivation, Kinetics:

Months 6-30: Mass balance studies, metabolic profiles and major metabolites identification completed; forward of information to WP4 & WP5.2 (labeled substances)

Months 18-36: Enzymatic constants and kinetic parameters (apparent Km, Vmax and/or hepatic clearance) determined, production of major metabolites for WP5 testing

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), INRAE (France), IBMT Fraunhofer (Germany), ISS (Italy), INRS (France), UMIL (Italy), ULFFA (Slovenia), ISCIII (Spain), CNRS (France), AUTH (Greece), TTL (Finland), MUI (Austria), LIH (Luxembourg), INSA (Portugal), MFUM (Slovenia), NILU (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 131 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 156 920 €

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment) – 2 PROJECTS

P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent

Project Title	Toxicity assessment of naturally occurring toxins on aquatic organisms		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AquaToxins		
Project Manager	Jana Asselman Jana.asselman@ugent.be	Ghent University	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Stefan Örn stefan.orn@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Natural toxins are regulated under EU regulations for human health and certain threshold values are set for safe human consumption. However, from an environmental health perspective, there are no **‘predictive no effect concentrations’ (PNECs)** available indicating safe exposure levels for aquatic species. In the frame of this activity, the toxicity of naturally occurring toxins will be investigated on aquatic organisms and more specifically on aquatic invertebrates and microalgae. Within aquatic ecosystems, invertebrates take up a crucial position in the food chain and the overall ecosystem as primary consumers and food sources for higher trophic levels. Microalgae are the food source for these invertebrates, being a lower level of the trophic chain. By studying the effects of natural toxins on aquatic invertebrates and microalgae, the environmental impact of natural toxins on aquatic ecosystems can be properly assessed and the need for regulations and mitigation measures can be properly evaluated depending on the risks. In vivo tests with invertebrates and microalgae are not considered animal tests in legislation, which is why in vitro and in silico- based methodologies for invertebrates are currently limited in comparison with vertebrate testing. For evaluation of chemical effects on complex biological processes, such as reproduction, invertebrate in vivo studies are the most appropriate and also environmentally relevant.

From a regulatory perspective, aquatic natural toxins are currently not assessed per se. Natural toxins are however significant factors that can impact the toxicity of regulated chemicals. The project will assess the impact of natural toxins in chemical mixtures. The results can also be integrated into the EU guidelines to achieve good environmental status for marine and freshwater environments (marine framework directive and water framework directive). It will also serve as a basis for the further regulation of nitrogen and phosphorus pollution within EU, as these contribute to eutrophication and are seen as a key driver in **‘harmful algae bloom’ (HAB)** formation.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will contribute significantly to the effect assessment of natural toxins in aquatic ecosystems using standard OECD testing procedures that can be directly linked to risk assessment approaches. Particularly, the project will also provide comprehensive information on the ecotoxicity of natural toxins in mixtures using standard OECD tests and therefore contribute to a more realistic risk assessment of natural toxins and their impact on achieving good environmental status (*i.e.* water framework directive and marine

framework directive).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Although toxicological knowledge in invertebrate species may remain overlooked, they account for 95% of all species, and they are highly sensitive targets of hazardous chemicals. The common presence of natural toxins in aquatic environments is a factor overlooked in risk assessment of other regulated chemicals. There is a lack of knowledge regarding how toxins behave in mixtures with other chemical substances. The project will fill this data gap and the results can, together with public available data from the literature, serve as a basis to derive PNECs for aquatic species. The project will generate direct insights on the life history effects of natural toxins in single and mixture exposures in several keystone aquatic species across freshwater and marine habitats. As such, the project will be helpful to other scientists and regulators studying the impact of natural toxins, including interactions with other chemicals, in the aquatic environment.

Key words: natural toxins, aquatic ecosystems, invertebrates, algae, ecotoxicology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to research knowledge for uptake of natural toxins, both in single as in mixture form, into regulatory assessment. The project results will provide a clear insight on the need to include natural toxins as key priority or emerging challenge. From a regulatory perspective, aquatic natural toxins are not currently assessed per se, although environmental status descriptors are significantly impacted by the presence of natural toxins. By assessing the ecotoxicity of single and mixtures –natural toxins can significantly impact the toxicity of regulated chemicals- of toxins using standard OECD testing procedures, this project will provide data that can be integrated in EU guidelines relating to the Marine and Water Framework Directives. The project results will provide a clear insight on the need to include natural toxins as key priority or emerging challenge. The data generated as part of this project will be useful to other projects within Workpackage 5, and cooperation is likely to take place with Workpackages 4 and 6. Six reports are planned in order to disseminate the findings of this project.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects) (between 2-8 lines):

- **WP4:** Task 4.2 Environmental and multisource monitoring. WP4 can provide potential exposure assessments supplementing the effect assessment done here.
- **WP5:** All tasks T5.1, 2, 3. The data from our project may serve as input for Task 5.3, and also as potential alternative vertebrate testing methods relevant to T5.2
- **WP6:** Task 6.1, 6.2, 6.4 and others: Data input for regulatory/risk assessment

Links outside PARC

At this point, there are no ongoing interactions with national or international activities, which are also not taking place (as far as the partners are aware). However, the partners can build on extensive available published data which will be leveraged to ensure no duplicate work is done.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

Project Reports	Month	Partner
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Lymnaea</i> for single toxins	M24	SLU
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Daphnia</i> /marine copepods for single toxins	M24	UGent
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Lymnaea</i> for mixtures of toxins	M36	SLU
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Daphnia</i> /marine copepods for mixtures of toxins	M36	UGent

Ecotoxicity data for <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> for single toxins	M24	UAVR
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> for mixture of toxins and toxins with other chemicals	M36	UAVR

Project Landmarks	Month , Partner
Selection of individual toxins to be tested	M6 (UGent, SLU, UAVR)
Selection of mixtures of toxins to be tested	M18 (UGent, SLU, UAVR)

Partners List:

Ghent University, UGent (Belgium), Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, SLU (Sweden), University of Aveiro, UAVR (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 18 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 25 425 €

P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU

Project Title	BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Bisphenols_ENV		
Project Manager	Ludek Blaha (ludek.blaha@recetox.muni.cz) Ondřej Adamovský (ondrej.adamovsky@recetox.muni.cz)	Masarykova univerzita (MU)	Czech Republic
Deputy Project manager	Katerina Kyriakopoulou (k.kyriakopoulou@bpi.gr)	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2 5.2.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The concerns regarding the potential adverse effects of bisphenol A (BPA) and tight restrictions of BPA in many countries has led to the development of alternative chemicals (*e.g.*, BPZ, BPE, BPS-MAE, BPP, BPAP, BPB, BPC, BPS, BPF, BPAF) resulting in emerging environmental contaminants found worldwide in various environmental components including water, sediment, sludge, soil, indoor dust and air. In addition, the use of BPA alternatives will be increased in the following years, since the use of BPA should be significantly reduced based on the upcoming EFSA scientific opinion in which EFSA has re-evaluated

the risks from BPA in food and propose a lower tolerable daily intake (TDI) than the one previously set. Regarding their properties most bisphenols are characterized as toxic (or very toxic) to aquatic organisms, have been shown to exhibit adverse effects on the endocrine, reproduction, metabolism and immune system in different species and some of them are persistent, mobile or bioaccumulative and are characterized as PBT/vPvB or PMT/vPvM). In parallel, BPA alternatives are molecules regulated under REACH and their chemical safety assessment is carried out at different levels of comprehensiveness according to the specific data requirements based on the tonnage levels in which the substance is produced. These data are not always adequate to assess the potential adverse effects of BPA alternatives not only on human health but also on non-mammalian species, also considering the widespread use of many bisphenols and the possibility of exposure in the environment.

Finally, the current regulatory risk assessment focuses on single chemicals, widely disregarding potential adverse effects of mixtures of BPA alternatives on different organisms, especially after long-term exposure to environmentally realistic concentrations. Consequently, the assessment of combined effects of BPA alternatives and chemicals in general is recognized as one of the major needs in chemical risk assessment and this need has been highlighted in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, in the European Green Deal and in PARC / HBM4EU prioritization survey.

Therefore, this project aims to fill the data gaps concerning the BPA alternatives (activities i and ii) and will serve as a platform for development of NAMs (activities iii-v).

Main expected outputs of the project

The specific aims and the relevant expected outputs of this project are the following:

- Investigation of the potential adverse effects (*e.g.*, apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action or MIE, effects on reproduction, effects on endocrine system) of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on non-mammalian organisms belonging to different taxa (*activity i and ii*)
- Development of *in silico* and modelling tools for hazard assessment of BPA alternatives to ultimately support grouping of substances and read-across approaches based on NAMs (*activity iii*).
- Development / advancing invertebrates’ models as NAMs for the hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and/or other prioritized chemicals (*activity iv*)
- Development / advancing alternative 3R-compatible vertebrate aquatic models for environmental hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals (*activity v*)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide *in vivo* and *in vitro* toxicological data for BPA alternatives relevant for different endpoints (*e.g.* endocrine disruption, reproduction, etc) and several species, that have not been assessed by the industry since they are not included in the specific data requirements under REACH. The project will also bring new data regarding the toxicity of BPA alternatives, as this topic is largely unexplored. Moreover, the project will contribute to the development of NAMs. Therefore, the project aims to assist risk assessors, Member State Regulatory Authorities, EU agencies and other relevant stakeholders in conducting hazard/risk assessment.

Key words: data gaps, NAMs, BPA alternatives, *in silico*, *in vivo*, *in vitro*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to the investigation and closing of data gaps regarding the hazard assessment of priority chemicals - bisphenols (single compounds and chemicals) with focus on the environment (Activity 5.1.2). In addition, this project will contribute to the development of innovative methodologies (NAMs) that will directly contribute to hazard identification and risk assessment not only for BPA alternatives but also for other chemicals (Activity 5.2.2). The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO4, OO7 and OO9 by developing and implementing R&I work programs based on priorities

set and generating results and knowledge to support the use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps in BPA alternatives hazard assessment, and by development of tools and methods to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes.

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), promote cooperation with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), develop new networks of laboratories (OO11), contribute to communication and dissemination of the results (OO6) and implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4: Task 4.2.1 and Task 4.2.2 - incorporation of environmental monitoring data into BPA selection process.

WP5: All tasks T5.1, 5.2, 5.3 - data derived in 5.1 and 5.2 will be valuable for AOP development / modeling in 5.3.

WP6: Task 6.1, 6.2 and others - discussion regarding building NAM confidence for regulatory purposes.

WP7: Data management – bilateral discussion regarding proper data storage and management.

WP3 and WP9: will be contacted for identification of synergies.

Links outside PARC

- **HBM4EU**: Information on exposure and real-life mixtures will be taken from information provided by HBM4EU.
- **POlySAFE** : French national program on assessment of plastic alternatives for food containers (Coordinated by CNRS)
- **Precision Tox**: A link to Precision Tox will be established to benefit from the 5-species 250 substances toxicogenomic approach, to create synergies and to avoid duplication of work.
- **PRORISK**: The activity will be synergized by sharing predicted and experimentally derived environmental hazard data to a novel integrative risk assessment platform developed in PRORISK (<https://prorisk-itn.eu/>) that links chemical-biological interactions, through AOPs, effects on organisms and populations up to predictions of risks for ecosystem services and the socio-economic costs of environmental damage.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.1: M9 (January 2023) - Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives. Associated Task: 5.1. Leader of the deliverable: BPI, MU. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task: 5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Project Reports	Month	Responsible Partner
Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v).	12, 42	MU
Reports on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	28	BPI
Reports on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (based on PARC environmental monitoring data) on different	42	BPI

organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).		
Project Landmarks	Related to activity	Month, Partner
Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on available existing data and discussion among partners / stakeholders	i.-v.	M9, BPI
Selection of datasets (for <i>in silico</i> tools) and selection of endpoints for experimental tests assessing individual chemicals or their mixtures emphasizing BPA alternatives a priority chemical	iii, iv, v	M9, MU
Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on PARC environmental monitoring data	i and ii	M30, BPI

Partners List:

BPI (Greece), SLU (Sweden), IISPV (Spain), SDU (Denmark), INERIS (France), NIB (Slovenia), IEP-NRI (Poland), UU (Sweden), UG-PL (Poland), UAVR (Portugal), EAWAG (Switzerland), NIVA (Norway), MU (Czechia), NIC (Slovenia), UFZ (Germany), BFG (Germany), UPO (Spain), UAntwerpen (Belgium), CNRS (France), MUI (Austria), SU (Sweden), INRAE (France).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 303 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 479 269 €

T5.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling - 5 PROJECTS

The focus of this task is on the improvement of the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies that logically combine novel methods with well-established approaches, preferably in a tiered manner. In brief, this task will evaluate the relevance and readiness of new technologies, e.g., genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, high-content analysis microscopy, high resolution mass spectrometry, and human inducible pluripotent stem cell technology, for the assessment of (eco)toxicological endpoints such as non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption and (developmental) neurotoxicity, thereby leveraging OECD's and PARC's AOP frameworks. Also, test methods, tools and methodologies will be developed to identify drivers of toxicity in mixtures and to support the grouping of chemicals, including the application of read-across. Furthermore, this task aims for the development and application of predictive *in vitro* and *in silico* tools to identify and characterise specific hazards. Through close collaboration with human biomonitoring communities in- and outside PARC, methods and computational approaches will be developed to study the metabolism of chemical substances in different biological (test) systems or matrices (e.g., cells, organoids, organs, blood) for comparison between species.

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling – 5 PROJECTS

P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE

Project Title T5.2.1_ Non-genotoxic carcinogens

Project Acronym NGTXCs

Project Acronym (15 letters)

max)			
Project	Marc Audebert	INRAE	France
Manager 1	marc.audebert@inrae.fr		
Project	Michael Oelgeschläger	BfR	Germany
Manager 2	Michael.Oelgeschlaeger@bfr.bund.de		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P 5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTxCs_INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

A range of organ and cellular model systems (including liver, breast, colon, adipocytes) will be investigated with innovative human-relevant NAMs, including state of the art transcriptomic approaches, high-content analysis, cell painting, epigenetics and high-throughput-compatible reporter systems addressing well established and relevant mechanisms of carcinogenesis, such as (oxidative) stress, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), inflammation, changes in metabolism, epigenetic marks or nuclear receptors signaling as well as proliferation. In addition, experimental approaches will be complemented by the optimization of *in silico* tools for the identification of NGTxCs to address the assay needs for the development of an NGTxCs IATA in cooperation with WP6.1 and ongoing activities at EU and OECD level. The project will improve our knowledge of the relationships between a range of different substances specific for distinct adverse outcome pathways that ultimately lead to cancer. In addition, methods with increasing complexity, from 2D cell culture up to 3D spheroids and zebrafish as a simple vertebrate model system, will facilitate the integration of the physiological and toxicological relevant information with respect to adversity in order to inform about potential carcinogens and to improve chemical assessment and regulation. The project will align with AOPs and IATA work under Task 5.3 as well as Task P6.1 and takes into account the ongoing work of the OECD expert group on NGTxCs as well as current EU initiatives.

Main expected outputs of the project

To develop internationally acceptable *in vitro* testing batteries (NAMs) and IATAs, the test methods (including *in silico* prediction tools) will be subject to testing of a sufficiently large set of reference compounds, including prioritized PARC compounds, to allow the evaluation of reliability and relevance taking into account sensitivity and specificity of the various systems as well as their complementarity detecting different MoAs involved on non-genotoxic carcinogenicity. The more complex systems will be further developed and optimized to allow a more physiological evaluation of activity for a subset of the reference compounds.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be particularly helpful from a risk assessor's as well as applicants from industry because the innovative, rapid, reliable and cost efficient methods developed therein will allow an efficient and relevant mechanistic NGTxCs hazard analysis of a high number of substances and mixtures thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances well as product optimization following the zero pollution ambition of the green deal and the chemicals strategy for sustainability.

Key words: Carcinogenesis, 3D cell models, OMICs, MoA, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Due to the composition of the consortium an efficient communication with other other WPs, National Hubs, research initiatives (Horizon projects) and the OECD is ensured and the project will cooperate with WP 9 to ensure FAIR data practices. The main aim is to develop new approaches and innovative concepts to detect and evaluate potential NGTxC /carcinogens taking into account current practices of

standardization and also aims at validation of some methods in cooperation with external activities. The consortium has already connected various labs from different European countries and is in contact with additional laboratories.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The priorities regarding the various regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate within WP5 “Hazard assessment” and with WP6 “Innovation in regulatory risk assessment” on topics related to NGTXCs and IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity; b) interaction with the other T5.2a subjects related to endocrine disruption and immunotoxicity end-points; c) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5; d) evaluation of NGTXCs IATA through case studies in WP6. The data generated in the project itself as well as the case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to ongoing H2020 projects, in particular the ASPIS and the EURION clusters and OECD activities, including the work of the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST), the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment as well as and the OECD NGTXCs expert group.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Project Reports:

R 1 – Evaluating NAMs for the assessment of chemicals with potential NGTxC activity (M30)

R 2 – Combining NAMS for the evaluation of various NGTxC activities (M48)

R 3 – Development of an efficient and reliable testing strategy for the identification of NGTxC (M60)

Projects Landmarks:

- Overview of NGTXCs assays (M12).
- Establish test method set up (M24)
- Selection of sufficient reference compounds for technical validation (M24).
- Evaluation of covering relevant MoA of potential NGTxC (M42)
- Establishment of an efficient and reliable testing strategy for NGTxC (M60)

Partners List:

INRAE (FR); BfR (DE); ANSES (FR); INSERM (FR); NIB (SI); UL-LACDR (NL); UNAV (ES); IRFM (IT); RIVM (NL); UKHSA (UK); UKL (DE); NILU (NO);

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 192 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 247 215 €

P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE

Project Title	T5.2.1_ Metabolic Endocrine Disruption		
Project	MD-EDC		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Daniel Zalko daniel.zalko@inrae.fr	INRAE	France
Deputy Project manager	Albert Braeuning Albert.braeuning@bfr.bund.de	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment	Germany
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Over the past decade, progress in endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDC) research has demonstrated that one specific adverse effect of a number of EDC is their capability to induce a lasting disruption of endogenous metabolism. These substances, referred as "metabolism disrupting chemicals" (MDC) are largely suspected to contribute to the incidence of obesity and related metabolic disorders such as type II diabetes and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, in association with genetic factors, nutrition and lifestyle. Nowadays, more than 50 million people in Europe suffer from metabolic disorders with the role of environmental stressors (either man-made or natural chemicals) being increasingly recognized.

According to WHO/IPSC (2002), specific criteria should be fulfilled for a substance to be considered as an EDC/MDC. Despite MDC are suspected to play a major role in the worldwide epidemics of metabolic disorders, there are currently no specific regulatory *in vivo* or *in vitro* tests allowing to identify their adverse effects. From a regulatory perspective, it is thus of paramount importance to validate methodologies allowing to identify and assess MDC-associated risks. This section will focus on the development of new approach methodologies (NAM) allowing to answer key regulatory needs.

Specific compounds under investigation will come from the PARC priority list (BPA alternatives), other EU projects such as the EURION Cluster, and agencies like ECHA or EFSA. The EDC/MDC section of Task 5.2, Activity 5.2.1 Human Health, will enhance synergies and avoid overlaps with ongoing projects such as EURION, by building on knowledge and experimental systems already established or in development, but with a focus on experimental systems not yet primarily addressed in these projects, as well as by extending the spectrum of MDC and focusing on priority-listed families of substances.

Main expected outputs of the project

A comprehensive exploration of Nuclear Receptor (NR)-driven effects will be carried out using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-going pre-validation of transient cell lines in EURION. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further Modes of Action (MoA) exploration, as well as adverse outcome pathway (AOP) and read-across development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, opening the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, as well as parallel additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. New developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models will enable to close major data gaps in the field of metabolic disruption, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Currently, there exists no regulatory test guidelines, approaches or testing strategies for MDCs. The sheer need for tests development in the field of metabolic disorders has been highlighted in recent work commissioned by DG Environment. In this project section, new methods will be developed for identifying MDC, with outcomes expected to be of great use for risk assessors. Work will be focused on projects aiming at a comprehensive exploration of NR-driven effects using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the ongoing pre-validation of transient cell lines. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, AOP and read-across development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, to open the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, but also additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. The goal is to produce new developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models, so to close major data gaps in the field of MDC, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs.

Key words:

Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals , EDC, Metabolism Disrupting Chemicals, MDC, metabolic disruption, obesity, energy metabolism, fatty acid metabolism, metabolic disorders, metabolism, cellular signalling, NAM

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project is directly related to the PARC DoA, as it is directed towards the development of new approach methods to allow for animal-free testing of compounds. The tests to be developed to detect metabolic disruption will close a gap for which until now no specific test systems or guidelines are in place. Thereby the project will directly contribute to improved risk assessment and an elevated level of consumer protection in the EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Task 2.1: complementarity with guideline tests
- Task 5.1a: link with the assessment of the fate of model EDs/MDCs and availability of major metabolites for testing.
- Task 5.2b: link with environmental package whenever EDs are involved (e.g.data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with WP5.2b, 5.3 and 6.1).
- Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- Task 6.1: use of NAMs for toxicity testing
- Task 6.3: several case studies of which some are concerned with EDs

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects HBM4EU & EDCmixrisk: compound selection.
- H2020 project cluster EURION (esp. projects GOLIATH, OBERON and EDCmet): compound selection, complementary test systems (duplication of work is avoided by focusing on other target organs and tissues), synergies in AOP and IATA development.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Project Reports:

- R 1: Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds (INSERM, M30).
- R 2: *In vitro* assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterization established (BfR/UIBK, M34).

Projects Landmarks:

Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds (INSERM, M30).

In vitro assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterization established (BfR/UIBK, M34).

Partners List:

BfR (DE); INSERM (FR); UU IRAS (NL); U Antwerpen (BE); UU (SE); UIBK (AT); UFZ (DE); IfADo (DE); INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/05/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 118 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 114 191 €

P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU

Project Title	T5.2a_Endocrine disruptors – Thyroid hormone system disruption		
Project	ED-Thyro		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Terje Svingen	DTU	Denmark
	tesv@food.dtu.dk		
Deputy Project manager	Tamara Vanhaecke	VUB	Belgium
	Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be		
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) has adopted the revised OECD Guidance Document 150 (OECD 2018) in its regulatory guidance for evaluating biocides and pesticides for ED activity. Despite these relatively recent advances, current test strategies and regulations are inadequate with regard to specifically identifying thyroid hormone system disruptors (THSDs). Some *in vitro* assays (non-OECD TGs) for certain Molecular Initiation Events (MIEs) relevant for THSD are available and are currently in the process of regulatory validation (<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/science-update/vitro-methods-detection-thyroid-disruptors>). However, there is still a pressing need to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs that cover a broader range of Key Events (KEs) i.e. from MIE to Adverse Outcomes (AO). The goal of this project is to fill this gap by gaining more mechanistic knowledge on THSD for targeted NAM development. In addition, this project will also help to understand key species differences in THSD as well as *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation by performing targeted *in vivo* rodent studies, *in silico* assays, human relevant stem cell-derived *in vitro* systems and zebrafish as whole organism model. The use of *in vivo* studies (e.g. rodents) is still required to elucidate the KEs responsible for THSD-mediated adverse outcomes in order to facilitate the development of NAMs predictive of human health effects, as this causal knowledge is still

unknown.

Main expected outputs of the project

Studies will be conducted that are aimed specifically at characterizing new mechanistic knowledge to enable the development of relevant NAMs. Especially the identification of upstream MIEs or KEs for downstream AOs relevant for THSD effect outcomes, Once identified, specific KEs can be targeted for NAMs development to increase the predictive power of non-animal test data for hazard identification and/or risk assessment purposes. The project thus focusses on points of vulnerability along the TH signalling pathway to chemical perturbation. For NAMs development, the project will examine direct versus indirect perturbation of the TH axis by exogenous agents; build a novel developmental stem cell-based assay with human relevance; characterize further the evolutionary conservation of the THS axis in order to make better use of non-human NAMS (e.g. fish, invertebrates) to inform on human health risks. New knowledge and NAMs will better enable development of a robust IATA specific for THSD.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will deliver valuable contributions to chemical safety assessors and regulators by providing evidence-based mechanistic knowledge for THSD that will enable better use of non-vertebrate animal test data for decision making. This will contribute greatly to the detection of hazardous chemical substances with focus on EDs and THSDs, thus adhering to the zero-pollution ambition of the Green Deal, as well as the Chemicals Strategy set out by the European Commission. Other end-users such as the chemical and cosmetic industry will benefit from gathered knowledge and developed test methods and strategies, as they may themselves adopt new and improved alternative test methods for a more rapid, reliable and cost-efficient internal testing regimen.

The long-term benefit for stakeholders will be a sizeable reduction in animals used for safety testing of chemical and cosmetic substances. Stakeholders will also benefit by minimizing exposure to unwanted THSDs, possibly leading to improved public health.

Key words: Thyroid hormone system disruptors; T3; T4; endocrine; brain; liver; risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project supports innovation by providing novel mechanistic knowledge that will be exploited for developing novel NAMs for THSD testing. The project will close much needed regulatory test-method and scientific gaps related to the thyroid hormone system and as such contribute towards improved regulation and consumer protection for THSD compounds. Cooperation with other R&I initiatives is assured through collaboration with other PARC activities related to NAMs (activity 5.2.2), systems biology (task 5.3) and IATA development and risk assessment (tasks 6.1 and 6.3). FAIR data practice is ensured through WP9 cooperation. Communication of the project results to the research community will be done via publication in peer-reviewed journals and participation in congresses.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP2 Task 2.1:** complementarity with guideline tests
- **WP3:** Synergies, Communication and awareness
- **WP5: Task 5.2.2:** link with environmental package whenever EDs and THDs are involved (e.g. data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with WP5.2.2, 5.3 and 6.1). **Task 5.3:** use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- **WP6 Task 6.1:** use of NAMs for toxicity testing. **Task 6.3:** several case studies of which some concerned with EDs and THSDs (e.g., case study 10)
- **WP7:** Data management plan
- **WP9:** Training, laboratory network

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects – EURION cluster: ATHENA project, SCREENED project and ERGO project

- Green Deal projects: PANORAMIX project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Project Reports:

Report on the Deliverables will be provided at the end of the project (M36 and M48).

- Expand on available THS MIEs by delivering a test battery of MIEs related to thyroid hormone transporters across physiological barriers (M36).
- Establish plausibility links between TH system MIEs and downstream effects using transcriptomics of TH target tissues and of 2D-and 3D-liver (stem) cell-based cultures; validate MIEs of THSDs and provide a framework for interpretation of *in vitro* and molecular data (M48).
- Establishment and testing of *in vitro* assays, *in silico* and zebrafish/amphibian assays to identify MIEs (M36).
- Investigate the use of non-mammalian NAMs for extrapolation to human health for THSD: zebrafish embryo assays to be used in a case study for cross-species extrapolation (M36).
- Release of QSAR predictions for 650,000 substances including 80,000 REACH-preregistered / 11,000 registered substances and QMRF documentation in free Danish (QSAR Models website (M48)

Projects Landmarks:

- Multi-organ transcriptomics (toxicogenomics) data from THSD rodents to identify pathways for incorporation in test assays or AOPs (M48)
- Toxicogenomics cross-species comparisons between rodent *in vivo* toxicity studies (liver) with human stem cell-based *in vitro* test assays (M48)
- Proteomics cross-species comparison between *in vivo* zebrafish toxicity studies with human cell-based *in vitro* assays (M48)

Partners List:

DTU (Denmark); VUB (Belgium), BfR (Germany); SDU (Denmark); UAntwerpen (Belgium); VUA (Netherlands); ISCIII (Spain); INSERM (France)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 126 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 242 479 €

P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm

Project Title	Immunotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Immunotox		
Project Manager	Robert Barouki	Inserm	France
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Deputy Project manager	Etienne Blanc etienne.blanc@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Outline of the project. During the first three years of PARC and in line with regulatory needs we will develop research aiming at characterizing new NAMs addressing three major endpoints in immunotoxicity: organ-related immunotoxicity with a focus on respiratory toxicity and sensitization; immunosuppression, in particular through response to vaccination; characterizing new models for cellular immunotoxicity assessing key events. The major outcome will be the development of NAMs in these immunotoxicity areas. For this, reference chemicals will be used and once the NAMs are developed, PARC priority substances will be tested when relevant. These new NAMs will be used for the development of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) (task 5.3) and the development of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) (task 6.1).

Regulatory relevance.

- REACH: several immune related outcomes are relevant for REACH: skin sensitization, respiratory sensitization, immunosuppression. Currently under REACH, the immunotoxicity investigations are triggered based on repeated dose toxicity studies (28- or 90-day) in case there are some indications of immunotoxicity. If indications of immunosuppression are seen, one can include e.g. Cohort 3 into the study design of EOGRTS (developmental immunotoxicity) or request to have an immunotoxicity investigation included in a standard repeated dose toxicity study (adult immunotoxicity).
- CLP (Reg EC 1272/2008): While respiratory sensitization is mentioned as a hazard in the CLP regulation, it is acknowledged, that there is no respective method to detect respiratory sensitizers. Hence, a need to develop methods to detect respiratory sensitizers is recognized. On top of that the CLP regulation foresees that non-animal testing is conducted wherever possible, implying support for the development of NAMs.
- Plant protection products (Reg EC 1107/2009) and biocides (Reg EC 528/2012): Sensitization is analysed as part of the data requirements for PPP and biocides. The need to develop methods for respiratory sensitization as well as alternative testing strategies is recognized.
- Cosmetic products: skin sensitization
- Food contact materials (Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004): allergenicity
- Food contaminants (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) and enzymes (Regulation (EC) No 1332/2008): allergenicity
- Chemicals strategy: Immunotoxicity is listed as one of the top priority hazard classes in the chemicals strategy (COM(2020) 667 final, 2020).

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver a set of *in vitro* systems that allow the assay of key events in the immune system function or dysfunction. New parameters will be developed to better explore the immune system cellular content and activity, cytokine and antibody production and release, as well as the effect of signaling. Different primary cell systems and cell lines as well as epithelial and immune cell co-cultures will be characterized. Depending on the advancement of the work on the characterization of the NAMs,

interlaboratory validation can be considered. The global aim is to provide task 5.3 and WP6 with assays and data that will support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs through a better characterization of key events in NAMs. For example if we show that chemicals that activate a receptor, also induce the expression of cytokine genes in an immune cell, this will support the relationship between receptor activation (MIE) and cytokine production (KE) and therefore the build up of an AOP.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow rapid mechanistic hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances, to the Zero Pollution Ambition of the Green Deal and to The Chemicals Strategy. Additionally, the methods will be able to screen mixtures thus contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry as *in vitro* methods they will be rapid, reliable and cost efficient. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health ultimately resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays.

Key words: immunotoxicity, sensitization, immunosuppression, vaccination, inflammation, NAMs, tests, AOPs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The aim of PARC is to develop new toxicity tests in compliance with the 3R concept, particularly in outcomes that have been prioritized in the chemical strategy for sustainability. Immunotoxicity is one of these outcomes and this project directly addresses this objective. By developing new NAMs that are biologically relevant, this project addresses the PARC objective of developing new models and innovative concepts for risk assessment.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP2, Task 2.1:** complementarity with guidelines tests
- **WP4, Task 4.1:** immunotoxicity studies in human (the COVID-19 vaccination study)
- **WP5, Task 5.2b:** complementarity with environmental immunotoxicity, **Task 5.3:** use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
 1. **WP6, Task 6.1:** use of NAM for IATA/DA validation for regulatory purposes: NAM will be developed that feed into these IATAs.

Links outside PARC

- H2020 project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- EHEN projects on immune effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EURION projects, including Oberon, Goliath, EDCmet
- ASPIS projects including Ontox, RISKHUNT3R, PrecisionTox
- Polyrisk,
- Aurora
- VHP4Safety
- MOMENTUM
- EFSA (sensitization)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA
 AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Project Reports:

- Characterization of in vitro systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity (M36)
- Immunosuppression and response to vaccination (M36)

- *In vitro* systems to assay key events in the immune system function or dysfunction (M36)

Projects Landmarks:

No global landmarks are foreseen for the project

Partners List:

INSERM (France), NIPH (Norway), MUI (Austria), NPHC (Hungary), RIVM (Netherlands), IRAS (Netherlands), UL-FFA (Slovenia), INSA (Portugal), UFZ (Germany), WR (Netherlands), LIH (Luxemburg), LIST (Luxemburg)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 159 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 292 056 €

P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU

Project Title	Neurotoxicity		
Project	DNT / NT		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Tamara Tal	UFZ	Germany
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Deputy Project manager	Ellen Fristche	IUF	Germany
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Deputy Project manager	Joëlle Rüegg	UU	Sweden
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Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Developmental (DNT) and acute (ANT) neurotoxicity are currently assessed via different OECD guideline studies. DNT/ANT guideline studies are extraordinarily resource-intensive and therefore not suited for studying adverse effects of large numbers of chemicals. In Reach regulation, DNT guideline studies are not mandatory and ANT testing is not performed for low tonnage compounds. There is international consensus, strongly supported by EFSA and the OECD that DNT testing has to be made faster and more human-relevant by implementing an alternative DNT testing battery for regulatory purposes.

The key strategy is to provide a comprehensive battery of NAMs that for DNT fills the gaps in the current DNT *in vitro* battery (IVB) and, for ANT, sets up such a battery, both according to DNT/ANT modes-of-action. The focus solely lies on (i) human cells that avoid the problem of species specificity and (ii) zebrafish, an alternative whole organism, low-cost screening tool with integrated nervous system functions. Novel methods include endocrine disruption-induced DNT, transcriptomic and epigenetic effects, synaptogenesis, neural network formation and function, blood-brain-barrier formation, myelin toxicity, startle response, anxiety-like behavior, and learning and memory tests. As there are currently not many neurotoxicity adverse outcome pathways (AOP) available, new AOPs will be generated (with T5.3).

Methods newly established or optimized in this WP will undergo test method set-up and mechanistic validation.

Main expected outputs of the project

- **New NAMs that fill the current DNT *in vitro* testing battery (IVB) gaps.** Here, test methods will be set up from existing test systems (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).
- **New NAMs for ANT.** Current test systems will be used for test method set-up (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- Additional IVB NAMs developed for DNT/ANT will provide **risk assessors** with rapid mechanistic hazard analysis supporting the green deal and the chemicals strategy.
- Mixture screening in these NAMs contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies.
- **Industry** will be strongly supported by developed NAMs as they will serve as valid tools for pre-screening and in-house prioritization based on rapid, reliable and cost-efficient methods.
- **NGOs** and **consumers** will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately, in the benefits for public health upon regulatory implementation of the assays.

Keywords: Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), Acute neurotoxicity (ANT), Alternative DNT testing battery, *in vitro* testing battery (IVB), New Approach methodologies (NAMs)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In the EU Green Deal strategy, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability specifically mentions neurotoxicity (DNT/ANT) as well as endocrine disruption-related developmental neurotoxicity (ED-DNT) as critical outcomes. Moreover, mental and behavioral health are part of the children’s health protection policy. Due to large data gaps, DNT has been recognized as a serious public health concern by many countries and regulatory agencies world-wide. The OECD provides the umbrella for current regulatory DNT efforts including the production of a guidance document for regulatory use of the DNT IVB. Within PARC, gaps within the DNT IVB will be closed and an ANT IVB will be established.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP4:** Make use of results from human biomonitoring studies for prioritizing hazard assessment.
- **T5.1.** Toxicity testing to address chemicals of concern. **T5.3:** Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs that are relevant for DNT/ANT.
- **T6.1:** Delivering IATAs ready for regulatory application. WP 5.2 will provide data, tools and concepts to improve risk assessment in general. DNT (ANT is to be clarified) is a priority area for developing qAOP but not in the first round (ED, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and liver are first).
- **WP7:** Data management plan. We will link with WP7 to make our data available, as soon as possible, for regulators, external researchers, and public. We need access to a database where we can store data, with immediate access for regulators and embargo dates for public use.

Links outside PARC

ENDpoiNTs and other projects within the EURION cluster. In ENDpoiNTs, a battery of assays (in silico, in vitro and in vivo) are developed that detect ED-induced DNT.

- ONTOX, Precisiontox and RiskHunter of the ASPIS cluster.
- H2020 Panoramix (panoramix-h2020.eu)
- US-EPA for common data analysis and DNT IVB assembly.
- ATHLETE project of the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) cluster (athleteproject.eu).
- VHP4safety Virtual Human Platform for Safety Assessment – VHP4Safety
- Human Biomonitoring Plattform Austria

Key PARC Deliverables (and Milestones to which the project contributes)

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports:

- R 1: Development of NAMs relevant for detection of ANT
- R 2: Fill existing gaps in the DNT IVB
- R 3: Complementary zebrafish assays for the DNT and ANT IVB Final Report (M36)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Selection of assays added to the DNT IVB.

Test method set up with information according to Crofton et al. provided for each method.

Delivery of test compounds for mechanistic (scientific) assay validation.

Full DNT/ANT test methods set-up.

Partners List:

INSERM-UBX (FR); UU (SE); NIPH (NO); IUF (DE); UKON (DE); RIVM (NL); UFZ (DE); ISCIII (ES); TiHo (DE); AIT (AT); NMBU (NO); [UG-PL \(PL\)](#)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 164 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 304 555 €

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

No project submitted at present.

T5.3 Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs - 3 PROJECTS

This task will contribute to the development of AOPs and provide data for the improvement of Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic (PBK) models. It further aims to integrate relevant human disease models and develop concepts facilitating *in vitro* - *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE). For this, systems biology methodology will be applied to *in silico*, *in vivo* and *in vitro* data (biochemical data, omics, endpoints). New data generated in tasks 5.1 and 5.2 as well as relevant data from databases will be mapped to existing (networks of) AOPs, with the aim to hypothesise adverse outcomes. Available literature will be automatically explored to fill gaps in AOPs and to link priority chemicals to events in AOPs using text mining and network analysis tools. This will support the identification and biological characterisation of effect markers that can, later on, be used in WP4. Using bioinformatic tools, this will allow informing human disease mechanisms based on omics and other information. Gaps in pathophysiological knowledge will then be filled by using datasets from existing human biobanks.

Regarding PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology, task 5.3 aim to develop IVIVE-PBK models,

to characterise the impact and predictivity of *in vitro* Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) parameters, to quantify the uncertainty by comparing to *in vivo* studies and to collaborate with WP6 on a wide range of case studies. Toxicokinetic parameters will be generated for all WP5 test compounds using the appropriate *in vitro* test systems, *in silico* predictions and analytical measurements. PBK modelling will be used to estimate internal exposure and to compare this to Points of Departure derived from *in vitro* mechanistic NAM assays for priority chemicals and pathways. Integration of toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic models in quantitative systems toxicology models will improve adverse outcome prediction.

Fig 7: WP5 contribution: Hazard assessment

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterization – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SysTox		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water b.water@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Olivier Taboureau olivier.taboureau@u-paris.fr	INSERM	FR
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Work package	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-	5.3.1 and

number

activity:

5.3.3

Project Id

P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The SysTox project is part of WP5 and reflect the activities of T5.3.1 and T5.3.3. The objective is to support the chemical risk assessment in the AOP framework, with the evaluation of mechanistic data for a quantitative hazard characterization through new approach methods (NAMs). Mapping and quantifying MIE activity and KE activation is essential for the ultimate application of the AOP framework in chemical safety assessment. Systems toxicology involves the holistic quantitative assessment of perturbations of biological systems by chemicals and typically involves omics approaches, including transcriptomics and metabolomics. To derive confidence in the application of NAM-based omics data, there is a necessity to determine the relevance of *in vitro omics* data with the *in vivo* situation. Various bioinformatics approaches are available to uncover hazard. There is a need to understand the validity of each method with respect to the qualitative and quantitative characterization of hazards. In this project we will validate innovative *in silico* and bioinformatics approaches for quantitative chemical hazard assessment and will be evaluated in this project. We will also address the human *in vivo* relevance of *in vitro* findings. The ultimate aim is that a quantitative assessment of hazard will contribute to classification of chemicals for specific health effects related to EDC, immunosuppression, DNT, NonGenotoxic carcinogenesis, areas that are of critical relevance for PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will have established innovative approaches for mechanism-based hazard assessment based on *in silico* prediction and omics approaches. This will involve both QSAR-based prediction of critical MIE activation as well as quantitative assessment of KE activation based on omics data. In addition, we will provide confidence in the relevance of *in vitro* transcriptomics responses with respect to responses occurring in the human *in vivo* situation. Results of this project should help to prioritize accurate and robust omics-based prediction for critical toxicological endpoints in chemical risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcome of the project will be interactive online systems toxicology tools that will allow rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. The tools will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry and regulatory agencies, since it will allow a cross-sector application of systems toxicology in a structured manner using similar bioinformatics tools. This will allow commonalities in the understanding of omics technologies in a quantitative manner for determination of point-of-departure for risk assessment. Stakeholders will also see benefits in the reduction of animal testing. Finally, the results of our project will allow for the regulatory implementation of omics strategies and, thereby, for the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances that will benefit public health from.

Key words:

Omics, transcriptomics, systems toxicology, gene network, key events, human translation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will ultimately lead to the development of NGRA tools that integrate human-relevant test methods, using *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches to provide quantitative mechanistic information on modes of action, and that allow the rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. As such, it will establish an initial framework for the application of omics data in a regulatory setting. Collaboration is taking place within and outside of Workpackage 5. A workshop on systems toxicology aiming to identify relevant datasets to be used in case studies was organized in January, and benefitted from the regulatory insight of EFSA and the BfR. Three reports will be produced to disseminate the results of this project.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The SysTox project is linked to the following tasks:

- Task 4.1: human studies and effect markers à translate candidate biomarkers from SysTox studies to human biomonitoring effect markers.
- Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental studies and NAM development (5.2) à data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case study.
- Task 5.3.2: use of NAM data for AOP development and effect marker validation à findings from SysTox project can be used in Project 5.3.2.
- Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation à information from SysTox can be used for data gap filling for qAOP development.
- Task 6.2: mixture effects à mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through SysTox tools
- Task 7.3: data and text mining à data provision
- WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of bioinformatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the SysTox project. Focus will be on omics datasets. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- OECD - Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA)
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4 : M14 (June 2023) - Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints Associated Tasks T5.3. Leader of the deliverable UL-LACDR

AD5.7: M18 (October 2023) – Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms. Associated Tasks T5.3. Leader of the deliverable UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO

Project Reports

1. Report on the inventory of *in vitro*, *in vivo* and human omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts and bioinformatics approaches in public domain repositories at PARC partners for all selected adverse outcomes. (M12)
2. Report on the applicability domain of systems toxicology bioinformatics approaches for regulatory implementation (M26)
3. Report on translation of systems toxicology data from *in vitro* NAM to human *in vivo* (M36).

Projects Landmarks

- Workshop on systems toxicology: data requirement and strategy; M9
- Datasets required for systems toxicology in data management systems; M16
- Novel human datasets for *in vitro* to *in vivo* translation established; M24

Partners List

Ugent (BE), MUI (AT), ISCIII (ES), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), BPI (GR), KIT (DE),

NPHC (NO), WR (NL), Sciensano (BE), NIPH (HU), UNIABDN (UK), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), IRFM (IT), UIBK (AT), UMIL (IT), AUTH (GR), IISPV (ES), UOB (UK).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 132 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 106 788 €

A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm

Project Title	AOP Development		
Project	AOP		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Robert Barouki robert.barouki@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Karine Audouze karine.audouze@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.2
Project Id	P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

New approach methodologies (NAMs) provide a large diversity and amount of data that are very challenging, if not impossible to implement in regulatory applications or mechanistic toxicology unless they are integrated and represented in a useful and widely accepted framework. Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) fulfill all requirements for providing such as framework. AOPs describe the causal relationships between molecular initiating events (MIE), subsequent key events (KE) at different biological levels and ultimately adverse outcomes. They are developed by integrating and connecting data from various sources i.e. databases and the scientific literature, in a logical sequence of causally-linked events.

The AOP development in this project will focus on the selected priority outcomes related to immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption. Different groups will first identify available AOPs (if any), gaps in knowledge, and will develop AOPs related to these outcomes. One group will focus on methodologies and tools for AOP development and another group will identify putative effect markers based on available AOPs. By providing a framework for the use of NAMs and/or IATAs for high-priority endpoints, the project will have an impact on legislations for chemicals (REACH and CLP), plant protection products and biocides, cosmetic products and food (food additives, food contaminants and food contact materials). **Main expected outputs of the project**

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow rapid mechanistic hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances and to the zero pollution ambition of the green deal and the chemicals strategy for sustainability. Additionally, the methods will be capable of screening of mixtures (AOP

network) thus also contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. AOPs are currently used by different agencies to support for hazard identification. They are the basis for IATA development and for the identification of relevant effect markers

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry because as a screening tool it will be rapid, reliable and cost efficient. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays. Other possible outcomes:

- Develop protocols to optimize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence
- Acquire available and most recent information on toxicity pathways leading to immune and hormonal dysregulation, neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, including chemicals able to interfere with all the identified pathways
- Identify missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting
- Link to the AOP-Wiki database contributing to the AOP- Knowledge Base project launched by OECD

Key words:

AOP, method, immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption, development

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Regulatory uptake will be fostered through the identification of missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting. Innovation in complex data analysis for RA will take place through, namely, the development of protocols aiming to optimize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence. Cooperation with other R&I initiatives is a core element of this project, as there will be a sustained collaboration with PARC activities related to NAMs (task 5.2), systems biology (activities 5.3.1, 5.3.3), and IATA development and risk assessment (task 6.1). Citizen's understanding of chemical RA will be improved through, for instance, the participation of the subgroup Endocrine and Metabolic disruption to SETAC Dublin for a poster presentation.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guidelines tests

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness

WP4, Task 4.1: Human studies and effect markers

WP5, Task 5.2, 5.1: complementarity with experimental studies and NAM development. Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation

WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation, Task 6.2: mixture effects, Task 6.3: text mining

WP7, Task 7.3: data and text mining. Data management plan

WP8, Task 8.2: emerging chemicals

WP9: Training

Links outside PARC

- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- EURION: European Cluster to improve identification of Endocrine Disruptors
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project

- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- OECD - Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA)
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP
- EFSA, ECHA, EEA
- PEPPER

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4 : M14 (June 2023) - Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints Associated Tasks T5.3. Leader of the deliverable UL-LACDR

AD5.5: M12 (April 2023) - Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC. Associated Task: T5.3 Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/ SCIENSANO/INSERM/ Fraunhofer

Project Reports:

Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritization and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12).

Progress report on AOP development in priority endpoints (M36).

Projects Landmarks:

Workshop on AOP methodologies and guidelines; M18

Partners List:

ACES or SU (SE); AU (DK); AUTH (GR); BfG (DE); BPI (GR); DTU (DK); IISPV (ES); Inserm (FR); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); KI (SE); KIT (DE); KU-Leuven (BE); LIST (LU), MUI (AT); NILU (NO); NIPH (NO); NPHC (HU); UG-PL (PL); SDU (DK); Sciensano (BE); UAntwerpen (BE); UGent (BE); UKK/UoC (DE); UIBK (AT); UL-LACDR (NL); UMIL (IT); UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL), Cefas-Defra (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022, M1

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025, M36

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 140 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 42 555 €

A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

No project submitted at present.

A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer

Project Title	PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBK_Kinetics		
Project	Sylvia Escher	ITEM	DE

Manager	sylvia.escher@item.fraunhofer.de		
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.4
Project Id	P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The aim of this project is to develop physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models and to integrate PBK models with AOPs as a basis for quantitative system toxicology. Several conceptual and data gaps will be addressed, such as i) individual human variability in bioavailable concentrations; ii) the impact of the human microbiome on the metabolism of xenobiotics iii) transport across the blood brain barrier; and iv) uptake of inhalable compounds via the respiratory tract. This project will refine and establish in a bottom up approach generic models that describe Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion (ADME) of chemicals in the human organism on the basis of compartments defined by physiological parameters. The developed models will facilitate quantitative in vitro to in vivo extrapolation in a reliable way to produce data of direct value for chemical risk assessment. Compound-specific input data will be derived by the validation and use of in silico and in vitro ADME approaches. For the initial phase, 9 case studies were defined, focusing on the expansion or refinement of physiologically-based kinetic (PBK) models using data-rich model compounds or the generation of predictive PBK models for PARC priority compounds. We aim to establish an initial framework for the application of qIVIVE-PBK models in a regulatory setting, so that a quantitative assessment of hazard will be possible starting from the in vitro hazard identification in e.g., 5.3.1 and 5.3.3. This work will therefore contribute to characterise the hazard of chemicals for specific health effects e.g., in the area of endocrine disruptive compounds (EDC), immunosuppression, DNT and NonGenotoxic carcinogenesis.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will have established innovative approaches to characterize the ADME processes of priority compounds by integrating *in silico* prediction and *in vitro* ADME data into PBK models for oral and inhalation exposures, accounting for uncertainty linked to relevant biological processes.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

By establishing innovative IVIVE-PBK models, this project will have an important impact on the integration of NAM based approaches into regulatory risk assessment. In vivo ADME data are to date available only for few chemicals, as in vivo ADME studies are generally not within the standard regulatory test requirements. Moreover, the extrapolation from the in vitro bench mark concentration to a human equivalent concentration or dose, called qIVIVE, is a key element to NAM based hazard characterization. This will enable users to determine POD for RA based on standardized interpretation and quantitative analysis of NAM data such as omics data. Thereby the project links directly to the project 1 and 2 in WP5.3 in this reporting period. The improved IVIVE_PBK models will also be used for in vitro to in vivo extrapolation in the IATAs developed in WP 6. A close link to WP 6.1 is already under development to assure that the work done in project 3 is applicable, once the IATAs are developed.

In addition, the project will show the applicability and by this will promote use of *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME data in PBK models for predicting human in vivo data. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry since it will allow a cross-sector application of kinetic modelling in a structured manner using similar PBK models.

Finally, this PBK project will enable regulatory implementation of NAM-based approaches and thus the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances, which will benefit public health.

Key words:

in vitro ADME models, in silico ADME models, physiologically based kinetic modelling, oral, inhalation, human equivalent concentration/dose, microbiome metabolism, transport processes

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Next generation risk assessment relies on NAM based hazard identification and characterization. PBK modelling is a central key element of NGRA, as it will be used for quantitative in vitro to in vivo extrapolation (qIVIVE), deriving equivalent plasma and tissue concentrations which serve as a NAM based point of departure for risk assessment.

Project 3 will close data and knowledge gaps in PBK modeling by using case studies. These case studies will be used to i) discuss the workflow for implementing PBK models and qIVIVE into regulatory decision making, ii) outline remaining uncertainties but also advantages compared to the current hazard assessment paradigm iii) to close data gaps for PARC priority compounds. WP5.3.4 core team will connect to other European projects, like e.g. ASPIS and in particular RisHunt3R to promote the development of a harmonized internal exposure framework. Data and modelling work are dedicated to FAIR data principles.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The PBK_kinetic project is linked to the following tasks:

- Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental *in vitro* ADME studies (5.2) → data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case studies to develop and validate IVIVE-PBK approaches.
- Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and PBK models to be integrated into IATAs. → information from PBK_Kinetics can be used for qIVIVE and for qAOP development.
- Task 7.3: Data and text mining → data provision
- WP8: PBK_Kinetics bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of PBK models for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the PBK_kinetic project. Focus will be on in vitro, in silico ADME model data, PBK modelling approaches as well as concepts for tiered testing strategies, starting from simple to more complex testing. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS) like ZeroPM
- OECD – IATA case studies
- EFSA ADME4NGRA
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4 : M14 (June 2023) - Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public

domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints Associated Tasks T5.3. Leader of the deliverable UL-LACDR

AD5.5: M12 (April 2023) - Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC. Associated Task: T5.3 Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/ SCIENSANO/INSERM/ Fraunhofer

Key Project Reports

- Report on *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME models available and needed for PBK case studies on model and priority compounds; M12
- Report on conceptual data gaps in IVIVE-PBK models and the thereof started case studies; M24
- Report on the first uncertainty analyses of case studies; M36

Projects Landmarks:

- Workshop with WP5.1 and 5.2 on data requirement and strategy for their implementation for the proposed case studies; M10
- Case studies defined and data needs and deadlines communicated to all involved partners in 5.1 and 5.2; M14
- Workshop on the applicability of the IVIVE-PBK framework from this project to the needs in WP6.1 and 6.2; M26

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); ETHZ (CHE); IISPV (ES); INERIS (FR); Inserm (FR); ISCIII (ES); ISS (IT); ITEM-Fraunhofer (DE); NVI (NO); UKK/UoC (DE); UIBK (AT); UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL); WU-Tox (NL); EA (UK), AUTH (EL), UFZ (DE), Cefas-Defra (UK), NIPH (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 116 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 144 227 €

WP6 Innovation in regulatory risk assessment – 26 PROJECTS

The overall goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal.

The specific objectives are:

- To deliver IATAs for a selected set of human health effects, developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and proven to be applicable through dedicated case studies
- To perform integrative RA based on internal and external exposure of humans exposed to chemicals and mixtures thereof *via* different routes of exposure, including the workplace
- To evaluate and map current methodologies employed in regulatory RA across sectors
- To identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge
- To develop and foster the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory RA approaches and methodologies
- To develop a framework to assess exposure of and facilitate enforcement of chemicals in articles and materials on the EU-market.

The work in WP6 is divided into four tasks:

T6.1 Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals 4 PROJECTS

The goal of this task is to establish IATAs, to be used for different European regulations on chemical safety for different industry sectors as well as for the CLP Regulation. The IATAs will be developed for a selected set of health effects (e.g. liver toxicity, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption). To provide a strong mechanistic basis for IATA development, existing and newly developed AOPs for selected health effects will be combined into AOP networks. Wherever possible and relevant, Key Event Relationships will be quantitated by applying computational methodologies. IATAs will be developed in close collaboration with stakeholders including OECD and through various cycles of optimisation. In addition, systematic quantitative determination of the uncertainty of application of a combined set of NAMs in an IATA will provide insight in the overall confidence for the application of a selected test battery for respective IATAs.

Fig 8: WP5.3_WP6.1 interactions on AOPs: IATA Development

A6.1.1 Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes – 4 PROJECTS

P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM

Project Title	Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Human Relevance		
Project Manager	Mirjam Luijten Mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl	RIVM	NL
Deputy Project manager	Elisavet Renieri elisavet_renieri@hotmail.com	AUTH	GR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health, which will be developed and evaluated in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders. Key elements of an IATA include Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and new approach methodologies (NAMs). This project is focused on the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathway under study. Such assessment requires a harmonized and accepted workflow. A framework for analysis of mode of action (MOA)/human relevance has been developed in initiatives of WHO/IPCS. In spite of detailed methodological instructions, additionally provided templates and case studies, application of the framework in practice, including the analysis of species concordance, remains challenging. Therefore, this project aims to further optimize an existing draft workflow (v0.1) that was developed based on the WHO/IPCS framework. The refinements will be done in close collaboration with WHO, OECD and other international and regulatory organizations, to ensure its readiness for regulatory implementation. The goal is to establish a harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment and to demonstrate its applicability through dedicated case studies. The resulting assessments will directly feed into IATAs developed in PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output of the project is a pragmatic, harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of both AOPs and its associated NAMs, accompanied by a set of case studies demonstrating how the workflow can be applied.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

A pragmatic, harmonized workflow for the assessment of human relevance of AOPs will inform on which networks of AOPs should be covered by an IATA for human health risk assessment, while assessment of the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathways under study will inform on which NAMs are well suited to be used for a regulatory assessment. Together, this information is highly valuable for end-users and other stakeholders.

Key words

human relevance, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), toxicological mechanisms, New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), weight of evidence, Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is directly linked to the following PARC projects:

- P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen
- P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA-GENTOX_Sciensano
- P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA-STOT_UL-LACDR

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

WP2, A common science-policy agenda: Achievement of regulatory readiness of the workflow for human relevance assessment will require dedicated discussions with various international regulatory bodies, to ensure that regulatory needs are being addressed.

WP3, Synergies, Communication and awareness: The development of a workflow that is ready for regulatory implementation will strongly benefit from raising awareness, proper communication of the (draft) workflow and collecting feedback from stakeholders by WP3.

WP7, Data management plan: see below for the section Data Management.

WP9, Training, laboratory network: Implementation of the workflow in regulatory processes will be greatly facilitated by training courses, developed as a joint activity of WPs 9 and 6.

Links outside PARC

The project will build on, among others, the Mode of Action/Human Relevance framework developed by the WHO/IPCS. It is also closely linked to the OECD AOP programme and IATA case studies. In that context, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen. Additionally, human relevance assessment is a topic of high interest to ILMERAC and the project will benefit from guidance documents on weight of evidence and uncertainty developed by e.g., EFSA.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables/additional deliverables/milestones of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72)
- AD5.5: Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (M24; UL-LACDR)

Project Reports:

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWP.

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Inventory of relevant available approaches and frameworks, including available approaches for uncertainty analysis and weight of evidence, available (M12)

Landmark 2: Case studies for testing and evaluating workflow v0.1 defined (M14)

Landmark 3: Case studies for v0.1 discussed with relevant stakeholders (M28)

Partners List:

AUTH (GR); RIVM (NL); ENSP-UNL (PT); BPI (GR); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); ISS (IT); ; IISPV (ES); LIST (LU); IRSN (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 42 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 48 777 €

P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-ED		
Project	Dries Knapen	UAntwerpen	BE

Manager	Dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be		
Deputy	Miriam Jacobs	UKHSA	UK
Project manager	Miriam.Jacobs@ukhsa.gov.uk		
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of this project within Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for endocrine disruption (ED), one of the health effects that has been prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Criteria for the identification of endocrine disrupting compounds have been stipulated for the Biocidal Products Regulation or the Plant Protection Products Regulation and a guidance document, i.e., “Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 825/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009”, was written to guide identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals to comply with these obligations. In addition, other regulations such as REACH and the Cosmetic regulation also require information on the endocrine disruptive potential of chemicals. The OECD guidance document 150 provides guidance on the application and use of standardised TGs (Test Guidelines) for the evaluation of chemicals for endocrine disruption (2018), which include oestrogen, androgen and steroidogenesis endpoints but this does not provide details of assays. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop IATAs for the identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals both in a human and environmental health context. This will structure, identify key gaps and facilitate direct regulatory application of PARC outcomes. Whilst at the moment there are no standardised *in vitro* assays for thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) (OECD Revised GD150, 2018), standardisation and further review is in progress under the auspices of the OECD, based upon the assays documented (OECD Series on Testing and Assessment 207, 2014). Some of the ED toxicological pathways are considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development on the basis of test method developments and existing data. This is especially the case for THSD, for which the first IATA will be developed, and for anti-androgenic adverse effects, for which a second IATA will be developed. To ensure that the IATAs will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies.

Main expected outputs of the project

The first main expected output is an IATA for THSD. Effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis are considered low-hanging fruit because of the relatively large number of AOPs available (e.g. Noyes et al 2022) or under development for this system and the ongoing project to assess the pre-validated *in vitro* assays for the detection of THSD, conducted at the JRC, the USEPA, and within the EURION cluster. Anti-AR signaling, and metabolic disruption work, following the completion of the EURION projects at the end 2023 will be considered as next priorities.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Regulatory strategies for identifying endocrine disrupting chemicals in line with the advancing legislation in this context are mostly lacking. This project will ultimately enable better regulatory decision making and significantly improve the hazard identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals with the long-term aim to limit exposure and improve human as well as environmental health. The use of predictive methods and NAMs will significantly reduce the need for long-term, low-throughput and costly toxicity tests requiring large numbers of animals, thus contributing to the replacement of animal tests.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), Endocrine disruption (ED), Thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD), Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), Risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The work described in this project is further connected to other WPs in PARC. Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment”, especially with T5.3.2 on AOPs and with T5.2 on NAMs to be used in IATAs. For the evaluation of IATAs through case studies, we will also closely collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4 and WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the used cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to the OECD Task Force on Endocrine Disruptors Testing and Assessment (EDTA), the EURION cluster and the PEPPER platform. It is also linked to work ongoing at OECD in relation to thyroid hormone system assay assessment, AOP development (OECD’s AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (M24; UL-LACDR)

Project Reports:

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWPs.

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: AOP network for ED and associated assays defined (M12)

Landmark 2: First data for ED collected (M18)

Landmark 3: Framework for qAOP for ED defined (M28)

Partners List:

UAntwerpen (Belgium); UKHSA (United Kingdom); MU (Czechia); AUTH (Greece); UGent (Belgium); INSERM (France); UL-LACDR (Netherlands); RIVM (Netherlands); ISS (Italy); DTU (Denmark); SDU (Denmark); LIST (Luxembourg); BPI (Greece); UG-PL (Poland); IISPV (Spain); STAMI (Norway); KI (Sweden); IRFM (Italy); ENSP-UNL (Portugal); Sciensano (Belgium); CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), UU-IRAS (NL), JRC (EU)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 116 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 84 544 €

P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Genotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-GENTOX		
Project Manager 1	Birgit Mertens birgit.mertens@sciensano.be	Sciensano	BE
Project manager 2	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inra.fr	INRAE	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for genotoxicity, one of the health effects that has been prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Moreover, genotoxicity is considered a low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and available test systems. The test strategies for genotoxicity that are in place under the current regulations for the different regulatory frameworks are somewhat similar but often rely on animal testing, and do not integrate NAMs such as Pig-a, Multiflow, ToxTracker or transcriptomic-based gene expression biomarkers. By delivering an IATA, the project aims to move towards the assessment of genotoxicity without the use of animals.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an IATA for genotoxicity that is based on an AOP framework. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a quantification AOP framework for this endpoint. Information on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) will be integrated as well through collaboration with T5.3. The applicability of the IATA will be demonstrated by means of case studies. Overall, this project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of genotoxicity that can be included for future assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for genotoxicity that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to

assess this endpoint without the use of animals. Furthermore, assessment of genotoxic potential is closely linked to assessment of carcinogenic potential due to the strong association between the accumulation of genetic damage and cancer. Hence, this project also directly relates to the ongoing review of the REACH testing requirements to see how they could be amended (if appropriate) to allow identification of carcinogens irrespective of the registration volume band. Where feasible, case studies to test and evaluate the IATA will also address the revised requirements for REACH. Furthermore, the utility and applicability of a shift towards a more quantitative approach for assessment of genetic toxicity hazard will be explored.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), genotoxicity, DNA damage, gene mutations, chromosome damage, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

For T6.1 the project is linked to the three other T6.1 projects in PARC (P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM; P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_Uantwerpen; P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR). To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways. Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for genotoxicity; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5 (e.g., data generated with toxins); c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3) and evaluation of IATA through case studies. Within WP6, the case study *T6.3_CS11: Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches* will be particularly relevant for the mapping of existing AOPs but also for the evaluation of IATA through case studies, we will closely collaborate with T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Integrative models developed in T8.3 of WP8 will be considered as well. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to work done by the HESI Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee (GTTC), on AOP development and Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). It is also linked to work ongoing at OECD, in relation to NAMs for genotoxicity (e.g., ToxTracker and miniaturized versions of the bacterial reverse gene mutation test), AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment are foreseen. The link with the work on AOP development for radiation effects done within the context of the MELODI project will also be investigated. Finally, wherever applicable and relevant, a link to ongoing activities on IATAs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity will be made as well.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (M24; UL-LACDR)

Project Reports

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWP.

Projects Landmarks

Landmark 1: AOP network for genotoxicity and associated assays defined (M12)

Landmark 2: First data for genotoxicity available (M18)

Landmark 3: Framework for qAOP for genotoxicity defined (M28)

Partners List

Sciensano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE),
 UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (GR), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO),
 IRFM (IT), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), WR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 92 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 159 066 €

P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Systemic Target Organ Toxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-STOT		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water b.water@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Joost Beltman j.b.beltman@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for specific target organ toxicity (STOT). The project will initially focus on liver toxicity, and at a later stage, but in parallel, other types of target organ toxicity will be started such as respiratory toxicity. Liver toxicity is the most often observed toxic effect in 90-day studies and also considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and liver test systems. Yet, liver toxicity is complex and involves different end-points that typically have different mechanisms as well as time course for development. An initial focus will be on liver fibrosis as a critical endpoint. In contrast, for respiratory toxicity there is a need for IATA development and implementation/application of scientifically developed in vitro methods. Lung fibrosis is an important human health end-point and we will consider how an IATA for liver fibrosis could be generalized to other target organs, including lung fibrosis.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an IATA for liver toxicity with an initial focus on liver fibrosis that is based on an AOP framework. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a quantification AOP framework for this endpoint. This project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of STOT that can be included for future assessment of systemic toxicity. The case study of the project will demonstrate the applicability of the established IATA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

There is currently no IATA for liver toxicity. The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for liver fibrosis that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this end-point without the use of animals. Moreover, it will move beyond a qualification and also give a quantitative assessment of the involved assays in relation to the adverse outcome.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), systemic toxicity, liver, fibrosis, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

For T6.1 the project is linked to three other projects in T6.1 (P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM ; P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_Uantwerpen; P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano. To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for endocrine disruption; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5; c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3); and c) evaluation of IATA through case studies. For the latter, we will also closely collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

Furthermore, the project is closely linked to the Horizon2020 projects EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (M24; UL-LACDR)

Project Reports

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWP6s and include a report on liver fibrosis case study for interim evaluation of IATAs (M24).

Projects Landmarks

Landmark 1: AOP network for liver fibrosis and associated assays defined (M12)

Landmark 2: First data for liver fibrosis available (M18)

Landmark 3: Framework for qAOP for liver fibrosis defined (M28)

Partners List

UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (GR), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WFSR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 50 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 79 667 €

A6.1.2 Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

This activity is incorporated in the projects listed under A6.1.1.

A6.1.3 Stakeholder engagement

This activity is incorporated in the projects listed under A6.1.1.

T6.2 Integrative exposure and risk assessment - 8 PROJECTS

The aim of this task is to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals *via* multiple sources across regulatory silos and routes during lifetime. Relative contributions of sources and routes will be determined. Living and working environment as well as chemical transfer from soil to water, food, and air and migration from consumer products, articles and materials will be integrated. For estimating and reconstructing chemical exposure through life, accounting for varying exposure scenarios and physiological and biochemical characteristics over time, PBK models will be developed. Simulations of concentrations in target tissues will be linked to AOPs and IATAs. Finally, data availability and methodologies to perform health impact and cost-benefit assessment for prioritised chemicals, exposure routes, windows of exposure, subpopulations, geographical locations, and health outcomes will be improved.

Innovative methods, tools and concepts to perform integrative risk and health impact assessments :
combining data and methods from different approaches and disciplines

Fig 9: W6.2: Risk and health Impact Assessment

A6.2.1 Aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO

Project Title	Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SourcetoDose		
Project Manager	Katleen De Brouwere	VITO	BE
	katleen.debrouwere@vito.be		
Deputy Project manager	Radu Duca	LNS	LU
	radu.duca@lns.etat.lu		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims to model from sources to doses, the human exposure of general population to chemicals, potentially arising from a variety of sources and routes. Sources include different types: environmental sources including 1) emissions from industrial facilities, traffic and households, etc. 2) diffuse environmental sources (e.g., historical soil contamination, water etc), and 3) consumer sources present in our everyday life, (e.g., construction products, household products, etc.) potentially releasing chemicals that may enter our bodies.

It is anticipated that for some source and route of exposure, models do exist, but are (overly) conservative in nature because of their intended uses for screening purposes. However, when it comes to combination of exposures from different sources into an aggregated exposure (and comparison with HBM values) and health impact assessment, realistic external exposure models are crucial, and needed for policy makers (e.g., in view of comparing impact of different policy or risk management options).

This project is connected to the project on aggregate exposure modelling. The scope of this project will be routes and sources for which realistic exposure models are currently lacking. Where models are lacking, they will be developed. Where possible, we will rely on existing models and improve them in order to shift from screening models to higher tier models generating realistic exposure estimates.

This project focus is on modelling as a complementary tool to human biomonitoring, for the general population (occupational exposure is out of scope). Case studies will be tailored toward chemical classes in line with PARC projects (e.g., case studies on PFAS, flame retardants, metals, pesticides).

The ultimate goal is to come up with robust, mechanistic model(s) and tools which are, at the same time relatively simple in use for risk assessors.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Improvement of existing models for generating realistic exposure assessment for selected consumer articles or products, and environmental sources
- Development of new model(s) for routes and sources for which there is currently a lack of models (for selected sources)
- Transcription of the conceptual model(s) to T8.3

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The role of modelling in aggregate exposure assessment is that modelling offers a complementary tool to human biomonitoring to perform chemical risk assessment.

This project will make it possible to end-users to perform risk assessment for chemicals (environment and consumer exposure) covered in this project. It will offer end-users the opportunity 1) to expand the assessment to other groups not included in HBM studies ((e.g. specific age groups, vulnerable groups), 2) to assess the relative contribution of different sources and exposure routes (given that that the models will generate realistic exposure estimates for each source and route) , and 3) to calculate the impact of risk management options (e.g. predicting impact of restrictions, mitigations). The latter can inform policy makers about the most efficient risk management strategies thus allowing for better informed decision making.

Key words: human exposure, modelling, consumer exposure, exposure *via* the environment, realistic exposure modelling, migration, articles

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO5: The project will identify data required for source to dose modelling for priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe. The project will use data and knowledge generated and published by other past and ongoing R&I projects and initiatives.

OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the data and models inventories, studies to fill these gaps may be initiated.

OO8: The project will support the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, since environmental and multisource data are key elements for parameterization and/or verification of source to dose models

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: The project will be developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes regarding source to dose models

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Connection with T4.1 (HBM data from T.4.1 will be used to validate the model outcome)
- Connection with A6.2.1 Interoperability of models for aggregate exposures:
 - gaps identified will steer the priorities in 6.2.1
 - model outcomes generated in this project can be included in aggregate exposure modelling in 6.2.1.
- Connection with T8.3: outcome (model) will be taken up in T8.3
- Project “Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures” (project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES)
- Projects from T8.3

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG), HBM4EU (WP 12), and 7th FP projects (e.g., 4-FUN)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (M12)
- D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

Project Reports and landmarks:

- Scientific developments and results will be part of the annual AD or Deliverable.

Partners List:

VITO (BE); RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); LNS (LU); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT), UoB (UK), IISPV (ES)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 34 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 14330 €

P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse

Project Title	Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Aggregate		
Project Manager	Crépet Amélie amelie.crepet@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	David Vernez david.vernez@unisante.ch	UNISANTE	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

In the context of a compartmentalized view of risk assessment, this project aims to advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. It will help to propose a more integrative risk assessment and management crossing regulatory silos. This project will draw up the strategy to aggregate exposures from multiple sources and routes in considering both general life and occupational exposures. It is divided into three parts. The first one aims to review available models, tools and data and draw a functional design for model connection. The second part is to work on methods and criteria to perform aggregate exposure and the last part is to organize and start the relevant case studies selected from the defined criteria and PARC priorities. Building from current knowledge, this project is an important step to propose advanced aggregate exposures assessment from multiple sources and routes. It will provide a better understanding of the main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life to support effective risk management measures.

Main expected outputs of the project

- The outputs for model interoperability and data inventory part are: selection of models for further analysis, models and tools description with their structural analysis, functional design for model connection for T8.3, data inventory for T7.1 and data gaps to be feed by T4.1 and T4.2. The outputs for methods for aggregate exposure part are: strategy and roadmap for aggregate risk assessment, innovative methods to perform aggregate risk assessment, criteria for prioritisation of case studies

and advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. The outputs for case studies for aggregate exposure part are: selection of relevant case studies of aggregate exposure including general life and occupational exposures, aggregated exposure results and prioritization of main sources and routes of exposure from general life and occupational exposures.

■

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Provide tools to facilitate comparisons between entry routes and exposure situations and, ultimately, prioritize areas for action and prevention. This project will also make it possible to end-users to perform risk assessment from several sources and routes of exposure. It will make possible to account for both general life and work activities in risk assessment. Concrete case studies will be conducted for prioritized chemicals.

Key words: Aggregate exposure, multiple sources, multiple routes, risk mitigations, occupational exposures, general life exposures,

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will develop methods, toolboxes, and organize relevant data to combine exposure from various environments including occupational and general life exposures. In identifying main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life, the output of the project will help to prioritize risk management measures. Training to the new methods and tools will be proposed with T8.3 to the different stakeholders.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is also strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. As example aggregate exposures can be used as input in mixture (P6.2.3) and health impact projects (P6.2.4). The output of the sources to dose (P6.2.1.a) and PBPK projects (P6.2.2.a) can be used as input of this project.

This project will be strongly connected to the T8.3 on integrative models in involving the task leader WR-BIOM. The objective is to deliver the functional design to task T8.3 for its implementation.

The data inventory will be conducted in connection with the T4.1 and T4.2 and the results of the data gap analysis will be discussed with the leaders to see how they can be handled.

A connection with T7.3 on methods to combine data to account for uncertainty will be also done as aggregate exposure can be a good case study.

It can also propose input for training in WP9.

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG). It is also linked to the Scientific Committee Consumer Safety.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (including inventory of databases, models and tools (M12)

D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

Project Reports and landmarks:

- Scientific developments and results will be part of the annual AD or Deliverable.

Partners List: ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), RIVM (NL), VITO (BE), UU (SE), NIOM (PL), INSA (PT), TNO (NL), NIJZ (SI), AU (DK), TTL (FI), RUMC (NL), GeoZS (SI), LNS (LU), ISSeP (BE), CSTB

(FR), EFSA (EU), MU (CZ), WR-BIOM (NL), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), NIPH (NO), KWR (NL), IVL (SE), ISCII (ES), FOPH (CH), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), UOB (UK), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 132 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 86140 €

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH

Project Title	Refinement and development of PBPk models for human risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBPk		
Project Manager	Aude RATIER aude.ratier@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Deputy Project manager	Spyros KARAKITSIOS spyros.karakitsios@gmail.com	AUTH	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.2
Project Id	P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPk) models are essential tools in toxicokinetic modelling and risk assessment as they describe the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion (ADME) processes in the human body. PBPk models are able to focus on the effective dose at the target site, providing a better characterization of the relationship between exposure dose and adverse effects (Andersen, 1995; Verner et al., 2010). Given the growing interest in using PBPk models in the risk assessment process, guidelines for appropriate extrapolations of species, doses, and exposure scenarios have been proposed. The mechanistic basis of PBPk models is well adapted to toxicological risk assessment (US EPA, 2006; IPCS, 2010; OECD, 2021), in particular for dealing with extrapolations inherent to these domains (in vitro to in vivo, laboratory animals to humans, various exposure or dosing schemes, etc.). The HBM4EU project reviewed available PBPk models for several compounds, highlighting a lack of toxicokinetic data for many prioritized compounds and a lack of models for sensitive populations such as pregnant women and their fetuses, newborns, young children, or the elderly. In this PARC project, PBPk models will be refined or developed to address population sub-group sensitivities, integrating multiple exposure routes and sources, and interpreting human biomonitoring data. Different sources of data will be

used (either from literature or from synergies with WP5) for refining or developing PBPK models necessary for the use of internal dose metrics for risk assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

- PBPK models will be refined or developed to address population sub-group sensitivities, integrating multiple exposure routes (oral ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact) and sources (occupational, consumer, and environmental), and new matrices of exposure predictive of specific exposure (e.g., hair or meconium for newborns). These models will be applied to biomonitoring data for one chemical or mixtures and will help to interpret them. The experimental needs with WP5 will be identified, and QSAR models will be used to obtain parameters related to kinetics and partitioning. The models developed in this task will be interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with open platform used for risk assessment
-

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

As PBPK models are tools used to support risk assessors and managers, it is essential to provide models that are adapted to their requirements and that follow the most up-to-date guidance, e.g., the OECD document on the characterisation, validation and reporting of PBK models for regulatory purposes (Series on Testing and Assessment No. 331, ENV/CBC/MONO(2021)1). This project within PARC will focus on the refinement or development of PBPK models for prioritized compounds and mixtures, e.g., with limited information, sensitive populations, and the aggregation of the various exposures. The models that will be proposed will be made interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with other modules in integrative open platforms used for risk assessment.

Key words: PBK models; multi-route exposures; lifelong exposure; sensitive human sub-groups; metabolic interactions; barrier models.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO5: The project will identify models for priority chemicals and sub-groups of population for which refine RA is needed across Europe. The project will use data and knowledge generated and published by other past and ongoing R&I projects and initiatives.

007: Based on data gaps that appear from the PBK models inventory, studies to fill these gaps may be initiated.

0010: Implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite. PBK models will be developed or implemented under the FAIR principles.

0012: PBK models will be developed to answer or to suggest innovative concepts for RA, and will be available on toolboxes to promote their acceptability.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Activities undertaken in WP5 (Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3) for the generation of toxicokinetic data and the development of AOP, WP8 (Task 8.3) for the model integration in an open platform, WP4 for the availability of HBM data.

Other T6.2 projects that aim to link internal and external exposures from multiple sources and for mixtures:

- Strategy for aggregate exposure in order to confirm external exposure assessment with HBM data.
- New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures

Links outside PARC

Bisphenols, PFAS, pesticides, metals and mycotoxins have been priority compounds among the HBM4EU project and modelling efforts, as well as review of existing models and identification of gaps has been carried out.

Some compounds are also endocrine disruptor compounds that are studied in the EURION cluster, specifically in the OBERON project.

Links to the exposome projects, such as ATHLETE.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.4: Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life and for in-vitro-to-in-vivo extrapolation (M12)

D6.2: 1st Report on innovative methods based on PBK models (M36)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Refinement of existing/development of PBPK models towards multi-route and lifelong exposure (M36)

Report 2: Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPK models in the risk assessment process (M48)

Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: INERIS (France), AUTH (Greece), IISPV (Spain), ANSES (France), RIVM (Netherlands), SLU (Sweden), NIPH (Norway), VITO (Belgium), WR-BIOM (Netherlands), WR-WFSR (Netherlands), IRFM (Italy), IVL (Sweden), TNO (Netherlands)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 134 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 53850 €

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM

Project Title	New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RealLifeMixtures		
Project Manager	Jacob Van Klaveren jacob.van.klaveren@rivm.nl	RIVM	Netherlands
Deputy Project manager	Amélie Crépet Amelie.crepet@anses.fr	Anses	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.3
Project Id	P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The mixture concerns are reflected in the prioritisation process and were ranked as a high priority for many stakeholders and Member States. Furthermore, there is a need to regulate chemicals in such a manner that potential mixture effects are already considered in the registration or authorisation process (prospective risk assessment of mixtures).

The project will build on scientific progress made on mixture risk assessment, by international organisations (such as EFSA, EEA and ECHA, EC-JRC, OECD), regarding hazard-based grouping of chemical and statistical approaches developed in previous project such as Euromix, HBM4EU and the EHEN exposome projects. The project combines risk assessment and epidemiological approaches to support scientific needs from Member States, DG SANTE and DG Environment. It will integrate the needs identified in the Chemical Strategy and the linked EC Policy Document SWD 250 final STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Progress report on the assessment and management of combined exposures to multiple chemicals (chemical mixtures) and associated risks.

The main objectives of the projects are to:

- Build a common strategy to perform human risk assessment to chemical mixtures
- Integrate exposome and risk assessment approaches
- Prioritize real-life mixtures from HBM data
- Develop hazard and kinetic information on prioritized mixtures
- Study the link between mixture biomarkers of exposures and effects
- Perform mixture risk assessment for prioritized mixtures

Main expected outputs of the project

- Prioritisation methods and/or grouping approaches to select the components to be considered;
- Options to use (eco)toxicity and exposure data on the single components to predict mixture hazard and/or risks, through component-based approaches based on dose additivity;
- Tiered approaches bringing together advances made for mixtures in regulatory risk assessment and in the field of exposome to refine the assessment depending on the availability and quality of exposure and hazard data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- EFSA, ECHA and EEA in future scientific opinions on risk assessment of mixtures
- EU Member States in communication towards stakeholders and the general public
- Industry addressing the risk of mixtures when assessing the risk of new chemicals before entering the market

The project includes training activities for end-users that will be organised by WP3 and WP9.

Key words: Mixture, HBM, co-exposure, health effects, AOP, RPF, PBPK, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Real-life mixture project will fill-in basic science gaps to explore how human bio-monitoring can be used in practice for mixture risk assessment and how to combine different sources of exposure in one exposure estimate.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project has strong connection with:

1. WP1 : management and indicators
2. WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
3. WP3: communication and dissemination of results
4. WP4:
 - Derivation of health-based HBM guidance values
 - Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys

5. WP5: further hazard characterisation for mycotoxins, PFAS and heavy metals
6. WP7: link with external data sources (e.g., IPCHEM, Tox data or EFSA data)
7. WP8 : task 8.3 integrative models

This project is strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. For, example aggregate exposures (T6.2.1) can be used as input in this project and development from PBPK projects (T6.2.2) will be directly applied in the context of mixture. This project is cooperating with T4.1 (generation of HBM data), WP7 (data formatting and data organisation) and T8.3 (integrative model development).

Links outside PARC

8. HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
9. EuroMix legacy and EuroMix follow-up: make use of the MCRA software developed in the EuroMix project
10. Green Deal projects addressing PFAS and mixtures (e.g., awarded projects as PANORAMIX for mixtures) and SPRINT (pesticides).
11. EFSA RACEMIC Roadmap for the
12. OECD activity effect biomarkers/AOPs

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (M36)

AD6.5. Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures (M12)

AD6.Y2 and AD6.Y4: it is planned to have an additional deliverable/deliverable each year

Project Reports:

Scientific developments and results will be described in Deliverable 6.3 and the added annual deliverables

Several scientific publications on the case studies

Oral lectures

Projects Landmarks: Discussions with regulators from DG SANTE, EC-JRC and EFSA and use of the MCRA Integrated Risk Assessment - Dashboard including the risk assessment based on HBM data (M24)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), UGR (ES), DTU (DK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIH (ES), IVL (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU Recetox (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), RUMC (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), Swiss SECO (CH), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UGPL (PL), UGR (ES), UNIPD (IT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), INRAE (FR), KWR (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), UNIVIE (AT), IRFM (IT), IPA (DE), INRAE (FR)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 228 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 113 788 €

A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators – 4 PROJECTS

P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO

Project Title	Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals		
Project	HIADDataAvailability		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
	jurgen.buekers@vito.be		
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO		

* The project has been broken at M66 (that corresponds to the last landmark of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then then this project could go on until M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including variation per geographical location and socioeconomic status), health outcomes (based on mode of action and dose-response data from toxicological as well as epidemiological studies), relative risk, disease incidence or prevalence, and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform Health impact assessment (HIA) for chemical exposures prioritized in PARC. However, data required to perform EBD or HIA are often incomplete. This project will evaluate and increase the availability of data for EBD or HIA for PARC priority substances for specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups, health outcomes etc. Increased availability of suitable data for EBD or HIA calculations for specific exposure scenarios will facilitate health impact assessments to be used by regulators for evaluation and prioritization exercises. This task supports the 1st and 3rd flagship of the Zero Pollution Action being reducing health inequalities as pollution has no equal impact across society and better monitor the impact of chemicals on our health and progress towards pollution relevant targets set under the ZPA and CSS.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment. Together with results of the project on ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’.

Main expected outputs of the project

The inventory and collection or generation of data required for health impact assessment of chemicals and exposure scenarios (specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups etc.) prioritized in PARC will be a recurring activity, to be initiated for a selected set of chemicals and populations every two years starting from PARC year 1.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from

chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Health impact assessment (HIA), data gaps

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO5: The project will identify data required for EBD or HIA calculations for priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe that are generated and published by other past and ongoing projects and initiatives.

OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the data inventory, exposure or hazard data generation and derivation of population-specific exposures may be initiated.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Measured or modelled internal and external exposure data will be collected in cooperation with WP3, WP4, WP8 and other T6.2 activities and with support from WP7
- Exposure-effect data may be generated by WP4 (epidemiological studies) and in WP5 (toxicity studies)
- T4.1.3 and WP9 will be consulted for information on health data registers
- Projects inside PARC :
 - T6.2.4 Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - T6.2.4 Case studies on health impact assessment
 - T6.2.4 Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU and NHANES for internal exposure data (*link via VITO, UU-IRAS, ANSES*)
- ATHLETE, EXPANSE, HEALS for exposure data (*link via ANSES*)
- EHEN for exposome data (*link via UU-IRAS*)
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network (*link via Sciansano*)
- EU health information projects (e.g., PHIRI, TEHDAS)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)
- D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Project Reports:

- Report 1: Approach for and results of derivation of population-specific exposures (e.g. stratified by SES, spatio-temporal variations) (M24)
- Report 2: Approach for and results of exposure modelling to fill data gaps for prioritized data-poor chemicals (M24)
- Report 3: Approach for and results of derivation of exposure-effect associations (M24)

Projects Landmarks:

- None identified at present

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); ISSeP (BE); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); NIPH (NO); NLZOH (SI); OI (SI); RUMC (NL); Sciansano (BE);

STAMI (NO); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Expected Costs (M1-M81):

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 40 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 18360 €

P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIAMethod		
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl	UU-IRAS	NL
Deputy Project manager	Jurgen Buekers jurgen.buekers@vito.be	VITO	BE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS		

* The project has been broken at M66 (that corresponds to the last landmark of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then then this project could go on until M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Data on exposure, exposure-effect relations, health outcomes, relative risk, and demographics can be used for burden of disease (BoD) calculations, analytical Health Impact Assessment (HIA), cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis for chemical exposures. Several aspects of HIA methodologies can be improved to reduce uncertainties in HIA calculations. The methodological improvements of HIA calculations to be realized via this project will reduce the uncertainties in health impact assessment and allow the use of a broader range of data as input for HIA calculations. This will improve the usability of HIA calculations by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises. This is especially useful in the context of the EU Green Deal, particularly the Zero Pollution Ambition policy in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, which aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposure.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment. Together with results of the project on ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’.

Main expected outputs of the project

Facilitation of burden of disease (BoD) calculations, analytical HIA, cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis and improved confidence in results due to further development and

improvement of methods to assess e.g., exposure-effect associations, dynamics in exposure and mixture risks.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Health impact assessment (HIA), methodologies, uncertainty

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3: Methodological improvements developed in this project may be incorporated in harmonized approaches for EBD and HIA calculations.

OO4: Reduction of uncertainty in EBD and HIA calculations will improve the usability of results by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises.

OO5: Information exchange and collaborations with other networks and initiatives in the area of EBD and HIA will be established.

OO7: Based on methodological issues and uncertainties that are identified via this project, methodological improvements will be developed and implemented during the course of PARC.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: Methods developed in this project may be disseminated inside and outside of PARC via training and exchange initiatives.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- P6.2.4.c: Case studies on health impact assessment
- P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- T6.2.4: Exposure through life
- T6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity
- T4.1: General population survey, Targeted surveys, Occupational surveys
- T5.3: projects identifying effect biomarkers

Links outside PARC

- HERA project: Guidelines for health impact assessment (HIA) of environmental factors
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network
- EPHOR: methodology for exposure dynamics (falling risk curves) and for appropriately adding effects estimates of correlated exposures
- HEALS, ICARUS, EXPANSE: ABM models for estimating the expected effect of environmental interventions

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)
- D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Project Reports:

- Report 1: Overview of current frameworks and methodologies of HIA for chemical exposure and associated uncertainties (M24)

- Report 2: Weight-of-evidence (WoE) approach for selection of exposure-effect functions including information from epidemiological, toxicological and mechanistic studies (M24)
- Report 3: Approach for incorporation of effect biomarker measurements as surrogate markers for toxicity (M24)
- Report 4: Overview of current methodologies, indicators and frameworks used for cost analysis related to health impact of chemical exposures (M30)

Projects Landmarks:

- Landmark 1: Selection of methodological improvements to be addressed in PARC and/or to be implemented in case studies and indicator development (M18-30-42-54-66)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); RIVM (NL); Sciensano (BE); UBA (DE); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Expected Costs (M1-M81):

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 46 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 11 860 €

P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Case studies on health impact assessment		
Project	HIACaseStudies		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
Deputy Project manager	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		
Project manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
Project manager	jurgen.buekers@vito.be		
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Environmental burden of disease (EBD) analyses are quantitative assessments of the burden of disease (including morbidity, mortality and financial costs) in a specific population that is attributable to environmental factors such as chemicals. Health impact assessment (HIA) is a tool to estimate the health impact of a policy or program on population health. EBD and HIA analyses for current chemical exposure of EU populations can be used to compare the burden of disease attributable to different environmental exposures and to prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken. Case studies will be performed for PARC priority substances.

Based on results of the T6.2.4 projects on data availability and methodological improvements, a selection of case studies will be performed to calculate the health impact and risk/benefit or cost/benefit scenarios for chemical substances, classes or mixtures, adverse health effects and exposed populations prioritized in PARC, using existing data and/or data generated in PARC. The results of the case studies will also feed into the T6.2.4 project ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’.

Main expected outputs of the project

In year 1, criteria for selection of case studies to be implemented will be defined (e.g., availability of required data, part of the population exposed above health-based guidance values, possibility for EU-wide assessment, ..) and the case studies to be initiated in year 2 will be selected and designed. In order to define the chemicals and exposure scenarios addressed in the case studies, a risk ranking exercise may be conducted based on evidence-based semi-quantitative methodologies. Prioritization of case studies will take the preferences of key stakeholders into account, across priority societal domains, quantified through multi-criteria decision analysis, and will be done in consultation with WP2 and PARC boards. The selection, design, and performance of case studies will be recurring activities during the course of PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), health impact assessment (HIA), case studies

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3: A prioritization framework is developed as part of this project for selection of case studies related to EBD and HIA calculations to be implemented during the course of PARC.

OO4: The project will increase the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases. This will support policy makers in the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and as such in the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health.

OO6: Increased understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases will support communication to citizens and increase their awareness about risks of chemical exposures.

OO7: Prioritization and selection of case studies will be a recurring activity to develop annual working plans during the course of PARC.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 for prioritization
- WP3 for stakeholder consultation and communication
- Use of existing data in cooperation with WP3 and data generated in WP4, WP5 and other T6.2 activities
- Data sharing options and integrative model tools provided by WP7 and WP8
- Projects inside PARC:
 - P6.2.4.a: Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - P6.2.4.b: Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators

- *Projects from other WPs/Tasks to be identified*

Links outside PARC

Projects generating quantitative chemical exposures and effects data e.g. ATHLETE, EXPANSE, NHANES, HEALS, NEUROSOME

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

AD6.6 (AWP Y1) Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC [M12]

Project Reports:

- Report 1: Framework for case study selection (criteria, weighing, documentation, ranking) (M12)
- Report 2: Reporting on design and results of case studies for health impact assessment (M24-36)

Projects Landmarks:

- Landmark 1: Prioritization of case studies for human health impact assessment to be started in 2023 (M12)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); BPI (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); KI (SE); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); RUMC (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Expected Costs (M1-M81):

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 29 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 3200 €

P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO

Project Title	Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIAIndicators		
Project Manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Indicators related to exposure, risk and health impact of chemical exposure support national and European

policy makers and can complement and support monitoring frameworks for eg. the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Strategy, and the 8th Environment Action Programme (EAP).

The suitability of one indicator over another depends on the policy questions that need to be answered, the availability and quality of data, the uncertainties of each indicator, and on the availability of resources and expertise. Indicators applying generally to detrimental effects of chemicals range from attributable cases to DALYs/QALYs and external costs. When insufficient data for health impact analysis are available, exceedance of health-based guidance values (RCR, MOE) can be used to indicate which part of the population is exposed to levels above such guidance values as a measure of potential health impact.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment and will interact with the three other projects: ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, and ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’.

Main expected outputs of the project

An inventory of different types of existing risk and health impact indicators for exposure to chemical (single, combined, aggregated, ...) will be made in year 1, followed by a proposal for development of (complementary) indicators based on PARC data and results (including outcomes of the T6.2 projects on data availability and methodological improvements). A selection of indicators integrating dynamic exposure and hazard data and accounting for variability in the population and for uncertainties will be developed in subsequent years, to assess the health impact of specific exposure scenarios (including between- and within-person variance estimates, and dynamics of population exposure and health risk via combining monitoring data with exposure trends as a function of specific socio-economic parameters that condition the level of population exposure per route and pathway).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S) CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations. Indicators related to health impact of PARC priority substances can be developed to support policymakers.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), health impact assessment (HIA), indicators

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3: Prioritization and selection of indicators to be developed during the course of PARC is part of this project.

OO4: Development of exposure, risk, health impact and cost indicators will increase the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases and support policy makers in the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and as such in the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health.

OO5: Information exchange and collaborations with other networks and initiatives in the area of EBD and HIA will be established.

OO6: Development of indicators will support communication to citizens and increase their awareness about risks of chemical exposures.

OO7: Prioritization and selection of case studies will be a recurring activity to develop annual working plans during the course of PARC.

OO9: Calculation and visualization tools for risk and health impact assessment may be developed in a later stage in this project.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will

generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: Indicator development applied in this project may be disseminated inside and outside of PARC via training and exchange initiatives.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Cooperation with T1.3 for the Partnership monitoring framework, WP2 for prioritization and policy uptake, and WP3 for communication
- Exchange of data and computation and visualization tools in collaboration with WP7 and Task 8.3.
- Projects inside PARC:
 - T6.2.4 Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - T6.2.4 Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - T6.2.4 Case studies on health impact assessment

Links outside PARC: None identified at present.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Project Reports:

- Report 1: Inventory of existing indicator types of relevance for PARC (M12)
- Report 2: Risk and health impact indicators developed under PARC and their policy implications (M42)

Projects Landmarks:

- Landmark 1: Proposal for indicators for risk and health impact to be developed in PARC (M13)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); OI (SI); Sciensano (BE); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Expected Costs (M1-M81):

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 23 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 2350 €

T6.3 Review of risk assessment methodologies - 3 PROJECTS

Review of current regulatory RA methodologies within and across relevant chemical sectors will be performed through a series of case studies. Effectiveness of the methodologies will be reviewed. The case studies will provide science-based support for method development, identify R&I needs as well as suggest improvements and harmonisation opportunities. For the first years, the case studies will focus on two areas: substance and effect specific reviews and use of tools, criteria, and methods. Thereafter the focus areas will be evaluated, and either be further analysed through additional case studies or, if relevant, replaced with new focus areas. Final conclusions and recommendations based on the case studies performed will be generated, also considering the EU-wide relevance.

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviewers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU

Project Title	Review of substance-specific risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SubstanceRA		
Project Manager	Marlene Ågerstrand Marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se	Stockholm University	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Olwenn Martin olwenn.martin@ucl.ac.uk	University College London	United Kingdom
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

There is a significant number of EU legislations in force that deal with chemicals directly or indirectly. These rules have been developed at different points in time and for different purposes. Attempts have been made to harmonize and streamline different parts of the regulatory system. Nevertheless, the regulatory system for risk assessment is still scattered across different laws and agencies, and between EU and national levels. This has led to a situation where there are inconsistencies between the different regulatory frameworks. Meeting the concerns about inconsistencies and inefficiency requires a move towards a more holistic approach. This is in line with the foreseen development towards a One Substance One Assessment approach.

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability sets the objective to move towards ‘one substance, one assessment’ approach by improving efficiency, effectiveness, coherence and transparency of the delivery of safety assessments of chemicals across all relevant legislation.

Case studies will be performed to review substance-specific assessments to understand the differences and similarities based on intended use, and subsequent implications, across legislations. The case studies will evaluate opportunities for improving particular aspects of the risk assessment of chemicals. This will include aspects such as data availability and/or data sharing mechanisms, methodologies for hazard and exposure assessment, and assessment of the effectiveness of potential mitigation measures considering the impact on the environment and safety of the consumer.

The project currently contains case studies on coordination needs towards a ‘one substance one assessment’ approach looking at specific substances (case study CS12_MethodOSOA_SU), plastic additives (case study CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL), and substances with biocidal properties (case study CS14_BiocidesRA_SU). Descriptions of the case studies included in the project are available in Annex I.

Main expected outputs of the project

An analysis of how to contribute to the harmonization or consolidation of requirements, guidance, and practices, and move towards a ‘one substance – one assessment’ approach in the EU.

Mapping of relevant legislation linking to functions of additives in specific polymers for various intended use, including a report describing current regulatory processes in relevant legislation, analysing

commonalities and differences and justification thereof, as well as barriers and opportunities for harmonisation, and recommendations for policymakers.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcomes of this project may serve as a ground for adjustments of the relevant regulations. The identification of dissimilarities in testing requirements and hazard assessments of substances depending on specific uses will offer valuable information for the implementation and potential impacts of the One Substance One Assessment approach on regulations targeting specific uses of chemicals. Further, the potential barriers and opportunities, and available methods, for harmonisation in a systematic way will be presented. The analysis of the justification for risk management measures will reveal implicit or explicit value judgment that may inform the development and refinement of the essential use criteria.

Keywords: One Substance One Assessment, harmonisation, biocides, plastic, polymer, additives, essential use, circularity

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO4, OO7, and OO9 by generating knowledge on substance-specific RAs performed across regulatory frameworks and thus informing and supporting the development and use of new risk assessment approaches and methods, regulatory processes, and policy developments (OO4, OO7). The project will be performed in close collaboration with authorities and agencies to promote and facilitate the uptake of the results in RA and regulatory contexts and will provide input to the design and implementation of projects in other Tasks and WPs related to the regulations and aspects reviewed (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for RA (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP2: Prioritizations of chemical substances.

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Various initiatives related to the issue of additives in polymers may be underway in European institutions such as the Commission, EFSA or JRC. Being alert to such developments, particularly if they are not widely advertised by responsible institutions could avoid the duplication of efforts or identification of synergies.

WP6: Potential interactions identified within WP6 that need to be explored further; Project 6.2.1.a Source-to-dose models, Activity 6.4.3 Comprehensive review and application of databases in materials.

WP7: Data management pla

WP8: Can inform case use studies for SSbD criteria (task 8.1).

Links outside PARC:

Work currently undertaken under the auspices of the Food Packaging Forum may potentially be of interest, specifically the FCCMigex database (<https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/fccmigex>) or other tools available from <https://www.plastiverse.org/tools>. The project will also take note of the Plastic additives initiative by ECHA 2016-2018 (Plastic additives initiative - ECHA (europa.eu)).

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group One Substance One Assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project

contributes:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42.
 Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81.
 Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42.

Expected Project Reports:

- R1. Publication of case study 1 (CS 12) - M15
- R2. Publication comparing regulation of relevant biocides (CS14) - M15
- R3. Publication of case study 2 (CS12) - M27
- R4. Publication of case study 3 (CS12) - M27
- R5. Publication on impact analysis (CS14) - M27
- R6. Publication/ report on mapping of relevant legislation and description of current regulatory processes (CS13) - M27
- R7. Publication of case study 4 (CS12) - M39
- R8. Doctoral thesis (CS12) - M39

The results will be published in a number of articles submitted for publication in international peer-reviewed journals.

Expected Project Landmarks:

None identified at present.

Partners List:

SU (SE), UCL (UK), Sciensano (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 31 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 5 600 €

P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI

Project Title	Review of effect-specific risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EffectRA		
Project Manager	Dimitra Nikolopoulou d.nikolopoulou@bpi.gr	BPI	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Emma Westerholm Emma.Westerholm@kemi.se	KEMI	SE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P.6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Chemical risk assessments are currently performed under various regulatory frameworks and at different points in time by responsible EU agencies, scientific committees, expert groups, or Commission

departments. The European Green Deal and Commission Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (COM(2020) 667 final, Brussels, 14.10.2020) highlight the need for innovation in regulatory risk assessment to rapidly and effectively identify chemicals with hazardous properties for human health and the environment through a simpler “one substance one assessment” process. The project will be implemented through case studies reviewing risk assessment methodology concerning specific endpoints that are highlighted as priority in the EC Chemicals Strategy. Currently, this includes endocrine disruption (case studies CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB, CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI CS18_ED-classes_BPI), skin sensitisation (case study CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH), genotoxicity and carcinogenicity (case study CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS), and developmental neurotoxicity (case study CS15_DNT_SU). Descriptions of the case studies included in the project are available in Annex I.

The case studies will review current regulatory practices across regulatory areas in EU. The goal is to evaluate and suggest opportunities for improving and harmonising particular aspects of risk assessment methodology, including bridging legislative inconsistencies.

Over the past few years, chemicals with endocrine disrupting (ED) properties have been identified under different regulatory frameworks, including Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 (Plant protection Products Regulation, PPPR), Regulation (EU) 528/2012 (Biocides Products Regulation, BPR), Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH) and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 (Cosmetic Products Regulation, CPR). Whilst all of these pieces of legislation endorse the WHO/IPCS (2002)⁴ definition for an endocrine disruptor, different methodology and approaches are followed for ED assessments of chemicals. The EFSA/ECHA Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009⁵ has been endorsed⁶ to provide harmonised scientific criteria for the identification of pesticides with ED properties but not for chemicals regulated under REACH or the CPR. Moreover, the use of experimental animals for safety assessment is fully prohibited under CPR since March 2013. The new hazard classes on ED properties are expected to substantially contribute to harmonization in the identification of ED chemicals across EU.

Skin sensitization is a systemic repeat dose toxicity caused by chemicals leading to permanent changes in the immune system and potentially chronic skin disease in case exposure continues. At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. Skin sensitization may lead to permanent skin disease, affect quality of life, and impair work ability. The economic expenses on a European level in considerable, alone skin sensitization due to fragrance ingredients are estimated to cost 11 -16 billion Euro/year.

Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity are essential components of human health safety assessment. Although various EU and international regulations are open to the use of approaches different from standard toxicology tests on animals, such as in vitro short-term tests and structure-activity based methodologies, today's alternative strategies generally rely on paradigms that fail to detect the full spectrum of genotoxic and carcinogenic chemicals.

An additional case will evaluate conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) studies considered under different legislative frameworks for regulation of plant protection products, biocides, food contact materials and chemicals under REACH, depending on data availability.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Development of specific criteria for evaluation of non-validated in vitro methods to facilitate ED assessments across regulatory frameworks ; identification of methodological differences in the assessment of substances with ED activity among legislative frameworks on cosmetics and on other chemicals; development of guidance on the added value of NAMs in classification of chemicals for endocrine disrupting properties under the new CLP criteria and for shifting away from animal testing through a WoE approach.
- Evaluation of the performance and efficacy of current legislation on skin sensitisation assessment, including practices for mixtures of skin sensitizers; identification of knowledge gaps and suggestions for improvements in risk assessment.

- Development of protocols and recommendations summarising the main directions for increasing the regulatory acceptance of QSAR-related methodologies in genotoxicity and carcinogenicity risk assessment.
- Advance the understanding of overall compliance in guideline DNT studies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to assist Member State Regulatory Authorities, EU agencies, Scientific Committees, Expert Groups, relevant Commission Departments and the Industry in adopting harmonised risk assessment methodologies on selected human health effects:

- Contribute to a harmonized way of using existing and emerging NAMs for risk assessment of compounds with potential ED concerns.
- Remove current bottlenecks regarding acceptance of non-validated *in vitro* ED test methods; provide confidence in risk assessors and consistency in the assessment of data from non-validated ED test methods for use in WoE assessment.
- Contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for endocrine disruption taking into consideration all available methods and tools.
- Contribute to the development of harmonised risk assessment methodology on skin sensitisation.
- Identify the most relevant gaps and inconsistencies in current legislation for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity risk assessment, highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization.
- Support the integration of information from different sources (e.g., NAMs, AOPs) identifying their best placement into genotoxicity and carcinogenicity risk assessment detailing and addressing the underlying uncertainties.
- Identify areas where further development of legislation or regulatory practice is needed regarding the performance of DNT studies highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization to ensure a high level of protection for human health.

Key words: risk assessment; endocrine; *in vitro*; skin sensitization; (Q)SAR; genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, DNT, reliability, relevance, NAMs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO4, OO7, and OO9 by reviewing current methodology for chemical risk assessment across different regulatory frameworks with focus on specific priority endpoints, i.e., endocrine disruption, skin sensitisation, genotoxicity and carcinogenicity and skin sensitisation. The project aims to identify knowledge gaps and areas where harmonisation is mostly needed and provide recommendations for increasing regulatory acceptance of NAMs in chemicals risk assessment (OO4, OO7). This outcome is expected to provide input to related projects on the use of NAMs and IATA development towards the transition to next generation risk assessment (OO7, OO9). Identification of potential limitations in the use of NAMs is expected to inspire the design of new projects and case studies under different WPs within PARC (OO4, OO9). Collaboration with regulatory agencies and authorities is expected to promote and facilitate the uptake of results in the regulatory context (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for risk assessment (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

The following links of this project to other PARC activities are identified:

- WP2: Contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment; contribute to the link between research and regulatory science.
- WP3: Foster synergies and collaborations with other projects at national, EU and international level.
- WP5: Provide feedback on assessment criteria of in vitro studies available in the open literature that could be used to assist identification of regulatory gaps for priority compound testing; DNT activities.
- WP5/Task 5.3: Assist the development of new AOP(s) for non-genotoxic carcinogenesis.
- WP6/Task 6.1: Provide feedback for the evaluation of in vitro studies for use in IATAs development on EDs and assist the development of quantitative networks of AOPs and IATA for genotoxicity.
- WP6/Task 6.4/Project 6.4.1: Provide feedback on the additive or synergistic effects of mixtures of skin sensitisers.
- WP6/Task 6.4/Project 6.4.2: Developing and fostering the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory approaches.
- WP7: Align with data management plan
- WP9: Scheduled training activities

Links outside PARC:

- Endocrine Disruption: Links with the EURION cluster, the work performed by the OECD Performance Based Test Guidelines (OECD PBTG), the OECD IATA Case Study Project, the ABU Project, Better use of academic data (CSS), the activities of the CARACAL Subgroup on Endocrine Disruptors (CASG ED), one-substance one-assessment.
- Skin sensitisation: Collaboration with University of Copenhagen on immune reactions to skin sensitizers, ongoing activities in France, Germany and Ireland on the potential need for regulatory action on skin sensitizers in consumer mixtures, workshop in Brussels on Application of the EU Cosmetics Regulation and relevant OSH Directives for the safe use of cosmetic products (25/10/2022), workshop in Basel on model development for quantitative risk assessment for skin sensitising pesticides (August 2022) by the State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) - Chemicals and Occupational Health, and the Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology together with an international scientific organising committee.
- Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity: Links with OECD (Chemicals and Biotechnology Committee (OECD / EHS Prog.), QSAR Assessment Framework project, IATA case studies project, QSAR Toolbox Management Group, Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics EAGMST (AOP Programme), WG on revision of Genotoxicity Test Guidelines); ECHA (Member State Committee (MSC), Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC), Risk Management and Evaluation (RiME+) platform, Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL)); and EFSA (Expert Panel on Food Additives and Flavouring (FAF), Working Group on Genotoxicity of the Scientific Committee, Working Group on Technological Additives of the Expert Panel on Feed Additives and Products (FEEDAP), and working groups on genotoxicity and toxicology).
- Developmental neurotoxicity: Links with EFSA, ECHA, EU Commission.

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group One Substance One Assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

The following project reports are proposed (may be subject to change depending on project outcomes):

- Report 1: Comprehensive list and report on in vitro test methods assessing prioritised ED endpoints (M12, BPI).
- Report 2: Report and database on existing in vitro assays, in silico tools and read-across approaches for ED assessment of EATS modalities under PPPR, BPR, REACH and CPR (M12, BPI).
- Report 3: Mapping of regulatory practices for skin sensitizers, including the handling of mixtures (M18, REGIONH)
- Report 4: Methodological differences between the legislative frameworks of cosmetics and chemicals, with emphasis on substances with ED activity (M20, VUB).
- Report 5: Systematic review on skin sensitisation risk assessment methodologies (M30, REGIONH)
- Report 6: Provide possible solutions, shifting away from animal use to a WoE approach which combines both existing and newly emerging NAMs making use of new technology, preferentially based on human material (M32, VUB).
- Report 7: Report on harmonised scientific criteria for consideration of data from non-validated in vitro methods for ED assessment across legislations (M36, BPI).
- Report 8: Report on the added value of NAMs (in vitro, in silico, read-across) to delineate human/population relevance aspects that are critical in deciding on classification of chemicals either as Category 1 or 2 for ED properties under the new CLP criteria (M36, BPI).
- Report 9: Mapping of strategic regulatory needs and strategies to fill them. Case story on skin sensitisation risk assessment: success and failures (M36, REGIONH)
- Report 10: Evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies (M36, SU).
- Report 11: Main outcomes of the analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches (M45-M48), (ISS)
- Report 12: Conclusions and recommendations on skin sensitisation risk assessment methodology (M54, REGIONH)

Findings from this project are expected to lead to several peer-reviewed scientific publications and a PhD thesis on risk assessment methodologies for skin sensitisation.

Expected Project Landmarks

- Landmark 1: Availability of a sufficiently high number of original DNT study reports is a necessary prerequisite for the successful performance in the evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies (M10, SU).
- Landmark 2: End-of systematic review on risk assessment methodologies for skin sensitization (expected M30). The contents will be decisive on whether a recommendation for a common risk assessment model is possible or this is not possible at this stage due to knowledge gaps (M30, REGIONH).

Partners List:

REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), EAA (AT), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 64 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 34 090€

A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods – 1 PROJECT

P6.3.2.a Y1_ToolsRA_SU

Project	Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in risk assessment
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Title			
Project	ToolsRA		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Jussi Reinikainen jussi.reinikainen@syke.fi	Finnish Environment Institute, SYKE	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Marlene Ågerstrand Marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se	Stockholm University, SU	Sweden
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

The European Green Deal and the Initiative on the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability set as a priority for the next generation chemical safety assessments the development and implementation of the ‘one substance – one assessment’ process. This project aims at reviewing current risk assessment practices, including tools, criteria and methods currently used within and across regulatory frameworks, assessing the level of protection to human health and the environment and making suggestions from improvements in the broader context of ‘one substance one assessment’.

This project will review the processes as well as the use of tools, criteria and methods, both within and across legislations, in order to promote more transparent and consistent evaluation of scientific information and data. The case studies will cover issues such as risk assessment methodologies, test requirements, effectiveness towards risk reduction, sources of uncertainty as well as methodological challenges in implementing uncertainty analysis and bridging of data gaps in risk assessment. Case studies related to the specific areas of environmental and occupational risk assessment have also been developed. Other specific areas in regulatory risk assessment may additionally be identified during the course of PARC.

- The project currently contains case studies on comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks (CS1_CARB_SYKE), identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk (CS2_RiskReduction_SU), holistic overview and agreements on strategic regulatory needs for a sustainable chemical control (CS6_SusChemControl_MUI (this case study will not continue in Y2)) practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment (CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND), and the status of chemical data gap filling approaches (CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU).

With regard to environmental risk assessment, two case studies are currently included on protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations (case study CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG) and secondary poisoning and protection of wildlife (case study CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS).

With regard to occupational risk assessment, two case studies are currently included on occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants (case study CS8_OccupReproDev_KI) and workplace chemical risk assessment (case study CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL).

Descriptions of the case studies included in the project are available in Annex I.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Identify inconsistencies, loopholes and gaps in the current chemical risk assessment frameworks.
 - Contribute to an increased understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of risk assessment aimed at reducing risk.
 - An overview of options beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development for a sustainable regulation of chemicals.
 - A general introduction to uncertainty analysis for risk assessment in a PARC context.
 - A systematic overview of currently used and state-of-the-art chemical data gap-filling approaches applied across EU legislations
 - A review on the current PPP environmental risk assessments under different regulations.
 - Practices for properly assessing the risk of secondary poisoning under different regulatory schemes.
 - Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs.
 - Evaluation of how regulatory information provided under different regulatory processes is utilized in workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practice.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders:

- The project will guide the future design of legislation on chemical risk assessment, focusing on sustainable management of chemical risks, as well as the implementation of the “One substance – One assessment” approach. The project will provide regulators, legislators and other stakeholders an in-depth understanding of the commonly used decision benchmarks and the significance of their appropriate foundation and application. The project will provide options for sustainable chemical control beyond NAM, AOP, and IATA development, including possible approaches for the assessment of non-chemical alternatives to chemical biocides and pesticides. The project will provide new knowledge about the practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment, as well as pedagogical examples on how to implement quantitative expressions of uncertainty and the benefit of these in assessment and communication. The project will provide recommendations for harmonizing data gap-filling approaches in relevant EU legislations, which will have an impact on the practices of filling data gaps during compliance reporting, monitoring and assessment by companies, scientists, and policymakers alike.

Keywords: data gaps, uncertainty, sustainable chemical control, effectiveness, comparative analysis, reference value, environmental risk assessment, OSOA, secondary poisoning, occupational exposure.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

This project will contribute towards the WP6.3 objective to “map and evaluate current methodologies employed in regulatory risk assessment to identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge”.

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4 ‘Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support the use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in risk assessment.’

The project will contribute to the PARC main objective ‘Drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with the implementation of NGRA as the ultimate goal’ by strengthening the implementation of uncertainty analysis in NGRA.

The project will moreover contribute to PARC objective OO9 ‘Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA’ by proposing recommendations that are harmonized across EU policies.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project has potential synergies with several other WPs, tasks, activities or projects that address holistic approaches to risk assessment. Plans for concrete cooperation will be specified during the study regarding other projects in WP6 as well as potential interactions at the task level e.g., with WP2, WP7 and WP3.

- WP2: This work will support the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.
 - WP3: Interaction with WP3 foreseen to clarify how to best communicate on recommendations for regulatory action and for aspects related to risk communication.
 - WP4/Task 4.2: “Case study on Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs)”. One of the aims of the project are to promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity by ensuring that the environmental and multisource monitoring is designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the identified regulatory needs. EDCs will include a variety of different classes of chemicals, among which pesticides. Besides, it will allow for the comparison of chemical approaches, such as in prospective assessment, with effects actually found in the field using effect-based tools. Exchange will be ensured through a common research partner (INERIS, EAWAG).
 - WP4: This work will be linked to WP4 for the collection of monitoring data in wildlife and their possible use in secondary poisoning assessment.
 - WP5: This project could provide feedback on the need of input data for ecotoxicity studies and models to be used for SP assessment.
 - WP6/Task 6.2: The project will provide feedback for the need of models for a better understanding of exposure kinetics.
 - WP6/Task 6.4: uptake of the outcome of the project in Regulatory frameworks
- WP7: the project will feed into the work of WP7, specifically task 7.3 which targets the development and implementation of innovative data analytical approaches from the computational, statistical, and mathematical fields, including quantification of the uncertainties and propagation of these uncertainties when combining different sets of data. This case study is a retrospective analysis of practitioners’ experience, which make the findings valuable for the work under task 7.3 which approaches the issue of uncertainty analysis from a more normative and methodological perspective. Data related to data gap-filling methods across relevant EU legislations will be collected and generated in the present project, which will be included in the data management plan of PARC under WP7.
- WP8: The project will connect to and explore synergies with 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD). Toolbox requirements of the PARC model network developed under WP8 will be explored to clarify how the harmonization of data gap-filling approaches across modelling, monitoring and assessment tools can consistently contribute to a strong and reliable PARC toolbox.

Links outside PARC

The project may contribute to other EU regulations and policy frameworks (i.e., those not currently or directly embedded in our project plan), such as the EU’s Soil Strategy, Circular Economy and Zero Pollution Action Plans, and the EFSA-funded projects RACEMiC (RA of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals) and PERA (Building a European Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment).

The Austrian Green Chemicals Platform (<https://www.grünechemieösterreich.at/>).

The project will harvest synergies with UNEP SAICM and with Mistra SafeChem.

- Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Implemented by risk assessors with a broad network regarding EU environmental risk assessment, the following list is a non-exhaustive list of their fields of collaborations and involvements: WG chemicals under the WFD. PPR panel under 1107/2009 EFSA project PERA. Premier project on improving pharmaceutical risk assessment, Norman Network (ecotoxicology database), EEA project on soil risk assessment.
- Secondary poisoning and protection of wildlife: This project will be complementary to EU and national activities regarding monitoring in biota, as a regular task under WFD, but also for the interpretation of biota level in wildlife. The project will also be linked to the Horizon project PROMISCES, in the interpretation of the risks due to the promotion of the circularity of natural resources (water, soil) during life cycle of chemicals. The project will also grounds on the EU LIFE VERMEER (Life Vermeer – Integrating VEGA, toxRead, MERLIN-Expo and ERICA in A Platform for Risk Assessment and Substitution of Risky Substance (life-vermeer.eu) for the use of the SPHERA Tools and models.

- Occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants: Partners closely connected to various OSH-stakeholders, expert group members and active researchers.

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group One Substance One Assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

The results will be published in a number of reports and peer-reviewed papers.

- Report 1: Differences and similarities between regulatory threshold values for surface waters, including sediment, under different EU legal frameworks (namely PPP, BPR and WFD); could be in the form of publication or policy brief including PPT set of slides (M24, Eawag).
- Report 2: Approaches to align the different frameworks and proposing feedback-loops between the different regulatory frameworks to bridge the identified differences in risk assessment outcomes to further the goal of OS-OA; could be in the form of publication or policy brief including PPT set of slides (M36, Eawag).
- Report 3: Report focussing on soil and air as a result of the second project phase; could be in the form of publication or policy brief including PPT set of slides (Month to be specified after finalisation of first project phase, Eawag).
- Report 4: Review and analysis of the existing approaches in regulatory framework and relevant research projects for the assessment of secondary poisoning (M10, INERIS).
- Report 5: case studies comparing the outcome of existing approaches for a selection of chemicals leading to the identification of gaps, inconsistencies, and uncertainties - Supporting material for workshop on the identification of priorities for improvement of guidance for secondary poisoning. (M18, INERIS).
- Report 6: Recommendations for the uptake of the results of the CS into regulations (M30, INERIS).
- Report 7: Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs, Analysis of the weight given to reproductive toxicity in OEL-setting, Quantitative estimates of OELs’ margin of safety to reproductive toxicity, Recommendations for regulatory actions, such as re-evaluation of specific OELs (M36, KI).
- Report 8: Analysis of different options to regulate occupational chemical exposure, results of the questionnaire study/interviews on the interpretation and implementation of limit values and other regulatory information at the workplace level, related recommendations and guidance (M36, FI).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

The case studies have either not reported a landmark or reported the same landmarks as in “expected project reports”.

Partners List:

SYKE (FI); ISSeP (BE); SU (SE); UBA (DE); STAMI (NO); UCL (UK); JSI (SI); MUI (AT); KEMI (SE); ULUND (SE); KI (SE); BPI (EL); DTU (DK); UCPH (DK); Eawag (CH); FOEN (CH); INERIS (FR); TTL (FI), LSMU (LT); RSU (LV).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 98 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 41 550 €

T6.4 Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies **11 PROJECTS**

This task will support regulatory processes for reducing risks to humans and the environment by undertaking scenario-based case-studies resulting in guidance documents and/or recommendations. First, in coordination with ongoing EC activities, a European framework for the regulatory assessment of mixtures encompassing all relevant chemical classes, exposure scenarios and protection goals will be developed. It will evaluate the availability and quality of data for regulatory assessment, analyse the additional risk caused by mixtures and its implications. The second activity aims to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of NAMs in RA across different chemical sectors. Focus will be put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by risk assessors. Long-term objectives include the definition of harmonised scientific criteria for acceptance of NAMs across regulations and of an evidence-based framework to ensure systematic, transparent, and reproducible application of NAMs in RA. Next, we will develop and apply tools and databases that enable a systematic identification of priority substances in products and materials. In doing so, the activity will promote a more effective and harmonised enforcement of legislation, support informed substitution of problematic chemicals in products and materials and inform how sustainability assessments can be achieved with respect to chemicals.

T 6.4 Transposing results to risk assessment methodologies

Develop and foster the uptake of innovative, efficient and protective regulatory risk assessment and management approaches and methodologies.

Fig 10: W6.3: Risk assessment methodologies

A6.4.1 Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures – 2 PROJECTS

P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot

Project Title	Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OPREMIX		
Project Manager	Thomas Backhaus	University of Gothenburg	Sweden
Deputy Project	Andreas Kortenkamp	Brunel University London	UK
	thomas.backhaus@gu.se		
	andreas.kortenkamp@brunel.ac.uk		

manager			
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1.
Project Id	P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project has its focus on the current approaches related to the management of mixtures across regulatory areas as e.g., REACH, CLP, Pesticides and Biocides, cosmetics, food contact material, pharmaceuticals. Further regulation on food and drinking water as well as on environmental media and emission will be considered. It will also explore the use of the MAF approach for the assessment and management of mixtures across regulatory areas and uses (beyond REACH) and compare it to other mixture approaches. This project will address the question if and under which circumstances a MAF is applicable or not and how different are the conclusion drawn by different mixture approaches when challenged with real word data sets and if there are differences to what extend would the MAF approach might provide biased results.

This project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “*Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures*”, while specifically focusing on and comparing the methods and tools currently used for the regulatory assessment and management and providing guidance for further development.

Main expected outputs of the project

A systematic comparative evaluation of current mixture tools (and those that are currently under development or might be developed within PARC). The mixture tools will be compared regarding their practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide the input to develop a “European cookbook” of mixture tools that describes the application domain for each tool, its data demands, protectiveness, feasibility and reliability, in the view of the different demands from regulators, industries and civil society.

Key words: mixtures, MAF, Mixture tools, European cookbook of mixtures.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Chemical mixtures were one of the highest scored topics in the first round of prioritisation within PARC, and this project will support in particular Objectives 9 and 12. The practical experiences with handling heterogeneous datasets of complex mixtures will also feed into Objective 10. The project focuses on comparing existing methods of mixture risk assessment with the Mixture Assessment Factor, which is to be implemented for industrial chemicals (REACH), as requested by the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: a cooperation for the foreseen survey would be of value, especially in distributing it to risk assessor

WP7: Data management plan

WP9: Training, laboratory network

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ (Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of

monitoring data and NAMs). Findings from WP 4 and WP5 regarding monitoring data and toxicity data will be considered in this Project. Further, there will probably be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In WP6.2 mixtures will be approached from a research science perspective with the focus on modelling, human health and dietary exposure. Relevant findings of Task 6.2 will be considered in this project for sizing one or more MAFs.

Links outside PARC

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remits of EFSA (e.g., food safety and pesticides), e.g., regarding the further development of the Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs), primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the European Commission will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Evaluation of the stakeholder feedback collected from a survey and expert interviews on the usefulness of current mixture assessment tools (Technical report, public, M18)

Report 2: Comparative assessment of mixture tools with respect to application domain, feasibility, data demands, protectiveness, reliability, bias. (Technical report, computer code, data repository, all public, M24)

Report 3: Draft for a European mixture framework, accompanied by a validated toolbox of instruments for mixture risk assessment and management (Technical report, public, M36)

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Updated inventory of current mixture assessment tools and compilation of current regulatory requirements (M12)

Landmark 2: Documented interviews with experts in chemical risk assessment (human health as well as the environment). (M18)

Landmark 3: Selection of case studies for the comparative assessment of current or newly developed mixture tools (M12)

Partners List: UGOT (SE), BUL (UK), AGES (AT), UBA (DE), BPI (EL), UI (IS), NIVA (NO), ENSP (PT), EAWAG (CH), KEMI (SE), UK Env. Agency (UK), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), UAVR (PT), NLZOH (SI), UK-CEH (UK), LSMU (LT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/4/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 63 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 19 895 €

P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ

Project Title	Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessments through the use of monitoring data and NAMs
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MONAMMIX

Project Manager	Wibke Busch wibke.busch@ufz.de	Helmholtz Environmental Research center (UFZ)	Germany
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX CS2_UFZ		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment by bridging data gaps. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “*Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures*” and strives to link prospective mixture assessment methods with monitoring and AOP knowledge. In particular, it is focusing on case studies on environmental monitoring under EU directives such as WFD, (Directive 2000/60/EC), Sustainable Use of PPPs Directive 2009/128/EC) and human biomonitoring initiatives such as HBM4EU or the cohort studies within the European Exposome Network. In this project the use of new approach methods (NAMs) i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data, to deal with unknown mixtures will be compared with mixture risk assessment methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information.

In this project we will address the following research question:

- How can data from NAMs be used to provide more comprehensive pictures of the chemical exposure that needs to be addressed in chemical risk assessment?
- How could available bioanalytical methodology and information from environmental monitoring contribute to mixture risk assessment?
- Are AOP networks a way to overcome data gaps and account for compounds mixture contributions?
- Can priority mixtures be defined with the application of non-target methods?
- Can NAMs complement component-based mixture risk assessment?

Main expected outputs of the project

The availability of empirically based support data from established monitoring efforts on human health and environmental quality, as well as adverse outcome pathway knowledge compiled under OECD efforts, will be important for developing the assessment and management of mixtures in several ways. It will for example be crucial to argue the size of a mixture assessment factor (MAF), to define common assessment groups, or to aggregate exposures across regulatory silos. Accepted use of pollutant monitoring and NAM generated data will be essential to provide support in these respects, while providing additional options for tiered mixture assessment strategies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

To advance the regulatory assessment of unintentional mixtures additional approaches are needed which are practicable in a regulatory context and capable of dealing with data constraints. It can be foreseen that monitoring information based on non-target chemical and bioanalytical methods will be utilised to define - unknown mixture exposures. Furthermore, mechanistic information from *in vitro* bioanalytical NAMs can be employed for establishing AOP networks to bridge data gaps in mixture assessment. End-users might e.g. be interested to using NAMS to consider the expectable additional effect of product formulation compounds to the toxicity of an individually assessed active ingredient.

Key words: chemical mixtures, new approach methods, environment, human health, regulatory acceptance

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In this project, the use of data of new approach methods (NAMs) (i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data) to deal with mixtures will be compared with mixture risk assessment methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information. During the project data integration will be performed in collaboration with WP7 and according to the FAIR principles. Reuse of data and workflows will be enabled. Chemical mixtures are an integral part in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS). Further, chemical mixtures were one of the highest scored topics in the first round of prioritisation within PARC. However, this project will highly support the Objectives 004,005, 0010 and 0012.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: we will do a survey in cooperation with Task 6.4.2, for that we will need some support in distributing the survey to risk assessor.

WP7: Data management plan

WP9: Training, laboratory network: for now, we see no need for support from WP9, but if we identify needs, we will contact WP9

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_UGot (Optimising regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) and with Task 6.4.2. Further, there will be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In a later stage, if available, the newly generated monitoring data from WP 4 and the outcome of WP 5 regarding toxicity testing and AOPs will be considered in our case studies.

Links outside PARC:

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remit of EFSA (e.g. food safety and pesticides), e.g. regarding the further development of the Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs), primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the European Commission will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH, which will be supported by a consultant study.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Literature review on use of NAM for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation (M18)

Report 2: Guidance document for use of NAM data for specific regulatory options (M36)

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Selection of case studies for the use of NAMs in specific regulatory areas (M12)

Partners List: UFZ (DE), UBA (DE), NIVA (NO), BPI (EL), UI (IS), AGES (AT), STAMI (NO), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), NLZOH (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 24 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 4 220 €

A6.4.2 Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods – 3 PROJECTS

P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS

Project Title	Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		
Project Manager	Martin F. Wilks martin.wilks@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Deputy Project manager	Nicolas Roth nicolas.roth@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Innovative approaches to regulatory science and chemical risk assessment are needed to meet the goals and vision laid down by the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the EU Green Deal. The overall aim of the project is to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for use in chemical risk assessment for human health and the environment. Emphasis is put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by risk assessors and regulators at desk level, e.g., situations with complex modes of action and/or often severe knowledge gaps. We will (i) review the status of development (incl. harmonization), integration, and use of NAMs in the different EU chemical sectors/regulatory frameworks/application contexts, through literature review and expert consultation activities (expert elicitation, survey); (ii) identify gaps, needs, barriers, opportunities, and drivers for success towards the regulatory acceptance and implementation of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory landscape

The validation and regulatory acceptance of NAMs has been lagging behind despite significant scientific developments over the last decade. One particular challenge for risk assessment is to integrate these scientific developments into existing regulatory frameworks and best practice at desk level. While policies have long had the vision to protect human health and ecosystems with new and innovative methods, solid downstream implementation has been lagging behind, often because novel scientific methods have failed to consider regulatory needs as a driver for successful use and integration into chemical risk assessment and management practice. The project intends to follow-up on these needs, consolidating knowledge and fostering scientific cross-fertilization and harmonization in the field to develop criteria for the acceptance of NAMs and guidelines to support their integration in the daily risk assessment workflow.

The mapping activities will inform on the current status of integration and use of NAMs in regulatory risk assessment processes across chemical sectors. The outcome of the project will advance use of NAMs in regulatory science and may all together benefit all chemical sectors and risk assessment frameworks, as well as support harmonization efforts (EU Green Deal, Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability).

Main expected outputs of the project

Outputs are planned in the form of three technical reports due M24, M26, and M36. They are aimed at knowledge consolidation, mapping gaps, needs, drivers, and areas of uncertainty for uptake of NAMs at risk assessment level. This initial phase of the work may promote and facilitate broader stakeholder engagement activities across regulatory, industry and academia, involved in similar research projects and initiatives at EU and international level.

- Summary of the landscaping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs at across sectorial frameworks
- Summary of the gaps & needs analysis, barriers, opportunities, drivers for integration and use of NAMs and roadmap for use at desk level across sectorial frameworks
- Action plan for prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies, as an output from an international workshop
- Research “Road map” that will map the potential use of NAMs to requirements for environmental risk assessment (e.g., species selection for testing and biomonitoring)
- Summary of the scenario-based case-studies

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Activities in years 1 and 2 will inform the development of regulatory-relevant case studies, looking across regulatory silos and product categories.

The selected scenario-based case studies will cover a variety of complex situations that regulators are facing when conducting hazard, exposure, and risk assessment, e.g., data-rich vs. data-poor chemicals, grouping decisions, different exposures, (occupational, environmental, consumer), identification and selection of species for testing and monitoring studies and model systems for hazard testing and assessment, classification and labelling, setting health-based guidance and environmental protection values, cumulative exposures etc.

The output of this project will be used to orientate future coordination and harmonization efforts, foster cross-fertilization of scientific knowledge, order research needs and sharing of best research-to-policy practice in relation to the development, use and regulatory uptake of NAMs.

Key words: New Approach Methodologies; landscaping; expert elicitation; survey; regulatory acceptance; gaps & needs analysis; research road-mapping, confidence, human health risk assessment, environmental risk assessment.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

- The project will support OO4 through the development of regulatory-relevant case studies across regulatory silos and product categories.
- It will contribute to OO5 by closely cooperating in particular with the ASPIS cluster of R&I initiatives.
- It addresses PARC operational objectives OO9 by promoting and facilitating the integration and use of NAMs in chemical risk assessment practice, as well as their regulatory acceptance and uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Important coordination efforts will be invested over the entire project duration within PARC to avoid overlaps and create synergies with:

- WP2, Task 2.1, Task 2.2
- WP5, Task 5.2, Task 5.3
- WP6, Task 6.1, Task 6.3

Links outside PARC

- ASPIS cluster: activities in PrecisionTox and RISK-HUNT3R are directly relevant to or even overlap with A6.4.2. ASPIS collaborators are partners in PARC 6.4.2 and/or WP6. PARERE at EURL ECVAM

Network for Preliminary Assessment of Regulatory Relevance, which includes validation of NAMs for regulatory purposes;

- EFSA and JRC, regarding ongoing projects in the field of computer-based approaches/automation of the systematic review approach and TK/TD approaches; advisors for PARC A6.4.2;
- OECD, regarding ongoing projects in the field of harmonization and regulatory acceptance of NAMs and development of the Adverse Outcome Pathway Wiki.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81)

AD6.16. Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (M24)

Project Reports:

R1: Technical report: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (M24, UNIBAS)

R2: Workshop report: Prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies (M26, UNIBAS)

R3: Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies (M36, UNIBAS)

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Technical report summarizing: (1) the mapping of activities and processes related to the status of development, integration and use of NAMs in selected regulatory environments (which informs the gaps and needs analysis in Y2); (2) the outcome of the gaps and needs analysis. This will prepare the workshop at the beginning of Y3.(M24)

Landmark 2: A workshop will be held to design regulatory scenario-based case studies resulting in an action plan prioritizing the case studies (M26)

Landmark 3: Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies (M36).

Partners List:

UNIBAS (Switzerland); NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UT (Estonia); ISS (Italy); UOB (United Kingdom); INERIS (France); UBA (Germany); BPI (Greece); EAA (Austria); UNL (Portugal); UKCEH (United Kingdom); UAVR (Portugal); NIVA (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 53 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 45 250 €

P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractive_VKM_NIPH

Project Title	Next generation risk assessment applied in practice		
Project	NGRApractive		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Gro Haarklou Mathisen Gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway

Deputy Project manager	Camilla Svendsen Camilla.svendsen@fhi.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Methods to incorporate NAMs in systematic reviews and other evidence synthesis processes such as risk assessments are currently not available. The VKM project “NGRA applied in practice” aim to create evidence-based tools and guidance’s for risk assessment based on NAMs, which will be included in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework usable for the evaluation of human health risk/safety across sectors (e.g. food and cosmetic). The framework will enable risk assessors to use NAMs as direct evidence in risk assessments. Using NAMs as direct evidence is expected to fill several critical knowledge gaps, and the outcome will be more robust risk assessments, reduced uncertainty in the risk assessments, and a better knowledge base for the regulators/risk managers. The VKM project “NGRA applied in practice” consists of several sub-projects. In 2023 we will create a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies and perform a user testing and validation. In 2023-2024 we will create a tool for the evaluation of external validity of in vitro studies. In 2023, we will also have a terminology project addressing core terms used in systematic reviews and chemical hazard assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Generic, sector-independent tools for evidence-based hazard assessment of chemicals using NAMs addressing potential adverse human health effects.
- Generic, sector-independent guidance documents on identification of a PoD from NAMs and on the evaluation of uncertainty in NAMs.
- Generic, sector-independent checklists (reporting standards) for different NAMs, to ensure adequate design and reporting for the research outcome of NAMs to be usable as evidence in risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We are starting with the creation of tools for evaluation of internal and external validity of NAMs, enabling risk assessors to use NAMs in evidence-based risk assessment. The tools are needed to ensure that only evidence of sufficient quality is included based on the weight of evidence principle, that the effects addressed are relevant for human adverse health effects, and that the hazard assessment process and product is objective, robust, transparent, and reproducible. The tool development will be followed by checklist for in vitro studies.

Key words:

Chemical risk assessment, evidence-based, guidance, NAMs, NGRA, systematic review, tool.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to the development of innovative tools that enable transition from traditional risk assessments largely depending on animal studies as evidence to evidence-based NGRAs using NAMs as evidence. This way, NGRAs will be useful for risk managers in policy and regulations.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

A scientific advisory group has been established for this project. Dimosthenis Sarigiannis (WP3) has the role as observers and will have the possibility to participate in all meetings.

It is important to ensure dissemination, communication, and awareness of the outcomes of this project. We would like to arrange a workshop and/or a symposium (year 2023/2024) to which the main stakeholders will be invited. An in-person workshop could e.g., include training people in use of the tools (presentation of the tools and the development methods, followed by hands-on training). Training could also be developed as online prerecorded material with on-demand Q&As to help users. A symposium could e.g., focus on making NAMs usable for risk managers (from science to evidence in chemical risk assessments to scientific basis for risk managers).

- WP7: This information is included in the section Data Management
- WP9: This project does not involve laboratory work. Hands-on training courses on the use of the tools, for assessors coming from different regulatory sectors including e.g., food safety, pesticides, cosmetics, consumer products, industrial chemicals, could be organised. Courses could be foreseen also for researchers and in Industries to make them aware of the tools.
- Other WPs: A scientific advisory group has been established for this project. Vera Ritz (WP2) has the role as observer and will have the possibility to participate in all meetings with the scientific advisory group.

This project is related to the two other Activity 6.4.2-projects:

- Status of integration & use of NAMs in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape
- Landscape and readiness of advanced ML & AI approaches for Next Generation Risk Assessment

Links outside PARC

Several projects outside PARC addressing similar topics are ongoing. A scientific advisory group has been established, consisting of experts in the topic of interest with the goal to ensure a broad, multidisciplinary representation of members from academia, regulatory authorities, and scientific organizations that will give advice related to the planned work on development of tools and share information about ongoing work addressing similar question.

The purpose of the Advisory Group is to give strategic guidance and content-related support to the project group related to aspects considered important for the development of the tools, and to share information about ongoing work addressing similar questions to ensure that the outcome of the project complements the work of others, thereby creating synergies and avoiding duplication of efforts.

The members of the scientific advisory group are linked to the following institutions/projects outside PARC: CAAT (Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing), EBTC (Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration), Johns Hopkins University, Karolinska Institutet, NTP (National Toxicology program, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services), OECD, ONTOX, Radboud University, U.S. EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency), EFSA, University of California San Fransisco.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81)

Project Reports:

- R1: Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies (Y1)
- R2: Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies (Y2)
- R3: Creation of INVITES-IN, a focus group study (Y2)
- R4: Protocol for harmonizing and cross-walking SR and CRA terms (Y2)
- R5: Creation of INVITES-IN, a Delphi survey (Y2)
- R6: Core SR and CRA terms; definitions and cross-walking two disciplines (Y2)
- R7: Protocol; creating an overview of external validity items (Y2)

- R8: Creation of INVITES-IN, user testing and validation (Y2)
- R9: INVITES-IN, a tool for evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies (Y2)
- R10: Protocol for designing INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of *in vitro* studies (Y3)
- R11: External validity items, a comprehensive overview (Y3)
- R12: Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of *in vitro* studies (Y3)

Projects Landmarks:

L1: Ethical approval of creation of INVITES-IN (Y1)

L2: INVITES-IN (Y2)

L3: Cross walking SR and CRA terminology (Y3)

L4: External validity items, a comprehensive overview (Y3)

Partners List:

NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UNIBAS (Switzerland); UT (Estonia); BPI (Greece); ISS (Italy); NIVA (Norway); UAVR (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Expected Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 17 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 23 400 €

P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT

Project Title	Landscape and readiness of computational New Approach Methods based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals' next generation risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NAMAM		
Project Manager	Uko Maran uko.maran@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Deputy Project manager	Sulev Sild sulev.sild@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Today more and more advanced machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) mathematical approaches are used to estimate effects and doses (QSAR) and to learn patterns of chemical behaviour from multiple data (*in silico* and *in vitro*). The aim of using these data-driven approaches is to make better

informed decisions for the protection of human health and environment while reducing animal testing. There is a lack of transparency due to limited documentation or accessibility to underlying data and algorithms. This makes advanced computational methods (ACM) in content of NAMs difficult to understand and characterise uncertainty associated with using them. Thus, there is a clear need for better standardisation, transparent reporting, validation and illustration of AI & ML driven in silico models. This project will address the existing landscape and the potential acceptance of AI & ML driven QSAR models to important properties in chemical risk assessment with an emphasis on the regulatory use. The aim is to conduct a review and analysis of the AI and ML QSAR models and to identify best practices and further actions to ensure a transparent regulatory use, uncertainty estimation and its communication towards end-users, independent verification and understanding of the outcome of such models. To develop reporting standards and decision-making criteria for ML and AI predictive models in the context of NAMs and NGRA. The best examples will be identified and made available as FAIR data through the QsarDB.org repository.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will provide a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI and ML models for regulatory purposes. This will help stakeholders (for better predictions' reporting) and regulators (for predictions' evaluation).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The main outcomes and impacts of the project include:

- Identification of ML and AI QSAR models of PARC focused properties that could be used for filling data gaps.
- Knowledge of the transparency and potential reproducibility of ML and AI models for chemical risk assessment and decision-making workflows.
- Identification of main roadblocks related to the applications of QSAR models, including applicability domain evaluation and uncertainty estimation related to ML and AI models.
- Case studies that attempt to reuse published ML and/or AI models to identify issues that need addressing to improve acceptance for regulatory use.

Limitation of ML and/or AI models:

Limitations of these non-animal approaches are related to their data-driven nature, because if they rely on prior knowledge, this knowledge must be present before reliable models can be developed. This can be overcome by developing reliable data source(s).

Also related to the actual regulations is the transparency of ML and/or AI models, which requires the development of various metrics that contribute to confidence and help adapt best practices.

Key words:

AI model, ML model, in silico models, QSAR, QSPR, NAMs, reporting framework, applicability domain, uncertainty

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In response to identified needs in Chemical RA (OO7) this project will focus on advanced ML and AI models. The project will address PARC operational objectives OO9 by facilitating the uptake of new approach methods in regulatory RA processes.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Interactions with other WPs in PARC are summarised as follows:

- Cooperation is foreseen with WP2 task 2.1 to define priorities for the research. Cooperation is established with WP2.2 in connection with NGRARoute. Potential cooperation with WP5 task 5.1 on the topic of computational NAMs for closing data gaps in human health and environmental endpoints. Potential collaboration with WP5 task 5.3 on the evaluation of in silico methods for ADME/Tox parameters in PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology.

- Potential collaboration with WP7 task 7.1 on the PARC’s FAIR Data Policy (PFDP).
- Cooperation is foreseen with WP task 7.3 in establishing FAIR predictive models.
- Cooperation with WP8 task 8.2 on the evaluation of computational NAMs for the early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks.
- Cooperation with WP8 task 8.3 on the integrating of computational NAMs.

Links outside PARC

- OECD-QAF: (OECD QSAR Assessment Framework, duration 2021-2024) develops criteria on how to assess (i) QSAR and any other computational model validity used as NAMs and (ii) how to assess validity of QSAR and any other computational prediction. Three partners (ISS, INERIS, UT) of the project are involved in OECD-QAF.
- ASPIS-cluster (<https://www.aspis-cluster.com/>): cluster acts as roof organisation for the RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX & PrecisionTOX projects. IRFM (E. Benfenati) is co-leading the WG on computational methods with other people from the lab being part of the WG; i.e., acting as liaison.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81)

Project Reports:

Project reports are organised on an annual basis to collect and provide final results to the stakeholders and regulators. Partner UT is in charge of all the reports.

- Report 1: Overview of exploratory analysis and identification of research priorities and requirements (M12)
- Report 2: Framework to facilitate an adequate reporting for the AI/ML NAMs to be used for regulatory purposes (M24)
- Report 3: Final report on the main outcomes of the project (M34)

Projects Landmarks:

The project plan includes the following landmarks that can be considered as “go” achievements:

- Landmark 1: Refined work plan and methodology for years 2 and 3 (M12)
- Landmark 2: Selection of case studies (M16)
- Landmark 3: Framework tested on case studies (M30)

Partners List:

UT (Estonia); UG-PL (Poland); IRFM (Italy); UNIBAS (Switzerland); NIPH(VKM) (Norway); ISS (Italy); INERIS (France); UKCEH (United Kingdom); NIVA (Norway), EA (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 28 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 10 200 €

A6.4.3 Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy – 1 PROJECT

P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU

Project Title	6.4.3.1 A comprehensive review and application of databases and testing methods for SUBstances in PROducts and Materials		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SuProM		
Project Manager	Lisa Melymuk lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz	MU (RECETOX)	Czechia
Deputy Project manager	Robin Vestergren robin.vestergren@kemi.se	KemI	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.3
Project Id	P_6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The European Commission's Green Deal and the Chemical strategy for sustainability provides the direction for a toxic free and sustainable future where chemicals are produced and used in a way that maximises their contribution to society while minimizing risks for the environment and human health. In these strategic documents it is envisaged that products and material used in society should be designed without the use of the most harmful chemicals and that the use of other harmful chemicals should be minimized.

Enforcement of EU chemicals safety and environmental legislation has a central role in implementing the European Green Deal agenda and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. No matter how ambitious the legislation is on paper, it will never fulfil the level of protection of consumers and workers if not properly enforced. The methods developed in this activity will facilitate a systematic risk-based identification of priority substances, products, and materials, as well as support and direct the development of efficient analytical methods for enforcement actions. This will support national enforcement authorities of chemicals legislation, including product specific legislations (for example, the RoHS Directive, EC Toys directive, regulations on food contact materials, etc.) and restrictions of chemicals in various products. Enforcement is essential, and without enforcement any law will be ineffective.

The newly proposed Sustainable Products Initiative (SPI) aims to reduce the environmental footprint of products throughout their lifecycle. The legislative proposal will extend the scope of the Ecodesign framework beyond energy-related products, while also considering additional sustainability principles to regulate the environmental impact of goods, including chemicals in products. A consistent and complete methodology for assessing the environmental, climate and health impacts of products (and services) over their life cycle are needed. The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) has been suggested as a basis for such a consistent and complete methodology. However, there is still a need to further develop the PEF methodology to more adequately address toxicity impacts of chemicals. The proposed project will evaluate how such sustainability assessments of products and materials are implemented with respect to chemicals, and provide a basis for future work providing recommendations on the application of this framework.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will evaluate the currently available information on substances in products and materials, and how this information can be integrated in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments, based on a comprehensive review of chemical databases and gap and needs analysis of analytical testing

methodologies. Based on this analysis, future projects on the development of new databases tools, and analytical testing methods will be designed. This will support the aim of Activity 6.4.3, in applying tools and databases that enable a systematic identification of priority substances in products and materials to support the transition to the circular economy.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The primary stakeholders for this project are national and EU agencies responsible for enforcement of chemical and product legislations. It is envisaged that the results from this project and follow-up projects will contribute to a more systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals.

Key words

substances in products; chemical databases; materials; consumer products; enforcement; product composition;

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In response to identified needs in Chemical RA (OO7) tThis project will synthesize existing information from regulatory databases, other research and industry activities (OO5) to assemble a comprehensive overview of the state of information on substances in products and materials in Europe, which will be of use by risk assessors, policy makers, other research activities within and outside of PARC (OO4, OO5), and in the longer term, through further development of the activity 6.4.3, can serve as an information source to the general public to increase knowledge and awareness on chemical exposures and risks (OO6). The project will include assessment of the FAIR and open aspects of existing databases, and recommendations for improved data structures that meet FAIR and open data criteria and are useable tools for further risk assessment related to substances in products and materials (OO10, OO12).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP3: Support in administering questionnaires to national chemical agencies as an information gathering exercises on the topics of chemical databases and enforcement of chemical regulations in products and materials.
 - WP7: Data management plan
 - WP9: Evaluation of chemical laboratories/methods involved in enforcement activities related to substances in products and materials; capacity-building related to enforcement activities
 - Other WPs: WP4 (Task 4.2 Prioritization of substances for screening/monitoring; Task 4.3 Analytical method development), WP6 (Task 6.2 Exposure via consumer articles); WP8 (Task 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design; Task 8.2 Early warning systems)

Links outside PARC

The research on developing databases and improving chemical information transfer is linked to several initiatives such as the SCiP database (ECHA), development of product passports and the use of product environmental footprints.

The research on new testing methods for products and materials will be carried out in close collaboration with national agencies responsible for enforcing chemical and product legislations.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.20 Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data M81

AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures – Leader: TUKES (M24)

AD6.15: Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards - Leader: MU (M24)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Report on existing database structures with recommended structures (M36 – MU)

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Stakeholder advisory board meeting to share information and recommendations on current

data structures relevant to products and materials (M6)

Landmark 2: Completion of information gathering from national chemical agencies (M12)

Landmark 3: Mapping of database structures and gaps (M12)

Landmark 4: Annual communication through online meetings with Stakeholder advisory board: (M12, M24)

Landmark 5: Identification of case study topics (M14)

Partners List:

MU (Czechia); KemI (Sweden); Rise (Sweden); TUKES (Finland); VUA (Netherlands), Vito (Belgium) (WP7); TNO (Netherlands) (WP7)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 36 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 9 200 €

A6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity – 5 PROJECTS

P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI

Project Title	Clarify regulatory needs – Transform EU strategies into regulatory useable research projects		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	CRNCS1		
Project Manager	Johan Axelman Johan.axelman@kemi.se	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Sabine Duquesne Sabine.Duquesne@uba.de	Umweltsbundesamt (UBA)	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The activity is tailored toward supporting strategic transition initiatives such as the roadmap to systems-based ERA (by EFSA - European partnership for next generation, system-based ERA [PERA]) and European co-funded partnership on biodiversity (Biodiversa+). The project is directly applicable to the environmental risk assessment for the authorisation of PPP and aims to better link the goal of the EU environmental and agricultural strategies to the EU regulation 1107/2009.

The activity aims at better assessing effects on overall biodiversity and the possibility to simplify (i.e. less

resource demanding) the methods used for the environmental risk assessment (ERA) of plant protection products (PPP) without compromising the level of protection to be ensured by the assessment. That will be achieved by benchmarking existing and new methods (such as NAMs) to against each other and against independent environmental monitoring data. Furthermore, we will explore new holistic approaches to environmental risk assessment to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically. Both existing and new models for prospective risk assessment will be reviewed and amended using monitoring data. The activity will also help to explore new frameworks for risk characterisation that support system-based approaches to risk assessment by expanding the current approach.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will ensure that the outcome of the other projects within 6.4.4 address the common goal of an improved ERA-scheme better aligning with EU strategies and assessing biodiversity. Considering regulatory needs and ensuring regulatory acceptance are key components of this project. It will be identified how the input from other stakeholders (risk managers, farmers, etc) can be integrated in the ERA development.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The current ERA scheme is well established, but has fallen out of step with environmental reality and technological possibilities. The project will provide a more realistic and resource-efficient ERA-scheme. However, the development needs to be supported by EFSA to be taken up by the risk assessors in the MS. The close collaboration with EFSA in this project, ensures a targeted and operational development of a new ERA-scheme and facilitates the application by end-users and stakeholders, e.g., risk assessors and applicants.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, Systems-based approach, Regulatory needs, Stakeholder engagement

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3 – This project’s key objective is to translate regulatory and policy needs into ERA research issues for the projects involved in 6.4.4 as well as other collaboration projects (see OO5 below). The translation process will be guided by an iterative and knowledge building dialogue with regulators, policymakers and other stakeholders. The dialogue involves mutual knowledge exchange between researchers in all projects of 6.4.4.

OO4 – See comment for OO3 (iterative knowledge-building dialogue).

OO5 – As a representative of all projects in Activity 6.4.4 this project is approached by and actively seeks out to establish collaboration with relevant other projects (Horizon Europe and other). A knowledge exchange platform with monthly meetings for all partners in 6.4.4 has been established.

OO12 – This project is designed to support a step-wise transition towards systems-based assessments, a process that includes a wide range of stakeholders. A scientific reframing of (E)RA driven by integration of knowledge from many different science disciplines requires an iterative knowledge building processes involves regulatory stakeholders.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- € PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4.
- € WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- € T 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- € Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.

- € Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- € T 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- € WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)
- AD6.7: Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (M24)

Project Reports:

- R1: Clarifying regulatory needs (Drivers of change, Problem description, Future state of ERA, Gap analysis, Short term-remedies and potential long-term solutions, Prioritised Areas of work and research questions) (M22)
- R2: Clarifying regulatory needs (M34)

Projects Landmarks:

L1: First recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M22)

Partners List:

KEMI (SE); UBA(DE); FOEN (CH); ANSES (FR); EFSA (EU); ULUND (SE); NIVA (NO); UOS (DE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Expected Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 30 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 8 910 €

P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEXPCS2		
Project Manager	Mikaela Gönczi	SLU	Se
	Mikaela.Gonczi@slu.se		
Deputy Project manager	Gusatf Boström	SLU	SE
	Gusatf.bostrom@slu.se		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	24*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU		

* The project has been broken at M24 (that corresponds to the end of phase 3 of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then new projects could be launched for the period M25-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims at investigating if the predictions in the exposure part of the ERA carried out in the context of authorization of PPPs under the Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 can be simplified, improved in predictive potential and validated by maintaining the level of protection required. In 2019 the SLU Centre for Pesticides in the Environment (CKB) at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences developed a new method for calculating predicted concentrations in surface water (called PEC CKB) (Boström et al., 2019). This approach successfully extends the type of methods which predict environmental concentrations of PPPs in water bodies with fewer input parameters, but on the basis of established knowledge of environmental processes (e.g. Kattwinkel et al. 2011). The proposed calculation method is very simple and requires minimal input data. Further work would aim at achieving even closer conformity between predicted (PEC) and measured (MEC) concentrations by focusing improvements on the most important factors of the calculations. This proposed project aims at exploring further ways of simplifying the PEC calculations within the ERA. This can be pursued through testing and further development of the PEC CKB or similar concepts like the German models Exposit and GERDA, and through comparing the predictability of these simpler models to MEC from different EU member states (MS). The new models will be validated against currently existing models and monitoring data additional to those used to derive the models.

Main expected outputs of the project

The comparison of several models for exposure, including different parameters, with the same dataset will give us information on differences and similarities of the models' predictive capacity and protection level. By various analyses we will be able to evaluate which factor are most important to explain the concentrations in the environment and how the predictive capacity can be improved. We will also assess the transferability of the models between data from different MS and identify factors that play an important role such as geography, climate or soil properties.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users of the research are mainly risk assessors in the context of authorization of plant protection products at MS and EU level. In addition, the project aims to contribute to a transition to a systems-based ERA by facilitating reusability of data generated within the ERA. In order to efficiently allocate resources, we need to examine if the ERA used for plant protection products can be simplified.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, exposure assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to fulfil the need to develop the ecological RA approaches to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically as identified in the DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- WP 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments

- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

A member of the former FOCUS (FORum for the Co-ordination of pesticide fate models and their USE) surface water workgroup is participating in the project. Since their work is the basis of the exposure component of the existing ERA this will improve the possibility that the results of the project will be implemented in a regulatory context. Other groups working with exposure models, such as GERDA will also be contacted.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Technical report describing comparison of different existing methods for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments validated against monitoring data from various European geographical regions (Year 2).

Project Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List:

SLU (SE), UFZ (DE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), University of Osnabrück UOS (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL), UoB (UK). Regulatory core group: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU).

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Expected Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 34 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 17 127 €

P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEFF CS3		
Project Manager	Matthias Liess	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Paulo Sousa	UC	PT
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ		

* The project has been broken at M36 (that corresponds to the end of phase 2 of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then new projects could be launched for the period

M37-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The risk assessment process of PPPs has developed into a highly sophisticated, time consuming and complex process. Despite this elaborated procedure, the occurrence of PPP has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that “Member States shall ensure that use of plant protection products does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species” (EU Commission, 2011). The aim of this project is moving towards a protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources required while keeping it as information-rich as necessary. This will be achieved by including only the information and processes that have been proven by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling to be relevant. This improves the extrapolation of effect information from lower tier laboratory investigations to field effects. The ecosystem effects will be modelled with the stress addition model (Liess et al. 2016) and compared with the effects monitored at the ecosystem level. This approach enables to identify the most parsimonious description of ecosystem processes related to the effects of PPP. A differentiation related to the mode of actions (MOA) of PPPs and in relation to the respective groups of species will be performed. This project will contribute to the development of a more resource-efficient and realistic ERA as described in 6.4.4.1. The framework will be made accessible by a software package to enable a practicable and reproducible ERA.

Main expected outputs of the project

Field monitoring data related to exposure and effects of PPP in a great variety of member states will be collated. Currently high-quality data have been identified for Germany, Sweden, Switzerland. Data from a variety of member states in different regions of the EU need to be included to reflect the European diversity. A feedback loop between existing risk assessment thresholds and retrospective ecosystem monitoring results will be formalized to constantly improve the level of realism and validation of ERA. By this the project will enable regulators to identify ecological process to be included into the risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users will be provided with the identification of the relevant factors needed to link laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at the ecosystem level to make better use of lower-tier test information. Additionally, effect information obtained from the ecosystem level will enable to better use higher-tier test information within the risk assessment framework

The implementation of the most relevant environmental factors into the risk assessment process so that the sensitive field populations can be identified and protected and that ERA at the same time strives an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.

Increase regulatory usability by documenting a transparent and easy to follow framework on how effect models can be replicated and adapted to ensure transferability between member states.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Under this project, we aim to collate monitoring data from different member countries to improve current risk assessment of chemicals. This involves validation of models such as SAM covering all relevant chemical and non-chemical stressors occurring in the field. using field monitoring data and hence contribute to risk assessment.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Project Reports:

- Report 1: Technical report on the most relevant factors describing the transfer function that enables a link between laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at ecosystem level. Ranking the relevance of the factors describing the lab to field transfer function. Identification to which extent interactions between PPPs and additional environmental factors increase the sensitivity of field populations (Year 2).
- Report 2: Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism (Year 3).

Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List:

UFZ (DE), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE); UKOLD (DE); ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCIII (ES)

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA (EU), ANSES (FR)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Expected Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 36 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 17 170 €

P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD

Project Title	Benchmark ERA to support the transition towards a holistic paradigm		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPBENCH		
Project Manager	Ralf Schäfer	UKOLD	DE
Deputy Project	schaefer-ralf@uni-landau.de		
	NA		

manager			
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims to ensure that results of any independently performed ERA of a PPP can be used as a benchmark for ERAs of other PPPs, i.e., comparing and ranking risk profiles of PPPs among substances and in different areas (e.g., for selected organism groups) of the ERA when assessed on the basis of similar level of refinement. This project aims to develop concepts and methodologies to improve the ERA so that results from the individual risk assessments become inter-comparable in terms of risk profiles considering each area of the ERA. This helps in delivering consistent ERA results and once compared to monitoring results, it will eventually improve its reliability regarding the estimation of environmental risks. The overall aim of the project is to contribute to a more holistic ERA that manages the overall risk in an efficient manner.

Based on available data sets and case studies on rejected products, the internal and external risk benchmarking will be conducted. Depending on the results, gaps will be identified in current ERA paradigm and short-term remedies proposed. Over the project period, a compatibility methodology will be suggested based on the future ERA paradigm that the partners develop in PARC. The project will thus have a direct impact on the development of an improved ERA under EU regulation 1107/2009.

Main expected outputs of the project

Expected output is an ERA concept and defined methodology to be used as a basis to develop a new guidance for ERA within the authorisation process. The resulting ERA should have an improved performance in terms of capturing the relative risk of different PPPs in a relevant spatial and temporal scale when assessed on the basis of similar data/ level of refinement. The improved ERA should also support systems-based risk assessments and facilitate use down the line, such as improved advisory services and systems-based risk management.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcome of this project will aid the aims defined under 6.4.4.1 to align EU regulations and improve the ERA-scheme by identifying how a risk assessment methodology should be designed to allow for benchmarking of PPPs against each other capturing their relative risk. Furthermore, the complexity of the current ERA will be reduced by identifying key descriptors of PPP-substances (physico-chemical properties, toxicological profiles) and use (exposure related parameters) that have the most weight in the description of the risk. Finally, the consistency of the risk assessments from different tiers regarding individual substances will be evaluated.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring, benchmarking, comparative risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the following PARC operational objectives OO4, OO5, OO10, OO12, OO9, and OO13. The expected output will promote the use of developed concepts with the possibility of their use in

the approval process and also foster the uptake of PARC knowledge to increase stakeholders' awareness. It will also provide some collaboration with other partners thus enabling.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4:
- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Compiled data for internal risk benchmarking (M12)

Report 2: Analyses for internal risk benchmarking accomplished (M27)

Report 3: Database of ERA results and complementary data (M27)

Report 4: Data compiled for external risk benchmarking (M30)

Report 5: Analyses for external risk benchmarking accomplished (M36)

Report 6: Technical report on results of benchmarking analyses with suggestions for methodology and most important factors having an impact on the result of the ERA (M42)

Projects Landmarks:

L1: Compiled data for internal risk benchmarking (M12)

Partners List:

UKOLD (DE), UFZ (DE), ISCIII (ES); EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE).

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Expected Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 33 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 13 987 €

P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII

Project Title	Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPOS

Project Manager	José Tarazona Jose.TARAZONA@efsa.europa.eu	ISCIH	ES
Deputy Project manager	Matthias Liess matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIH		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Despite elaborate regulation of agricultural pesticides, their occurrence has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This situation does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that states “Member States shall ensure that use of plant protection products does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species.” (EU Commission, 2011). This project investigates how multiple PPP and additional stressors can be integrated in ERA on a landscape level considering agricultural intensification and vulnerability of populations. The aim is moving the ERA paradigm from single chemical-crop combination to landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures into the current risk assessment methods. Due to the complexity of environmental landscape-scale assessments, the identification of the key “drivers” for exposure and effects and the benchmarking proposed in the other three projects constitute a prerequisite. This project will build landscape models considering the results from the three previous projects, which will be used for the identification of the key modelling blocks under different landscape conditions. In addition, the EFSA proposals for setting protection goals based on ecosystem services and biodiversity in ERA will be implemented to develop risk characterisation tools that could be used as information source for environmental impact assessments; this will help to overcome the currently too fragmented ERA approaches.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project has direct connections and will benefit from the outcomes of the projects aiming to compare predictions with monitoring data, using the agricultural landscape characteristics for strengthening the feedback loop from environmental monitoring and vigilance and ensure focus on factors that trigger the risk and overall impact on biodiversity in terrestrial agro-biosystems and aquatic ecosystems. In addition to supporting regulatory decisions, including the design and implementation of National Plans under the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD), a complementary long-term goal is to deliver management tools to advise and support practitioners to make informed decision (e.g. considering in selection of a PPP versus another PPP the local and regional levels/ ecotype) in the design and implementation of Integrated Pest Management and optimizing use and effects of ecosystem restorations with multiple purposes (i.e. improving biodiversity, reducing PPP pollution etc. through e.g. Nature Based Solutions).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to deliver methodologies and tools to promote a transition to a system-based ERA. End-users will be actors responsible for a systems-based risk assessment, such as authorisation, enforcement and agricultural advisors. Comprehensive data on environmental impact and tools will enable these actors to take informed decisions.

The project will provide direct support to the implementation of measures under the SUD and reduction of pesticide impacts under the EU Green Deal and specifically the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The integration of farm management with agricultural landscape characteristics will provide support to decisions on sustainability at local, regional and national level, supporting the integration of sustainability concepts in food production and the CAP.

These new approach for ERA would support other policies, including WFD and the Habitats Directive. Optimizing the overlap of concepts and terminologies between central compartments in environmental management is essential for a (cost)efficient collaboration between different public management bodies. The outcomes will successfully pinpointing key stressors at regional level that impair biodiversity, ecological quality, and ecosystem services.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, landscape assessment, multiple stressors, holistic risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will develop new conceptual approaches, methodologies and tools for improving the environmental risk assessment of pesticides (007). The project outputs will provide additional value to regulatory risk assessments, facilitating the interpretation of the risk characterisation outcome as environmental impacts, supporting not only the regulatory process for PPPs, but also associated regulatory needs connected to biodiversity protection and sustainable agriculture (0012, 009). Direct links with EU projects, and EU Agencies activities have been already identified (004, 005). A key element for the project is to address the combined effects of pesticides on the environment, offering realistic alternatives to the current substance-by-substance regulatory approach (007).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.2 and 6.3. The landscape approach for ERA will be used as the basis for case studies on aggregated human pesticide exposure from the environment, including the integrative prospective assessments (case study under 6.2) and a retrospective assessment (case study under 6.3) using human biomonitoring data
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and BiodivERsA.

The proposed work will be interlinked with several national and international projects including the Norwegian Agriculture monitoring program for pesticides and supporting cumulative risk assessments (<https://www.nibio.no/en/subjects/environment/the-norwegian-agricultural-environmental-monitoring-programme-jova>), the project « Cumulative hazard and risk assessment of complex mixtures and multiple stressors (MixRisk) » (www.niva.no/mixrisk), and several activities of NIVAs Computational Toxicology Program, NCTP (www.niva.no/nctp).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Project Reports:

- Report 1: Conceptual models for aggregate and combined exposure to pesticides at landscape level covering the local and regional needs as well as national and EU needs. The tools will support the selection of the best IPM approach allowing an ERA-based scientifically sound assessment of sustainability regarding pesticide use as well as a comparative impact with other stressors (M12)
- R2: Case studies report (M30)
- R3: Final conceptual approach, including problem formulation and implementation options (M36)

Projects Landmarks:

- Landmark 1: Identification on protection needs covering also for SUD, CAP and biodiversity strategy (M12),
- Landmark 2: Prioritisation of case studies (M12),
- Landmark 3: Verification of key elements for landscape ERA from the case studies (M24),
- Landmark 4: Extrapolation of the case study outcomes into quantitative landscape ERA tools (M30),
- Landmark 5: Adaptation of the tools to different regulatory/policy and voluntary initiatives through networking activities (M36).

Partners List:

ISCHII (ES), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück UOS (DE), UOB (UK), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), UAVR (PT), SYKE (FI), INERIS (FR), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH)

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Expected Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 86 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 39 524 €

WP7 FAIR data – 3 PROJECTS

In the context of the EU's Open Science Policy (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en), PARC will promote harmonisation of data and exchange between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology...) to promote transparency, support RA, and allow for reuse. It will ensure data and associated information is FAIR, i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, and addresses the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679) related challenges for data exchange.

T7.1 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and DMP - No project submitted at present

Data “FAIRification” will be a key activity of PARC to facilitate data reuse. Implementing FAIR data practices is among the main operational objectives of PARC and will be measured by the proportion of datasets developed in PARC that will be FAIR, and the number of deliverables reusing existing data. A

common Data Management Plan (DMP) will be established and shared.

The PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) will define the principles and conditions that govern provision, management, access, use and re-use of data, in line with the FAIR principles, while taking into account legal aspects (i.e. GDPR), security, transparency, sustainability and quality of the data. WP7 will provide the framework (guiding principles, data policy, framework DMP), set up specific methods and tools and guidance to FAIRify data and facilitate data reuse in the R&I WPs and in regulatory agencies. Through training, FAIR implementation will be broadly embedded in PARC. PARC will establish collaboration with specialised FAIR initiatives and projects (e.g. EOSC-Life, ENVRIFAIR, WorldFAIR), and collaborate with experts from the Go FAIR Foundation to kick start the FAIRification process in the first two years.

T7.2 Data libraries – 2 PROJECTS

Data will be made FAIR at the source whenever possible, described by FAIR metadata, and associated with a persistent identifier. PARC will use established FAIRification approaches such as the Three Point FAIRification framework (3PFF), elaboration of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) defining concrete implementation choices for each of the 15 FAIR principles (Schultes et al.¹, 2020; Wilkinson et al.², 2016), and established software solutions to manage FAIR data sources. Specific use cases will enable the multi-faceted FAIRification process to be developed gradually and pragmatically. Compatibility assessment, efforts for harmonisation and maximum interoperability will start from these FIPs. Standardised templates will be created, as necessary, based on domain specific standards, formats and vocabularies whenever available. PARC will perform landscape exercises and FAIRness assessments to identify potential partners to functionally integrate and exchange different types of data from different domains, and different national and transnational levels. It will build further upon DG ENV's Common Data Platform for Chemicals (CPCD), which will be the default option for data that are currently used in standard RA. A joint exercise will be set up to align PARC activities with the CPCD roadmap. For data that are currently not commonly used in regulatory RA, the content and accessibility of specialised data centres (e.g. ESFRI (European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructure) research infrastructures (i.e., EIRENE, ELIXIR), MS Open Data initiatives, domain-specific repositories, institutional repositories, open generic repositories such as Zenodo) will be explored, integrating efforts and achievements from recently ended projects such as EuroMix (<https://www.euromixproject.eu/>), NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.net/>) and HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>), ongoing project clusters such as the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) cluster or the European Cluster to Improve Identification of Endocrine Disruptors (EURION), and community databases such as NORMAN. Integration with IPCHEM – the EC's Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring - and the OECD eChemPortal will be implemented also, through semantic mapping of the underpinning data schema. A dedicated FAIR data hub hosting core functionalities (such as querying of data, use of searchable catalogues and metadata services) complementary to existing platforms, will be implemented. Establishment of new FAIR Data Points (FDPs) (Thompson et al.³, 2020) or dedicated repositories will be considered in cases where existing solutions do not satisfy the needs of the PFDP.

A7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.2 PARC FAIR data hub – 2 PROJECTS

P7.2.2.a Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO

Project Title	Chemicals in the Environment data reuse
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENV DATA (RE)USE

Project Manager	Richard Hůlek richard.hulek@recetox.muni.cz	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Deputy Project manager	Jana Klánová jana.klanova@recetox.muni.cz	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Over the years various tools and database platforms were created to provide for storage, analysis, and visualization of occurrence data and trends in chemical exposure in the environment at global, EU, and national levels (for example, GMOS, EMEP, EBAS, GENASIS, GMP data warehouse, NORMAN, IpCHEM, etc.). Nevertheless, each of the tools or knowledge hubs was developed for different communities and comprise different services and scopes. Available datasets are often organized by environmental matrix, contain different scopes and contents, and are at various stages of development (harmonization principles, ontology, tools).

The environmental monitoring and exposure component of PARC explores the presence of (priority) chemicals in a multicompartiment environment and the resulting exposure of humans when chemical substances come from multiple sources and move along different pathways, fostering a “one health” chemical risk assessment strategy. Aggregated, combined, and cumulative exposures will be assessed through surveys of the co-occurrence of chemical substances, their metabolites, and degradation products in different matrices.

Members in R&I work packages in PARC ask for solutions to access/connect to existing data resources* in monitoring programs, databases, and libraries to help them with mapping and accessing the information available in the various data resources. This comprises a need to extract and combine information on (priority) chemicals in the environment that will then guide their further work on improvements of human and environmental/ecological risk assessment.

* *Data resources in this project and in WP7 represent “the major existing and planned databases, repositories, platforms, registries, portals and libraries relevant for chemical risk assessment”.*

Main expected outputs of the project

The project’s main goal is to support the reuse of existing data in relation to environmental exposure and the production and management of newly generated data in accordance with FAIR principles and in view of the concepts of Open Data and One substance, one assessment. Therefore, the project is structured around three main activities:

- i) map the existing data resources relevant for environmental exposure to chemicals and assess the current landscape;
- ii) when having sufficient knowledge about the existing landscape, develop solutions for accessing and re(using) exposure data available in the existing/newly developed data resources,
- iii) cooperate and support other WPs in producing and managing data in line with FAIR principles and in accordance with the Open Data approach, which should ultimately support the concept of “One substance, once assessment”.

This will be achieved via a series of steps:

- a) mapping the existing data resources relevant for exposure to chemicals in the environment (*landscaping*),

MI-12

b) comparison of existing platforms and systems and assessment of their FAIRness (*architecture & assessment*), **MI-M12**

Output (a+b): selection of best-fit components (cornerstones) for “Initial architecture for PARC FAIR data platform for chemicals risk assessment”.

c) creating access to existing data resources that successfully passed through the FAIRness assessment and updating other data resources so that they become FAIR (*solutions for data reuse*), **M10**

d) developing FAIR data libraries if the appropriate solutions are missing (*solutions for FAIR data libraries*), **M12**

Output (c+d): online platform(s) connecting existing data resources on (priority) chemicals for reuse in risk assessment in PARC (and in particular in WPs 4, 6, 8), but also for national users, regulatory agencies, and the research community.

The ultimate goals of the project are that:

- data on (priority) chemicals in across environmental matrices are available for re-use between different risk assessment actors,
- existing and new relevant data resources are connected across silos and geographical areas (national, EU, and international)
- data to be re-used are harmonized, validated, FAIR, and cover the most complete available datasets with relevant metadata and are easily accessible.
- PARC generated data are stored in a FAIR online platform

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project contributes to REACH - supports human and environmental/ecological risk assessment, and allows for reuse of data and knowledge - regulatory agencies to have direct access to environmental data, and indirectly that data will be available for reuse in models and toolboxes or for addressing research questions.

Key words: (meta)data, data resources, libraries, FAIR, harmonization, (open) access, open data, environmental exposure

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project supports the achievement and is closely aligned with operational objective 0010 “Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment”. It aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR data on chemicals (specifically environmental exposure data) between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse both scientific and regulatory data for application and innovation in risk assessment, thus empowering the European Green Deal Data Space.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: The project in 7.2 would need to establish synergies with existing projects such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users’ uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans and also shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI).

WP7: Data management plan: The project is planned and will be implemented in task 7.2. Therefore, it is expected that partners in 7.2 will assist in the development of DMPs in other projects, mainly of WP 4, 6, and 8.

WP9: Training, laboratory network: Currently, the capacities and expertise of partners involved in WP7, and in particular task 7.2, are not considered sufficient to respond to the various needs that may arise from PARC WPs in relation to the data reuse and data FAIRfication. This issue will be circumvented by employing Go Fair Foundation experts who will assist in building a network of experts within PARC (i.e.,

of the FAIR implementation task group comprising a subset of data champions and data liaisons). Training will consist of several “train the trainer” sessions which will be organized and performed in close collaboration with task 9.4 on Training. Apart from task 9.4, the project will cooperate with tasks 9.1 and 9.2 in the development of the best-fit architecture for WP9 catalogues on laboratory and exposure monitoring networks. This cooperation between WP9 and WP7 is already ongoing and described in more detail in WP9 led by ISCIII and MU.

Other WPs:

For this particular project, close collaboration is expected with task 4.2 Environmental exposure and monitoring. Projects developed and implemented under 4.2 will focus on environmental exposure data and multisource monitoring. It is therefore expected that data from various data resources would need to be brought together, assessed against the FAIR principles, and combined to allow for multiple source exposure assessment. This project will cooperate and support 4.2 project partners in finding and applying the best solutions for accessing all the relevant data, their connection, re(use) and management in accordance with FAIR principles and if needed, making them available and accessible via a FAIR platform/repository. Similarly, close cooperation is foreseen in regard to WP6 and WP8, whenever data generated outside or within PARC are to be used in models.

The specific needs arising from the R&I WPs and solutions to be developed in 7.2 will be defined as individual project cases, so-called “use cases”. For each relevant R&I WP project, a data champion (from within WP7) and a data liaison (from within the respective WP and project) will be appointed to support the establishment of a horizontal link between WP7 (task 7.2) and the project of WPx. These will then further cooperate in the preparation of the data management plan and its implementation, and the definition of a use case, if relevant.

Links outside PARC

This project serves experts/data holders and data users in tasks 4.2, 4.3, 6.2., 6.4., and WP8 but would need to establish synergies with existing projects and infrastructures, such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users’ uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans, and shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project will partly contribute to the following deliverables of WP7 (task 7.1):

D7.1. Data Management Plan (DMP) (M6)

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (M18)

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (M12)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (M24)

Project Reports: None identified at present.

Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: MU (CZ), VITO (BE), UFZ (DE), BRGM (FR), UNILU (LU), ISSEP (BE), JSI (SI), ANSES (FR), NIVA (NO), UBA (DE), KWR (NL), AUTH (GR), UNIVIE (AT)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 184 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 14 090 €

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Project Title	FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HBMdatasets		
Project Manager	Jan Theunis Jan.theunis@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Dirk Devriendt Dirk.devriendt.ext@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project deals with availability and (re)use of existing Human Biomonitoring (HBM) datasets (including datasets from HBM4EU, but also datasets produced in other projects), as well as with new datasets generated in PARC (i.e., in Task 4.1). HBM dataset will be made available as FAIR datasets for potential reuse by the broad risk assessment community. HBM datasets are challenging for reuse as they contain personal, sensitive data, which poses specific challenges for storage and reuse, related to ethical and legal issues. The full strength of the data for scientific and regulatory purposes will only be attained if analyses can be carried out on the individual data, if the coherence of the dataset is maintained, and if the data can be linked to different domains (e.g., health, biomolecular, spatial-environmental data, food, consumption, occupational). Finally, HBM datasets contain analyses of chemical metabolites for which no standardized identifications exist.

HBM datasets will be made available to allow reuse by different user groups: scientific users who may want to reuse the entire datasets (for research questions on exposure determinants, geographical comparisons, time trends, exposure-effect analyses, link with environmental sources, ..., comparing modelled exposure with observed exposure, ...), regulatory users who may be interested in the core occurrence data (for assessment and follow-up, integration of HBM data in models and toolboxes), and the general public. As such this project indirectly supports multiple regulatory processes and frameworks through support for improved human risk assessment, and for reuse of data and knowledge.

The broader relevance of the project lies in the development and implementation of scalable solutions for reuse of personal sensitive data while safeguarding legal and ethical constraints, including cross-domain linking of data, semantic and technical interoperability, and development and implementation of cross-domain ontologies, vocabularies and metadata schemes.

The project will be strongly aligned with Task 4.1, and more specifically with Task 4.1.5 as part of a sustainable HBM system.

Methodologically the project will investigate the feasibility to make use new developments in federated data infrastructures and federated data analysis. These methods are still in an early phase.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Short-term operational data infrastructure for exchange of HBM data between PARC partners
- Hybrid federated data infrastructure allowing
 - Reuse of HBM datasets by *new parties* while respecting privacy and consent

- New data collected in PARC
- New PARC partners working with the data
 - Integration with *external HBM datasets* from other projects (e.g. EHEN projects)
 - Federated data analysis
- Metadata, schema mappings and search engines to increase *findability and interoperability* across disciplines (health, biomolecular, lifestyle, ...) for cross-domain linking
- Identification scheme for metabolites linking metabolites and parent chemicals

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Facilitated access and reuse of both (individual) HBM datasets and core HBM (occurrence) data by researchers and risks assessors

Regulatory agencies improve human risk assessment

Decision makers evaluate effectiveness of adopted regulatory measures (Chemicals policy)

Researchers make new generation risk assessment tools and models available

Key words: human biomonitoring, FAIR data, personal sensitive data, federated data analysis, metadata schemas, ontologies

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project supports the achievement and is closely aligned with operational objective 0010 “Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment”. It aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR data on chemicals (specifically human biomonitoring data) between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse both scientific and regulatory data for application and innovation in risk assessment, thus empowering the European Green Deal Data Space.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is obviously strongly related with Task 4.1 and more specifically 4.1.4 and 4.1.5, with Task 6.2 for linking predicted exposure to observed exposure, with Task 8.3 for integrating HBM data in the modelling toolbox, and with Task 2.2 (data layer of PARCopedia).

WP3: a strategy will be developed on communication and awareness on FAIR data, both in general and in specific communities. This project will benefit from organisation of synergy networks and networking events. Collaboration on these aspects will be discussed with WP3.

Internally in WP7 the project will exchange with Task 7.1 on data policies, and on training and awareness on FAIR data, and with Task 7.3 for exploration of novel approaches towards enhanced privacy preservation for personal sensitive data (e.g., federated data analysis).

WP9 will be involved for the inventory of HBM projects and datasets, and for collaboration on training and awareness on FAIR data.

Links outside PARC

The project will start from the achievements of HBM4EU. It will link with other initiatives that are working on similar data, such as the European Human Exposome Network, EOSC-Life, EIRENE RI, and on generic metadata schemas and ontologies, such as HL7, Bioschemas, RDA, OHDSI. It will align with the EC’s roadmap and activities towards a Common Open Platform on Chemicals data, and i.e., with IPCHEM’s activities on HBM data.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (M18)

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M42)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (M12)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (M24)
 Indirectly, the project will contribute to deliverables in the related Tasks mentioned above.
 ADs will be defined when drafting AWP2.

Project Reports: None identified at present.

Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List:

VITO (BE); MU (CZ); UU (SW); UBA (DE); ISSEP (BE); JSI (Slovenia), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 43 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 152 950 €

A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation

No project submitted at present.

T7.3 Innovative analyses – 1 PROJECT

Innovative analytical approaches to maximise use and insights from increasing amounts of open and FAIR data for RA will be introduced. Promising approaches will be applied to use cases, selected together with WPs 4-8, to evaluate and showcase their usefulness. A range of advanced approaches will be developed and documented, including pooling and meta-analysis of heterogeneous datasets, uncertainty analysis, and knowledge and text mining via on-the-fly ontological mapping, Bayesian networks, machine learning and other approaches. Analytical tools will be made available as FAIR algorithms and supplied to WPs 4-8 for use and integration into toolboxes. Good practice guidelines describing the approaches and their applications for regulatory risk assessment will be published.

A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data – 1 PROJECT

P7.3.3a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV

Project Title Alternative Predictive Testing Strategy for the Safety of Chemicals based on Integrative Systems Toxicology

Project ALT-IST

Acronym (15 letters max)

Project Manager	Vikas Kumar Vikas.kumar@iispv.cat	IISPV	ES
Deputy Project manager	Luke Slater l.slater.1@bham.ac.uk	UoB	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	6	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.3.3
Project Id	P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The ALT-IST project is a part of T7.3. It involves the development of an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and risk assessment. Followed up by the development of tools using the database of risk assessment. Several regulatory agencies such as OECD, EFSA and ECHA have adopted evidence-based methodologies for risk assessment i.e. AOP (Adverse outcome pathway). The utmost requirement for developing this mechanistic pathway is data. The well-curated, connected, structured and unambiguous database will ease the accessibility of information and also compliments AOP development by filling experimental data gaps. Ontology-based data integration will further help toward the broader application of Advance data science including network biology and machine learning to predict the chemical adverse effect on the human system. The developed tools and methodologies will be validated by real case studies selected in collaboration with other WPs (WP4, WP5, WP6). Project will explore different text mining tools (e.g. INDRA, TRIPS or other tools) during scoping study to understand its usability and set the agenda for future research needs. Aside the application in developing (quantitative) adverse outcome pathways and supporting network biology approaches to identify and describe hazards in relation to disease development (i.e. AOP), other applications of AI, network approaches, text mining and ontology assisted hazard identification are foreseen as well. These, to accommodate the need for the faster detection of potential emerging risks from imported goods/chemicals into the EU, as well as the identification of data gaps within heterogeneous hazard data sources to help the further prioritization of testing.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and risk assessment. Linked case studies with WP5 and WP6 will establish NAM for risk assessment using new data discovery and integration of other available data and the data developed in different work packages. This will involve ontology-based data curation and its automated maintenance using NLP (Natural language processing). In addition, developed ontology will assist the further development of QAOP in collaboration with different partners.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project is designed according to the perspective of a computational toxicologist, epidemiologists and risk assessor because it introduces a novel *in-silico* approach toward defining associations between human health outcomes and exposure to chemicals through the integrated use of advanced analytical and predictive tools for hazard and risk assessment and chemical screening for regulatory purposes. It will employ natural language processing, cheminformatics and bioinformatics techniques directly to the data mining of the integrated data set which will lead to the advancement of *in-silico* methodologies for OECD's integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) and support the 3R strategy of chemical testing.

Key words:

Ontology, Text mining, Artificial intelligence, Natural Language Processing, System toxicology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO9, OO10, and OO12 by developing and implementing R&I work programmes for new in silico tools and generating results and knowledge (data discovery from text mining) to support the use of new approaches and methods (AI assisted text mining), develop models and innovative concept for RA (predictive AI models) to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes. The project will also

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), facilitate PARC wide collaboration with different case studies and promoting cooperation with other R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6) and implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Task 5.3.2: AOP developed in 5.3.2 can be used as case study and data generated in this project can help in developing AOPs

Task 6.1: data generated in this project can help in the development of qAOPs and IATA.

Task 6.2: mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through targeted data mining and network modelling

WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in the toolbox

WP9: training of informatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

Relevant text mining AI data initiatives (ELIXIR, Bio.Tools). Furthermore, the project is closely linked to other EU project in similar domain like EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.4: 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA (M36)

Project Reports:

Report 1: Scoping study of AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment (M18)

Report 2: Report on the available tool and framework, and different methodologies (like NLP and text mining) used for human health risk assessment, including ontology development.

Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Workshop on Ontology-assisted text mining for human health risk assessment strategy (M10)

Landmark 2: Case Study 1 and 2 presentation of results with respective stakeholders (M24)

Landmark 3: Integrated knowledge base /datasets for selected case studies (like AOPs development) established (M30)

Partners List:

IISPV (ES), UoB (UK), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (GR), MU (CH), UL-LACDR (NL), KI (SE), NIVA (NO), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Cost:

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 29 PM
Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 12 110 €

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

No project submitted at present.

List of Project Reports, Project Landmarks and Deliverables, Additional deliverables, Milestones to which the projects contribute

Only Deliverables and Additional Deliverables are contractual documents to be submitted to HaDEA.

Project reports and landmarks correspond to intermediate or significant stage in the development of the scientific results of the projects that will be part of the annual **Additional Deliverables** or **Deliverables**.

WP4

Project ID	D_AD_M-R_L ¹ number	Title	Expected delivery date	Project end	Partner Responsible
P4.1.1.2.a	R1	First interim progress report	M18	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	R2	Second interim progress report	M42	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	R3	Third interim progress report	M66	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	R4	Final report	M81	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	L1	Selection of the studies to contribute to the General Survey	M8	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	L2	All sample collections completed	M48	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	L3	All chemical analysis completed	M53	81	ISCIII/VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	L4	All data available for planned statistical evaluation	M56	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	D4.3	D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey	M36	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	D4.8	D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey	M48	81	VITO
P4.1.1.2.a	D4.12	D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey	M60	81	UBA
P4.1.1.2.a	D4.13	D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach	M81	81	INERIS
P4.1.1.4.a	AD4.8	AD4.8 Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies	M18	81	TTL
P4.1.1.4.b	L1	Mapping exercise: inventory of opportunities and barriers in each country	M1 -M6	48	tbd
P4.1.1.4.b	L2	Setting up the sentinel system in a selection of countries on national levels, network building	M7 -M12	48	tbd
P4.1.1.4.b	L3	Implement proof-of-concept of the sentinel system for recruitment and sample collection for the general population survey in adults in the selected countries:	M13-M42	48	tbd
P4.1.1.4.b	L4	Evaluate the successfulness	M43-M48	48	tbd
P4.1.1.4.b	L5	Expand the network/awareness campaigns/ Design an EU-wide sentinel system	M49-M84	48	tbd
P4.1.1.4.b	D4.13	D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach	M81	48	INERIS
P4.1.1.4.c	L1	Study protocol	M12	48	RUMC
P4.1.1.4.c	D4.7	D4.7 1st Progress report on occupational surveys.	M48	48	TTL
P4.1.1.4.d	L1	List of selected chemicals for each waste stream and corresponding exposure biomarkers	M10	48	ENSP-UNL, TTL, LNS
P4.1.1.4.d	L2	Study protocol including standard operating procedures	M12	48	TTL, LNS
P4.1.1.4.d	L3	Online training on the SOPs implementation	M14-M16	48	ENSP, INSA, TTL

P4.1.1.4.d	L4	Field work collection completed	M27	48	All
P4.1.1.4.d	L5	Analyses of the samples collected	M32	48	All
P4.1.1.4.d	L6	Data analysis completed	M36	48	All
P4.1.1.4.d	L7	First paper with main messages	M39	48	All
P4.1.1.4.d	L8	Policy briefs and guidance for companies	M42	48	All
P4.1.1.4.d	L9	Final results and recommendations	M48	48	All
P4.1.1.4.d	D4.7	D4.7 1st Progress Report on occupational surveys	M48	48	TTL
P4.1.3.1.a	R1	Substance dossier on Cyhalothrin (pyrethroid) and proposal of HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level	M12	36	UBA
P4.1.3.1.a	R2	Substance dossier on UV filter Uvinul A plus and HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level	M12	36	UBA
P4.1.3.1.a	R3	Substance dossier on aluminium and compounds and HBM-GVs for the general population and workers, coordinated at project level	M12	36	ANSES
P4.1.3.1.a	L1	Draft substance dossier on nickel	tbd	36	TTL
P4.1.3.1.a	AD4.3	AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances) (postponed from M12 to M24)	M24	36	UBA
P4.1.3.3.a	R1	Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including Standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data	M14	52	SpF
P4.1.3.3.a	R2	Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC general and occupational surveys	M12	52	VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	R3	Progress report on investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts	M22	52	SpF
P4.1.3.3.a	R4	Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome	M52	52	SpF & VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	L1	Identification of effect biomarkers associated with exposure to the chemicals and age groups studied in (add ons of) the general HBM survey and first occupational surveys + implementation plan	M12	52	VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	L2	Data management plan on implementation in the HBM4EU surveys	M15	52	SpF & VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	L3	Finalization of the case study, data analysis and data transfer	M40	52	SpF & VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	MS10	MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys	M12	52	VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	AD4.1	AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	52	SPF
P4.1.3.3.a	AD4.2	AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (postponed from M12 to M36)	M36	52	ISCIH
P4.1.3.3.a	D4.3	D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey	M36	52	VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	D4.8	D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey	M48	52	VITO
P4.1.3.3.a	D4.12	D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey	M60	52	UBA
P4.1.3.3.a	D2.22	D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report	M81	52	INSERM
P4.1.4.2.a	R1	Statistical analysis plan	M18	36	VITO
P4.1.4.2.a	R2	Progress report statistical analyses	M36	36	VITO
P4.1.4.2.a	L1	Access to the HBM4EU data is granted	M14	36	VITO
P4.1.4.2.a	D7.1	D7.1 Data management plan	M6	36	TNO
P4.1.4.2.a	MS7	MS7 Establishment of working groups	M12	36	ANSES

P4.1.5.a	R1	1st Interim progress report	M24	66	VITO
P4.1.5.a	R2	2nd interim progress report	M48	66	VITO
P4.1.5.a	R3	Final report	M66	66	VITO
P4.1.5.a	D2.22	D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report	M81	66	INSERM
P4.2.a	R1	Final report on on-going projects	M36	36	INERIS/AU
P4.2.a	L1	Draft technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows)	M12	36	INERIS/AU
P4.2.a	AD4.5	AD4.5. Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	36	INERIS, AU
P4.2.a	AD4.4	AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories (postponed from M12 to M24)	M24	36	INERIS, AU
P4.2.b ²	R1	Final project report (PR)	M30	30	AU/INERIS
P4.2.b	L1	Workshop 3 to reach consensus for technical specifications/features for the prioritisation methodology and the on-line tool	M18	30	INERIS/AU/UBA
P4.2.b	L2	Launch of the online operational tool for prioritization of environmental multi-source monitoring	M24	30	tbd
P4.2.b	L3	Results of case studies	M28	30	AU/INERIS/UBA
P4.2.b	L4	Results of first implementation of the online tool	M28	30	tbd
P4.2.b	D4.1	D4.1. Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals / matrices / endpoints for projects	M20	30	INERIS
P4.3.1.a	R1	Common definitions for NTA/EDA approaches	M12	12	MU
P4.3.1.a	L1	Draft concept paper	M9	12	MU
P4.3.1.a	L2	Submitted concept paper	M12	12	MU
P4.3.1.a	AD4.6	AD4.6 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTA/EDA approaches – M12 (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	12	INRAE, VUA
P4.3.1.b	R1	Protocol/guidances for QA/QC in suspect and non-target screening methods	M36	36	WR
P4.3.1.b	R2	Guidance on identification (levels) of substances found by SS/NTS	M36	36	WR
P4.3.1.b	L1	Completion of review of existing QA/QC procedures in HRMS-based SS/NTS	M20	36	tbd
P4.3.1.b	L2	Completion of review of existing QA/QC procedures in EDA	M20	36	tbd
P4.3.1.b	L3	First draft guidance on best practices in non-target measurements	M24	36	tbd
P4.3.1.b	L4	Verification of practical feasibility of procedures and criteria from draft guidance	M30	36	tbd
P4.3.1.b	AD4.5	AD4.5 Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	36	INERIS, AU
P4.3.1.b	MS7	MS7 Establishment of working groups	M12	36	ANSES
P4.3.1.c	L1	Conceptual framework for innovative (self-)sampling for early warning monitoring tools has been established	M40	60	tbd
P4.3.1.c	L2	Conceptual framework for integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning systems has been established	M50	60	tbd

P4.3.1.c	D4.10	D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	M60	60	VUA/SLU
P4.3.1.d	R1	Report on the Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS	M60	60	EHESP
P4.3.1.d	L1	Conduct a strategical review of already existing initiatives and tools worldwide with all involved partners to select the best options for the envisaged workflow	M9	60	EHESP
P4.3.1.d	L2	Assignment of most of the tasks and development to all partners completed	M12	60	EHESP
P4.3.1.d	L3	Release of an operational prototype version of the user-friendly workflow	M12	60	EHESP
P4.3.1.d	L4	All planned outputs on track	M60	60	EHESP
P4.3.1.d	D4.9	D.4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from suspect/NTS approaches (e.g. inspired from W4M/Galaxy)	M54	60	INRAE
P4.3.2.a	L1	Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners	M6	48	INRAE
P4.3.2.a	L2	Sample sourcing and sharing completed	M12	48	INRAE
P4.3.2.a	L3	At least 50% of planned analyses completed	M24	48	INRAE
P4.3.2.a	L4	All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track	M48	48	INRAE
P4.3.2.a	D.4.5	D.4.5: 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring	M48	48	INRAE
P4.3.2.b ²	L1	Refined study design of case studies co-built and completed with all involved partners	M24	60	tbd
P4.3.2.b	L2	Sample sourcing and sharing completed	M30	60	tbd
P4.3.2.b	L3	At least 50% of planned analyses completed	M48	60	tbd
P4.3.2.b	L4	All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track	M60	60	tbd
P4.3.2.b	L5	Identification of emerging chemicals and contribution to the prioritisation process of chemicals of interest	M60	60	tbd
P4.3.2.b	D4.10	D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	M60	60	VUA/SLU
P4.3.3.a	R1	Final report	M36	36	UFZ
P4.3.3.a	L1	Targeted WBE methods developed and harmonised	M22	36	UBATH
P4.3.3.a	L2	WBE Suspect- and Nontarget screening methods developed and harmonised	M22	36	MUI
P4.3.3.a	L3	New sampling and enrichment tools developed and tested	M22	36	MU
P4.3.3.a	L4	Prioritisation of source-related features and patterns conducted	M22	36	UFZ
P4.3.3.a	L5	Methods for retrospective mining of heterogeneous datasets	M24	36	UCPH
P4.3.3.a	L6	Methods for high-throughput EDA developed	M30	36	UFZ
P4.3.3.a	L7	Pan-European study for WBE and environmental exposure by wastewater conducted	M30	36	tbd
P4.3.3.a	L8	Datasets from Pan-European Study evaluated	M36	36	tbd

P4.3.3.a	D4.2	D.4.2 1st Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for environmental monitoring	M35	36	VUA
P4.3.3.b ²	R1	Report on the application of innovative methods combined with suspect/NTS/EDA approaches for animal sentinel species	M60	60	ONIRIS
P4.3.3.b	L1	Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners	M24	60	tbd
P4.3.3.b	L2	Sample sourcing and sharing completed	M30	60	tbd
P4.3.3.b	L3	At least 50% of planned analyses completed	M48	60	tbd
P4.3.3.b	L4	All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track	M60	60	tbd
P4.3.3.b	L5	Relevant actors approached for promoting the dissemination of the findings at regulatory level within the CSS framework via interaction with ECHA and EEA and other national agencies	M48-M60	60	tbd
P4.3.3.b	D4.14	D.4.14. Final report on the application of new exposure assessment approaches (i.e. from sampling to data interpretation) to support regulatory needs (i.e. lessons learnt and conclusions/perspective for sustainable follow-up)	M81	60	INRAE
P4.3.4.a ²	R1	Final report on the application of the developed suspect screening/NTS/EDA approaches to real samples originated from food survey designed by other PARC components	M48	48	ANSES
P4.3.4.a	L1	Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners	M18	48	all
P4.3.4.a	L2	Sample sourcing and sharing completed	M24	48	all
P4.3.4.a	L3	Methods development/improvement completed	M24	48	all
P4.3.4.a	L4	At least 50% of planned analyses completed	M30	48	all
P4.3.4.a	L5	All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track	M42	48	all
P4.3.4.a	L6	Relevant actors approached for promoting the dissemination of the findings at regulatory level within the CSS framework via interaction with ECHA and EEA and other national agencies	M36-M48	48	ANSES
P4.3.4.a	D4.10	D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	M60	48	VUA/SLU

¹D = Deliverable/AD = Additional deliverable/M = Milestone/R = Project Report/L = Project Landmark (in grey D/AD/M/R/L year 1)

²Projects starting Y2

WP5

Project ID	D_AD_M-R_L number ¹	Title	Expected delivery date	Project end	Partner Responsible
P5.1.1.a	R1	Submission of two review papers on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins addressing the relevant endpoints of the project	M11 (<i>Alternaria</i>), M13 (<i>Enniatins</i>)	36	UNIVIE, BfR
P5.1.1.a	R2	Reports available with data generated	M36	36	UNIVIE, BfR
P5.1.1.a	L1	First test item available to start experimental studies	M13	36	BfR
P5.1.1.a	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	36	ANSES, BfR
P5.1.1.b	R1	Closing data gaps report: Gathering the data obtained within this project with the contribution from each one of the five mentioned endpoints.	M36	36	BfR
P5.1.1.b	L1	Review BPA alternatives addressing the five endpoints of the project. This will result in a Paper	M14	36	INSA
P5.1.1.b	L2	Acquisition or synthesis/purification of labeled compound R-HPLC methods developed for the profiling, optimized separation and quantification of selected BPA alternatives and their metabolites (labeled molecules). For Metabolism endpoint: HPLC methods developed to monitor the metabolism of BPA alternatives not available as radio-labeled compounds	M18	36	LIH, INRAE
P5.1.1.b	L3	Metabolism, Bioactivation, Kinetic Mass balance studies, metabolic profiles and major metabolites identification completed; forward of information to WP4 & WP5.2 (labeled substances)	M30	36	INRAE
P5.1.1.b	L4	Metabolism, Bioactivation, Kinetics Enzymatic constants and kinetic parameters (apparent Km, Vmax and/or hepatic clearance) determined, production of major metabolites for WP5 testing	M36	36	INRAE
P5.1.1.b	AD5.1	AD5.1 Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.	M9	36	BPI, MU
P5.1.1.b	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	36	ANSES, BfR
P5.1.1.b	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	M24	36	UL-LACDR,/SCI ENSANO/INS ERM/Fraunhofer
P5.1.1.b	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	M36	36	NIPH/INSA
P5.1.2.a	R1	Ecotoxicity data for Lymnaea for single toxins	M24	36	SLU
P5.1.2.a	R2	Ecotoxicity data for Daphnia/marine copepods for single toxins	M24	36	UGent
P5.1.2.a	R3	Ecotoxicity data for Lymnaea for mixtures of toxins	M36	36	SLU

P5.1.2.a	R4	Ecotoxicity data for Daphnia/marine copepods for mixtures of toxins	M36	36	Ugent
P5.1.2.a	R5	Ecotoxicity data for Chlorella vulgaris for single toxins	M24	36	UAVR
P5.1.2.a	R6	Ecotoxicity data for Chlorella vulgaris for mixture of toxins and toxins with other chemicals	M36	36	UAVR
P5.1.2.a	L1	Selection of individual toxins to be tested	M6	36	UGent, SLU, UAVR
P5.1.2.a	L2	Selection of mixtures of toxins to be tested	M18	36	UGent, SLU, UAVR
P5.1.2.a	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	36	ANSES, BfR
P5.1.2.b	R1	Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v).	M12	42	MU
P5.1.2.b	R2	Report on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	M28	42	BPI
P5.1.2.b	R3	Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v).	M42	42	MU
P5.1.2.b	R4	Report on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	M42	42	BPI
P5.1.2.b	L1	Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on available existing data and discussion among partners / stakeholders	M9	42	BPI
P5.1.2.b	L2	Selection of datasets (for in silico tools) and selection of endpoints for experimental tests assessing individual chemicals or their mixtures emphasizing BPA alternatives a priority chemicals	M9	42	MU
P5.1.2.b	L3	Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on PARC environmental monitoring data	M30	42	BPI
P5.1.2.b	AD5.1	AD5.1 Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.	M9	42	BPI, MU
P5.1.2.b	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	M12	42	DTU, VUB
P5.2.1.a	R1	Evaluating NAMs for the assessment of chemicals with potential NGTxC activity	M30	60	INRAE, BfR
P5.2.1.a	R2	Combining NAMS for the evaluation of various NGTxC activities	M48	60	INRAE, BfR
P5.2.1.a	R3	Development of an efficient and reliable testing strategy for the identification of NGTxC	M60	60	INRAE, BfR
P5.2.1.a	L1	Overview of NGTxC assays	M12	60	All
P5.2.1.a	L2	Establish test method setup	M24	60	All
P5.2.1.a	L3	Selection of sufficient reference compounds for technical validation	M24	60	All

P5.2.1.a	L4	Evaluation of covering relevant MoA of potential NGTxC	M42	60	All
P5.2.1.a	L5	Establishment of an efficient and reliable testing strategy for NGTxC	M60	60	All
P5.2.1.a	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	60	ANSES, BfR
P5.2.1.a	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	M12	60	DTU, VUB
P5.2.1.b	R1	Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds	M30	36	INSERM
P5.2.1.b	R2	In vitro assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterization established	M34	36	BfR/UIBK
P5.2.1.b	L1	Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds	M30	36	INSERM
P5.2.1.b	L2	In vitro assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterization established	M34	36	BfR/UIBK
P5.2.1.b	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	M12	36	DTU, VUB
P5.2.1.c	R1	Expand on available THSD MIEs by delivering a test battery of MIEs related to thyroid hormone transporters across physiological barriers	M36	48	VUA
P5.2.1.c	R2	Establish plausible links between TH system MIEs and downstream effects using transcriptomics of TH target tissues and of 2D-and 3D-liver (stem) cell-based cultures; validate MIEs of THSDs and provide a framework for interpretation of in vitro and molecular data	M48	48	DTU/VUB/BfR
P5.2.1.c	R3	Establishment and testing of in vitro assays, in silico and zebrafish/amphibian assays to identify MIEs	M36	48	ISCI
P5.2.1.c	R4	Investigate the use of non-mammalian NAMs for extrapolation to human health for THSD: zebrafish embryo assays to be used in a case study for cross-species extrapolation	M36	48	SDU/UAntwerpen
P5.2.1.c	R5	Release of QSAR predictions for 650,000 substances including 80,000 REACH-preregistered / 11,000 registered substances and QMRF documentation in free Danish (Q)SAR Models website	M48	48	DTU
P5.2.1.c	L1	Multi-organ transcriptomics (toxicogenomics) data from THSD rodents to identify pathways for incorporation in test assays or AOPs	M48	48	DTU/INSERM
P5.2.1.c	L2	Toxicogenomics cross-species comparisons between rodent in vivo toxicity studies (liver) with human stem cell-based in vitro test assays	M48	48	DTU/VUB/INSERM
P5.2.1.c	L3	Proteomics cross-species comparison between in vivo zebrafish toxicity studies with human cell-based in vitro assays	M48	48	ISCI
P5.2.1.c	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	48	ANSES, BfR
P5.2.1.c	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	M12	48	DTU, VUB
P5.2.1.d	R1	Characterization of in vitro systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity	M36	36	INSERM

P5.2.1.d	R2	Immunosuppression and response to vaccination	M36	36	INSERM
P5.2.1.d	R3	In vitro systems to assay key events in the immune system function or dysfunction.	M36	36	INSERM
P5.2.1.d	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	36	ANSES, BfR
P5.2.1.d	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	M12	36	DTU, VUB
P5.2.1.e	R1	Development of NAMs relevant for detection of ANT	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	R2	Fill existing gaps in the DNT IVB	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	R3	Complementary zebrafish assays for the DNT and ANT IVB	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	R4	Final Report	M36	36	UFZ, UIF, UU
P5.2.1.e	L1	Selection of assays added to the DNT IVB	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	L2	Test method set up with information according to Crofton et al.7 provided for each method	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	L3	Delivery of test compounds for mechanistic (scientific) assay validation	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	L4	Full DNT/ANT test methods set-up	tbd	36	tbd
P5.2.1.e	AD5.2	AD5.2 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	M12	36	ANSES, BfR
P5.2.1.e	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	M12	36	DTU, VUB
P5.3.1.a	R1	Report on the inventory of in vitro, in vivo and human omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts and bioinformatics approaches in public domain repositories at PARC partners for all selected adverse outcomes.	M12	36	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO
P5.3.1.a	R2	Report on the applicability domain of systems toxicology bioinformatics approaches for regulatory implementation.	M26	36	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO
P5.3.1.a	R3	Report on translation of systems toxicology data from in vitro NAM to human in vivo.	M36	36	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO
P5.3.1.a	L1	Workshop on systems toxicology: data requirement and strategy	M9	36	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO
P5.3.1.a	L2	Datasets required for systems toxicology in data management systems	M16	36	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO
P5.3.1.a	L3	Novel human datasets for in vitro to in vivo translation established	M24	36	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO
P5.3.1.a	AD5.4	AD5.4 Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	36	UL-LACDR
P5.3.1.a	AD5.7	AD5.7 Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms (postponed from M12 to M18)	M18	36	UL-LACDR, SCIENSANO
P5.3.2.a	R1	Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritization and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC.	M12	36	INSERM

P5.3.2.a	R2	Progress report on AOP development in priority endpoints	M36	36	INSERM
P5.3.2.a	L1	Workshop on AOP methodologies and guidelines	M18	36	INSERM
P5.3.2.a	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC. Associated	M12	36	INSERM
P5.3.2.a	AD5.4	AD5.4 Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	36	UL-LACDR
P5.3.4.a	R1	Report on <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in silico</i> ADME models available and needed for PBK case studies on model and priority compounds	M12	36	ITEM-Fraunhofer
P5.3.4.a	R2	Report on conceptual data gaps in IVIVE-PBK models and the thereof started case studies	M24	36	ITEM-Fraunhofer
P5.3.4.a	R3	Report on the first uncertainty analyses of case studies	M36	36	ITEM-Fraunhofer
P5.3.4.a	L1	Workshop with WP5.1 and 5.2 on data requirement and strategy for their implementation for the proposed case studies	M10	36	ITEM-Fraunhofer
P5.3.4.a	L2	Case studies defined and data needs and deadlines communicated to all involved partners in 5.1 and 5.2	M14	36	ITEM-Fraunhofer
P5.3.4.a	L3	Workshop on the applicability of the IVIVE-PBK framework from this project to the needs in WP6.1 and 6.2	M26	36	ITEM-Fraunhofer
P5.3.4.a	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC. Associated	M12	36	INSERM
P5.3.4.a	AD5.4	AD5.4 Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M14)	M14	36	UL-LACDR

¹D = Deliverable/AD = Additional deliverable/M = Milestone/R = Project Report/L = Project Landmark (in grey D/AD/M/R/L year 1)

WP6

Project ID	D_AD_M-R_L number	Title	Expected delivery date	Project end	Partner Responsible
P6.1.1.a	L1	Inventory of relevant available approaches and frameworks, including available approaches for uncertainty analysis and weight of evidence, available	M12	36	AUTH
P6.1.1.a	L2	Case studies for testing and evaluating workflow v0.1 defined	M14	36	RIVM
P6.1.1.a	L3	Case studies for v0.1 discussed with relevant stakeholders	M28	36	AUTH
P6.1.1.a	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC	M12	36	INSERM
P6.1.1.a	MS15	AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies	M24	36	UL-LACDR
P6.1.1.a	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M42	36	Sciensano
P6.1.1.a	D6.11	D6.11 Report on harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	M72	36	RIVM
P6.1.1.a	D6.12	D6.12 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M81	36	Sciensano
P6.1.1.b	L1	AOP network for ED and associated assays defined	M12	36	tbd
P6.1.1.b	L2	First data for ED collected	M18	36	tbd
P6.1.1.b	L3	Framework for qAOP for ED defined	M28	36	tbd
P6.1.1.b	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC	M12	36	INSERM
P6.1.1.b	MS15	AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies	M24	36	UL-LACDR
P6.1.1.b	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M42	36	Sciensano
P6.1.1.b	D6.11	D6.11 Report on harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	M72	36	RIVM
P6.1.1.b	D6.12	D6.12 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M81	36	Sciensano
P6.1.1.c	L1	AOP network for genotoxicity and associated assays defined	M12	36	tbd
P6.1.1.c	L2	First data for genotoxicity available	M18	36	tbd
P6.1.1.c	L3	Framework for qAOP for genotoxicity defined	M28	36	tbd
P6.1.1.c	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC	M12	36	INSERM
P6.1.1.c	MS15	AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies	M24	36	UL-LACDR
P6.1.1.c	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M42	36	Sciensano

P6.1.1.c	D6.11	D6.11 Report on harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	M72	36	RIVM
P6.1.1.c	D6.12	D6.12 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M81	36	Sciensano
P6.1.1.d	L1	AOP network for liver fibrosis and associated assays defined	M12	36	tbd
P6.1.1.d	L2	First data for liver fibrosis available	M18	36	tbd
P6.1.1.d	L3	Framework for qAOP for liver fibrosis defined	M28	36	tbd
P6.1.1.d	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC	M12	36	INSERM
P6.1.1.d	MS15	AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies	M24	36	UL-LACDR
P6.1.1.d	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M42	36	Sciensano
P6.1.1.d	D6.11	D6.11 Report on harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	M72	36	RIVM
P6.1.1.d	D6.12	D6.12 Reports on IATAs plus associated case studies	M81	36	Sciensano
P6.2.1.a	AD6.3	AD6.3 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	M12	36	UNISANTE, ANSES
P6.2.1.a	D6.1	D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies	M36	36	ANSES
P6.2.1.b	AD6.3	AD6.3 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	M12	48	UNISANTE, ANSES
P6.2.1.b	D6.1	D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies	M36	48	ANSES
P6.2.2.a	R1	Refinement of existing/development of PBPK models towards multi-route and lifelong exposure	M36	48	tbd
P6.2.2.a	R2	Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPK models in the risk assessment process	M48	48	tbd
P6.2.2.a	AD6.4	AD6.4 Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life	M12	48	INERIS, AUTH
P6.2.2.a	D6.2	D6.2. 1st report on innovative methods based on PBK models (M36)	M36	48	AUTH
P6.2.3.a	L1	Discussions with regulators from DG SANTE, EC-JRC and EFSA and use of the MCRA Integrated Risk Assessment - Dashboard including the risk assessment based on HBM data	M24	48	tbd

P6.2.3.a	AD6.5	AD6.5 Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures	M12	48	RIVM, ANSES
P6.2.3.a	AD6.x	AD6.Y2 Report describing the ongoing developments and results of the mixture RA strategy and its application	M24	48	tbd
P6.2.3.a	D6.3	D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA	M36	48	RIVM
P6.2.3.a	AD6.x	AD6.Y4 Report describing the results of the mixture RA strategy and its application	M48	48	tbd
P6.2.4.a	R1	Approach for and results of derivation of population-specific exposures (e.g. stratified by SES, spatio-temporal variations)	M24	66	tbd
P6.2.4.a	R2	Approach for and results of exposure modelling to fill data gaps for prioritized data-poor chemicals	M24	66	tbd
P6.2.4.a	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	M12	66	VITO, UU-IRAS
P6.2.4.a	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	M36	66	VITO
P6.2.4.b	R1	Overview of current frameworks and methodologies of HIA for chemical exposure and associated uncertainties	M24	66	tbd
P6.2.4.b	R2	Weight-of-evidence (WoE) approach for selection of exposure-effect functions including information from epidemiological, toxicological and mechanistic studies	M24	66	tbd
P6.2.4.b	R3	Approach for incorporation of effect biomarker measurements as surrogate markers for toxicity	M24	66	tbd
P6.2.4.b	R4	Overview of current methodologies, indicators and frameworks used for cost analysis related to health impact of chemical exposures	M30	66	tbd
P6.2.4.b	L1	Selection of methodological improvements to be addressed in PARC and/or to be implemented in case studies and indicator development	M18-30-42-54-66	66	tbd
P6.2.4.b	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	M12	66	VITO, UU-IRAS
P6.2.4.b	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	M36	66	VITO
P6.2.4.c	R1	Framework for case study selection (criteria, weighing, documentation, ranking)	M12	42	tbd
P6.2.4.c	R2	Reporting on design and results of case studies for health impact assessment	M24-36-48-60-72-81	42	tbd
P6.2.4.c	L1	Prioritization of case studies for human health impact assessment to be started in 2023	M12	42	tbd

P6.2.4.c	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	M12	42	VITO, UU-IRAS
P6.2.4.c	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implicatinos	M36	42	VITO
P6.2.4.d	R1	Inventory of existing indicator types of relevance for PARC	M12	42	tbd
P6.2.4.d	R2	Risk and health impact indicators developed under PARC and their policy implications	M42	42	tbd
P6.2.4.d	L1	Proposal for indicators for risk and health impact to be developed in PARC	M13	42	tbd
P6.2.4.d	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implicatinos	M36	42	VITO
P6.3.1.a	R1	Publication of case study 1 (CS 12)	M15	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	R2	Publication comparing regulation of relevant biocides (CS14)	M15	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	R3	Publication of case study 2 (CS12)	M27	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	R4	Publication of case study 3 (CS12)	M27	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	R5	Publication on impact analysis (CS14)	M27	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	R6	Publication/ report on mapping of relevant legislation and description of current regulatory processes (CS13)	M27	48	UCL
P6.3.1.a	R7	Publication of case study 4 (CS12)	M39	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	R8	Doctoral thesis (CS12)	M39	48	SU
P6.3.1.a	D6.6	D 6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	M42	48	KEMI
P6.3.1.a	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	M42	48	ANSES
P6.3.1.a	D6.17	Deliverable 6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	M81	48	KEMI
P6.3.1.b	R1	Comprehensive list and report on in vitro test methods assessing prioritised ED endpoints	M12	48	BPI
P6.3.1.b	R2	Report and database on existing in vitro assays, in silico tools and read-across approaches for ED assessment of EATS modalities under PPPR, BPR, REACH and CPR	M12	48	BPI
P6.3.1.b	R3	Mapping of regulatory practices for skin sensitizers, including the handling of mixtures	M18	48	REGIONH
P6.3.1.b	R4	Methodological differences between the legislative frameworks of cosmetics and chemicals, with emphasis on substances with ED activity	M20	48	VUB

P6.3.1.b	R5	Systematic review on skin sensitisation risk assessment methodologies	M30	48	REGIONH
P6.3.1.b	R6	Provide possible solutions, shifting away from animal use to a WoE approach which combines both existing and newly emerging NAMs making use of new technology, preferentially based on human material	M32	48	VUB
P6.3.1.b	R7	Harmonised scientific criteria for consideration of data from non-validated in vitro methods for ED assessment across legislations	M36	48	BPI
P6.3.1.b	R8	The added value of NAMs (in vitro, in silico, read-across) to delineate human/ population relevance aspects that are critical in deciding on classification of chemicals either as Category 1 or 2 for ED properties under the new CLP criteria	M36	48	BPI
P6.3.1.b	R9	Mapping of strategic regulatory needs and strategies to fill them. Case story on skin sensitisation risk assessment: success and failures	M36	48	REGIONH
P6.3.1.b	R10	Evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies	M36	48	SU
P6.3.1.b	R11	Main outcomes of the analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches	M45-M48	48	ISS
P6.3.1.b	R12	Conclusions and recommendations on skin sensitisation risk assessment methodology	M54	48	REGIONH
P6.3.1.b	L1	Availability of a sufficiently high number of original DNT study reports is a necessary prerequisite for the successful performance in the evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies.	M10	48	SU
P6.3.1.b	L2	End-of systematic review on risk assessment methodologies for skin sensitization. The contents will be decisive on whether a recommendation for a common risk assessment model is possible or this is not possible at this stage due to knowledge gaps.	M30	48	REGIONH
P6.3.1.b	D6.6	D 6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	M42	48	KEMI
P6.3.1.b	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	M42	48	ANSES
P6.3.1.b	D6.17	Deliverable 6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	M81	48	KEMI
P6.3.2.a	R1	Differences and similarities between regulatory threshold values for surface waters, including sediment, under different EU legal frameworks (namely PPP, BPR and WFD); could be in the form of publication or policy brief including PPT set of slides	M24	48	Eawag

P6.3.2.a	R2	Approaches to align the different frameworks and proposing feedback-loops between the different regulatory frameworks to bridge the identified differences in risk assessment outcomes to further the goal of OS-OA; could be in the form of publication or policy brief including PPT set of slides	M36	48	Eawag
P6.3.2.a	R3	Report focussing on soil and air as a result of the second project phase; could be in the form of publication or policy brief including PPT set of slides (Month to be specified after finalisation of first project phase)	tbd	48	Eawag
P6.3.2.a	R4	Review and analysis of the existing approaches in regulatory framework and relevant research projects for the assessment of secondary poisoning	M10	48	INERIS
P6.3.2.a	R5	Case studies comparing the outcome of existing approaches for a selection of chemicals leading to the identification of gaps, inconsistencies, and uncertainties - Supporting material for workshop on the identification of priorities for improvement of guidance for secondary poisoning	M18	48	INERIS
P6.3.2.a	R6	Recommendations for the uptake of the results of the CS into regulations	M30	48	INERIS
P6.3.2.a	R7	Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs, Analysis of the weight given to reproductive toxicity in OEL-setting, Quantitative estimates of OELs' margin of safety to reproductive toxicity, Recommendations for regulatory actions, such as re-evaluation of specific OELs	M36	48	KI
P6.3.2.a	R8	Analysis of different options to regulate occupational chemical exposure, results of the questionnaire study/interviews on the interpretation and implementation of limit values and other regulatory information at the workplace level, related recommendations and guidance	M36	48	KI
P6.3.2.a	D6.6	D 6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	M42	48	KEMI
P6.3.2.a	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	M42	48	ANSES
P6.3.2.a	D6.17	Deliverable 6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	M81	48	KEMI
P6.4.1.a	R1	Evaluation of the stakeholder feedback collected from a survey and expert interviews on the usefulness of current mixture assessment tools	M18	36	UGoT, BUL
P6.4.1.a	R2	Comparative assessment of mixture tools with respect to application domain, feasibility, data demands, protectiveness, reliability, bias.	M24	36	UGoT, BUL
P6.4.1.a	R3	Draft for a European mixture framework, accompanied by a validated toolbox of instruments for mixture risk assessment and management	M36	36	UGoT, BUL
P6.4.1.a	L1	Updated inventory of current mixture assessment tools and compilation of current regulatory requirements	M12	36	UGoT, BUL
P6.4.1.a	L2	Documented interviews with experts in chemical risk assessment (human health as well as the environment)	M18	36	UGoT, BUL

P6.4.1.a	L3	Selection of case studies for the comparative assessment of current or newly developed mixture tools	M12	36	UGoT, BUL
P6.4.1.a	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	M81	36	Ugot
P6.4.1.b	R1	Literature review on use of NAM and monitoring data for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation	M18	36	UFZ, UBA
P6.4.1.b	R2	Guidance document for use of NAM data for specific regulatory options	M36	36	UFZ, UBA
P6.4.1.b	L1	Selection of case studies for the use of NAMs, NAM data and monitoring data in specific regulatory areas	M12	36	UFZ
P6.4.1.b	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	M81	36	Ugot
P6.4.2.a	R1	Technical report: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis	M24	36	UNIBAS
P6.4.2.a	R2	Workshop report: Prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies	M26	36	UNIBAS
P6.4.2.a	R3	Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies	M36	36	UNIBAS
P6.4.2.a	L1	Technical report summarizing: (1) the mapping of activities and processes related to the status of development, integration and use of NAMs in selected regulatory environments (which informs the gaps and needs analysis in Y2); (2) the outcome of the gaps and needs analysis. This will prepare the workshop at the beginning of Y3	M24	36	tbd
P6.4.2.a	L2	A workshop will be held to design regulatory scenario-based case studies resulting in an action plan prioritizing the case studies	M26	36	tbd
P6.4.2.a	L3	Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies	M36	36	tbd
P6.4.2.a	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions	M81	36	UNIBAS
P6.4.2.b	R1	Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies	M11	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R2	Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies	M12	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R3	Creation of INVITES-IN, a focus group study	M13	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R4	Protocol for harmonizing and cross-walking SR and CRA terms	M14	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R5	Creation of INVITES-IN, a Delphi survey	M15	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R6	Core SR and CRA terms; definitions and cross-walking two disciplines	M25	36	NIPH, represented by VKM

P6.4.2.b	R7	Protocol; creating an overview of external validity items	M22	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R8	Creation of INVITES-IN, user testing and validation	M22	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R9	INVITES-IN, a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies	M24	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R10	Protocol for designing INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of in vitro studies	M28	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R11	External validity items, a comprehensive overview	M34	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	R12	Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of in vitro studies	M35	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	L1	Ethical approval of creation of INVITES-IN	M10	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	L2	INVITES-IN	M24	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	L3	Cross walking SR and CRA terminology	M26	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	L4	External validity items, a comprehensive overview	M34	36	NIPH, represented by VKM
P6.4.2.b	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions	M81	36	UNIBAS
P6.4.2.c	R1	Overview of exploratory analysis and identification of research priorities and requirements	M12	36	UT
P6.4.2.c	R2	Framework to facilitate an adequate reporting for the AI/ML NAMs to be used for regulatory purposes	M24	36	UT
P6.4.2.c	R3	Final report on the main outcomes of the project	M34	36	UT
P6.4.2.c	L1	Refined work plan and methodology for years 2 and 3	M12	36	UT
P6.4.2.c	L2	Selection of case studies	M16	36	UT
P6.4.2.c	L3	Framework tested on case studies	M30	36	UT
P6.4.2.c	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions	M81	36	UNIBAS
P6.4.3.a	R1	Report on existing database structures with recommended structures	M36	36	MU
P6.4.3.a	L1	Stakeholder advisory board meeting to share information and recommendations on current data structures relevant to products and materials	M6	36	KEMI
P6.4.3.a	L2	Completion of information gathering from national chemical agencies	M12	36	MU
P6.4.3.a	L3	Mapping of database structures and gaps	M12	36	MU

P6.4.3.a	L4	Annual communication through online meetings with Stakeholder advisory board	M12, M24	36	KEMI
P6.4.3.a	L5	Identification of case study topics	M14	36	MU
P6.4.3.a	AD6.14	AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures	M24	36	TUKES
P6.4.3.a	AD6.15	AD6.15: Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards	M24	36	MU
P6.4.3.a	D6.20	D6.20. Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data	M81	36	MU
P6.4.4.a	R1	Clarifying regulatory needs (Drivers of change, Problem description, Future state of ERA, Gap analysis, Short term-remedies and potential long-term solutions, Prioritised Areas of work and research questions)	M22	42	KEMI
P6.4.4.a	R2	Clarifying regulatory needs	M34	42	KEMI
P6.4.4.a	L1	First recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	M22	42	KEMI
P6.4.4.a	AD6.7	Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas	M24	42	UBA/KEMI/FO EN
P6.4.4.a	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	M81	42	UBA
P6.4.4.b	Report 1	Technical report describing comparison of different existing methods for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments validated against monitoring data from various European geographical regions.	M24	24	SLU
P6.4.4.b	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	M81	24	UBA
P6.4.4.c	R1	Technical report on the most relevant factors describing the transfer function that enables a link between laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at ecosystem level. Ranking the relevance of the factors describing the lab to field transfer function. Identification to which extent interactions between PPPs and additional environmental factors increase the sensitivity of field populations.	M24	36	UFZ
P6.4.4.c	R2	Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.	M36	36	UFZ
P6.4.4.c	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	M81	36	UBA
P6.4.4.d	R1	Compiled data for internal risk benchmarking	M12	42	UKOLD
P6.4.4.d	R2	Analyses for internal risk benchmarking accomplished	M27	42	tbd
P6.4.4.d	R3	Database of ERA results and complementary data	M27	42	tbd

P6.4.4.d	R4	Data compiled for external risk benchmarking	M30	42	tbd
P6.4.4.d	R5	Analyses for external risk benchmarking accomplished	M36	42	tbd
P6.4.4.d	R6	Technical report on results of benchmarking analyses with suggestions for methodology and most important factors having an impact on the result of the ERA	M42	42	tbd
P6.4.4.d	L1	Complied data for internal risk benchmarking	M12	42	tbd
P6.4.4.d	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	M81	42	UBA
P6.4.4.e	R1	Conceptual models for aggregate and combined exposure to pesticides at landscape level covering the local and regional needs as well as national and EU needs. The tools will support the selection of the best IPM approach allowing an ERA-based scientifically sound assessment of sustainability regarding pesticide use as well as a comparative impact with other stressors.	M12	42	ISCIII
P6.4.4.e	R2	Case studies report	M30	42	ISCIII for the compilation, case study leaders for each case study report
P6.4.4.e	R3	Final conceptual approach, including problem formulation and implementation options	M36	42	ISCIII
P6.4.4.e	L1	Identification on protection needs covering also for SUD, CAP and biodiversity strategy	M12	42	ISCIII
P6.4.4.e	L2	Prioritisation of case studies	M12	42	ISCIII and case study leaders
P6.4.4.e	L3	Verification of key elements for landscape ERA from the case studies	M24	42	Each case study leader
P6.4.4.e	L4	Extrapolation of the case study outcomes into quantitative landscape ERA tools	M30	42	ISCIII, UFZ
P6.4.4.e	L5	Adaptation of the tools to different regulatory/policy and voluntary initiatives through networking activities.	M36	42	ISCIII, UFZ, all
P6.4.4.e	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	M81	42	UBA

¹D = Deliverable/AD = Additional deliverable/M = Milestone/R = Project Report/L = Project Landmark (in grey D/AD/M/R/L year 1)

WP7

Project ID	D_AD_M-R_L number ¹	Title	Expected delivery date	Project end	Partner Responsible
P7.2.2.a	D7.1	D7.1. Data management plan	M6	36	TNO
P7.2.2.a	MS11	MS11 Network of trained FAIR data stewards	M12	36	TNO
P7.2.2.a	D7.2	D7.2. PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP)	M18	36	TNO
P7.2.2.a	MS12	MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	M24	36	VITO
P7.2.2.a	D7.3	D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data	M36	36	VITO
P7.2.2.b	MS11	MS11 Network of trained FAIR data stewards	M12	42	TNO
P7.2.2.b	D7.2	D7.2 PARC FAIR data policy	M18	42	TNO
P7.2.2.b	MS12	MS12 Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	M24	42	VITO
P7.2.2.b	D7.3	D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data	M36	42	VITO
P7.2.2.b	D7.5	D7.5 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	M42	42	TNO
P7.3.3.a	R1	Scoping study of AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment	M18	60	tbd
P7.3.3.a	R2	Report on the available tool and framework, and different methodologies (like NLP and text mining) used for human health risk assessment, including ontology development.	tbd	60	tbd
P7.3.3.a	L1	Workshop on Ontology-assisted text mining for human health risk assessment strategy	M10	60	IISPV
P7.3.3.a	L2	Case Study 1 and 2 presentations of results with respective stakeholders	M24	60	IISPV
P7.3.3.a	L3	Integrated knowledge base /datasets for selected case studies (like AOPs development) established	M30	60	IISPV
P7.3.3.a	D7.4	D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA	M36	60	UU-IRAS

¹D = Deliverable/AD = Additional deliverable/M = Milestone/R = Project Report/L = Project Landmark (in grey D/AD/M/R/L year 1)